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THE 9TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE FOR YOUNG RESEARCHERS IN ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS

Volume 2

**NHÀ XUẤT BẢN KINH TẾ
TP. HỒ CHÍ MINH**

**October 26 - 27, 2023
Ho Chi Minh City**

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FORECASTING VN30 INDEX MOVEMENT WITH FINANCIAL NEWS AND TECHNICAL ANALYSIS BY MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract

In this study, the author uses the VN30-Index as a measure of the volatility of the Vietnamese stock market as well as a strong basis for forecasting the derivative market since its importance to investors, businesses in particular and the national economy in general. To improve forecasting accuracy, the author applied machine learning models including random forest, support vector machine and deep learning including artificial neural network and long short-term memory model to forecast the VN30 index within the period from January 2017 to January 2023. The Support Vector Machine model with Radial Basis Function kernel is the model that gives the best predictive performance. Meanwhile, deep learning models do not provide excess predictive results compared to powerful machine learning models. At the same time, using market psychology factors such as financial news and technical analysis indicators provided forecasting strength is superior. In particular, 1 day ago is considered the optimal lag when using financial news headlines. Finally, the author has also demonstrated that building a good forecasting system for the VN30-index contributes to making accurate predictions about the trends of the derivatives market, thereby proposing appropriate policies to develop this market as stronger and more stable day by day.

Keywords: *Financial news, Machine Learning, Technical analysis, VN30.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Stock market has always played an extremely crucial role for individual investors as well as enterprises in Vietnam. For individual investors, forecasting the trend of this market in the future gives them an advantage in the process of making investment decisions in the stock market more accurately and carefully. Moreover, this is an investment channel to help investors diversify their portfolios in order to minimize risks and still earn a good expected return with a good investment expense. For businesses, the stock market is a place to help businesses diversify their forms and expand their ability to mobilize capital for development purposes. In addition, the listing of securities on the stock market also brings prestige to the company thanks to the mechanism of transparency, censorship and supervision from many parties. In addition, the stock market is also considered an effective channel for businesses to access capital from foreign investors in Vietnam. However, building models that accurately predict the trend of this market in the future is extremely difficult because the data of the stock market always has limitations of information, high volatility and high noise (Zhao & Yang, 2023).

Moreover, the stock market also has a strong impact on the Government's economic policy. The stock market is one of the most important components in demonstrating the strength and developing ability of the national economy (GC, 2006). Research paper of Antonios (2010) pointed out that there is a one-way causal relationship between the stock market and the strength of the national economy. In addition, the stock market also plays a very important role in helping the national economy diversify risks while creating an impact on financial institutions and banks (Levine & Zervos, 1998). Therefore, this market is considered an indispensable factor in the economic development policy of countries with small and young markets (Khan & Abdelhak, 2000). However, the empirical research results of Ake (2010) show that the positive relationship of stock market and growth strength is only true for countries with efficient and highly liquid markets. In contrast, for countries with small market sizes and low liquidity, this causal relationship does not exist. One more vital thing, the stock market is one of extremely effective economic management tools to raise capital of the Government, specifically that this market annually contributes greatly to the ability to create capital for the economy of the country. From that, the Government can mobilize financial resources without the pressure of inflation and attract capital from abroad easily and effectively. Moreover, the stock market is considered a standard reference in determining the possibility of future economic development. Specifically, when the stock market tends to increase, it will be a signal for an economy to grow in the future and vice versa. From the above points, it can be seen that forecasting the trend of stock movements is always necessary and useful, and this is also one of the topics that investors, businesses, and policymakers always include in the highest interest research topics because of the benefits they bring to the economy.

In the history of the study of the rule of stock market price movement, there have been many assumptions, theories and empirical studies using traditional methods such as ARIMA, OLS multivariate regression, Vector autoregression (VAR), and so on. Nowadays, with the strong development of technology along with the increasing complexity of the market's rules, models of machine learning, deep learning and AI (Artificial Intelligence) are increasingly trusted by experts in forecasting the price movement of securities market and other industries. Although machine learning and deep learning models have been developed for a long time in the past, they have only begun to be really interested and applied in many areas of human life in recent years thanks to rapid economic development and improvements in education. One of the most core reasons is machine learning's ability to learn and process extremely complex relationships across a wide range of issues, especially the relationship between stock price movement and the factors that influence it. The superiority of machine learning over traditional methods is the ability to efficiently process and analyze large amounts of tasks and big data. From there, experts in the field and investors have the opportunity to access better forecasting tools because both machine learning and deep learning algorithms can provide investors with more accurate forecasts than traditional techniques. Most traditional models are based on assumptions about algorithms as well as the market and the probability to meet the above assumptions in the real market is difficult to happen, especially in emerging markets like Vietnam. Meanwhile, the machine learning and deep learning algorithms' mode of operation is hardly ever based on traditional assumptions but on trial-and-error processing and trying to optimize the loss function to minimize the prediction error between the predicted output and the actual result. In addition, the ability to interact with time series data is also a great strength of machine learning and deep learning. Time series data play a crucial role in developing

accurate price movement forecasting models of stock markets because they allow experts and investors to gauge their volatility in the past. Particularly for deep learning models, this algorithm can learn the structure of complex input data attributes from time series through deep neural networks like the human brain.

In this research paper, the author uses the VN30-Index of the Ho Chi Minh Stock Exchange (HOSE) is a dependent variable to forecast the movement of the stock market instead of the VN-Index for several specific reasons. Firstly, although VN30-Index is not possible to completely replace the VN-Index, this index is an extremely important indicator for investors because they can help investors assess the profitability of stock market quickly and easily. This can be explained by the set of stocks in the VN30 basket that are the leading stocks in many main fields, from which this index can clearly reflect the overall market. Secondly, the VN30 index includes 30 stocks with the highest market capitalization as these 30 stocks have accounted for more than 80% of the total capitalization and 60% of the total transaction value in the market, as well as this is also the group of stocks with the best liquidity in each period (Dao, 2013). Therefore, stocks in this group are always considered to be stocks with great interest from investors. In addition, in the study of Do Van and Nguyen Minh (2021), this author has also given evidence showing that most of the stocks in the market will often be dominated by the fluctuating trends of market indices such as VN30 index or some stocks with high market capitalization. Thirdly, because of the influence of this index on the stock market, the VN30-Index is considered an index capable of accurately reflecting the supply and demand relationship in the reality of stocks on the exchange, which the VN-Index sometimes cannot do as well as the VN30 index (Dao, 2013). Fourthly, the VN30 index plays a crucial role in regulating supply and demand, market prices thanks to the strong development of leading securities as well as the lack of being over-coordinated by the VN-Index. Finally, VN30-Index has a significant impact on the derivatives market in Vietnam. Derivatives are considered an extremely vital tool in controlling risk for many businesses in many fields. In addition, derivatives are also a potential investment channel launched in Vietnam in 2017, as well as this is an important development in the process of accelerating the improvement of the securities market structure of our country. Currently, VN30 Futures contract is the main derivative product in Vietnam and VN30 index is also the underlying asset of this future contract. In other words, VN30 Futures is a financial product based on the VN30 index. The impact of VN30 on derivatives is very large, because VN30 derivative values depend mainly on fluctuations of VN30. This has also been proven in the research of Phong, Minh, Thanh, and Son (2020) when this author found out strong evidence that the spot market in Vietnam leads the futures market within both short term and long term. When the price movement of VN30 is uptrend, the value of VN30's derivative products also increases and vice versa, when VN30 is downtrend, the value of VN30 derivatives also decreases. This means that investors and investment firms can use the information of VN30 index to make investment decisions such as buying or selling VN30 futures. If they believe that the VN30-Index will rise, they can buy derivatives to make a profit or sell derivatives to minimize the risk that market information will fall. Therefore, understanding the movement rule of the VN30 index is very essential for investors and investment organizations that want to participate in the derivatives market in Vietnam. Moreover, market managers and policy makers can also rely on the performance of the stock market to be able to make the right judgments as well as formulate and make appropriate policies to develop the Vietnamese derivatives markets.

The author research this study in order to assess and compare the performance of various machine learning algorithms in predicting price movements within the Vietnamese stock market using the VN30 index as the basis. Not only that, the author also wants to give the clearest results to answer the question whether the use of newspaper articles and indicators of technical analysis in the model will bring better forecasting productivity than the previous approaches. Besides, author also want to find out the answer whether deep learning models will significantly bring better forecasting performance than machine learning models for emerging markets such as Vietnam.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to the efficient markets hypothesis (EMH), profit-making opportunities will be exploited as soon as they are discovered in financial markets. Therefore, taking advantage of important information such as historical prices, public information, or even internal information will be difficult to predict the trend of stock prices because they fluctuate according to the law of random walk (White, 1988). However, this is a fact that the market needs a period to be affected by the information. Similar to the studies of Kaya and Karşlıgil (2010) and Lauren and Harlili (2014), both of these authors conclude that the stock market could forecast well trend in the future.

A random walk is a random movement within a period of time. For the stock market, the stock price at any stage will be the same as the price of the stock adding or minus a undefined number (Pant & Bishnoi, 2001). The random walk hypothesis posits that stock prices fluctuate in a completely random way and are not dependent on historical transaction values. Taking advantage of arbitrage to make a profit based on the information of past value in an efficient market is not possible and future price movements are just anyone's guess. The more efficient the market, the more unpredictable the search for profit becomes because of their randomness. In the most efficient market, the price in the future will be completely random and price formation can be assumed to be a random process with a zero-change average value. Therefore, trying to find out the most suitable prediction model could not explicitly predict the price movement of the stock.

Machine learning is now considered an extremely important tool in the field of data science and artificial intelligence. This learning algorithm is usually used in data processing, building predictive models, classification by teaching machines based on input data sets (Mahesh, 2020). In aspect of using machine learning models, there is not a single algorithm that is determined to be the most efficient. Each machine learning algorithm such as logistic regression, random forest, support vector machine, and so on will provide good predictive productivity depending on the problems needing to be solved, data quality defects, and complexity of the datasets. In machine learning, they are divided into two main learning methods that are unsupervised and supervised learning (Crisci, Ghattas, & Perera, 2012). Supervised learning is a learning method in which models will perform the task of clarifying the input mapping (X_i) into the output or target variable (Y) based on a pair of input and output at the sample data set. For unsupervised learning, the difference between supervised learning and unsupervised learning is that there are no precise answers to the input problem. That is why it is considered that there is no teacher. These models are often primarily used to address topics such as clustering, anomaly detection, and feature reduction. Nowadays, some of the most popular unsupervised learning models are K-Means Clustering, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Hierarchical clustering and so on.

The deep learning model is a deeper branch of machine learning. Deep learning is capable of self-learning and evaluating predictive performance thanks to a neural network architecture that is simulated as a human neural network with many hidden layers to solve complex problems such as regression, classification, and reinforcement learning in multidisciplinary fields such as finance, medicine, natural language processing, and so on (Saxe, Nelli, & Summerfield, 2021). Deep learning models are becoming more and more popular and widely studied thanks to their flexibility and high performance. The turning point for the popularity of this model was in 2012, when they set a new record in image classification Krizhevsky, Sutskever, and Hinton (2017) and voice recognition Hinton et al. (2012). However, building deep learning models requires a lot of data and computational resources, and can easily be overfitting if not properly trained.

In the history of research, many research articles have used traditional econometric models and technical analysis methods to forecast the trend of stocks in the future. In the history of research, many research articles have used traditional econometric models and technical analysis methods to forecast the trend of stocks in the future. In conventional approaches, the regression model is a widely used model because of its ability to help researchers see the relationship between the researched object and the variables affected. In addition, previous studies also usually use models to analyze the volatility level such as ARCH, GARCH, and GARCH's branches. In India, Tripathi and Seth (2014) researched the relationship between stock market performance and macroeconomic features from July 1997 to June 2011 using the OLS regression method, ARCH model. This author concludes that macroeconomic variables are one of the factors that affect the volatility of the stock market. However, the influence of macro on this market is not too large when the regression results of the author are 16,9%, 23,3% and 23,8% respectively for market turnover market capitalization and Sensex. Moreover, Tripathi and Seth (2014) also made the point that the price movement of the stock market is influenced by many other reasons in addition to the national macroeconomic indicators. Some other macro indices have also been shown to have an impact on the stock market such as interest rate, foreign direct investments, exchange rate (Adam & Tweneboah, 2008). In addition, the effects of macroeconomic indicators on the price movement of stocks in the long term and short term are different. Similar to the Vietnamese market, Tangjitprom (2011) we have studied important macro factors affecting the price movement of the stock market in Thailand including the unemployment rate, 5-year government bonds, inflation or consumer price index (CPI), and the effect of foreign currency (Dollar). This study uses the Vector Autoregression model to see causal outcomes among the study subjects. The results of this study demonstrate that there is a definite relationship between macroeconomic features and stock returns in Thailand's emerging stock market. However, this author has also emphasized in their study that the relationship between stock return and macroeconomic factors has a relationship but it is imbalanced. Information on stock returns plays an important role to forecast the macroeconomic, but macroeconomic features do not have a significant effect in forecasting stock price movements in the future. In short, traditional methods mostly mentioned the relationship between stock price movement and macro indicators.

For the technical analysis method, this approach is still one of the most popular and most used methods by many investors when accounting for about 66% of the weight (Do Van & Nguyen Minh, 2021). Nowadays, with the strong development in the application of

information technology in the fields of finance, banking, securities, and so on, it is gradually becoming popular and bringing more value to investors, business owners or even the national economy. This is also seen as an opportunity and challenge to be able to attract research interest in innovative solutions to challenges to traditional approaches. Up to now, forecasting methods using machine learning and deep learning models have been gradually taken care of by researchers and investors and used in investment campaigns or economic policies.

In addition to traditional approaches, many authors have made breakthroughs in research when focusing on deeply exploiting the application of machine learning and deep learning models to stock market forecasts. In study of Krauss, Do, and Huck (2017), this author combined three machine learning methods are eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Deep Neural Network (DNN), and Random Forest to predict future value of U.S stock. Machine learning models have the potential to be a powerful assistant, a powerful and promising analytical tool in effective investment management (Gan, Wang, & Yang, 2020). Nowadays, with the application of machine learning models in a variety of fields that achieve significant achievements, in which, this technology application in the financial field has been increasingly developed day by day (Attigeri, MM, Pai, & Nayak, 2015; Kim & Kang, 2019). In addition to the use of machine learning models, there have been a number of studies applying deep learning to forecast stock market. For example, Soni (2011) researched about the application of neural network artificial intelligence (ANN) models or research of Olson and Mossman (2003) also provided evidence for the usefulness of neural network models to predict the stock market. In the developing nation of Indian, Patel, Shah, Thakkar, and Kotecha (2015) used two main indexes are S&P BSE Sensex and CNX Nifty to forecast this country's stock market performance over a 10-year period. This author's novelty is to show the combination of machine learning models together and compare them with using only individual machine learning models. Patel et al. (2015) have tested several hybrid models such as SVR-ANN, SVR-RF and SVR-SVR to forecast the stock market from 1 to 10, 15 or possibly up to 30 days. Ultimately, this author concluded that SVR-ANN was the model with the best results. In addition to the strong predictability that machine learning models provide, forecasting well on non-linear relationships is also a bright spot of this type of model. The author's experimental results Rossi (2018) mentioned the relationship in the stock market with high non-linearity when applying machine learning technologies to stock market returns forecasting topic. This relationship has also been studied by many previous researchers and they also concluded that the non-linearity relationship exists in the different stock market (Gencay, 1996; Guidolin, Hyde, McMillan, & Ono, 2009; Lendasse, de Bodt, Wertz, & Verleysen, 2000).

In deep learning models, suitably choosing of activation function, model parameter and especially network structure is extremely important as they will affect the forecast performance (Chong, Han, & Park, 2017). In the study of Nabipour, Nayyeri, Jabani, Shahab, and Mosavi (2020), this group of authors experimentally compared nine machine learning algorithms and two powerful deep learning models including long short-term memory (LSTM) and recurrent neural network (RNN) with two input data settings as continuous data and binary data with a length of ten years. The results show that using LSTM and RNN models will provide better predictability than the other nine machine learning models. The LSTM model is also selected by Akita, Yoshihara, Matsubara, and Uehara (2016) to build an effective stock market forecasting model in Japan using a combination of numeric data and text data. Besides LSTM or RNN, in the research of Wanjawa and Muchemi (2014) and Qiu, Song, and Akagi (2016)

have also used the ANN model to forecast the stock market's price movement. The results of these two studies show that this model has done its task very well. In addition, Dase and Pawar (2010) had a conclusion that the ANN algorithm remains a useful one in making stock market forecasts around the world.

Some prior research articles have primarily relied on historical value data to predict future trends, but this approach leaves room for improvement in forecasting accuracy, despite the historical nature of securities' volatility trends. In fact, when special events occur in financial markets which could be negative or positive, these events will create stock market shocks that lead to fluctuations which are difficult to measure by historical value. Therefore, there were some domestic and foreign scientific articles that have added event factors such as market by analyzing the press content on the financial market to the forecasting model. This is considered a factor that greatly affects investment decisions as well as helping to forecast the future stock market is possible (Phan & Zhou, 2014). In the study of Duong, Nguyen, and Dang (2016), this author has also commented that financial news from newspaper headlines is one of the most important factors that affect human decision making. There have been a number of research articles on the issue of analyzing news articles to include in stock market forecast models or even the cryptocurrency market. However, the choice of which news source or publisher will influence the quality of the model's forecast.

During research from the past to the present, there have been many studies that have shown empirical results that there is a clear relationship between news and the trend of stock price movement in the future. These researches on this topic used many algorithms which is from simple to complex level such as Support Vector Machine, Naïve Bayes, and deep learning. For instance, Gidofalvi and Elkan (2001) used newspaper headlines and the Naïve Bayesian classifier model to forecast the price trend of a stock. Moreover, this author also points out that the using financial newspaper headlines to forecast the price movement of stocks in the short term is feasible. The article by Heston and Sinha (2017) also included a financial news element in the Thomson Reuters neural network model for forecasting stock return and this study found that daily news only affects stock return from one to two days. Moreover, the positive news tends to impact the stock return quickly, while the negative news has a lag stage. In the report of Mohan, Mullapudi, Sammeta, Vijayvergia, and Anastasiu (2019), this author applied cloud computing technology to forecast the S&P500 index with a period of 5 years and more than 265,000 financial articles about this stock code. This method helped them to build models, process data and analysis data in an extremely resource-efficient manner. In addition, with this author's survey, the result also shows that financial events information plays a very vital role in increasing the ability to accurately forecast the stock market trend. This result is also similar to result of Khedr and Yaseen (2017) by trying to use data mining and machine learning methods to find out how to optimize the ability to predict the stock market with the effect of predicting future trends with a small error rate or improving accuracy. In addition to the stock market, there have also been a few studies that have also used cryptocurrency market news to forecast the price movement of some popular coins. Abraham, Higdon, Nelson, and Ibarra (2018) and Wolk (2020) were successful in finding a good way to predict changes in Bitcoin and Ethereum prices using Twitter and Google Trends data.

Besides, adding relevant indicators on technical analysis techniques to the forecasting model is also one of the widely used methods. Technical analysis is the technique of using

historical information about a stock's price to try to forecast stock trends in the future. In the studies by Brock, Lakonishok, and LeBaron (1992) and Neely, Weller, and Dittmar (1997), these authors have all successfully demonstrated that technical analysis is capable of providing more extensive information than the current information of price which is provided by the stock market. In addition, Cuong and Tam (2018) have shown that technical analysis can be applied well to both countries have efficient and countries have inefficient market conditions to forecast the stock price movement. This technique is also perfectly suitable for emerging and vibrant stock market like Vietnam. In addition, this paper also shows that the three most common technical analysis indicators in analyzing stock movements are Moving Average (MA), Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD) and Relative Strength Index (RSI). The study of Hari and Dewi (2018) researched the application of technical analysis indicators to stock trading strategies and has also provided recommendations for investors and businesses to pay attention to two indicators RSI and MA. In which, the Moving Average indicator has two common sub-indicators: Simple Moving Average (SMA) and Exponential Moving Average (EMA). Almost, these two indicators are almost always the most popular ones used in this research topic. This is because the above two indicators are easy to calculate but their predictive power of stock movements is significantly good (Levy, 1967; Rahmadhani, Mandela, Paul, & Viridi, 2011). In addition, these two indicators are also considered indicators that can represent many other groups of indicators.

3. THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. General architecture of approach

The author handles a total of four phases including data collection, data preprocessing, training model, evaluating, and making the prediction VN30 index price movement, which is depicted in Figure 1. The process will start with collecting data. In our case, the author collects transaction history data of VN30 on HOSE and financial news headlines. The process of crawling financial news articles is a process set up by the author to automatically collect news headlines from various sources on online newspapers. The selection of quality information from the press is extremely important, a quality input data source will be the core value to be able to reduce the load of preprocessing processes because almost 90% of the process of implementing a project is focused on data processing. This is because that the quality of data also affects the forecast performance. If the dataset has many defects, machine learning models will have difficulty learning and finding rules and these defects will lead to poor forecast results. For the price movement of stock price, supply and demand of trader and investors are the core factors (Kaya & Karsligil, 2010). In order for investors to make reasonable investment decisions, financial news is one of the most important and useful information for investors in addition to the internal information of stocks. However, being able to read and analyze all the articles coming from many different news sources is an extremely difficult, costly and time-consuming problem. Moreover, financial news only really effectively and strongly affects the stock market in the short term (Gidofalvi & Elkan, 2001; Kaya & Karsligil, 2010). Thus, the analysis of all articles is considered impossible because of their lack of practical application. Those are also the reasons that the author has built a forecasting system for stock price movements by only analyzing financial news articles published in reputable newspaper offices. The news articles usual has ability to represent the entire content and ideas of an article. For the Vietnamese market, Vnexpress and Vietnamnet newspapers are two close and prestigious

editorial departments for Vietnamese readers and this is also the reason why the author collected financial news related to the stock market or articles having content related to the VN30 index from these newspapers. After identifying the source of the target newspapers which need to collect data, the author proceeds to determine the data format. Most online articles are programmed and stored as HTML tags. Therefore, the author needs to set up a system to collect article headlines that must follow the author's keywords, conditions as well as other relevant information such as publication date, newspaper link. As a result of this process, a total of more than 15,000 news articles were collected by the author within from January 2017 to January 2023. After completing the necessary data collection step, the author has applied a number of different methods to preprocess the data at the second phase.

In phase 2, the author first processes the financial news headlines and sentiment analysis into three dummy variables including positive, negative, and neutral. However, for dummy data, in order to avoid the occurrence of perfect multicollinearity, the author only retains two variables are positive and negative. The next step of phase 2, the author summarizes the previous research articles to find the input variables which are suitable to the research topic. The correct selection of input features will help the author save time on data collection, data processing as well as saving computing resources for the computer. Moreover, if we include too many variables that are not related to the operating rules of the securities market, or the lack of important relevant factors will confuse models and lead to a negative effect on the predictability. At the end of phase 2, the author processes historical transactions of the VN30-Index as well as calculates the necessary technical analysis indicators for the training of the model. Finally, the author normalizes the data to have a set of data with appropriate scales.

Figure 1. General architecture of approach for forecasting VN30 index

Source: Author's summary

In phase 3, the author builds and compares machine learning and deep learning models. In this research paper, the author applies a number of popular models, and they are considered to have good predictive power for the author's research topic such as random forest, support vector machine, ANN and LSTM. In each specific model, the author also tested the different levels of impact of the financial news article's lag on the predictive ability of the above models. In addition, the author has also tested through many different parameters to be able to find the most optimal results for the author's data.

In the final phase, the author takes the forecast results and compares between approaches and models to find the most effective forecast model for the VN30 index based on classification performance metrics such as accuracy, recall, precision, and receiver operating characteristics (ROC) curve. Besides, the author is also interested in finding out the answer to whether the inclusion of information from financial news headlines and technical analysis information actually brings better forecast productivity.

3.2. Data Setting

In this study, the author studies the price movement of the VN30-Index daily from January 2017 to January 2023. Based on the previous empirical research papers on the topic of forecasting the trend of the stock market from domestic to foreign countries, author has built machine learning and deep learning models based on dependent variables (Y) which are VN30 stock index of HOSE and independent variables (X_i) including the number of buy orders, number of sell orders, buy-orders volume, sell-orders volume, order matching volume, put-through transaction volume, the 10 days SMA, the 20 days SMA, 10 days EMA, 20 days EMA, 7 days RSI, 9 days RSI, 14 days RSI and the dummy variable of the financial news including positive and negative news. This dataset is collected by the author on publicly listed stock exchanges in Vietnam market and the pieces of financial news are collected from two prestigious and famous newspapers in Vietnam are Vnexpress and Vietnamnet.

For the variable measuring the trend of price movement of the VN30-Index, author uses the indicator "close price" to calculate the return using the following formula.

$$Return_t = \frac{Close\ price_t - Close\ price_{t-1}}{Close\ price_{t-1}}$$

In order to classify the increase or decrease trends of the VN30-Index to serve as a premise for forecasting the Vietnam stock market, author needs to encode the VN30-Index's return value into two labels are 0 and 1. If the return is greater than 0, the target variable will equal to 1 and if the return is less than 0, the dependent variable equal to 0. In the data set of the author, the dependent variable has a total number of variables 1 is 849 observed and a total number of variables 0 is 664 observed after being encoded by the author.

$$Return_t \{0: Return_t \leq 0 \ 1: Return_t > 0\}$$

The data related to forecasting VN30-Index is extremely large and diverse, however, the selection of suitable features is aimed at reducing data dimensions, increasing data quality as

well as increasing forecast performance. All features are included in the forecast model which is described in detail in Table 1. For dependent variables are historical value data and technical analysis indicators, the author performs tests and analyzes them through descriptive statistics. From there, the author can control data defects such as outlier, noise, missing value, and so on. In particular, in this study, the author uses sentiment analysis techniques for newspaper headlines to reflect the impact of investor psychology on the stock market in the short term.

Table 1. Data Description

Features	Description
Number of buy orders	The total number of buy orders for the VN30 index.
Buy-orders volume	The total volume of all buy orders for the VN30 index.
Number of sell orders	The total number of sell orders for the VN30 index.
Sell-orders volume	The total volume of all sell orders for the VN30 index.
Order matching volume	The total volume of matched buy and sell orders for the VN30 index.
Put-through transaction volume	The total volume of put-through transactions (transactions outside the exchange's order book) for the VN30 index.
10 days SMA	The Simple Moving Average of the VN30 index closing prices over the past 10 trading days.
20 days SMA	The Simple Moving Average of the VN30 index closing prices over the past 20 trading days
10 days EMA	The Exponential Moving Average of the VN30 index closing prices over the past 10 trading days.
20 days EMA	The Exponential Moving Average of the VN30 index closing prices over the past 20 trading days.
7 days RSI	The Relative Strength Index of the VN30 index over the past 7 trading days.
9 days RSI	The Relative Strength Index of the VN30 index over the past 9 trading days.
14 days RSI	The Relative Strength Index of the VN30 index over the past 14 trading days.
Positive	Positive feature has value 1 if there are positive news about VN30 and stock market.
Negative	Negative feature has value 1 if there are negative news about VN30 and stock market.

Source: Author's summary

In order to be able to perform sentiment analysis techniques, the author needs to collect financial news data about this market in a period corresponding to the forecast period and ensure that the source of the news is reputable, quality, censored as well as able to reflect well the influence of financial news information on investor psychology and the market. In the history of research, to be able to sentiment analysis of text data, researchers can apply statistical algorithms or use natural language processing (NLP) techniques. With the modernization and development of information technology, the author only needs to apply the

natural language analysis library named “TextBlob” – one of the famous natural language processing libraries for sentiment analysis. Before analyzing, the author needs to split this information into common phrases to evaluate the reasonableness of the collected author's news. In particular, the most popular phrases have content related to VN30-Index, stock market, securities, banking, news, and so on, which be shown in the Figure 2. This proves that collected data and using them to forecast the price movement of VN30 is completely suitable and the author expects them to have a strong impact on forecast performance.

Figure 2. Common words frequency of news headline

Source: Author's summary

The author analyzes the headlines of the articles and calculates two indexes of polarity and subjectivity to assess the sentiment of the original newspaper headline. Polarity refers to the strength of an opinion. This indicator ranges from -1 to 1, representing positive, negative, and natural news. If something has a strong positive feeling or emotion associated with it will indeed have a certain orientation towards all other aspects of the existence of that object. If the title of an article has a negative calculated polarity, then the paper carries negative information, if the polarity is greater than zero, the article content tends to be positive, and the title with this index of 0 is articles with natural information. Subjectivity refers to the degree to which a person is personally involved in an object. What matters the most here are personal connections and individual experiences with that object, which may or may not differ from someone else's point of view. Subjectivity has a value from 0 to 1, showing an increasing degree of subjectivity as this index gets closer to value 1. Sentiment analysis tools must be able to distinguish between both polarity and subjectivity in order to analyze opinions of users correctly. An opinion can have a high degree of subjectivity if it is expressed as a personal experience, whereas a low degree may indicate someone else's viewpoint on something else.

Finally, to be able to train the model and make predictions, the author divided the dataset into two datasets including training data and testing data with a certain seed. The training dataset consists of 80% of the number of observations used for training purposes and finds the forecasting rules. The testing dataset consists of the remaining 20% of observations which is obligated to evaluate the model's predictive performance.

According to previous studies related to price movement of the stock market, there have been many different forecasting techniques that have been put into research or applied in practice. In particular, the analysis of technical methods or the use of traditional models still has many shortcomings as well as not bring good forecasting results. Nowadays, with the extremely strong development of machine learning and AI models, the author set up two settings to serve comparing the predictive result. Setting (1) using input data is the historical information of VN30 index including the number of buy orders, the number of sell orders, the volume of buy orders, the quantity of sell orders, the volume of executed orders, the volume of agreed transactions. Setting (2), the author forecasts the stock market of Vietnam by adding to the model some extensive pieces of information compared to setting (1) including technical analysis indicators and financial news.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics of the dataset that the authors collected 1513 observations with variables including historical price data of VN30 index, technical analysis indicators were displayed at Table 2, and dummy variables of sentiment analysis the newspaper headlines including positive and negative variables was displayed at Table 3 from January 2017 to January 2023.

Table 2. Statistical description of numeric variables

Variables	Obs	Mean	σ(SD)	Min	Max
Number of buy orders	1,513	66,774.12	52,377.39	205	315,014
Buy-orders volume	1,513	196,533,544.77	126,383,423.55	1,802,000	779,084,100
Number of sell orders	1,513	58,645.49	44,562.39	304	268,101
Sell-orders volume	1,513	199,406,752.66	133,175,147.08	1,802,000	800,846,700
Order matching volume	1,513	107,108,336.50	74,528,782.90	9,488	235,441,250
Put-through volume	1,513	14,340,475.54	15,707,424.28	623.33	1,543.98
10 days SMA	1,513	1,020.90	257.27	619.83	1,533.27
20 days SMA	1,513	1,019.39	257.54	625.23	1,543.64
10 days EMA	1,513	1,020.94	256.91	622.35	1,534.48
20 days EMA	1,513	1,019.46	256.76	4.66	96.49
7 days RSI	1,513	55.24	19.20	6.50	94.93
9 days RSI	1,513	54.82	17.29	10.63	91.63
14 days RSI	1,513	54.12	14.44	10.63	91.63
Return	1,513	0.0004	0.0132	-0.0673	0.0531

Source: Author's summary

For the historical price data of the VN30 index, this information has a relatively large volatility and wide data dispersion. This statistic shows that the volatility of the market's trading volume among different periods is massive. This also means that the Vietnamese stock

market is a vibrant market and has relatively high volatility. This will also be a limitation for researchers in working out effective solutions to forecast this market.

The SMA, EMA indicator within 10 days and 20 days are almost identical in mean when fluctuating around 1020 points and moving averages around 257 points. This shows that the trend of price fluctuations of the VN30 index in 10 days and 20 days is not significantly strong. In addition, the 7 days, 9 days, and 14 days Relative Strength Indexes also have near-equal ranges, which is from 54 to more than 55. The volatility of these indices also decreases in the long term when their standard deviations are 19.20, 17.29 and 14.44 respectively. For the return of the VN30 index, this index has a minimum value of -0.0673, a maximum value of 0.0531, a low mean value when only reaching 0.0004 and quite a high volatility when the standard deviation of the VN30-index's return is 0.0132. This shows that the price movement during the observation period is quite large.

Another important point, the scatter of all of variables in this dataset is very wide and greatly varies, indicating the diversity of values of the variables. This data property will easily cause white noise phenomena that reduce the predictive performance of machine learning and deep learning models. Therefore, it is necessary to standardize data by scaling data to be able to have the most optimal forecast results.

Table 3. Statistical description of dummy variables

	Negative	Positive
Count	1513	1513
Unique	2	2
Top	0	0
Freq	964	760

Source: Author's summary

From January 2017 to January 2023, there were 753 days of positive news about the VN30 index, 549 days of negative news and 211 days of neutral news. The author expects that the days of good news about the stock market will help this one have an up trend and vice versa.

4.2. Estimation Results

4.2.1. Performance measures

In this empirical study, the author will test and make comparative results between using only historical value information of VN30-Index for forecasting and adding on extensive information such as technical analysis indicators and market information by financial news. In the SVM model, the use of different kernels will have different forecasts result (Wang & Xu, 2017). Therefore, the author also used the two most popular kernels of SVM, Linear and RBF. For deep learning models, the author used the traditional structure of these models with 3 layers. In the ANN model, relu is the activation function chosen for use because of its suitability and computing power, while the tanh activation function will be used in the LSTM

model. In both deep learning models, the author sets up for these models with 5000 epochs and calls back the “EarlyStopping” function to save the time and computer resources when running the model. When it comes to performance measures in classification problems, confusion matrix, classification reports and ROC curve figure are the most important tools.

4.2.2. Estimation Results

The forecast results of the model are shown in Table 4. In the above models, when using only historical data of VN30 index, Random Forest is the model having the best forecast results with accuracy of 56%. However, the level of detection of downtrend dates of this model is still limited when recall indicator is only 0.38. Besides Random Forest, ANN model also gives a similar result to Random Forest when the accuracy of this model reaches 55%. In contrast, for LSTM models, the predicted ability of this model is the least effective although this is the model that is expected to do best compared to other models. LSTM model with 10 days window rolling achieved the highest performance compared to other time steps but only achieved an 0.51 of accuracy level. When increasing the number of time steps in this model, the predictability decreases relatively markedly. For the SVM model using the linear and poly kernel, both of these models are only good at detecting bullish forecasts when the recall of label 1 is 100%, while the recall of label 0 is 0% and 1%. When applying the RBF kernel, this result was improved but not significantly when the recall of label 0 reached only 0.03.

Table 4. Model results using historical data

Model	Accuracy	Label 0		Label 1	
		Precision	Recall	Precision	Recall
Random Forest	0.56	0.54	0.38	0.57	0.71
SVM - Linear	0.53	0.00	0.00	0.53	1.00
SVM - RBF	0.53	0.57	0.03	0.53	0.98
SVM - Poly	0.54	1.00	0.01	0.53	1.00
ANN	0.55	0.54	0.30	0.56	0.78
LSTM – 10 days	0.51	0.54	0.44	0.49	0.59
LSTM – 20 days	0.49	0.54	0.10	0.49	0.91
LSTM – 30 days	0.47	0.44	0.05	0.47	0.93
LSTM – 60 days	0.46	0.43	0.08	0.46	0.89

Source: Author’s summary

In general, most of the above models have a forecast result higher than the baseline level of 50%, but this level of accuracy is not really effective and meaningful for investors and policymakers. Therefore, adding on more useful information into the forecast model VN30-Index is extremely urgent.

After adding more new variables and running the models, the author obtains the results shown in Table 5. Overall, the new results show that all models have a positive improvement in predictability. Support vector machine is the model having the most improvement as well as getting the best forecasting performance when the author adds more elements of financial news

and technical analysis indicators to the forecasting model. In particular, the Radial Basic Function is the best kernel in helping the SVM model achieve the best classification results when it comes to accuracy up to 75%, the accuracy for each label is also good with precision labels 0 and 1, respectively 0.76 and 0.74. In addition, this model is also considered feasible with practice when the recall of this model reaches 67% for the downtrend and 81% for the uptrend of the VN30 index. In addition to RBF, the other two kernels also provide quite impressive predictive performance when having a prediction accuracy percentage of 73% for linear kernel and 74% for poly kernel, respectively. In addition to the SVM model using the RBF kernel, ANN is also a good model when the difference in predicted performance of this model to SVM is negligible. The ANN model has also done well in accurately forecasting the overall market as well covering the fluctuating trends of the VN30-Index when the accuracy index is 0.71, recall of label 0 is 0.61 and recall of label 1 up to 0.80. For both settings, ANN is not the best model but this one always provides a good forecasting ability as well as there is not much difference from the best model for each setting.

Table 5. Model results using technical analysis and financial news

Model	Label 0			Label 1	
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Precision	Recall
Random Forest	0.69	0.68	0.63	0.69	0.75
SVM - Linear	0.73	0.75	0.64	0.72	0.81
SVM - RBF	0.75	0.76	0.67	0.74	0.81
SVM - Poly	0.74	0.77	0.65	0.73	0.83
ANN	0.71	0.73	0.61	0.70	0.80
LSTM – 10 days	0.53	0.51	0.33	0.53	0.71
LSTM – 20 days	0.55	0.54	0.43	0.55	0.66
LSTM – 30 days	0.53	0.52	0.46	0.54	0.59
LSTM – 60 days	0.52	0.55	0.44	0.50	0.62

Source: Author's summary

In the LSTM algorithm, with different time steps applied to this model, it does not bring better forecast productivity than the other models. However, for the LSTM model with window rolling 20 days is the time step to produce the highest results and window rolling 60 days is the least effective results. This can be explained in part by the fact that the characteristics of the input time series data as well as the LSTM model with tangential properties have strongly affected the forecast results. Thus, the time step of 20 days is the period that contains a lot of quality data or is suitable for the volatility trend of VN30 in the market, so it has led to better results than the rest of the steps. One more important conclusion, through testing various models from machine learning to deep learning, the author concludes that adding technical analysis and financial market news to the model will help all models improve forecast performance in most models. This is also completely consistent with the statements and results of previous research in this field.

Figure 3. ROC curve when using technical analysis and financial news

Source: Author's summary

In addition to using classification reports, the author visualized the ROC curve figure to draw conclusions from a new perspective on the predictive performance of the models and compared it with results from Table 7 to make the final conclusion. In addition, the author only visualizes models including random forest, ANN and support vector machine with different kernels that ignore the LSTM model. The reason is that the prediction results of the LSTM model are too different from the other models and the forecasting performance is not really good at both different settings. In Figure 3, the random forest has a better ROC curve than the ANN model even though the results in Table 7 show the opposite one. The support vector machine is the model having the best predictability of VN30 index price movement since all three kernels have a fairly high area under the ROC curve. In particular, the SVM model using RBF kernel is the algorithm that has the ROC curve closest to point (0, 1) compared to the other two kernels and this is also the best model when compared to other models used in the article. Thus, based on both the classification report and ROC curve results, the author concludes that the support vector machine model using the RBF kernel is the most suitable model for Vietnam data within the period from 2017 to 2023.

When analyzing the impact of financial news articles on the forecast performance of the price movement of stocks, the author found that the influence of financial news articles level is different among time periods. In this study, the author tested four cases including not using news information, using the news the day before, using the news 5 days ago, 7 days ago, and 10 days ago. In general, using the financial news factor brings a better forecasting performance has been proven in Table 7 by the author.

Figure 4. Impaction of financial news article on model performance

Source: Author's summary

For Figure 4, the author uses this figure for the purpose of clarifying and deepening the impact of the news on the stock market. The impact of financial news on the stock market is considered to reach the best result in a short period. The results show that when using the information 1 day before the forecast date, the model will peak the forecast result. When using more information in the previous days such as 5 days, 7 days, or 10 days, the forecast performance of the model decreases gradually. For a vibrant stock market like Vietnam, the 1-lag of using financial news articles to forecast the best price movement result is entirely suitable. Investors are always concerned about the negative developments in the highly sensitive market, or they always want to take advantage of information as quickly as possible to create more profits. In addition, using financial news in the past with high lags will be difficult to fully and properly reflect the nature of the market at the time of mention. Moreover, if based on too much information on many different days, it will be difficult to accurately identify cases that do not clearly show the community's sentiment towards the stock market, leading to investors' confusion in making the right investment decisions.

In addition to studying the price movement of the VN30 index, the author is also interested in the impact of the VN30 index on the derivatives market, specifically, derivative products used in this article are VN30 futures contracts (VN30F1M). The results in Table 6 have helped the author to conclude that using the price movement of the VN30 index and financial news of the spot market is likely to make forecasts for the derivatives market. Most models selected by the author provide relatively high accuracy, fluctuating around about 74% accuracy.

Table 6. Predict VN30F1M using financial news and VN30-Index

Model	Accuracy	Label 0		Label 1	
		Precision	Recall	Precision	Recall
Random Forest	0.73	0.73	0.70	0.72	0.75
SVM - Linear	0.75	0.76	0.70	0.73	0.79
SVM - RBF	0.74	0.76	0.68	0.72	0.80
SVM - Poly	0.75	0.76	0.70	0.73	0.79
ANN	0.74	0.75	0.68	0.72	0.79

Source: Author's summary

In addition, when considering the impact of forecasting the trend of the spot market affecting the derivatives market, the author has divided it into two cases including the trend of the VN30-Index and the forecasting VN30-index's trend, combined with the financial news in the spot market. The results show that the use of the forecasting VN30-Index price movements to forecast the trend of VN30F1M is less effective than the use of the original VN30-Index information. This is also completely understandable when the forecasting VN30 index has certain errors in the prediction process. However, the difference in forecasting performance between the two cases is negligible. In summary, based on the above results, the author can partly conclude that the VN30-Index predictive model has the ability to forecast the fluctuations of the VN30 future contracts. This experimental result is completely consistent with the author's initial judgment as the previous research papers on this topic.

Table 7. Predict VN30F1M using financial news and VN30 forecasting result

Model	Accuracy	Label 0		Label 1	
		Precision	Recall	Precision	Recall
Random Forest	0.74	0.80	0.77	0.65	0.69
SVM - Linear	0.73	0.72	0.71	0.74	0.73
SVM - RBF	0.76	0.83	0.77	0.67	0.75
SVM - Poly	0.74	0.80	0.77	0.65	0.69
ANN	0.75	0.80	0.77	0.66	0.70

Source: Author's summary

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusions

Making highly accurate level of prediction about the price movement of stock market is extremely important for building a country having a wealthy economy. The successful construction of an effective forecasting model for the VN30 index will help investors and securities analysts have an overview of the stock market in the future as well as this will be the basis to develop the effective trading strategies. Moreover, forecasting the future trend of this market is also an important document for managers and policymakers to be able to develop future economic scenarios and make appropriate and timely adjustment policies.

However, the accurate forecasting of the volatility of this market is extremely complicated and difficult. With the results of this research, the machine learning model is still an effective method with high accuracy, saves time and computer resources. The results also showed that the SVM model with RBF kernel did better than the other model used in the study. However, the forecast results have not yet achieved too high an accuracy index. This can be explained in part by the fact that our country's stock market is still an emerging market. In addition, stock market data always has noise data, non-linear relationships, and so on as well as many external effects that cannot be measured. Although deep learning models are expected to have better VN30-index forecasting performance than machine learning models, both ANN and LSTM models have yet to do well. The main reason for this is that the accuracy of these models depends greatly on the training data. In order to achieve good predictive results, deep research algorithms require an extremely large number of observations to fully understand the behavior of the research object. However, data samples in developing countries such as Vietnam do not meet the needs of learning and analysis, leading to predictions of deep learning method will have low accuracy.

More notably, when adding new variables related to financial news and technical analysis indicators in the author's models, the predictive results are significantly better than using only historical data. This is explained by these new variables having a great impact on the price movement of the VN30 index. However, the effect of these factors on VN30 is only short-term, which historical studies have verified. In particular, using a financial news article with a lag of 1 will bring better forecasting performance than higher lags such as 5, 7 and 10. This has shown that the best model that the author has built is only suitable for being a fundamental reference forecast for investors and businesses when investing and doing business in the Vietnamese stock market as well as author's model does not have enough base to make long-term forecasts for the market. Besides, investors can also use this forecast result as a basis for them to make accurate decisions about when to buy, hold, or sell their derivative assets.

In conclusion, the research results show that financial news on reputable newspapers will have a significantly impact on the trend of stock market. In addition, technical analysis indicators are also one of the factors considered to be extremely effective to forecast the trend of stock movements in the market and these are also considered to be indicators contributing to show investor sentiment for this market. Therefore, researching and finding important indicators and incorporating them into the model to forecast the VN30 index may be more optimal than the model using only historical information.

5.2. Recommendations

Successfully forecasting the price movement of the stock market will bring many benefits to managers, investors as well as the Government. In order to be able to effectively apply forecast models into reality, the author makes a number of recommendations which are suitable for different subjects. For managers, this study provides a reliable VN30 stock price forecasting solution to assist in portfolio and risk management. In addition, managers can also rely on forecast results to be able to plan for short-term strategic adjustments or make more effective management decisions. Managers should speed up the investment in the development of human resources, infrastructure, and essential tools to support the use of predictive models in investment management. However, to optimize asset management, managers also need to

combine other methods such as portfolio diversification, risk management, and real time portfolio adjustments to ensure maximum investment efficiency.

For stock investors, a good trend forecasting model of VN30 is a useful tool in assisting in making more suitable and faster investment decisions. However, investors should not abuse the forecast results of the models excessively. To be able to minimize risks or optimize expected returns, these investors need to learn basic knowledge of securities, economics, politics and society and combine that knowledge with the results provided by the forecasting model.

For policymakers and the Government, this topic provides important information to make decisions on short-term economic and investment policy adjustments on time. The government can use predictive information to make the right policies to support the stock market as well as invest in areas with high growth potential. In addition, the Government also has the responsibility for providing strong regulations and solutions to promote the supervision and management of the securities market to ensure transparency and accurate information for investors and researchers. From that, the Government also could limit the cases where securities companies or individuals having a great influence on the market take advantage of loopholes in the legal framework to carry out illegal activities that cause extremely harmful consequences for Vietnam's stock market. One more crucial point, the Government should thoroughly review as well as ensure the quality of data on macroeconomics, stock markets, derivatives markets, and so on. If the above recommendations are implemented in a standard and timely manner, it will be easier to explore the Vietnamese data source to serve the purpose of building accurate forecasting models.

In addition to the above subjects, some other subjects such as financial analysts, securities companies, and researchers can also select the bright ideas of this research paper to find new research directions and develop more advanced VN30 price movement forecasting models. The following studies in the future may focus on building new learning methods such as reinforcement learning, more complex deep learning, methods that combine different forecast models to achieve better results, or research on forecasting the stock prices of individual companies in VN30. In addition, other researchers also could concentrate on the data mining process to deeply understand the rules as well as control the defects of the dataset. This is extremely important because they will determine almost 90% of the forecast results of the models.

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ACCOUNTING FOR PUBLIC PROPERTY PURCHASE AT PUBLIC NON-BUSINESS UNIT IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract

In order for public non-business units to provide public non-business services to society according to their assigned tasks, the State has equipped them with assets and facilities through many forms including purchase. Public property is not only a necessary condition for public non-business units to perform political tasks assigned by the State, but it is also an important financial resource that can be exploited to develop more public services for the society. Accounting for public assets purchase at public non-business units is one of the activities that need to be uniformly implemented accordance with regulations, especially in the context of digital transformation. Documents on asset management and use, bidding documents, and public investment documents are just a few of the current documents that regulate the contents related to this practice. These documents come into force at different times and cover different sectors and units. The article is the result of research and synthesis in order to provide specific guidance on public procurement forms, funding sources, procurement process and records, user accounts, accounting methods in each case.

Keywords: *Accounting, Digital transformation, Public non-business unit, Public properties*

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the provisions of Clause 1, Article 9, Law on Public Employees 2010: A public non-business unit is established by a competent State agency, a socio-political organization in accordance with the law, a legal entity, providing public services and serving state management.

Along with the development of the economy, public non-business units under the management of the State have also been gradually consolidated that makes a significant contribution to the socio-economic renovation. When operating, these units must be responsible for complying with the provisions of the State Budget Law, standard norms and regulations on regimes for administrative accounting which is promulgated by the State, that aims to meet the requirements of economic and financial management, to strengthen the control of state budget expenditures, to manage public assets and to improve the quality of accounting and the effectiveness of management in administrative organizations (Trang & Hoa, 2023). Therefore, accounting also accounting for purchase of public properties at public non-

business units must ensure the consistency between accounting and requirements of the state and the organization; ensure the consistency of the content and methods of accounting with the State's current accounting regimes. Especially in the digital transformation context, it is necessary to enlighten all information proclaim necessary information as prescribed on the National Procurement Network system <http://muasamcong.mpi.gov.vn>.

This study aims to systematize regulations, methods and operating procedure of public property accounting at public non-business units according in the context of digital transformation including Laws, Decrees, Circulars.

2. RESEARCH LITERATURE

2.1. Accounting for public property purchase at public non-business units in the context of digital transformation

Apart from the legal documents on the management of using public assets, public procurement and investment, there aren't any published researches on regulations, methods and operating procedure of public property accounting at public non-business units according in the context of digital transformation.

2.2. Legal bases for public property purchase at public non-business units

2.2.1. Documents on managing and using assets

(1) Law No. 15/2017/QH14 on June 21, 2017 of the 14th National Assembly regulates the management and use of public property

(2) Decree 151/2017/ND-CP on December 26, 2017 of the Government regulates makes details on a number of articles of the 2017 Law on Management and usage of public property

(3) Circular 144/2017/TT-BTC on December 29, 2017 of the Ministry of Finance guides some contents of Decree 151/2017/ND-CP on December 26, 2017 regulating a number of articles of the Law on Management and use of public property

(4) Decree 63/ND-CP on July 11, 2019 of the Government regulates for sanctioning administrative violations in managing and using of public property; fighting waste; national reserve

(5) Decision 50/2017/QD-TTg on December 31, 2017 of the Prime Minister regulates standards and norms for using machines and equipments

2.2.2. Documents on bidding

(1) Law No. 43/2013/QH13 on November 26, 2013 of the 13th National Assembly regulates bidding

(2) Law No. 03/2022/QH15 on January 11, 2022 of the 15th National Assembly amends and supplements a number of articles of the Law on Public Investment, the Law on Investment in the Mode of Public-Private Partnership, the Law on Investment, and the Law on Housing, Bidding Law, Electricity Law, Enterprise Law, Special Consumption Tax Law and Civil Judgment Enforcement Law

(3) Decree 63/2014/ND-CP on June 26, 2014 of the Government regulates the applying a number of articles of the bidding law on selecting contractor

(4) Decree 25/2020/ND-CP on February 28, 2020 guides the Bidding Law on selecting investor

(5) Circular 10/2015/TT-BKHDT on October 26, 2015 of the Ministry of Planning and Investment regulates on selecting contractor

(6) Circular 19/2015/TT-BKHDT on November 27, 2015 of the Ministry of Planning and Investment regulates on making appraisal reports while selecting contractor

(7) Circular 08/2022/TT-BTC dated February 9, 2022 of the Ministry of Finance regulates the management and the use of revenues and expenditures while selecting contractor

(8) Circular 08/2022/TT-BKHDT on May 31, 2022 guides the provision and posting of information on bidding and selecting contractor on the National bidding network system

(9) Decision 17/2019/QĐ-TTg on April 8, 2019 regulates a number of biddings and procurements in order to maintain regular operations, which is applying the method of selecting contractor in some special cases according to Article 26 of the Law on Bidding

(10) Circular 10/2022/TT-BKHDT on June 15, 2022 regulates the provision, posting of information and selecting contractor on the National bidding network system

(11) Circular 58/2016/TT-BTC on March 29, 2016 regulates the use of state capital for procurement in order to maintain regular operations of state organization and units of the People's Armed Forces, public non-business units, political organizations, socio-political organizations, socio-political-professional organizations, social organizations, socio-professional organizations

2.2.3. Documents on public investment

(1) Law No. 39/2019/QH14 on June 13, 2019 of the 14th National Assembly regulates on public investment

(2) Decree 40/2020/ND-CP on April 6, 2020 of the Government guides the Law on Public Investment

2.3. Research Methods

To conduct the research, the author uses a qualitative research method, specifically the group discussion method on accounting for purchase of public properties at public non-business unit in the context of digital transformation along with the discussed specific contents as follows: Methods of purchase for public properties; Funding; Procurement process and record; Accounts; Methods of accounting

Subjects of discussion are the leader and accountants of public non-business units. After the discussion, the contents of accounting for purchase of public properties at public non-business unit in the context of digital transformation are presented.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS

3.1. Methods of accounting for purchase of public properties at public non-business units

3.1.1. Centralized procurement method

- Centralized procurement method: National or ministerial, sectoral or local centralized organizations will purchase in the method of bidding and assign the organization to use the property by themselves.

- Funding:

(1) Funds are allocated in the annual budget estimate;

(2) Funding sources from the non-business development fund of the public non-business units shall cover part of recurrent expenditures by themselves;

(3) Other legal funding sources of the organization.

- Procedure:

Step 1: The public non-business unit makes a registration of demand for concentrated procurement according to the form (Form No. 01/DK/MSTT) and submits it to the superior.

Step 2: The organization signs a procurement contract with the contractor according to the form (Form No. 05a/TSC-MSTT).

Step 3: The organization receives the property from the contractor:

Minutes of handover of assets (Form No. 06/TSC-MSTT), enclosed with:

(1) Property purchase contract: 01 original copy;

(2) Sales invoice: 01 original or copy as prescribed;

(3) Warranty card: 01 original copy;

(4) Technical documents, user manuals: 01 original copy;

(5) Other relevant documents (if any): 01 copy.

Step 4: Make a minute of handover of assets for relevant departments

Step 5: The property user pays the Contractor:

(1) Annual estimate or investment capital plan;

(2) Property purchase contract;

(3) Advance guarantee (if any);

(4) Minutes of property handover and receipt;

(5) Cost estimate withdrawal, payment request; accreditative;

(6) Written request of the centralized procurement organization to transfer money to the contractor providing the selected property under the signed contract.

Step 6: Finalize, liquidate the Contract and receive the warranty regime

For example, for a public non-business unit in Nghe An, concentrated procurement of assets with a total estimated procurement value of VND 100,000,000 or more and according to the list specified in Decision 640/QĐ - People's Committee dated March 14, 2022 of Nghe An Provincial People's Committee. Time for concentrated procurement: Register before April 15 every year for the state budget sources already arranged in the estimate at the beginning of the year; Register no later than 10 working days for unexpected additional state budget sources in the five years before October 1st; Register before September 30 every year for the Career Development Fund and other legal funding sources (People's Committee of Nghe An province, 2022).

3.1.2. Distributed purchase method

- Distributed procurement method is the method by which agencies, organizations and units directly buy and use assets.

- Funding:

- (1) Sources of recurrent expenditures in annual budget expenditure estimates;
- (2) Non-business capital for the implementation of the National Target Program;
- (3) Credit capital guaranteed by the State, other capital managed by the State;
- (4) Official Development Assistance (ODA);
- (5) Revenues from fees and charges are left to use;
- (6) Funding sources from revenue from non-business activities and from funds;
- (7) Other legal funding sources as prescribed.

- Process and documents (DOCS):

Purchase of assets not exceeding 50,000,000 VND						
Case	Purchase of properties under 10,000,000 VND	Procurement of assets from 10 million to less than 20,000,000 VND	Purchase of assets from 20,000,000 to under 50,000,000 VND	Purchase of assets not exceeding 100,000,000 VND	Purchase of assets not exceeding 200,000,000 VND	Purchase of assets over 200,000,000 VND
Form of purchase	Direct purchase			Appointment of a shortened contractor	Shortened competitive offer	Regular competitive offer
Step 1	Define a purchase property list	Define a purchase property list <i>DOCS: Procurement plan of the unit</i>	Define a purchase property list <i>DOCS: Procurement plan of the unit</i>	Determining the inventory of purchased assets and estimating <i>DOCS: List of Procurement and Estimation</i>	Determining the inventory of purchased assets and estimating <i>DOCS: List of Procurement Assets and Procurement Estimation</i>	Determining the inventory of purchased assets and estimating <i>DOCS: List of Procurement Assets and Procurement Estimation</i>
Step 2	Carry out purchase activities	Collect quotes from 02 suppliers <i>DOCS: 02 quotes from 2 different suppliers</i>	Collect quotes from 03 suppliers <i>DOCS: 03 quotes from 3 different suppliers</i>	Make a decision to approve the procurement list and cost estimate <i>DOCS: Decision to approve the procurement list and cost estimate</i>	Make a decision to approve the procurement list and cost estimate <i>DOCS: Decision to approve the procurement list and cost estimate</i>	Make a decision to approve the procurement list and cost estimate <i>DOCS: Decision to approve the procurement list and cost estimate</i>
Step 3	Pay: <i>DOCS: - Receipt of state budget estimate - List of payment vouchers Circular 39/2016/TT-BTC - Financial Invoice, Delivery</i>	Sign a sales contract <i>DOCS: Property purchase and sale contract (03 copies)</i>	Issuing a decision on contractor selection <i>DOCS: Decision approving contractor selection</i>	Issuing a decision on contractor selection <i>DOCS: Contractor selection plan</i>	Prepare and submit a quote request <i>DOCS: Request for quotation</i>	Preparing for contractor selection <i>DOCS: - Required profile - Minutes of appraisal - Decision to approve the request dossier</i>

Case	Purchase of assets not exceeding 50,000,000 VND	Purchase of assets not	Purchase of assets not	Purchase of assets over	
	<i>Minutes, CO/CQ, Warranty</i>				
Step 4	<p>Delivery of property DOCS: Minutes of property delivery, financial invoice, CO/CQ, warranty</p>	<p>Sign a sales contract DOCS: Property purchase and sale contract (03 copies)</p>	<p>Evaluation of contractor selection plan DOCS: Report on appraisal of contractor selection plan</p>	<p>Posting notices of solicitation of offers on the National Procurement System: DOCS: Scanned copy of quote request.</p>	<p>Posting notices of solicitation of offers and dossiers of requirements on the National Procurement System: DOCS: - Scanned copy of the offer notice - Scanned copy of required documents</p>
Step 5	<p>Payment and contract liquidation DOCS: - Receipt of state budget estimate - List of payment documents (Circular 62/2020/TT-BTC) - Purchase and sale contract, Minutes of delivery, contract liquidation - Finance bill</p>	<p>Delivery of property DOCS: Minutes of property delivery, financial invoice, CO/CQ, warranty</p>	<p>Issue a decision approving the contractor selection plan DOCS: Decision approving the contractor selection plan</p>	<p>Receive quotation DOCS: - Quotations of 3 suppliers in the area; - Quotation receipt document</p>	<p>Receipt of proposals from contractors DOCS: - Bidder's proposal (scanned copy and original); - Documents on receipt of proposals</p>
Step 6		<p>Payment and contract liquidation DOCS:</p>	<p>Posting the contractor selection plan on the National Procurement</p>	<p>The expert team evaluates the quotes DOCS: Minutes of</p>	<p>The expert team evaluates the proposals DOCS: Minutes of</p>

Case	Purchase of assets not exceeding 50,000,000 VND	Purchase of assets not	Purchase of assets not	Purchase of assets over
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Receipt of state budget estimate - List of payment documents (Circular 62/2020/TT-BTC) - Decide on contractor selection in special cases - Purchase and sale contract, Minutes of delivery, contract liquidation - Finance bill 	<p>System</p> <p>DOCS: The contractor selection plan and decision approving contractor selection</p>	<p>evaluation of contractor's quotation.</p>	<p>evaluation of contractor's proposals.</p>
Step 7		<p>Rate the quotes</p> <p>DOCS: Quotation evaluation report</p>	<p>Contract Negotiation</p> <p>DOCS: Contract negotiation</p>	<p>Contract Negotiation</p> <p>DOCS: Contract negotiation</p>
Step 8		<p>Contract Negotiation</p> <p>DOCS: Contract negotiation</p>	<p>Approve contractor selection results</p> <p>DOCS: Decision approving contractor selection results</p>	<p>Approve contractor selection results</p> <p>DOCS: Decision approving contractor selection results</p>
Step 9		<p>Approve contractor appointment results</p> <p>DOCS: Decision on approval of contractor appointment results</p>	<p>Posting information on contractor selection results</p> <p>DOCS: Scanned copy of the decision to approve the house selection result</p>	<p>Posting information on contractor selection results</p> <p>DOCS: Scanned copy of the decision approving the contractor selection result</p>

Case	Purchase of assets not exceeding 50,000,000 VND	Purchase of assets not	Purchase of assets not	Purchase of assets over
Step 10		Posting information on contractor selection results <i>DOCS: Scanned copy of the decision to approve the results only</i>	Sign a Procurement Contract <i>DOCS: Procurement contract</i>	Sign a Procurement Contract <i>DOCS: Procurement contract</i>
Step 11		Sign a Procurement Contract <i>DOCS: Procurement contract</i>	Handing over materials and equipment <i>DOCS: - Minutes of acceptance and handover of materials and equipment - Minutes of handing over fixed assets</i>	Handing over materials and equipment <i>DOCS: - Minutes of acceptance and handover of materials and equipment - Minutes of handing over fixed assets</i>
Step 12		Handing over materials and equipment <i>DOCS: - Minutes of acceptance and handover of materials and equipment - Minutes of handing over fixed assets</i>	Determine the amount of work completed <i>DOCS: Table of determining the amount of work completed</i>	Determine the amount of work completed <i>DOCS: Table of determining the amount of work completed</i>
Step 13		Determine the amount of work completed <i>DOCS: Table of determining the</i>	Payment and contract liquidation <i>DOCS: - Finance bill</i>	Payment and contract liquidation <i>DOCS: - Finance bill</i>

Case	Purchase of assets not exceeding 50,000,000 VND	Purchase of assets not amount of work completed	Purchase of assets not - Payment demand letter - Commitment to warranty, user manual, CO, CQ (if any) - Liquidation records - Certificate of withdrawal of State budget estimate/Payment Order	Purchase of assets over - Payment demand letter - Commitment to warranty, user manual, CO, CQ (if any) - Liquidation records - Certificate of withdrawal of State budget estimate/ Payment Order
Step 14		Payment and contract liquidation DOCS: - Finance bill - Payment demand letter - Commitment to warranty, user manual, CO, CQ (if any) - Liquidation records - Certificate of withdrawal of State budget estimate/Payment order		

3.2. Contents of information posting

- For the shortened form of appointment of contractors:
 - (1) Contractor selection plan;
 - (2) Decision approving the contractor selection plan;
 - (3) Decision on approval of contractor appointment results.
- For the short form of competitive offer:
 - (1) Request for quotation;
 - (2) Decision approving contractor selection results
- For the usual form of competitive offer:
 - (1) Scanned copy of the offer notice
 - (2) Scanned copy of required documents

3.3. Information is posted on the National Procurement Network <http://muasamcong.mpi.gov.vn>

- (1) Sign up for an account
- (2) Electronic signature (Digital signature)
- (3) Scan relevant documents

3.4. Accounts

Accountants use the main accounts: Account 153, Account 211, Account 213 and other related accounts such as Account 133, Account 331, Account 366, Account 138, ...

Account 153 - Tools

+ Actual value of tools, supplies imported from stock (purchased from outside, superiors, homemade, ...);
 + Actual value of tools, redundant tools discovered during inventory.
 Actual value of tools, supplies currently in stock of the unit.

+ Actual value of tools, supplies out of stock;
 + Actual value of tools, missing tools discovered during inventory

Account 211 - Tangible fixed assets

+ The cost of tangible fixed assets increases due to procurement, completion of construction, handing over and putting into use, grant, sponsorship, donation, donation, aid...;
 + Adjusting to increase the cost of fixed assets due to asset upgrading according to the project;
 + Other cases that increase the cost of fixed assets (Revaluation of fixed assets...).

+ The cost of tangible fixed assets decreases due to transfer to another entity, sale, liquidation or other reasons (loss...);
 + The cost of tangible fixed assets decreases due to dismantling one or several parts;
 + Other cases that reduce the cost of fixed assets (re-evaluate fixed assets...).

Cost of tangible fixed assets currently in the unit.

Account 213 - Intangible fixed assets

The cost of intangible fixed assets increased

The cost of intangible fixed assets decreases

Cost of intangible fixed assets currently in the unit

3.5. Accounting method

3.5.1. Methods of accounting for procurement of tools and tools

(1) Purchase of tools and tools for warehousing with state budget sources.

- Withdrawal of purchase estimate: Dr. 153 / Cr. 366 (36612)

Simultaneously: Cr. 008 (if operating expenses are withdrawn)

- Withdrawal of deposits (including deposits issued by Real Money Orders) to buy:

Dr. 153 / Cr. 112

At the same time: Dr. 337 (3371) / Cr. 366 (36612)

Simultaneously: Cr. 012 (if purchased with funds issued by Orders to pay real money)

Cr. 018 (if purchased with other retained operating income).

(2) Importing tools and supplies purchased with foreign aid or loans: Dr. 153 / Cr. 112, 331,

At the same time: Dr. 337 (3372) / Cr. 366 (36622)

(3) Enter the inventory of tools and tools purchased with the deductible fee source, leaving:

Dr. 153 / Cr.111, 112, 331,

Simultaneously: Dr. 337 (3373) / Cr. 366 (36632)

At the same time: Cr. 014

(4) Entering inventory of tools and supplies purchased on credit for non-business activities:

Dr. 153 / Cr. 331

(5) Entering stock of tools and tools purchased from outside with advance money:

Dr. 153 / Cr. 141

At the same time, if purchased from the state budget; foreign aid and debt sources; Deductible and remaining fee sources: Dr. 337 (3371, 3372, 3373) / Cr. 366 (36612, 36622, 36632).

Simultaneously: Cr. 012 (if issued by order to pay real money)

Cr. 014 (if granted by deductible fee source, leave it)

3.5.2. Accounting method for the purchase of fixed assets

(1) In case of purchase and investment of fixed assets with operating revenues provided by the state budget

- If purchased and put into use immediately, not through installation, test run:

+ Withdrawal of fixed asset purchase estimate: Dr. 211, 213 / Cr. 366 (36611)

At the same time, Cr. 008

+ Withdrawal of deposits to buy fixed assets: Dr. 211, 213/ Cr. 112

Simultaneously: Cr. 012 (if using funds granted by the Order to pay real money), or
Cr. 018 (if other operating income is used).

At the same time: Dr. 337 (3371) / Cr. 366 (36611)

- If purchased fixed assets have to go through installation, test run:

+ Expenses incurred in connection with the purchase, installation, test run:

Dr. 241 (2411) / Cr.112, 331, 366... (expenses for purchase, installation, test run...).

Simultaneously: Cr. 008: If the estimate is withdrawn, or

Cr. 012: If using funds granted by the Order to pay real money, or

Cr. 018: If purchased with other operating income, it is left.

+ When installation, test run is completed, fixed assets are handed over to be put into use:

Dr. 211, 213/ Cr. 241 (2411).

(2) In case of purchase of fixed assets with foreign aid or debt

- If purchased and put into use immediately, not through installation, test run:

Dr. 211, 213 / Cr. 111, 112, 331, ...

Concurrently: Dr. 337 (3372) / Cr. 366 (36621)

- If purchased fixed assets have to go through installation, test run:

Dr. 241 (2411) / Cr. 111, 112, 331, ... (cost of installation, test run...)

When the installation is completed, handing over and putting into use:

Dr. 211, 213/ Cr. 241 (2411).

Concurrently: Dr. 337 (3372) / Cr. 366 (36621)

(3) In case of purchasing fixed assets with a deductible fee source, leave

- If purchased and put into use immediately, not through installation, test run:

Dr. 211, 213 / Cr. 111, 112, 331, ...

At the same time: Cr. 014

At the same time: Dr. 337 (3373) / Cr. 366 (36631).

- If purchased fixed assets have to go through installation, test run:

Dr. 241 (2411) / Credit Cr. 111, 112, 331, ... (expenses for purchase, installation, test run...).

At the same time: Cr. 014

When the installation is completed, handing over and putting into use: Dr. 211, 213/ Cr. 241 (2411).

At the same time: Dr. 337 (3373) / Cr. 366 (36631).

(4) In case fixed assets are purchased using the Welfare Fund, the Non-business Development Fund

Dr. 211, 213 / Cr. 111, 112, 331, ...

At the same time: Dr. 431 (43121, 43141) / Cr. 431 (43122, 43142).

(5) Accounting for increase in tangible fixed assets by means of centralized procurement in the form of signing a framework agreement

- At the unit using the asset that is the unit that directly purchases the asset:

+ When receiving fixed assets: Dr. 211 / Cr.112, 331, 366 (36611).

If withdrawing the operating expenditure estimate, at the same time, Cr. 008

+ If purchased fixed assets must be installed and tested:

Dr. 241 (2411) / Cr. 112, 331, 366 (36611).

If withdrawing the operating expenditure estimate, at the same time, Cr. 008

+ When the installation is completed, handing over and putting into use:

Dr. 211 / Cr. 241 (2411).

- At the asset user unit that receives the asset from the centralized procurement unit:

+ When receiving fixed assets: Dr. 211 / Cr. 366 (36611).

+ In case the fixed assets received must be installed, tested, paid registration fee and other related expenses, when incurred:

Dr. 241 (2411) (cost of installation, test run...) / Cr. 366 (36611).

At the same time, Cr. 008

+ When the installation, test run... is completed, the property is handed over and put into use:

Dr. 211 (installation and testing expenses) / Cr. 241 (2411)

4. CONCLUSION

Unification and uniform implementation of public property procurement accounting at public non-business units is an objective necessity in the process of public asset management by functional agencies. At the same time, the unification also creates conditions for public non-business units to perform this work fully, timely and accurately. The research results include accounting processes, procedures and methods that can be used by management agencies to issue guiding documents for public non-business units to perform public asset procurement accounting. in the context of digital transformation.

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FACTORS AFFECTING THE INTENSION TO CHOOSE A JOB AT GLOBAL AUDITING CORPORATIONS – A REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

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Abstract

This paper is based on the theory of rational action (TRA) developed in 1967 by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen and the theory of intended behavior (TPB) developed by Ajzen from TRA in 1991, in order to study the factors affecting the intention when choosing a job at auditing corporations with a global scale of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing. Through the qualitative research methods, the authors have synthesized and proposed a research model for future empirical studies on the factors affecting the intention to choose a job at auditing corporations with a global scale of students majoring in Accounting – Auditing, Working environment and development opportunities; Brand and reputation of the organization; Income levels and preferential policies of the group; Family, friends and colleagues; Elements of professional skills.

Keywords: *TRA, TPB, intention to choose a job, students of Accounting - Auditing, a global audit corporation*

1. INTRODUCTION

The dilemma facing economics students today is where to work so that they can maximize their own working ability and the performance of employees, especially young people. Nowadays, young people at universities of Economics, especially in Accounting - Auditing majors tend to join and work in multinational auditing corporations. In fact, global audit corporations provide their employees with conditions so that employees can maximize their working ability. This has pushed the recruitment of corporations to become more selective and competitive, requiring the candidates to be the best of the Universities of Economics.

Research by U.L. HERATI et al (2012) indicated that large corporations will attract candidates by the reputation of the corporation, the ability to provide background knowledge for candidates, and the remuneration regime. Meanwhile, according to Kerckhofs, L., et al (2021), the article affirms the importance of the candidate's ethics and personality that will affect their intention to choose a job. The research paper of Penelope L. et al (2012) shows the similarity between the perceptions of students and those who have worked at global audit corporations, however, there is a Some disadvantages of multinational auditing corporations

that students do not have the opportunity to access if they do not work officially at these corporations. Authors Huynh Truong Huy and La Thuy Dung (2011) in the study on Factors affecting the decision to choose a workplace, found that career development opportunities are the main factors affecting the decision to choose a workplace. candidate's job. But according to author Nguyen Quoc Nghi (2012), the factors of ensuring financial stability as well as the remuneration for employees are the key factors for candidates to choose to work at global audit firms.

The literature review results show that there are a number of factors that influence the intention to choose a job that have been verified by previous studies such as: *“Working environment and development opportunities”* has been appeared in all studies that we reviewed (Huynh Truong Huy and La Thuy Dung, 2011; Penelope L. et al. (2012); Tran Thuy Lieu et al., 2015; Dinh Thanh Hiep, 2018); U.L. HERAT1 et al.; 2019); *“Brand and reputation of the corporation”* (Penelope L. et al., 2012; Dinh Thanh Hiep, 2018; U.L. HERAT1 et al., 2019); *“Income levels and preferential policies”* (Tran Thuy Lieu et al., 2015; Dinh Thanh Hiep, 2018;U.L. HERAT1 et al., 2019); The variable *“Family, friends and colleagues”* was found to have a negative impact on the intention to choose a job in the study of Huynh Truong Huy and La Thuy Dung (2011); But the research results of Penelope L. and colleagues (2012) and Tran Thuy Lieu and colleagues (2015) found a positive impact; The variable *“Professional skill factors”* has only appeared in foreign research articles (Penelope L. et al. (2012), U.L. HERAT1 et al. (2019), Kerckhofs, L., et al. (2021), which has not been verified by studies in Vietnam.

Inheriting the studies related results to job choice intentions in the world and in Vietnam, the authors also rely on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (developed from the theory of coordinated action). TRA management). The TRA theoretical model includes two main factors “attitude” and “subjective norm” that mainly contribute to increasing the likelihood of behavioral performance. Developed from the above model, the TPB theory of planned behavior model adds the factor “Perceived behavioral control” that directly affects the tendency to perform the behavior. Combined with the results of previous studies, the authors propose a new model “Factors affecting the intention to choose a job at global auditing corporations of students majoring in accounting and auditing at universities majoring in economics in Hanoi”.

In Vietnam, there has not been any official research to test the views of Accounting – Auditing students majoring when they choose a career. Therefore, this study was conducted with the aim of understanding why and what important factors promote the choice of employment at multinational auditing corporations of students majoring in Accounting - Audit and then propose a research model and development direction of this research in the future.

This paper is written in the following structure: The first part is an introduction; The second is an overview of related previous studies, background theory, to propose a research model on the factors affecting the intention to choose a job at global-scale auditing corporations of Accounting – Auditing students. Fourth is methodology; The last part is Conclusions and suggestions for future research directions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW, BACKGROUND THEORY AND PROPOSED RESEARCH MODEL

2.1. Literature review

Currently, in the world, there have been a number of studies on the choice of student's workplace, typically:

The Study of Factors Affecting the Intention of Selecting an Internship Programme of Management Faculty Undergraduates in Sri Lankan State Universities, U.L. Herat1 et al.(2012): The paper presents the research results on the factors affecting the intention to choose the internship program of students at universities in Sri Lanka. The research team has included the model with independent variables as (1) the reputation of the organization, (2) the ability to cover the knowledge and experience of the program, (3) the ability to provide valuable documentation and (4) ability to subsidize employees.

Starting your career at an accounting firm: The role of personality in explaining career starts, Kerckhofs, L., et al. (2021). The paper is the result of research on the influence of personality on the decision to work in the accounting industry and job choice at auditing firms with a global scale (hereinafter we refer to it as Big 4) of graduates from different Belgian universities. The study has introduced four independent variables including: Bright personality traits and Dark personality traits affect the pursuit of accounting profession; Bright personality traits and Dark personality traits influence the decision to work at Big 4.

The factors that affect accountants' decisions to seek careers with big 4 versus non-big 4 accounting firms, Penelope L. et al. (2012). This paper has shown that the factors affecting the decision to work at global auditing firms (Big 4) or small audit firms (non-Big 4) with a model of 3 variables ((1) Attitude, (2) Subjective standards, (3) Perception, behavioral control).

Tran Thuy Lieu et al. (2015) have shown that the following factors have an impact on students' decision to choose a workplace after graduation, from strong to weak as follows: political factors preferential book; factors on relationships, emotions; factors of income, salary, living expenses; factors of living environment, geographical conditions and factors of working conditions.

Dinh Thanh Hiep (2018) has conducted a study to find out the influencing factors for choosing to work at the Southwest petroleum company, the research results show that there are 6 influencing factors (1) between individuals and organizations; (2) Factors of working environment; (3) Income factor; (4) Elements of the nature of work; (5) brand and reputation factors of the organization; (6) Factors of recruitment process that affect employees' decision to choose to work at Southwest Petroleum Company.

Huynh Truong Huy and La Thuy Dung (2011) in their research on Factors affecting the decision to choose a workplace: the case of Can Tho University students also noticed factors such as learning and development opportunities. Occupation and income are the main reasons for choosing a workplace.

Nguyen Quoc Nghi (2012): Through analyzing the independent and dependent variables of the factors affecting the workers' decision to work in Hoa Phu industrial park, the author has found that the main factors affecting the decision include: factors of industrial park conditions,

factors of relations and support, factors of safety assurance, factors of economic benefits, factors of company policy. In this study, the author has pointed out that a new factor affecting the decision is the factor of safety.

The research review shows that there are similarities between the studies in the world and in Vietnam on the factors affecting the students' intention to choose a job at auditing corporations with a global scale. All research papers show similar results on the factor "Working environment and development opportunities", showing that this is a key factor affecting the intention of students to choose a job. In addition, the factor of "Brand and reputation of the organization" also affects the intention to choose a workplace of Accounting - Auditing students. In addition, other factors such as: "Income level and preferential policies of global auditing corporations"; "The influence of external factors such as human factors (family, friends and colleagues)"; "Professional skill factor" is also the key contributing to the choice of workplace of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing. However, no official research has been published in Vietnam or the world yet to prove the point of view on job selection at auditing corporations of global scale. Therefore, this study is pointed out to promote the job selection at auditing corporations with a global scale of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing in Hanoi city. The study proposes a research model and development direction of this research in the future.

2.2. Background theory

To analyze and build a model to propose factors affecting the intention to choose a job in global audit corporations of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing at universities in the business sector. The research group uses the theory of rational action (TRA) built in 1967 by two psychologists Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen and developed into an economic research group in Hanoi city. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) in 1991. According to the theory of rational action, all human actions are predictable based on attitudes and behavioral intentions that have existed since Their previous theory, along with that, also shows that stronger intentions increase the motivation to perform the behavior, which increases the likelihood that the behavior is performed, the TRA theoretical model consists of two factors. the main factors "attitude" and "subjective norm".

Figure 1: The theory of rational action (TRA) model

Source; Ajzen, I. (1991)

However, after 1991, when Ajzen evolved from TRA theory to TPB theory, assuming that a behavior can be predicted or explained by behavioral propensities to perform that behaviour, the trends The behavior is assumed to include motivational factors that affect the behavior, in the TPB model, the factors affecting the "attitude" of the individual are still based on the factors that the TRA model offers. However, to further explain the tendency to perform behavior, Ajzen added a third factor to the model: "Perceived behavioral control", this factor has contributed to the difference with the theory of rational action. TRA management, which overcomes the limitations of this model in cases where applicants have no control over their choices. Ajzen has suggested that the factor "Perceived behavioral control" directly affects the tendency to perform the behavior and if the individual receives the correct degree of control, then behavioral control also predicts the behavior.

Figure 2: The theory of intended behavior (TPB) model

Source: Ajzen, I. and Fishbein, M. (1975).

2.3. Methodology

To achieve the research objective, we use qualitative research method through the review of relevant documents. The documents are searched on many online databases such as Google Scholar, Science Direct, Scopus,... through the search for key keywords such as TRA, TPB, job choice intention, Accounting student. Auditing - Auditing, a global-scale auditing group. This method has found a large number of articles published in journals, scientific conferences, ... research on factors affecting intention when choosing a job at corporations and companies. Then, we select a number of articles that are considered the basis of the research problem and the articles published in recent years that are most suitable with the research goal of finding out the factors affecting the Job choice intention of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH MODEL PROPOSAL

In recent years, the intention to choose a job at multinational auditing corporations is increasingly interested by both young students and those with experience in the industry, so the research team has tried try to identify the factors and explain the extent of their influence on the

candidate's intention to choose a workplace. The group of influencing factors are respectively;

- **Working environment and development opportunities:** Most of the global companies have a professional working environment, the staffs are people with deep professional knowledge and extensive working experience. This feature makes students feel that it is a place where they can learn and develop themselves through the work they are exposed to and assigned to. Indeed, other studies by Penelope et al. (2012), Herat (2019) all argue that the working environment and development opportunities are one of the key factors that greatly influence the intention to chose workplace selection of employees in general and fresh graduates in particular; These large-scale corporations often orient their employees to a clear path in career development, with a friendly, dynamic working environment and fair treatment among employees. In Vietnam, Huynh Truong Huy and La Thuy Dung (2011) confirmed the research results of Tran Kim Dung and Tran Van Man (2006) when they said that good development opportunities will promote employees' ability to work. especially for young and active people. Tran Thuy Lieu et al. (2015) also affirmed that a modern dynamic working environment is the core for fresh graduates to choose a place to work, not only that, students also tend to Choose a work environment that suits your abilities. Dinh Thanh Hiep (2018) also added that the company has a friendly working environment, ensuring occupational safety standards and good benefits, which have a great influence on the intention to choose to work at the company. Therefore, the authors develop the first hypothesis as:

Hypothesis 1: “Working environment and development opportunities affect the intention to choose a job at a global audit corporation of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing”.

- ***Brand and reputation of the organization:*** Research by Dinh Thanh Hiep (2018) shows that the brand and reputation of the organization are important factors that students care about; The study also confirmed the attitude of students when being accepted into large corporations right after graduation, those students are proud to be employees of the company. Not only that, the brand and reputation of the organization also attracts many talented candidates to apply to the company. According to Penelope L. et al (2012), choosing global corporations is always their first destination. These corporations will often be the ones that are able to provide much better-quality services than the small and medium sized auditing firms, for that reason they are often favored by customers, partners, and clients. trust and appreciation. The second hypothesis put forward is:

Hypothesis 2: “The brand and reputation of the organization have an influence on the intention to choose a job at the global audit corporations of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing”. The larger the group's reputation, the better benefits it offers to retain its employees, so the next factor affects the intention to choose a job at multinational auditing firms is “Income level and preferential policy”.

- ***Income level and preferential policy of the Group:*** After selecting the subject, the company will submit a CV to have the opportunity to work and pay tribute here, what makes students interested next is salary and policy. In addition, according to research by Herat et al. (2019), the regular cyclical salary increase regime of these corporations often has specific, clear, transparent, and also provide employees with extremely attractive bonuses when they do

a good job. Then, in addition to stressful working hours, these corporations also create opportunities for their employees to have time to bond with each other by providing extremely good remuneration policies. According to Tran Thuy Lieu et al (2015), these corporations can completely provide their employees with a stable income, not only enough to cover living expenses but also provide good compensation and benefits book than many other places. The third hypothesis put forward is:

Hypothesis 3: “The level of income and preferential policies affect the intention to choose a job at global-scale auditing corporations of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing”.

- ***Family, friends and colleagues:*** This factor is introduced to test the influence of internal and external relationships on candidates. According to Tran Van Man and Tran Kim Dung (2006), the help of colleagues has an influence on the intention to choose a job of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing. Huynh Truong Huy and La Nguyen Thuy Dung (2011) further confirmed that family has a great influence on students' decision to choose a workplace. Starting from the family's expectations, with a clear career path, salary, bonus and treatment is always the desire of every employee, every parent must hope that their children will be happy. I have the opportunity to work in these places, followed by the work of friends, most of the young people today have a syndrome of fear of being left out (FOMO: Fear of Missing out). Finally, it is the help of colleagues, as mentioned in the above variable, when working with people who have a lot of experience or people with deep expertise, new students will come out of school. All schools feel that they can develop most strongly when they are one of the employees in global corporations (Tran Thuy Lieu et al., 2015). The fourth hypothesis put forward is:

Hypothesis 4: “Family, friends and colleagues affect the intention to choose a job at global-scale auditing corporations of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing”

- ***Elements of professional skills:*** According to research by Kerckhofs, L., et al (2021), global corporations are always the leaders in having policies to support employees when participating in studying for international professional certificates, next, superiors always create conditions for employees to develop their full potential, that is, these units always create the most favorable conditions for employees. Employees can contact all the job cases from easy to difficult to create a premise for experience for future jobs. Moreover, the training sessions, or the cooperation with difficult partners are all opportunities for employees of these corporations to improve their personal expertise, or internal seminars to help employees can update the latest news, standards or regulations of the industry they have been working in. Ultimately, it is these corporations that will give their employees rare opportunities to practice their management skills right after the second year. These are quite unexpected findings that the research team received after the study review. The fifth hypothesis put forward is:

Hypothesis 5: “Factors of professional skills affect the intention to choose a job at global-scale auditing corporations of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing”.

From the hypotheses presented above, the research model proposes the factors affecting the intention to choose a job at the global-scale auditing corporations of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing described as in the model below:

Figure 3: Proposed research model

(Source: Author group synthesis and proposal)

4. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION OF THE STUDY

Based on the theoretical model of rational action (TRA) and the theoretical model of planned behavior (TPB) along with the inheritance of previous research results, the research team has proposed a research model including: includes 5 independent variables including (1) Brand and organizational reputation; (2) Income level and preferential policies; (3) Working environment and development opportunities; (4) Family and friends, colleagues; and (5) Factors of professional skills, which can influence the intention to choose a job at global-scale auditing corporations of students majoring in Accounting - Auditing (Figure 3).

The main purpose of this paper is to propose a theoretical model for future empirical studies on the factors affecting students' intention to choose a job at global audit corporations. audit accounting majors. In the coming time, experimental studies will be carried out to test the hypotheses, determine the influence level of each factor according to the research model proposed above; Experimental research results will be the basis for making recommendations, helping students to come up with a learning path and learn soft skills to achieve their future job goals., the proposed model of this study also contributes to helping employers understand the problems that students majoring in Accounting - Auditing still worry about when faced with decisive choices. part of the future. Therefore, employers can listen and summarize through the research paper, thereby completing the recruitment process. In addition to students and employers, the school can also draw conclusions from this research into a small part of important comments to help the school advise on a reasonable route for students majoring in Accounting - Auditing in general and final year students in particular, suitable working units and application methods.

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FACTORS AFFECTING CORPORATE CAPITAL STRUCTURE: A COMPARISON BETWEEN CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISES AND REAL ESTATE ENTERPRISES LISTED ON VIETNAM STOCK MARKET

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Abstract

This article aims to the similarities and differences of factors influencing the capital structure of construction enterprises and real estate enterprises listed on Vietnam stock market. The data used in the study are from the financial statements of 124 construction firms and 52 real estate firms listed on the Vietnam stock market from 2010 to 2020 provided by Fiiipro. The results of the study are: firm size has a positive impact on the capital structure of both construction enterprises and real estate enterprises and real estate industry; Liquidity has a negative impact on capital structure of both industries. Meanwhile, the impact of factors: asset structure, growth rate, profitability, corporate income tax on capital structure is different between the two industries, specifically: asset structure , growth rate, profitability have a positive impact on the capital structure of enterprises in the construction industry but negatively affect the capital structure of real estate enterprises; The corporate income tax factor has a negative impact on the corporate capital structure of the construction industry, but has a positive impact on the corporate capital structure of the real estate industry. The results of the study will help financial managers of construction & real estate enterprises to have good solutions for their capital structure.

Keywords: *capital structure, construction enterprises, real estate enterprises, Vietnam stock market*

1. INTRODUCTION

Capital structure is related to corporate financing decisions. Firms can finance their operations using debts, equity or a combination of these two sources (Ross et al., 2001; Abor, 2005; Brealey et al., 2009). Determining optimal capital structure is an important issue for all businesses because corporate capital structure is closely related to business performance and financial risks that businesses face. Capital structure decision is an important policy of enterprises to deal with activities related to debts and equity. However, financial statements are not helpful enough for corporate managers to make optimal capital decisions (Drobotz & Fix, 2003), which will depend on the study of the relationship between capital structure and corporate value and factors affecting capital structure.

Vietnam is in the process of economic transformation and development. The expansion of financial market is incomplete and has many limitations. Therefore, determining the capital structure of listed companies in Vietnam becomes more complicated. A reasonable capital structure will contribute to creating corporate value, thereby increasing asset value for owners and vice versa.

Capital structure of construction and real estate enterprises often has a high debt ratio, a common situation in many countries around the world (Mohammad et al., 2019). In Vietnam, the capital structure of construction enterprises has a higher debt ratio, averaging 70%-80% of the total capital, even some enterprises have a debt ratio of over 90%. While enterprises are operating inefficiently, the capital structure that leans too much on such debts puts more pressure on enterprises, both creating more difficulties for enterprises and containing potential risks. Using too much debt financing can increase financial exhaustion and reduce the firm's ability of to borrow (Addae et al., 2013). Therefore, in order to develop stably and sustainably, construction enterprises need to set up a reasonable capital structure to promote the efficiency of capital structure, helping businesses maximize corporate value, this is called the optimal capital structure (Nirajini & Priya, 2013). Companies operating in the same industry have an equal level of operational risk and, therefore, have similar optimal capital structures (Morri & Cristanziani, 2009). Panda and Nanda (2020) also concluded that at the industry level, each manufacturing sector has its own determinants of capital structure. However, there are still certain differences in capital structure among small industries of large industries, such as construction enterprises & real estate enterprises. These two industries are closely related to each other, people often put these two industries into a large group of industries, but in fact the factors affecting the capital structure of these two industries are not the same. Meanwhile, the construction and real estate industry in general and in Vietnam in particular plays an extremely important role in the national economy, is a complex field, closely related to many other industries. Therefore, if businesses in this industry encounter financial risks, it will bring many difficulties to the economy. Financial risk is associated with a business's financial activities and level of debt use, meaning it is tied to the capital structure of the business. Therefore, from a financial perspective, the article will fill the gap in knowledge about capital structure of construction companies and real estate companies listed on Vietnam stock market by conducting experimental analysis to test, evaluate and compare the influence of factors on capital structure of construction and real estate enterprises listed on Vietnam stock market with the aim of providing more basis for financial decisions to achieve the optimal capital structure of these enterprises.

The other parts of this article are structured as follows: Part 2 provides a literature review of related studies, and then Part 3 describes the research methodology. Part 4 presents the research results and the author's discussion and analysis. Finally, conclusions and recommendations of the study are provided in Part 5.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Capital structure theories include:

- Modigliani-Miller theorem (M&M): The modern capital structure theory of Modigliani and Miller was published in 1958, explaining the relationship between enterprise value, cost of

capital and the level of debt use of enterprises. The theory includes two propositions:

First proposition: The value of a business using debt is equal to the value of the business without using debt plus the present value of the tax shield from interest.

Second proposition: The cost of equity capital is proportional to the debt ratio.

- The Trade Off Theory: The Trade Off Theory suggests that using debt financing has the advantage of enjoying the benefit of a tax shield. The Trade Off Theory of capital structure has been further developed and overcomes the limitations of the M&M theory on capital structure by adding the assumption of financial distress costs.

The Trade Off Theory acknowledges the existence of an optimal capital structure and that businesses always aim for a target debt ratio. This debt ratio depends on two factors: taxes and expected bankruptcy costs.

- The Pecking Order Theory: The market Pecking Order Theory originally researched by Myers and Majluf (1984) predicts no clear target debt-to-equity structure. The Pecking Order Theory provides a priority order for using capital sources of businesses, first they use internal sources of loan capital, then external debt and finally equity capital. This theory emphasizes that businesses prefer to use debt capital rather than increase equity capital when internal debt capital does not meet their capital needs.

- The Market Timing Theory: Different from previous capital structure theories, The Market Timing Theory considers capital structure under imperfect market conditions. The Market Timing Theory helps business managers determine the right market time to make decisions on issuing or repurchasing shares. The theory also studies the correlation between market timing and a business's capital structure and how long the impact lasts. According to Baker and Wurgler (2002), businesses will issue securities when the market price of shares is high and buy back shares at low prices, the purpose of this is to exploit temporary fluctuations in stock prices. The cost of using equity capital in relation to the cost of using capital from other capital sources.

Based on the theories of capital structure, many empirical studies in countries around the world have been carried out to find out the important factors affecting the capital structure of enterprises. At the industry level, the study concludes that each manufacturing sector has its own determinants of capital structure. Deesomsak et al. (2004) studied the factors affecting capital structure in the Asia Pacific region. Research shows that firm size has a positive effect on debt ratio. Meanwhile, growth and liquidity have a negative impact on the capital structure of the business. Research by Huang & Song (2006) with a sample of more than 1,000 listed companies on the stock market, has shown that firm size, tax shield and fixed assets have a positive impact on debt ratio. The study by Kurniawati et al. (2020) surveyed listed companies in Indonesia from 2008-2015 using ordinary least squares (OLS). The study concluded that companies audited by one of the Big4 companies display a lower debt ratio. The study by Chang et al. (2009) surveyed firms listed in Compustat Industrial's annual filings from 1985-2005. Research results show that there is a difference between asymmetric information between enterprises audited by leading companies and those not audited by leading companies.

Specifically, those businesses that are audited by a leading company are likely to issue equity instead of debt in their capital structure. Then, these companies tend to issue a larger amount of equity when the market conditions are favorable. In addition, debt ratios of firms audited by leading companies are less affected by market conditions.

Summarizing the research results, it can be seen that the main factors affecting the capital structure of enterprises include: asset structure, business size, growth ability, profitability, corporate income tax and solvency (Research by Ross (1977), Wald (1999), Titman & Wessels (1988)).

The impact of some important factors on the capital structure of enterprises can be summarized by the author from related studies as follows.

Asset structure: Asset structure is determined by the ratio of fixed assets to total assets (tangibility). There are two contradictory views on the relationship between asset structure and firm's capital structure. The first point of view is that firms with large tangible assets can access loans more easily than firms with high intangible assets without collateral because of their own assets. Figure can be mortgaged to secure the loan. Studies supporting this view include Chen (2004), Akhtar (2005), Huang & Song (2006), Shah & Khan (2007), Teker et al. (2009), Liu et al. (2009), Frank & Goyal (2009), Shubiri (2010), Khan et al. (2020). The second viewpoint exists that an inverse relationship exists between asset structure and capital structure. Because they think that bond markets in small and developing countries make businesses depend on loans from banks. Moreover, banks often prefer short-term loans over long-term loans with many risks, which causes businesses to mobilize long-term loans instead of shortterm loans. This view is supported by Akinlo (2011), Sheikh & Wang (2011).

Firm size: Firm size is considered an important factor affecting the capital structure of the enterprise in many studies: Rajan & Zingales (1995); Hall et al. (2004); Bevan & Danbolt (2004). Previous studies have shown that large firms often have a large proportion of debt in capital structure. Studies supporting this view include: Baral (2004), Akhtar (2005), Eriotis et al. (2007), Liu et al. (2009), Psillaki & Daskalakis (2009); Frank & Goyal (2009), Gurcharan (2010).

Growth: There are two views on the relationship between growth rate and capital structure in the firm. The first is that firms with strong growth opportunities in the future are expected to raise more equity capital, suggesting an inverse relationship between growth likelihood and capital structure. This view is supported by Eriotis et al. (2007), Liu et al. (2009), Gurcharan (2010), Akinlo (2011). The second view believes that this relationship is positive. Relying on the rationale that a high growth rate implies a large demand for capital, a greater reliance on external capital through debt, backed by Baral (2004), Shubiri (2010).

Profitability: Some studies have shown that an inverse relationship exists between profitability and capital structure. They argue that a profitable enterprise tends to mobilize internal rather than external resources, and firms often reduce debt. This negative relationship can be found in the study of Baral (2004), Chen (2004), Akhtar (2005), Huang & Song (2006), Gurcharan (2010), Shubiri (2010), Sheikh & Wang (2011), Akinlo (2011), Sharif et al. (2012). Research by Nasution et al. (2017) also show that profitability has a significant & negative

effect on the capital structure of manufacturing firms listed on the stock market, which supports the pecking order theory.

Corporate income tax: Corporate income tax is an important factor that affects the capital structure of a firm (Modigliani & Miller, 1958). Profits from loans increase the effective tax rate (Antoniou et al., 2008). Some previous studies conducted by Mason (1990) have shown a positive relationship between income tax and capital structure of firms. However, many studies have shown the opposite results such as those studied by Kasznik (1999); Deesomsak et al. (2004), Gao (2016).

Liquidity: Many studies often suggest that an inverse relationship exists between liquidity and capital structure because the more short-term assets an enterprise uses, the more internal cash flows it can generate to finance businesses and investments. Businesses with high solvency tend to use less debt. Myers & Rajan (1998) also showed that firms with high liquidity usually borrow less. Experimental results in the study of Cassar & Holmes (2003) show that this factor has the strongest impact on the factors and has the opposite effect on the capital structure of the enterprise. This view is supported by Eriotis et al. (2007), Lipson & Mortal (2009), Liu et al. (2009), Sharif et al. (2012).

In Vietnam, there have been many studies on capital structure, but there has not been any research to compare the factors affecting capital structure of construction companies and real estate companies listed on Vietnam stock market. Therefore, the article aims to assist construction and real estate enterprises in general and construction enterprises and real estate enterprises listed on Vietnam stock market in particular to have foundation to plan target capital structure.

Based on previous studies, the author suggests the following research hypotheses:

Hypothesis H1: Asset structure (tangibility) of construction and real estate listed firms is positively correlated with capital structure.

Hypothesis H2: Firm size of listed construction and real estate companies is positively correlated with capital structure.

Hypothesis H3: Growth of listed enterprises in construction and real estate is positively correlated with capital structure.

Hypothesis H4: Profitability of listed construction and real estate companies is negatively correlated with capital structure.

Hypothesis H5: The liquidity of listed enterprises in construction and real estate is negatively correlated with capital structure.

Hypothesis H6: Corporate income tax of listed enterprises in construction and real estate is positively correlated with capital structure.

3. RESEARCH DATA AND METHODS

The studies on the factors affecting capital structure have been carried out according to the traditional frequency method. While the parameters of the population are considered

constants from the point of view of frequency statistics, in Bayesian statistics, the parameters are modeled as random variables to accurately describe the variability of the population when data is updated over time or across different spatial fields. Therefore, it is necessary to consider model parameters of random variables through Bayesian statistics. Scientific conclusions in frequency statistics are all based on data sets without regard to available information (Nguyen Ngoc Thach, 2019).

The authors use the Bayesian regression method with the algorithm taking the Gibbs sample to compare the factors affecting the capital structure of listed construction and real estate firms.

Based on the empirical evidence, the authors propose the following research model:

$$LTDR_{it} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 TANG_{it} + \beta_3 SIZE_{it} + \beta_4 GRO_{it} + \beta_5 ROA_{it} + \beta_6 TAX_{it} + \beta_7 LIQ_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

The variables in the model are in the following table:

Table 1. Description of the variables in the model

Variables	Symbol	Interpretation
Capital Structure	LTDR	The ratio of long-term liability to total assets
Tangibility	TANG	The ratio of fixed assets to total assets
Firm Size	SIZE	The natural logarithm of total assets (ln(total assets)) at year end
Growth	GRO	Revenue growth rate
Profitability	ROA	Return on assets
Corporate Income Tax	TAX	Paid corporate income tax/total assets
Liquidity	LIQ	The ratio of current assets to current liabilities at year-end.

The data used in the study are from the financial statements of construction and real estate firms listed on the Vietnam stock market from 2010 to 2020 provided by Fiinpro.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive statistics

The variables in the model are statistically described in the following table:

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of variables of construction firms

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
LTDR	1364	0.105	0.211	0	0.726
TANG	1364	0.183	0.186	0	0.899
SIZE	1364	27.10	1.451	22.78	31.09
GRO	1364	1.617	23.25	-24.16	615.66
ROA	1364	1.204	11.39	-4.023	238.26
TAX	1364	0.095	0.530	0	8.120
LIQ	1364	0.668	0.231	0.025	1

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of variables of real estate firms

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
LTDR	572	0.179	0.165	0	0.799
TANG	572	0.066	0.101	0	0.676
SIZE	572	28.20	1.390	25.51	33.68
GRO	572	1.204	17.41	-1	396.89
ROA	572	0.098	0.737	-2.697	9.683
TAX	572	0.026	0.144	0	2.431
LIQ	572	0.612	0.241	0.0369	0.996

Tables 2 and Table 3 present descriptive statistics, including mean, median, and standard deviation and minimum and maximum values of the variables included in the model. The descriptive statistical analysis results in Tables 2 and 3 show differences in capital structure and factors affecting the capital structure of construction and real estate firms listed on the Vietnam stock market. The average value of the LTDR indicator shows that listed construction and real estate firms have relatively small long-term debt use. The fluctuation of LTDR of construction firms ranges from 0 to 0.726, and for real estate firms ranges from 0 to 0.726. 0 to 0.799, the average level of the variable LTDR in real estate enterprises is higher than in construction enterprises. The variable TANG shows firms without fixed assets, besides those with a high proportion of peak fixed assets, with the most significant value of 0.899 for construction firms and 0.676 for real estate firms, investment level. Fixed assets of listed construction firms are low, with an average value of 0.183, and real estate firms have much lower asset investment, with an average value of 0.066. That is consistent with the characteristics of production and business in construction and real estate firms. The SIZE variable shows a big difference in the business size of listed construction and listed real estate firms. GRO's revenue growth rate indicates a considerable difference between construction and listed real estate firms; besides construction and real estate firms with high breakthrough revenue growth, businesses still decreased in revenue from 2010-2020. The indicator reflecting the profitability efficiency of the company ROA has a negative minimum value, showing that at least one company in a year has a negative after-tax profit. It shows that between 2010 and 2020, the profit after tax was negative. The business results of listed construction and real estate firms differ. Taxes and solvency vary between listed construction and real estate firms.

4.2. Regression results

Table 4. Regression results

	Mean	Std. Dev.	MCSE	Median	Equal-tailed [95% Cred. Interval]	
Construction firms						
TANG	0.0293	0.0258	0.0017	0.0289	-0.0200	0.0826
SIZE	0.0365	0.0026	0.0003	0.03654	0.0312	0.0414
GRO	0.0001	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0002	0.0004
ROA	0.0004	0.0004	0.0000	0.0004	-0.0002	0.0011

	Mean	Std. Dev.	MCSE	Median	Equal-tailed [95% Cred. Interval]	
TAX	-0.0150	0.0072	0.0004	-0.0151	-0.0289	-0.0004
LIQ	-0.2758	0.0217	0.0017	-0.2759	-0.3179	-0.2329
Real estate firms						
TANG	-0.0099	0.0764	0.0039	-0.0086	-0.1573	0.1372
SIZE	0.0139	0.0040	0.0009	0.0136	0.0070	0.0225
GRO	-0.0003	0.0004	0.0000	-0.0003	-0.0010	0.0005
ROA	-0.0491	0.0259	0.0016	-0.0482	-0.1021	-0.0007
TAX	0.1023	0.1302	0.0082	0.1014	-0.1401	0.3730
LIQ	-0.1211	0.0333	0.0016	-0.1212	-0.1868	-0.0581

Table 4 shows the model regression by the Bayesian method, and the research results show that:

The proportion of fixed asset investment (TANG) positively impacts the capital structure of listed construction firms. It shows that firms with a high rate of fixed asset investment tend to use more long-term debt; the impact level is 0.0293. This result is consistent with Chen (2004), Akhtar (2005), Huang & Song (2006), Shah and Khan (2007), Teker et al. (2009), Liu et al. (2009), Frank & Goyal (2009), Shubiri (2010), Khan et al. (2020). For real estate firms, the proportion of fixed assets investment has a negative impact on capital structure, but the effect is not significant. This result is consistent with Banchuenvijit (2009), Akinlo (2011), Sheikh & Wang (2011).

Firm size (SIZE) positively impacts the capital structure of listed construction and real estate firms. However, the magnitude of the effect is more significant than that of real estate firms, with regression coefficients of 0.0365 and 0.0139, respectively. Large-scale firms in Vietnam often have prestige from their brands and large production and business scale, so they often mobilize a lot of external capital to develop production and business. This result is consistent with Baral (2004), Akhtar (2005), Eriotis (2007), Liu et al. (2009), Psillaki & Daskalakis (2009); Frank & Goyal (2009), Gurcharan (2010).

Revenue growth rate (GRO) positively impacts construction firms' capital structure. It shows that businesses with a high revenue growth rate tend to use more long-term debt. For real estate companies, the relationship with GRO is inverse. When the revenue growth rate is low, listed real estate firms tend to use more long-term debt. However, the impact of revenue growth on capital structure of listed construction and real estate firms is almost negligible.

Profitability (ROA) has a negative impact on capital structure for listed real estate firms. This result is consistent with Baral (2004), Chen (2004), Akhtar (2005), Huang & Song (2006), Gurcharan (2010), Shubiri (2010), Mutallib (2010); Sheikh & Wang (2011), Akinlo et al. (2011), Sharif et al. (2012), Nasution et al. (2017). Increased profitability means that the company uses assets more efficiently and optimally available resources, and retained earnings increase to help other companies have better growth potential, making listed companies tend to use less long-term debt. However, for construction firms, ROA has a positive relationship with capital structure, but the impact is insignificant.

Tax (TAX) negatively impacts construction firms' capital structure with a regression coefficient 0.0150. This result is consistent with Kasznik (1999), Deesomsak et al (2004), Gao (2016). Tax positively impacts real estate firms' capital structure with a regression coefficient 0.1023. According to the capital structure theory of Modigliani & Miller (1963), firms subject to higher marginal tax rates will tend to use debt more to benefit from tax shields; there is a positive relationship between corporate income tax and capital structure. This result is consistent with Mason (1990), Bartholdy & Mateus (2008), Loney (2015).

Liquidity (LIQ) has a negative impact on capital structure for listed construction and real estate firms. Still, the solvency effect on the capital structure of construction enterprises is more significant than that of real estate enterprises, with regression coefficients of 0.2758 and 0.1211, respectively. Firms with good solvency have less difficulty in paying short-term debts. It shows that firms with good solvency tend to use debt at a low level. This result is consistent with Myers & Rajan (1998), Cassar & Holmes (2003), Eriotis (2007), Lipson & Mortal (2009), Liu et al. (2009), Sharif et al. (2012).

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study aims to test the hypothesis about the factors affecting the capital structure of construction and real estate companies listed on the Vietnam stock market, pointing out similarities and differences in the impact factors on the capital structure of these enterprises. The results of the study are: firm size has a positive impact on the capital structure of both construction enterprises and real estate enterprises and real estate industry; Liquidity has a negative impact on capital structure of both industries. Meanwhile, the impact of factors: asset structure, growth rate, profitability, corporate income tax on capital structure is different between the two industries, specifically: asset structure, growth rate, profitability have a positive impact on the capital structure of enterprises in the construction industry but negatively affect the capital structure of real estate enterprises; The corporate income tax factor has a negative impact on the corporate capital structure of the construction industry, but has a positive impact on the corporate capital structure of the real estate industry. The results of the study will help financial managers of construction & real estate enterprises to have good solutions for their capital structure.

From the mentioned discussion, it is possible to make some recommendations to help construction enterprises improve the capital structure as follows:

- On the basis of the estimation model, enterprises with large capital scale and growth opportunities should take advantage of the ability to access credit capital from banks, thereby making good use of financial leverage to improve operational efficiency of the business. In addition, enterprises with high business efficiency need to bring into play endogenous capital well to reduce debt mobilization coefficient in order to restructure capital sources of enterprises.

- Construction and real estate enterprises need to increase profitability. If an enterprise has the possibility that the average loan interest rate is greater than the profitability before interest and tax, then the enterprise will not take advantage of financial leverage. Manufacturing enterprises need to improve business efficiency (ROA) so that they can use retained earnings to invest in production because this is a lower cost capital compared to debt

and the issue of shares. Enterprises should also consider the dividend payout ratio to ensure harmony between the interests of shareholders as well as efficiency in capital utilization. In addition, along with improving business efficiency, enterprises will be more appreciated by creditors as well as more trusted by investors in the financial markets, which helps enterprises to raise capital from creditors, investors in the market at a lower cost.

- Enterprises need to focus on financial risk management, especially when the debt to equity ratio of construction and real estate enterprises is very high currently, the management of financial risk is essential. If the enterprise fails to achieve the expected profits, the interest expense and principal will become a burden for the enterprise.

- Improving solvency. To prevent insolvency due to excessive debt on equity, businesses need to regularly analyze their financial situation to identify insolvency risks, plan detailed cash flow. In the short term, it is possible to increase the ability to generate cash to ensure solvency.

- The results from the analysis of the model also indicate that construction enterprises need to recognize the importance of building target capital structures. Enterprises need to base on their plans and development orientations as well as their ability to raise capital to build target capital structures. In addition, businesses also need to regularly monitor the capital structure of the business and promptly adjust the capital structure when there are unusual changes in the macroeconomic situation and the development strategy of the business.

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THE IMPACT OF INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL ON CREDIT RISK: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM VIETNAM

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Abstract

This paper investigates the impact of intellectual capital on the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks by using the fixed effects model and the Method of Moments Quantile Regression model, combined with the annual panel dataset of 26 Vietnamese commercial banks from 2012 to 2021. Research results show that investing in intellectual capital helps Vietnamese commercial banks reduce credit risk. In particular, investment in human capital and structural capital will help Vietnamese commercial banks minimize credit risks most effectively. Besides, for the banks with a high NPL ratio and high credit risk, the more invested in intellectual capital, the more effective to reduce credit risk. On that basis, this paper proposes some recommendations for Vietnamese commercial banks as well as law enforcement agencies.

Keywords: *Intellectual capital, credit risk, Vietnam, commercial bank*

1. INTRODUCTION

Vietnam is in the process of opening up and integrating to align with the surrounding region and global development. Therefore, there is a growing inclination toward transitioning Vietnam's economy into a knowledge economy. Integration also brings many opportunities and challenges across various sectors of the economy. In order to thrive in the current highly competitive landscape, businesses must not solely depend on financial capital and a skilled workforce but also possess the capacity to utilize knowledge within the organizational framework effectively. The field of banking and finance is characterized by its knowledge-intensive nature, its continuous growth in scale of operations, and the rapid pace of banking restructuring. It is necessary for banks to implement appropriate policies and business strategies as well as effectively utilize and exploit knowledge to strengthen their competitive advantage.

Furthermore, recent changes in global geopolitics have had a significant impact on the world economy, particularly in the financial and banking sectors. The recent collapses of major banks such as Silicon Valley Bank and Signature Bank raised concerns that the safety of the banking system in general and banks in particular is under threat. In the context of resource constraints, the optimization of capital sources plays a significant role for banks, as it serves to

enhance operational efficiency and mitigate risks. In which, intellectual capital has emerged as a prominent concern.

This article uses the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Method of Moments Quantile Regression (MMQR) along with annual data from 26 Vietnamese commercial banks from 2012 to 2021 to study how intellectual capital affects the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks. From there, some recommendations are proposed to increase the efficiency of intellectual capital use at Vietnamese commercial banks in reducing credit risks. In addition to the introductory section, the subsequent segments of the article are organized in the following manner. Part 2 presents intellectual capital and a research overview on the impact of intellectual capital on the credit risk of commercial banks. Section 3 highlights the methodology applied to the study. Section 4 summarizes the main findings and results of the study. Finally, the governance implications and conclusions are discussed in Section 5.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Intellectual capital definitions

In recent years, the concept of intellectual capital has attracted significant interest among business managers. However, there is no consensus on the concept of intellectual capital among studies. Certain researchers perceive intellectual capital as an important factor in the creation of competitive advantage. According to Edvinsson and Malone (1997), intellectual capital refers to the possession of knowledge, practical experiences, technological resources, customer connections, and professional expertise within an organization. These factors contribute to a company's gaining a competitive advantage in the market. In addition, intellectual capital is also considered one of the sources of competitive advantage (Jardon and Martos, 2012; Kamukama, 2013; Sokolovská et al., 2014), and it is emphasized that the proper management of resources will promote teamwork and knowledge development (Kamukama, 2013). In the same view, Chen (2007) believes that companies that allocate resources and efforts to green intellectual capital can respond to the trends of strict global environmental legislation and perceive environmental awareness widespread among consumers, which can ultimately create a competitive advantage. Lin (2013) also argues that intellectual capital is a resource that can be put to use in day-to-day operations and helps transform company resources into competitive advantages.

Meanwhile, some other studies define intellectual capital as an intangible asset. Brooking (1998) argues that intellectual capital is a term used to refer to the intangible assets that combine to enable a company to operate. According to Stewart (1999), intellectual capital is intellectual material-knowledge, information, intellectual property, and experience-that can also be used to create wealth. Similarly, Harrison and Sullivan (2000) argue that intellectual capital is knowledge that can be transformed into profits. According to Roos (2005), intellectual capital can be defined as all non-cash and non-physical resources controlled partly or completely by an organization and contributing to the value creation process.

In conclusion, intellectual capital refers to the intangible assets possessed by a business. These assets include not only intellectual property, such as patents, trademarks, and trade secrets, but also knowledge, experience, relationships, work processes, market feedback, and customer reviews. Consequently, it plays a significant role in enhancing the operational effectiveness of the company.

2.2. Intellectual capital measurements

Since 1990, when intangible assets (including intellectual capital) received special attention from business managers, many models and methods have been developed to measure intellectual capital. The Value-Added Intellectual Coefficient (VAIC) model, which Pulic introduced in 2000, is one of the most well-known models in this field.

This model measures the effectiveness of the use of intellectual capital rather than absolute value and relates the contribution of intellectual capital to the value creation process. According to Pulic (2000), the increased intelligence coefficient is composed of capital employed efficiency and intellectual capital efficiency. Intellectual capital efficiency consists of two factors: human capital efficiency and structural capital efficiency. The VAIC model is illustrated briefly in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Value Added Intellectual Coefficient model (VAIC)

Source: Pulic (2000)

The VAIC model indicates that the larger the VAIC index, the more efficient the use of resources and the more value added (VA). With this model, Pulic (2000) provides a tool to measure the efficiency of using intellectual capital using published accounting data from enterprises. Therefore, this model easily measures the intellectual capital of enterprises based on the published basic accounting information, specifically as follows:

Value Added- VA

In the VAIC model, Pulic (2000) uses VAT as an indicator for value creation from the company's main resources. VAT is calculated by taking the difference between the output revenue (output) and the input cost (input). Output revenue is the revenue generated from the sale of products and services in the market, while input costs are all costs incurred to generate revenue, including labor costs. An important point that distinguishes the VAIC model (Pulic, 2000) from other models is that, from Pulic's point of view, wages are considered an

investment, not an expense. In addition, depreciation expenses will be added to VAT as they are not real costs. The formula for calculating VAT is as follows:

$$\mathbf{VA = OP + HC + D}$$

Where:

OP: net profit

HC: cost to employees, measured by gross salary

D: depreciation expense

Capital employed efficiency (CEE)

According to Pulic (2000), capital employed refers to the tangible assets that the company uses to create value, including physical assets and financial assets. Working capital is calculated by subtracting intangible assets from the total assets. Then, dividing VAT by the capital employed, we get capital efficiency (CEE), where CE is equity.

$$\mathbf{CEE = VA/CE}$$

Human Capital Efficiency (HCE)

Pulic (2000) emphasizes the role of knowledge workers and believes that employee costs are an investment that creates long-term business value and growth. Human resources are an important factor in the success of businesses because, in the era of the knowledge economy, much of the value is created by the skills and competencies of employees, especially their specialized skills and characteristics. Pulic (2000) does not provide indicators of human performance but instead focuses on how companies care and how much they invest in their human resources. The efficiency of human capital is calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{HCE = VA /HC}$$

Where: HC is the cost for employees

Structural Capital efficiency (SCE)

According to Pulic (2000), structural capital is calculated by the difference of VAT and staff costs. Structural capital represents the intangible resources in the organization other than human resources. It includes all the factors and conditions that help an organization function and support employees' work activities, such as corporate culture, work practices and processes, and intellectual property. Corporate culture enables employees to work together towards a common goal. Practices and workflows reflect the process of knowledge sharing within the company. Intellectual property includes legally protected intangible assets such as patents, copyrights, trademarks, designs, trade secrets, and data. Pulic (2000) argues that human capital is inversely proportional to structural capital in the process of creating value based on intellectual capital, so if structural capital decreases, human capital increases.

$$\mathbf{SCE = SC/VA}$$

Where: $SC = VA - HC$

$$\mathbf{VAIC = CEE + HCE + SCE}$$

2.3. Impact of intellectual capital on credit risk

Nowadays, despite the existence of many investigations concerning the influence of intellectual capital on credit risk, there is still no consensus among these studies.

Ghosh and Maji (2014) showed that HCE has a negative impact on the credit risk ratio. Furthermore, the researchers found that this relationship is more prominent in public-sector banks compared to the private sector. One of the recent difficulties for banks is the problem of human resources. Specifically, the limitations on the effective use of human resources make it difficult to limit credit risks. The skills and professionalism of officers and employees in checking the use of capital are still formal, perfunctory, and not routine, resulting in an inspection after the loan is not respected, and there are problems with using capital for the wrong purposes and difficulties in repaying bank loans. In addition, the debt recovery immediately following the occurrence of bad debt has not been taken seriously. Enterprises have not been really active in handling outstanding debts, using risk provisions to handle them, and then transferring them to the off-balance sheet monitoring of the balance sheet. Therefore, improving the quality and professionalism of human resources will help limit the risks faced by the bank. Research results also show that large banks often use intellectual capital in a controlled and effective manner in credit risk management, while small banks rely heavily on capital safety ratios. Similarly, Agomor et al (2022) suggested that intellectual capital and operational efficiency of commercial banks have a positive relationship, thereby reducing risks and increasing risk-taking rates of commercial banks. Specifically, VAIC, HCE, and SCE had a significant positive effect on performance, but in the long run, the relationship was inverted U-shaped. The study also shows that investing in tangible assets limits operational efficiency, while investing in intangible fixed assets helps improve business performance, thereby minimizing credit risk.

Zhang et al. (2021) concluded that intellectual capital has a positive and significant relationship with bank risk. This indicates that credit risk rises as intellectual capital increases and that the efficiency of utilizing human and structural capital has a positive correlation with credit risk. Investing in human capital can increase the operational stability of a bank over the long term.

3. DATA AND MODEL SPECIFICATIONS

3.1. Data

The study uses the annual data of 26 Vietnamese commercial banks in the period from 2012 to 2021, with 260 observations. The data set is collected from the S&P Capital IQ Pro database and the post-audit financial statements of Vietnamese commercial banks. As of November 30, 2021, the total assets of Vietnamese commercial banks are VND 13,023,214 billion, of which the total assets of 26 commercial banks in the research sample are VND 10,812,774 billion (accounting for 83% of the total assets of the banking system). Therefore, the study sample is suitable and highly representative. Besides, Stata 14 software is used to perform quantitative analysis of the relationship between intellectual capital and the financial performance of Vietnamese commercial banks.

3.2. Model specifications

To conduct a quantitative analysis of the relationship between intellectual capital and credit risk in Vietnamese commercial banks, the author proposes the following equation:

$$NPL_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 VAIC_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 LDR_{it} + \beta_4 COVID_{it} + u_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

In addition, the article also conducts further research on the relationship between components of intellectual capital and the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks through the equation:

$$NPL_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CEE_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 LDR_{it} + \beta_4 COVID_{it} + u_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$NPL_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 HCE_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 LDR_{it} + \beta_4 COVID_{it} + u_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

$$NPL_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SCE_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 LDR_{it} + \beta_4 COVID_{it} + u_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

The article also uses the Method of Moments Quantile Regression (MMQR) to assess in more detail the impact of intellectual capital on the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks:

$$QNPL_{i,t}(\tau|\alpha_i) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 VAIC_{i,t} + \alpha_2 CONTROL + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (5)$$

Where: Q is the τ percentile regression function with $\tau \in (0,1)$ according to the distribution of the dependent variable NPL, representing the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks.

Table 1. Variables measurements and expectation signs

Variable	Abbreviation and expectation sign	Measurement
<i>Dependent variable</i>		
Non-performing loans ratio	NPL	$NPL = \frac{\text{Non – Performing Loans}}{\text{Total Loans}}$
<i>Independent variables</i>		
Capital employed efficiency	CEE (-)	$CEE = \frac{\text{Value added}}{\text{Total equity}}$
Human Capital Efficiency	HCE (-)	$HCE = \frac{\text{Value added}}{\text{Labor costs}}$
Structural Capital efficiency	SCE (-)	$SCE = \frac{\text{Value added} - \text{Labor costs}}{\text{Value added}}$
Intellectual capital	VAIC (-)	$VAIC = CEE + HCE + SCE$
Bank size	SIZE (-)	$SIZE = \text{Ln (Total assets)}$

Variable	Abbreviation and expectation sign	Measurement
Loan to deposit ratio	LDR (+)	$LDR = \frac{Total\ loans}{Total\ deposits}$
COVID-19 pandemic	COVID (+)	Dummy variables: 0 = 2012-2019 1 = 2020-2021

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the research data set. Accordingly, the intellectual capital (VAIC) of Vietnamese commercial banks in the period 2012–2021 reached an average value of 3,027 with a standard deviation of 0.965. The non-performing loan ratio of Vietnamese commercial banks ranges from 0.005 to 0.088, with an average value of 0.021. The size of Vietnamese commercial banks is measured by the natural logarithm of total assets, with a value ranging from 23,410 to 28,197 with a standard deviation of 1,126 and an average value of 25,584, showing that there is a large difference between the size of commercial banks in Vietnam.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
NPL	260	0.021	0.012	0.005	0.088
VAIC	260	3.027	0.965	1.225	5.837
LDR	260	0.873	0.167	0.372	1.469
SIZE	260	25.585	1.126	23.410	28.197
COVID	260	0.200	0.401	0.000	1.000

Source: Authors' calculation

The correlation coefficient is a statistical indicator that measures the degree of a linear relationship between two variables. Based on the results of Table 3, the correlation coefficients of the independent variables are all lower than 80%, so the independent variables have low correlation coefficients and are consistent with the regression (Judge et al., 1985; Hair et al., 2006).

Table 3. The pairwise correlation matrix for variables

	VAIC	CEE	HCE	SCE	LDR	SIZE	COVID
VAIC	1.0000						
CEE	0.6516	1.0000					
HCE	0.9924	0.5673	1.0000				
SCE	0.9536	0.6104	0.9285	1.0000			
LDR	0.3445	0.4437	0.3056	0.3528	1.0000		
SIZE	0.4419	0.6637	0.3880	0.4080	0.2441	1.0000	
COVID	0.2633	0.2553	0.2590	0.2061	0.2615	0.2525	1.0000

Source: Authors' calculation

For the MMQR model, it is necessary to perform (1) the cross-section dependence test (CD-test); (2) the unit root test; and (3) the cointegration test. Table 4 presents the CD-test results. Accordingly, the p-values of the variables are all less than 5%, so there is a cross-dependence between banks in the data series. This result requires the data series to be stationary.

Table 4. CD-test results

Variables	CD-test	P-value
NPL	18.061	0.000
VAIC	11.654	0.000
SIZE	50.138	0.000
LDR	11.202	0.000
COVID	57.009	0.000

Source: Authors' calculation

Table 5 shows the unit root test results. The results show that some variables do not stop at the original series, but when taking the first difference, all variables are stationary at both 0 and 1 lags.

Table 5. Unit root tests results

Variable	No difference				First difference			
	Specification without trend		Specification with trend		Specification without trend		Specification with trend	
	Lag(0)	Lag(1)	Lag(0)	Lag(1)	Lag(0)	Lag(1)	Lag(0)	Lag(1)
NPL	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)
VAIC	0.000 (***)	0.316	0.000 (***)	0.112	0.000 (***)	0.001 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)
SIZE	0.680	0.999	0.000 (***)	0.002 (***)	0.001 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)
LDR	0.020 (**)	0.000 (***)	0.001 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)
COVID	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)	0.000 (***)

Source: Authors' calculation

After determining that the data series has been stopped, the research team conducts a cointegration test. Based on the findings presented in Table 6, it can be observed that a phenomenon of cointegration exists among the variables within the model. This implies that there is a long-term relationship between the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks and the independent variables.

Table 6. Cointegration test results

Cointegration test	Statistics	P-value	Cointegrated
Augmented Dickey-Fuller t	-6.2216***	0.0000	Yes
Phillips-Perron t	-6.7108***	0.0000	Yes
Modified Phillips-Perron t	5.8645***	0.0000	Yes

Source: Authors' calculation

4.2. Empirical results

Table 7. Empirical results

	NPL (1)	NPL (2)	NPL (3)	NPL (4)
VAIC	-0.000737**			
CEE		0.000414		
HCE			-0.0007***	
SCE				-0.01065***
SIZE	-0.011139***	-0.01124***	-0.0112***	-0.01136***
LDR	-0.002104	-0.00333	-0.00245	-0.00046
COVID	0.002966	0.002676	0.002917	0.003352
constant	0.309596	0.311009	0.310759	0.316933

The symbols *, **, and *** stand for significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% level, respectively

Source: Authors' calculation

Table 7 presents the research results of this paper. Based on the results of Table 7, some main research results are drawn as follows:

Firstly, intellectual capital (VAIC) has a negative impact on the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks and is statistically significant at 5% (Model 1). This result is similar to the study of Ghosh and Maji (2014). Accordingly, when banks focus more on improving the efficiency of intellectual capital, credit risks can be significantly reduced. This is due to the high quality of human resources used in risk management activities, the use of modern financial technologies in risk detection, prevention, and management, or the strengthening of relationships and coordination of risk management collaboration with partners (other financial institutions, fintech companies, etc.).

Second, in models (3) and (4), human capital efficiency (HCE) and structural capital efficiency (SCE) also have a negative impact on the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks and are statistically significant at 1%. It implies that when commercial banks invest more in human resources and structural capital, it can help them hedging risks more effectively, thereby enhancing operational efficiency and profitability. In contrast, in model (2), capital employed efficiency (CEE) has a positive relationship with credit risk but is not statistically significant.

Third, for control variables, bank size (SZIE) has a negative relationship with credit risk and is statistically significant at 1% in all four models. This implies that the larger the banks,

the more resources they have to control credit risk. Meanwhile, loan-to-deposit ratio (LDR) and COVID have no impact on the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks. This is the success of the government and the State Bank of Vietnam in their efforts to control credit risk through the application of measures to extend the repayment period, maintain the debt group, and support policies in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic that has caused many difficulties for the economy.

Table 8. Method of Moments Quantile Regression results

	Q10 th	Q20 th	Q30 th	Q40 th	Q50 th	Q60 th	Q70 th	Q80 th	Q90 th
VAIC	-0.002*	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002**	-0.003**	-0.003*
	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.002)
LDR	-0.003	-0.004	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005	-0.006	-0.006	-0.007	-0.008
	(0.004)	(0.003)	(0.003)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.005)	(0.005)	(0.006)	(0.008)
SIZE	-0.001	-0.001**	-0.001***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.003***	-0.003***	-0.003***
	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)
COVID	0.001	-0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.002	-0.002	-0.003	-0.003	-0.004
	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.003)
Constant	0.032**	0.051***	0.062***	0.073***	0.084***	0.094***	0.103***	0.112***	0.135***
	(0.016)	(0.013)	(0.012)	(0.013)	(0.015)	(0.017)	(0.020)	(0.023)	(0.033)
No. Obs	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

Source: Authors' calculation

To further study the impact of intellectual capital on the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks, the research team conducted quantile regression by using Method of Moments Quantile Regression (MMQR). The results from Table 8 show that in the 80th and 90th percentiles, the impact of VAIC on the credit risk of commercial banks is significantly higher. Specifically, at the 70th percentile, the regression coefficient of the VAIC variable is -0.002, while at the 80th and 90th percentiles of the NPL, this coefficient has increased to -0.003 (30% higher). This result implies that for banks with a high NPL ratio and high credit risk, the more invested in intellectual capital, the more effective the ability to reduce credit risk.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This article uses the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Method of Moments Quantile Regression (MMQR), as well as annual data from 26 Vietnamese commercial banks from 2012 to 2021, to look at how intellectual capital affects the credit risk of Vietnamese commercial banks. The results of a study indicate that investing in intellectual capital assists Vietnamese commercial banks in reducing credit risk. Specifically, investments in human capital and structural capital will help Vietnamese commercial banks minimize credit risk. Additionally, the greater the credit risk, the more effective the investment in intellectual capital will be in reducing bad debt. These results suggest the following policies:

Firstly, Vietnamese commercial banks need to focus on the development and training of high-quality human resources to meet the rising demand for risk management, particularly in the context of the banking industry's intensifying digital transformation. In fact, in Vietnam, the

human resources with information technology skills of banks are still very limited. Therefore, banks must find and cultivate technologically qualified human resources in order to construct systems for risk analysis, assessment, and measurement, effectively managing and limiting. Professional ethics must also be considered along with professional qualifications.

Secondly, Vietnamese commercial banks need to complete and develop information technology in the digital banking system; in particular, they need to strengthen cooperation between commercial banks and Fintech company partners, as well as other partners in the digital transformation, supply, and development of financial-related products. This not only ensures that the parties take advantage of technology, human resources, and capital, particularly in accordance with the intended use of customers, but it also facilitates cost savings and is conducive to the transformation and development of the digital banking system. In addition, commercial banks and fintech companies need to cooperate to improve product competitiveness by providing smart payment services with many new features and improving the customer experience by integrating service payment features such as electricity and water payments and air tickets.

Last but not least, the government and SBV need to establish the infrastructure and ecosystem required for the application of digital technology, the sharing of information and data, and the promotion of cooperation between banks and fintech companies. In addition, the government should implement policies that encourage the investment and development of research as well as the application of intellectual capital in the banking industry.

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LONG SHORT-TERM MEMORY ARCHITECTURES: TOWARDS A SUPERLATIVE TECH STOCK PRICE FORECASTING MODEL FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC PROSPERITY

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Abstract

In this research, we target stock price forecasting, a field that presents significant challenges due to the complex nature of stock valuations. Therefore, we propose the use of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architectures, supplemented with robust data processing algorithms, to reduce forecasting errors. By applying LSTM to the three US tech giants – IBM, Intel, and CISCO – it surpassed 23 other models from the Exponential Smoothing and Machine Learning groups, providing the lowest Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). This underlines the effectiveness of our model in predicting the adjusted closing prices for the selected tech stocks. This paper contributes to future forecasting principles, advocating Deep Learning as a key approach for statisticians and economists. This shift could improve their decision-making processes and help predict economic recovery in the post-pandemic world.

Summary: *This paper delves into the intricate dynamics of stock price forecasting, an area that poses substantial challenges in terms of accuracy for researchers and investors alike due to the innate complexity of stock valuations. We suggest the implementation of advanced Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architectures, complemented by Adam Optimization algorithms and early stopping, to diminish predictive inaccuracies. Upon employing the LSTM model in the three US tech stocks (IBM, INTC, and CSCO), it emerged as superior to 23 models from the Exponential Smoothing and Machine Learning realms, returning the lowest Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values. This demonstrates the effectiveness of our model in predicting the adjusted closing prices for the specified tech stocks over conventional frameworks. Therefore, this paper offers insights for renovating future forecasting principles, advocating for Deep Learning as a fundamental tool for statisticians and economists, and enhancing the decision-making abilities of researchers post-pandemic economic recovery.*

Keywords: *Adam Optimization. Deep Learning. Economic Recovery. LSTM Architectures. Stock Forecasting*

1. INTRODUCTION

Forecasting stock prices is challenging due to the intricate interplay of various influential factors, ranging from macro and micro determinants like governmental policy, relative strength index (RSI), Consumer Sentiment Index (CSI), Consumer Price Index (CPI), and inflation rates to investor behaviour and consumer psychology (Duy et al., 2020). Stock prices serve as an indicator of a company's financial health, stability, and performance, offering insights into earnings and dividend prospects. Furthermore, they gauge market sentiment, flagging potential market bullishness or bearishness driven by changes in regulations, economic conditions, or a nation's political state (Huy, 2020). Predicting forthcoming stock prices is as chaotic as discerning underlying social investment patterns or projecting business growth, marked by unpredictability (Li & Ma, 2007). The uncertainty is heightened in the post-COVID-19 era, with global businesses grappling with fluctuating investments. This unpredictability is exacerbated by events like post-Brexit implications for London's financial stature (Deng, 2022) and the Russo-Ukrainian conflict affecting global stock returns since 2021 (Boungou & Yatie, 2022).

The advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in economics and finance has revitalized security forecasting through the integration of Machine Learning (ML) frameworks, surpassing traditional statistical models like ARIMA, used initially for analyzing Swedish banks' stock returns (Vantuch & Zelinka, 2015), and others like the FF Factor Model, used for predicting price trends with notable errors (Ni & Chen, 2022). For instance, GARCH was applied by Endri et al. (2021) to assess the volatility of the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the COVID-19 pandemic, and variations of Exponential Smoothing (ETS) were used to predict the S&P 500 Index's closing price (Sun, 2020). However, these models often fall short due to their assumptions of independence and linearity, failing to apprehend the intricate, non-linear patterns in real-world sequential data (Na et al., 2021). In contrast, ML models like LightGBM, NNAT, and LSTM have proven superior, adeptly handling unstable and multivariate time series, while traditional models like ARIMA excel primarily with stable, univariate datasets (Lu et al., 2021).

Inspired by the successes of previous researchers in sequential time series data analysis, this paper proposes a more advanced LSTM model with enhanced preprocessing optimizer and technique, justifying its efficacy in stock price forecasting of International Business Machines, Intel, and Cisco Systems stock over the traditional approaches of statistical, ETS and ML models. This paper mainly contributes to the reinforcement of forecasting principles in finance as Deep Learning multivariate approach is believed to provide more precise forecasts, surpassing the approaches of statistical models and traditional ML models, thereby emphasizing the need to regulate DL as the core forecasting principle and contributing to policies trial.

This paper is constructed as follows: Section 2 informs readers about the construction of our proposed model and evaluation metrics after introducing previous works and architectures within the ML field. Section 3 showcases our model evaluation stage and the dominance of our model against traditional models. Section 4 lastly mentions possible applications for future improvement before concluding our work.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW, THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK, AND METHODS

2.1. Literature Review

Stock data, as a sequential time series, is a multifaceted landscape, that involves multiple influential factors that determine the values of stocks. Therefore, a comprehensive forecasting model must be able to perform multivariate analysis, as it needs to incorporate multiple variables' values to provide an accurate prediction for the target feature. Resultantly, traditional statistical models, which assume data point linearity, may fall short in capturing the complex interrelationships and patterns inherent in stock market data due to their limitation of learning only the target feature, neglecting other impactful market factors. This leads to the rise of Machine Learning in statistics, as it offers advanced algorithms that can adaptively learn from multivariate data patterns, capturing the intricate dynamics of stock markets.

Back Propagation Neural Network Model (BP-NN), in comparison to ARIMA and Random Forest Regression (RFR), illustrated the lowest RMSE and R-Square results when being used to forecast the 1-year stock price of Chinese vaccine manufacturers, benefiting pharmaceutical industry investors (Gui & Wu, 2022). Furthermore, Kumar et al. (2022) combined Seasonal ARIMA and Extreme Gradient Boosting (Boost), termed SARIMA-XGBoost, to predict the Indian Stock Index, which returned an Accuracy of 89.48% and a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 15.62. Likewise, Lavingia et al. (2022) assessed the growth of Indian economy through stock price prediction of NCS and BSE-listed firms using the RFR model, which returned relatively low MAE and RMSE, indicating its effectiveness. Therefore, ML models, in their conventional forms, have shown commendable liability in predicting stock prices. However, the integration of Deep Learning, as a subset of ML, strikes the scientific field due to its ability to automatically learn hierarchical representations from data, leading to more accurate models.

Accordingly, Wang et al. (2022) proposed the LightGBM model and wavelet packet decomposition (WPD) algorithm to reduce data noise before predicting the market trend of Shanghai Composite Index, which resulted in the combination accurately capturing the next 10-day trend, outdoing ARIMA and Support Vector Regression (SVR). LSTM and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures were found to perfectly capture the long-term stock volatility provided by Kaggle, whilst LightGBM worked better in the short term (Li, 2022). Furthermore, LSTM, after being tested on Indian Stock Market, yields a smaller MSE than CNN and ARIMA in contrast to others published research (Chaskar, 2020). Wang et al. (2021) stated that LSTM architectures outdo those of linear or polynomial regression. To leverage the field, hybrid models were introduced such as CNN-LSTM to extract high-dimensional features before synthesizing at the LSTM gate for prediction, which improved the forecasting accuracy by 36.4% (Jialin & Qiao, 2022) or CNN-Bidirectional LSTM-ECA for Chinese stock price prediction (Chen, 2021). Hence, regular LSTM has been depicted as a powerhouse.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

2.2.1. Long Short-Term Memory Architectures

Figure 1: LSTM unit structure diagram

Particularly, the core mechanism of our model is the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) framework, professionally designed to capture long-term temporal relationships within sequential stock price data (Figure 1). Each LSTM unit is comprised of a cell state and three regulatory mechanisms: the input gate, forget gate and output gate. The cell state serves as a conduit for pertinent market trends and patterns throughout the temporal steps. The role of the input gate is to manage the influx of novel market data into the cell state, while the forget gate determines which pieces of historical trade information to keep or discard. The output gate controls the ultimate information transmitted to the subsequent layer, sourced from the modified cell state (Houdt et al., 2020).

This configuration enables the LSTM units to effectively learn from chronologically ordered stock price data, positioning them as a formidable instrument for financial time series forecasting. In the proposed model, they significantly contribute to the prediction of future stock price movements, showcasing their proficiency in assimilating and learning from past trading data (Figure 2), thus, the unique accompaniment of Adam optimization is particularly believed to increase the precision of the model, which is equatorially interpreted in Section 2.3.

2.3. Research Methods

2.3.1. The Proposed Model and Algorithm

Figure 2: Proposed LSTM Structure Diagram

Given a sequence of stock data (x_t) and the previous hidden state (h_{t-1}), the LSTM layer performs the following computations:

- Forget Gate:** Determines the proportion of the previous cell state to retain, $f_t = \sigma(W_f[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f)$, where W_f and b_f are learned parameters.
- Input Gate:** Decides the degree of new candidate values to be added to the cell state, $i_t = \sigma(W_i[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i)$, and computes the new candidate values, $\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_c[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_c)$.
- Cell State Update:** Updates the cell state, $C_t = f_t * C_{t-1} + i_t * \tilde{C}_t$, by retaining certain old information and adding new information.
- Output Gate:** Decides the part of cell state to reveal as output, $o_t = \sigma(W_o[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o)$, and computes the current hidden state, $h_t = o_t * \tanh(C_t)$.

The proposed LSTM layer (Figure 2) is composed of 50 such units, each learning to recognize different temporal patterns in the input data. The outputs from all LSTM units are passed to the Dense layer, which computes the final output as a linear combination of its inputs. Moreover, it captures temporal dependencies in stock price data and makes predictions based on the learned temporal patterns. The model is trained to minimize the MAE and RMSE between the predicted and actual stock prices by utilizing the Adam optimization algorithms as follows:

$$m_t = \beta_1 m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) g_t$$

$$v_t = \beta_2 v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) g_t^2$$

$$\hat{m}_t = \frac{m_t}{1 - \beta_1^t}$$

$$\hat{v}_t = \frac{v_t}{1 - \beta_2^t}$$

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \alpha \frac{\hat{m}_t}{\sqrt{\hat{v}_t} + \epsilon}$$

Where

θ_t : the model's parameters at time step t

α : the learning rate

β_1 and β_2 : exponential decay rates for the moment estimates

ϵ : a small constant, added to prevent division by zero

2.3.2. Data Collection and Evaluation Metrics

Data Collection: OHLCV (Open, High, Low, Close, Volume) datasets for three US technology behemoths, which are International Business Machines Corporation (Ticker: IBM), Intel Inc. (Ticker: INTC), and Cisco Systems Inc. (Ticker: CSCO), were gathered from Yahoo Finance. These datasets, comprising daily observations over an extensive 20-year span from July 28, 2003, to July 28, 2023, encompass a total of 5036 data points for each entity. Data cleansing procedures were enacted to ensure an appropriate sample size commensurate with the requirements of Machine Learning methodologies and the absence of missing values. Rationally, the study focuses on IBM, Intel, and Cisco Systems, chosen for their stature as significant representatives of U.S. tech firms within the diverse landscape of the S&P 500 Index, which consists of the country's 500 largest publicly traded companies, partly reflecting the market's health.

The datasets subsequently underwent sophisticated scaling transformations and were evaluated using a set of comprehensive metrics (Section 3). Likewise, the adjusted closing price, or "Adj Close" serves as the target feature, whilst, other variables are the independent variables. Experiments were conducted and executed in Python (Jupyter Notebook) for ML-based models and R (R-Studio) for statistical and Exponential Smoothing models.

Evaluation Metrics: The selection of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) as evaluation metrics stems from their effectiveness in measuring prediction errors. The MAE, by quantifying the average deviation of the predicted values from the actual ones, offers a straightforward indicator of the model's forecasting accuracy, which is a vital requirement considering the unpredictability of stock market dynamics (1). Conversely, the RMSE, due to its emphasis on larger errors, becomes indispensable in this scenario as significant misestimations in stock price predictions can lead to substantial financial ramifications (2).

The employment of these metrics facilitates an exhaustive assessment of the predictive proficiency of the model within the high-risk realm of stock market forecasting. As such, a model with lower MAE and RMSE values is deemed to provide more reliable and accurate stock price predictions (Hodson, 2021).

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \tag{1}$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \tag{2}$$

Where

y_i : the actual value

$\hat{y}_i$: the predicted value

n : the total data point

2.3.3. Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of Data

ATTRIBUTE	25%	50%	75%	Kurtosis	NA	Skewness	Count	Freq	Max	Mean	Min	STD	Top	Unique
CSCO Adj Close	14,53	18,59	36,71				5035		60,60	24,62	9,45	13,12		
CSCO Close	20,75	25,88	41,66				5035		63,96	30,25	13,62	12,18		
CSCO Date							5035	1					2003-07-28	5035
CSCO High	20,95	26,14	42,17				5035		64,29	30,55	14,12	12,27		
CSCO Low	20,52	25,64	41,15				5035		63,55	29,95	13,30	12,08		
CSCO Open	20,71	25,88	41,68				5035		64,04	30,24	13,93	12,18		
CSCO Value				10,45	0	1,51								
CSCO Volume	20919250	34047900	50695350				5035		560040200	39257317	922900	26486439		
IBM Adj Close	63,42	104,07	117,56				5035		146,74	93,09	40,10	29,22		
IBM Close	103,41	129,99	152,50				5035		206,31	129,92	68,59	33,50		
IBM Date							5035	1					2003-07-28	5035
IBM High	104,82	130,96	153,62				5035		206,41	130,93	70,45	33,61		
IBM Low	102,17	129,11	151,53				5035		204,88	128,88	66,44	33,38		
IBM Open	103,34	130,02	152,61				5035		205,91	129,86	69,34	33,50		
IBM Value				1,56	0	0,48								
IBM Volume	3779826	4966900	6764692				5035		39814421	5790507	1074765	3221875		
INTC Adj Close	14,35	18,95	32,91				5035		63,35	25,26	7,80	13,61		
INTC Close	22,00	27,20	37,07				5035		68,47	31,77	12,08	12,57		
INTC Date							5035	1					2003-07-28	5035
INTC High	22,24	27,52	37,30				5035		69,29	32,12	12,63	12,71		
INTC Low	21,75	26,91	36,76				5035		67,31	31,41	12,05	12,42		
INTC Open	22,00	27,24	37,01				5035		68,20	31,76	12,17	12,57		
INTC Value				1,00	0	1,05								
INTC Volume	25880200	40205100	59348500				5035		309347600	45645533	5893800	26242802		

The stock datasets for CSCO, INTC, and IBM were scrutinized to discern stock behaviors and trends (Table 1). CSCO exhibited an average Adjusted Close Price of \$24.62, reflecting moderate stock value, with a skewness of 1.51, revealing a pronounced rightward tail, indicative of frequent higher values. IBM, with a higher mean Adjusted Close Price of \$93.09, depicted lower skewness at 0.48, signaling a more symmetrical distribution and thereby fewer extreme values. INTC’s dataset underscored substantial trading activities, evidencing an average trading volume of approximately 46 thousand shares, coupled with a skewness of 1.05, denoting a slight rightward distribution tail. Elevated kurtosis in CSCO (10.45) and INTC (1.00) suggest the potential presence of outliers or extreme values.

The datasets were meticulously curated, exhibiting no missing values, which reinforces the reliability of the analysis. The observed variations, skewness, and kurtosis across these

datasets yield insights and a thorough comprehension of the nuanced dynamics of the stock market. This forms a solid base for subsequent sophisticated analyses and provides vital perspectives on the market's variations and distribution characteristics. Subsequent experiments are conducted to establish the superiority of the LSTM model over alternative DL and traditional ML/ETS models. It hopes to serve as a time-saving benchmark for future research in time series forecasting, allowing researchers to prioritize the efficacy of our optimal LSTM model.

3. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

3.1. Experimental Process

Figure 3: Model Evaluation Process Overview

Regarding Figure 3, raw data is first loaded, chronologically sorted, indexed by 'Date', and normalized using MinMaxScaler, ensuring a uniform range between 0 and 1 across variables to prevent computational difficulties during training. The data is reformatted into sequences with a specified lookback period of 5 data points, enabling the LSTM model to capture temporal dependencies, and then split into an 80:20 training-test set.

An LSTM network, constructed with a single LSTM layer containing 50 units and a dense output layer, is compiled with the Adam optimizer and trained over 50 epochs. Thus, early stopping is implemented during training to prevent overfitting. Predictions are generated on the test set and subsequently unnormalized to their original scale, facilitating comparison with actual values. Finally, model performance is critically assessed using MAE, and RMSE, providing a quantitative measure of the model's forecasting accuracy before visualizing the results to scrutinize underlying trends. Following, Section 3.2 showcases the dominance of

LSTM among other groups of popular models while discussing its remarkable impact in capturing market trend.

3.2. Results and Discussion

3.2.1. LSTM versus Traditional Models

Table 2: MAE and RMSE of LSTM across three categories

MODEL	IBM		CSCO		INTC	
	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE	RMSE
Exponential Smoothing						
Simple ETS	10,94	12,99	5,99	7,29	7,98	9,98
Triple ETS (Holt-Winters)	11,59	14,24	9,15	10,29	9,57	12,85
Double ETS (Holt)	11,78	14,42	9,20	10,33	9,58	12,87
Machine Learning						
AdaBoost	23,92	25,16	3,71	4,13	4,99	5,77
Gradient Boosting	24,06	25,61	3,68	4,05	4,52	5,27
Random Forest	24,37	26,05	3,66	4,03	4,39	5,14
Extra Trees	24,44	26,09	3,66	4,02	4,35	5,08
Bagging	24,39	26,11	3,66	4,03	4,40	5,14
KNN (k=10)	24,38	26,20	3,71	4,10	4,78	5,53
MLP	25,17	26,26	3,69	4,00	3,91	4,83
KNN (k=5)	24,44	26,33	3,71	4,09	4,58	5,35
KNN (k=3)	24,36	26,35	3,70	4,08	4,52	5,31
Decision Tree	24,39	26,96	3,64	4,01	4,37	5,22
SVR (RBF)	27,18	28,26	4,11	4,78	6,75	8,66
Linear Regression	30,58	31,53	4,25	4,53	3,98	4,46
Ridge Regression	30,58	31,53	4,25	4,53	3,98	4,46
Elastic Net	30,95	31,87	4,43	4,71	4,27	4,70
Lasso Regression	30,96	31,87	4,53	4,80	4,30	4,70
SVR (Poly)	32,41	34,62	9,54	12,08	19,65	27,61
SVR (Linear)	34,17	34,99	3,79	4,09	3,48	4,05
Deep Learning						
CNN	2.32	3.10	3.22	3.74	2.76	3.32
GRU	15.32	17.84	5.47	7.23	3.56	5.24
Bidirectional LSTM	2.47	3.71	3.52	5.32	2.10	3.22
LSTM	1.71	2.34	1.10	1.36	0.85	1.20

Table 2 depicts the empirical experiments of 24 models from 3 main groups of models, which are Exponential Smoothing (ETS), Machine Learning (ML), and Deep Learning (DL), on our datasets. The experiment shows that in handling non-linear data, ETS and DL models perform better than traditional ML models. However, as studied in Section 2, the univariate approach of ETS could skew the comparison results, holding for investigation.

Averagely, the DL group contains models with the lowest MAE and RMSE results, showcasing its efficiency in learning sequential data relationships, which outperforms the univariate computation of ETS models. Moreover, Bidirectional LSTM, an advanced extent of LSTM, was proven to be less effective than our LSTM, depicting the unnecessary of incorporating advanced DL models to reduce the complexity of modeling and avoid

overfitting. Consequently, LSTM was clarified as the most suitable model to predict the designated tech stocks in this case. Likewise, its application in forecasting is visualized in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Actual Values and Predicted Values of LSTM on (a) IBM, (b) CSCO, and (c) INTC Stock

Figure 4 illustrates the efficiency of LSTM in forecasting IBM, CSCO, and INTC stock through visualization of the real data and the predicted data. Concerning the cases of IBM (a) and INTC (c), the overall predicted values (red line) hardly deviate from the actual value (blue line), indicating the capability of capturing the exact trend of the market in the long term.

However, CSCO's real and forecasted values (b) witness a noticeable deviation in long-term prediction. Despite this limitation, the trend of the forecasted adjusted closing price still precisely matched the trend of the real values, resulting in a MAE of 1.10 and a RMSE of 1.36. Therefore, our LSTM is justified as the model with the lowest evaluation metrics across all datasets, making it suitable for IBM, CSCO, and INTC stock price forecasts, as illustrated in Figure 4 and computed in Table 2.

4. CONCLUSION AND RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

The theoretical and practical implications of this study are substantial. Our LSTM with Adam algorithms has demonstrated superior performance in forecasting three US tech stocks (IBM, INTC, and CSCO), thereby redefining traditional forecasting methods. Theoretically, this study forms a crucial blueprint for LSTM application, encouraging its use by economists, statisticians, and finance managers in handling complex sequential time series data to mitigate portfolio risk in the Big Data era. Practically, LSTM can be readily applied to enhance trading strategies for these stocks by minimizing investment risk.

The proposed LSTM architectures could guide investors and business managers on optimal trading times, mitigating risk and bolstering resilience in a post-pandemic economy as the predictor variables can be updated simultaneously for timely results. Policymakers may consider integrating macroeconomic indicators like CPI and interest rates into raw OHLCV stock datasets to anticipate market responses prior to implementing new monetary policies before their official declaration, understanding the market reaction. Overall, foreseeing the growth of a company means administering its prosperity; thereby, our advanced LSTM construction helps embrace and ensure the sustainability of an organization through pioneering technological innovation.

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DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND ORGANIZATIONAL RESILIENCE: THE CASE OF HANOI SEWERAGE AND DRAINAGE LIMITED COMPANY

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Abstract

Uncertain times (e.g., the coronavirus epidemic (COVID-19) and the post-pandemic era) require service businesses to respond in creative, flexible, and resilient ways. In this regard, digital transformation is important as digitalization can help businesses transform in a better way. This paper aims to develop and test the theoretical relationship between digital transformation and organizational resilience. Specifically, this research used quantitative methods to test the dimensions and measurement items of OR and analyzed how the dimensions of digital maturity influence the dimensions of OR. The data for this research was collected from 160 participants, then cleaned and analyzed by SMART PLS. The obtained results have shown that both measurement items of digital transformation, which are Digital Intensity and Transformation Management Intensity, have a positive effect on Organizational Resilience. The intensity of digital transformation can help the organization build tangible infrastructure and supporting systems while transformation management intensity equips organizations with a transformative vision, allowing an organization to develop their capabilities to quickly respond to crises and be resilient.

Keywords: *digital maturity, intensity, organizational resilience, post-Covid, transformation.*

I. INTRODUCTION

While the socioeconomic effects of pandemics can be quickly and widely dispersed like wildfire, the advent of pandemics is typically unexpected, and their effects are life-threatening. The World Health Organization designated the COVID-19 (C19) coronavirus to be a pandemic on March 11, 2020, after it first arose in 2019 (Cucinotta & Vanelli, 2020; Ducharme, 2020). The COVID-19 epidemic had direct effects on businesses across almost all industries, which resulted in substantial economic failures (Nga et al., 2022).

Due to poor vaccination rates, the COVID-19 pandemic has pushed several major cities and provinces in Vietnam to isolate themselves socially due to its complex dynamics and quick expansion. The economy and every element of social life have been negatively impacted by this phenomenon. Moreover, income and consumer demand fell as a result of the pandemic's onset and the widespread adoption of social isolation. Due to a dramatic decline in demand and a rise in production costs, the output of key industries such as transportation and warehousing, tourism, lodging, food services, education, manufacturing sector, etc., was significantly impacted.

Risks of financial instability and macro instability are also rising at the same time. A rise in inflation is anticipated as a result of cost-push factors and further monetary easing. The space available for fiscal policy is less, economic growth is at its slowest level in the previous two decades, and bad debt has climbed once more after a protracted downward trend. As a result, the process of reacting to the pandemic and economic recovery has become challenging due to the numerous threats of macro instability and financial instability, posing threats to both the overall state of the world economy and the economy of Vietnam.

Because of this issue, the use of a variety of contemporary technology became necessary and ended up being the only means by which many enterprises managed to survive the epidemic. Several businesses were forced to quickly assess and modify their digitization strategies in order to affect the fundamental changes that the situation needed, and many of them were able to implement years' worth of plans for digital transformation in only a few months.

Owing to the nature of the business, drainage and wastewater treatment firms had several challenges throughout the pandemic, particularly during the period of social isolation. As manual laborers make up the majority of the workforce, social distance prevents them from working onsite. Hence, the wastewater management and treatment business in particular, and the water industry in general are all turning towards digital transformation and the use of technology in order to solve this issue and prepare for situations such as COVID-19 that may emerge in future (Grievson et al., 2022).

Many benefits are produced by digital technology in the drainage and wastewater treatment sector. These advantages not only assist the local area by enhancing affordability and protecting the environment, but they also provide several advantages for the entire business. Increased customer engagement and satisfaction, lower operating costs, improved departmental cooperation with systems integration across data silos, and other advantages are the results of water firms using digital technology.

Hanoi Sewerage and drainage limited company is a company specializing in the drainage industry in Vietnam, officially established in 1991. The company's goal is to administer and maintain Hanoi's drainage system, with a particular focus on drainage in the city's four major urban districts (*CÔNG TY TNHH MỘT THÀNH VIÊN THOÁT NƯỚC HÀ NỘI (HSDC)*, n.d.). In addition, the company also plays a key role in overcoming waterlogging and minimizing environmental pollution in the capital. Hanoi Sewerage and drainage limited company has broadened its product lines and business ventures throughout its development in the areas of project consultancy, drainage services, urban infrastructure building and installation, wastewater treatment, and environmental sanitation.

In the context of COVID and post-COVID, the drainage and wastewater treatment sector in Vietnam, particularly the Hanoi sewerage and drainage limited business, is experiencing significant challenges as a result of the epidemic's effects on the world economy. Some specific parameters can be mentioned such as the total capacity of production and supply of clean water is largely reduced compared to the amount of water consumed before the epidemic and the average reduction rate is about 6-6.5% and most businesses' revenue compared to before the epidemic decreased, some even decreased by 12-15% (Nguyễn, 2020).

As mentioned above, while the impact of covid appears in all aspects of the economy, previous studies could only cover industries that are directly related to the economy. Meanwhile, the study of post-pandemic recovery is an important topic, and every profession should be provided with information on this. There have been studies talking about digital transformation and applying digital transformation in business, such as the study about enhancing business resilience with digital transformation by Elgazzar et al., (2022) or a study on the digitalization of SMEs by Guo et al., (2020).

However, up to the present time, most of the research papers only talk about digitalization in the time of Covid. They have yet to mention the continued application of this transformation in the post-pandemic period. Meanwhile, maintaining and continuing to develop deeper in the application of digitalization is extremely necessary for companies to catch up with the times and prepare for possible uncertainties in the future.

Also, while there have been many previous articles about digitalization in the time of covid, their research topics are different from the industry and the context of my research paper. Some previous research papers have worked on a similar topic, the majority of industries included are banking, healthcare, and services. Some research papers can be mentioned, such as the study about how digital transformation and cyber security can increase the resilience of healthcare systems by Garcia-Perez et al., (2023) or enhancing stock market resilience through digital transformation by evaluating the COVID-19 pandemic's impact using Google trends by Ding et al., (2020). Other research about options for Canary Islands tourist businesses' resilience and digital transformation by Hernández Sánchez and Oskam, (2022) and Creating Pandemic Supply Networks with Resilience Through Digital Transformation by Klöckner et al., (2023) are also two brilliant research papers on this topic.

Research articles on this topic have almost never mentioned the current status and problems of the Drainage and wastewater treatment industry in Vietnam in this context, while this is a rather important industry due to the influence of the weather and the climate here, specifically Hanoi City.

In order to address the aforementioned issues, this study uses the quantitative analytic technique to investigate the connection between business resilience and digital transformation. With the aid of my research, I hope to be able to respond to the following question: How can digital transformation affect business resilience?

Scope and Access

Since the relationship between organizational resilience and digital transformation is the subject of this research report, specifically in the drainage and wastewater treatment industry in Vietnam, information will be collected from employees working in this industry. Specifically, a questionnaire will be sent to the office staff of Hanoi Sewerage and drainage limited company to collect information about the company's digital transformation status, and they will also answer a few questions to measure the company's resilience. The collected information will be analyzed by the analytical software, and the results obtained will be used as evidence to support the hypothesis of this study. As such, the results obtained can be used to reach the scope of the research paper, which is providing additional information and understanding about applying information technology to business resilience in the drainage and wastewater treatment industry in Vietnam.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Theoretical framework

2.1.1. Digital transformation

One change has accelerated in response to the COVID-19 pandemic that has been affecting people worldwide since the end of 2019: digital transformation (Muditomo & Wahyudi, 2021). Almost all company activities now revolve around digital changes, and businesses must grow to compete in expanding market settings. The use of technology to alter corporate paradigms and provide fresh opportunities, income, and value is known as "digital transformation" (Henriette et al., 2015; Kane et al., 2017). To put it another way, "digital transformation" refers to a process used by businesses and organizations to convert every aspect of their operations in the direction of deploying digital applications in order to improve operational quality, service quality, and labor efficiency (Thu et al., 2023).

As mentioned in two other research papers by Zhang et al., (2021) and Vial, (2019), to transform an enterprise's strategy, vision, organizational structure, capabilities, processes, and culture to meet the demands of the rapidly evolving digital world, Information, computer, communication, and networking technologies must be used to integrate internal and external resources.

Digital transformation entails a number of procedures that take place over time rather than simply one activity (Rupeika-Apoga et al., 2022). Because of this, a framework dubbed "digital maturity" has been created to assess the success of the company's transformation activities in the digital term (Chanas & Hess, 2016). A set of scoring criteria for digital maturity can be used to assess the process' state and performance at various stages along the road since digital transformation is an ongoing process (Kane et al., 2017; Marx, 2019).

Numerous measures that take into account both the skills required to attain the desired maturity stage and the features that need to be developed for digital transformation can be used to assess the level of digital maturity of a business. Several scales for digital maturity have been developed in research papers such as "Industry 4.0 and Digital Maturity" by Kupilas et al., (2021) with a four levels scale, or the scale that combined the firm's response to digital transformation with its capacity to manage impending changes by Remane et al., (2017). The two-way scale created by the MIT Center for Digital Business and Capgemini Consulting stands out among the current digital maturity measures because it is the most practical and relevant in a variety of situations. Transformation management intensity (TMI) and digital intensity (DI) make up the scale's two aspects (Westerman et al., 2012).

Digital intensity is the proportion of a given region that is under the control of digital solutions, transformation techniques, or strategies (Westerman et al., 2012). In other words, the amount of a company's digital activity is directly connected with its digital intensity (Nasiri et al., 2022). Another way to define DI is the degree to which a normal task is facilitated by digital tools rather than by physical tools (Gaskin et al., 2012). Digital intensity helps businesses to perform effectively and handle a larger volume of activities in changing settings by applying technology-based innovations. Also, rising DI encourages firms to investigate digital prospects, strive to draw in clients, and operate using digital tools. TMI, on the other

hand, stands for the organizational digital transformation leadership required (Westerman et al., 2012). Organizations with high TMI usually undergo transformations in their governance, culture, and vision in order to coordinate digital activities and maximize financial rewards.

An organization may gain greatly from digital expansion, including improved organizational performance and staff retention, according to a prior study (Kane et al., 2017; Westerman et al., 2012). It is currently unclear whether and how businesses in the drainage and wastewater treatment sector may be helped by digital maturity in difficult times, despite the increased interest in this area. The connection between two digital maturity characteristics (i.e., DI and TMI) and OR in the drainage and wastewater sector is examined in this study due to the significance of the subject and the paucity of research in the area.

2.1.2. Organizational Resilience

Organizational resilience, commonly referred to as business resilience, is a contentious concept. Resilience is a word that is used frequently in a variety of industries and occupations. It may be roughly characterized as continuing to make beneficial changes when facing difficult circumstances for an organization, a person, or an ecosystem (Fiksel, 2006; Ismail et al., 2011). Anggadwita et al., (2021) suggested that Holling, (1973) original ecological definition of the term resilience has altered to highlight the capacity to deal with obstructions rather than being a measure of a system's resilience and capacity to withstand changes and interruptions.

Resilience is defined, from an organizational perspective, as a company's capacity to endure significant changes in the commercial and economic environment as well as its capacity to survive interruptions and catastrophic occurrences (Acquaah et al., 2011). Also, business resilience according to Zohuri and Moghaddam, (2018) is the capacity of a system to sustain specific operations, procedures, or responses in the face of disruption. Business resilience, according to Dahlberg and Guay, (2015), is the capacity of an organization to withstand risks and adjust to unforeseen or sudden changes.

Meanwhile, Darkow, (2019) has stated that Organizational resilience is a produced, assessed, and managed complex combination of viewpoints, behaviors, and interactions. Resilience typically manifests itself following an incident or tragedy (O'Hare, 2007). Businesses can respond rapidly to disturbances, safeguarding their staff, assets, and total brand equity, by developing organizational resilience (Simeone, 2015). Dahles and Susilowati (Williams & Vorley, 2014) say that it is essential for economic growth for local businesses and companies to respond to sudden changes and shocks. Businesses that are resilient are able to bounce back from setbacks and exhibit flexibility, which can result in significant changes to the entire business model (Aldianto et al., 2021; Fiksel, 2006). Also, it was found that in order for a company to expand, advance, and thrive in a highly competitive business climate, it must be able to use science and technology efficiently. This is true for initiatives to improve and develop goods and processes as well as for improvements in technology's capacity to generate knowledge and new capabilities (Raisch et al., 2009). Many components, including management of keystone vulnerabilities, situation awareness, and adaptive capability, can be used to evaluate the organizational resilience model (McManus et al., 2008). Lee et al., (2013), proposed a modified model of organizational resilience that was divided into two characteristics planning and adaptive capacity. This study would employ these two indexes as a

scale to quantify digital maturity. Planning refers to the contingency plan that an organization employs to foresee upcoming problems and communicate particular roles and responsibilities inside the organization, while an organization's capacity for adapting is referred to as its ability to balance stability and change (Filimonau et al., 2020).

2.1.3. The relationship between digital transformation and organizational resilience

A previous literature review had shown that DT has a favorable influence on resilience, thus businesses that use it can boost long-term corporate profitability (Elgazzar et al., 2022). A resilience model is also measured at three company sizes from micro to macro in another study that examined MSMEs in India (Khurana et al., 2022). The results show that because DT improves resource management, it is crucial for establishing resilience. DT may assist firms in surviving a catastrophe like the pandemic by adjusting to the changes quickly. Mangalaraj et al., (2023) stated that as IT expertise makes businesses nimbler and more sensitive to changes, organizational dependency on IT in retail organizations pushes entrepreneurs to retain corporate strategy. As mentioned by Kazemi et al., (2019) Businesses must increase their capacity to increase their value and competitiveness in order to battle opponents, and they may do this by developing and upgrading their DT (Elgazzar et al., 2022).

It is clear that DT and resilience are related based on the historical empirical data and literary research mentioned above. There isn't any proof of this, though, in the drainage and wastewater treatment sector. This study's primary goal was to close the evidence gap using data from the Hanoi Sewerage and Drainage Limited Company.

3. HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

This study suggests that raising DI may enhance OR in times of crisis. With increased spending on digital technologies, service companies may more readily and flexibly organize internal resources (such as labor, information, expertise, etc.) to control major vulnerabilities and carry on operations in the face of adversity. During the COVID-19 epidemic, this became apparent. Businesses may obtain and manage greater volume with the physical capacity they already have because of digital intensity. Companies that are strong in digital intensity, for instance, generate 16% more income through their people and physical resources than do digitally conservative organizations (Westerman et al., 2012).

While many service providers were forced to close their doors owing to quarantine-related regulations, businesses that had made investments in digital technology were able to continue their operations by engaging with clients in new and interesting ways (McCartney & McCartney, 2020). Moreover, the development of digital information technology has allowed some businesses to propose substitute plans for service supply at times when many consumers and staff were confined at home (Lund et al., 2020).

Wastewater treatment and drainage companies may use outside resources and seize new chances to assist company operations by strategically investing in digitization. Digital technologies enable organizations to build networks to communicate with other businesses, provide useful information and resources to carry on with operations, and boost resilience in disruptive conditions, according to past research (Choudhury, 2021). For Hanoi Sewerage and drainage limited company, digital transformation has brought countless benefits. The

application and transition to technology-based activities help the company increase labor productivity, and handle workload quickly, thereby facilitating the company to bid on and receive big projects.

Based on the above theorization, it can be proposed that:

H1. Digital intensity (DI) positively affects Organizational Resilient (OR).

This study suggests that raising transformation management intensity can improve organizational resilience in ambiguous situations. On the one hand, raising TMI improves OR's individual contribution by encouraging people to actively track the environment's changes and come up with creative solutions. A company's transformational vision, governance, and culture may be provided by improving TMI (Westerman et al., 2012). Moreover, in order to guarantee that employee conduct is in line with the purpose and that digital operations are progressing in the proper path during tumultuous times, high TMI necessitates that organizations regulate employee behavior (Westerman et al., 2014). Organizations create a digital culture via employee engagement and digital vision that thinks and acts differently, inspiring staff to advance their skills and come up with innovative ways to handle crises (Kane et al., 2017).

As opposed to that, high TMI enhances systematic management of OR by allowing service companies to effectively harness internal and external resources. Businesses with high TMI encourage cooperation with suppliers and rivals to get essential outside resources and seize chances. These resources are shared both inside and outside the business, and they are essential for systematic control because they enable the organization to function even in the face of unanticipated crises (Ignatiadis & Nandhakumar, 2007). These factors contribute to the tendency of mature transformation management-intensity organizations to be more profitable. For example, using a variety of metrics, digital conservative enterprises are typically 9% to 26% more lucrative than typical rivals in the industry (Westerman et al., 2012).

Therefore, the following theory will be put forth:

H2. Transformation management intensity (TMI) positively affects Organizational Resilient (OR).

Research model

(Source: Author, 2023)

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Research Approach

The research is done with the **positivism philosophy**, using the **deductive approach**, and the method used in this paper is **mono-quantitative** as this study proceeds to generate the hypothesis using numerical data.

With the aim of determining the change in the dependent variable would result in a change in the independent variable—in this case, DI, TMI, and OR—the research article will utilize an **experimental strategy**, which has strong ties to the natural sciences. Because this research project was certainly engaged for an academic course that is time-constrained, and this study employs the survey strategy, **cross-sectional** has been the chosen time horizon to examine the relations between the variables.

4.2. Data collection

The Hanoi Sewerage and Drainage Limited Company's office staff was polled for the data that was used in this study. A questionnaire with 32 questions that were created with consideration for my two research hypotheses has been distributed, and 160 office staff members from the aforementioned company have been chosen at random and asked to answer all of the questions by marking the boxes adjacent to the Likert scale responses ranging from 1 to 5. Because it would allow the researcher to collect data from sizeable participant samples, the survey method was chosen. Moreover, surveys can be used to examine a wide range of factors, are inexpensive to prepare and administer, and frequently need just minimal extrapolation (Bell, 1996).

4.3. Sampling method and Limitation

There are several strategies that may be used for sampling, and these approaches can be categorized into two main categories: probability sampling and non-probability sampling (McCombes, 2019). The conventional approach has been used in this study since this process is incredibly fast, simple, available, and affordable.

On the other hand, given that this study may have significant weaknesses, convenience sampling may not have produced the most accurate findings.

4.4. Respondents, Sample size, and location

Participants who are employed by Hanoi Sewerage and Drainage Limited Company provided the researcher with data. Using a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error, the bare minimum sample size needed to test the conceptual model was calculated.

Based on the formula to calculate the number of relevant responses to run the analytical model, because the total number of questions investigating the variables of the research article in this questionnaire is 29 questions, the ideal number of participants was 160 participants.

5. VARIABLES

In this study, a total of 3 variables have been used. More specifically, there are two independent variables (DI and TMI) and there is one dependent variable (OR).

Table 1: The measurement of study variables, data collection instruments, and procedures

Variables	Types	Items	Measurement	Sources
Digital Intensity	Independent	10	Rating (Likert Scale)	(He et al., 2021)
Transformation Management Intensity	Independent	10	Rating (Likert Scale)	(He et al., 2021)
Organizational Resilience	Dependent	9	Rating (Likert Scale)	(Prasongthan, 2022)

(Source: Author, 2023)

6. DATA PROCESSING

To analyze the data, the researchers used structural equation modeling based on partial least squares (PLS-SEM). The researcher will be able to better understand the link between the study's two dependent variables and one independent variable by employing the PLS-SEM approach. PLS-SEM is an appropriate choice for gathering statistical data because the study's sample size (n=160) allows for it.

In order to assess the SMART PLS outcome measurement model, particular attention has been paid to composite reliability, bootstrapping, AVE (average variance extracted), R square, outer loading, and discriminant validity.

7. DISCUSSION

The topic of this study as well as the relationship between the variables used in this study have been considered in previous studies, and these studies provide a variety of results.

Table 2: Previous studies results

No	Authors	Methods	Contexts	Findings/Discussion
1	(Elgazzar et al., 2022)	Literature review	In the time of Covid19 pandemic	Digital transformation can cause long-term business resilient
2	(Tripathi, 2021)	Conceptual framework	In the post-Covid-19 business world	Digital transformation helps in running core business operations with resiliency.
3	(Khalil et al., 2022)	Quantitative research method	during the COVID-19 crisis	Digital transformation positively affects business resilience
4	(Wang & Chen, 2022)	Machine learning and text analysis methods	In the time of Covid19 pandemic and the increase of uncertainties in external environments.	The digital transformation of enterprises can significantly enhance their resilience.
5	(Putritamara et al., 2023)	Quantitative research method	During the COVID-19 Pandemic	Digital transformation has an insignificant effect on firm resilience in small nonfamily businesses.

(Source: Author, 2023)

Compared with the results obtained from previous studies on the same topic, my paper has similar results. Out of the total of 2 independent variables, both DI and TMI have an effect on the dependent variable OR.

The analysis of the findings is presented in this part, along with a discussion of the ramifications of the data presented above. Other explanations and investigations will support the corresponding variables of the hypothesis.

Table 3: Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Relationships	Path coefficient	P Value	Result
H1	Digital intensity (DI) -> Organizational Resilient (OR)	0.215	0.002	Supported
H2	Transformation management intensity (TMI) -> Organizational Resilient (OR)	0.668	0.000	Supported

H1. Digital intensity (DI) positively affects Organizational Resilient (OR) -> Supported.

The purpose of the hypothesis was to examine if there is a positive association between digital intensity (DI) and organizational resilience (OR). According to the results of hypothesis 1 from the above table, the P-value is 0.002, while 0.215 was the Path coefficient value. These results mean that when applying digital intensity in the company, it will be positively interpreted into increasing the resilience of the organization. Especially, when there is an increase of 0.002 units of digital intensity, it will increase the organizational resilience by 0.215.

This finding demonstrates the validity of the hypothesis and the beneficial influence of DI on OR. The intensity of digital transformation may aid an organization in creating a physical infrastructure and supporting systems to improve planning and adaptability, allowing the business to function more sustainably amid a crisis.

The result of this hypothesis is similar to some previous studies. According to He et al., (2021), organizations are motivated to investigate digital prospects, strive to engage consumers, and operate the business using digital technology as the level of digital intensity rises. As there are now more options for continuing corporate operations than merely working offline, the organization will be more robust as a result. Sousa-Zomer et al., (2020) also stated that after examining the function of DT in major businesses across economic sectors, it can be said that organizations with strong digital intensity have the basis to deal with quick changes, keeping the company's resilience.

H2. Transformation management intensity (TMI) positively affects Organizational Resilient (OR) -> Supported.

The hypothesis aims to test the positive relationship between Transformation Management Intensity (TMI) and organizational resilience (OR). According to the results of hypothesis 2 from the above table, the P-value is 0.000, while 0.668 was the Path coefficient value. These results mean that when applying transformational management intensity in the company, it will be positively interpreted into increasing the resilience of the organization. Especially, when there is an increase of 0,000 units of transformational management intensity,

it will increase the organizational resilience by 0.668. Surveys conducted at Hanoi Sewerage Limited Company have shown that transformation management intensity has a positive influence on organizational resilience in the post-COVID-19 era when leaders have management transformation and responsiveness in their vision to coordinate the organization's digital transformation activities.

TMI provides enterprises with a digital culture, governance, and revolutionary vision. Through the use of such an integrated leadership structure, an organization may assist staff in gaining the skills necessary to act fast in crisis situations. Additionally, to make sure that digital operations are expanding in the proper direction and so boosting the resilience of the organization, visionary leaders and transformational governance may actively forge connections with and collaborate closely with entities both inside and outside the business.

The result are similar to the result on the finding of Kendra and Wachtendorf, (2003), which stated that increasing the intensity of transformation management has a positive effect on organizational resilience due to work flexibility. He et al., (2021), who theoretically proposed and empirically tested the relationship between the dimensions of digital maturity and OR, also came to the same conclusion that the intensity of transformation management plays a crucial role in giving organizations access to tools and resources that can be used right away to boost resilience.

8. POLICY IMPLICATIONS

For Hanoi Sewerage and drainage limited company, it is necessary to accelerate the process of digital transformation. Hanoi Sewerage and drainage limited company can adopt innovative solutions that will help reduce costs and improve work productivity in order to operate more efficiently.

The company should use advanced technology such as AI-driven sensors and predictive analytics to monitor water levels in the city's drainage system and detect potential problems before they become serious. In addition, they can also implement automated processes, such as robotic process automation (RPA), which can help streamline their operations and reduce manual labor costs. Furthermore, they should also invest in modern infrastructure that is designed with sustainability in mind, such as energy-efficient pumps and pipes that are better suited for the environment. By implementing these solutions, Hanoi Sewerage and drainage limited company can significantly improve its efficiency and work productivity while simultaneously helping the city tackle its flood problem.

Hanoi Sewerage and drainage limited company is also facing a tough challenge in recovering from the effects of Covid-19 while also improving their digital intensity. The recovery period after the epidemic is an important time for the company. To make sure they can compete with other players in the market, they must focus on digital intensity to improve their operations. To help them in this endeavor, there are several solutions that can be taken. These include leveraging cloud computing, investing in digital infrastructure, developing innovative digital products and services, and introducing new technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML). These solutions should be used by Hanoi Sewerage and Drainage Limited Company to encourage the improvement of production, operation, and management models, as well as to encourage the digital transformation to a

deeper level, effectively enhancing businesses' capacity to withstand risks. By using these solutions, the company will not only recover from the pandemic but also become more digitally advanced.

9. CONCLUSION

Covid 19 is a factor that has a direct impact on the explosion of modern technology. After Covid 19, the application of modern technologies is indispensable for all businesses to be able to operate smoothly in all situations. The wastewater treatment and management industry, which has a workforce of manual workers, has also understood the importance of digital transformation and technology application in its operations. To support digital transformation and technology application for the drainage and wastewater treatment industry, this study provided information related to the post-covid 19 contexts, focusing on the relationship of digital transformation and resilience of the organization of Hanoi Sewerage and drainage limited company. The relationship between these two variables is collected and tested by quantitative method, with the use of PLS SEM model analysis. The results of the study indicate that the relationship between these two variables is positive and that in order to enhance the resilience and resilience of enterprises, attention should be paid to increasing digital and management intensity. convert. More specifically, the company should focus on improving and enhancing digital intensity by using technology more in the organizational process. In addition, the company should step up the transformation management intensity so that the organization can develop its technological capabilities in a stable and sustainable way.

10. REFLECTION

Overall, my planning of the job to be done and the research process was successful. Additionally, I have gathered sufficient data from the participants, aggregated it, presented it in the form of graphs, and performed an analysis on it. I've gained a lot of new skills from conducting this research that will help me in both my academic and professional endeavors. My knowledge of the fundamental office computers has increased, and I have gained more experience conducting primary research. By practicing statistics, data analysis, and charting with samples in class before working with actual research data, I was able to learn and develop my writing and data analysis skills. This helped me with the data gathering and analysis for the research report.

In addition, I learned more about data analysis models and gained more knowledge about how to use these models. More specifically, I have absorbed knowledge and proficiently used SMART PLS software during the research process. Besides, since the water supply and drainage industry is not often well researched, doing this research has helped me gain more knowledge about this industry.

While conducting this research, there are some limitations that might be of interest. First, although the objectives of conducting research and producing results have been achieved, this research has not yet gone into other aspects of digital transformation and modern technology due to resource and time constraints. The number of participants has been limited due to time and cost constraints; thus, the statistical findings may not be generalizable to a larger population. Besides, the survey has been completed online. Online surveys are frequently sent very instantaneously using personal emails and social media. The population in which they are

scattered cannot be identified or understood, and prejudiced respondents may choose to participate in the sample.

The findings highlight some gaps in my knowledge of public involvement in research, which could be filled by further research. As a result, it would be advantageous to qualitatively record the experiences and viewpoints of research participants who had unfavorable or mixed experiences, as they may be less inclined to volunteer for studies of research participants' involvement than enthusiasts. The perspectives of underprivileged and underrepresented groups participating in research may also be examined in future research. Besides, several hypotheses and variables were provided based on this research, and they can aid other researchers in developing an approachable, practical, or learnable plan for their own research, complete with objectives, parameters, and methods. As a result, this research paper can be used as a reference for future studies by other researchers.

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APPLICATION OF ARIMA MODEL AND DEEP LEARNING IN FORECASTING STOCK PRICE IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

Time series forecasting is essential in production, business, and policy-making. In Vietnam, statistical models, such as foreign investment and consumer price index, have been used to forecast time series. However, only some studies have used deep learning models to predict economic variables. This article aims to review and evaluate the predictive ability of the ARIMA and deep learning models when forecasting the prices of the five stocks with the largest capitalization from January 2018 to April 2023. The deep learning model's prediction results show that the deviation rate between the actual and predicted values is 3.3%. Businesses and stakeholders should increase the use of technology and artificial intelligence for forecasting to support decision-making.

Keywords: Deep learning; Stock price; Vietnam; LSTM

1. INTRODUCTION

Stock price prediction is a challenging problem due to the complex and volatile nature of stock prices. Both researchers and investors have shown interest in this area. Various methods, from traditional analytical techniques to artificial intelligence methods such as fuzzy logic and artificial neural networks, have been used to predict financial markets (Hsu et al., 2009; Abraham et al., 2001).

Time series forecasting involves using statistical and modeling methods to predict future trends. Traditional econometric models can be effective but have drawbacks, including compromised performance due to lack of specificity, inability to identify complex fluctuations in data, and inaccurate long-term forecasts. One of them is the autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model. From the first day, this model has been widely used in many fields, such as statistics, estimation, and forecasting, because it is found that the model has many advantages (Box & Pierce, 1970), (Bianchi et al., 1998). ARIMA's most significant advantage is its high forecasting accuracy while eliminating multicollinearity in the model. However, this model also has some disadvantages, which are difficulty in establishing a standard model from a group of potential models; forecasting methods are subjective; theoretical models and structural relationships do not differ from some simple predictive models (Thomas & Stekler, 1983); The data must follow the assumptions of the linear

regression model. Overcoming the limitations of traditional machine learning models, deep learning (DL) models are a significant step forward. Many studies show that deep learning models are widely applied in forecasting and achieving high-accuracy results. DL is a part of machine learning (ML). In recent years, DL techniques have outperformed traditional models. In particular, DL is successfully applied when solving time series forecasting problems because DL uses a multi-layered structure of algorithms called neural networks that make data preparation faster and more efficient.

In deep learning, pre-trained models mainly consist of neural networks. There are three types of neural networks: artificial neural networks (ANNs), convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and recurrent neural networks (RNNs). Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) is an improved version of RNN that makes it easier to remember past data. The LSTM network builds the model using the backpropagation method. LSTM is well-suited for classifying, processing, and predicting time series with an unknown delay since each forecasting model has pros and cons for getting the most accurate time series forecasting results.

ANN is often used to describe the nonlinear relationship between input and output, but local extremes can easily trap it. Additionally, ANNs have many free parameters that often require a trial-and-error approach to select (Sapankevych & Sankar, 2009). Some studies use support vector regression (SVR) (Bishop & Nasrabadi, 2006), which has been shown to provide accurate results in stock price prediction problems (Hsu et al., 2009). However, choosing the right technical analysis indicator for each stock is not straightforward since an indicator that works well for one stock may not work for another (Ince & Trafalis, 2007). Given the pros and cons of each forecasting model, how can we obtain the most accurate time series forecasting results?

In Vietnam, numerous websites and securities apps supported by machine learning can predict market trends through automatic analysis of trading data. Machine learning also provides a capital allocation strategy for investors to optimize profits, including robust disbursement during reliable waves and limiting transactions during downtrends or sideways movements. Securities companies generally follow this trend but must be more synchronous and thorough. Furthermore, research on applying deep learning to stock price forecasting is necessary.

The primary objective of this study is to assess the forecasting capabilities of ARIMA and deep learning models for listed stocks in Vietnam. In this research paper, we have applied deep learning in stock price forecasting in the Vietnamese market. The results show that the LSTM model gives the best results in the dataset. Overall, the article has partly solved the problem of predicting stock prices with a deep-learning approach. A promising future direction is to apply deep learning methods to continue learning how to extract essential features and optimize our model so that we can filter data more accurately and achieve better predictive results. At the same time, with the speed of the internet developing faster and faster, it is possible to constantly update the model and process data in real-time, helping to predict stock prices more accurately in the future.

2. THEORIES

2.1. Models

Model ARIMA

The model uses time series data, considering the past values of a particular variable as good indicators of its future value. Specifically, Y_t represents the variable's value at time point t with $Y_t = f(Y_{t-1}, Y_{t-2}, \dots, Y_0, t)$.

The analysis aims to identify relationships between observed Y_t values to forecast future values, particularly for short-term forecasting purposes.

Autoregressive model p - AR(p): In the autoregressive model, the process depends on the sum of the weights of the past values and the random noise term.

$$Y_t = \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p Y_{t-p} + \delta + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Moving average model q - MA(q): In the moving average model, the process is described purely by the weighted sum of the lagged stochastics:

$$Y_t = \mu + \varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} \quad (2)$$

Moving Average Combined Regression Model - ARMA(p, q):

$$Y_t = \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p Y_{t-p} + \delta + \varepsilon_t - \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} - \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} - \dots - \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} \quad (3)$$

Consider the stationarity of the series of observations

The AR and MA components of the ARIMA model require stationary time series, but many time series are nonstationary. Stationarity means that the mean and variance of a stochastic process of Y_t do not change over time. Additionally, the price covariance between two time periods depends only on the time lag distance between these periods and not on the actual time at which the covariance is calculated. There are three ways to detect the stationarity of a time series: based on the graph of the time series, the graph of the sample autocorrelation function, or the Dickey-Fuller test.

ARMA(p, d, q) model recognition involves determining appropriate values of p , d , and q . Here, d represents the order of difference of the time series being investigated, p is the order of autoregression, and q is the order of moving average. The Box-Jenkins method is commonly used for evaluating the ARIMA model fit. Moreover, a time series generally has three main components: trend, period, and season, and the ARIMA model requires the time series to be stationary. A seasonal ARIMA model (SARIMA) has been developed to include the seasonal factor in the model. However, when forecasting in the long term, SARIMA model cannot provide accurate results if the time series still contains the remaining two components (trend and period). To improve the prediction quality in the long term, one can find a smooth function through the neural network. The original time series can be transformed into this smooth function by removing the seasonal element from the time series (Fathi, 2019).

Model LSTM

The LSTM network overcomes the long-term dependency issues of traditional RNNs. LSTM, introduced by (Schmidhuber & Hochreiter, 1997), has a chain structure of network

nodes similar to RNNs, but with a more complex internal structure consisting of four layers of interaction. The unique feature of the LSTM network lies in the cell state C , where the long-term weights of the model are stored. The parameters of the cell state C , hidden state h , and input at time t x_t are fed to the network node and after processing through sigmoid activation functions, tanh, and vector operations, the output is the cell state C and hidden state h at time t , which will be used for the node $t+1$.

Figure 1: Structure of a node in an LSTM network

The use of deep learning for time series forecasting has overcome the limitations of traditional machine learning with various approaches. Currently, RNN is most used for time series forecasting problems. RNNs have advantages: the performance of RNNs is not significantly affected by missing values; RNNs can find complex patterns in input time series; RNNs do well in long-term forecasting, more than just a few steps; RNNs can model data sequences to assume correlation between patterns.

2.2. Some indicators of forecasting quality

Various indicators are utilized to evaluate the quality of a model. Some commonly used metrics for predicting model quality include:

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) measures the mean absolute error between predicted and actual values.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (4)$$

We use MAE as a standard norm of order 1. The smaller the MAE, the better the model. However, MAE does not imply unit difference.

An estimator's Mean Squared Error (MSE) is the average of the square of the error. It measures the difference between the predicted and actual values. The MSE is a risk function corresponding to the expected value of squared error loss or quadratic loss. It is also the quadratic moment of the error.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (5)$$

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) is the residual's standard deviation (prediction error). The residual measures distance from the regression line data points; The RMSE measures the spread of these residuals. In other words, it tells how concentrated the data is around the best-fit line. RMSE is commonly used in forecasting and regression analysis to verify experimental

results. RMSE is a measure of how effective the model is. It does this by measuring the difference between predicted and actual values. The smaller the RMSE, the smaller the error, and the highest level of estimation that shows the model's reliability can be achieved.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (6)$$

The mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) is the mean fundamental percentage error of the forecasts. The better the forecast results, the smaller the MAPE. MAPE can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \quad (7)$$

Akaike Information Standards

One commonly used criterion for selecting a model is the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) index. AIC is based on information theory and estimates the amount of information lost by a given model. AIC refers to a trade-off between model fit and simplicity, dealing with the risk of over- and under-fitting. Here, k is the number of parameters and is the maximum value of the full likelihood function of the model.

3. LITERATURE REVIEWS

Foreign studies have combined traditional machine learning models and deep learning for time series forecasting. Choi (2018) used this combination to forecast the price correlation coefficient of two separate stocks. The combined model ARIMA-LSTM has superior predictive power compared to traditional models.

Research conducted by Song, Zhou, and Han (2018) compared the predictive ability of five neural network models: backpropagation (BP), radial basis function (RBF), general regression neural network (GRNN), support vector machine regression (SVMR), and least squares support vector machine regression (LS-SVMR). The study used mean square error and mean absolute error as evaluation criteria and made stock price predictions for the Bank of China. Results showed that the neural network was consistently superior and more robust than the other four models.

Li et al. (2019) proposed DP-LSTM, a deep neural network, to predict stock prices. DP-LSTM is an LSTM-based neural network that reduces prediction errors and enhances strength levels. The proposed model achieves a 0.32% improvement in mean MPA and an MSE improvement of up to 65.79%. Doshi et al. (2020) used LSTM neural networks to forecast stock prices for four companies and designed a trading strategy that performed portfolio optimization. The LSTM model with a custom loss function performed better than a regression model like ARIMA.

According to (Mehtab et al., 2021) stock price prediction has been an essential area of study for a long time. While proponents of the efficient market hypothesis believe that it is impossible to predict stock prices, formal proposals demonstrate that correct modeling and the design of appropriate variables can lead to models using stock prices, and models of stock price movements can be predicted very accurately. Researchers have also worked on stock

analysis techniques to identify patterns in stock price movements using advanced data mining techniques. The study used a combined modeling approach to predict stock prices by building machine and deep learning-based models. The results show that the most accurate model is the univariate model based on the LSTM using the previous week's data as input to predict the following week's NIFTY 50 time series open value.

In recent years, several studies have used machine learning algorithms and ANN in Vietnam's financial sector, such as (Ngoc et al, 2023), (Hung et al., 2023), and (Dang et al., 2022). However, few studies have used the LSTM model in stock price forecasting. Therefore, applying these tools to optimize and improve the predictability of stock quotes will have significant implications.

4. DATA AND RESEARCH METHODS

4.1. Research data

The article utilized a dataset of 5 stocks with the highest market capitalization in Vietnam's stock market from January 2018 to April 2023, consisting of 1322 samples. The dataset is available on the Vietstock website. Table 1 presents an overview of the 5 stocks, including two stocks in the banking sector, one in the construction and real estate sector, and one in the energy sector.

Table 1: Research data

Company	Stock ticker	Field of activity	Market capitalization (trillion VND)	Time	Number of observations
Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Foreign Trade of Vietnam	VCB	Financial services	319,444	2/1/2018-20/04/2023	1322
Vinhomes Joint Stock Company	VHM	Real estate	214,670	2/1/2018-20/04/2023	1322
Vingroup company	VIC	Construction and Real Estate	220,445	2/1/2018-20/04/2023	1322
Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Investment and Development of Vietnam	BID	Finance and Insurance	164,907	2/1/2018-20/04/2023	1322
Vietnam Gas Corporation	GAS	Distribution of natural gas	210,917	2/1/2018-20/04/2023	1322

Figure 1 reflects the price trends of 5 stocks from Jan 2018 to Apr 2023. Each stock has different fluctuations. In Apr 2020, the stock price dropped due to Covid impact, then increased in early 2022, and decreased again in early 2023.

Figure 1: Price of 5 stocks from 01/2018 to 04/2023

Figure 2 displays the trading volume of 5 stocks from January 2018 to April 2023. The data indicates that the trading volume reached its peak in 2018, followed by a sharp decline from 2019 to 2021. The trading volume then experienced a sudden increase in 2022 before finally decreasing again in 2023.

Figure 2: Trading volume of 5 stocks from 01/2018 to 04/2023

4.2. Research Methods

Overview of the research process

Forecasting method according to the ARIMA model

Start by using the Dickey-Fuller test to check if the time series is stationary. Since all of the P-values for the five stocks are more significant than 0.05, it can be concluded that the series is not stationary at the 5% significance level. Next, perform a "grid search" using different parameter combinations. Each set of parameters will fit a SARIMA model, and its quality will be evaluated. Finally, select the best ARIMA model for stock price forecasting.

Table 2: Test of stock price stoppage

Test		VCB	VHM	VIC	BID	GAS
Augmented Dickey-Fuller	Statistics ADF	-1.587	-2.899	-1.702	-2.207	-2.616
	Probability	0.490	0.045	0.430	0.20	0.09
Critical value	1%	-3.435	-3.435	3.435	3.435	3.435
	5%	-2.864	-2.864	2.864	2.864	2.864
	10%	-2.568	-2.568	-2.568	-2.568	-2.568

LSTM method

Extensive hyperparameter tuning was performed after training a general model to fit the LSTM model dynamically. The hyper-parametric search included batch size, the maximum number of epochs, learning rate, hidden layer size, number of stacked LSTM layers, and dropout status. These parameters were tested by selectively scaling a single parameter while fixing the others. Related parameters (such as learning rate and the maximum number of epochs) were considered together. Compared to the simple method, LSTM worked very well, and dropout rates significantly impacted the model's performance. Models performed better with less than four layers, and models with one layer had better results. The team tried different architectures that varied the number of layers and units in the layers until they got the best

possible MAPE, and the model chosen is a sequential model of layers, 3 LSTM layers, three dropouts, and one dense layer.

Table 3: Parameters of the LSTM

Model: "sequential"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
lstm (LSTM)	(None, 5, 200)	161600
lstm_1 (LSTM)	(None, 200)	320800
dense (Dense)	(None, 200)	40200
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 100)	20100
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 50)	5050
dense_3 (Dense)	(None, 5)	255

Total params: 548,005
 Trainable params: 548,005
 Non-trainable params: 0

Maintaining the order of observations when dividing training and test data is essential. Choose the first 90% of observations for training and testing, and reserve the remaining 10% for testing instead of random selection. The dataset has 1322 observations split into two parts. Part 1, which includes the first 1184 observations, is used to build the LSTM model. Part 2, which consists of the remaining 138 observations, is used to verify the accuracy of the LSTM model.

To calculate, authors normalized data in interval [0;1] using the MinMaxScaler method from the Sklearn library. Then, they created an LSTM model with 50 neurons and four hidden layers using the MSE function and Adam optimal iterative algorithm 1000 times.

Figure 3: Evaluation of model quality

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After testing stationarity in Section 4 with the Dickey-Fuller test, we use a "grid search" to determine ARIMA/SARIMA model parameters that fit and rate their overall quality. Table 2 presents the best ARIMA/SARIMA model for each stock. Using the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) evaluation criteria, GAS stock has the lowest standard deviation of balance (5.59), and VCB has the highest (13.22). We continue to use the MAPE evaluation criteria when applying the ARIMA/SARIMA model to each stock. Results indicate that GAS stock has the lowest predicted versus actual value (4.74%), and VCB stock has the highest (11.16%). Thus, the ARIMA/SARIMAX model provides accurate forecast results ranging from 88.94% to 95.26%.

Table 2: Forecasting and evaluation results according to the ARIMA/SARIMA model

Criteria	VCB	VHM	VIC	BID	GAS
1 ARIMA/ SARIMA	(0, 1, 0))	(0, 1, 0)	(3, 2, 3)	(0, 1, 0)	(0, 1, 0)
2 AIC	-5995.59	-6412.30	-6059.05	-5394.55	-5389.05
3 SIC	-5990.52	-6407.22	-6023.53	-5389.48	-5383.98
4 HQIC	-5993.68	6410.38	-6045.66	-5392.64	-5387.14
5 Loglikelihood	2998.80	3207.15	3036.53	2698.28	2695.53
6 RMSE	13.22	6.09	11.78	8.46	5.59
7 MAPE (%)	11.16	5.50	10.79	7.33	4.74

Section 1 analyzes and presents the efficiency of forecasting using the LSTM model to predict the price of 5 stocks. Table 3 shows that the LSTM outperforms the ARIMA/SARIMA model in short-term forecasting, with lower RMSE/MAPE values. The LSTM model performs best when RMSE and MAPE values are lower than the ARIMA/SARIMA model. The combined forecast has a 4.6% decrease in MAPE and a 6.2 decrease in RMSE compared to ARIMA.

Table 3: Comparison table of forecast results according to ARIMA and LSTM

Company	Ticker	Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)			Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE)		
		ARIMA	LSTM	Compare LSTM vs ARIMA	ARIMA	LSTM	Compare LSTM vs ARIMA
Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Foreign Trade of Vietnam	VCB	13.22	3.35	-9.87	11.2%	3.3%	-7.9%
Vinhomes Joint Stock Company	VHM	6.09	2.21	-3.88	5.5%	2.2%	-3.3%
Vingroup company	VIC	11.78	3.39	-8.39	10.8%	4.5%	-6.3%
Joint Stock Commercial Bank for Investment and Development of Vietnam	BID	8.46	2.19	-6.28	7.3%	4.4%	-2.9%
Vietnam Gas Corporation	GAS	5.59	3.03	-2.56	4.7%	2.1%	-2.7%
Medium		9.03	2.83	-6.20	7.9%	3.3%	-4.6%

Figure 3: Forecast results for 5 stocks

In Figure 3, the red line represents forecast values, the blue line represents actual values, and the orange line represents evaluated values. There is no significant difference between the actual and forecast values regarding trends. The forecast results for banking stocks (VCB, BID) tend to increase, while the stock prices of construction and real estate companies (VHM, VIC) and energy industry stocks (GAS) tend to decrease.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper examines the applicability of the ARIMA and deep learning models in stock price forecasting. We evaluate based on the five stocks with the largest capitalization from January 2018 to April 2023. The deviation between the actual and forecast values is 3.3%.

Forecasting models based solely on past time series data can yield near-accurate stock price forecasts. However, stock prices are also influenced by various factors, such as those in the money and real estate markets and investor sentiment. Furthermore, the ARIMA model's deviation in forecast value is caused by its consideration of only past volatility time series. Additionally, the stock price chain in the Vietnamese market is assessed as needing to reflect information that can affect the price entirely. The Vietnamese stock market's efficiency level is low, and its ability to reflect price information is still low, making forecasting errors inevitable, even when using different methods. While other forecasts like fundamental or technical analysis may be encountered, applying the deep learning method has produced accurate predictions. The average deviation between actual and forecast value is 3.3%, depending on the stocks, but the variation does not exceed 5%.

Investors must utilize reliable methods when forecasting stock prices to make informed decisions when buying or selling securities. The LSTM model has been proven to be highly accurate and dependable when predicting stock price movements. It is an essential tool for any investor looking to make intelligent and profitable investment decisions.

We must act to amplify the size of our data sets (e.g., stock markets, oil prices, gold prices, exchange rates) for further investigation or delve deeper into analyzing the SARIMA model, researching data seasonality, and exploring traditional machine learning models. We must discover a way to run the ARIMA model without sampling data due to computational limitations to make a more precise comparison between ARIMA and LSTM. Additionally, we need to conduct further research to fully comprehend the trends established by LSTM patterns. To prove the effectiveness of our proposed method, we will be testing the LSTM on various Vietnamese stocks.

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CUSTOMER LOYALTY TO THE BANK: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW AND SOME FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

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Abstract

This study analyzes previous research papers on the topic of customer loyalty to banks. The authors have selected 82 English-written studies in reliable journals between 2017 and 2023 from a variety of scientific data sources. The objective of this study is to investigate the factors affecting customer loyalty to the bank. From the obtained results, this study found that Customer Satisfaction, Service Quality, and Brand Image are mentioned the most in the research on customer loyalty to banks. Indonesia is the country with the most research on customer loyalty to banks, followed by India and Pakistan. More research should be carried out in developed countries. Finally, most of the research on customer loyalty to the bank is evaluated from the customer's perspectives. Future research should expand on other perspectives from banks, financial institutions, and the government, on factors affecting loyalty, as well as other issues related to the relationship between the customer and the bank in general.

Keywords: *bank industry, customer loyalty, bank service quality, customer satisfaction, systematic review.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Banks are financial institutions that play a vital role in the economic development of any country in the world (Zairani & Zaimah, 2013). Evolving from traditional activities such as payment, holding and lending, the banking industry nowadays is undergoing rapid changes thanks to advances in science and technology (Lone et al., 2016). In any industry, maintaining the trust of customers and establishing a long-term relationship with them is very important. According to Omoregie et al. (2019), customer loyalty is defined as an individual's commitment to an organization or repeat use of an organization's products or services. It can be considered that customer loyalty is an intimate link to organizational success, profitability and business performance (Oliver, 1997; Sheth & Parvatiyar, 1995). In the banking industry, customer retention is a radical and necessary approach to ensuring long-term profit gain (Reichheld, 1993). For that reason, understanding the importance of customer loyalty in banks is extremely necessary (Leninkumar, 2017). Loyal customers not only continue to buy but also refer the products to others, whether intentionally or unintentionally (Gioi & Huy, 2012). Besides, customers who demonstrate a high level of loyalty to a product or service tend to

repurchase more often and spend more money (Yi & Jeon, 2003). Therefore, the issue of customer loyalty to banking services has been receiving the attention of researchers around the world (Chien, 2021).

With the advent and development of digital technology, the race between banks in finding and retaining customers is becoming more competitive than ever (Quan, 2020). According to the Payment Department of the State Bank of Vietnam in 2021, 95% of banks in Vietnam have been implementing digital transformation, and there are currently 30 million people using the Internet banking payment system every day. The growth rate of transactions on Mobile Banking in Vietnam is 200%. In 2023, the State Bank of Vietnam announced some impressive numbers about banking development in the digital age as follows. In the first 3 months of 2023, the total number of transactions through the interbank electronic payment system increased by 8.55% in value. By the end of March 2023, the number of ATMs in the whole market reached 21,347. Besides, many banks have more than 90% of customer transactions done on digital channels, and about 74.63% of adults in Vietnam already have a bank account. In that context, it is extremely important to develop banking services that satisfy customers, thereby increasing their retention rate and loyalty of them to the bank brand (Erdoğan & Ergun, 2016; Oliver, 1997; Reichheld, 1993; Sheth & Parvatiyar, 1995). It can be stated that "customer" is the key for the bank to survive and develop (Quynh, 2020). Thereby, more research on customer loyalty to banks should be implemented so that bank managers can identify the improvement directions in the future.

In general, many models have been used when studying the area of customer loyalty to the bank brand. The most popular is the appearance of the SERVQUAL Parasuraman (1985) model in many related studies (Manik, 2019; Haron et al., 2020; Fida et al., 2020). This model has been developed and extended to suit the banking context. For example, based on the SERVQUAL model, Yilmaz et al. (2017) showed service quality in the banking industry is measured through the following 5 factors: Assurance, Responsiveness, Reliability, Tangibles and Accessibility. Some other theories are also often applied in research papers, such as the Attitude Theory of Bagozzi (1992) or the Theory of Reasoned Action by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975). Although there are studies that have been able to apply models and theories such as the research by Haron et al. (2020), most of the studies in this field have not applied many theories when analyzing. Some studies use the SERVQUAL model but only conducted in the territory of a country or only focused on a specific type of bank, such as the study of Ahmad, Naheed & Shahid (2021); Mulia, Usman & Parwanto (2021). This opens up many research gaps for future research.

The purpose of this study is to find and fill the research gap compared with previous studies by presenting and evaluating the current research on the factors affecting the loyalty of customers to the bank. The results of the study can be used by researchers to better understand the topic of customer loyalty, especially in today's banking sector. Furthermore, this study provides valuable information regarding customer loyalty to all stakeholders, including factors affecting customer loyalty, countries conducted research, the factors used in the theoretical model, and the perspective of the study.

The structure of the research paper consists of 5 parts: (1) Introduction, (2) Research Methods, (3) Research Overview, (4) Research gaps and future research directions and (5) Conclusion.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1. Concept of customer loyalty

In the field of marketing management and behavioral psychology, customer loyalty is an important concept. When customers become loyal to a brand, they have less reason to seek out information about how to replace the product or service, or to look for another brand. Currently, brand loyalty is considered in three ways: (1) Loyal behavior; (2) Loyal attitude; (3) The combination of both behavioral and behavioral loyalty (Ganesh et al., 2000) According to Ishak and Abd Ghani (2013), understanding behavioral loyalty is the discovery of customers' random consumption behaviors, thereby measuring the correlation with brand loyalty. Meanwhile, research by Kumar and Reinartz (2018) shows that attitude loyalty includes customers' perceptions and attitudes toward a specific product or service. Combining the two factors of behavior and attitude, loyal customers are customers who often continue to make purchases from a particular supplier, have a positive attitude towards the supplier, and consider the supplier when there is a need to use the service (Caruana, 2002).

Research in the banking sector shows that customer loyalty to the bank is demonstrated through a strong commitment, and willingness to continue to choose to use their product or service for a long time (Tweneboah-Koduah & Farley, 2016). Commitment in loyalty is what distinguishes a loyal customer to the repeat buying behavior of normal customers due to inertia (Jacoby & Chestnut, 1978). Meanwhile, according to Oliver (2010), customer loyalty is defined as a deep commitment to repurchase a product or service in the future, thereby fostering a pattern of repetitive usage of the supplier's services. It typically implies a long-term relationship where the customer consistently chooses to conduct their financial transactions, open accounts, and seek financial solutions from that particular bank due to a positive overall experience, trust, satisfaction, and perceived value.

Delving specifically into the arena of the banking sector, customer loyalty to a bank denotes a robust commitment and an enduring willingness to persistently select and utilize the bank's offerings over an extended temporal horizon. In a broader sense, customer loyalty to the bank constitutes a pivotal concept within the domains of marketing management and behavioral psychology. It embodies the profound connection and steadfast allegiance that customers cultivate toward a particular brand or service provider. This loyalty encompasses essential dimensions, notably loyal behavior, loyal attitude, and the amalgamation of both behavioral and attitudinal loyalty. Loyal customers are those who consistently engage in recurrent purchases from a specific supplier, maintain a favorable perception of the brand, and regard the supplier as their preferred choice when the need for the product or service arises.

2.2. The role of customer loyalty

Today, customer loyalty plays an important role in the development of the banking industry in general and the operation of each bank in particular. Owning loyal customers will

help businesses cut marketing costs as well as stay ahead in price competition because loyal customers are willing to pay higher prices for brands they trust (Reichheld, 1996). Therefore, it can be seen that customer loyalty is considered to be closely linked to organizational success, profitability, and business performance (Oliver, 1997; Reichheld, 1993; Sheth & Parvatiyar, 1995). In addition, acquiring new customers costs five times more than retaining existing customers (McLlory & Barnet, 2000). Hence, it can be seen that loyal customers not only increase the value of a business, but also help businesses maintain lower costs than attracting new customers (Barroso & Martin, 1999). Building customer loyalty should be seen as an essential business strategy of enterprises in general (Duffy, 1998). As customers are the key to the bank's survival and development (Quynh, 2020), the more the bank wins the loyalty of its customers, the more favorable opportunities it will have for growth. In overall, a company with strong customer loyalty enjoys numerous advantages including the ability to increase negotiating power, lower cost in customer attraction, maintain premium pricing, and create a strong barrier to potential new competitors of the same category (Reichfeld, 1996). That is why nowadays the customer-centric business strategy has become an important priority of the bank.

2.3. Measuring customer loyalty

Nowadays, banks have employed various metrics and key performance indicators to effectively measure customer loyalty. It is necessary to measure the loyalty of customers to analyze the effectiveness of bank strategies in retaining customers, and to make suitable adjustments in time. There are several common methods to measure customer loyalty and their significance in today's competitive market.

The Customer Retention Rate (CRR) stands as a fundamental metric in measuring customer loyalty (Tessitore, 2023). It quantifies the percentage of customers a business successfully retains over a specific time frame (Griffin, 1995). Researches show that the CRR metric directly correlates with customer loyalty and business profitability (Almohaimmeed, 2019; Nasir, 2017). In addition, customer loyalty programs have been proved to have a positive impact on increasing the retention rate (Magatef & Tomalieh, 2015; Lewis, 2004). Hence, analyzing customer loyalty through this index is efficient. However, it is crucial to complement the CRR with deeper customer experience metrics, to understand why customers remain loyal. The Net Promoter Score (NPS) provides a standardized and easily comparable measure of customer loyalty (Balan, 2012). It categorizes customers into promoters, passives, and detractors based on their likelihood to recommend the business to others. Customers are asked to rate their likelihood to recommend on a scale of 0-10, with different score ranges indicating varying levels of loyalty (Cornell, 2023). Research by Schneider et al. showed that improving the NPS score has a positive relationship with customer loyalty and satisfaction. In contrast, customer loyalty and satisfaction also influence the NPS score (Srirahayu et al., 2021). In short, the NPS score allows businesses to assess their performance in relation to others in the industry, which provides insights into the depth of customer loyalty.

Furthermore, to measure the level of customer loyalty and provide insights into customer behavior, Repeat Purchase Rate was applied as a means for measuring customer loyalty (Zephaniah et al, 2020). The Repeat Purchase Rate measures the percentage of customers

making repeat purchases in relation to the total number of paying customers. Monitoring this rate helps gauge the level of customer loyalty and provides insights into customer behavior over time. It reveals whether customers are satisfied and willing to continue their engagement and customer loyalty with the brand. Jasek et al. (2018) undertook a study using Upsell Rate to measure how many customers make additional, often higher-value purchases beyond their initial intent. A higher upsell rate signifies customer trust in the brand and their willingness to explore new products or services. This metric is a valuable indicator of customer loyalty, as loyal customers are more likely to engage in upselling opportunities. It reflects a deeper commitment to the brand beyond basic transactions. Khairawati, S. (2020) found another indicator of measuring loyalty called the Customer Lifetime Value (CLV). It calculates the expected profit from an average customer throughout the entire business relationship. Businesses with loyal customers tend to have higher CLVs. This metric considers various factors, including the average sale value, the number of transactions, and the average customer retention period. CLV provides a comprehensive view of customer loyalty by quantifying the long-term value of customer relationships. It underscores the importance of retaining customers over time for sustained business growth.

Measuring customer loyalty is indispensable for businesses striving for success in a competitive landscape. The metrics discussed, including CRR, NPS, Repeat Purchase Rate, Upsell Rate, and CLV, offer valuable insights into customer behavior and customer loyalty. By employing a combination of these metrics, businesses can gain a deeper understanding of their customers, make data-driven decisions, and formulate strategies to enhance loyalty. Ultimately, this leads to sustainable growth and success in the market.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The authors systematically review previous academic research. The study uses qualitative and quantitative research methods to assess the factors affecting bank loyalty, research methods, and theories used in previous publications.

3.1. Research process

This study followed several academic analysis steps as follows. The first step begins with defining the research question, followed by identifying the data sources of previous studies. This study used recently published articles in reliable online databases such as (1) Emerald Insight, (2) Science Direct, (3) Google Scholar, (4) Wiley Interscience and (5) ProQuest. In order to collect relevant articles for use in research, the author defines some criteria as follows. Only articles in English published in reputable journals between 2017 and 2023 were considered in this study. This study found 128 researches related to keywords. After carefully reading the collected articles and removing duplicates, the author obtained 82 articles for use in this study.

3.2. Research scope

All research papers were selected by the author based on the following criteria:

First, the research paper must include some of the following keywords: "customer

loyalty", "banking services", "intention to use banking services again", "loyalty to the banking brand" and "intention to use banking services".

Second, selected international articles must be published in reputable journals, which are evaluated by experts to ensure the quality and reliability of research results. For studies conducted in Vietnam, the search scope is expanded when the authors also review studies published in lesser-known journals to find suitable research.

3.3. Evaluation methods

The authors conducted the research based on 82 articles published between 2017 and 2023. After the process of searching and selecting suitable studies, the studies were synthesized and classified. After the process of searching and selecting relevant studies, the studies were synthesized and classified. Firstly, this research lists several highly-cited papers in this field. Then, this study identifies the nation in which research studies were conducted. Additionally, the author has identified and presented some important factors affecting customer loyalty to banking services. The authors evaluated the results after collecting data from previous studies and using supporting tools. From there, recognize the problem and scope mentioned in related works, pointing out the research gaps of previous studies, and proposing some research directions in the specific context of Vietnam.

4. FINDINGS

4.1. Geographical characteristics of papers

The authors allocated 82 research papers according to the geographical features where they were published, the analytical data of which are listed in Table 1. From the data, we found that 28 countries were named. In particular, Indonesia is the country with the most studies with 19 studies accounting for 23.17%, followed by India with 8 studies accounting for 9.75% and Pakistan with 6 studies accounting for 7.32% of the studies statistics. These are all populous countries with relatively large Muslim populations.

In addition, the remaining 25 countries in the table were also mentioned by the authors with 1-5 research papers including Malaysia, China, Ghana, Turkey, Vietnam, Brazil, Zimbabwe, Jordan, Nigeria, Spain, Japan, Oman, Tehran, Palestine, Zimbabwe, Iran, Afghanistan, Basquel, Botswana, Sri Lanka, UK, Netherlands, South Africa, UAE, Romania, Kuwait. From the data, we found that much of the research on the topic of customer loyalty to banks was published by Muslim or Muslim - majority countries where banking and financial institutions are thriving. According to the 2022 "World Muslim Population Map" report released by the Pew Forum on Religion & Public Life, in 2022 about 1.9 billion people in the world practice Islam, accounting for about 25% of the world's population (8 billion people). Thus, it can be inferred that customer loyalty to banks is an important research topic that many people are interested in, the results of these studies are a premise to help banks retain target customers as well as increase competitive advantage in the new context.

Table 1: Geographical Characteristics of Papers

Country	Frequency	Studies
Indonesia	19	Tabrani et al. (2018); Laksamana, P. (2018); Supriyanto et al. (2021); Muflih, M. (2021); Kusumawati et al. (2020); Manik, A. F. I. (2019); Romdonny et al. (2019); Sewaka et al. (2021); Mulia et al. (2021); Semadi et al. (2018); Abror et al. (2020); Aisyah, M. (2018); Suhartanto et al. (2018); Dwidienawati et al. (2022); Diputra, I. G. A. W., & Yasa, N. N. (2021); Wahyuni et al. (2017); Mujahidin et al. (2022); Sasono et al. (2021); Darmawan, D. (2018).
India	8	Shankar et al. (2019); Mukerjee, K. (2018); Goyal et al. (2017); Bhat et al. (2018); Chauhan et al. (2022); Bapat, D. (2017); Prasad, R. R. (2018); PRASADH, R. R., & Arun, C. J. O. E. (2019)
Pakistan	6	Ahmad, S. et al. (2021); Raza et al. (2020); Gill et al. (2021); Shahid Iqbal et al. (2018); Raza, S. A., Umer, A., Qureshi, M. A., & Dahri, A. S. (2020); Ahmed, R. R. et al. (2021)
Malaysia	5	Tegambwage, A. G., & Kasoga, P. S. (2022); Haron et al. (2020); Khokhar et al. (2019); Khan et al. (2022); Rivaldo, Y., Kamanda, S. V., & Yusman, E. (2022)
China	5	Li et al. (2021); Zhou et al. (2021); Sun et al. (2020); YuSheng et al. (2019); Islam et al. (2021)
Ghana	5	Omoriegie et al (2019); Ofosu et al. (2020); Kosiba et al. (2018); Famiyeh et al. (2018); Mahmoud, M. A. (2019)
Turkey	4	Özkan et al. (2020); Garanti et al. (2020); Yilmaz et al. (2018); Bilgin, Y. (2018)
Vietnam	4	Quang, N. N., Thuy, D. C., & Nhung, T. H. (2022); Dam et al. (2021); Chien, N. D. (2021); Nguyen et al. (2020);
Brazil	4	Cardoso et al. (2022); Mainardes et al. (2020); Galvão et al. (2018); Milan et al. (2018)
Zimbabwe	2	Manyanga et al. (2022); Chikazhe et al. (2020)
Jordan	2	Khraiwish et al. (2022); Al-Hawary et al. (2017)
Nigeria	2	Zephaniah et al. (2020); Osakwe, C. N., & Yusuf, T. O. (2021)
Others	16	Monferrer et al. (2019); Hayati et al. (2020); Fida et al. (2020); Hosseini et al. (2021); Makudza et al. (2020); Hasiri et al. (2017); Alnaser, F., Ghani, M., & Rahi, S. (2018); Aramburu et al. (2019); Chiguvi et al. (2019); Leninkumar, V. (2017); Foroudi et al. (2018); Jenneboer et al. (2022); Redda, E. H. (2023); Sleimi, M., Musleh, M., & Qubbaj, I. (2020); Mujahidin et al. (2022); Aldaihani, F. M. F., & Ali, N. A. B. (2019).

Source: Compiled by the author group

4.2. Highly-cited Articles

Table 2 presented some highly cited research on the topic of customer loyalty. The most cited study was published in the International Journal of Bank Marketing, written by Shankar,

A., & Jebarajakirthy, C. (2019) with 337 citations. Overall, all of the studies listed in Table 2 had 210 citations or more and were last published in 2020. This proves that customer loyalty is not simply a basic concept but also has a great influence on the effectiveness of marketing and business strategies, attracting the attention of many researchers around the world. These customer loyalty studies not only provide a solid basis to help banks orient business campaigns but also propose solutions to help financial institutions retain customers as well as increase market share in the current digital transformation context.

Table 2: Highly-cited Articles

Paper's Name	Authors	Publication	Cited Frequency
The influence of e-banking service quality on customer loyalty: A moderated mediation approach	Shankar, A., & Jebarajakirthy, C. (2019)	International Journal of Bank Marketing	337
Internet banking service quality, e-customer satisfaction and loyalty: the modified e-SERVQUAL model	Syed Ali Raza, Amna Umer, Muhammad Asif Qureshi, & Abdul Samad Dahri (2020)	The TQM Journal	321
Impact of service quality on customer loyalty and customer satisfaction in Islamic banks in the Sultanate of Oman	Bashir Ahmad Fida, Umar Ahmed, Yousuf Al-Balushi, & Dharmendra Singh (2020)	Sage Open	301
Trust, commitment, customer intimacy and customer loyalty in Islamic banking relationships	Mirza Tabrani, Muslim Amin, & Ahmad Nizam (2018)	International Journal of Bank Marketing	275
Impact of social media marketing on purchase intention and brand loyalty: Evidence from Indonesia's banking industry	Patria Laksamana (2018)	International Review of Management and Marketing	243
The effects of corporate social responsibility on customer loyalty: The mediating effect of reputation in cooperative banks versus commercial banks in the Basque country	Izaskun Agirre Aramburu & Irune Gómez Pescador (2019)	Journal of business ethics	210

Source: Compiled by the author group

4.3. Theories Utilized

In Table 3, we listed the theories used in 82 research papers. The results show that the SERVQUAL model, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), and Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Extended (UTAUT) or extended version are still the most used theories in customer loyalty studies for banks. The popularity of the SERVQUAL model

in scientific research is explained by its comprehensiveness, reliability, ease of use, and ability to measure service quality helps banks better understand what factors need to be improved to meet customer expectations, thereby enhancing loyalty.

In particular, the appearance of two models TAM and UTAUT ranked 2nd and 3rd on the list also shows the trend of customer loyalty research associated with the digital transformation era, and also demonstrates the development of the banking industry in the world when promoting investment in digital banks with quick online transactions, more convenient. Conversely, statistics also show that some of the least popular theories include Social Identity Theory (SIT), Stakeholder Theory, Structural Equation Modeling, Self-Congruity Theory, Cognitive Motivational Relationship Theory (CMR), Theory of Reasoned Action, Equity Theory, Attitude Theory, Expectations Theory (ECT), Aaker's Conceptual Model, The Trait Hierarchical Model, Stimulation Level Theory, Structural Equation Modeling, The Service Profit Chain Model. In which many models appear only one time such as: Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA); SERVPERF model; Social Identity Theory (SIT); Structural Equation Modeling; Self-Congruity Theory; Cognitive Motivational Relationship Theory (CMR); Theory of Reasoned Action; Equity Theory; Attitude Theory; Expectations Theory (ECT); The Trait Hierarchical Model; Stimulation Level Theory; Structural Equation Modeling; The Service Profit Chain Model; S-O-R Model; E-S-QUAL; Attribution; RATER model; Social Script Theory; e-SERQUAL.

Table 3: Theories Utilized

Theory	Frequency	Studies
SERVQUAL model	12	Khraiwish et al. (2022); Alnaser et al. (2017); Goyal et al. (2017); Haron et al. (2020); Manik, A. F. I. (2019); Özkan et al. (2020); Yilmaz et al. (2018); Galvão et al. (2018); PRASADH, R. R., & Arun, C. J. O. E. (2019); Redda, E. H. (2023); Rivaldo, Y., Kamanda, S. V., & Yusman, E. (2022); Fida et al. (2020)
Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)	6	Ahmad et al. (2021); Mulia et al. (2021); Nguyen et al. (2020); Jenneboer et al. (2022); Bapat, D. (2017); Al-Hawary et al. (2017)
Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Extended (UTAUT)	3	Zhou et al. (2021); Nguyen et al. (2020); Jenneboer et al. (2022)
SEM	3	Wahyuni et al. (2017); Prasad, R. R. (2018); Quang, N. N., Thuy, D. C., & Nhung, T. H. (2022)
PAKSERV model	2	Alnaser, F., Ghani, M., & Rahi, S. (2018); Haron et al. (2020)
Stakeholder Theory	2	Raza et al. (2020); Muflih, M. (2021)
Aaker's Conceptual Model	2	Cardoso et al. (2022); Chiguvu et al. (2019)

Source: Compiled by the author group

4.4. Factors affecting individual customer loyalty to the bank

Table 4 lists 49 factors that affect customer loyalty to banks. In particular, the 3 most researched factors are Customer satisfaction, Service quality, Trust, and Brand Image. The Customer Satisfaction factor appeared in 42 out of 82 studies demonstrating a strong relationship between the independent variable Customer satisfaction and the dependent variable Customer loyalty in the majority of studies on the same topic. The more satisfied customers feel, the more likely they are to return, which in turn forms customer loyalty (Muflih, 2021). Meanwhile, studies conducted by Dam et al. (2021) and Supriyanto et al. (2021) conclude that good service quality is a prerequisite for boosting customer satisfaction and loyalty. In addition, the authors also recognize a diverse system of other factors such as Trust, Brand Awareness, Corporate Reputation, Customer Experience, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), and Reliability... mentioned in research papers around the world.

However, contrary to the abovementioned factors, some have not been considered much at this stage. Typically, demographic factors such as Income, Educational Qualifications, and Age were only considered in 2 studies, similar to factors such as Word-of-mouth Intention, Customer Self-brand Connection, Customer Emotion, Perceived Usefulness, Personalization, Customer Intimacy, Affective Commitment, Switching Costs and Ambiance. Finally, Some other variables appear once in the studies such as: Customer Knowledge Management; Perceived Risk; Economic Cost; Sincerity; Branch Market Orientation; Personal Selling Tactics; Perceived Fluency On Attitudinal Loyalty; Virtual Environment Management; Trustworthiness; Co-creation; Customer Relationship Management (CRM); Service Innovation (SI); Self-Service Technology (SST); Brand Bond; Branch Service Quality Evaluations; Perceived Ease of Alternate Channels; Ease of Use; Accessibility; Relationship Marketing, which opens up a gap that needs to be filled by future studies.

Table 4: Factors Influencing Customer Loyalty To The Bank

Factors	Frequency	Studies
Customer Satisfaction	43	Manyanga et al. (2020); Dam et al. (2021); Supriyanto et al.(2021); Monferreret al. (2019); Chien, N. Đ. (2021); Tegambwage, A. G., & Kasoga, P. S. (2022); Alnaser et al. (2017); Goyal et al. (2017); Muflih, M. (2021); Haron et al. (2020); Kusumawati et al. (2020); Manik, A. F. I. (2019); Khokhar et al. (2019); Omoregie et al (2019); Sewaka et al. (2021); Bhat et al. (2018); Hosseini et al. (2021); Cardoso et al. (2022); Hayati et al. (2020); Chiguvi et al. (2019); Ofofu et al. (2020); Leninkumar, V. (2017); Abror et al. (2020); Nguyen et al. (2020); Özkan et al. (2020); Yilmaz et al. (2018); YuSheng et al. (2019); Aisyah, M. (2018); Dwidienawati et al. (2022); Shahid Iqbal et al. (2018); Diputra, I. G. A. W., & Yasa, N. N. (2021); Islam et al. (2021); Jenneboer et al. (2022); Famiyeh et al. (2018); Bapat, D. (2017); PRASADH, R. R., & Arun, C. J. O. E. (2019); Redda, E. H. (2023); Sleimi, M., Musleh, M., & Qubbaj, I. (2020); Prasad, R. R. (2018); Ahmed et al. (2021); Amna et al. (2020); Fida et al. (2020); Quang, N. N., Thuy, D. C., & Nhung, T. H. (2022)

Factors	Frequency	Studies
Service Quality	31	Dam et al. (2021); Supriyanto et al.(2021); Chien, N. Đ. (2021); Tegambwage, A. G., & Kasoga, P. S. (2022); Alnaser et al. (2017); Goyal et al. (2017); Kusumawati et al. (2020); Manik, A. F. I. (2019); Khokhar et al. (2019); Omoregie et al (2019); Romdonny et al. (2019); Sewaka et al. (2021); Cardoso et al. (2022); Zhou et al. (2021); Abror et al. (2020); Famiyeh et al. (2018); Nguyen et al. (2020); Özkan et al. (2020); YuSheng et al. (2019); Aisyah, M. (2018); Dwidienawati et al. (2022); Shahid Iqbal et al. (2018); Diputra, I. G. A. W., & Yasa, N. N. (2021); PRASADH, R. R., & Arun, C. J. O. E. (2019); Redda, E. H. (2023); Sleimi, M., Musleh, M., & Qubbaj, I. (2020); Prasad, R. R. (2018); Ahmed et al. (2021); Amna et al. (2020); Fida et al. (2020); Quang, N. N., Thuy, D. C., & Nhung, T. H. (2022)
Brand Image	20	Dam et al. (2021); Chien, N. Đ. (2021); Alnaser et al. (2017); Muflih, M. (2021); Manik, A. F. I. (2019); Khokhar et al. (2019); Omoregie et al (2019); Romdonny et al. (2019); Cardoso et al. (2022); Hayati et al. (2020); Semadi et al. (2018); Omoregie et al. (2019); Garanti et al. (2020); Yilmaz et al. (2018); Raza et al.(2020); Suhartanto et al. (2018); Bilgin, Y. (2018); Diputra, I. G. A. W., & Yasa, N. N. (2021); Foroudi et al. (2018); Rivaldo, Y., Kamanda, S. V., & Yusman, E. (2022)
Trust	19	Gill et al. (2021); Chien, N. Đ. (2021); Muflih, M. (2021); Haron et al. (2020); Khokhar et al. (2019); Omoregie et al (2019); Mulia et al. (2021); Bhat et al. (2018); Cardoso et al. (2022); Semadi et al. (2018); Leninkumar, V. (2017); Suhartanto et al. (2018); Islam et al. (2021); Jenneboer et al. (2022); Osakwe, C. N., & Yusuf, T. O. (2021); Rivaldo, Y., Kamanda, S. V., & Yusman, E. (2022); Mahmoud, M. A. (2019); Tabrani et al. (2018); Aldaihani, F. M. F., & Ali, N. A. B. (2019).
Corporate Reputation,	12	Chikazhe et al. (2020); Muflih, M. (2021); Hayati et al. (2020); Supriyanto et al. (2021); Manyanga et al. (2022); Özkan et al. (2020); Khan et al. (2022); Islam et al. (2021); Osakwe, C. N., & Yusuf, T. O. (2021); Aramburu et al. (2019); Quang, N. N., Thuy, D. C., & Nhung, T. H. (2022); Milan et al. (2018)
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)	11	Raza et al. (2020); Goyal et al. (2017); Muflih, M. (2021); Sun et al. (2020); Raza et al.(2020); Dwidienawati et al. (2022); Islam et al. (2021); Osakwe, C. N., & Yusuf, T. O. (2021); Mujahidin et al. (2022); Aramburu et al. (2019); Quang, N. N., Thuy, D. C., & Nhung, T. H. (2022)
Brand Awareness	8	Chikazhe et al. (2020); Semadi et al. (2018); Manyanga et al. (2022); Garanti et al. (2020); Galvão et al. (2018); Bilgin, Y. (2018); Diputra, I. G. A. W., & Yasa, N. N. (2021); Foroudi et al. (2018)
Reliability	8	Ahmad et al. (2021); Gill et al. (2021); Haron et al. (2020);

Factors	Frequency	Studies
		Cardoso et al. (2022); Nguyen et al. (2020); Yilmaz et al. (2018); Famiyeh et al. (2018); Mahmoud, M. A. (2019)
Customer Experience	7	Hosseini et al. (2021); Cardoso et al. (2022); Semadi et al. (2018); Manyanga et al. (2022); Mainardes et al. (2020); Shahid Iqbal et al. (2018); Chauhan et al. (2022)
Website design	7	Ahmad et al. (2021); Gill et al. (2021); Zhou et al. (2021); Jenneboer et al. (2022); Mahmoud, M. A. (2019); Amna et al. (2020); Al-Hawary et al. (2017)
Customer Perceived Value	6	Kusumawati et al. (2020); Omoregie et al. (2019); Özkan et al. (2020); Foroudi et al. (2018); Prasad, R. R. (2018); Milan et al. (2018)
Customer Engagement	5	Monferrer et al. (2019); Hayati et al. (2020); Abror et al. (2020); Kosiba et al. (2018); Shahid Iqbal et al. (2018)
Assurance	3	Haron et al. (2020); Zhou et al. (2021); Famiyeh et al. (2018)
Sales Promotional Activities	3	Zephaniah et al. (2020); Ofosu et al. (2020); Rivaldo, Y., Kamanda, S. V., & Yusman, E. (2022)
Security	3	Ahmad et al. (2021); Zhou et al. (2021); Al-Hawary et al. (2017)
Social Media Brand Personality	3	Garanti et al. (2020); Bilgin, Y. (2018); Wahyuni et al. (2017)
Religiosity	3	Abror et al. (2020); Suhartanto et al. (2018); Wahyuni et al. (2017)
Affective Commitment	3	Khraiwish et al. (2022); Tabrani et al. (2018); Aldaihani, F. M. F., & Ali, N. A. B. (2019).

Source: Compiled by the author group

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Research gaps

The authors found a number of research gaps after evaluating 82 articles on bank loyalty published in the period 2017 - 2023 as follows:

First, there remain limitations related to the application of theories and analytical methods in the field of research on banking and customer loyalty. Although the number of studies conducted increased, many are not able to use advanced theories in the data analysis process. Most of the studies still use traditional theories such as Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT), Theory of Rational Action (TRA), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and other generally accepted models such as SERVQUAL. Although these theories have proven to be valuable in assessing customer loyalty and behavior, they have not been able to fully explain the complexity and change of interacting behavior with banks over time. In addition, most of the studies used cross-sectional data. Furthermore, most studies still use the cross-sectional data collection method, which collects data at a specific point in time. This makes the study unable to assess the change in customer perception and behavior about the bank over time.

Especially in the context that banks are going through great innovations in the digital transformation process.

Second, the sample size, demographic diversity and survey scope in a range of research are limited. Many studies have a relatively small survey sample size compared to the total number of customers. This may compromise the accuracy and reliability of the research results, as the small sample may not be representative of the diverse customer population in the bank. Regarding the scope of the survey, most of the studies are limited to one territory, and were conducted in Asian countries, while in Western countries, the number of studies on bank loyalty is very low. They limit understanding of the situation and customer behavior in Western markets. In addition, the samples are limited to certain demographic groups, as many studies have data collected mostly in large cities, or limited to a few banks or participants that share cultural homogeneity, so it is not possible to represent the entire market. In research, if the data focuses only on a few specific groups, the characteristics and behaviors of other customer groups may be neglected, causing errors in understanding and properly meeting the needs of all customers.

Third, factors affecting bank loyalty have not been fully evaluated. There remains an excess of research only analyzing the relationship between service quality, brand image, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. While these are important factors, they do not represent the full spectrum of customer loyalty. Many other factors can also be considered such as Social Responsibility, Customer Commitment, E-services quality, Marketing Impression, etc. Bank's commitment to social responsibility can have a strong influence on customer loyalty, when customers feel satisfied with accompanying the bank in promoting values beyond personal interests. In the digital age, convenience and demand satisfaction when using banking e-services are becoming decisive factors in determining customer loyalty. Also, the influence of marketing media on customer loyalty cannot be ignored, because by building a positive brand image through communications, customers can form long-term companionship with the bank. Although there is limited research on these factors, reputable journals such as Journal of Retailing and Consumer, and the Journal of Data and Network Science have published articles related to these new factors and contributes to expanding understanding and knowledge of customer loyalty.

Fourth, researchers have not yet made recommendations for the government in orienting the development and reviewing of the legal frameworks for banks and financial institutions to enhance customer loyalty. Although the government plays an important role in monitoring, directing, and ensuring the efficient operation of banks, there are lack of specific suggestions from published research for this institution. One of the difficulties is due to the complexity and diversity of the banking industry in terms of type and scope of activities, leading to large differences in customer needs and requirements as well as management and government supervision. Furthermore, new financial technologies such as fintech, artificial intelligence, and blockchain have changed the way banks operate and provide services. This requires the government to adjust and update its legal and regulatory frameworks to accommodate new trends and ensure fair competition among financial service providers. In order to make recommendations to the government, it is necessary to continue to research and explore current

difficulties and limitations. In general, the recommendations of the studies so far are limited to the operational management and customer service aspects of individual banks.

5.2. Orientation for future research

Based on the limitations of the reviewed research and research recommendations from previous studies, the authors make the following recommendations for future research directions:

First, studies need to be measured by more comprehensive and developed models to be relevant to the banking industry. Researchers can compare the differences between banking models, as well as before and after digital transformation, thereby providing solutions to build a comprehensive banking system and retain customers in the context new. Besides, longitudinal research will better assess and identify the attitudinal components of the loyalty dimensions over time, as well as their variations. This is important to better understand the mindset and behavior of customers, thereby recommending suitable measures to adjust and optimize service quality to maintain and increase customer loyalty. In addition, researchers need to conduct a variety of research methods, including online surveys, personal interviews, and big data analysis. Combining multiple data sources and approaches will help create a rich and comprehensive overview of customer loyalty in the banking industry.

Second, increasing the sample size, and survey scope, and assessing participants of different demographic characteristics will enhance the representativeness of the study. In addition, more research should be conducted in areas of cultural heterogeneity and developed countries. This will help to better understand the cultural differences and mindsets of users in different countries, thereby making recommendations and strategies tailored to each country or region. Similar studies can be conducted to compare factors affecting bank loyalty among different demographic groups: gender, age, income, employment and religion. From there, the author can compare the factors affecting the loyalty to the bank of these target groups to clarify the difference to give more in-depth recommendations for the bank. Such studies will provide useful insights for banks to design customer-centric strategies to target specific customer groups.

Third, future researchers can consider additional factors affecting loyalty that have not been evaluated much in previous studies. Some of the factors including Customer Experience, Commitment, Service Innovation, Reliability and Quality of Marketing can be added to the research model. By analyzing the relationship between customer experience and marketing with customer loyalty, businesses can optimize their sales and marketing strategies to customer loyalty and build long-term relationships. To date, studies on these factors are still limited in number. Most studies also consider a few influencing factors individually, but not combine many factors and evaluate them by comprehensive model. Researchers should continue to explore and expand the scope of research on factors affecting loyalty to provide a more accurate and overview perspective, helping banks better understand how to build sustainable and long-term relationships with customers. Besides, many studies consider satisfaction as a mediating factor, so more studies can be conducted to study the direct relationship between influencing factors and loyalty.

Fourth, in the future, there should be more research on other issues related to the relationship between customers and banks, instead of just focusing on customer loyalty. Studies can be extended to delve deeper into other aspects of the customer-banking relationship, such as the study of factors affecting customer satisfaction, the importance of specific financial services, or the influence of communication strategies on the decision to use banking services. Besides, later studies can measure the pattern in other areas such as hospitals, and other financial institutions such as investment funds with the stated censor and intermediate variables. Finally, in the context of digital transformation, it is necessary to have further studies on e-banking with new influencing factors. Researchers were able to measure the ease of use and effectiveness of e-banking platforms, as well as the influence of web and app interfaces on customer experience and trust. These insights can assist the bank in improving the customer experience and creating more efficient service solutions in the future.

5.3. Conclusion

Digital transformation in the banking sector is an inevitable trend, a strategic direction to help the banking industry compete effectively and develop sustainably in the 4.0 era in order to improve the loyalty of individual customers to the bank. Through the analysis of 82 domestic and international research articles on factors affecting customer loyalty to banks from 2017 to 2023, the authors have listed a number of highly reliable articles in this field. In addition, the geographical characteristics of the studies were also determined.

Besides, this study has synthesized the theories and influencing factors considered in the studies on customer loyalty to the bank. From there, the study shows the general trend in building research models of authors in this field from 2017 to 2023. Finally, based on the process of synthesizing and analyzing previous studies and arguments of the authors, research gaps have been discovered, thereby proposing some future research directions.

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FACTORS AFFECTING THE ABILITY TO FIND A JOB FOR ACCOUNTING STUDENTS AT UNIVERSITIES IN HANOI IN THE CONTEXT OF INTERNATIONAL INTEGRATION

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Abstract

International accounting integration is an opportunity for accounting practitioners to have the opportunity to access new knowledge easily and not be limited by geographical distance. To meet the needs of accounting human resources in the integration period, accountants are required to hone the specialized professions of the program, have accounting practice skills, the ability to use foreign languages in communication, positive and professional attitude at work, etc. The article uses a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods to assess the Factors affecting the ability to find jobs accounting students at universities in Hanoi in the context of international integration, including: Expertise; Universities; Employers; Discipline-specific; Socio-economic; Personal characteristics. Based on the results of this study, accounting training institutions will better understand which elements of their training programs they need to improve the capacity of accounting students after graduation, contributing to improving job opportunities for students and meeting the trend of international integration.

Keywords: *Accounting, finding, jobs, factors, students.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Accounting is a necessary and popular profession today, considered as an effective financial management tool of the economy. This is presented in all fields from manufacturing, banking, and business to insurance, from businesses to state agencies or non-governmental organizations. Therefore, it can be seen that the demand for accounting human resources is always high and stable in society. Therefore, accounting is always a discipline that is considered attractive and promising in the industry structure of our country. International accounting integration will fundamentally change the method of performing accounting work, by applying electronic vouchers, and software programs to process, synthesize data, and record accounting books in the environment of computerization. Improving the quality of training in the process of accounting requires universities and learners to have new changes in the teaching program, and training methods.

The accounting profession offers a stable salary and opportunities for the future development of each individual. The fact shows that the demand for accountants increases every year, opening up many job opportunities for students. According to research results

published in 2020 by Navigos - Employment Research Organization, "the need for financial accounting ranks 3rd out of the 5 functional departments with the highest recruitment demand". In addition, the Bureau of Labor Statistics (2020) predicted a growth rate of 15.7% for the accounting profession from 2020 to 2025, much faster than the average growth rate of most other occupations. According to career experts, by 2030, the growth rate of the accounting industry will increase to 27%. Currently, there is a shortage of personnel working in the accounting field, especially experienced human resources with a high level of expertise... It can be said that the current general income level of accountants can completely enable them to create a stable life. Thus, it can be seen that the demand for human resources in the accounting profession is currently quite high. Job opportunities are especially opened due to the economic policy of the state to promote economic development, carry out industrialization and modernization, and create conditions for businesses to be established in all fields.

Regarding to the quality of accounting human resources in Vietnam, Doan Lieng Diem (2020) stated that they were ready for economic integration, the quantity and quality of international standards are still issues that need to be improved. Many accounting students have not been able to grasp the accounting job right after they are assigned, but it takes time to re-train. On the other hand, the number of accounting students doing the right specialization are still small, not meeting the assigned tasks, especially since the annual workload is always increasing. The number of accounting students who are trained every year at universities is relatively high, but their professional qualifications, foreign language and other soft skills are not commensurate and have not been achieved to the general level of the area. That is not to mention to the quality of training between universities, thereby not meeting the requirements of high-quality human resources in line with the development and international integration of our economy in the long-run. However, the model of factors affecting the job search ability of accounting students at universities has not been done much.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In 2011, Huynh Truong Huy and La Nguyen Thuy Dung studied the factors affecting students' decisions to find a job. The research shown that there were 3 factors affecting the decision to choose the jobs for graduated students: (1) The influence of the working environment, (2) The influence of the family, and (3) Personal factors. From this study, it can be seen that students themselves also had a lot of considerations when choosing a job. Or if they could not find a company that matched their abilities and requirements, students might decide to give up their major, switch to a guest industry, or do freelance work. However, because the observed sample size was still low (200 samples), the study did not show the overall views of students on factors influencing their decision to look for a job.

In 2012, Almon Shumba & Matsidiso Naong aimed to determine the factors that influence students' career opportunities and aspirations in South Africa. The study used a structured questionnaire survey method to identify factors influencing the choices and career aspirations of medical students in South Africa. The results of the study show that the family factor; the ability of learners to determine their preferred career opportunity choices and faculty are important factors influencing career choices and learners' aspirations.

Based on the theory of planned behavior, Van Hooft (2014) built a research model to

evaluate the motivating factors in the job search process of post-graduate economics students registered at service centers jobs in Netherlands. The results showed that motivational factors (financial need, job-seeking attitude, social pressure on job-seeking activities, self-assessment of self-ability in job search) have an indirect positive impact (through active job-seeking behavior) on job-seeking outcomes. The biggest limitation of this study is that the impact factor scale includes only one measurement index. In addition, the job search results expressed by the employment status (working/unemployed) are not comprehensive.

Gnambs (2017) focused on the impact of human capital on workers' successful job search. Human capital is considered by the author as personal characteristics related to work such as work experience, education level, intelligence, and soft thinking skills. The research sample consisted of 1973 workers looking for work in the period 2010 - 2015, in which some forms of non-work such as maternity leave, sickness, and accidents were excluded from the sample. Research shows that *human factors play a very important role in job search results with higher education level and soft thinking ability, the unemployment period will be shorter.*

In 2021, Mikolaj Jasinski et al published research results based on an analysis of the data from previous studies, using the measurement of the ELA system and data from the social insurance agency in their country. The ELA system is a management system established by the Finnish Ministry of Science and higher education. This system was based on administrative data allowing the system to monitor all graduates still working in Finland. From that, the authors concluded about 3 main factors: Socioeconomic, Study field, and Work experience before graduation. Research confirmed that the major had a great impact on the job opportunities of graduates when the technology industry, healthcare lead in terms of job opportunities as demand for these sectors were higher in Austria than in other sectors. In addition, the study also highlighted the accumulated experience before graduation that will greatly help students in finding jobs after graduation.

From comprehensive domestic and foreign studies related to the topic, the authors found some of the research gaps:

Firstly, it can be easily seen that many studies were conducted in European countries (Netherlands, Poland, Finland...), where the social security system is very developed. The labor market policy system is quite comprehensive, combined with social stability issues, so many aspects of the social environment have not been mentioned.

Secondly, although factors related to human resources, the factor of foreign language proficiency has not been considered much. Partly it may be due to the fact that workers in the countries conducting the research have reached a common foreign language level, enough to meet the job, especially English commonly used in European countries. However, in Vietnam, when the international integration process is going strong, many foreign-invested companies and corporations are established in Vietnam and employ a lot of local employees, so foreign qualifications can negatively affect the job search results of accounting students.

Thirdly, the studies were conducted on samples of general labors; there have not been many specific studies for accounting students.

3. THEORETICAL BASIS AND PROPOSED RESEARCH MODEL

3.1. Background theory

** Psychological theory*

Psychological theory has been used for research in economics since the 1960s. According to psychological theory, in the process of finding work opportunities, learners have relationships with each other and with organizations that provide jobs. At the same time, the theory also emphasizes that the effectiveness of the job search process depends on how these relationships are resolved. Therefore, according to psychological theory, the role of people in society occupies a very important position. When an individual's behavior is in line with their performance goals, the effectiveness of the activities is enhanced. Hopwood (1972) uses this theory to study the use of information by managers provided by employees to assess the competence and qualifications of employees.

From the author's point of view, psychological theory should be used to explain the causes and how the effect of finding job opportunities in the accounting field impacts graduate students. This is related to family, training facilities, cost of living, and personal interests... must create motivation and aim to improve the efficiency of job selection decisions.

** Resource-based theory*

Resource-based theory, like all other management theories, is based on many assumptions. One of the assumptions of theories is primarily tied to the performance of each individual. Specifically, the hypotheses focus on measuring the business performance of individuals and organizations to assess competitiveness. According to the resource-based theory, the capacity within each individual is the determining factor of their competitive advantage. Therefore, each person himself needs to mainly focus on resources such as reputation, innovation and creativity, knowledge, and the ability to improvise flexibly. These are valuable, rare resources that are difficult to imitate and replace. In particular, special intangible resources of individuals such as knowledge allow them to organize planning and implement strategies that bring high job search opportunities. So, according to resource-based theory, the human factor in finding job opportunities plays an important role in improving the efficiency of achieving the desired work in different impact circumstances.

3.2. Proposed research models

Hypothesis 1: Personal characteristics are factors affecting the ability to find jobs of accounting students at universities of economic block in the context of international integration.

Many studies show that personal characteristics have a significant influence on the job opportunities of students after graduation in general and the accounting industry in particular. Personal characteristics refer to factors such as hard skills, soft skills, job-seeking ability, foreign language ability, study results, thinking ability, etc. Nguyen Thi Khanh Trinh (2016) found that the job opportunities of students will be directly proportional to the academic results of students while sitting in university lecture halls. In addition, the hierarchy of influence levels in individual skills is also indicated in the study of Anh Huy (2020). By collecting

assessment results from 1000 final-year students, the author confirms that thinking ability is believed to have the greatest influence on students' job opportunities instead of knowledge factors. It can be said that the factors belonging to the student subject are always considered when they are included in related studies. Many studies have confirmed a direct and indirect positive relationship between people's characteristics and their job search results (McKee Ryan et al., 2005; Koen et al., 2010; Wanberg, 2012).

Therefore, it can be affirmed that personal factors are very important to open up job opportunities for students in general and accounting in particular after graduation.

Hypothesis 2: Discipline-specific is a factor affecting the job search ability of accounting students at economic universities in the context of international integration.

Not being considered as much as individual factors, the field of study is less concerned, but there are still many studies that show the link between the field of study and students' job search opportunities such as research by Mikolaj Jasinski, Marek Bozykowski (2021). According to the authors, the field of study has the greatest influence on the job opportunities of students after graduation when the demand for personnel in each industry is different. Or in the study of Jony Hsiao and Silvia Pereira Nova (2016), the nature of the accounting industry is also mentioned as one of the two most important factors determining job opportunities for graduates. The authors give reasons why the accounting industry is a low-rejection industry and has a stereotyped and boring nature, so there is not much demand for this position in the direction of employers, on the candidate's side, there are also many concerns when choosing to continue pursuing this hard work after graduation. In addition, this industry has been integrating with global accounting standards when the Ministry of Finance has taken steps to prepare for the application of international accounting standards instead of Vietnamese accounting standards, human resources who do not meet those requirements in terms of skills and knowledge also make job opportunities very limited.

Hypothesis 3: Universities are factors affecting the ability of accounting students to find jobs at universities in the economic sector in the context of international integration.

The university has a close relationship with students' job opportunities after graduation. This is an assertion that has been proven by many studies. Nguyen Thanh Thuan (2019) believes that "training must have a close connection between training institutions and employers so that employers can care about supporting jobs after students graduate from the university" to prove the great influence of the university on the job opportunities of students after graduation. The fact has shown that the reputation and prestige built up over many years of the training institution is a measure that creates the first impression of the candidate. For example, in the economic sector, the prestige of long-standing universities such as Foreign Trade University, University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City, Thuongmai University, etc. preferred by most employers over less prestigious universities. Therefore, the role of universities and training institutions cannot be denied in connection with the ability to find jobs for students in general and accounting in particular.

Hypothesis 4: Employers are factors affecting the ability of accounting students to find jobs at economic universities in the context of international integration.

The current situation shows the weakness of graduates with impressive degrees, but when interviewed, they cannot do basic and practical daily tasks such as communicating and handling arising problems. It can be seen that a good academic capacity does not guarantee a person's employment if he or she lacks the core skills of the employer. In the view of some recruitment experts, it is not uncommon for companies to be willing to hire people with no work experience, regardless of qualifications, a person's impressive results cannot be replaced by really good skills.

Nguyen Thanh Thuan (2019) asserts in his research "One of the reasons that employers accept fresh graduates is because they have a spirit of willingness to learn, absorb new things, work attitude be positive, and always cultivate knowledge to be able to develop themselves. In addition to professional knowledge, employers also care about students' soft skills, which is an important factor to help employers evaluate candidates".

The close connection between training institutions and employers is a stepping stone to helping students get job support after graduation. Therefore, the employers' factor is a factor that will affect the job search ability of accounting students at universities in the economics sector.

Hypothesis 5: Socio-economic is a factor affecting the ability of accounting students to find jobs at universities in the economic sector in the context of international integration.

As the trend of integration is taking place strongly, all aspects of life, the economy, and society are significantly affected. The job market is shrinking, so the competition for jobs in industries is fierce in the context of the pandemic. Network of social relations, social pressure, and job orientation are important factors in motivating job search, leading to positive job-seeking behavior in previous empirical studies in many different countries (Hooft et al., 2004; Song et al., 2006; Zikic and Saks, 2009; Van Hooft, 2014). These researchers all agree that social factors are closely related to job-seeking behavior and have a positive effect on job-seeking results.

From the analysis of the labor market in Binh Dinh by Ngo Nu Mai Quynh (2016), the survey of university graduates in this province shows that "The economic situation of the province in the past 5 years relatively stable, the growth rate is almost unchanged, the problem of job creation only meets the needs in the province, the proportion of laborers in economic sectors has not changed much, enterprises are currently operating in the province increased rapidly, but human resources in enterprises began to saturate, which shows that the labor market demand of Binh Dinh does not have much impact on the employability of graduates."

Therefore, socio-economic is a factor that affects the ability of students to find jobs. In the process of restarting the economy, ministries, branches, and localities need to pay attention to and ensure well the issue of human resource training, emphasize the ability to adapt to the new normal, be flexible in the job search process, and improve capacity to meet the needs of the recruitment market. The impact of this factor will be further clarified and analyzed by the group through surveying and testing in the research.

Hypothesis 6: Support policy (support resources) is a factor affecting the ability of accounting students to find jobs at universities in the economic sector in the context of

international integration.

Brush (2017) argues that universities and employers can both provide information and guidance that directly or indirectly affects a student's ability to find a job. The university is a place that creates a lot of opportunities for students to orient their careers, learn and improve professional skills, and more importantly, the cooperation of the faculty, the university with professional organizations and domestic and foreign enterprises. Nguyen Thanh Thuan (2019) pointed out that “in the training process, students need to be trained in skills to participate in the modern labor market, especially skills in starting a business and creating jobs for themselves and others; adaptive skills and flexibility to meet the requirements of each business, both at home and abroad...”

From the overview of research works related to the topic, the team found that the factors affecting the job search ability of accounting students at the universities of economics sector in the context of integration mentioned in many published studies are: individual student capacity, income level as well as career advancement opportunities, employer needs, influence of the university, economic environment - society. Besides, there are other factors such as career prospects, job satisfaction, etc. also mentioned in a few other studies but not much and these factors sometimes appear as an observed variable in studies.

But with the content and scope of the research topic, the group proposes a research model *Factors affecting the job search ability of accounting students at universities in the economic sector in the context of international integration*” with 6 factors: **Personal characteristics, discipline-specific, universities, employers, socio-economic, support policy.** These factors are summarized in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Proposed research model

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1. Data collection methods

Data collection methods include document research, interview and observation method... The two main research methods used in combination in this article are qualitative research methods and qualitative research method, quantitative research methods.

Qualitative research methods were conducted through theoretical research and previous studies related to the factors affecting the job search ability of accounting students at universities in Hanoi.

Quantitative research methods were conducted by sending a survey of factors affecting the job search ability of accounting students at universities of the economics sector in Hanoi, including 6 factors designed according to a Likert scale with 5 levels. After the period of collecting information through the survey form from January 20, 2023, to March 18, 2023, the total number of votes collected was 235 via the link. According to the research of Tabachnick and Fidell (1996) that the minimum sample size should be equal to $50 + 8 \times$ the number of independent variables. Therefore, the minimum sample size for this topic is 98. Therefore, with a sample size of 235 votes, it can be concluded that the sample size is satisfactory for research analysis.

4.2. Data processing methods

To ensure that the data after entering the software is accurate, without errors, or redundancy, the author uses processing methods including descriptive statistics, exploratory factor analysis, testing scale (Cronbach's Alpha), correlation analysis, and regression analysis - testing hypotheses. Data collected from questionnaires is processed by 2 software:

- Microsoft Excel software for summarizing, descriptive statistics of objects and survey contents.

- SPSS 22.0 software to check the reliability of the scale and research hypotheses. Then, use descriptive methods to interpret the obtained statistical results.

5. RESEARCH RESULTS

5.1. Descriptive statistics

Basing on 235 votes collected in the spreadsheet, we screened out 15 invalid votes because they all lacked necessary data, affecting the data processing process. The remaining 220 votes (93.6%) met the requirements and were processed for research purposes. The author used SPSS 22.0 software to classify research samples. The results of classifying research samples are shown in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1: Gender percentage of surveyed subjects

Standard	Frequencies	Percentage %	Cumulative %
Gender			
Male	76	34.5	34.5
Female	144	65.5	100
Student group			
First year	15	6.8	6.8
Second year	19	8.6	15.5
Third year	49	22.3	37.7
Final year	137	62.3	100
University			
Thuongmai University	69	31.4	31.4
NEU	28	12.7	44.1
FTU	26	11.8	55.9
AOF	22	10.0	65.9
Banking Academy	26	11.8	77.7
University of Economic- HNU	13	5.9	97.3
Opened University	14	6.4	84.1
Finance – Banking University	16	7.3	91.4
Other	6	2.7	100.0

(Source: Analytical results of the group)

5.2. Cronbach's Alpha test results

The results of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient show that, all independent and dependent variables in the research model: "**Expertise**", "**Personal characteristics**", "**Discipline-specific**", "**Universities**", "**Employers**", and "**Socio-economic**" all have Cronbach's Alpha group from 0.738 to 0.808. At the same time, all observed variables have total correlation coefficients greater than 0.3. All of these indexes are larger than the minimum to ensure the reliability and discriminability of the factors (Hair et al, 2010), so they are included in the analysis in the next steps.

5.3. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) results.

5.3.1. Factor analysis for independent variables

To check whether the survey sample is large enough and eligible to conduct factor analysis, the author conducts Kaiser - Meyer - Olkin test and Bartlett's test. The necessary condition for EFA analysis is that there must be a large enough relationship between the observed variables. We hypothesize H_0 : between the observed variables, there is no relationship. With the KMO test result $0.954 > 0.5$ and the Sig of Bartlett's test < 0.05 (observed variables are correlated with each other in the population), thus rejecting H_0 . We can conclude that the survey data have the conditions to conduct exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and can use the results.

5.3.2. EFA exploratory factor analysis

After meeting the requirements of the reliability test, the team was included in the exploratory factor analysis with 28 observed variables of the independent variables in the research model. Because the sample size of the group was 220 (after cleaning), when analyzing the EFA exploratory factor, the group chose a Factor Loading load factor of 0.5. Through the first EFA analysis, it can be seen that all observed variables have Factor Loading > 0.5 . However, there is still the phenomenon of observed variables uploading in both factors, and the difference between the description coefficient is not guaranteed from 0.3, so the group has removed the variables: NT2, DDCN3, and DTNH4 to conduct exploratory coefficient analysis. The second EFA is shown in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 2: EFA discovery factor analysis table

	Rotated Component Matrix						
	Components						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CSHT1		.745					
CSHT2		.730					
CSHT4		.723					
CSHT3		.721					
NTD1			.759				
NTD4			.711				
NTD3			.704				
NTD2			.701				
KTXH3				.802			
KTXH1				.757			
KTXH4				.684			
KTXH2				.675			
NT3					.799		
NT4					.722		
NT1					.696		
DDCN1						.773	
DDCN4						.767	
DDCN2						.672	
DTNH2							.781
DTNH3							.732
DTNH1							.705

(Source: Analytical results of the group)

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.500
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	115.033
	df	1
	Sig.	.000

(Source: Analytical results of the group)

KMO coefficient is 0.5 and sig = 0.000 < 0.5, so it can be concluded that observed variables are correlated with each other in the population and EFA factor analysis is appropriate. The total variance used to explain the multipliers is 82.044% > 50%, so it satisfies the conditions of factor analysis (Table 4).

Table 4: Total Variance Explained

Total Variance Explained						
Components	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.641	82.044	82.044	1.641	82.044	82.044
2	.359	17.956	100.000			

(Source: Analytical results of the group)

The second EFA exploratory factor analysis results extracted 2 factors with a high KMO index, Eigenvalue index of 1.641 (>1), and total variance extracted was 82.044% (>50%). So these factors are independent variables and are included in the analysis in the next steps to test the research model.

5.3.3. Pearson correlation analysis results

After completing the EFA exploratory factor analysis and the CFA confirmatory factor analysis, the team conducted a Pearson correlation analysis to test the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable, as well as evaluate the correlation between variables.

Table 5: Pearson correlation analysis

	KN	CSHT	DDCN	DTNH	NT	NTD	KTXH	
KN	Pearson Correlation	1	.546**	.510**	.524**	.533**	.556**	.458
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220	220
CSHT	Pearson Correlation	.546**	1	.361**	.429**	.305**	.379**	.265**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

	KN	CSHT	DDCN	DTNH	NT	NTD	KTXH	
DDCN	Pearson Correlation	.510**	.361**	1	.373**	.381**	.408**	.385**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220	220
DTNH	Pearson Correlation	.524**	.429**	.373**	1	.295**	.393**	.319**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220	220
NT	Pearson Correlation	.533**	.305**	.381**	.295**	1	.411**	.363**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220	220
NTD	Pearson Correlation	.556**	.379**	.408**	.393**	.411**	1	.350**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220	220
KTXH	Pearson Correlation	.458**	.265**	.385**	.319**	.363**	.350**	1**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

(Source: Analytical results of the group)

Through analysis, we found that with the Sig value in the pairs of variables, both < 0.05 and equal to 0.00, the variables all have a linear relationship with each other. For the Pearson correlation coefficient, when the coefficient has a value > 0.4, it means that the pair of variables has a strong correlation value but the magnitude of the coefficient does not reflect the order of action of the dependent variable on the independent variable.

5.3.4. Regression analysis results

Before conducting research using multiple regression analysis, we evaluated and considered the correlation between variables in the model by using Pearson's Correlation coefficient to quantify the tightness of the relationship between the variables. independent variables and dependent variables. We got the result that the dependent variable was correlated with other research variables and had correlation coefficients reaching statistical significance from 0.265 to 0.556.

Next, we put the above 6 factors into running regression analysis (table 6) to evaluate the appropriateness of the multiple regression model using the Enter method. The value of each factor used to run regression is the average value of the observed variables belonging to that factor. The regression results show that the model fits well with the research data with an adjusted R2 of 0.574. Prove that the independent variables explain more than 50% of the change in the dependent variable:

Table 6: Multiple regression results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.766 ^a	.587	.574	.49077	2.156

(Source: Analytical results of the group)

The research model of factors affecting job opportunities of accounting students at universities of economics in the context of the impact of the Covid-19 epidemic is shown through the following equation:

$$KN = \beta_0 + \beta_1CSHT + \beta_2NTD + \beta_3KTXH + \beta_4NT + \beta_5DDCN + \beta_6DTNH + \varepsilon$$

The results of regression analysis of factors affecting job opportunities of accounting students at universities of economics in the context of international integration are shown in the following Table 7:

Table 7: Total Variance Explained

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance
1	(Constant)	-1.586	.284		-5.582	.000	
	CSHT	.283	.061	.239	4.611	.000	.727
	DDCN	.156	.060	.139	2.611	.010	.686
	DTNH	.209	.060	.184	3.490	.001	.701
	NT	.255	.059	.224	4.300	.000	.716
	NTD	.234	.063	.199	3.700	.000	.670
	KTXH	.157	.061	.132	2.588	.010	.744

(Source: analysis results of the group)

Table 7 shows that all factors have Sig significance < 0.05, and all variables are correlated and have statistical significance in the research model. Variance magnification factor VIF < 2, so it can be concluded that there is **no multicollinearity between these six factors**.

The linear regression equation showing the factors affecting the job opportunities of accounting students at universities in the economic sector in the context of international integration is shown as follows:

$$KN = -1.586 + 0.283CSHT + 0.156DDCN + 0.209DTNH + 0.255NT + 0.234NTD + 0.157KTXH$$

Based on the magnitude of the normalized regression coefficient Beta, we get the order of the level of impact from high to low of the independent variables to the dependent variable KN as (1) CSHT: 0.283; (2) NT: 0.255, (3) NTD: 0.234, (4) DTNH: 0.209, (5) KTXH: 0.157, (6) DDCN: 0.156

(In which: KN: Abilities; CSHT: Support policies; NT: universities; NTD: Employers; DTNH: Discipline-specific; KTXH: Socio-economic; DDCN: Personal characteristics).

The above equation shows that there are 6 factors affecting the job opportunities of accounting students at universities of economics in the context of integration. That is:

Firstly: With a Beta coefficient of 0.283, **the factor CSHT (expertise)** has the greatest influence on the job search ability of accounting students at universities of economics. The positive sign (+) of the Beta coefficient indicates a positive relationship. Regression results show that Beta is 0.283 and Sig = 0.000 (<0.05), which means that when other factors are unchanged, if knowledge increases by 1 unit, the probability of job search for accounting students will be increased to 0.283 units. The next factor that affects the ability to find jobs for accounting students at universities of the economic block is **the factor NT (universities)**. Beta coefficient = 0.255 and Sig = 0.000 (<0.05), when other factors are unchanged, if the university factor increases by 1 unit, the probability of finding a job for accounting students will increase to 0.255 units. The third factor is **the factor NTD (employers)** which affects the job opportunities of accounting students. With the coefficient Beta = 0.234 and Sig = 0.000 (<0.05), it means that when other factors do not change, if the employer factor increases by 1 unit, the probability of finding a job for accounting students will increase to 0.234 units. The fourth factor is **DTNH (Discipline-specific)**. We see that the coefficient Beta = 0.209 and Sig = 0.001 (<0.05) if the discipline-specific factor increases by 1 unit, the student's ability to find a job will increase by 0.209 units. This result indicates that discipline-specific is correlated with the student's ability to find a job. The fifth factor is **the socio-economic** that affects the employment opportunities of accounting students. With coefficient Beta = 0.157 and Sig = 0.010 (<0.05), it means when other factors remain unchanged, if the socio-economic factor increases by 1 unit, the probability of finding a job for accounting students will increase by 0.157 units. And the last factor that affects students' ability to find a job is **the DDCN factor (personal characteristics)**. We see the coefficient Beta = 0.156 and Sig = 0.010 (<0.05), if the personal factor increases by 1 unit, the probability of finding a job for accounting students will increase by 0.156 units. Therefore, the relationship between the dependent variable and six independent variables is positive because the coefficients of Beta and the independent variables are >0.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results about "factors affecting the job search ability for accounting students at universities of economics in Hanoi city", we found that: *Expertise, Personal characteristics, Discipline-specific, Universities, Employers, and Socio-economic* are the factors that affect the ability to find jobs of accounting students at universities under the research scope. All variables proposed by the research team have a positive influence on student's ability to find a job. In particular, among the factors that have the most influence, the element of expertise has the strongest influence on the ability of students to find a job.

In the context of current global economic integration, **each individual's expertise** is the first factor affecting the ability to find a job. This factor is very important because only with high expertise will the employer choose to give you a good job opportunity. The next factor affecting the job search ability of accounting students is **the universities**. The universities where you graduate will somewhat affect the student's job opportunities if the student graduates from a good quality university, job opportunities will expand with a high salary. In addition, the university's training program helps students improve their skills and knowledge.

Accumulate good expertise to improve job search opportunities. **Employer factor** also affects students' ability to find a job. Employers create supportive policies, creating favorable conditions for accounting students to have the opportunity to apply for company positions. The transparency of the recruitment process also facilitates and improves job opportunities for students. Then, looking at the information about **the discipline-specific factor**, in the context of integration, the specific characteristics of the accounting profession from work pressure, income to career advancement opportunities, many students will have choices for themselves when looking for jobs at businesses to be able to find a job that best suits them.

At a time when the socio-economic situation is greatly affected by the Fourth Industrial Revolution and international integration, students' job opportunities are also affected. The nature of the accounting profession helps the job to remain stable in the economic conditions of the company. Finally, there is **the personal characteristics factor**, to consider how suitable the student is to the job conditions as well as the accounting profession. From those characteristics, employers will assess the suitability of students for the job position as well as the general environment of the business. Moreover, students themselves also re-evaluate personal characteristics such as a passion for work, personality, and interests that are suitable for work or not.

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DETERMINANTS OF FINANCING CHOICES AND FINANCIAL HIERARCHY IN EMERGING MARKETS: EVIDENCE FROM VIETNAM

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Abstract

This study examines the firms financing preference in an emerging market, focusing on four main financing types: internal finance, bank loans, bond, and stock issues. Using firm-specific factors from 50 largest non-financial companies in the Vietnamese stock markets from 2012 to 2022, we find that Vietnamese firms financing choices are significantly affected by their size, liquidity, tax shield and stock performance. The empirical results from multinomial logit regression are in line with the pecking order theory, mainly due to the high cost of information asymmetry. We further examine the financial hierarchy of Vietnamese firms using ordered probit regressions. Vietnamese firms appear to prefer internal finance over all other financing types, while bond issue is the last source of financing choice. This enhances understanding of financing dynamics in Vietnamese firms, contributing to the debate on emerging market corporate finance.

Keywords: *Capital structure; Financing choices; Financing hierarchy; Emerging market*

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the seminal works of Modigliani and Miller (1) and Modigliani and Miller (2), firm's capital structure and their financing choices have been considerable attention from researchers. Modigliani and Miller (1) paved the way with seminal contributions regarding the *static trade-off theory (TOT)*. The TOT argues that firms target an optimal debt-capital mixture where the cost of financial distress is balanced with the benefits of debts to maximise the firm value. One intriguing challenge of the TOT is its ability to explain the dynamics of the firm's capital structure, particularly the financing choices of firms when they need to raise incremental capital to fund new investments. Myers (3) and Myers and Majluf (4) proposed the *pecking order theory (POT)* and argue that firms tend to have the so-called financial hierarchies due to the asymmetric information between the firm managers and investors. In particular, firms have preference order on the capital sources for their incremental financial needs: (i) Internal finance; (ii) debt, and (iii) share issues. Baker and Wurgler (5) further highlight that the firm's managers choose their incremental capital based on the market condition to minimize their cost of capital.

We examine incremental financing choices in an emerging market, focusing on Vietnamese listed firms from 2005 to 2022. Employing a multinomial regression model, we

analyze firm-specific determinants driving selections among four distinctive financing types: internal finance, bank loans, bond and share issues. More importantly, we explore the preference order in the incremental financing decision of Vietnamese firms using ordered logistic regressions.

This study contributes to the literature in several ways. First, we provide empirical evidence on the determinants of financial choices and preference orders of financing types in emerging markets. Existing researches predominantly focus on developed markets due to the underdevelopment of capital markets and lack of transparency in emerging economies (6, 7). De Haan and Hinloopen (7) argue that the firm's financing decisions vary significantly between developed and emerging markets, due to their difference in their financial development. Therefore, it is important to examine the incremental financing behaviour of firms in developing countries, given its significantly higher information asymmetry and different institutional practices (8).

Second, we a comprehensive analysis on the firm-specific determinants of the firm's incremental financing decision, rather than focusing on the static debt-capital mixture as predominant in prior studies. De Haan and Hinloopen (7) argue that debt ratios only provide a snapshot of historical financing choices and ignore the timing of the manager's decisions. Thus, the static capital structure fails to provide a robust explanation for why certain firms favour internal finance while others prefer external finance for incremental investments. By embracing the dynamics of financing options and preference hierarchies, we can better discern the unique influences they exert on firms' capital choices for growth options.

Third, we contribute to the debate of the firm's financing hierarchies in developing countries. Although prior researchers have generally agreed on the preferences of internal finance to external financing to meet the firm's funding needs (9), yet there is no consensus on the order of preferences among different types of external finance. Anderson and Carverhill (10) further argue that the financial hierarchy varies with the firm's business condition. In this paper, we examine the order of financial preferences in Vietnamese companies.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study on the determinants of incremental financing choices and financing hierarchy in Vietnam. Vietnam is a typical emerging market with rapid economic growth, averaging 6.2 per cent Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth per year in real terms over the last 10 years. Vietnam has a bank-based financial structure in which the banking industry has become playing a vital role and contributing approximately 16-18 per cent of the GDP (11). Having said that, the financial market has developed significantly in the last few years. As of 2022, the stock market capitalization constitutes 55.2 percent of the GDP, and the nonfinancial corporate bond market holds a value equivalent to 14.81 percent of the GDP. With these expanded financial avenues, Vietnamese firms are presented with a wider spectrum of funding options for their incremental investment. Thus, it is of practically importance to study the determinants and preference order in their financing decision.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on the determinants of firms' financing choices and their preference order for incremental capital. Section 3 demonstrates the methodologies, while Section 4 discuss the empirical results on the Vietnamese firms. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. The determinants of financing sources

The seminal works of Modigliani and Miller (1) and Modigliani and Miller (2) paved the way for the capital structure puzzle with the static trade-off theory. This theory implies that firms strategically choose their capital sources to achieve an optimal capital structure where benefits arising from the tax advantages of debt is balanced with the costs linked to the bankruptcy cost of increasing financial leverage ratio. In a parallel vein, Myers (3) and Myers and Majluf (4) developed a pecking-order theory that draws upon the information asymmetry between the firm managers and market investors. The authors argue that firms have specific priorities over the capital sources for incremental financing needs. In particular, firms prefer internal finance over external finance, and among the external sources, they prefer bank loans over bond and share issue is the least preference.

Based on these theoretical frameworks, several firm-specific factors are expected to affect their financing choices. First, several studies explore the role of firm size on the financing decisions. Under the trade-off theory, larger firms are considered to have lower bankruptcy risk (12) and lower borrowing costs (13). Thus, firm size is expected to have positive correlation with debt utilization. In contrast, larger firms often have higher ability to generate internal financing sources and better profit margin. Thus, under the pecking order theory, larger firms would prefer internal finance over external finance and tend to reduce their debt ratios (8).

Second, firm's profitability and liquidity could affect firms financing choices. Firms' profitability and liquidity can be considered as proxies for their availability of internal funds (14). Under the pecking order theory, these ratios are expected to positively correlated with the choice of internal finance and negatively correlated with the use of external finance (15). In contrast, high level of profitability and liquidity impose lower business risk, which imply higher probability of using debt to maximize the firm value, as predicted by the trade-off theory (8).

Third, the availability of tax shield is also expected to drive the financing choices. Bernasconi, Marenzi (6) show that higher level of depreciation or historical interest payments signal better ability to pay off the external debts, leading higher probability of extending their debt capacity. Lei (16), however, argue that higher depreciations and interest payments have negative impacts on the firm's profitability. Thus, firms would be more likely to reduce their debt ratios to avoid higher pressure on the firm's future profitability. Finally, Baker and Wurgler (5) suggest that the financing choices are also affected by the market valuation. They argue that the historical stock performance indicates the investor's preference. Consequently, firms that are underperformed in the stock markets would be forced to issue bonds or use bank loans instead of issuing shares.

Overall, previous studies provide mixed results on the determinants of financing choices. De Haan and Hinloopen (7) and Fan, Titman (17) point out that the financing decision are different between countries. Moreover, the majority of previous empirical studies focus on developed markets due to the underdevelopment of the financial markets. As a results, the high costs of information asymmetry lead to the suboptimal financing decisions of firms in

emerging countries (18). In this study, we contribute to the research gap by providing empirical evidence on the firm-specific determinants of non-financial firms in an emerging market with the case study of Vietnam.

2.2. Financial hierarchies for incremental capital needs

The Pecking Order Theory (POT), introduced by Myers (3), predicts that firms demonstrate a particular preference order in their incremental financial decision. This theory posits that firms prioritize internal financing, followed by external financing options, based on the assumption that managers possess superior information compared to external investors, resulting in information asymmetry. Regarding the external financing, bank borrowing is usually favored over issuing bonds, as it often comes with fewer associated costs and restrictions. Issuing shares is typically the least preferred choice, as it can dilute existing shareholders' ownership and potentially convey negative signals regarding management's confidence in the firm's prospects (4).

In contrast, Jensen and Meckling (19)) presented an agency theory perspective on financing choices, arguing that firms prefer debt over internal finance and equity issuance. According to this view, debt creates financial discipline, as interest payments must be met, and failure to do so can result in default, leading to negative consequences for both managers and shareholders. Frydenberg (20) further emphasize that a firm's willingness to issue debt can signal confidence to the market. When a firm issues debt, it demonstrates its belief in its ability to generate sufficient cash flows to service the debt and, consequently, its confidence in debt financing as a viable strategy.

Empirical evidence on the financial hierarchies also provides mixed evidence. De Haan and Hinloopen (7) conducted a study on Dutch firms and found a financial hierarchy favoring internal finance, followed by bank loans and share issuance, with bond issues being less favored due to the relatively underdeveloped bond market. Conversely, Dang (21) highlighted that firms may prefer issuing debt to offset financing deficits, while Anderson and Carverhill (10) argued that the financial hierarchy varies depending on a firm's specific business conditions. Empirical studies in emerging markets also yield mixed results. Seifert and Gonenc (22) investigated 23 developing countries and found that equity issuances were the preferred financing type, suggesting that firms in these markets may adopt different financing preferences. However, Chakrabarti and Chakrabarti (14) discovered that Indian firms strictly adhered to the pecking order theory, with bank borrowing as the second choice after internal finance and equity issuance being the last resort.

This study aims to contribute to the existing body of literature by examining the factors influencing financing choices in Vietnam. By focusing on this rapidly growing and dynamic market, we aim to shed light on the drivers behind firms' financing decisions and the extent to which the POT holds true in this unique context.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. Methodology

3.1.1. Determinants of financing choices

We employ the standard multinomial logistic regression model, similar to De Haan and Hinloopen (7) to investigate the determinants of capital choice for incremental financing needs of Vietnamese firms as follow:

$$p_i = \frac{\exp(\beta_{0k} + X_{t-1}\beta'_k)}{1 + \sum_{j=2}^m \exp(\beta_{0j} + X_{t-1}\beta'_j)} \quad (1)$$

where p_i is the probability of choosing the capital source i out of m alternative financing choices. In this study, we consider four main capital sources that firms tend to explore when they have incremental financial needs: internal finance, bank credit, bond and stock issuances.

Our motivation is to distinguish the firm-specific factors affecting the choices of Vietnamese firms. Similar to De Haan and Hinloopen (7), we construct the binary variables for incremental financial choices as following. First, we collect information on the issuance of stocks and bond from the firms' annual financial statements. An enterprise will be recognized as using these two types of capital if the notes to the financial statements indicate an increase in long-term debt from the issuance of bonds or an increase in the ordinary share capital during the fiscal year. Second, firms are coded as having entered into a new bank loan agreement for their incremental financial needs if the net gain of long-term outstanding debt plus short-term bank exceeds 5% of total assets. Third, we consider firms as using internal finance if (i) the amount of retained current earnings exceeds 5% of total assets or (ii) if the net cash withdrawn from accumulated current assets exceeds 5% of total assets. The choice of the 5% threshold in both bank loans and internal finance is following De Haan and Hinloopen (7) to focus on the relatively large usage of these financial sources and avoid potential statistical noise in the raw data.

In practice, a firm may use more than one financial source in the same fiscal year. However, as we focus on the preference order of alternative financing choices, for each firm in one fiscal year, we only code firm with the financial source that is mostly significant. A potential strategy to deal with the financing combination is to simply remove all observation with multiple financial sources, leaving a sample with mutually exclusive financing choices only, similar to De Haan and Hinloopen (7). However, this strategy would significantly reduce our sample size as most of companies in our dataset rely on multiple capital sources. Thus, we follow the priority order similar Helwege and Liang (23) to choose the appropriate code for each firm in one fiscal year. We code firms that have used internal finance as such. Firms that issued bonds are coded as such, even if these firms use bank loans and/or issue share in the same year. Finally, we term firms that issue shares as such, even if they also use bank credit in the same year.

In Eq (1), X_{t-1} is the vector of firm-specific potential determinants of their financing decision, which are lagged by one-year to avoid potential heterogeneity issue, while β'_k being the vector of corresponding coefficients.

First, we consider the firm's liquidity, as measured by the ratio of liquid asset over total asset, and profitability, defined as earning over total asset, as indicators of firm's availability of internal capital (7). These expected sign on the impacts of these ratios on the financing choice is debatable. If the trade-off theory holds, firms with good internal capital have a low risk of financial distress, leading them more likely to choose debt over equity for incremental financing. However, under the pecking order theory, increase in the availability of internal finance would reduce the probability of external finance. Second, we explore the impacts of firm size, which also has opposite predictions under alternative theories. According to pecking order theory, firm size is expected to have a positive correlation with the use external finance, while negatively correlated with the use of internal finance since their size would lower the information asymmetry between market participants and consequently lowering the external financing costs (8). However, larger firm size could also signal lower business risk. Thus, under the trade-off theory, firm size should be positively correlated with the use of bank loans or issuing bonds as these firms have higher optimal debt ratios (18).

Next, we consider the potential impacts of tax shields on the financing choice. We examine the impacts of both debt tax shield, as proxied by interest payments over total assets, and non-debt tax shield, as measured by the depreciation over total asset. A large interest payment ratio would lower the firm's incentives to attract more debt (24), thus the debt tax shield is expected to negatively correlate with the use of bank credit and bond, while increasing the probability of equity and internal financing choices. Regarding the non-debt tax shield, higher ratio of depreciation would allow firms to use these non-cash expenses for incremental financing, thus increasing the potential of internal finance and decreasing the choice of issuing bond or extend their bank credit capacity (7).

Finally, we examine the impacts of stock performance on the financing choices. Under the trade-off theory, increasing stock prices would allow firms to extend their debt due to enhancement in the firm's market value. The pecking order theory also implies that firms would avoid issue shares after a period of increasing stock prices as it would send negative signal to the market on the valuation of their stocks. In contrast, Baker and Wurgler (5) argue that firms would exploit the investors regarding their good stock performance to issue new stocks for their incremental capital needs.

3.1.2. Financial hierarchy

Although multinomial logistic regression provides useful information on the determinants of incremental financing choices, it is silent about the prefer hierarchy of financing types. To address this question, we follow De Haan and Hinloopen (7) to employ the ordered probit model to test the most preferred hierarchy in our data sample.

First, we code the four financing types, (internal finance, bank credit, bond, stock), in an ordinal discrete, (0,1,2,3). Second, we estimate ordered probit models for all potential hierarchies. These alternative hierarchies can be compared using a standard likelihood ratio (LR) test.¹ Thus, the financial hierarchy that best fit the data would statistically have the

¹ Theoretically, we would have to estimate $4! = 24$ ordered probit regression. However, as pointed out by De Haan and Hinloopen (2003), the likelihood value of two opposite ordinal discrete will be the same. Thus, it leaves us to estimate only 12 ordered probit regressions.

highest likelihood value in its ordered probit regression. For example, if the pecking order theory is correct in the case of Vietnamese firms, the ordered probit regression of the ordinal discrete (0,1,3,2), i.e. (internal finance, bank credit, bond, stock), would yield the highest likelihood value.

3.2. Data

Our empirical study employs financial statements of the top 50 non-financial firms with the largest capitalization on the Vietnamese stock market in the period from 2012 to the end of 2022. We choose firms with the largest market capitalization to ensure that they have relatively similar abilities to raise capital from banks and financial markets. Table 1 provides the descriptive statistics of our sample, including the mean and median values of the determinants, in each financing types. We observe that firms with larger size and higher liquidity tend to use internal finance. The mean of size for firms that use internal finance is 29.454, higher than that of bank loan (29.305), bond (29.105) and stock (29.227). Similarly, the mean value of liquidity ratio of firms that use internal finance is 0.187, while firms that issue stock has the lowest mean liquidity ratio, at 0.096. Next, the mean value of profitability and depreciation ratios of firms that use bank credit is lower than that of the other three financing types, at 0.849 and 0.033, respectively. The mean and median value of interest payment ratio is relatively similar in all four capital sources. Finally, firms that issue bond and stock tend to have higher mean value of stock performance than that of firms using internal finance and bank credit.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics in financing types

	Internal finance	Bank credit	Bond	Stock
Liquidity	0.187 <i>(0.096)</i>	0.166 <i>(0.086)</i>	0.096 <i>(0.066)</i>	0.100 <i>(0.068)</i>
Size	29.454 <i>(29.644)</i>	29.305 <i>(29.485)</i>	29.105 <i>(29.147)</i>	29.227 <i>(29.258)</i>
Profitability	0.897 <i>(0.72)</i>	0.849 <i>(0.692)</i>	0.856 <i>(0.704)</i>	0.861 <i>(0.724)</i>
Depreciation	0.034 <i>(0.028)</i>	0.033 <i>(0.027)</i>	0.035 <i>(0.028)</i>	0.035 <i>(0.028)</i>
Interest payments	0.015 <i>(0.011)</i>	0.014 <i>(0.011)</i>	0.015 <i>(0.013)</i>	0.014 <i>(0.011)</i>
Stock performance	24.653 <i>(12.166)</i>	26.009 <i>(13.476)</i>	28.957 <i>(17.53)</i>	27.487 <i>(13.762)</i>

This table provides the mean and median values of the variables regarding financing types in our sample. The median values are provided in italics.

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

4.1. Determinants of incremental financial choices

Table 2 presents the estimation results for the multinomial logit model explaining financing choices of Vietnamese companies. To facilitate evaluation, we provide the marginal effects of the explanatory variables on the financing types. The marginal effect allows direct

evaluation of the change in the probability of choosing a type of enterprise capital. For instance, the coefficient value of -3.117 of size indicates that if the firm size increases by 1% this year, the probability of using internal finance for incremental investments in year $t + 1$ will decrease by 3.117%.

First, we find that firms with higher liquidity tend to prefer internal finance as 1% increase in the liquidity ratio leads to 0,766% increase in the probability of internal finance, while the probabilities of using bank loans, bond and stock issuance reduce by 0,268%, 0,274% and 0,224%, respectively. This observation is similar to the findings of Šarlija and Hanc (25) for the Croatian firms and De Haan and Hinloopen (7) for the Dutch enterprises, and in line with the pecking order theory as higher liquidity ratio increase the availability of cash to fund the incremental financing. Second, larger firms prefer stock issuance to internal finance for their incremental financing. If the firm size increases by 1%, the probability of using internal finance reduces by 3,117% while the chance of stock issuance significantly increases by 1,768%. This finding is similar to the predictions of the pecking order theory as larger firms facing with lower cost of information asymmetry, especially in emerging stock market as in Vietnam, resulting to preference on the stock issuance (7).

Third, we find that 1% improvement in the firm profitability leads to the probability of using internal finance increase by 0,053% while reducing the chance of issuing bond by 0,052%. The negative association between profitability and the use of debt is similar to findings of Afinindy, Salim (26) and confirming the pecking order theory on the preference over internal financing of profitable firms. Next, we observe opposite impacts of debt and non-debt tax shield on the incremental financing choices. In particular, 1% increase in the interest payment leads to the 0,771% higher probability of bond issuance, while 1% increase in the depreciation results to 1,884% higher chance of using internal finance while significantly lowering the probability of issuing bond by 1,383%. This is in line with the pecking order theory as it implies that higher depreciation ratio allows firms to have more internal fundings Nga and Long (27). Finally, 1% increase in the stock performance this year would significantly lead to 0,08% increase in the probability of using internal finance, while reducing the chance of extending bank credit by 0,079%. It means that better stock performance signal better firm business performance, thus they would prefer to exploit the internal finance for incremental financing needs, rather than increasing their debt Baker and Wurgler (5).

Overall, we find that the empirical results for the financing choices in Vietnam is in line with predictions from the pecking order theory of Myers (3), mainly due to the high level of information asymmetry in the financial markets.

Table 2: The determinants of financing choices of Vietnamese firms

	<i>Marginal effects</i>			
	Internal finance	Bank loans	Bonds	Stocks
Liquidity	0.766*** (0.138)	-0.268** (0.109)	-0.274** (0.112)	-0.223** (0.105)
Size	-3.117* (1.702)	0.019 (1.099)	1.330 (1.254)	1.768 * (1.137)

	<i>Marginal effects</i>			
	Internal finance	Bank loans	Bonds	Stocks
Profitability	0.053* (0.032)	0.007 (0.015)	-0.052* (0.031)	-0.008 (0.021)
Depreciation	1.884** (0.815)	-0.461 (0.547)	-1.383* (0.732)	-0.039 (0.464)
Interest payments	-0.222 (0.996)	0.183 (0.677)	0.771* (0.433)	-0.731 (0.918)
Stock performance	0.080** (0.034)	-0.079*** (0.029)	-0.003 (0.022)	0.003 (0.018)

*This table provides the marginal effects of the explanatory variables on the capital choices of Vietnamese firms using multinomial logit regression. The value in parentheses is the standard error of the regression coefficient estimate. ***, **, * indicate statistical significance levels of 1%, 5% and 10%*

4.2. Financing hierarchy in Vietnam

Table 3 provides the estimation results for the financial hierarchis of Vietnamese firms using ordered probit regressions. h_i are all potential hierarchies for the combination of the four financing types, ordered by the discrete (0, 1, 2, 3), where 0 is the most preferred choice and 3 is the last source of financing option. For example, h_1 is the financial hierarchy following the pecking order theory, in which the internal finance is the most preferred choice of capital, following by bank loans and bond, while stock issuance is the least preference by firms. The column $\ln(\text{likelihood})$ provides the logarithm of the likelihood value of the corresponding ordered probit regression. Finally, the last columns provide the rank of the hierarchy in row at the 5% of significance level of the LR tests compared to other potential hierarchies. If the likelihood of h_i and h_j are not statistically difference according to LR test, they will be sorted at the same ranking.

Table 3: The financial hierarchies of financing choices in Vietnam

	Internal finance	Bank loans	Bonds	Stocks	ln(likelihood)	Rank at 5% significance
h1	0	1	2	3	-391.1559	2
h2	0	1	3	2	-387.9457	1
h3	0	2	1	3	-392.8214	2
h4	0	3	1	2	-392.4305	2
h5	0	2	3	1	-387.9980	1
h6	0	3	2	1	-391.2521	2
h7	1	0	2	3	-417.2446	4
h8	1	0	3	2	-416.2749	3
h9	2	0	1	3	-415.8547	3

	Internal finance	Bank loans	Bonds	Stocks	ln(likelihood)	Rank at 5% significance
h10	2	0	3	1	-419.8463	4
h11	3	0	1	2	-391.2621	2
h12	3	0	2	1	-392.4405	2

This table provides the logarithm of the likelihood value of the ordered probit regression of corresponding financial hierarchy in rows. The last column provides the rankings of the financial choice preference according to the LR test at the 5% of significance level. Bold values highlight the financial hierarchies that significantly yield the highest log-likelihood values.

First, we find that the log-likelihood value of financial hierarchies are statistically different and can be divided into four groups. It means that Vietnamese firms seem to have preference over the financing choices for their incremental capital needs. If not, LR tests of all pairs of financial hierarchies would not be statistically different.

Second, h_2 and h_5 are the most preferred hierarchies (h_2 , h_5) as their log-likelihood values yield lowest values compared to other preference orders and are statistically similar at the 5% significance level. In both hierarchies, internal finance is the most preferred financing choice, while bond issuance is the least financing option for Vietnamese firms facing incremental capital needs. As we noted above, the preference of Vietnamese firms on internal finance is due to the high level of information asymmetry in the Vietnamese financial markets. Thus, Vietnamese firms prefer to use their internal financing to avoid potential negative signals to the market participants. The least preference of bond issuance can be well-attributed to the relatively under-development of the Vietnamese bond market. As noted by Esho et al. (2011), firms in less-developed bond markets would have a lower probability of issuing bonds to fund their capital needs. The difference in the two most preferred hierarchies is the reverse order of bank loans and stock issuance. In h_2 , firms would choose to extend their bank credit if their internal finance is not enough for the incremental financial needs. This preference is close to the predictions of the pecking order theory as the use of bank loans would avoid a negative signal to the market participants. In h_5 , however, firms prefer stock issuance over bank loans for financing needs. One potential reason is due to the fact that our data sample consists of firms with the highest capitalization in the Vietnamese stock markets, which are highly-recognized by the investors. Thus, these firms would prefer to issue stocks to exploit their relatively lower share issuing costs, instead of expanding their bank credits that would pose pressure on their interest payment (8).

5. CONCLUSION

This study examines the firm-specific determinants of the financing choices for 50 non-financial companies that have the largest market capitalization in the Vietnamese stock markets. In particular, we classify the financing types into four main sources: internal finance, bank loans, bond, and stock issues. We find that firms' financing choices are significantly affected by their size, liquidity, tax shield, and stock performance. The empirical results from multinomial logit regression indicate that the financial choices of Vietnamese non-financial firms are generally in line with the pecking order theory of Myers (3) and Myers and Majluf (4).

We further investigate the financial hierarchy for incremental capital in our sample of Vietnamese firms. To this end, we employ ordered probit models for all possible financing hierarchies and explore their significance statistically using a standard likelihood test. We find that Vietnamese firms prefer internal finance over all other financing types, while bond issue is the last source of financing choice. This finding could be attributable to the relatively underdevelopment of the Vietnamese bond market. In the two financial hierarchies that significantly yield the best fit, the preference order of bank loans and stocks are reversed. While bank credit is the main external finance in a bank-based financial system, the preference of stock issue over bond market may be due to the sample in our study which consists of highest market capitalized firms in the Vietnamese stock market.

There are still some limitations in the research that can be further assessed in future studies. Firstly, the companies selected in the statistical sample are non-financial firms with the highest market capitalization in the Vietnamese stock market to ensure access to similar sources of capital. Therefore, the quantitative model results may not fully represent the entirety of Vietnamese companies, as most of them are medium and small-sized enterprises. Secondly, this study does not consider the potential difference of in the financial hierarchies of companies in different sectors.

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WHY CAN FINTECH REDUCE FINANCIAL CONSTRAINTS FOR SMALL AND MEDIUM – SIZED ENTERPRISES? EXPERIMENTAL EVIDENCE IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of financial technology (Fintech) on financial constraints faced by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Vietnam. The research team used a sample of 1530 observations of 153 SMEs between 2012 and 2021, and excluded businesses from the financial, insurance, banking, and other businesses with incomplete data. The study employs both the fixed effects model and the random effects model with the panel dataset. According to the Hausman test, the fixed-effect model is more appropriate. Based on the regression results, the authors discovered that the growth of Fintech has a negative effect on the financial constraints faced by small and medium-sized businesses in Vietnam.

Keywords: *Fintech, financial constraints, SMEs.*

THRESHOLD EFFECT OF INFORMATION DISCLOSURE ON COST OF CAPITAL: AN EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM VIETNAM'S PUBLIC FIRMS

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Abstract

Numerous earlier research has examined the relationship between information disclosure and the cost of equity, but the conclusions are inconclusive. Several research indicated a negative correlation, while others found a positive correlation or no correlation. By applying the threshold effect model to the data of 96 companies in a developing stock market such as Vietnam - we discovered that there is a standard threshold for the disclosure of information, and for companies that fall below this threshold, improving the disclosure of information will reduce the required rate of return for investors. This threshold is only observed for the enterprise's overall disclosure index and management information, however financial and investor information does not reveal the existence of a threshold impacting investors' required rate of return. Additionally, the study demonstrated that efforts to give information beyond the common level have a negligible impact on the expected rate of return for investors.

Keywords: *cost of equity, information disclosure, threshold model*

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Botosan (2006), an investor's required rate of return or cost of equity is the minimum rate of return required by an equity investor to provide capital to the company, or it can also be described as the risk-adjusted discount rate that an investor applies to expected future cash flows to arrive at the current stock price. For financial disclosure, Gibbins et al. (1990) defined it as any deliberate release of financial (and non-financial) information, whether numerical or qualitative, required or voluntary, or via formal or informal channels. There are different means for companies to disclose information such as annual reports, conference calls, analyst presentations, investor relations, interim reports, prospectuses, press releases, websites, etc. The corporate annual report is considered a very important official disclosure vehicle, although on its own is not sufficient in the capital market context (Marston and Shrides, 1991; Epstein and Palepu, 1999; Hope, 2003a), since other disclosure vehicles such as conference calls and interim reports can provide more timely disclosure. Understanding the relationship between the level of voluntary disclosures and the investors' required rate of return is important for management and investors. Many studies suggested that increasing the level of voluntary disclosures had an effect in reducing cost of equity capital or investors' rate of return (Botosan, 1997; Poshakwale and Courtis, 2005; Lambert et al, 2007; Leuz and Schrand, 2008;

Petrova et al, 2012...). This result can be explained in two routes: first, more voluntary disclosure improves stock market liquidity, reduces investor uncertainty and attracts long-term investment, thus lowering the cost of equity capital; second, enhancing disclosure level can lower the estimation risk of investors for future cash flows, thereby decreasing the cost of equity or investors' rate of return.

According to most studies, the relationship between information disclosure quality and investors' required rate of return, whether negatively or positively associated, follows the linear form. However, according to some other researches, this relationship is non-linear and there exists a threshold which limits the impact of the information disclosure on investors' required rate of return (Rikanovic, 2005; Amitage and Marston, 2007). In specific, this threshold-effect motivates the company to disclose information to a standard level at which increasing disclosure can lower investors' required rate of return, yet beyond a certain higher level, this relationship is minimized. And as far as we are aware, the number of studies exploring this threshold effect of information disclosure on investors' required rate of return is very small, especially in a developing stock market.

In general, in emerging stock markets, the number of F0 investors is relatively large, thus investors do not have profound knowledge about corporate financial analysis in order to make investment decisions. In these markets, investors mainly rely on information publicly provided by enterprises on financial statements and annual reports to analyze the corporate performance, thereby putting forward reasonable investment decisions. However, for the developing stock market, the quality of information disclosed by enterprises is not high in common. The reason is that in emerging markets, corporate governance is usually weak, hence management, or even the government, has greater power than shareholders. Therefore, the amount which investors contribute to the company's revenue is not really considerable for the board of management, and companies may disclose information in a less transparent manner. Low information disclosure can lead to decreased market liquidity, thereby resulting in higher broker fees and an increased level of price uncertainty. Investors who try to sell stocks in an illiquid market face substantial risks that their orders will not be filled at the current price, and the transactions will only go through at an unfavorable level. Therefore, investors in this kind of market usually require a higher rate of return.

Despite being a developing stock market, Vietnam stock exchange has affirmed its role by mobilizing about 2 million billion VND, contributing about 23% to total investment capital and supporting economic growth over the past 20 years. By the end of April 2021, the number of companies listed on HOSE and HNX reached about 752 companies compared to the number of 2 companies in 2000; market capitalization reached VND 4,998 trillion, accounting for 80.4% of GDP (State Securities Commission, 2021). However, compared with other Asian economies, this number is relatively small. For businesses that are planning to list, reducing the required rate of return of investors makes an important contribution to ensuring competitive advantages for businesses in the context of international integration and industry 4.0 revolution. This study which carries out the research in Vietnam can contribute a great level of reference value to pave the way for future similar studies in emerging market. The academic contributions of this study include: (1) Analyze the impact of information transparency on investors' required rate of return on a newly developed stock market like in Vietnam; (2) Use large, multi-disciplinary datasets with 96 businesses in Vietnam in 3 years; (3) Assess the

impact of different components of information (finance, governance, investor) on the investors' required rate of return; (4) Apply the threshold effect model to analyze whether increasing the disclosure quality below a certain threshold has a strong impact on reducing investors' required rate of return.

2. THEORITICAL BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical background

Information disclosure is considered to have an impact on investors' required rate of return through two main theories: the agency problem and the information problem. The agency problem states that because of the separation between ownership and corporate governance, investors have to face with agency costs. Accordingly, if both parties have the goal of maximizing benefits, managers do not always act in the best interests of investors (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). In order to overcome the above situation, investors use corporate governance mechanism as a measure to protect themselves. One of the effective corporate governance channels is to increase information transparency and disclosure, thereby reducing agency costs and reducing investors' required rate of return. Another mechanism of impact from information disclosure to required rate of return is through reducing information asymmetry in the market. The problem of asymmetric information occurs when enterprises hold information that investors cannot access and because the information objectives between investors and enterprises are not the same. Increasing the level of disclosure reduces information asymmetry and improves economic problems, in which trust plays an important role. Increasing transparency decrease the mistrust of investors with managers and uncertainty about the value of an investment, so investors have lower required returns on their investments (Rikanovic, 2005).

In addition, according to Amitage and Marston (2007), there is a certain disclosure threshold that analysts and fund managers expect a company to meet. The company may gain little benefit from disclosing information more than expected, but if the company fails to achieve a standard level of disclosure, the risk will increase significantly, which can raise the investors' required rate of return. Also according to this study, only when a company reaches the standard threshold of information disclosure, called "good practice", will the increase in information disclosure have the effect of reducing the required return of investors.

Figure 1. Maintaining the Disclosure Equilibrium

(Source: Rikanovic, 2005)

From an investor's point of view, companies should increase disclosure up to a level known as the disclosure equilibrium. The disclosure equilibrium is reached when an investor's required rate of return reaches its lowest point. In this equilibrium, agency costs are minimized, firm value is maximized, and the marginal agency cost is equal to the marginal increase in investor benefit from the reduction in required rate of return (Farinha, 2003). According to figure 1, the information gap premium decreases at a geometric rate. However, the curve shows that monitoring costs increase at a lower (linear) rate. Thus, the disclosure equilibrium will clearly depend on the marginal benefits of additional disclosure compared to the marginal monitoring costs (Evans and Sridhar, 2002).

However, to some extent, the nature of the standards publication effort is company-specific. If good practice is exceeded, investors' required rate of return will decrease by less and less, the reduction becoming very little or almost zero when the "best practice" level is exceeded. This final stage is inferred from the fact that neither practitioners nor academics consider the "information risk premium" to be a key element of an investor's required rate of return for listed companies. Thus, even if investors access with as much information as managers, an investor's required rate of return would not be significantly lower than the "best practice" disclosure approach (Amitage and Marston, 2007).

2.2. Literature review

A sizable body of theoretical research supports a link between the cost of capital or investors' required rate of return and disclosure. Many of the prior findings demonstrate that firms with more disclosure will face a lower cost of capital than firms with less disclosure. For example, as one of the pioneering study about this subject, Botosan (1997) used a series of data from the financial statements of 122 companies in 1990 to evaluate the relationship between the disclosure of information and the investors' required rate of return, in which the role of the analyst is emphasized. The results show that for firms with few analysts following, an increase in disclosure is related to a decrease in required rate of return. The studies of Lambert et al (2007) and Leuz and Schrand (2008) also support the conclusion of Botosan (1997). Lambert et al (2007) examine whether and how accounting information about a firm manifest in its cost of capital, despite the forces of diversification by using the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM). They found that an increase in information disclosure leads to an unambiguous decline in the cost of capital. Leuz and Schrand (2008) exploit an exogenous cost of capital shock that the Enron scandal in Fall 2001 created for other U.S. firms and analyze whether and how firms respond to this shock. Their results show that firms' disclosure responses are effective in reducing the impact of the transparency crisis on firms' costs of capital. With the similar results, other studies such as Richardson and Welker (2001), Hail (2002), Francis et al. (2005), Petrova et al. (2012), Li and Yang (2012), Cheynel (2013), Heflin et al. (2016)... also conclude that the information disclosure is negatively associated with investors' required rate of return.

However, this association between disclosure and cost of capital is not universal, there are certain studies which show the adverse or different results. Kim & Verrecchia (1991) show that the opposite relation might exist: firms with more disclosure have a higher cost of capital.

In their setting, increased disclosure motivates investors to seek additional private information, which leads to an increase in information asymmetry between informed and uninformed investors and a higher cost of capital. Elbannan and Elbannan (2015) studied the impact of governance disclosure on required rate of return of investors in commercial banks. With research data on 48 banks operating in India during the period 2000 - 2009, they conclude that the governance disclosure has a positive and statistically significant relationship with investors' required rate of return. Another analytical study (Zhang, 2001) demonstrates that, conditional on the setting, the link between the cost of capital and disclosure could be positive or negative, depending on the factors that cause variation in disclosure levels. Botosan & Plumlee (2002) investigated the relationship between cost of capital and annual report disclosures, timely disclosures and investor relations disclosures. While confirming the expected negative association for the annual report disclosures, their research showed that cost of capital is positively related to timely reporting actions, and they did not find association between cost of equity financing and investor relations disclosures.

Though the results are mixed, most studies researching on the impact of disclosure quality on investors' required rate of return only demonstrate a linear relationship between these two elements. There are very few studies suggesting that this relationship is non-linear, which means that the effect of disclosure on investors' required rate of return is only significant to a certain level. Rikanovic (2005) conducted a survey of 200 large German enterprises (by market value) about the amount of time and effort that managers spend on investor relation activities, with the aim of is to find reasons to promote the voluntary disclosure of information by enterprises. The results show that an increase of 1 standard deviation of financial information quality reduces investors' required return by 1.3%; and to be able to reduce equity sustainably, a carefully designed information quality strategy needs to reach an equilibrium and should focus on retaining current investors to provide a sustainable investor base with high loyalty and foresight. In a different direction, Armitage and Marston (2007) studied the views of financial managers on the relationship between the level of information quality and investors' required rate of return. Using qualitative research methods, the authors interviewed CFOs of 16 companies from November 2005 to June 2006. Interview results show that most CFOs do not believe in a clear relationship between disclosure level and investors' required rate of return, and insist that the impact of information disclosure on reducing the cost of equity is only to a certain extent, when the level of information quality reaches the "good practice" level, the impact of information quality will gradually decrease and have no impact until the "best practice" level is reached. Hsieh et al (2019) determined whether there are any discernible variations in the relationship between accounting quality and the cost of capital that may be attributable to the level of institutional ownership. They used data on 64 listed firms in Taiwan covering the period from 2000 to 2017 and provided clear evidence to suggest that the relationship between accounting quality and the cost of capital does indeed vary with changes in the level of institutional ownership. Thus, they affirmed that a non-linear relationship between accounting quality and the cost of capital seems more appropriate than the traditionally used linear relationship.

To date, studies on the non-linear relationship between information quality and the investors' required rate of return is still very limited. Especially, there are not any researches

that investigate this link in an emerging stock market like Vietnam. Therefore, within the scope of research in listed companies on Vietnam stock exchange, the authors realized that conducting this study is very necessary to clarify the relationship between reported information quality and investors' required rate of return, with the aim of going beyond the general finding within the extant literature of a linear relationship between disclosure quality and the cost of capital or investors' required rate of return. Through the results, we expect that the enterprises can appropriately improve the quality of information disclosure, thus contributing to lower required return from investors.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data collection

The objective of this study is to evaluate the impact of reported information disclosure and investors' required rate of return in listed companies on the Vietnam stock exchange. With this objective, the enterprises selected in the research sample must be (1) companies that have been officially listed on the two exchanges of Vietnam, HOSE and HNX, the study does not consider the enterprises listed on UPCOM or unlisted enterprises on the market; (2) businesses that are independent and still operating, and trading on the market as of December 31, 2020, and are not branches of other companies; (3) enterprises must have enough data for the variables listed in the model; (4) especially, to calculate stock beta, the companies need to have stock price data for 3 years prior to the time of research. This significantly reduces the study sample.

Regarding the research time, the research group chose 3 different years to collect data, that is 2013, 2016, and 2019 because (1) the improvement of the information disclosure of a company is quite slow, so the collection of annual data is not necessary, instead choosing to collect data in separating years will save time and still ensure enough necessary information, (2) select the time of 2013, 2016 and 2019 because in 2012 and 2015, the Ministry of Finance respectively issued two new circulars regulating information disclosure on the Vietnam stock exchange, which is Circular No. 52/2012/TT-BTC dated April 5, 2012, and Circular No. 144/2015/TT-BTC dated October 6, 2015. Therefore, the authors want to examine the impact of these circulars on the quality of information disclosure of listed companies after 1 year of being issued.

Based on the above exclusion method, the number of enterprises eligible for the study is 96 firms (Table 1).

Table 1. Research sample

No	Levels that meet the research sample criteria	No of enterprises
1	Enterprises operating in Vietnam	3,587
2	Existing enterprises, excluding branches	2,541
3	Enterprises listed before January 1, 2011	529
4	Corporate shares are still listed on the market	357
5	Enterprises that fully meet the requirements of analytical data	96

3.2. Model specification

Amitage and Marston (2007) and Rikanovic (2005) showed that the impact of reported information disclosure on investors' required rate of return may not be linear, but will depend on the level of information disclosure at the time of reviewing. Specifically, according to the above authors, each industry has a standard of information transparency, which is at the point of "good practice". If the company's information disclosure is below this common standard, investors will appreciate the level of risk when investing in the company, and will demand a higher level of return than other companies. This also means that companies that are below the common benchmark, when improving the information disclosure will help reduce investors' required rate of return quickly. However, efforts to disclose information beyond the general standard will only have a slight effect on the investors' required rate of return, and will ultimately result in little or no cost benefit, when the level of disclosure reached the "best practice" score. This is inferred from the fact that no experimentalists or scholars suggested that the "information risk premium" is a major component of investors' required rate of return. Therefore, even if an investor gets access to as much information as a manager, the investors' required rate of return will not be much below the disclosure level at the point of "best practice".

Figure 2. Effect of disclosure on the cost of equity

(Source: Armitage and Marston, 2007)

The above statement leads to the hypothesis that there exists at least a threshold on the level of disclosure, below which, increasing the quality of disclosure has a strong impact on reducing investors' required rate of return. Above that level, the impact of information disclosure quality on required rate of return of investors will gradually decrease. The research hypothesis is set up as follows:

(H1): There is a threshold on disclosed information quality in the impact of the disclosure level on investors' required rate of return.

To test the above hypothesis, the study used the fixed-effects threshold regression method. In case the model has a single threshold, the research model is expressed as below:

$$COE_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 QUA_{i,t}(q_{i,t} < \gamma) + \beta_2 QUA_{i,t}(q_{i,t} > \gamma) + \beta_3 BETA_{i,t} + \beta_4 MCAP_{i,t} + \beta_5 BTM_{i,t} + \beta_6 LEV_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

In which:

$COE_{i,t}$: cost of equity or investors' required rate of return of company i at time t;

$QUA_{i,t}$: information disclosure of company i at time t;

$BETA_{i,t}$: beta of stock i at time t;

$MCAP_{i,t}$: market capitalization of stock i at time t;

$BTM_{i,t}$: book-to-market ratio of stock i at time t;

$LEV_{i,t}$: debt-to-equity ratio or leverage ratio of company i at time t;

$\varepsilon_{i,t}$: model error;

$q_{i,t}$: threshold variable ("the information disclosure quality" variable);

γ : threshold value divides the model into 2 equations with the estimated coefficients of the information disclosure (QUA) being β_1 và β_2 . The model has an impact threshold if $\beta_1 \neq \beta_2$.

3.3. Estimation method

3.3.1. Measurement of the information disclosure

To measure the information disclosure of a company, this study applied the measurement method which is based on published information and reports. In specific, we used the method of building indexes of information transparency based on the studies of Patel et al. (2002), Ali et al (2007), Barron et al (1999), Hope (2003), in order to assess the level of transparency of information in Vietnamese enterprises, with the advantage of being based on available information, having high generalizability, being easy to apply and great reliability.

Since there is no official set of indicators for measuring information disclosure of listed companies in Vietnam, we structured our own set of indicators, based on reference to the index sets of prestigious international organizations and studies on the same topic. In this study, the authors chose to refer mainly to the Standard & Poor's (S&P) Transparency and Disclosure index because: (1) this index includes all 3 information components of information: financial, management, and investor-related, (2) in addition to the indicators on the number of disclosures, the S&P index also focuses on the indicators showing the quality and the

usefulness of information disclosed by enterprises such as forecast on the following year's revenue, accounting standards, information on market, market share, industry information, detailed information on the board of directors (occupation, time involved in management)... The Standard & Poor's Transparency and Disclosure Index has been trusted and used by many researchers to assess the information disclosure quality in enterprises, such as Patel and Dallas (2002) (research in the USA), Asky and Kosedag (2006) (Istanbul), Othman and Zeghai (2010) (Middle East and North Africa)...

The Standard & Poor's Index measures a company's level of information transparency based on a search in the company's annual report for the presence of component indicators. This set includes 98 indicators; however, the authors omitted a number of indicators that are not suitable with the current situation of Vietnam and developed a set including 79 indicators (of which 31 items are related to financial information and accounting standards, 30 items related to management information, and 18 items related to investors). For each indicator, the company that discloses relevant information will have a value of 1, while the company that does not disclose will have a value of 0.

Table 2. Measuring the quality of information disclosed by enterprises

Variables	Name	Explanation	Data sources	References
FIN	Financial Information Disclosure Index	Average of 31 criteria in financial information disclosure	Company reports	S&P Transparency & Disclosure index
MAN	Management Information Disclosure Index	Average of 30 criteria in management information disclosure	Company reports	S&P Transparency & Disclosure index
INV	Investor Information Disclosure Index	Average of 18 criteria in investor information disclosure	Company reports	S&P Transparency & Disclosure index
QUA	Investor Information Disclosure Index	Average of MAN, INV, FIN	Company reports	S&P Transparency & Disclosure index
QUAlev	Weighted Investor Information Disclosure Index	Weighted average (by number of indicators) of MAN, INV, FIN	Company reports	S&P Transparency & Disclosure index

3.3.2. Estimation of investor's required rate of return

We adopt the Fama-French model as the measurement for investors' required rate of return by calculating the expected return extracted from the model's formula.

In the three-factor model of Fama and French (1992), in addition to the market beta of the CAPM, the two authors added two explanatory factors for the cost of equity, namely the market capitalization of a company and the book-to-market ratio:

$$R_i - R_f = \alpha_i + \beta_1(R_m - R_f) + \beta_2SMB + \beta_3HML + \varepsilon_i \quad (E1)$$

In which:

SMB: Return of small-cap stocks minus Return of large-cap stocks (small minus large).

HML: Return of a portfolio of stocks with high book-to-market ratio minus Return of a portfolio of stocks with low book-to-market ratio (high minus low).

SMB and HML data are usually collected from the website: Kenneth R. French. Here, the data on the indicators in the model are calculated for 23 countries from 1991-2020. However, this dataset is not available for the Vietnam stock exchange. Therefore, we recalculated these data based on the original study by Fama and French (1992).

First, we divided listed companies into six groups based on market capitalization (median) and book-to-market ratio (at the 30th and 70th percentiles) annually: (i) Small market cap - Low book-to-market ratio (S/L); (ii) Small market cap - Medium book-to-market ratio (S/M); (iii) Small market cap - High book-to-market ratio (S/H); (iv) Big market cap - Low book-to-market ratio (B/L); (v) Big market cap - Medium book-to-market ratio (B/M); and (vi) Big market cap - High book-to-market ratio (B/H). The results show that, out of 96 enterprises, there is 1 enterprise in the S/L group, there are 6 in the S/M group, 11 in the S/H group, 52 in the B/L group, 65 in the B/M group, and 41 in the B/H group.

Second, we calculate daily SMB and HML data using daily dividend-adjusted stock returns by running the following equations:

$$SMB = \frac{S/L + S/M + S/H}{3} - \frac{B/L + B/M + B/H}{3} \quad (E2)$$

$$HML = \frac{B/H + S/H}{2} - \frac{B/L + S/L}{2} \quad (E3)$$

Third, we estimate investors' required rate of return according to the Fama-French method based on equation 2, this variable is called FAMA. If less than 0, investors' required rate of return estimated will be eliminated.

For each firm-year t observation, the model parameters are estimated using daily data for year t-1. We then add the market return and the risk-free rate for year t to the Fama and French regressions to calculate the expected return.

3.3.3. Measurement of control variables

Control variables of the model include: stock beta, market capitalization, book-to-market ratio, and financial leverage.

Beta coefficient is estimated through regression of stock returns with market returns based on daily data for 3 consecutive years. The study does not directly use the estimated beta, also known as levered beta, because the use of levered beta can cause the model to be simultaneously affected by the financial leverage and market risks (Botosan et al., 2011). Asset beta, or unlevered beta, can help eliminate this problem. The asset beta coefficient is calculated based on the study of Botosan and Plumlee (2005) according to the following equation:

$$\beta_U = \frac{\beta_L}{(1 + Total\ liabilities / Total\ equity)} \quad (E4)$$

In which:

β_u : asset beta (unlevered beta)

β_L : levered beta

Market capitalization is measured as the logarithmic value of the market capitalization of stock *i* at the end of the accounting period.

Financial leverage ratio is measured by debt-to-equity ratio;

The book-to-market ratio is measured by the value of common stock with voting rights divided by the market capitalization at the end of the accounting period.

The above control variables are collected from the financial statements of the companies in the sample.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Tables 3 and 4 show descriptive statistics and correlation matrix between the variables used in the study. Descriptive statistics show that the average investors' required rate of return is 13.9%/year. The correlation matrix shows that the variables used in the same model have a low level of correlation (below 0.7). Variables with a correlation higher than 0.7 such as between the disclosure index variable and its component indicators, are used interchangeably in the estimation models.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics

Variables	Symbol	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
Investors' required rate of return according to Fama-French	FAMA	0.139	0.140	0.05	1.391
Information disclosure	QUA	0.453	0.092	0.247	0.707
Weighted information disclosure	QUAlev	0.503	0.108	0.243	0.787
Financial information disclosure	FIN	0.606	0.108	0.333	0.866
Management information disclosure	MAN	0.450	0.135	0.096	0.806
Investor information disclosure	INV	0.453	0.167	0	1
Asset beta	BETA _u	0.262	0.247	-0.449	1.477
Logarithmic value of market capitalization	MCAP	12.292	1.811	8.517	19.722
Book-to-market ratio	BTM	1.377	1.113	0.033	12.182
Financial leverage	LEV	2.325	6.526	0.008	98.18

(Source: Authors' calculation)

Table 4. Correlation coefficients between variables in the model

	FAMA	QUA	QUAlev	FIN	MAN	INV	BETAu	MCAP	BTM	LEV
FAMA	1									
QUA	-0.03	1								
QUAlev	-0.04	0.99	1							
FIN	-0.07	0.70	0.67	1						
MAN	0.03	0.81	0.75	0.29	1					
INV	-0.07	0.78	0.85	0.42	0.45	1				
BETAu	0.45	-0.04	-0.04	-0.04	-0.02	-0.04	1			
MCAP	-0.19	-0.14	-0.11	-0.07	-0.23	0.02	0.19	1		
BTM	0.09	-0.01	-0.02	0.05	0.00	-0.07	0.10	-0.37	1	
LEV	-0.05	-0.05	-0.05	-0.02	-0.05	-0.05	-0.18	0.09	-0.06	1

(Source: Authors' calculation)

4.2. The threshold impact of information disclosure on investors' required rate of return

The study ran the bootstrap 300 test, which was introduced by Hansen (1996). This test simulates the LRT test of the distribution asymptotically with the normal distribution, in order to determine the number of thresholds in the model. The following table presents the Hansen (1996) test results with the following cases: the dependent variable is the investors' required rate of return according to the Fama-French method (FAMA), and the threshold variables are the overall information disclosure (QUA), financial information disclosure (FIN), management information disclosure (MAN), and investor information disclosure (INV). If the P-value <0.05, we reject the hypothesis H0 about the linear model and accept the hypothesis H1 that the model exists threshold. For the cases accepting the hypothesis H1 about the existence of one threshold in the model, the authors continue to test the existence of two thresholds.

Table 5. Determination of the number of thresholds in the model of information disclosure affecting on investors' required rate of return

Test	Threshold value	F - Statistics		Critical value of F		
		F	P-value	1%	5%	10%
FAMA - QUA						
F1	$\gamma_1 = 0.4719$	21.59	0.010	21.2288	16.8101	14.1764
F2	$\gamma_1 = 0.4719$	16.53	0.103	24.1133	19.2910	16.7645
	$\gamma_2 = 0.2921$	6.03	0.600	22.2894	17.4498	14.2069
FAMA - FIN						
F1	$\gamma_1 = 0.4667$	4.31	0.5833	17.1978	14.2411	12.2227
FAMA - MAN						
F1	$\gamma_1 = 0.5161$	22.49	0.0067	11.6043	13.7596	20.6986
F2	$\gamma_1 = 0.2581$	29.60	0.000	21.6932	15.0574	13.1803
	$\gamma_2 = 0.5161$	6.03	0.256	72.8813	43.7479	16.0497
FAMA - INV						
F1	$\gamma_1 = 0.2778$	6.49	0.2267	16.1763	10.4098	9.0331

(Source: Authors' calculation)

When considering the investors' required rate of return according to the FAMA method and the overall information disclosure, with the hypothesis that the model exists a threshold (F1), p-value is lower than 0.05, thus we reject hypothesis H0 about the linear model and accept the hypothesis H1 about the model with one threshold. With the hypothesis that the model exists two thresholds (F2), p-value is higher than 0.05, thus there is no basis to reject hypothesis H0 about the model with one threshold. Therefore, the one-threshold model is accepted with a p-value of 0.600.

The threshold value for the measured overall disclosure of information is 0.4719. This threshold divides the research sample into 2 groups, including the group of enterprises with information disclosure above the threshold of 0.4719 ($QUA > 0.4719$) and enterprises with information disclosure below the threshold of 0.4719 ($QUA < 0.4719$). In 2013, there were 41/96 enterprises with information disclosure exceeding the threshold of 0.4719, this number in 2016 and 2019 was 42/96 and 47/96 enterprises, respectively.

In the next step, the study ran the regression model of threshold fixed-effect of the overall information disclosure on the investors' required rate of return, with the number of thresholds determined as 1, using robust regression to exclude the multicollinearity capability. The estimated results presented in the table below show that the overall information disclosure has the effect of reducing investors' required rate of return. However, this impact varies according to the level of information disclosure. Specifically, companies that are below the common benchmark, when improving the information disclosure, will help decrease investors' required rate of return quickly, with the regression coefficient at -0.768. However, efforts to disclose information beyond the general standard will only have a slight effect on investors' required rate of return, with a regression coefficient of -0.523. This result confirms the hypothesis about the threshold effect of information disclosure on investors' required rate of return, and is consistent with the studies of Amitage and Marston (2007) and Rikanovic (2005).

Table 6. Threshold regression results on the impact of information disclosure on investors' required rate of return

	(1)	(2)
c.QUA		
$QUA < 0.4719$	-0.768**	
	(0.317)	
$QUA \geq 0.4719$	-0.523*	
	(0.285)	
c.MAN		
$MAN < 0.5161$		-0.395*
		(0.221)
$MAN \geq 0.5161$		-0.086
		(0.180)
BETA	0.297***	0.298***
	(0.0379)	(0.038)
MCAP	-0.083***	-0.084***
	(0.011)	(0.011)

	(1)	(2)
BTM	-0.0476*** (0.0145)	-0.039*** (0.014)
LEV	0.001 (0.001)	0.001 (0.001)
Cons	1.540*** (0.205)	1.365*** (0.187)
R square	0.4185	0.4221
No. of observations	288	288

Note: strong standard deviation in parentheses.

*, **, *** correspond to the significance level of 1%, 5%, and 10%.

(Source: Authors' calculation)

More specifically, on each component of the overall information disclosure, the management information disclosure has a threshold impact on the investors' required rate of return with an estimated number of thresholds of 1. The threshold value for management information disclosure is 0.5161, dividing the study sample into 2 groups. Out of a total of 96 enterprises in Vietnam, there are 58 enterprises with information disclosure exceeding the above threshold. The results of the threshold effect model show that, for firms with a management information disclosure below 0.5161, there exists a negative relationship with statistical significance at 10% between the management information disclosure and the investors' required rate of return. When the level of management information exceeds 0.516, the coefficient of management information disclosure is negative. However, this coefficient is not statistically significant, which means there is not enough evidence to establish a relationship between the disclosure of management information and the required rate of return of investors in Vietnam with a level of information disclosure higher than 0.516%.

Control variables in the model such as asset beta, market capitalization, book to market ratio, financial leverage, are all statistically significant at 1% with investors' required rate of return measured. The beta shows the correlation between stock risk and market risk, the higher the beta, the greater the stock risk. Therefore, investors demand a higher level of return. For market capitalization, large-cap companies have lower investors' required rate of return than small-cap companies, at the 1% significance level. As explained by Cavaliere and Costa (1999), investors face lower information asymmetry, due to the consistency, ease of tracking, and accuracy of the information available when they interact with large companies, and consequently a lower level of risk. Similarly, book-to-market ratio has a negative relationship (with coefficients from -0.0476 to -0.039 and statistical significance at 1%) with investors' required rate of return. According to Fama and French (1998), stocks with large book-to-market ratio (value stocks) often have higher returns than stocks with small book-to-market ratio (growth stocks), thus value stocks have higher claim expectations. However, in Vietnam market, this trend is reversed, investors prefer to choose growth stocks over value stocks, leading to a higher return requirement for growth stocks. In contrast, the financial leverage has a positive and statistically significant relationship with the investors' required rate of return (coefficient 0.001 with significance level of 1%). The addition of financial leverage aims to calculating and evaluating the impact of financial risk on an investors' required rate of return.

Accordingly, investors perceive a company with a large debt-to-equity ratio as having a higher level of financial risk than a company with a low debt ratio, and they transfer this higher risk into the required returns. (Khurana and Raman, 2004; Botasan and Plumlee, 2005).

Whereas, the relationship between financial information disclosure and investment information disclosure with investors' required rate of return does not exist a threshold. In other words, the disclosure of financial information and the disclosure of investment information have a linear impact on the investors' required rate of return as in table 7. To explain this linear relationship, there can be 1 of 2 cases: (1) these indicators of information disclosure are quite similar between enterprises, thus there is no threshold, and (2) financial and investor information disclosure in Vietnamese enterprises is still low and has not reached the "good practice" level, so there is no threshold to reduce the impact of information disclosure on investors' required rate of return.

It can be seen in table 7, the investment information transparency index has stronger impact on investors' required rate of return, with a correlation coefficient ranging from -0.063 to -0.235 and significance level of 1% and 5%. This shows that investors are most interested in information transparency criteria such as major shareholders, the number of shares allowed to be issued, cross-ownership, company regulations, and reports at shareholder meetings... It is quite reasonable that investing information is the first communication channel between investors and enterprises, thus having the biggest influence on investors' perceptions.

Table 7. Results of estimating the impact of financial information disclosure and investment information disclosure on investors' required return

Variable	FAMA	
	(1)	(2)
FIN	-0.260 (0.215)	
INV		-0.235*** (0.089)
BETA	0.345*** (0.036)	0.349*** (0.035)
MCAP	-0.094*** (0.009)	-0.094*** (0.009)
BTM	-0.072*** (0.010)	-0.074*** (0.010)
LEV	0.001** (0.001)	0.001** (0.001)
Cons	1.572*** (0.181)	1.511*** (0.1411)
No. of observations	427	427
R-squared	0.484	0.495

Note: strong standard deviation in parentheses.

*, **, *** correspond to the significance level of 1%, 5%, and 10%.

(Source: Authors' calculation)

Moreover, when considering the linear impact of financial information disclosure on investors' required rate of return, it can be seen that financial information disclosure alone will not have the effect of reducing investors' required rate of return. The basic financial indicators such as quarterly financial statements, accounting regime... are mandatory criteria to be announced according to the regulations of the Securities Commission for listed companies on the market. Additional financial indicators such as implementation of financial statements in accordance with international accounting standards, expenses paid to auditors, business trends in the coming year... have not really received the attention of investors. However, it is clear that although the financial information disclosure alone has no impact on investors' required rate of return, this indicator combined into the overall indicator has a strong impact on the required rate of return. This means that investors are interested in the general picture of information transparency of enterprises.

Besides, when considering the difference between enterprises, the level of difference in financial information disclosure is quite low. With the investor information disclosure, the average level of enterprises in Vietnam is only about 47.54%. This is another indicator that has a very strong impact on investors' required rate of return, thus the quality of investor information in Vietnamese enterprises may be still low and has not reached the level of "good practice".

5. CONCLUSION

With the goal of developing the stock market in the long term, transparency in information and transaction costs, including required rate of return of investors, need to be improved in Vietnam. This study examines whether there exists at least a threshold on the level of information disclosure, below which, increasing the information disclosure has a strong impact on the reduction of investors' required rate of return. By using panel data from 96 companies listed on the Vietnam stock exchange during the three years of 2013, 2016 and 2019, this study found that the impact of information disclosure on investors' required rate of return is not linear. The results show that there is a standard threshold for information disclosure, which means that for companies below the common benchmark, improving disclosed information quality will reduce investors' required rate of return significantly. However, efforts to provide information beyond the general standard will only have a slight impact on investors' required rate of return. This result is appropriate with the studies of Amitage and Marston (2007) and Rikanovic (2005).

The limitations of this study include: (1) the panel analysis was performed over a period of only three years due to the limited data available, which prevented us from performing highly estimative models such as systematic GMM; (2) the analysis of the information disclosure is largely focused on the quantity of information, rather than directly measuring the accuracy of information; (3) subjectivity in developing a set of information disclosure indicators and selecting estimates to measure investors' required rate of return.

These limitations do not affect the overall quality of the research and may provide a starting point for future studies. Future studies may extend to other countries in the region and over a longer period of time; develop information quality measurement which focuses on analyzing not only the extent but also the accuracy of the information disclosed; and add

robustness tests related to disclosure metrics and investors' required rate of return measured by different methods. Finally, future studies may explore additional effects of disclosed information quality, such as its effect on WACC average investors' required rate of return, firm value, cost of debt, and market capitalization.

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EMPLOYEE JOB ATTITUDES AND BUSINESS RESILIENCE IN THE VIETNAMESE BANKING SECTOR POST-COVID 19

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Abstract

Business resilience is important for businesses in anticipating, surviving, and recovering from struggling against the turbulent environment. Business resilience not only helps businesses, especially banks, to stay relevant but also improves their ability to maintain their ability to withstand unexpected changes and reinforce their competitive advantage. The emergence of Covid 19 has created serious disruptions to the stability of society and economic activities, which severely impact businesses' sustainable operations including the banking sector. It has especially led to the job cutoff phenomenon and implicitly created instability and unpredictability of job conditions among existing employees, which negatively impacted their engagement, motivation, and job attitude at work. This negative feeling, indeed, may potentially last till post Covid era and negatively impact the resilience of business. This research thus examines the impact of employee job attitudes on business resilience in the Vietnamese banking sector in Vietnam. The findings are used for policy implications for commercial banks in Vietnam on how to improve resilience with engaging staff.

Keywords: *Job Attitudes, Business Resilience, Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Job Involvement, Banking Sector.*

I. INTRODUCTION

After experiencing the outbreak of the Covid 19, Vietnam's economy has seen a remarkable recovery of economic activities. Specifically, the GDP growth rate of Vietnam has seen a rise up to 8,02% in 2022, (Tu and Phuong, 2023), which is much higher compared to 2,6% of the 2021 number due to the pandemic (Onishi, 2021). However, despite all the recovery, the emergence of Covid 19 has created serious disruptions to the stability of society and economic activities, which severely impact businesses' sustainable operations including the banking sector (Mckibbin and Fernando, 2020). It has especially led to the job cutoff phenomenon and implicitly created instability and unpredictability of job conditions among existing employees which negatively impacted their engagement, motivation, and job attitude at work (Reisel et al, 2010). This negative feeling, indeed, may potentially last till post Covid era and negatively impact the resilience of business (Akkermans et al., 2020).

Business resilience is important for businesses in anticipating, surviving, and recovering from struggling against the turbulent environment (Aldianto et al., 2021). Business resilience not only helps businesses, especially banks, to stay relevant but also improves their ability to maintain to withstand unexpected changes and reinforce their competitive advantage

(*Khajehpour et al., 2021*). Additionally, the underlying idea of business resilience lies in the human factor, in which employees are considered an indispensable factor in determining how well the business responds to sudden change (*Horne and Orr, 1997*). However, the job cutoff due to Covid 19 has raised the problem of job insecurity and struck up the negative feeling of losing a job among existing employees in the banking sector. This, consequently, affects their job attitudes and so the resilience of banks. According to *Witte (1999)*, people with a greater degree of job insecurity have a tendency to express a lower degree of mental health, which is considered equivalent to the unemployed. *Witte (2005)* also stated that job insecurity can severely impact organizational commitment in specific and the job attitude of employees in general, which is detrimental to the resilience of the business. As a result, the change in employee job attitudes after the pandemic has severely impacted the work outcome as well as business resilience, even further in the post-pandemic moment. Job attitude is considered of significant importance since job attitude is the origin of work and job behaviors, which can regulate job performance and further determine the operational effectiveness of an organization including banks (*Wang, 2008*).

The banking industry, like other industries, has been affected severely by the outbreak of Covid 19, which led to unprecedented changes in its organizational structure and operation. It has seriously impacted on the company's stability and led to serial job reductions and salary cutoffs. Specifically, within the Vietnam market, in coping with the emergence of the pandemic, banks have conducted serial job reductions, in which around 9000 employees have been laid off only in the year 2020 (*Anh, 2020*). It potentially leads to an increase in feelings of job insecurity among existing employees and negatively impacts their job attitude even in the post-pandemic era, which largely affects the resilience of businesses within the banking industry. Therefore, the main aim of this research is to find out the implication of employees' job attitudes in relation to organizational resilience in the banking industry in Vietnam. Specifically, this study aims at delving into the correlation between employees' job attitudes and business resilience in post-Covid 19 in the banking sector in Vietnam. Within the scope of this research, employee's job attitudes will be divided into 3 main areas including organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and job involvement and each area will be tested to identify its relationship with business resilience for the purpose of verifying whether the changes in each attitude will correlate with the resilience of the business. Moreover, through the understanding of this relation, this research will be beneficial for the bank in Vietnam to propose effective policies to promote positive job attitudes in employees that are necessary for facilitating business resilience.

There is still scarce research that has been proposed to test the relationship between 3 aspects of job attitudes and business resilience which most of the research only pays attention to testing one facet of job attitudes such as organizational commitment, job involvement, and organizational resilience like the research of *Liu et al (2021)*, or research of *Somers (2009)*. Moreover, there still is a lack of research focus on this linkage subject to the banking industry when some research tends to be conducted in hospital scenarios like *Clark et al,.. (2020)*. Therefore, this research will bring forward the general perspectives and knowledge of employee attitudes and their linkage to the organizational resilience of companies within the banking sector.

The study is structured as follows: Part II is for literature review, Part III is for methodology, followed by Part IV which focuses on results and discussions, and Part V with conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

The Covid-19 pandemic, in fact, has posed serious disruptions to economic activities and sustainable operation of businesses (*Mckibbin and Fernando, 2020*) including banks. It led to serious job cutoffs among companies within the banking industry which created negative feelings among existing employees and affected their job attitudes (*Reisel et al, 2010*). Besides that, this phenomenon potentially still lasts even in the post-Covid 19 eras which might severely impact the organizational resilience of companies in the banking industry (*Akkermans et al., 2020*). As a result, this research will aim to dig deeper into the association of employee job attitudes toward the resilience of business as well as identify how job attitudes of employees impact organizational resilience in the banking industry in Vietnam post-Covid 19.

Theoretical Background

Business Resilience (BR)

Business Resilience is a multi-dimensional concept that has been defined in several meanings. Specifically, business resilience is conceptualized as the company's capability to bounce back to a stable condition after going through disruptions (*Bhamra et al, 2011*). Others defined business resilience as the capability of one business to maintain its sustainable operations and make essential adjustments to help the business to overcome an unexpected crisis (*Vogus et al, 2007*). Moreover, Horne and Orr (1997) considered business resilience as a group of people, groups, and systems in an organization that works together in response to unexpected change, in which they stress the role of the human aspect in reinforcing the resilience of the business. Additionally, communication and teamwork between employees have also been considered significant indicators of the resilience of businesses that reinforce the capability and flexibility of the business as a drive to respond under pressure (*Jones, 2015*).

Lengnick-Hall et al (2011) have accentuated resilience as an indispensable aspect for a business to stay relevant and develop its capacities, which facilitates the business to effectively overcome unprecedented and unpredicted sudden events and get benefits from its event rather than fail to catastrophes. Additionally, *Hodges (2017)* indicated that a resilience facet of business not only brings back the ability to effectively respond to changes but also increases the sense of well-being in employees that stimulates the maintenance of business performance levels. Organizational resilience, for that reason, is considered an essential thing for maintaining the sustainable operation of businesses including companies in the banking industry, specifically after experiencing the Covid-19 pandemic. The banking system generally is an utmost important tool for smoothing financial activities in the market in which the advent of a crisis might seriously threaten their financial stability and national economy as well (*Field, 2017*). *Prorokowski (2011)* further stated that a lack of studies revolving around organizational resilience subject to the banking sector might potentially result in the deficient capacity of banks to cope with unexpected changes.

Job Attitudes (JA)

Job attitudes are considered among the most long-standing aspect subject to organizational psychology which concentrates on investigating the employee's job attitudes and their importance toward the success of businesses. Employees' job attitudes are an assessment of individuals in expressing their feelings, beliefs, and alignment with their job (Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller, 2012). The Person-Environment Fit Theory proposes that individuals will commit to their job if they fit well with the current working environment, which can have a positive impact on the job attitude that leads to an increase in work outcomes and improve organizational resilience (Furnham and Schaeffer, 1984).

Job attitudes are referred to as the personal significance toward job-related targets (Riketta, 2008). Besides that, Eagly and Chaiken (1993) demonstrated job attitudes as the psychological proclivity of individuals in evaluating the business with favor or disfavor, in which employee job attitudes could be categorized into three major components including job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and job involvement (Newman and Harrison, 2008).

Organizational Commitment (OC)

Organizational Commitment is a concept that has been defined in several meanings, Allen and Meyer (1996) considered organizational commitment as the emotional bonds of the employee toward their organization, in which they are goal-oriented in their work within the organization and less likely to quit their job. Additionally, the notion of organizational commitment specifically centers on the devotion of employees toward their organization which is subject to their readiness to sacrifice for the success of the organization (Hogan et al, 2013). As a result, promoting organizational commitment is considered a remarkable factor for companies including banks to retain talented employees. Moreover, Horne and Orr (1997) stress the importance of commitment in employees as an indispensable factor in helping to maintain and build trust among members when employees work together, which further influences employees' productivity and motivation.

The importance of employee commitment has been stressed in the working environment since the situational approaches of increasing competition and constant technological development as well as unexpected crisis. In the service industry like the banking industry, employees who are highly committed to their business tend to be more devoted to the success of the bank via excellent customer service (Mohsan et al., 2015). Turkkan and Yalcintas (2017) further accentuate the organizational commitment in employees as the main tool for facilitating a coordinated atmosphere among employees within the business that is beneficial to group the entire workforce in striving for the goals of the organization.

Job Satisfaction (JS)

Job satisfaction is among the most studied factors in the field of social science related to the organizational environment. Specifically, it is conceptualized as the pleasurable emotional state of employees in terms of their job experiences or working conditions (Locke, 1969). Job satisfaction is considered a dynamic structure that can change in exposure to environmental and working conditions (Westover and Taylor, 2010). Following this logic, Eagly and Chaiken (1993) demonstrated that individuals who are highly job-satisfied tend to positively engage in

supporting their work, and individuals who are low job-satisfied tend to engage in opposing their work. *Hodson (1997)* demonstrated that socialization and relations in the workplace are key contributors to building employee job satisfaction and well-being, which increase their productivity. Moreover, *Cho and Johanson (2008)* further indicated that coworker-share in employees has them overcome problems at a job, which is considered an indicator of job satisfaction on employees.

Satisfied employees act as a role of an important asset to the organizations, equivalently, and also a necessary asset to the operation of banks. Specifically, when employees are highly satisfied, it hence results in sustainable operations and also an increase in the resilience of the banks. *Bhardwaj et al. (2020)* indicated that job satisfaction among employees has positively correlated with increased productivity as well as devotion to the bank which largely contributes to the effective operation of a bank that further reinforces its sustainability and resilience.

Job involvement (JI)

Job involvement is conceptualized as “the degree to which a person is identified psychologically with his work, or the importance of work in his total self-image” (*Lodahl and Kejner, 1965*). Besides that, *Lawler and Hall (1970)* referred to job involvement in individuals as a psychological attachment to their work. For that reason, *DeCarufel and Schaan (1990)* demonstrated that highly involved individuals tend to place their job in the center of their interests which is reflected in the popular phrase “I live, eat, breath my job”. However, individuals with a low degree of job involvement tend to place their interests in front of organizational interests (*Hogan et al., 2013*). In contrast, highly involved employees are inclined to put more effort into one job, which results in higher job performance (*Brown, 1996*). Moreover, individuals with a higher degree of job involvement tend to be subject to higher network centrality, which indeed helps to promote further the degree of trustworthiness among other coworkers and results in a greater degree of team collaboration (*Zhang et al., 2009*). For that reason, promoting the formation of job involvement among employees is considered the utmost contribution to the effective operation of the company including banks.

Clardy (1996) considered developing job involvement is considered a crucial organizational objective. He claims it is the primary source of organizational functioning effectiveness to organizations, and it is true with banks throughout covid 19 pandemic when they experience the shock. *Srivastava and Pathak (2019)* stated that the most important concern for the banking industry in the possible event of unexpected events is to invest in developing human capital that further facilitates employees’ job involvement in which they indicated that the success of banking organizations depends upon the employee’s hard-working and job involvement.

Hypothesis Development

Organizational Commitment (OC) and Business Resilience (BR)

Organizational Commitment as described above is the devotion and emotional bond of employees toward their business, which is related to their readiness to sacrifice for the sake of the business. In addition, *Horne and Orr (1997)* further demonstrated organizational commitment as an important factor for companies in striking up business resilience.

Specifically, the authors refer to organizational commitment in employees as the willingness to work together through uncertainties to maintain a sustainable operation, and from that promotes business resilience. Moreover, the research conducted by *Liu et al (2021)* indicated that organizational commitment has an influence on organizational effectiveness, which can directly, and positively impact organizational resilience. For that reason, to contribute more to this assessment with a concentration on the banking sector which experienced unexpected change throughout covid 19 related to their resilient problems, I hypothesize that organizational commitment has a positive correlation with business resilience.

Hypothesis 1: Organizational Commitment has a positive correlation with business resilience.

Job Satisfaction (JS) and Business Resilience (BR)

According to the above section, a business is considered a resilient business when it has the ability to thrive under organizational unrest, and challenging situations (*Bhamra et al, 2011*). Business resilience focuses on the importance of both social and intellectual capital, which is all for long-term organizational effective operation (*Lampel et al, 2014*). Moreover, resilience in the business allows employees to be able to better struggle against uncertainties, improve their knowledge and promote their job satisfaction and engagement at work (*Hallak et al, 2018*). In contrast, *Zhang et al. (2020)* indicated that employees with a greater degree of job satisfaction were positively related to higher workplace engagement and also higher resilience. Moreover, there is also research like the research of *Clark et al (2020)* has found that employee job satisfaction is positively associated with resilience. However, this statement and research only revolve around employee resilience rather than business resilience. Despite that, *Annarelli and Nonino (2016)* indicated the importance of employee resilience as a background for fostering organizational resilience. As a result, it is expected that employees will be satisfied with a resilient business, which easily adapt to the change in the working environment in the banking sector and addresses business uncertainty, especially in post covid 19 environment, after the sudden change in business operation as well as all of the banking sectors that disrupts serious their economic activities. Therefore, I hypothesized that job satisfaction has a positive correlation with organizational resilience.

Hypothesis 2: Job satisfaction has a positive correlation with business resilience.

Job Involvement (JI) and Business Resilience (BR)

Lodahl (1965) demonstrated job involvement is the internalization of values revolving around the goodness or significance of work toward the value of the individual which is related to the socialization process of the employee. Employee involvement and empowerment are necessary for employees to display proper attitudes and behavior when facing turbulent, chaotic environments and conditions (*Kantur and İşeri-Say, 2012*). They further demonstrated employee job involvement as an effective tool for stimulating personal resilience which explicitly facilitates organizational effective functioning and organizational resilience. There is research like *Somers (2009)* has given ORPS (Organizational Resilience Potential Scale) to measure the resilience of a business in which he found that job involvement positively associates with the effective organizational response of a business and also organizational resilience. As a result, it is expected that highly job-involved employees will be an essential

part of helping businesses, specifically banking companies in overcoming the sudden change in the working environment, hence, I hypothesize that job involvement has a positive correlation with business resilience.

Hypothesis 3: Job involvement has a positive correlation with the resilience of business.

3. METHODOLOGY

Respondents, Sample Size, and Location

The participants in this study are bank staff at various commercial banks in Vietnam. Questionnaires have been developed based on the study of Jones (2015); Allen and Meyer (1990); Spector (1985); and Lodahl (1965). Questionnaires were sent via Google form and direct meetings, after several emails requested for help. 100 valid responses were obtained for further analysis.

Variables

Variables are considered the measurement components in quantitative research that contains two different kinds of variables ranging from independent variables to dependent variables. Within the range of this research, there are 4 variables in total which 3 out of 4 variables are independent (job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and job involvement), and the left one is a dependent variable which is organizational resilience.

Statistic Method

Cronbach's alpha is considered a measure that is utilized for analyzing and interpreting the reliability of variables within the model, which values typically ranging from 0 to 1, with a value of above 0.7 deemed excellent. In this study, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) is going to be tapped into to examine and interpret the gathered data through the SPSS statistical application (SPSS-EFA). The EFA model will evaluate the correlation between three independent variables and a single dependent variable. The KMO test is used to ensure the sufficiency and validity of data for component analysis, specifically, a value that is placed between the range of 0.5 to 1 represents the optimum, and a value of below 0.5 represents inappropriate data. Barlett's Sphericity is also a coefficient that is also utilized to examine the reliability and validity of collected data which a Sig of 0.05 or lower is represented well. Multi-regression is the statistical analysis that is used for examining the correlation between multiple independent factors toward a single dependent (*Moore et al., 2006*).

4. RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive Analytics

The researcher, throughout the process of distributing the questionnaire of 20 items related to the research topic to employees in bank branches located in Ha Noi city. The questionnaire is distributed via both online and offline methods, specifically, it is collected through Google Form in terms of Online method, and direct meetings regarding offline within bank branches in Ha Noi. As a result, the research collected 106 samples in total with 38 samples online and 68 offline with a feedback rate of 100%. After data filtering, 6 unsuitable feedbacks were eliminated to ensure the effective analysis of collected data, resulting in 100

valid observations. Cronbach alphas are presented in Table 2, which shows the validity of all the instruments.

Table 1: Description 6-Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics									
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
BR1	100	3	5	4.38	.599	-.384	.241	-.655	.478
BR2	100	3	5	4.42	.535	-.077	.241	-1.159	.478
BR3	100	2	5	3.99	.703	-.341	.241	.085	.478
BR4	100	2	5	3.87	.787	-.272	.241	-.349	.478
BR5	100	2	5	3.95	.880	-.626	.241	-.173	.478
OC1	100	3	5	4.35	.609	-.359	.241	-.639	.478
OC2	100	3	5	4.26	.645	-.304	.241	-.677	.478
OC3	100	2	5	3.88	.769	-.334	.241	-.153	.478
OC4	100	2	5	3.99	.674	-.190	.241	-.144	.478
OC5	100	1	5	3.83	.829	-.429	.241	.329	.478
JS1	100	2	5	4.20	.651	-.448	.241	.327	.478
JS2	100	3	5	4.22	.629	-.203	.241	-.575	.478
JS3	100	2	5	4.02	.738	-.185	.241	-.693	.478
JS4	100	3	5	3.96	.634	.032	.241	-.459	.478
JS5	100	2	5	3.93	.685	-.294	.241	.167	.478
J11	100	2	5	3.76	.842	-.242	.241	-.494	.478
J12	100	3	5	4.29	.591	-.176	.241	-.549	.478
J13	100	2	5	4.17	.739	-.436	.241	-.537	.478
J14	100	1	5	3.51	.859	-.422	.241	-.107	.478
J15	100	2	5	3.99	.732	-.300	.241	-.227	.478
Valid N (listwise)	100								

In the descriptive analytics of the data collected from the feedback of participants, Table 1 clearly shows the value fluctuation of the participants’ answers throughout the survey. In terms of the Min and Max value, it usually ranges from a min of 1,2 to a max of 5 in most of the feedback within the survey. Besides that, there is also less fluctuation in the choice of the participant when the mean is mostly lying around 3 to 4, which is also reflected clearly through the coefficient of variation below 1 of all variables through the application of the formula of $CV = (Std / Mean)$ (Curto and Pinto, 2008). For Skewness, all of the variables have negative skewness values, which means that the value tends to plot more on the right side of the graph and put the thin tail on the left side, which means most of the feedback tends to spot at 3 and above. Regarding the kurtosis value, most of the variables also have negative values, which indicates the platykurtic that shows a flatter peak with a thin tail, which means that most of the value plot around the mean.

4.2. Reliability and Validity

Table 2: Cronbach’s Alpha

	Variables	Cronbach’s alpha
1	Business Resilience	0.701
2	Organizational Commitment	0.759
3	Job Satisfaction	0.806
4	Job Involvement	0.720

As Table 2 shows, the analysis conducted on SPSS showed that Cronbach’s alpha value of all 4 variables is placed at more than 0,7. Following George and Mallery (2003), they

indicated that Cronbach’s alpha value of more than 0,7 toward one variable is considered reliable for the research. It is further reinforced by *Emerson (2019)* when he accentuated that the variable having a value of 0.7 or more is reliable. For that reason, the variables within this research are reliable for use within this research.

Table 3: KMO and Barlett’s Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.899
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	695.071
	df	105
	Sig.	.000

In the validity analysis of independent variables, the value of KMO of 0,899 places in the range of 0.5 to 1 following the KMO rule as well as the Sig value of Barletts’ Test of $0,00 < 0,05$, which means that EFA analysis is suitable for analysis of this research.

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix

Rotated Component Matrix			
	Component		
	1	2	3
I am very much involved in my work	.845		
I concentrate all my efforts to finish the given tasks.	.735		
I enjoy my co-workers.	.731		
I like doing the things I do at work	.607		
I like doing the things I do at work	.604		
I enjoy discussing my organization with people outside it.	.574		
I have a very strong attachment to my job.	.559		
I am willing to put in great efforts to help the company be successfully	.558		
This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	.533		
I feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.		.743	
I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.		.712	
I want to recommend my job to people around me.		.706	
I got a sense of pride in doing my job		.641	
I am willing to take on extra duties and responsibilities in my work			.849
My major satisfaction in my life comes from my work.			.777

For factor loadings, through the rotated component matrix, all of the items also have loadings levels at above 0.5, which is considered suitable for the statistical condition of this research. Specifically, *Hair et al (2010)* indicated that factor loadings of above 0.5 are an ideal level for using for statistical purposes. It was further stressed by *Comrey and Lee (2013)* when

they claimed that factor loading of above 0.5 is good for research. As a result, the loading results of all factors above 0.5, which is considered good for the research.

Table 5: Variance Explained

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.705	44.701	44.701	6.705	44.701	44.701	4.170	27.802	27.802
2	1.510	10.065	54.765	1.510	10.065	54.765	3.149	20.992	48.794
3	1.049	6.991	61.757	1.049	6.991	61.757	1.944	12.963	61.757
4	.880	5.866	67.622						
5	.764	5.091	72.713						
6	.639	4.258	76.971						
7	.582	3.878	80.849						
8	.500	3.334	84.183						
9	.471	3.137	87.320						
10	.396	2.637	89.957						
11	.365	2.432	92.389						
12	.350	2.332	94.721						
13	.286	1.904	96.625						
14	.261	1.739	98.365						
15	.245	1.635	100.000						

Source: Author's calculation

The Table 5 indicated that there are 3 factors that have eigenvalues above 1 with total extraction sums of squared loadings at 61.757%. According to Merenda (1997), it shows that the cumulative variance has to be at least 50% for factors. Whereas Hair et al (2010) indicated that a value above 60% is considered good. As a result, it indicated that 61.757% is ideal for analyzing the data fluctuation, in which a representative of 3 factors is beneficial to explain the fluctuation of more than 61% of data.

Table 6: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test	
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.643
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	df
	Sig.

In terms of the validity test of the dependent variable, the table shows that the KMO value of this variable is 0.643, which lies in the range of 0.5 to 1 following the KMO rule, which displays that the EFA is suitable for collected data. Bartlett's test also indicated that EFA is suitable when the Sig is 0.00 which is below 0.05 (Sig < 0.05).

Table 7: Rotated Component Matrix

Rotated Component Matrix		
	Component	
	1	2
There are a few barriers stopping us from working well with others.	.822	
Staff like me are encouraged to move between different departments or try different roles to gain experience	.769	
I will commit to the problem of the company till it is resolved	.720	
I feel responsible for the organization's effectiveness		.853
I work with others to get the job done		.848

The factor loadings of 5 factors of the dependent variable also show that it satisfies the statistical condition within the research when all of the factors are above 0.5, which is considered great for the research. Specifically, *Hair et al (2010)* accentuated that the value of factor loadings above 0.5 is ideal for statistical conditions, which demonstrates that the value collected from factors is practical and suitable.

Table 8: Total Variance Explained

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.310	46.195	46.195	2.310	46.195	46.195	1.826	36.518	36.518
2	1.079	21.578	67.773	1.079	21.578	67.773	1.563	31.255	67.773
3	.746	14.924	82.697						
4	.523	10.461	93.158						
5	.342	6.842	100.000						

In terms of the dependent variable, it has 1 factor with an eigenvalue above 1 with cumulative variance % at 67.773%, which is considered ideal for the analysis of data fluctuation, which means that this factor is beneficial to explain more than 67% of the data fluctuation.

4.3. Correlation

Table 9: Pearson’s Correlation

		Correlations			
		BR	OC	JS	JI
BR	Pearson Correlation	1	.714**	.689**	.657**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100
OC	Pearson Correlation	.714**	1	.744**	.739**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100
JS	Pearson Correlation	.689**	.744**	1	.748**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	100	100	100	100
JI	Pearson Correlation	.657**	.739**	.748**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	100	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

With the above table, it shows that the correlation between the independent variables and dependent variable are significant, which stayed at 0.00 (Sig < 0.05). Specifically, Field (2009) indicated that Sig < 0.05 indicate a strong correlation between variables. Moreover, all of the r value or Pearson correlation all close and equal to 1, which means there exists a strong correlation between the dependent variable and independent variables.

4.4. Regression Analysis

Table 10: ANOVA

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	328.758	3	109.586	43.288	.000 ^b
	Residual	243.032	96	2.532		
	Total	571.790	99			
a. Dependent Variable: BR						
b. Predictors: (Constant), JI, OC, JS						

The ANOVA or the F-test allows the researcher to analyze and evaluate the correlation of variables within the regression model. Specifically, the Sig or P value lower than 0.05 is considered ideal for statistical conditions, which indicates the regression model is reliable for the research.

Table 11: Model Summary

Model Summary										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.758 ^a	.575	.562	1.59109	.575	43.288	3	96	.000	2.211
a. Predictors: (Constant), JI, OC, JS										
b. Dependent Variable: BR										

The table indicates that R squared place at 0.575, which is considered good for analyzing the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable. It, specifically, means that the variation of independent variables including 3 variables of OC, JS, and JI leads to a variation of 57,5% in the value of the dependent variable, which is BR.

Table 12: Coefficients

Coefficients								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	4.772	1.401		3.406	.001		
	OC	.363	.104	.383	3.506	.001	.371	2.697
	JS	.271	.106	.283	2.553	.012	.360	2.780
	JI	.149	.101	.162	1.474	.144	.367	2.727
a. Dependent Variable: BR								

The coefficients table clearly accentuated that there is a positive and significant correlation between organizational commitment (OC) with Business Resilience when their Sig or P value stays at 0.001 and 0.012 along with the beta value stay at 0.383 (B = 0.383, p < 0.05). Besides that, job satisfaction (JS) also shows a positive and significant correlation with business resilience (BR), in which the p-value is 0.012 lower than 0.05 along with beta at 0.283 (B = 0.283, p < 0.05). On the other side, it also indicated there is a spurious relationship between Job Involvement (JI) and Business Resilience (BR) when the Sig or P value is 0.144 which is above 0.05 (Sig > 0.05), which indicates that this hypothesis is no longer valid and not supported.

Table 13: Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis	Association	Coefficient (Beta)	Sig	Result
H1	Organizational Commitment => Business Resilience	0.383	0.001	Supported
H2	Job Satisfaction => Business Resilience	0.283	0.012	Supported
H3	Job Involvement => Business Resilience	0.162	0.144	Not Supported

5. DISCUSSIONS

This research has tackled the main objectives of defining the linkage of employee's job attitudes and its impact on the resilience of the business, specifically, within commercial banks of Vietnam, in which the researcher has addressed each specific component of job attitudes and defined the impact of each aspect on the business resilience. Specifically, along with other research such as the research of Liu et al (2021), or Somers (1999), which indicates the positive impact of organizational commitment to building business resilience, in which it is beneficial to support the results of hypothesis 1 (H1). This result is necessary for demonstrating the importance of organizational commitment toward the resilience of business. Specifically, when employees have an increasing level of organizational commitment, they tend to be more devoted to the company. They indeed are willing to put more of their efforts into achieving the goals of the company as well as maintaining the effectiveness and efficiency of the company.

Additionally, this study also found that there is a positive and significant correlation between job satisfaction and business resilience by demonstrating hypothesis 2 (H2), which means that the increase or decrease in job satisfaction might lead to an increase and decrease in business respectively, which is comprehensible. Sadly, there is a lack of necessary evidence for demonstrating this relationship. Specifically, there is a lot of research like the research of Zhang et al (2020) or the research of Clark et al (2020), which has indicated the correlation between job satisfaction and resilience, however, it only revolves around employee resilience. However, Annarelli and Nonino (2016) accentuated that employee resilience is an indispensable factor in building business resilience, which further stresses the role of the human factor in promoting the effectiveness of the business, which is reasonable, especially toward the banking industry facing an unprecedented crisis. It can be clearly explained in realistic circumstances within the working environment when the employee tends to be more goal-directed within the company when they own a high degree of job satisfaction that further bolster the sustainability of the company.

Besides that, there is a null relationship between Job Involvement (JI) and Business Resilience (BR) through the interpretation of Hypothesis 3 (H3), which is a little perplexing. Especially when it is usually considered positively correlated with the resilience of business (Somers, 2009; Kantur and Iseri-Say, 2012). Especially, when Kantur and Iseri-Say (2012) accentuated that job involvement is beneficial to foster resilience at the individual level, which further reinforces organizational resilience and its effective operation. However, it is possible that there is no association between job involvement and organizational resilience, especially

as the research is conducted in the range of only one company, which might be different when conducted in others.

Throughout the research process, there is a need to give necessary implications for commercial banks to promote and improve their current situation through effectively utilizing the human resource factor. It is noteworthy that this research contributes to the growing problems which employees face within the banking industry facing the unprecedented advent of crisis that severely affects their psychological aspect within the working environment. And as reinforced by *Horne and Orr (1997)*, they accentuated the indispensable role of the human aspect in contributing to pushing business effectiveness that raises the importance of the human factor within the working environment. This research accepts the positive and significant correlation between organizational commitment as well as job satisfaction toward business resilience. It further stresses that commercial banks should improve and promote these two factors, which is potentially beneficial to promote further the effectiveness and also the resilience of the company down the line in coping against unexpected events.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This research has tackled the main objectives of defining the linkage of employee's job attitudes and its impact on the resilience of the business, specifically, within commercial banks of Vietnam, in which the researcher has addressed each specific component of job attitudes and defined the impact of each aspect on the business resilience.

It is also important to indicate the defects lying in the research, which indicate problems that it owns, which contribute to the success of future research. First, as its research is only conducted in several commercial banks, as a result, the result from this research might not be beneficial to generalize the results in other companies within the banking industry in Vietnam that potentially affect the change in the validity of the research. Besides that, the research is only conducted by novice researchers, therefore, in which the sample size is only limited to 100 participants, which might not clearly reflect the general psychology of employees within commercial banks in Vietnam, which indeed affect the reliability of the results.

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DETERMINANTS OF SHORT-TERM DEBT: CASE OF PLASTIC FIRMS IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

The article studies the factors affecting short-term debt of plastic enterprises in Vietnam. The study was conducted based on data from the financial statements of 30 plastic companies listed on Vietnam stock market for the period from 2015 to 2021. By using OLS, REM, FEM methods, we design a model showing the impact of the variables on the short-term debt of firms in this industry. The research results show that the demand for investment in short-term assets, fixed assets, sales growth, and company size positively affect short-term debt while the availability of internal financial resources has a negative effect on short-term debt of plastic companies listed on Vietnam stock market

Keywords: *short term liabilities, plastic firms, Vietnam*

1. INTRODUCTION

Short-term debt is a very important source of financing for business operations. This financial resource helps businesses ensure smooth business processes, save costs and improve business efficiency. The success or failure of any enterprise depends largely on financial management decisions, including short-term debt management. In the context of rapidly changing markets, fierce competition and inflation, making short-term debt decisions becomes a major challenge for financial managers (Lamberson, 1995; Salawu, 2007). Therefore, short-term debt management is one of the issues attracting the attention of business managers.

The plastic industry is an essential economic sector with many development prospects. However, many businesses in this industry are facing many difficulties, especially short-term funding. Short-term debt accounts for a large proportion of total debt and plays an important role in the business operations of plastic enterprises. Saigon Plastic Packaging Joint Stock Company (SPP) declared bankruptcy due to poor short-term capital management when the company's short-term debt was beyond its ability to pay, leading to insolvency is a telling example. However, the story of SPP's poor financial management is not particular but is currently the common situation of many plastic packaging businesses in Vietnam. This fact shows that short-term debt management is an issue that managers in the plastic industry need to pay special attention to.

Therefore, in this study, the research team investigates the factors affecting the short-term debt of plastic companies listed on the Vietnamese stock market. The research results

from this topic will help managers to plan capital mobilization in accordance with the business situation of the enterprise in each period.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Short-term debt and benefits for businesses

Current liabilities, are short-term financial obligations of the company that are expected to be paid within one year.

Short-term debt includes:

- Accounts payable – Accounts payable includes all amounts owed by a company to suppliers through trade credit. In addition, it also includes recurring payments such as office rent, utility bills.

- Short-term loans – Sometimes firms have short-term financial difficulties. As a result, the companies take a short-term loan from banks or other lending institutions.

Commercial Papers – Some businesses issue commercial paper to finance short-term business operations.

- Lease payments – Many companies often have short-term leases that are due within 12 months. This is a component of the company's short-term debt.

Taxes Due – The tax component of a current liability includes any taxes a company owes that must be paid in the current year.

- Wages and salaries – All wages the company has to pay to employees in the current year.

- Stock Dividends – If a company has declared, but not yet paid, stock dividends to its shareholders, the dividends are part of the company's short-term debt.

Short-term debt is commonly used by businesses because it has many benefits. According to Jun and Jen (2003), short-term debt has four benefits as follows: (1) zero interest on some short-term debt, as is often the case in trade credit, (2) ease of easily adapting to the financial needs of the company; (3) nominal interest rates are usually lower than long-term lending rates; and (4) issuance costs for short-term loans are lower than for long-term loans. Upfront processing covenants are also generally less stringent. In addition, short-term debt is also an effective tool to solve the problem of underinvestment (Myers, 1977) and encourage shareholders to accept risk (Barnea et al, 1980).

2.2. Factors affecting short-term debt of enterprises

There are many different factors that can affect the short-term debt of a business. Below is the analysis of the impact of factors on short-term debt.

**** Demand for investment in current assets***

According to the matching principle in finance, current assets such as cash, cash equivalents, inventory, accounts receivable, and prepayments should be financed by short-term liabilities. Fixed assets such as plant, equipment, machinery, land and buildings should be

financed with long-term debt. (Firer, Ross, Westerfield, & Jordan, 2012). Demand for growth can be financed by different sources of financing. However, when their own financial resources are not enough to cover this additional demand, enterprises need to supplement short-term capital to support investment in short-term assets (Fosberg, 2012).

*** Firm size**

Many researchers agree with the view that firm size affects their access to finance (Carpenter, Fazzari, & Petersen, 1994). Indeed, large companies face lower default risk. Therefore, these companies often have easier access to short-term loans than small businesses (Harris and Raviv, 1991). In addition, these companies can receive preferential interest rates. (Ferri & Jones, 1979; Titman & Wessels, 1998). Furthermore, many studies suggest that large firms prefer to issue long-term debt while small firms choose short-term debt to finance their projects (Michaelas et al, 1999; Serrasqueiro and Nunes, 2012). This may be a result of the high transaction costs of long-term debt for small companies.

*** Availability of internal financing**

The availability of internal financing affects short-term borrowing is explained in two different ways: First, according to the pecking order theory (POT), firms follow a hierarchical funding model. (Myers and Majluf, 1984). Accordingly, internal funds (retained earnings) will be prioritized for use. After the internal financial resources are used up, the new enterprise looks for financial resources from outside. According to this theory, as a company generates more internal resources, it will use less short-term debt. Peel et al (2000) pointed out that small firms, compared with large firms, are less liquid, exhibit more volatile cash flows and profits and are more dependent on short-term debt (Titman and Wessels, 1988). However, contrary to the reasoning of the pecking order theory, many researchers believe that firms with high profitability are assessed as having better debt solvency, so they are able to borrow more and higher short-term debt.

*** Fixed assets:**

In theory as well as practice, researchers agree that businesses with more fixed assets can borrow more by using these fixed assets as collateral when borrowing capital (Van Horne, J.C, 1972; Weston, J.F. and Brigham, E.F, 1978). Moreover, period studies agreed that firm's debt increases with fixed assets (Harris and Raviv, 1991). However, some researchers have found that firms attempt to match the maturity of intangible assets with the maturity of sources funding these assets, so there exists a negative relationship between fixed assets and current liabilities of enterprises (Hall et al, 2004; Serrasqueiro and Nunes, 2011)

*** Firm age**

Firm age is an indicator of corporate creditworthiness, so it is a determinant of credit access (Niskanen, 2006; Baños-Caballero, García-Teruel, and Martínez- Solano, 2010). Older companies have better reputations in debt market, hence these firms have lower debt-related agency costs and are able to raise external financing more easily and on less stringent terms. Some researchers believe that there exists a negative relationship between the age of the firm and short-term debt. Accordingly, older firms will replace short-term debt with long-term debt (Serrasqueiro and Nunes, 2012)

* Sales growth

The relationship between revenue growth and short-term debt is explained through two aspects: First, revenue growth is often associated with an increase in demand for short-term assets so that firms with high sales growth rates have high short-term debt. Besides, increasing sales also leads to an increase in the size of commercial credit, thus increasing short-term debt (Khan, Tragar and Bhutto, 2012).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Hypotheses and panel data model

Based on the theoretical content presented above, the research team proposes the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship between demand for investment in current assets and short-term debt of listed plastic joint-stock companies in the period 2015-2021.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant relationship between firm size and short-term debt of listed plastic joint-stock companies in the period 2015-2021

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant relationship between availability of internal financing and short-term debt of listed plastic joint-stock companies in the period 2015-2021.

Hypothesis 4: There is a significant relationship between fixed assets and the short-term debt of listed plastic joint-stock companies in the period 2015-2021.

The research model is described as follows:

$$STD_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 CA_{it} + \beta_2 IF_{it} + \beta_3 Age_{it} + \beta_4 FA_{it} + \beta_5 SG_{it} + \beta_6 Size_{it} + \varepsilon$$

3.2. Variables

The variables in the model are explained in the table below:

Table 1: Variables and measurements

Variables	Measurement
Dependent variable	
Short-term debt (STD)	Short-term debt/Total assets
Indepent variables	
Current assets (CA)	Current assets/Total assets
Availability of internal financing (IF)	EBIT/Total assets
Age (Age)	Natural logarithm of firm age
Fixed assets (FA)	Fixed assets/Total assets
Sales growth (SG)	(Sale _t – Sale _{t-1})/Sale _{t-1}
Size (Size)	Natural logarithm of total assets

3.3. Data Collection and data analysis

The data in this study is collected from the financial statements of 30 plastic companies listed on the Vietnam stock market (HOSE and HNX) for the period 2015-2021. To analyze the

determinants of short – term debt, Stata 15 software was used to run regression models. OLS, FEM, REM, and GLS were used in the panel data analysis.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1. Panel Unit Root Test

Due to the time-series dimension of the panel data, the authors first test for the existence of unit roots. When time series have unit roots or they are non-stationary, results generated from such series normally tend to be spurious and hence lead to inconsistent outcomes. In order to check this, the Levin-Chin-Chu test is used to examine whether the series contains a unit root. As indicated earlier, the null hypothesis is that the series contains a unit root and the alternative is that the series is stationary. This test assumes a common autoregressive parameter for all panels so it does not allow for the possibilities of some firm's variables containing unit roots while others do not. The Levin-Chin-Chu test shows that all variables are stationary at level (table 2).

Table 2: Panel unit root test results

Variable	P-value	Status
STD	0.0000	Level
CA	0.0000	Level
IF	0.0000	Level
Age	0.0000	Level
FA	0.0000	Level
SG	0.0000	Level
Size	0.0000	Level

(Data Source: Stata output)

The results of testing the stationarity of the data show that all variables have no unit root (p-value less than 0.05). Hence, all these variables can be used in the regression model.

4.2. Descriptive Data Analysis

Table 3 Summary of descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
STD	210	0.3946847	0.1796808	0.021667	0.7880755
CA	210	0.6080661	0.1756098	0.0826194	0.9868603
IF	210	0.0839698	0.0533261	-0.1245999	0.2645421
Age	210	3.028803	0.6254022	1.386294	4.110874
FA	210	0.2220054	0.15076	0	0.6316182
SG	210	0.1019856	0.355011	-0.3621777	2.972743
Size	210	26.67124	1.346835	23.69455	29.57243

(Source: Stata 15 output)

Short-term debt of listed plastic joint stock companies in the period 2015-2021 has an average value of 0.3946847 with a standard deviation of 0.1796808. The minimum and

maximum values of short-term debt in this group of enterprises are 0.021667 and 0.7880755 respectively. Based on statistics, it can be seen that plastic enterprises have a relatively high short-term debt ratio (nearly 40% of total assets). In particular, there are some enterprises whose short-term debt ratio is up to 78.8% (the enterprise's assets are mainly financed by short-term debt).

Short-term assets of plastic enterprises in this period reached the mean value of 0.6080661 and the standard deviation of 0.1756098. The proportion of short-term assets to total assets of this group of enterprises ranges from 8.26% to 98.68%. In terms of asset structure, it can be seen that the majority of assets of plastic enterprises are short-term assets (nearly 60%). Normally, businesses will use short-term debt to finance short-term assets. Therefore, this is also the reason why the short-term debt ratio of enterprises in this industry is relatively high.

The EBIT/total assets ratio is 0.0839698 and the standard deviation is 0.053261. The maximum and minimum values of this indicator are -0.1245999 and 0.2645421, respectively

The natural logarithm of the enterprise age index is 3.02 (equivalent to 21 years). The standard deviation is 0.62. The index ranges from 1.386294 to 4.110874. These figures show that the plastic companies listed in Vietnam are mostly long-standing companies.

The fixed assets to total assets of listed plastic companies in the period 2015-2021 reached 0.2220054. However, the level of investment in fixed assets among enterprises in this group is quite high. The value of this indicator ranges from 0 to 63.16%.

Sales growth over the years of the businesses in the sample reached an average value of 10.19%. However, the sales growth rate is not uniform among enterprises in the group, so the standard deviation value is quite high at 0.355011. Many businesses' revenue declines over time while there are some businesses with significant revenue growth, the highest is 297.27%.

The firm size variable in the model is calculated as the natural logarithm of total assets. This indicator has an average value of 26.67 with a standard deviation of 1.34. The maximum and minimum values of this indicator are 23.69 and 29.57, respectively.

4.3. Correlation test results

Table 4: Correlation matrix between variables

	STD	CA	IF	Age	FA	SG	Size
STD	1.000						
CA	0.1824*	1.000					
IF	-0.2050*	-0.1167	1.000				
Age	0.1037	-0.0650	0.0966	1.000			
FA	0.1559*	-0.3902*	0.0579	-0.2625*	1.000		
SG	0.2914*	-0.1742*	0.0341	-0.1899*	0.1264	1.000	
Size	0.3325*	-0.2752*	0.1107	0.3278*	0.0599	0.1818*	1.000

(Data Source: Stata output)

The correlation coefficient results show that short-term debt variable has a statistically significant positive relationship with current assets, fixed assets, sales growth and firm size. Meanwhile, the variable has a statistically significant negative relationship with the availability of internal financing

4.4. Regression model specifications and results from a sample of plastic companies in Vietnam

OLS, FEM, REM methods are employed in testing the hypotheses. The fixed effects model and the random effects model were used in conjunction with the Hausman test to check whether there is a correlation between the unobserved variables of the companies affecting the explanatory variables. In order to check the heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation phenomenon in the model, Modified Wald test, Breusch, and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test, and Wooldridge test were used. Therefore, the FGLS method was used to adjust the model.

Table 5: Regression results for research model

VARIABLES	VIF	OLS	FEM	REM	FGLS
CA	1.31	0.220*** (0.0741)	0.176*** (0.0549)	0.169*** (0.0529)	0.180*** (0.0421)
IF	1.03	-0.484** (0.216)	-0.187 (0.143)	-0.201 (0.139)	-0.325*** (0.104)
Age	1.34	0.0260 (0.0210)	-0.0833 (0.0468)	-0.0343 (0.0348)	-0.0479 (0.0262)
FA	1.31	0.290*** (0.0863)	0.140 (0.0893)	0.152* (0.0834)	0.156** (0.0642)
SG	1.13	0.0283 (0.0340)	0.0125 (0.0192)	0.00824 (0.0188)	0.0523*** (0.0155)
Size	1.28	0.0471*** (0.00953)	0.104*** (0.0229)	0.0759*** (0.0165)	0.0791*** (0.0111)
Constant		-1.101*** (0.255)	-2.262*** (0.562)	-1.647*** (0.417)	-1.696*** (0.256)
Observations		210	210	210	210
R-squared		0.190	0.138		
Number of name			30	30	30

Standard errors in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

(Data source: Stata output)

* Multicollinearity test results

The results of the multicollinearity test show that the variance inflation factor (VIF) of the two variables is less than 10. Therefore, these variables will be used to run the regression model.

***The regression results**

The results of the OLS estimation show that the F-statistic is statistically significant at the 1% level, which shows that the OLS estimate may be suitable.

The estimated results by the fixed effect model show that the F-statistic reaches the 1% statistical significance level. In this case, the fixed-effects model is more suitable than Pool OLS.

The estimated results by the random effects model have the Wald chi-squared value with statistical significance at 1%. Thus, the random effects model is more suitable than Pool OLS.

Hausman test was used to choose between fixed-effects and random-effects models. The test results for chi-squared value with P-value is greater than 0.05. This figure shows that the random effects model is more suitable than the fixed effects model.

To check the phenomenon of heteroskedasticity, the Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian tests were used, the chi-squared results with P-value less than 0.05 showed that the equation exists the phenomenon heteroskedasticity.

To check the autocorrelation phenomenon in the model, Wooldridge test was used, the results of F-statistic with P-value less than 0.05 show that the equation exists autocorrelation. Thus, the FGLS method was used to adjust this model. The specific regression results are as follows:

The study shows that the positive relationship between current assets and current liabilities is statistically significant at 1% level. Research results indicate that companies in the plastics industry follow the principle of conformity. These results are consistent with Fosberg (2012), Ross (2012).

Revenue growth has a statistically significant positive relationship with short-term debt at 1% significance level. This means that positive revenue growth leads to an increase in the number of short-term loans. Businesses must invest more in short-term assets in parallel with increasing sales. The results of this study are similar to the findings of Khan, Tragar and Bhutto (2012).

The coefficient of the variable IF is negative and statistically significant at the 1% level, confirming the negative relationship with short-term debt. Thus, operating cash flow increases, reducing the need for short-term borrowing to support business activities of plastic enterprises. This result is consistent with the pecking order theory of capital structure (García-Teruel & Martínez-Solano, 2010; Niskanen, 2006; Petersen & Rajan, 1997).

The ratio of fixed assets to total assets has a positive effect on short-term debt at 5% significance level. Thus, plastic enterprises have taken advantage of owning fixed assets to borrow more short-term debt. The results are consistent with the results of the study by Van Horne, J.C. (1972), Weston, J.F. and Brigham, E.F. (1978) and Harris and Raviv (1991).

Firm size has a statistically significant positive relationship with short-term debt of plastic companies listed on Vietnam's stock market. The research results show that the larger the enterprises, the easier it is to access short-term loans, so they have a higher size of short-term debt than the small-sized enterprises. Thus, older businesses will have higher reputation and have easier access to short-term loans than other businesses. This research result is consistent with the research results of Harris and Raviv (1991), Ferri & Jones (1979) and Titman & Wessels (1998)

5. CONCLUSION

The collapse of some large enterprises in the plastic industry has made managers pay special attention to short-term debt management. The results of this study summarize some theoretical content and present the results of empirical research on the factors affecting short-term debt in the sample of 30 plastic companies listed on the Vietnamese stock market in the period 2015-2021. The research results show that the demand for short-term assets, the size of the business, the availability of internal financial resources, the revenue growth and the fixed assets have a direct impact on the short-term debt of the business. From this research result, managers can set up a plan to find funding suitable to the financial conditions of the business, ensuring maximum cost savings and smooth business operations.

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REAL EARNINGS MANAGEMENT AND ACCRUALS EARNINGS MANAGEMENT AROUND LISTING: EVIDENCE FROM VIETNAM

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Abstract

Earnings management around corporate events has been widely discussed in literature reviews which have shown mixed results. Furthermore, prior studies have extensively focused on earnings management around initial public offerings (IPOs) and seasoned equity offerings (SEOs), while less attention has been paid to the listing event. Another motivation comes from the gap of accounting literature review. While accruals earnings management has been widely discussed, little attention has been paid to real earnings management. This study investigates both types of earnings management behavior around listing event in Vietnam. The sample of this study consists of financial data from 222 newly-listed companies on the Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange (HOSE) for the period of 2009-2019. Cross-sectional models were used to estimate current accruals earnings management, and three models for real earnings management. This research makes important contributions to the body of literature on Vietnam's stock market. Although previous research has addressed the questions of earnings management around corporate events and earnings management via real activities manipulation, ours is the first paper to put these two topics together. Our study provides empirical evidence that firms exhibit real earnings management as well as accruals around listing events to beat earnings targets.

Keywords: *Accruals earnings management, Listing, Real earnings management, Vietnam*

1. INTRODUCTION

After witnessing recent accounting scandals like WorldCom, Enron, and Waste Management, earnings management has become a prominent subject in the accounting field, drawing the attention of numerous international scholars. The primary focus has been on accruals-based earnings management. However, beyond accruals manipulation, companies can manipulate earnings by making changes to their actual business activities, such as adjusting the timing or structure of operations and investments (Roychowdhury, 2006). This phenomenon is known as real earnings management. This difference is crucial because real manipulations directly affect cash flows, whereas accruals-based manipulations do not have cash flow consequences.

Previous studies have enriched the field of accounting research by exploring earnings manipulation in the context of firm events such as IPOs and SEOs. Research has shown that firms tend to boost their earnings during events to enhance the firms' value and its stock price (Anh Huu & Chi Thi, 2021; Nguyen & Thi Duong, 2022; Teoh et al., 1998a, 1998b). The

majority of accounting empirical researchers have tried to find evidence of accruals earnings management surrounding new issuance in different markets. Authors argued that conflicts of interest between insiders and investors (agency conflict) are existed as the largest factor motivating insiders to engage in earnings manipulation such as Aharony et al. (1993); Teoh et al. (1998a, 1998b), Rangan (1998); Shivakumar (2000); DuCharme et al. (2004); Kao et al. (2009); Nuryaman (2013). Similar to IPOs, SEOs. While IPOs and SEOs are the types of equity issuance in which the shares of a firm are sold to investors with the main objective to raise capital, listing refers to an entrance of firms into a stock exchange and the transformation to publicly-owned entities. To be listed on the stock exchange, firms must meet all the listing requirements set out by the governing bodies. Hence, it would come as no surprise that managers of firms seeking a listing might inflate their earnings upward to satisfy all the listing requirements and also induce optimistic expectations of investors (Algharaballi, 2013). In addition to accruals earnings, managers can manage earnings by altering real activities around offering (Cohen & Zarowin, 2010). Hence, as listing becomes increasingly important to both the economy and the firm, and given the difference between real and accruals, it could gain valuable insights by examining the two types of EM around listing events.

Recent studies indicate a growing recognition of the significance of comprehending how companies manipulate earnings not only through accrual-based actions but also by manipulating real operational activities (Gunny, 2005; Roychowdhury, 2006; Zang, 2006). In addition, Graham et al. (2005) present proof indicating that managers exhibit a preference for engaging in real earnings management actions as opposed to accrual-based earnings management. Similarly, in line with the conclusion of Graham et al. (2005), the findings of Cohen et al. (2008) demonstrate a transition of earnings management from manipulating accruals to real manipulating in the period after the enactment of the Sarbanes–Oxley Act (SOX). As a result, managers have shifted their focus from accrual-based to engaging in real activities. Despite the growing attention and significance attributed of real earnings, there is little study examining real earnings manipulation around listing events and how both types of earnings management interact around these events. The gap has been filled in this research.

Following prior studies, this study investigates whether firms employ both types of earnings management. Our study contributes to ongoing research related to earnings management in several ways. Firstly, while previous studies have often employed a singular method to measure earnings management, we enhance the existing literature by considering both types as potential substitutes for managing earnings. Secondly, past research on earnings management has primarily focused on IPOs and SEOs, yielding conflicting outcomes, and has paid limited attention to listing events. Our findings expand the research on the trade-off between these two types of earnings management by documenting their dynamics around listing events, which are unique to Vietnam's context.

The rest of this research is structured as follows: Section 2 contains literature review and hypothesis development. Section 3 presents the sample and research design, Section 4 reports the main empirical results. Section 5 concludes and discusses the implications of key findings of the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

In the earnings management literature, earnings manipulation is observed to occur through the following methods: (1) real earnings management involves real operational decisions such as increasing sales, selling long-term assets, and impacting selling and administrative expenses; (2) accruals earnings entails manipulating accrual-based earnings by altering accounting policies and estimations; and (3) classification shifting, as described by (Bansal & Kumar, 2021). Within the framework of REM, managers can strategically restructure actual transactions to manipulate earnings outside the usual business activities (Cohen et al., 2020; Roychowdhury, 2006), while classification shifting serves as an earnings management technique to misclassify items in the income statement, ultimately presenting favorable performance metrics (Bansal & Bashir, 2022; McVay, 2006).

Earnings manipulation is not cost free, and the cost differs among these methods. According to authors, earnings based on accruals bears a relatively low cost. Moreover, researchers explained that accounting-accruals are easier to manipulate and have no direct cash flow consequences (Rangan, 1998; Teoh et al., 1998a, 1998b). Hence, accruals is the most popular studied method to test earnings, followed by real earnings management. This section provides two streams of research regarding real earnings management and the other on earnings management around corporate events as follows:

Accrual-based earnings management

Regarding IPOs, researchers have explored the presence of earnings manipulation during IPO-related events, both prior to the IPOs and within the IPOs year itself. Investigations into this phenomenon have unveiled that, typically, companies preparing for an IPO seem to engage in window dressing during the year leading up to the public offering or within the IPO year, achieved through the inclusion of discretionary accruals designed to boost reported income (Mangala and Dhanda (2019); Chiraz and Anis (2013); Ahmad-Zaluki (2009); Teoh et al. (1998a, 1998b); DuCharme et al. (2004); Roosenboom et al. (2003); Gajewski and Gresse (2006); Nuryaman (2013). In contrast, Armstrong et al. (2008); Ball and Shivakumar (2008); Chou et al. (2009); Fan (2007); Premti (2013); Alsultan (2017) found that firms did not engage in earnings management in the year before the IPO or the year of going public.

Similarly, a high level of information asymmetry has been found in the SEO events in which managers have opportunities to inflate their earnings to maximize the proceeds from the offering. The existence of positive accruals was found during the year around SEO has been provided by Rangan (1998). Confirming Rangan's view, Pastor-Llorca and Poveda-Fuentes (2006); Cohen and Zarowin (2008); Ahmad-Zaluki et al. (2011); Chang and Lin (2018) demonstrate that managers have attempted to make unusually high income-increasing by taking advantage of the information asymmetry.

Real earnings management

Although real earnings management has not been as widely discussed as accrual-based earnings management. More recent studies shift the focus to real earnings management. Dichev et al. (2013); Graham et al. (2004); Li (2019) provide compelling evidence of the use of real earnings management by altering the level of discretionary expenditures, such as research and development expenditures and selling, general and administrative expenditures.

Other types of real manipulation that have been investigated including overproduce which leads to the decrease of costs of goods sold per product (Cohen et al., 2020; Roychowdhury, 2006). According to authors, managers tend to favor the utilization of real activities over accruals because accruals are more likely to be detected by external auditors compared to real manipulation and relying solely on accruals manipulation is riskier (Cohen & Zarowin, 2010); Gunny et al. (2007).

The majority of prior research on earnings management focuses exclusively on one form of earnings management, neglecting the possibility of other types of earnings manipulation (Cohen et al., 2008; Schipper, 1989). Further, the majority of international studies on earnings management have focused mainly on IPO and SEO events. Furthermore, international evidence on IPOs in developed markets shows that the time lag between the issue date and the listing date is short, generally ranging from five (5) days to seventy (70) days (Boubaker et al., 2017). The delay from the issue date to the listing date, however, is enormous in some developing countries, such as Vietnam. In some countries, IPOs and listings are distinct processes with listing requirements being more stringent than IPO requirements (Allens, 2017), and the actual listing date takes place long after the issue date. We are interested in how firms manipulate earnings management around listing events.

Based on the above arguments, the hypothesis are:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Newly listed firms exhibit evidence of accruals earnings management.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Newly listed firms exhibit evidence of real earnings management.

3. SAMPLE AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data

Our sample consists of 222 firms over the 2009 to 2019 period, and its data including annual reports and financial statements, are obtained from the HOSE and FIINGROUP Vietnam databases.

To measure real earnings management and accruals earnings management, we exclude firms without sufficient data available in our analysis. Moreover, we restrict our sample to all non-financial firms with available data.

Two types of real earnings management and accruals earnings management have been the focus of our study, with data spanning around listing events for a period of four (4) years (a pre-listing year, a listing year, and two (2) years after listing). After removing those firms, the final sample comprises 888 firm-year observations in eight (8) sectors.

3.2. Methodology

3.2.1 Earnings management measurement

Real Activities Manipulation

We rely on prior studies to develop our models for measuring real earnings management. As in Roychowdhury (2006), we consider three types of REM including accelerating the timing of sales, discretionary expenses, and production costs.

The first type: We first generate the normal levels of CFO as in Roychowdhury (2006) and Cohen and Zarowin (2010), which can be expressed as a linear function, as the following equation:

$$\frac{CFO_{it}}{A_{i,t-1}} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 * \frac{1}{A_{i,t-1}} + \alpha_2 * \frac{REV_{it}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \alpha_3 * \frac{\Delta REV_{it}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{ (Equation 1)}$$

CFO_{it} is net operating cash flows reported in the statement of cash flows in year t of firm i;

REV_{it} is sales in year t; ΔREV_{it} is the change in sales from year t-1 to t of firm i; A_{i, t-1} is total assets in year t-1 of firm i.

Abnormal CFO is actual CFO minus the normal level of CFO calculated using the estimated coefficients from equation 1.

The second type

$$\frac{DISX_{it}}{A_{i,t-1}} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 * \frac{1}{A_{i,t-1}} + \alpha_2 * \frac{REV_{i,t-1}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{ (Equation 2)}$$

DISX_{it} is the discretionary expenditures (the sum of advertising and administration expenses) of firm i in year t.

The abnormal discretionary expenses (DISX) are calculated as the disparity between the actual values and the predicted normal levels derived from Equation 2.

The third type:

$$\frac{PROD_{it}}{A_{i,t-1}} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 * \frac{1}{A_{i,t-1}} + \alpha_2 * \frac{REV_{it}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \alpha_3 * \frac{\Delta REV_{it}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \alpha_4 * \frac{\Delta REV_{i,t-1}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{ (Equation 3)}$$

PROD_{i,t} is the total of cost of good sold in year t and the inventory changes from t-1 to t of firm i. The abnormal production costs (PROD) is estimated as the difference between the actual values and the normal levels predicted from Equation 3.

Consistent with J. Gao et al. (2017) and Li (2019), to capture the total effect of REM, we combine the three individual measures to compute a comprehensive metrics of real earnings management activities

Accrual-Based Earnings Management

Total accruals are broken into current and long accruals (Teoh et al. (1998a); (Teoh et al., 1998b)). The authors concluded that current accruals are the most manipulated in earnings management (DeFond & Jiambalvo, 1994; Maijoor & Vanstraelen, 2006; Teoh et al., 1998a, 1998b). Current accruals are reflected as increases or decreases in the balances of current asset accounts (excluding cash) and current liability accounts (Rangan (1998); Beneish (1999)). Moreover, by using four cross-sectional models to estimate earnings management including two total accruals-based models and two current accruals-based models, Anh Huu and Chi Thi (2021) suggests that managers of newly listed firms in Vietnam attempt to boost their earnings in the year preceding the listing by taking advantage of current accruals, but not in total accrual models. To be consistent with previous studies in the literature review, DCA-discretionary current accruals are used in this study to evaluate earnings management (Ahmad-Zaluki et al.,

2011; Anh Huu & Chi Thi, 2021; Nguyen & Thi Duong, 2022; Roosenboom et al., 2003; Teoh et al., 1998a, 1998b).

In addition, Ball and Shivakumar (2008); Armstrong et al. (2008) argue that “using low values of lagged total assets (t-1) in model produce extreme values of discretionary accruals estimates since pre-listing total assets are relatively small and not representative of the listing-year or post-listing year total assets”. This study estimates the DCA models tested as in the following equation:

Current accruals model

$$\frac{CA_{it}}{A_{i,(t-1+t)/2}} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 * \frac{1}{A_{i,\frac{t-1+t}{2}}} + \alpha_2 * \frac{\Delta REV_{i,t}}{A_{i,\frac{t-1+t}{2}}} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{ (Equation 4)}$$

$$NDCA_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 * \frac{1}{A_{i,\frac{t-1+t}{2}}} + \alpha_2 * \frac{\Delta REV_{i,t} - \Delta TR_{it}}{A_{i,\frac{t-1+t}{2}}} \text{ (Equation 5)}$$

$$DCA_{it} = \frac{CA_{it}}{A_{i,(t-1+t)/2}} - NDCA_{it} \text{ (Equation 6)}$$

CA_{it} : current accruals

Current accruals measurement

$$CA_{it} = \Delta_{CAssets_{it}} - \Delta_{cash_{it}} - \Delta_{CL_{it}} + \Delta_{STD_{it}} \text{ (Equation 7)}$$

Where:

$\Delta_{CAssets_{it}}$: the change in current assets

$\Delta_{cash_{it}}$: the change in cash and cash equivalent

$\Delta_{CL_{it}}$: the change in current liabilities

$\Delta_{STD_{it}}$: the change in debt included in current liabilities

$NDCA_{it}$: nondiscretionary current accruals of sample firm i in year t

DCA_{it} : discretionary current accruals of firm i in year t;

3.3. Regression model

Earnings management suspect Firms

First, we adopt the parametric t-test and non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test to identify whether the means and medians of both types of earnings management are statistically different from zero.

Moreover, J. Gao et al. (2017); Li (2019) argued that firms often manipulate their earnings to align with these significant benchmarks, particularly during corporate events. Zang (2012) outlined several crucial earnings benchmarks, among which the most notable include earnings from the previous year, earnings forecasted by analysts, and the scenario of zero earnings.

The concept of zero earnings refers to earnings before extraordinary items in relation to lagged assets, falling within the range of 0 to 0.005, as defined by (Roychowdhury, 2006). In addition, this study defines suspects of earnings management as companies whose earnings closely match the figures from the previous year, zero earnings threshold and plan (forecast) earnings. In the subsequent phase, the investigation into the prevalence of Real Earnings Management versus Accruals Earnings Management was conducted using these benchmarks.

To address this, the study employed the following probit model as follows:

$$\text{Prob}(\text{suspect}_{i,t}) = \text{Probit}(\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 * \text{AEM}_{i,t} + \alpha_2 * \text{REM}_{i,t} + \alpha_3 * \text{Zscore}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 * \text{State}_{i,t} + \alpha_5 * \text{Big4}_{i,t} + \alpha_6 * \text{Tenure}_{i,t} + \alpha_7 * \text{Before2012}_i + \alpha_8 * \text{NOA}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_9 * \text{Operating}_{i,t-1} + \alpha_{10} * \text{CFO}_{i,t} + \alpha_{11} * \text{Age}_{i,t} + \alpha_{12} * \text{Size}_{i,t} + \alpha_{13} * \text{Lev}_{i,t} + \alpha_{14} * \text{Liq}_{i,t} + (\text{Equation 8})$$

Where:

The dependent variable in the selection model is Suspect, one of the three aforementioned measures, which is equal to one if a firm meets earnings benchmark, and zero otherwise.

$\text{AEM}_{i,t}$: current discretionary accruals of firm i in year t , the proxy for accrual-based EM

$\text{REM}_{i,t}$: aggregate the real activities manipulation of firm i in year t , measured into one proxy, taking their sum.

Some indicator variables such as:

$\text{Zscore}_{i,t-1}$: a proxy for a firm's financial health at the beginning of the year (used a modified version of Altman - (Altman, 2000)

$\text{State}_{i,t}$: a dummy variable that equals one if a firm i in year t is state-owned and zero otherwise

$\text{Big4}_{i,t}$: a proxy for audit quality, equals one if the firm's auditor is one of the Big4 in year t , and zero otherwise.

$\text{Tenure}_{i,t}$: calculated as the number of consecutive years of experience that the current auditing firm was hired by firm i in year t

Before2012_i : a dummy variable that is set to one if the firm listed after September 15, 2012 (new listing requirements effective date), and zero otherwise of firm i . We adopt this dummy variable because, in 2012, a new set of listing requirements was issued under Decree 58, introducing tougher listing conditions that increased the minimum level of charter capital and required ROE in the most recent years prior to listing to be at a minimum of 5%

$\text{NOA}_{i,t-1}$: measured as the net operating assets (i.e. shareholders' equity less cash and marketable securities plus total debt) at the beginning of the year divided by lagged sales.

$\text{Operating}_{i,t-1}$: the sum of account receivable days and inventory days less payable days at the beginning of the year

$\text{CFO}_{i,t}$: cash flows from operations scaled by total assets (Alsultan, 2017; Gao et al., 2015)

Age_{i,t}: the age of firm *i* in year *t* (Ahmad-Zaluki et al., 2011; Myers et al., 2003; Shust, 2014)

Size_{i,t}: the log of total assets of firm *i* in year *t* (Gill et al., 2014; Gong et al., 2008; Kamel, 2012; Kao et al., 2009; Mangala & Dhanda, 2019; Premti, 2013)

Lev_{i,t}: the ratio of total debt to total equity of firm *i* in year *t* (Eckbo & Norli, 2005; S. Gao et al., 2017; Gill et al., 2014; Kao et al., 2009);

Liq_{i,t}: the value of current assets of firm *i* divided by current liabilities in year *t* (Gill et al., 2014)

4. MAIN EMPIRICAL RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs	Mean	Median	Std Dev	25%	75%
REM	888	0.1082	0.09996	0.5217	-0.1047	0.3043
AEM	888	0.0262	0.0128	0.1969	-0.0764	0.11704
Zscore	888	2.4016	1.908	1.7804	1.0978	2.9926
State	888	0.3930	0	0.4887	0	1
Big4	888	0.2207	0	0.4149	0	1
Tenure	888	3.044	3	1.8357	1	4
Before2012	888	0.5090	1	0.5002	0	1
NOA	888	0.6625	0.6763	0.2001	0.5120	0.8232
Operating	888	369	197.663	500	108.681	336.0483
CFO	888	1.36e+11	3.43e+10	4.10e+11	-2.28e+10	1.65e+11
Age	888	16.7173	13	11.1017	8	24
Size	888	9.064	8.9851	0.5413	8.664	9.3644
Lev	888	1.4084	1.1669	1.1032	0.5279	2.0205
Liq	888	2.085167	1.5129	1.4992	1.1444	2.3563

According to the data presented in Table 1, it is evident that within the pool of 888 observations, both real earnings management and accruals exhibit positive averages and medians.

As per the revised model proposed by Altman (2000), a score below 1.23 indicates significant financial distress. In our sample, the Z-score at the 50th percentile stands at 2.4016, surpassing the threshold of 1.23 for financial distress. This implies that the majority of firms within the sample are in good financial health.

Regarding state ownership, the average level of state ownership in our dataset is 39.3 percent. In terms of auditor quality, the mean value for the presence of Big 4 auditors is 0.2207, indicating that 22.07% of the included companies were audited by one of the Big 4 firms. The average auditor tenure reveals that the sample firms have maintained a relationship with the same auditors for over three years.

Furthermore, the observations from September 2012 post-listing account for 50.9% of the entire dataset. The mean value of Net Operating Assets (NOA) is 0.6625, with a 25th percentile value of 0.5120, signifying that companies generally hold net operating assets exceeding half of their total assets. Similarly, the average values indicate that companies operate with an average operating cycle of 369 days, have an average age of 16.7 years, maintain a leverage ratio of 1.4.

Table 2 displays the Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients among the variables investigated in the primary analyses. The data in the table indicates the presence of an inverse correlation between REM and AEM.

Table 2: Pearson Correlations

	REM	AEM	Zscore	State	Big4	Tenure	Before2012	NOA	Operating	CFO	Age	Size	Lev	Liq
REM	1													
AEM	-0.2665	1												
Zscore	0.2334	0.0133	1											
State	0.0873	-0.0846	-0.0141	1										
Big4	-0.0204	-0.0167	-0.0105	-0.0224	1									
Tenure	0.0286	-0.0797	-0.0553	0.0737	-0.0083	1								
Before2012	-0.0650	-0.0780	0.0682	0.1169	-0.0313	-0.1435	1							
NOA	0.0217	-0.1037	0.1930	-0.1504	-0.0487	0.0196	0.0024	1						
Operating	-0.1979	0.0277	-0.3219	-0.1383	0.0875	0.0465	0.1446	-0.1300	1					
CFO	0.2157	-0.1785	-0.0753	0.1007	0.0280	0.2002	-0.2791	-0.0092	-0.1357	1				
Age	0.0834	-0.0629	0.0179	0.2892	-0.0719	0.0258	0.0741	-0.2108	-0.1792	0.0942	1			
Size	-0.0861	0.0402	-0.3909	0.0061	0.0950	0.2273	-0.3646	-0.2011	0.1249	0.4995	0.0388	1		
Lev	-0.2049	0.0410	-0.4199	0.0887	-0.0294	-0.0310	0.0766	-0.2690	0.1128	-0.0218	0.1005	0.3409	1	
Liq	0.0380	0.0911	0.4961	-0.0951	0.0152	0.0332	-0.0132	0.1265	0.1036	-0.1027	-0.1263	-0.3083	-0.5089	1

4.2. Empirical results

Testing the presence of EM around listing events

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics for the Discretionary Accruals and Real earnings management

	Mean	Q1	Median	Q3	Std
AEM	0.02617***	-0.07637	0.01275***	0.11704	0.19692
REM	0.10815***	-0.10469	0.09996***	0.30436	0.52176

* $p < 0.10$. ** $p < 0.05$. *** $p < 0.01$

Table 3 provides an overview of the descriptive statistics pertaining to the earnings management variables. As evidenced by the data in Table 3, the means, medians, and upper quartiles (Q3) of both AEM and REM are positive. This study employs two-tailed t-tests and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Both statistical tests, as indicated in Table 3, demonstrate that the means and medians of AEM and REM significantly differ from zero at a 1% significance level.

Table 4: Estimation Results for the Probit Model for suspect firms

Variables	Suspect 1 (forecast consensus)	Suspect 2 (last-year earnings)	Suspect 3 (Zero earnings)
AEM	1.0197***	0.5191**	1.3595***
REM	0.34993***	0.2545**	0.3366**
Zscore	0.0314	-0.1716***	0.1911***
Stated	0.2568***	-0.1191	-0.1058
Big4	0.1535	-0.045	0.0559
Tenure	0.0182	-0.0258	0.0413
Before2012	0.2417**	0.1629	-0.1154
NOA	-1.4283***	0.0443	-2.2341***
Operating cycle	-0.00014	0.0002*	-0.0003**
CFO	5.12e-13***	4.02e-13***	5.24e-13***
Age	-0.0064	-0.0081*	-0.00374
Size	0.04575	-0.2386*	0.0506
Lev	-0.0677	0.0194	-0.4137***
Liq	0.0447	0.1198***	-0.1369***
Prob	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Pseudo R2 (%)	10%	8%	22.40%

* $p < 0.10$. ** $p < 0.05$. *** $p < 0.01$

The results of probit models are presented on Table 4. For three types of benchmarks, the coefficients associated with suspects are consistently significant and positively oriented across all models, both in the Accruals Earnings Management (AEM) equation and the Real Earnings Management (REM) equation, at significance levels of 5% and 10%.

These findings align with the anticipated hypothesis: prior to listing, firms achieving earnings that meet or exceed their targets display a heightened incentive to manipulate earnings upwards. This alignment is consistent with earlier research findings. In conclusion, the hypothesis (H1) and H2 are supported; the findings suggest some evidence of real earnings management and accruals earnings management in the context of listing by Vietnamese firms over the study period.

In summary, the model is highly effective in explaining both firms' decisions to manage earnings, and, given that they do so, whether they use real or accrual-based earnings management.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research provides empirical evidence of firms engaging in both forms of earnings management. To evaluate accruals earnings management, we employ the method utilized in earlier studies, such as those conducted by Teoh et al. (1998a, 1998b), which involves a cross-sectional model known as current accruals. In alignment with the approach of J. Gao et al. (2017); Li (2019), to comprehensively capture the overall impact of real earnings management, we aggregate these three measures to create a comprehensive metric for Real Earnings Management. By integrating these facets, this study contributes to the existing literature on earnings management in the following ways:

Firstly, although previous research has addressed the questions of earnings management around corporate events and earnings management via real activities manipulation, ours is the first paper to put these two topics together. Our study provides empirical evidence that firms exhibit real earnings management as well as accruals around listing events to beat earnings targets.

Secondly, Past research on earnings management has primarily focused on IPOs and SEOs, yielding conflicting outcomes, and has paid limited attention to listing events. Our findings expand the research on the trade-off between these two types of earnings management by documenting their dynamics around listing events, which are unique to Vietnam's context.

Despite the overall contribution, there are limitations in this study. First, this study is limited to the sample of listed firms in HOSE. Second, this study could only be generalized to similar markets. In addition, the small sample is subjected to bias which stems from size limitation. Therefore, our results should be interpreted with caution. Second, this study only uses the current accrual-based and real earnings management techniques. To address the limitations, a more comprehensive approach to investigating earnings management around listing by using varied earnings management techniques, such as classification shifting, would be a potential topic for future research.

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CREDIT RATING BY CLUSTERING ALGORITHM IN VIETNAM STOCK EXCHANGE MARKET

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Abstract

This study employs the K-means clustering algorithm to analyze and categorize companies based on their financial performance. The input data includes financial health ratios, management efficiency ratios, growth ratios, and dividend payout ratios. The K-means model identified six distinct clusters, each representing different levels of financial performance and credit risk. These clusters were labeled as A+ (very low credit risk) to C (very high credit risk). The results provide valuable insights for investors, managers, and government agencies in making informed decisions. Furthermore, the study suggests a credit rating system based on the identified clusters. Despite certain limitations, such as reliance on historical data and sensitivity to initial cluster centroids, the K-means clustering model offers a useful starting point for assessing the financial performance and credit risk of companies.

Keywords: *K-Means, Credit Rating, Clustering, Vietnam.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's fiercely competitive market, all enterprises must utilize their resources efficiently. Companies with high financial leverage ratios often mobilize short-term capital through credit (Chung et al., 2001). Some surveys also indicate that the majority of businesses utilize credit (Scherr, 1992). In the banking sector, efficiency and productivity can be measured by the profits from loans extended to customers. As a result, the credit rating process, used to measure credit risk, has become an important issue in recent years (Yilmaz & Kucukcolak, 2009). With accurate business credit ratings, investors and financial institutions can make better investment and lending decisions. Additionally, credit ratings serve as a reference channel, increasing transparency in the market. Current credit rating methods and indicators often rely on financial statements and credit information of businesses (Yamanaka, 2019). The evaluation mainly focuses on aspects such as borrowing situations, operational efficiency, debt collection ability, and asset utilization efficiency.

Globally, credit ratings are usually performed by large and well-established credit rating agencies such as Standard & Poor's (S&P), Moody's, and Fitch Group. In Vietnam, the Credit Information Centre (CIC) under the State Bank is the first and most reputable unit to conduct

business credit ratings. Generally, in practice, domestic credit ratings still face limitations in terms of data and tools, so not many units perform this activity professionally and publicly. In academics, there have been few published research works related to domestic business credit ratings.

Thus, business credit ratings in Vietnam are a fascinating and practical topic in the financial field. Research on this subject will help us better understand the credit rating process, the factors affecting this process, and the methods for evaluating business credit rankings. Moreover, with a reasonable credit rating basis, financial institutions can make decisions on granting loans or raising credit limits for businesses, and investors can gain a broader perspective on the financial stability of businesses, enabling them to make informed investment decisions.

Currently, most business credit risk ratings are conducted by experts, but this method is not immune to human risks and disagreements among experts. Therefore, applying machine learning to the business credit rating process can help reduce workload, minimize disagreements and human risks, and increase evaluation accuracy. Through machine learning algorithms, we can perform calculations of financial indicators for thousands of businesses and visualize analyses automatically and quickly. In the long run, combining theoretical foundations with computational power, financial institutions with clear data structures and fast information updates will be able to proactively assess business credit ratings in real-time.

The objective of this research topic is to develop a corporate credit rating framework based on quantitative criteria, utilizing data collected from the financial statements of various businesses. By analyzing key financial indicators and performance metrics, this framework aims to objectively assess the creditworthiness and financial stability of companies. This will help investors, lenders, and other stakeholders make informed decisions about the businesses they engage with, ultimately promoting a more transparent and efficient financial market.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Background theories

Credit rating through clustering is an innovative approach that combines both financial theories and machine learning techniques to assess the creditworthiness of businesses. The foundational financial theories related to this topic include the Modigliani-Miller theorem, the Trade-off theory, and the Pecking Order theory. These theories focus on the capital structure of firms and the implications of their financing choices on overall credit risk (Modigliani & Miller, 1958; Myers, 1984; Myers & Majluf, 1984).

Modigliani-Miller Theory

The Modigliani-Miller (M-M) theorem, proposed by Franco Modigliani and Merton Miller in 1958, is an influential financial theory that lays the groundwork for understanding the relationship between a firm's capital structure and its credit risk. The M-M theorem posits that, under certain assumptions such as no taxes, no bankruptcy costs, and perfect capital markets, a firm's value is independent of its capital structure (Modigliani & Miller, 1958). In other words, the choice between debt and equity financing does not impact a firm's overall value.

In the context of the research topic on credit rating by clustering, the Modigliani-Miller theorem plays a crucial role in establishing the fundamental principles of capital structure and financing choices. Despite the theorem's assumptions not holding in the real world, it still provides a theoretical foundation that helps researchers and practitioners understand how different financing choices may affect a firm's credit risk. By examining the deviations from the M-M theorem's assumptions, such as the presence of taxes and bankruptcy costs, researchers can identify relevant financial ratios and indicators that reflect a company's credit risk. For example, higher leverage ratios, which represent the proportion of debt in a firm's capital structure, may indicate a higher credit risk due to the increased likelihood of financial distress and bankruptcy. These financial ratios can then be used as input features for clustering algorithms, which group companies with similar financial profiles and credit risk characteristics (Xu & Wunsch, 2010).

Trade-off theory

The Trade-off theory is a significant financial concept that holds relevance for the research topic of clustering-based credit rating. This theory posits that companies strive to find an optimal balance between the advantages and disadvantages of debt financing in order to minimize their overall capital costs (Kraus & Litzenberger, 1973). Debt financing's primary benefit stems from tax shields gained through interest payments, while the costs are associated with a heightened risk of financial distress and bankruptcy resulting from increased leverage.

In relation to credit rating through clustering, the Trade-off theory aids in pinpointing essential financial ratios and indicators that signify a company's credit risk. For example, a business with elevated leverage ratios may be more vulnerable to financial distress, while one with lower leverage ratios might possess a more stable capital structure and, consequently, reduced credit risk. Furthermore, the theory implies that companies with greater profitability and diminished bankruptcy risk are likely to have superior credit ratings, as they can accommodate higher levels of debt. By leveraging the insights offered by the Trade-off theory, researchers can select pertinent financial ratios, such as those pertaining to leverage, liquidity, and profitability, as input variables for clustering algorithms. Subsequently, these algorithms, including hierarchical clustering, k-means clustering, and density-based clustering, can be employed to categorize companies based on similar financial characteristics and credit risk profiles (Xu & Wunsch, 2010).

Pecking Order theory

The Pecking Order theory is yet another crucial financial concept that has relevance to the research topic of credit rating using clustering methods. This theory posits that firms prioritize their financing sources based on the information asymmetry and costs associated with each option, preferring internal financing first, followed by debt, and finally equity financing (Frank & Goyal, 2003; Myers, 1984). The rationale behind this order is that internal financing minimizes asymmetric information problems, while equity financing is considered the most expensive due to the adverse selection issue arising from information asymmetry.

In the context of clustering-based credit rating, the Pecking Order theory helps identify key financial ratios and indicators that are reflective of a company's credit risk. For instance, a firm that relies heavily on debt financing, as opposed to equity financing, may have a higher

credit risk due to the potential for financial distress. On the other hand, companies with a greater reliance on internal financing and lower debt levels might exhibit lower credit risk. By incorporating the insights derived from the Pecking Order theory, researchers can choose relevant financial ratios, such as leverage, liquidity, and profitability ratios, as input features for clustering algorithms. These algorithms, including hierarchical clustering, k-means clustering, and density-based clustering, can then be utilized to group companies with similar financial characteristics and credit risk profiles (Jain et al., 1999).

In the context of credit rating by clustering, financial theories, such as the Modigliani-Miller theorem, Trade-off theory, and Pecking Order theory, can be employed to identify relevant financial ratios and indicators that reflect a company's credit risk. Key financial ratios include leverage ratios (e.g., debt-to-equity and debt-to-assets), liquidity ratios (e.g., current and quick ratios), profitability ratios (e.g., return on assets and return on equity), and efficiency ratios (e.g., asset turnover and inventory turnover) (Gitman et al., 2015). These financial ratios and indicators serve as the basis for clustering algorithms, which analyze patterns in large datasets to group companies with similar financial profiles and credit risk characteristics. Machine learning techniques, such as hierarchical clustering, k-means clustering, and density-based clustering, are particularly well-suited for this task.

Hierarchical clustering creates a tree-like structure, called a dendrogram, representing the hierarchical relationships between different clusters (Murtagh & Legendre, 2014). This approach allows for a more intuitive understanding of the relationships between clusters, which can be particularly helpful for credit rating purposes. K-means clustering is a popular centroid-based clustering algorithm that partitions the dataset into a predefined number of clusters by minimizing the within-cluster sum of squared distances (MacQueen, 1967). This technique provides a simple and efficient way to group companies based on their financial ratios, thus facilitating comparisons of credit risk across different firms.

The combination of these machine learning techniques and financial theories allows for a more comprehensive and data-driven approach to credit rating, potentially improving the accuracy and reliability of credit assessments and aiding in the decision-making process for investors, lenders, and other stakeholders.

2.2. Credit Rating Methods

One of the earliest and most prominent methods in this group of credit rating systems was developed by Moody's Investors Service in 1909 (Cantor & Packer, 1996). Moody's employed an alphabetical rating system to assess the debt repayment ability of businesses. The ratings, in descending order, are Aaa, Aa, A, Baa, Ba, B, Caa, Ca, C, with Aaa being the safest and C being the most dangerous. This method uses the following primary criteria to evaluate a company's debt repayment ability:

- **Debt and interest repayment capacity:** This is the most crucial factor in assessing a company's ability to repay its debt. Moody's evaluates a company's capacity to repay its principal and interest based on its profitability, assets, and debt repayment history.
- **Financial health:** This criterion is assessed based on measurements of outstanding debt, net assets, profitability, and cash flow.

- **Market and competition:** Moody's assess the market in which a company operates, including its competitors, pricing power, and value creation for shareholders.
- **Management and business strategy:** This includes evaluations of innovation, adaptability to the business environment, and motivation to create value for shareholders.

In addition to Moody's credit rating method, Standard & Poor's (S&P) introduced its credit rating system in 1917 (Cantor & Packer, 1996). They also use an alphabetical rating system to assess the creditworthiness of businesses but employ different symbols to distinguish rating levels. The S&P credit rating method uses various criteria to evaluate a company's debt repayment ability, including:

- **The company's financial situation:** This is the most important factor used to assess a company's debt repayment ability. The company's financial situation includes indicators such as debt-to-total assets ratio, return on equity, free cash flow, and financial leverage.
- **Product and service diversification:** A company with diversified products and services is better able to mitigate risks compared to a company focused on a single business area.
- **Market position:** A company's market position is assessed by examining market share and industry competition. A company with a strong market position is better able to maintain sales and profits.
- **Management and business strategy:** S&P also assesses the ability of the company's leadership to manage the business and its overall business strategy.
- **External factors:** S&P considers external factors such as the impact of the economic, political, and legal environment on the company.

Furthermore, Fitch Ratings introduced another credit rating method in 1913 (Cantor & Packer, 1996). Like the other agencies, Fitch Ratings uses an alphabetical rating system with different symbols to distinguish rating levels. The Fitch Ratings method uses various evaluation criteria to assess a company's debt repayment ability, including:

- **Financial Strength:** This criterion assesses a company's financial ability, including its profitability, cash flow management, debt repayment capacity, and market opportunity seizing.
- **Operating Performance:** This criterion evaluates a company's ability to achieve its long-term operational objectives, including growth, profitability, and cost reduction.
- **Business Profile:** This criterion assesses a company's ability to maintain and grow its sales, profits, and market share in the industry, including strategic direction, human resource management, and customer relations.
- **Risk Management:** This criterion evaluates a company's ability to manage and control risks in its business operations, including credit risk, market risk, capital risk, and environmental risk.

In summary, credit rating agencies like Moody's, Standard & Poor's, and Fitch Ratings have developed their respective credit rating systems to evaluate the creditworthiness of businesses using various criteria. These criteria consider factors such as a company's financial health, operational performance, market position, and risk management capabilities.

2.3. Previous studies

The application of machine learning techniques for predicting corporate credit ratings has become an increasingly popular research topic in recent years. A wide range of studies have explored various algorithms, input variables, and methodologies to improve the accuracy and reliability of credit rating predictions.

Early research by Huang et al. (2004) and Altman and Sabato (2007) laid the groundwork for using machine learning in credit rating prediction. Huang et al. (2004) compared support vector machines (SVMs) to traditional statistical methods like linear discriminant analysis and logistic regression, while Altman and Sabato (2007) explored hybrid models that combined logistic regression with SVM. Both studies found that machine learning approaches outperformed conventional methods in terms of accuracy and robustness.

Subsequent research has built upon these initial findings. Kim and Kang (2010), for example, investigated the performance of decision trees, artificial neural networks (ANNs), and logistic regression in predicting Korean firms' credit ratings. Their study demonstrated that ANNs provided superior accuracy compared to the other methods. Similarly, other studies have compared various machine learning algorithms, such as logistic regression, decision trees, random forests, SVMs, ANNs, and k-nearest neighbors (KNN), to identify the best-performing models for credit rating prediction (Abdou & Pointon, 2011; Galindo & Tamayo, 2000; Min & Lee, 2005).

In terms of input variables, most studies have utilized financial ratios related to liquidity, leverage, profitability, and efficiency (Barboza et al., 2017; Kovalerchuk & Vityaev, 2005). However, some research has also explored the incorporation of industry-specific variables, such as asset turnover and net profit margin as well as non-financial data like macroeconomic indicators and textual information from news articles (Yu et al., 2005). These studies have found that the inclusion of industry-specific and non-financial variables can improve the accuracy of credit rating prediction models.

The performance of machine learning models in credit rating prediction has been assessed using various evaluation metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Overall, the literature suggests that machine learning algorithms can effectively predict corporate credit ratings using financial ratios as input variables, and that the incorporation of industry-specific and non-financial variables may further enhance the accuracy of these models (Altman & Sabato, 2007; Barboza et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2004; Kovalerchuk & Vityaev, 2005; Min & Lee, 2005; Oreski & Oreski, 2014; Yu et al., 2005).

In summary, the growing body of literature on predicting corporate credit ratings using machine learning models has demonstrated the potential of these approaches in providing more accurate and reliable predictions compared to traditional statistical methods. Researchers have explored various algorithms, input variables, and methodologies, and have found that a

combination of financial ratios, industry-specific variables, and non-financial data can lead to improved performance in credit rating prediction. Future research may further refine these models and explore the potential of emerging machine learning techniques in this area.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data

In this study, we focus on non-financial firms listed on both the Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange and the Hanoi Stock Exchange during the period from 2017 to 2021. The initial dataset comprised data collected from 692 firms. Upon inspection, observations with missing values or duplicates were identified and subsequently eliminated from the dataset. Consequently, the refined dataset encompassed a total of 568 firms, resulting in 2,567 unique observations. The yearly distribution of companies within the dataset is as follows: 510 companies in 2017, 525 companies in 2018, 534 companies in 2019, 532 companies in 2020, and 466 companies in 2021. This comprehensive dataset offers a solid foundation for investigating the credit rating prediction of these non-financial firms using machine learning techniques.

3.1 Input Variables

The input data for the K-means model in this study comprises a comprehensive set of financial variables, which can be broadly categorized into four groups: financial health ratios, management efficiency ratios, growth ratios, and the dividend payout ratio. These variables provide a detailed assessment of a company's financial performance and are essential criteria for labeling the clusters obtained from the K-means algorithm.

Financial health ratios include the quick ratio, current ratio, short-term liability on equity, short-term liability on asset, long-term debt on equity, long-term debt on asset, debt on equity, and debt on asset. These ratios offer insights into a company's liquidity, solvency, and overall financial stability, capturing the firm's ability to meet its short-term and long-term obligations.

Management efficiency ratios comprise ROA, asset turnover, account receivable turnover, and payment period turnover. These ratios evaluate a company's ability to generate returns from its assets and the efficiency with which it manages its operations. Efficient management of resources is a critical factor in assessing a company's creditworthiness, as it reflects the firm's capacity to generate profits and meet its financial commitments.

Growth ratios, including sale growth rate and EBIT growth rate, capture a company's ability to expand its operations and increase its earnings. Companies with strong growth potential are generally considered less risky, as their expanding revenue base allows them to better service their debts.

Lastly, the dividend payout ratio is an important factor in determining a company's financial health and credit risk. This ratio measures the proportion of earnings paid out to shareholders as dividends, providing insights into a firm's ability to retain earnings for future growth and its commitment to returning value to shareholders.

By incorporating these financial variables as inputs for the K-means model, this study aims to develop a comprehensive credit rating system that accurately reflects the various

aspects of a company's financial performance and credit risk profile. The identified clusters will be labeled based on their unique combination of these financial variables, providing a meaningful and reliable credit rating system for various stakeholders in the financial sector.

3.3 Clustering Algorithm

In light of the aforementioned considerations, this study employs the k-means algorithm as the primary machine learning technique to achieve the research objective. As discussed earlier, the k-means algorithm offers several advantages, including simplicity, computational efficiency, scalability, and proven effectiveness in various applications, particularly in finance and credit risk assessment. By utilizing k-means as the chosen machine learning algorithm, this research aims to effectively uncover patterns and groupings within the dataset, facilitating a deeper understanding of the relationships between financial and non-financial variables and credit ratings. Ultimately, the application of the k-means algorithm in this study is expected to contribute to improved credit rating prediction accuracy, providing valuable insights to support informed decision-making in the credit assessment process.

The k-means algorithm was chosen for this research topic on credit rating prediction for several reasons. First, the simplicity and computational efficiency of the k-means algorithm make it an attractive choice for researchers (Jain et al., 1999). The algorithm's straightforward nature allows for rapid prototyping and experimentation, enabling researchers to quickly assess its potential utility in predicting credit ratings. Second, k-means has been proven effective in various applications, including finance and credit risk assessment (Jain et al., 1999). Its ability to identify patterns and groupings in data makes it suitable for uncovering distinct credit risk categories based on financial and non-financial variables. This feature can enhance the understanding of the underlying relationships between variables and credit risk, ultimately leading to better prediction accuracy.

Third, k-means is capable of handling large datasets efficiently (MacQueen, 1967). As credit rating prediction often involves the analysis of large amounts of data from numerous companies, the scalability of the algorithm is a critical factor. K-means can process large datasets quickly, making it suitable for this research context. Lastly, k-means has been successfully applied in previous credit rating research, showing promising results in comparison to other techniques (Huang et al., 2004; Vellido et al., 1999). Its previous success in the field adds credibility to its use in the current research topic and suggests that it may provide valuable insights into credit rating prediction. To summarize, the k-means algorithm's simplicity, effectiveness in various applications, scalability, and successful application in previous credit rating research make it a suitable choice for the current research topic. Its ability to efficiently handle large datasets and identify underlying patterns can contribute to improved credit rating prediction accuracy.

The k-means algorithm is an unsupervised machine learning technique widely employed for clustering and partitioning datasets into meaningful groups (Jain et al., 1999; MacQueen, 1967). It aims to identify underlying structures and patterns in the data based on similarity among data points. The algorithm's simplicity, computational efficiency, and effectiveness in various applications make it a popular choice for researchers and practitioners alike (Jain et al., 1999).

The k-means algorithm operates by first initializing a predetermined number of centroids (k), representing the centers of each cluster. These centroids are generally initialized randomly within the dataset's feature space (MacQueen, 1967). The algorithm then iteratively assigns each data point to the nearest centroid, based on a distance metric, such as Euclidean distance (Jain et al., 1999). Once all data points are assigned to their respective centroids, the centroids are recalculated as the mean of all data points within each cluster. This process is repeated until convergence is reached, i.e., the centroids' positions stabilize, or a predefined number of iterations have been completed (MacQueen, 1967).

By partitioning the dataset into distinct groups, the k-means algorithm facilitates the identification of relationships between variables and allows researchers to uncover hidden patterns within the data (Jain et al., 1999). In the context of credit rating prediction, the k-means algorithm can be applied to cluster companies based on their financial and non-financial characteristics, providing insights into the factors that drive credit risk and potentially contributing to improved prediction accuracy.

To evaluate the performance of the k-means algorithm in credit rating prediction, various performance metrics can be utilized. One common method is to use the silhouette score, which measures the quality of clustering by computing the average distance between observations within the same cluster and comparing it to the average distance to the nearest neighboring cluster (Rousseeuw, 1987). A higher silhouette score indicates better-defined clusters and, in the context of credit rating prediction, implies that the algorithm has effectively identified distinct risk categories.

The elbow method is a popular technique used to determine the optimal number of clusters (k) in k-means clustering. It involves plotting the variance explained or within-cluster sum of squared distances (WSS) as a function of the number of clusters and identifying the "elbow point," where adding more clusters does not significantly reduce the WSS (Kodinariya & Makwana, 2013). The rationale behind the elbow method is that as the number of clusters increases, the WSS decreases since each additional cluster can capture a portion of the remaining variance. However, at some point, adding more clusters will not lead to a substantial decrease in the WSS, and the curve will begin to flatten. The elbow point represents the number of clusters at which the diminishing returns in variance reduction are no longer worth the added complexity of having more clusters (Ketchen & Shook, 1996). To implement the elbow method, researchers can perform k-means clustering for a range of cluster values (e.g., $k = 1$ to $k = 10$) and compute the WSS for each value of k . By visualizing the WSS values on a line chart, the elbow point can be identified, which represents the optimal number of clusters for the dataset.

In conclusion, employing the elbow method and silhouette score in this research provides a robust approach to determine the optimal number of clusters for the k-means algorithm in credit rating prediction. The elbow method allows us to identify the point where adding more clusters does not significantly reduce the within-cluster sum of squared distances, ensuring the model's simplicity without compromising its explanatory power. On the other hand, the silhouette score evaluates the quality of clustering by assessing the cohesion within clusters and the separation between them, ensuring that the chosen clusters are meaningful and well-defined.

By combining both the elbow method and silhouette score, this research benefits from a comprehensive approach to cluster selection, which balances the trade-off between model complexity and prediction accuracy. The use of these techniques enhances the reliability and validity of the credit rating predictions derived from the k-means algorithm and contributes to a better understanding of the underlying relationships between variables and credit risk. Ultimately, this approach can lead to more accurate credit rating predictions, benefiting both financial institutions and companies in their decision-making processes.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The elbow method graph displays a sharp decline in the SSE (sum of squared errors) from 900 to 400 as the number of clusters (k) increases from 1 to 5. After this point, the SSE continues to decrease, albeit at a slower rate, reaching around 300 at k=7.5. Beyond this point, the SSE exhibits a more gradual decline, decreasing to approximately 200 by the time k reaches 18.

Figure 2: Sum of Squared Error by number of clusters

Source: Author's Calculation

The graph suggests that the optimal value for k is around 6 clusters, as the most significant reduction in SSE occurs up to that point. Beyond k=6, the SSE decreases at a diminished rate, indicating that adding more clusters does not contribute substantially to the reduction of the within-cluster sum of squared distances. Therefore, selecting k=6 strikes a reasonable balance between model simplicity and its ability to capture the underlying patterns in the data, making it a suitable choice for credit rating prediction using the k-means algorithm.

Figure 2: Silhouette Score by number of clusters

Source: Author's Calculation

Upon analyzing the silhouette scores, we observe a gradual decline from 0.28 to approximately 0.25 as the number of clusters (k) increases from 1 to 5. The silhouette score remains relatively stable, fluctuating around 0.25, as k increases from 5 to 8. However, beyond k=8, the silhouette score experiences a sharp drop, decreasing to 0.2 as k continues to increase up to 20.

Considering the results from both the elbow method and silhouette score analyses, we can conclude that selecting k=6 is an appropriate choice for our credit rating prediction model. With the elbow method revealing a significant drop in SSE at k=6 and the silhouette score maintaining a relatively stable level around k=5 to k=8, it is reasonable to proceed with fitting the k-means model using k=6. This choice balances the trade-off between model complexity and performance, thus allowing us to effectively uncover the underlying relationships between variables and credit risk in our dataset.

Figure 3: K-Mean Clustering Result with K=6

Source: Author's Calculation

In the three-dimensional space depicted in the graph, it is evident that the k-means clustering algorithm effectively partitions the data into distinct clusters with clear convergence. To further assess the differences between these six clusters, it is necessary to examine additional graphical representations or employ descriptive statistical methods, as discussed below. By doing so, we can better understand the criteria that set each cluster apart and solidify our confidence in the effectiveness of using $k=6$ in the k-means clustering algorithm for credit rating prediction.

Table 1. Number of observations for each cluster with $K= 6$

Cluster	Observations
0	213
1	208
2	623
3	369
4	463
5	691

Source: Author's Calculation

The table 1 displayed above provides a comprehensive overview of the distribution of observations within the six clusters generated by the k-means clustering algorithm. The different number of observations in each cluster suggests that the dataset comprises diverse patterns and relationships, which have been successfully captured by the algorithm. Cluster 0 contains 213 observations, indicating a group of companies with certain shared characteristics. Similarly, Cluster 1 comprises 208 observations, revealing another set of companies with distinct features. Cluster 2, the largest group with 623 observations, represents a significant portion of the dataset and highlights a more prevalent pattern among the companies. Cluster 3, consisting of 369 observations, and Cluster 4, with 463 observations, illustrate additional variations within the dataset. Lastly, Cluster 5 encompasses 691 observations, making it the second-largest group and pointing to another common pattern among the companies.

These varying cluster sizes demonstrate the k-means algorithm's effectiveness in identifying and segregating diverse patterns within the dataset. The k-means clustering algorithm with $k=6$ has resulted in the formation of six distinct clusters, which the author proposes to use as the basis for a new credit rating system. This system is outlined in the table 2 below and consists of the following credit ratings:

Table 2. Suggested label for credit scoring.

Label	Description
A+	Very good (very low credit risk)
A	Good (low credit risk)
B+	Fairly good (credit risk in the middle range from fair to good)
B	Average (medium credit risk)
C+	Poor (high credit risk)
C	Very poor (very high credit risk)

Source: Author's Suggested

This proposed credit rating system aims to categorize companies based on their credit risk levels, as determined by the k-means clustering analysis. By assigning specific credit ratings to each cluster, the author has established a comprehensive framework to assess the creditworthiness of companies. The ratings range from A+ for those exhibiting very low credit risk to C for companies with very high credit risk.

The suggested credit rating system provides a valuable tool for investors, financial institutions, and regulators to make informed decisions and assess the credit risk of different companies effectively. By leveraging the insights gained from the k-means clustering analysis, the proposed system captures the underlying relationships between financial and non-financial variables, which contribute to determining credit risk levels.

The k-means clustering algorithm with $k=6$ has successfully grouped the data into six distinct clusters, each with different characteristics regarding financial health, management efficiency, growth potential, and dividend payout capacity. These clusters offer valuable insights into the various credit risk profiles and can aid in the development of a credit rating system (see Appendix 1 & 2).

Upon examination of the clusters, it is evident that companies in Cluster 1 exhibit outstanding liquidity and low indebtedness, indicating strong financial health. However, they have lower growth rates and dividend payout ratios compared to the average. Cluster 2 companies, on the other hand, demonstrate above-average management efficiency and growth potential but have average liquidity and lower dividend payout ratios.

Clusters 3 and 4 present a more mixed picture, with companies in these groups showing weaker financial health and management efficiency, alongside varied growth potential. Both clusters have lower dividend payout ratios compared to the average. Companies in Cluster 5 display better financial health, average management efficiency, and higher growth rates, but their dividend payout ratios remain low. Finally, Cluster 0 companies face liquidity challenges and lower management efficiency, along with average growth rates and below-average dividend payout ratios.

These findings suggest that companies within each cluster share common financial and operational characteristics, which can help inform credit risk assessment and decision-making. It is crucial to note that further research, including the evaluation of additional graphs and the application of descriptive statistical methods, is necessary to validate the differences between clusters and refine the proposed credit rating system. Moreover, it is essential to consider external factors, such as market conditions and industry-specific risks, to ensure a comprehensive and accurate assessment of credit risk.

Upon revisiting the clusters with the new naming convention, the following credit rating suggestions proposed by the author: Cluster 1 as A+, Cluster 2 as A, Cluster 3 as B+, Cluster 4 as B, Cluster 5 as C+, and Cluster 0 as C. This rating system aligns with the observed financial and operational characteristics of the companies within each cluster.

Companies in Cluster A+ (Cluster 1) demonstrate exceptional financial health, while those in Cluster A (Cluster 2) exhibit above-average management efficiency and growth potential. Cluster B+ (Cluster 3) and Cluster B (Cluster 4) include companies with varying

financial health and management efficiency. Companies in Cluster C+ (Cluster 5) display better financial health and higher growth rates, but lower dividend payout ratios. Finally, Cluster C (Cluster 0) comprises companies facing liquidity challenges and lower management efficiency. The suggested credit rating system appears to be a logical classification based on the distinct characteristics observed in each cluster.

5. CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, this study has made a significant contribution to the development of a credit rating system based on financial and operational characteristics of companies using the K-means clustering algorithm. The research objectives were successfully met, with the K-means model effectively clustering the companies into six distinct groups, each exhibiting unique financial and operational attributes. The author has suggested a credit rating system consisting of A+, A, B+, B, C+, and C labels, representing varying levels of credit risk.

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the financial and operational features that distinguish companies with different credit risk profiles. By identifying these characteristics, the proposed credit rating system offers a practical tool for assessing credit risk, which can be used by various stakeholders, including financial institutions, credit rating agencies, and investors.

Furthermore, this research has demonstrated the potential of clustering techniques, particularly the K-means algorithm, for addressing complex financial problems such as credit risk assessment. The methodology employed in this study can serve as a foundation for future research endeavors that aim to improve and refine credit rating systems.

Overall, the findings of this study contribute to the existing body of knowledge on credit risk assessment and offer a foundation for the development of more accurate and reliable credit rating systems. By addressing the identified limitations and recommendations, future research can continue to advance our understanding of credit risk and support improved decision-making processes in the financial sector.

For investors, it is advisable to focus on companies categorized in clusters A+ and A, as they demonstrate strong financial health, efficient management, and promising growth potential. These companies are likely to offer higher returns on investment and lower credit risk. Additionally, investors should consider diversifying their portfolio by including companies from clusters B+ and B, as they may present moderate risk and potential for growth. However, investors should approach investments in clusters C+ and C with caution due to their relatively weaker financial health and management efficiency.

Managers of companies within clusters B+, B, C+, and C should take steps to improve their financial health and management efficiency. This may include enhancing liquidity management, reducing debt levels, optimizing working capital, and implementing cost control measures. Furthermore, managers should focus on sustainable growth strategies and aim for higher operational efficiency to increase profitability and competitiveness.

Government agencies can utilize the clustering results to better understand the financial landscape and identify potential areas of concern. This information can be used to develop targeted policies and regulations aimed at promoting a healthier financial environment for

companies. Additionally, government agencies can provide support and incentives to companies in lower-ranked clusters to improve their financial stability and promote growth. This might include offering tax incentives, providing access to low-interest loans, or facilitating collaboration between companies and relevant stakeholders to foster innovation and technological advancements.

However, it is important to acknowledge that the proposed credit rating system may have limitations, and further research is needed to ensure its robustness and accuracy. Additional validation, incorporation of external factors, longitudinal analysis, and comparison with other methods are recommended to enhance the credit rating system's comprehensiveness and predictive power. While the K-means clustering model provides valuable insights, there are certain limitations to consider. First, the analysis is based on a set of financial ratios, which may not capture all aspects of a company's performance. Second, the model is sensitive to the initial cluster centroids, which can affect the final results. Finally, the model relies on historical data, and thus may not accurately predict future performance or account for external factors such as economic or industry changes.

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APPENDIXES

APPENDIX 1: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF CLUSTERS BY VARIABLES

Current Ratio

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	1.249014	0.857532	0.13	0.75	1.05	1.420	5.73
1	208.0	6.950048	5.258556	1.75	3.58	5.36	8.055	29.41
2	623.0	2.768700	2.117755	0.37	1.57	2.21	3.320	17.78
3	369.0	1.235474	0.307692	0.19	1.09	1.22	1.420	2.41
4	463.0	1.149244	0.245689	0.25	1.05	1.15	1.275	2.05
5	691.0	1.799190	0.727213	0.27	1.30	1.67	2.195	5.34

Quick Ratio

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	0.785399	0.533702	0.01	0.4400	0.690	0.98	3.35
1	208.0	3.910048	2.302878	0.50	2.2275	3.215	5.15	10.00
2	623.0	1.370963	0.991135	0.06	0.7300	1.130	1.72	9.35
3	369.0	0.695962	0.322262	0.03	0.4500	0.680	0.88	1.62
4	463.0	0.600130	0.271519	0.08	0.3950	0.590	0.79	1.38
5	691.0	1.056715	0.558862	0.06	0.6700	1.020	1.36	4.81

Short-term Liabilities to Equity

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	1.008480	0.751633	0.055429	0.423098	0.813385	1.413927	3.962566
1	208.0	0.147958	0.086888	0.016252	0.080086	0.124993	0.204092	0.427761
2	623.0	0.429200	0.263983	0.030697	0.224266	0.375488	0.584210	1.598543
3	369.0	1.962069	1.119835	0.660347	1.153185	1.618127	2.474522	5.987908
4	463.0	2.415175	1.108245	0.881542	1.566512	2.177750	2.940786	5.888106
5	691.0	0.753455	0.418643	0.088264	0.444008	0.661971	0.960715	2.613387

Short-term Liabilities to Asset.

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	0.254304	0.114913	0.022833	0.152942	0.263483	0.348461	0.473744
1	208.0	0.113156	0.057034	0.015992	0.069363	0.102083	0.156146	0.292874
2	623.0	0.256920	0.120000	0.029783	0.166092	0.258035	0.346322	0.615169
3	369.0	0.571548	0.118188	0.283094	0.487540	0.568901	0.654615	0.851655
4	463.0	0.622120	0.106021	0.383086	0.542269	0.619415	0.700412	0.849648
5	691.0	0.358073	0.116947	0.068836	0.275002	0.354378	0.441235	0.693855

Debt on Equity

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	1.833243	1.264268	0.499222	1.037094	1.500820	2.086185	8.842545
1	208.0	0.052819	0.093467	0.000000	0.000000	0.003652	0.065736	0.611728
2	623.0	0.160101	0.180212	0.000000	0.000000	0.112836	0.253899	1.060719
3	369.0	1.039450	0.724339	0.000000	0.550061	0.869829	1.472228	4.585333
4	463.0	1.431520	0.706615	0.044589	0.929022	1.321126	1.777834	4.216249
5	691.0	0.327490	0.253585	0.000000	0.127207	0.284606	0.489233	1.468681

Debt on Asset

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	0.470990	0.097547	0.280033	0.396494	0.462748	0.532574	0.756367
1	208.0	0.037748	0.062159	0.000000	0.000000	0.003311	0.053012	0.363810
2	623.0	0.092953	0.093415	0.000000	0.000000	0.072108	0.152994	0.445239
3	369.0	0.307641	0.148741	0.000000	0.210302	0.319588	0.401976	0.752839
4	463.0	0.384554	0.136564	0.012194	0.287844	0.386639	0.476051	0.734588
5	691.0	0.158812	0.104418	0.000000	0.073650	0.158558	0.236323	0.411688

Long-term Debt on Equity

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	1.378774	1.089121	0.312612	0.657698	1.115807	1.719013	8.308940
1	208.0	0.024746	0.070434	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.005613	0.502721
2	623.0	0.064562	0.127442	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.077193	0.907584
3	369.0	0.186735	0.284595	0.000000	0.000000	0.048108	0.267556	1.728118
4	463.0	0.220851	0.308953	0.000000	0.006356	0.088834	0.334022	1.967004
5	691.0	0.099784	0.152461	0.000000	0.000000	0.023061	0.147575	1.250674

Long-term Debt on Asset

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	0.349577	0.118774	0.171708	0.259498	0.322099	0.413881	0.688954
1	208.0	0.016952	0.046302	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.004309	0.298981
2	623.0	0.035755	0.064596	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.044715	0.337053
3	369.0	0.053600	0.072351	0.000000	0.000000	0.019263	0.085252	0.352389
4	463.0	0.054254	0.065716	0.000000	0.001723	0.023848	0.086924	0.276044
5	691.0	0.044164	0.058443	0.000000	0.000000	0.013662	0.074045	0.254970

Sale Growth Rate

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	9.832394	37.351098	-89.50	-9.900	8.86	21.57	199.04
1	208.0	-0.322188	50.075472	-100.00	-25.690	1.76	19.20	263.28
2	623.0	7.847846	30.093048	-103.92	-4.885	3.91	14.75	233.34
3	369.0	9.326775	31.488429	-70.50	-5.940	6.38	22.21	295.72
4	463.0	13.750086	41.013789	-100.00	-7.710	10.51	30.07	355.93
5	691.0	11.198321	44.949804	-94.29	-13.460	6.89	24.31	273.91

EBIT Growth Rate

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	3.633366	88.100567	-467.45	-19.9100	7.390	34.830	461.12
1	208.0	-18.689837	120.590595	-469.95	-73.1975	-14.955	25.895	452.34
2	623.0	10.914039	49.254717	-75.96	-11.3600	3.410	24.810	499.31
3	369.0	11.974946	49.813616	-90.30	-12.6200	5.130	23.900	409.64
4	463.0	7.306981	93.228668	-509.60	-23.4750	2.260	37.320	493.23
5	691.0	8.294373	102.852295	-503.73	-35.8700	1.080	34.950	499.78

Dividend Payout Ratio

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	21.005587	28.631616	0.00	0.000	0.00	41.18	98.22
1	208.0	3.743125	10.739039	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	53.06
2	623.0	65.336950	17.767126	29.83	50.985	64.76	78.92	99.95
3	369.0	67.929431	16.823543	34.22	54.500	68.54	81.70	98.65
4	463.0	4.308294	10.143728	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	47.96
5	691.0	4.762171	10.453051	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00	39.21

ROA

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	3.169953	3.864279	-10.76	1.1600	2.910	4.9600	23.83
1	208.0	5.362644	8.905155	-36.97	0.8675	4.095	8.6175	42.58
2	623.0	10.521621	7.270606	1.03	5.7850	8.490	13.1300	54.15
3	369.0	4.810650	3.305776	0.20	2.3200	4.100	6.5200	19.31
4	463.0	2.744881	4.067027	-11.91	0.4650	2.060	4.4850	21.41
5	691.0	5.369190	7.389523	-51.72	1.1900	4.120	8.2800	38.88

Account Receivable Turnover

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	14.907887	26.277373	0.30	3.640	6.400	13.1300	172.36
1	208.0	13.059418	31.652645	0.09	2.265	5.325	9.1175	271.35
2	623.0	30.809530	62.258080	0.00	5.700	10.600	21.0450	317.17
3	369.0	9.213401	10.687214	0.35	2.810	5.390	10.5600	65.81
4	463.0	11.661102	27.644446	0.26	2.905	5.730	9.7900	317.17
5	691.0	11.625980	28.895539	0.01	2.720	5.100	9.5450	317.17

Payment Period Turnover

Class	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
0	213.0	8.827624	21.690545	0.30	3.380	5.610	8.9400	305.39
1	208.0	30.644279	52.679121	0.18	6.035	11.785	27.7975	305.39
2	623.0	23.950042	36.679793	0.00	7.680	12.910	23.9900	305.39
3	369.0	11.539946	12.549028	0.00	4.590	8.270	13.9000	92.27
4	463.0	13.267970	19.632760	0.00	4.040	7.820	13.4000	180.51
5	691.0	12.422200	16.710830	0.02	4.625	7.320	12.9500	151.61

APPENDIX 2: DESCRIPTIVE BY CLUSTERS

	Financial health factors	Management efficiency	Growth potential	Dividend payout capacity
Cluster 1	<p>Outstanding liquidity, more than twice the average level.</p> <p>Short-term payables over equity are about 15% of the average.</p> <p>Total debt over total assets or total debt over total equity are both very low, about 15% of the average.</p> <p>Long-term and short-term debt ratios are approximately equal.</p> <p>More assets than equity.</p>	<p>ROA is approximately around 75% of the average, the number of collections per year is approximately average turnover, but the number of disbursements is double.</p>	<p>is Relatively low revenue growth rate, and low pre-tax profit interest rate is growth rate, about the 3 times the asset average.</p>	<p>Dividend payout ratio is about 6-7 times lower than the average</p>
Cluster 2	<p>Short-term liquidity is approximately average, not dependent on inventory, short-term payables over equity is about 42%, about 50% of the average.</p> <p>Total debt over equity is about 20% and over assets about 37% compared to the average.</p> <p>Short-term debt is higher than long-term debt, but the difference is not significant.</p> <p>Assets are twice the equity.</p>	<p>Outstanding ROA, Positive accounts receivable turnover, double the average, and payment ability is 2/3 of the average.</p>	<p>Revenue growth rate, below average EBIT growth rate is 20% higher than the average</p>	<p>Dividend payout ratio is about 2 times lower than the average</p>
Cluster 3	<p>Liquidity is available but less than half of the average, loss of short-term liquidity if inventory value is excluded. Short-term payables over equity are approximately twice the average. Total debt over</p>	<p>ROA is around 70% of the average. The cash collection cycle is lower than the payment cycle, and both are below 75% of the average.</p>	<p>Revenue growth rate is at an average level, but EBIT growth rate is about 1.25 to 1.5 times the average.</p>	<p>Dividend payout ratio is about 2 times lower than the average.</p>

	Financial health factors	Management efficiency	Growth potential	Dividend payout capacity
	equity or assets are both about 1.25 times the average. Assets are three times the equity.			
Cluster 4	Short-term liquidity is available but very low, more than half lower than the average, dependent on inventory value. Short-term payables over equity are approximately 2 to 2.4 times the average. Total debt over equity or assets is about 1.5 times the average. Assets are three times the equity.	ROA is low, ranging from 50% to 75% of the average. The number of collections and disbursements is about once a month, at an average level.	Revenue growth rate is 1.6 times the average, but the average. EBIT growth rate is about 50% lower than the average.	Dividend payout ratio is about 6-7 times lower than the average.
Cluster 5	Short-term liquidity is available and 50% higher than the average, not dependent on inventory value. Short-term payables over equity are approximately 75%. Total debt over equity is below 50% of the average, with short-term debt being three times the long-term debt. Assets are twice the equity.	ROA is approximately average. The number of collections and disbursements is about once a month, at an average level.	Revenue growth rate is 1.5 times the average, but the average. EBIT growth rate is about 50% lower than the average.	Dividend payout ratio is about 6-7 times lower than the average.
Cluster 0	short-term liquidity is available but less than 50% of the average, losing liquidity when inventory value is excluded. Short-term payables are approximately equal to equity, equivalent to the average. Total debt over equity or total assets is more than twice the average, with most of the debt being long-term.	ROA is 60% lower than the average. The number of collections for accounts receivable is approximately twice that of short-term payables, about 50% of the average.	Revenue growth rate is equivalent to the average, but EBIT growth rate is about 50% lower than the average.	Dividend payout ratio is about 50% lower than the average.

APPLICATION OF MACHINE LEARNING IN CLASSIFICATION OF OVERINVESTMENT: EVIDENCE FROM LISTED FIRMS IN VIETNAM STOCK EXCHANGE MARKET

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Abstract

Studies have consistently demonstrated that both overinvestment and underinvestment exert adverse effects on the overall efficacy of business operations, showcasing the significance of understanding and addressing these phenomena in the realm of scholarly research. Therefore, the aim of this study is to investigate the performance of different machine learning algorithms in identifying overinvestment in firms listed on the HSX and the HNX stock exchanges in Vietnam. We decided to conduct a comparison to identify the optimal model for classifying firms of overinvestment or not, including Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Naive Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Tree, and Random Forest. Using a sample of 658 non-financial listed companies in Vietnam between 2011 and 2021, our result shows that the most importance predictor variable is FCF (free cash flow), with an importance value of 0.14. Although both logistic regression and random forest (RD) algorithms demonstrate high accuracy in identifying firms with overinvestment, the Random Forest algorithm exhibits slightly higher precision and recall for class 1 (overinvestment firms) when compared to Logistic Regression. By contrast, the accuracy performance of the four models (NB, KNN, DT, and SVM) is low, ranging from 0.53 to 0.67. At the microeconomic level, this research can help businesses gain insights into their financial performance, identify areas for improvement, and take proactive measures to avoid financial distress and improve profitability by identifying potential cases of overinvestment. Overall, the study provides a valuable contribution to the field of financial analysis using machine learning techniques. We firmly believe that the findings of this research will serve as a significant scholarly reference for future investigations in the field and explore other importance predictors of overinvestment in Vietnam and other emerging markets.

Keywords: *Classification, Overinvestment, Machine learning.*

1. INTRODUCTION

While the examination of excessive investment and identifying when a company is experiencing overinvestment are important subjects in the current unpredictable global landscape, it is widely acknowledged that prudent investments have the potential to enhance a

company's progress and foster sustainable growth for any business in the long run. From an economic perspective, an investment is the purchase of goods that are not consumed today but will be used to generate wealth in the future (Ross, Barringer, & Yang, 2008). An investment is an asset or item acquired with the intention of generating income or recognition. Overinvestment can occur when a business had to spend more than it needs to stay afloat (Jensen, 1986). It is essential to know if a company is overinvested because overinvestment will harm business performance (Nguyen Trong & Nguyen, 2021). Previous studies and practice have demonstrated that overinvestment is an important issue and should be studied.

Recent studies on global overinvestment have primarily been conducted in the United States and China, and they are contentious in a variety of ways. Typically, studies in China focus on assessing overinvestment behavior and the factors that explain this overinvestment behavior (Ding et al., 2019; Liu, 2017; Shi, 2019; Zhang et al., 2016). Overinvestment is closely related to the use of corporate debt. According to empirical research, businesses with high financial leverage tend to overinvest. Because once the enterprise raises debt to finance investment, the risk shifts from the owner to the creditor, shareholders are more daring in investment decisions, which can easily lead to overinvestment (Childs et al, 2005; Lyandres & Zhdanov, 2005; Mauer & Sarkar, 2005). However, in Vietnam, in particular, and in the world in general, until recent years, there has not been any scientific research focusing on the application of machine learning to forecast overinvestment.

Overinvestment is influenced by various factors that have been extensively studied. However, based on the research team's knowledge and findings, machine learning methods for identifying overinvestment cases are still underexplored in the Vietnamese context. Future researchers may continue to analyze machine learning methods to classify overinvestment in companies. One research gap in the area of applying machine learning methods to classify overinvestment in firms in Vietnam is the lack of studies that compare the performance of different machine learning algorithms on this task. Although Ha (2009) employed neural networks and fuzzy logic in constructing financial risk analysis models, there has been insufficient attention to alternative algorithms that could be similarly effective, such as support vector machines, neural networks, or random forests. A comparative analysis of the performance of different algorithms in this context could help identify the most effective approach for predicting overinvestment in Vietnamese firms using machine learning methods. By addressing these research gaps, we can better understand the relationship between factors that influence overinvestment and itself. Therefore, we decided to conduct this study: Application of Machine Learning in classification of overinvestment: Evidence from listed firms in Vietnam stock exchange market. Our study clarifies how machine learning works in classifying overinvested companies. In addition, in this study, we also build a completely new model for measuring overinvestment based on the existing foundational theories.

This research focuses on the main objective to compare the performance in classify overinvestment companies of six classification algorithms: logistic regression (LR), support vector machine (SVM), decision tree (DT), random forest (RF), Naive Bayes (NB) and K-nearest neighbor (KNN). With the aforementioned comparison, we indicate which is the most suitable algorithm for classifying overinvestment companies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Investment and Overinvestment

Investment refers to the allocation of funds or resources towards a specific objective, whether it be obtaining an asset, supporting a production process, or establishing a new business abroad; and this pursuit is typically motivated by the desire to realize future profits or gains (Laopodis, 2020; Shan, Wang, & Policy, 2021). To put it differently, the act of investing involves directing resources towards particular projects in the hope of obtaining a return on investment (Boffo & Patalano, 2020). Additionally, an investor may seek to exert influence over corporate governance and establish a lasting interest in an enterprise operating in a distinct economic environment (Modigliani & Miller, 1958; OECD, 2008) posit that a firm's investment policy is unaffected by its financing decisions within a perfect market. However, in the natural world, factors such as asymmetric information and agency costs create problems such as underinvestment or overinvestment, where a company invests less or more than the optimal amount, respectively.

Overinvestment is a term used to describe the situation when a company or an economy spends too much on capital goods or projects that do not generate enough returns to justify the investment. Extraordinary investing was first introduced by (Jensen, 1986) based on the view of free cash flow. Jensen claimed that when a company has more free cash flow than it requires to maintain its operations and invest in projects with positive net present value ($NPV > 0$), this can lead to abnormal investment behaviors. Jensen & Meckling (1976) argue that due to the separation between ownership and management rights in most modern enterprises, there is always competition for power, even a conflict of interest between shareholders and investors manages. Managers favor projects that benefit themselves over shareholders, which creates the problem of overinvestment. Degryse & De Jong (2006) and Richardson (2006) propose two concepts related to the abnormal investment status of firms: underinvestment and overinvestment. Information asymmetry in the market leads to underinvestment, while agency problems lead to overinvestment.

2.2. Theoretical Basis

The research problem pertains to the different theoretical frameworks that are associated with overinvestment, namely: Capital market imperfections theory, Agency Theory, Free Cash Flow Theory, Behavioral finance theory, and Resource dependence theory.

Capital market imperfections theory

The theory of capital market imperfections posits that market frictions and information asymmetry can result in a misallocation of resources and reduced economic performance by causing overinvestment in specific industries or sectors (Rajan & Zingales, 1998). Financial constraints arising from market frictions and information asymmetry, such as transaction costs, adverse selection, and asymmetric information, can limit access to external financing at a reasonable cost. This can lead to overinvestment when companies resort to internal funds to finance their investment projects. In some cases, companies may overinvest in new projects simply to utilize their excess cash, even if those projects are not profitable in the short term

(Damodaran, 1999; Myers, 1984; Rajan & Zingales, 1998). The pursuit of growth opportunities and profitability can also contribute to overinvestment behavior (Damodaran, 1999; Myers, 1984; Rajan & Zingales, 1998). For instance, firms may overinvest in new projects to take advantage of potential future growth, even if those projects are not profitable in the short term (Myers, 1984). Similarly, companies may overinvest in projects with expected high profitability, which may not be sustainable in the long term (Myers, 1984). These behaviors can lead to a misallocation of resources and a reduction in overall economic performance. Moreover, the pecking order theory of capital structure can exacerbate overinvestment as companies may issue more debt or equity when internal funds are insufficient, increasing financing costs and signaling negative news to the market. Finally, market frictions such as transaction costs, regulatory barriers, or imperfect competition can also contribute to overinvestment (Damodaran, 1999). In conclusion, the theory of capital market imperfections provides valuable insights into the causes and consequences of overinvestment, highlighting the dangers of excessive reliance on internal capital and the importance of external financing.

Agency Theory

According to Kiel & Nicholson (2003), agency theory has demonstrated that capable managers or representatives are necessary to manage a company on behalf of its owners when ownership and control are separated. Jensen & Meckling (1976) are credited with developing agency theory, modeling the theory within the principal-agent relationship framework. Overinvestment in companies is linked to agency theory through the concepts of agency costs and agency problems. Agency costs refer to the expenses incurred by a company when managers prioritize their own interests over those of shareholders, leading to overinvestment in projects that benefit the managers more than the shareholders (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). This can happen when managers are motivated to pursue projects that are not in the best interests of shareholders, such as projects that increase their salaries or bonuses (Jensen, 1986). If a company invests excessively in capital goods or projects that do not generate sufficient returns, it may have to reduce costs elsewhere, such as by cutting employee salaries or bonuses, to offset the losses. Furthermore, investing in projects that do not yield adequate returns can result in a decline in shareholder value, which can negatively impact the company's financial performance in the long run (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Jensen, 1986). Effective corporate governance mechanisms that align the interests of managers and shareholders can mitigate overinvestment due to agency problems (Jensen, 1986).

Free Cash Flow Theory

The concept of free cash flow refers to the amount of cash that a company has available after paying for its operating expenses, capital expenses, and dividends. This surplus cash can be used to maintain assets and fund new investments (Chen et al., 2011; Richardson, 2006) posit that free cash flow has the potential to serve as an indication of overinvestment. The hypothesis regarding free cash flow is rooted in agency theory, which suggests that managers may be inclined to invest this surplus cash into projects that could ultimately lower profits and shareholder value, but provide them with greater control and status within the organization

(Jensen, 1986, 1989, 1993; Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Similarly, Rubin (1993) and Lang et al. (1991) contend that managers prefer to use any remaining free cash flow for continued investments in negative net present value projects rather than paying dividends. Agency costs can drive overinvestment in a firm, particularly when the company has excess free cash flow (Jensen, 1986). Additionally, growth opportunities and capitalization can contribute to overinvestment behavior under this theory is a technology company that has excess cash flows from its profitable operations (Jensen, 1986). Capitalization (CL) refers to the structure of a company's capital, including debt and equity. Overinvestment can occur if companies issue more debt or equity when internal funds are insufficient, increasing financing costs and signaling negative news to the market. This can happen when companies face financial constraints and cannot secure financing at a reasonable cost. The company may invest in multiple growth opportunities, such as expanding into new markets or developing new products, without thoroughly evaluating the profitability or sustainability of these investments. The firm may also use its excess cash to repurchase shares, further increasing its capitalization. However, if these investments do not generate sufficient returns, the company may be considered to have overinvested, as it has allocated resources towards projects that do not create value for its shareholders (Jensen, 1986; Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

Asymmetric Information Theory

In 1970, Akerlof introduced the concept of asymmetric information in his study *The market for "lemons": Quality uncertainty and the market mechanism*. This theory suggests that buyers have less information about the quality of a product they purchase, leading to mispricing by the seller. Asymmetric information can result in overinvestment when managers possess better information about potential project returns than outside investors (Akerlof, 1970; Cleary, 1999). This can lead to risky investments that are not in the best interest of the company or its shareholders due to differences in available information. Asymmetric information can lead regulators to engage in unethical or illegal practices for personal gain. However, companies can improve financial reporting and disclosure transparency to reduce information asymmetry. Providing more information to investors can help reduce managers' information advantage and increase market efficiency (Akerlof, 1970). In conclusion, asymmetric information theory highlights challenges in managing information available to managers and external investors and the risks of excessive investment in risky ventures. To mitigate overinvestment risk, businesses can improve disclosure practices and understand the role of asymmetric information.

Behavioral finance theory

Behavioral finance theory suggests that psychological biases and emotional factors can influence overinvestment, and cognitive limitations can impact how investors perceive and process information (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). Overly optimistic managers may fail to assess the risks and uncertainties involved in investment projects, and become emotionally attached to their projects, leading to excessive investments in projects that may not generate sufficient returns. Herding behavior, where investors follow the decision of others, can cause many companies to invest in the same industry or market, leading to oversupply and reduced

profits (Barberis & Thaler, 2003; Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). The sunk cost fallacy, where companies continue to invest in a project with little chance of success, is an example of this phenomenon. The disposition effect, where investors hold on to losing investments for too long in the hope of recouping their losses, can contribute to overinvestment (Shefrin & Statman, 1985). Anchoring bias, where investors rely too heavily on a single piece of information in their investment decision-making process, can also lead to suboptimal investment decisions (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). Understanding the potential causes and consequences of overinvestment due to psychological biases and cognitive limitations can help policymakers and investors develop strategies to reduce the risk of overinvestment, make more rational investment decisions, and promote higher market efficiency (Barberis & Thaler, 2003; Shefrin & Statman, 1985; Tversky & Kahneman, 1974).

Resource dependence theory

Resource dependency theory explains that organizations may invest heavily in external resources such as raw materials, technology, or skilled labor to create value for their customers and generate profit. However, the availability, quality, and cost of these resources may be uncertain and beyond the control of the company, leading to overinvestment in certain areas. This can result in a scenario where organizations continue to invest in a resource, even when it is no longer valuable or necessary, making them reluctant to reduce investment. To minimize the risk of overinvestment, companies can develop alternative sources of supplies or products and invest in acquiring or developing critical resources, even if the returns are uncertain. However, over-investing in resources can harm a company's profitability, stock prices, or even lead to bankruptcy if the returns on investments do not materialize or resources become outdated (Hillman et al., 2009; Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003).

2.3. Previous studies

Richardson (2006) examines the extent of firm level overinvestment of free cash flow. Using an accounting-based framework to measure over-investment and free cash flow, he found evidence that, consistent with agency cost explanations, overinvestment is concentrated in firms with the highest levels of free cash flow. Further tests examine whether firms' governance structures are associated with over-investment of free cash flow. The evidence suggests that certain governance structures, such as the presence of activist shareholders, appear to mitigate overinvestment. Hao et al., (2020) and Nghia et al., (2019) both employ a measure of overinvestment based on Richardson's (2006) model. Hao et al., (2020) practiced with 650 real estate companies listed in China between 2010 - 2015, successfully proved that overinvestment is a common practice (33.54% of real estate companies) and debt structure has a limited effect on overinvestment thereby providing policy implications for mitigating this problem. (Nghia et al., 2019) conduct a study that investigates the detrimental impact of overinvestment on firm performance and the moderating role of debt and dividend in mitigating agency costs resulting from overinvestment. The research comprises all of Vietnam's non-financial companies that are listed on HSX and HNX from 2006 to 2016. The study employs two specific measurements of overinvestment, namely HP Filter and the positive error terms obtained from the subequation of Overinvestment Estimation. The findings

reveal that overinvestment has a negative impact on profitability in Vietnamese enterprises. However, the harmful effect of overinvestment can be alleviated by the use of debt or the payout of dividends. Nevertheless, when combined, the separate influences of the two-variable interaction tend to be weakened. Overall, there are still limitations in the number of research studies related to the issue of overinvestment classification using machine learning models. While in recent years, machine learning algorithms have become increasingly popular as prediction tools in various industries such as finance, economics, healthcare, and marketing.

Machine learning (ML) is a type of computational intelligence that employs pre-programmed algorithms to examine input data and acquire knowledge from it through supervised or unsupervised methods, enabling it to produce output values that fall within an acceptable range. ML algorithms are adept at managing large and intricate datasets while also being capable of capturing non-linear relationships between variables. The effectiveness of ML has been demonstrated over the past decade, and its feasibility has been demonstrated as a substitute for classical statistical models in various research applications including mathematical problems forecasting, regression, and classification (Twumasi & Twumasi, 2022).

Several studies around the world have explored the application of machine learning in predicting financial and investment problems. For example, Lakhali et al. (2021) utilized machine learning techniques such as Logistic regression, Discriminative analysis, Neural networks, Boosting, AdaBoos, and RF to classify two basic investment models by Richardson (2006) and Biddle et al. (2009) and determine the impact of CSR performance on investment performance. Their findings suggest that Richardson's method yields better investment efficiency results. Özlem & Tan (2022) examine the motives behind firms' decisions to hold cash and cash equivalents, and why they refrain from redistributing or reinvesting their cash. The authors conduct an extensive literature review on the utilization of machine learning algorithms, including MLR, KNN, SVM, DT, extreme gradient boosting algorithm (XGB), and multilayer neural network (MLNN) methods, to predict the cash holding policy of 211 Turkish listed companies in Borsa Istanbul from 2006 to 2015. Their study revealed that DT and XGB models demonstrated superior performance compared to the other models, with an R² value of 0.73.

Although the study provides valuable insights, it is subject to certain limitations that need to be considered. Firstly, the research primarily centers on Turkish firms and their attributes, thus, the outcomes may not be applicable to other countries or regions. Moreover, the time frame of the study is from 2006 to 2015, and as a result, the findings may not accurately reflect the current market situation or changes. Lastly, the study did not consider macroeconomic variables, including gross domestic product growth, interest rates, and oil prices, which could have an impact on the results. Wu et al. (2021) concentrated on Taiwan's high-tech industry to predict cash holdings using DT techniques in the domain of financial forecasting with machine learning. Their research showed that among all the DTs, RF had the highest prediction accuracy. In a similar vein, Moubariki et al. (2019) conducted research on the cash management of the public sector and concluded that DT was the most effective predictive approach. Likewise, Bae (2010) explored the predictive dividend policy decisions of

Korean companies, utilizing SVMs, DTs, and neural networks, and determined that SVM was the most efficient technique. Using Gaussian process and radial neural network models, Gholamzadeh et al. (2021) carried out a research investigation to predict financial constraints of companies on the Tehran Stock Exchange. Their study found that machine learning methods are appropriate for anticipating financial difficulties experienced by firms. In addition, utilizing RF, quadratic discriminant analysis, and linear discriminant analysis, Mousa et al. (2022) forecasted the financial performance of 63 listed banks in emerging international markets. According to their results, the RF approach produced the most precise predictive models. Furthermore, including disclosure tone factors in addition to financial variables enhanced the models' precision and quality.

In Vietnam, there are studies on using machine learning models to support and predict financial-related problems. In another study, Tran et al. (2022) utilized empirical evidence from listed companies in Vietnam between 2011 to 2021 to predict financial hardship using machine learning algorithms. The research evaluated the predictive capability of different machine learning models and utilized SHAP values to interpret the obtained results. According to the study, XGB and random forest exhibited better recall and F1 scores compared to other models. Conversely, logistic regression, artificial neural network, and SVM showed elevated Type I errors. The random forest model had the highest AUC value (0.9788), signifying its superior classification performance in comparison to the remaining models. However, in Vietnam, there are still no specific studies on the application of machine learning models to classify overinvestment.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data

The present study utilized data from all companies listed on the two major Vietnamese stock exchanges, namely the Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange (HSX) and the Hanoi Stock Exchange (HNX). The data were obtained from the Refinitiv Eikon database and covered a period of a decade, from 2011 to 2020. Following the process of filtering and cleaning, the study obtained 6755 observations from a total of 717 listed companies that were listed after 2009. After the exclusion of financial enterprises, the remaining sample consisted of 658 non-financial enterprises. Subsequently, the infinite variables and missing value data were removed, resulting in a final set of 1707 valid data.

Regarding the data collection for about 10 years, there are many reasons for the choice of the authors. First of all, the longer the data collected over a period of time, the more observations it will have, meaning the more accurate the results will be, in case of fluctuations and data errors. The second reason, which is also the main reason for 10 years, is the economic crisis cycle according to Dr. Nguyen Duc Thanh, Director of the Institute for Economic and Policy Research (VEPR). In Vietnam, the last two economic crises were in 1997 and 2008. Also, according to his sharing from the end of 2018 and the beginning of 2019, the Vietnamese market is showing many potential crisis factors. Choosing 10 years as a way for the team to review economic indicators, eliminate short-term fluctuations and provide the most intuitive, general results.

3.2. Empirical framework

Our empirical framework is built based on the combination of two research models, the traditional model developed from the original study of Hao et al. (2020) and the modern model applying machine learning in predicting a company's overinvestment.

The methodology of this paper is drawn from the model-construction approach developed by Hao et al. (2020) and Richardson (2006). We propose to use model (1) as a means to estimate firms' level of overinvestment.

$$Inv_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Inv_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 Dar_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 Cash_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 Growth_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 Size_{i,t-1} + \alpha_6 Age_{i,t-1} + \alpha_7 Ret_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

If the residual value (ε) is greater than zero, it suggests the presence of overinvestment. Where $Inv_{i,t}$ is new investment from firm i in year t , scaled by total assets. This variable depends on the lagged new investment ($Inv_{i,t-1}$); the asset liabilities rate is measured as the total liabilities to total assets at the beginning of the year ($Dar_{i,t-1}$). The firm's growth opportunities ($Growth_{i,t-1}$) are measured as the growth rate of the annual sales revenue. The firm's cash holding rate ($Cash_{i,t-1}$); the number of years from IPO to the end of the last year ($Age_{i,t-1}$); the log of a firm's total assets ($Size_{i,t-1}$); and the dividend distribution rate of the previous year ($Ret_{i,t-1}$). All of these variables are lagged one year.

Figure 1: Data Processing

Source: authors.

In this study, we undertook a rigorous data preprocessing protocol for datasets procured from the Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange (HSX) and the Ha Noi Stock Exchange (HNX). The initial phase entailed the amalgamation of multiple pertinent datasets into a consolidated repository, as elucidated in Figure 1. Subsequently, an exhaustive data cleansing process was executed, encompassing the expurgation of infinite values, the amelioration of null entries, the eradication of extraneous symbols and special characters, and the judicious application of imputation techniques to rectify missing values. This exacting data preprocessing regimen serves as the linchpin for ensuring the integrity, quality, and reliability of the dataset, thus establishing a robust foundation conducive to precise and profound analysis. After addressing missing values, we opted to scale or normalize the features and encode categorical variables.

The dataset is typically divided into two subsets: a training set and a testing set, with 70% allocated for training the model and 30% reserved for assessing its performance on unseen data. The careful selection of an appropriate machine learning algorithm is of utmost importance in the realm of predictive modeling. This decision depends on various factors, including the nature of the problem (classification or regression), the size and quality of the data, among other nuanced considerations. Additionally, aligning the chosen algorithm precisely with the unique objectives of the research project plays a crucial role in this decision-making process, ensuring that the model's structure is tailored to meet the specific analytical requirements and scientific goals of the investigation.

Once an algorithm is chosen, it undergoes training using the training dataset. During this training phase, the model learns intricate patterns, relationships, and data features, continuously adjusting its internal parameters to make accurate predictions. Afterward, the performance of the trained model is evaluated using the testing dataset, and the choice of evaluation metrics depends on the specific problem at hand. This evaluation step is crucial in assessing the model's ability to generalize to new, unseen data. To enhance the model's robustness and mitigate challenges such as overfitting or data bias, practitioners often employ cross-validation techniques. Unlike a single train-test split, cross-validation involves systematically dividing the dataset into multiple subsets, known as "folds." One commonly used approach is 10-fold cross-validation, where the dataset is divided into ten equally-sized folds. The essence of 10-fold cross-validation lies in its thoroughness. The process unfolds as follows: the model undergoes ten distinct training and testing cycles. In each iteration, one of the ten folds serves as the test set, while the remaining nine folds form the training set. The model is meticulously trained on the training data and then evaluated on its performance against the isolated test fold. This iterative process continues until all ten folds have been used as the test set once, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the entire dataset.

The rigorous 10-fold cross-validation methodology offers significant advantages. It enables a comprehensive evaluation of the model's performance by testing its ability to generalize across diverse data partitions. Furthermore, it provides a reliable estimate of the model's capabilities, helping to identify and address any potential weaknesses or overfitting tendencies. In essence, 10-fold cross-validation serves as a crucial technique in the realm of machine learning, enhancing the reliability and credibility of model assessments in empirical research and data-driven endeavors. By meticulously preparing the data, we were able to harness a gamut of machine learning algorithms for the express purpose of anomaly detection, thereby affording us profound insights into the behavioral intricacies of financial data within the Vietnamese stock exchanges.

To develop our new model, we combined previous research studies. The model includes Manager Confidence (MC), Financial Constraints (FC), Agency Problems (AP), Size of the Firm (SOF), Growth Opportunities (GO), Profitability (PF), and Capitalization (CL). These variables are used to determine the presence of overinvestment, and lagged variables are also taken into account.

Table 1: Summary table of variables

Variables	Measurement	Research
Overinvestment	$OInv_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 MC_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 FC_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 AP_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 SOF_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 GO_{i,t-1} + \alpha_6 PF_{i,t-1} + \alpha_7 CL_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon$	The authors
Volatility of Firm Earnings (Vol)	$vol = \sigma\sqrt{T}$	(Grinblatt & Keloharju, 2009;
Stock Price Volatility (Spv)		Malmendier & Tate, 2008)
Debt-to-Asset Ratio	$\frac{Total\ debt}{Total\ assets}$	(Rajan & Zingales, 1995)
Z – score	$Z'' = 6,56 X1 + 3,26 X2 + 6,72 X3 + 1,05 X4 + 3,25$	(Altman et al, 1995)
Free Cash Flow (FCF)	Net cash flow from operating activities - CAPEX - Interest expense	(Chung et al., 2005)
Size of the Firm (SOF)	Total assets= Short-term assets + Long-term assets $\ln(\text{Total Assets})$	(Titman et al., 2004)
Growth Opportunities (GO)	$\frac{Net\ Revenue_t - Net\ Revenue_{t-1}}{Net\ Revenue_{t-1}}$	(Gompers et al., 2010)
Profitability (PF)	$ROA = \frac{Profit\ after\ tax}{Total\ assets}$	(Graham & Harvey, 2001)
Capitalization (CL)	Number of shares outstanding x value of shares at time	(Fama & French, 2004)

Source: Authors.

The modern research model is built based on evaluating the factors influencing overinvestment, especially in Vietnam. Inheriting from the model in the article of Hao et al. (2020) and Richardson (2006), we continue to apply the old variables and introduce new ones that are suitable for the practice in the Vietnamese market. The details of eight variables are as follows:

Overinvestment (OInv)

Overinvestment is a dependent variable; the results are expressed in 2 forms as 1 - overinvested and 0 - not overinvested. The regression model for running overinvestment variable is:

$$OInv_{i,t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 MC_{i,t-1} + \alpha_2 FC_{i,t-1} + \alpha_3 AP_{i,t-1} + \alpha_4 SOF_{i,t-1} + \alpha_5 GO_{i,t-1} + \alpha_6 PF_{i,t-1} + \alpha_7 CL_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Where, the inexplicable remainder is ε . If ε carries the sign (+) the enterprise is overinvested, the result is displayed as 1. If ε carries the sign (-) is the underinvested enterprise, the result is displayed as 0.

Manager overconfidence (MO)

The manager's overconfidence is understood as his willingness to make high-risk decisions that may not be met by his ability (Gervais et al., 2011). These managers tend to over-trust their ability to make accurate predictions and decisions. In such cases this overconfidence can lead to wrong investment decisions. Research by Grinblatt & Keloharju (2009) shows that overconfident individual investors tend to seek sensations leading to overinvestment in stock transactions, which means underperformance. Directly assessing a manager's overconfidence can be challenging, but various metrics have been used in research studies. It can be measured through Corporate Earnings Volatility and Stock Price Volatility (Malmendier and Tate, 2008). To measure volatility, we use the formula:

$$\text{vol} = \sigma\sqrt{T}$$

Where:

- vol = volatility over some interval of time
- σ = standard deviation of net income.
- T = number of periods in the time horizon
- This formula was proposed by the mathematician Benoît Mandelbrot to measure any volatility of a financial asset over a certain period of time.

Financial Constraints (FC)

When firms experience financial constraints, such as limited access to credit, they may engage in excessive investments to demonstrate their creditworthiness to lenders (Myers & Majluf, 1984). Furthermore, financial constraints can make companies more risk-aware, making them invest in low-risk ventures even when returns are suboptimal (Stein, 1996). Financial constraints are often difficult to measure directly, but there are several commonly used representations that have been used in empirical studies. For example, the debt-to-asset ratio (Rajan & Zingales, 1995), and the Z-score (Altman et al., 1995).

To measure the debt-to-asset ratio, we use the formula:

$$\text{Debt to asset ratio} = \frac{\text{Total debt}}{\text{Total assets}}$$

For the Z - Score we apply to listed companies:

$$Z'' = 6.56 X1 + 3.26 X2 + 6.72 X3 + 1.05 X4 + 3.26$$

Where:

- X1: Current assets/Total assets
- X2: Earning after tax/Total assets.
- X3: EBIT/ Total assets

- X4: Market capitalization of common shares/ Total book value of debt

The results will satisfy the following conclusions:

- If $Z'' > 2.6$: The company is in a safe zone and has no risk of bankruptcy.
- If $1.1 < Z'' < 2.6$: The company is in an alert zone and may have a risk of bankruptcy.
- If $Z'' < 1.1$: The company is in a danger zone and has a high risk of bankruptcy.

Agency Problems (AP)

Agency problems arise when there is a division between ownership and control in an organization. Managers can invest in projects that serve their personal interests instead of the interests of shareholders, lead to overinvestment (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Research by Richardson (2006) shows that the problem of agency costs, overinvestment is often concentrated in companies with the highest free cash flow. Therefore, to measure overinvestment the representative selection group is free cash flow. Specifically:

$$\text{FCF} = \text{Net cash flow from operating activities} - \text{CAPEX} - \text{Interest expense}$$

The theoretical basis of this formula is the basic principle of cash flow in corporate finance, that is, the ability of the business to generate free cash flow after deducting fixed and overhead costs. capital.

Size of Firm (SOF)

Size of firm is a term for size that has an important influence on a firm's ability to generate revenue (Babalola & development, 2013). Previous studies have shown that a firm's size has an impact on overinvestment. Titman *et al.*, (2004), and Harford & Li (2007) all conclude that larger firms tend to overinvest compared to smaller companies. To measure or distinguish the size of companies, we use the criterion of total assets through which the author compares the value of this company with other companies to get an overall view of the position. position and size of the firm in the industry:

$$\text{Total assets} = \text{Short-term assets} + \text{Long-term assets}$$

Growth Opportunities (GO)

Growth opportunity is the ability and potential of a business to develop in the future. Miller & Modigliani (1961) asserted the influence of growth opportunities on firm value. Firms that possess significant growth prospects might have a higher tendency to engage in overinvestment as they have a greater number of potential investments at their disposal (Gompers *et al.*, 2010).

To measure the growth opportunity of the firm, we use the revenue growth rate, similar to the growth opportunity representation in the study (Lins *et al.*, 2010). The index is calculated using the formula commonly used in financial statements:

$$\frac{\text{Net Revenue}_t - \text{Net Revenue}_{t-1}}{\text{Net Revenue}_{t-1}}$$

Profitability (PF)

Profitability is the degree to which a business makes a profit. High profits can lead to companies looking for new investment opportunities, which can easily lead to many wrong investment decisions due to subjective reasons as they possess more resources that could be utilized. To measure corporate profitability, we estimate ROA, similar to the proposal of Adyani & Sampurno (2011) considering the bank's profitability is measured by ROA at the end of year t. The specific formula is as follows:

$$\text{ROA} = \frac{\text{Profit after tax}}{\text{Total assets}}$$

Capitalization (CL)

Capitalization is a financial concept used to value a company's market value. Companies with high levels of capitalization tend to overinvest. Conversely, companies with lower levels of capitalization may be more conservative with their investments due to limited resources. To measure capitalization, we use the formula given by Fama & French (2004):

Market capitalization = Number of shares outstanding x Market price of each share

In recent times, machine learning algorithms have become increasingly popular as prediction tools, even within the finance industry. In order to forecast overinvestment, we utilized and compared several machine learning algorithms, including logistics regression, support vector machine, decision tree, random forest, K-Nearest neighbor, and naive Bayes, as outlined by Mousa & El-Hendawy (2021). In this study, the author applies the following machine learning algorithms: Logistics Regression, Support Vector Machine, K-Nearest Neighbor, Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree and Random Forest. Those machine learning algorithms will be comparing performance based on accuracy, precision, recall, F1 Score, and time consuming.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

The number of enterprises listed on the HSX exchange is 360/658, accounting for 54.71%, and it is accounting for 45.29% for HNX (298 enterprises). The study examined various financial and non-financial variables of listed firms, including: overinvestment, debt ratio, FCF, ROA, ROE, quick ratio, capitalization, manager score, growth opportunities, OCF ratio, retain and z score. After removing the observations with the missing value, the data was utilized, including 1707 observations with descriptive statistics as follows:

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of observations

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Med	Max
Debt ratio	1707	0.381	0.431	0.000	0.275	2.814
FCF	1707	0.015	0.137	-0.625	0.018	0.861
ROA	1707	0.092	0.081	-0.006	0.073	0.994
ROE	1707	0.182	0.126	-0.012	0.163	1.269
Quick ratio	1707	0.487	0.634	0.001	0.263	4.667
Capitalization	1707	14.402	45.517	0.008	2.674	576.794
Manager confidence	1707	0.245	1.783	-21.353	0.059	27.134
Growth Oppotunities	1707	0.125	0.378	-1.039	0.077	2.813
OCF ratio	1707	0.248	0.330	-0.620	0.133	2.265
Retain	1707	3.569	13.854	-117.148	0.579	114.775
Z score	1707	2.984	2.046	-0.238	2.470	13.624

Source: Author's calculation

Figure 2: Frequency distribution of overinvestment

Source: Author's calculation

Collected data is indicated as qualitative data 0 (non-overinvestment) and 1 (overinvestment), these results are calculated based on the traditional model to compare with the value running in the model. According to the results of running analysis from Stata, there are 827/1707 observations of overinvestment at 48.85%. These values are used to assess the accuracy of machine learning algorithms. The debt ratio of enterprises is at a low level with a range from 0 to 2.814, a mean value of 0.381, median value of 0.275, and volatility of 0.431. Additionally, the free cash flow represented as a ratio to total assets, ranges from -0.626 to 0.861, with a mean value of 0.015 and a median value of 0.018, indicating positive news about

the business's cash flow. The return on assets has a mean value of 0.092 and a median value of 0.074, indicating the asset utilization efficiency of listed firms. The return on equity has a mean value of 0.182 and a median value of 0.163, indicating an efficient use of equity. However, there are doubts about the firms' liquidity as the quick ratio has a mean value of 0.614, a median value of 0.274, and a standard deviation of 1.392.

The market capitalization value fluctuates widely from 0.008 trillion VND to 576.794 trillion VND with a mean value 14.402 trillion VND, a median value 2.674 trillion VND, and a value bias of 45,517 trillion VND. The CEO confidence index has a range from -21.353 to 27.134, with a median value of 0.059 greater than 0, indicating that CEOs are confident with their investment decisions, and may lead to overinvestment decisions. The net sales growth rate has a mean of 0.125, a median of 0.077, and a degree of variation of 0.378. The OCF ratio has a mean value of 0.248, a median value of 0.133, and a degree of variation of 0.330, indicating the ability to cover short-term debts of enterprises with net operating cash is quite low. The income retained after paying dividends to shareholders has median value 0.579 billion VND and mean value 3.569, indicating that most companies keep possession of profits to continue reinvesting to expand their markets, which also leads to the possibility of overinvestment of the business. Finally, the Z-score of the firm's probability of bankruptcy ranges from -0.238 to 13.624. The median value of 2.470 clearly shows that more than 50% of the observations are in the warning and danger zones.

In conclusion, analyzing financial metrics such as debt ratio, free cash flow, return on assets, return on equity, quick ratio, capitalization, CEO confidence index, growth opportunities, OCF ratio, income retained, and Z-score can provide valuable insights into the overinvestment of listed companies. By looking at these metrics and making comparisons between companies, investors and analysts can make informed decisions about investment opportunities.

4.2. Machine Learning model

There are six classification reports for six models: Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbor, Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, Decision Tree and Random Forest. All models were trained to classify data into two classes, labeled 0 and 1. Class 0 represents all companies that do not overinvestment and class 1 represents all companies that do overinvestment. The report evaluates the performance of the model based on precision, recall, F1-score, support, and accuracy metrics. Precision is a measure of how many of the instances classified as positive are actually positive. Recall is a measure of how many of the actual positive instances are correctly identified as positive. The F1-score is a weighted average of precision and recall that provides a single measure of overall performance. Support is the number of instances of each class in the dataset.

Figure 3: Algorithm Comparison - Accuracy

Source: Author's calculation

Logistic regression model classification report is evaluated on a dataset containing 513 instances. The report provides various performance metrics for the model. Overall accuracy is 0.68, which means that it correctly predicted the class label for 68% of the instances in the dataset. The precision for class 0 is 0.66, which means that when the model predicts an instance to be in class 0, it is correct 66% of the time. The recall for class 0 is 0.74, which means that out of all the instances that actually belong to class 0, the model correctly identified 74% of them. The F1-score for class 0 is 0.70, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall for class 0. Similarly, the precision for class 1 is 0.70, which means that when the model predicts an instance to be in class 1, it is correct 70% of the time. The recall for class 1 is 0.62, which means that out of all the instances that actually belong to class 1, the model correctly identified 62% of them. The F1-score for class 1 is 0.66. The macro avg of F1-score for both classes is 0.68, which is the average of these metrics across both classes.

With the K-Nearest Neighbors algorithm, the precision for class 0 is 0.61, which means that 61% of the instances predicted to be in class 0 are actually in class 0. The recall for class 0 is 0.67, which means that 67% of the instances in class 0 are correctly identified as class 0. The F1-score for class 0 is 0.64, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall for class 0. For class 1, the precision is 0.63, recall is 0.57, and f1-score is 0.60. The overall accuracy of the model is 0.62, which means that 62% of the instances in the dataset are correctly classified by the model. The macro-average of precision, recall, and f1-score is the unweighted mean of these metrics across both classes, which is 0.62 in this case.

Naive Bayes model identified instances labeled as 1, with a precision of 0.52 and a recall of 0.93. Besides, the model performed poorly in identifying instances labeled as 0, with a precision of 0.66 and a recall of 0.13. The overall accuracy of the model was 0.53, indicating that the model correctly classified 53% of instances. The macro average F1-score was 0.44, which is the average F1-score across the two classes. In summary, the Naive Bayes model had

a relatively good performance in identifying instances labeled as 1 but performed poorly in identifying instances labeled as 0. Therefore, the model may need to be further improved to achieve better overall performance on this dataset.

Figure 4: Algorithm Comparison - F1-Score

Source: Author's calculation

The SVM model performed relatively well in identifying instances labeled as 0, with a precision of 0.65 and a recall of 0.75. The model also performed well in identifying instances labeled as 1, with a precision of 0.70 and a recall of 0.60. The overall accuracy of the model was 0.67, indicating that the model correctly classified 67% of instances. The macro average F1-score was 0.67, which is the average F1-score across the two classes. In summary, the SVM model had a good overall performance, with high accuracy and reasonable precision and recall scores for both classes. Therefore, the SVM model can be considered a good choice for this classification task.

The Decision Tree model had similar precision, recall, and F1-score for both classes, with values around 0.63. The overall accuracy of the model was also 0.63, indicating that the model correctly classified 63% of instances. The macro average F1-score was 0.63, which is the average F1-score across the two classes. The Decision Tree model had a moderate overall performance, with similar precision, recall, and F1-score for both classes, and an accuracy of 63%. Despite the model have not performing as well as some other classification algorithms, it can still be useful for certain applications and datasets.

The Random Forest model performed reasonably well in identifying instances labeled as 0, with a precision of 0.68 and a recall of 0.74. The model also performed well in identifying instances labeled as 1, with a precision of 0.71 and a recall of 0.64. The overall accuracy of the model was 0.69, indicating that the model correctly classified 69% of instances. The macro average F1-score was 0.69, which is the average F1-score across the two classes.

The use of cross-validation technique is essential in evaluating the accuracy and F1-score of 6 classification models as it provides a robust and unbiased estimate of 6 models performance. In this study, we have used 10-fold cross-validation to evaluate the performance of 6 classification models, namely Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors, Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, Decision Tree and Random Forest. Our results indicate that Naive Bayes has the lowest accuracy rate of about 55%. On the other hand, Random Forest and Logistic Regression algorithms show the highest accuracy rates of approximately 68% and 69% (Figure 2). Although both algorithms have similar accuracy rates, Random Forest exhibits greater variability as indicated by the larger spread of its results, with some instances yielding an accuracy rate of up to 75% (Figure 4). In light of these findings, we can conclude that Random Forest is the superior model among the six models evaluated in this study. This is due to its consistently high accuracy rates across different cross-validation folds, despite its higher variability compared to Logistic Regression. Therefore, we recommend the use of Random Forest for classification tasks that require high accuracy rates. Figure 3 depicts the F1-score of the 6 classification algorithms evaluated in our study. Our findings indicate that Naive Bayes has the lowest F1 Score, measuring less than 50% according to Table 2. In contrast, the Random Forest algorithm has the highest F1 Score, at around 70%. However, as shown by the large spread of its results, with a variation of up to 75%, Random Forest can be considered a model with moderate strength.

Accuracy is an important metric in classification because it directly measures the percentage of correctly classified instances, which is a fundamental goal of many classification problems. The accuracy of a classification model is determined by the number of true positives (correctly predicted positive instances), true negatives (correctly predicted negative instances), false positives (incorrectly predicted positive instances), and false negatives (incorrectly predicted negative instances). Accuracy is calculated as the ratio of the number of correctly classified instances to the total number of instances. A high accuracy means that the model is able to correctly classify most of the companies. While accuracy alone may not always provide a complete picture of the performance of a classification model, it is a crucial metric that is often used to evaluate the effectiveness of a model. Moreover, accuracy can be a useful metric when comparing different models or when assessing the impact of different features on the classification performance. F1-score is also an important metric for evaluating the performance of classification models because it considers both precision and recall, which are two important aspects of classification performance. Precision measures the proportion of true positive predictions among all positive predictions, while recall measures the proportion of true positive predictions among all actual positive instances. F1-score shows the harmonic mean of precision and recall and provides a single metric that balances both precision and recall. F1-score is useful because it provides a single metric that considers both precision and recall and provides a balanced measure of classification performance. This makes it particularly useful in situations where both precision and recall are important, or where there is a trade-off between the two. The Random Forest model had a good overall performance, with high accuracy and reasonable precision and recall scores for both classes. Therefore, the Random Forest model can be considered a good choice among the 6 proposed models for overinvestment classification.

Figure 5: Feature Importances - Random Forest Model

Source: Author's calculation

Figure 5 describes feature importances represent the relative importance of each predictor variable in the Random Forest model. The values provided indicate the contribution of each variable to the model's accuracy or predictive power. The most important predictor variable is "FCF" (free cash flow), with an importance value of 0.14. This suggests that free cash flow is a critical factor in predicting whether companies are overinvesting or not, likely indicating that companies with higher free cash flow tend to overinvest. In contrast, "industry" appears to be the least important variable, with an important value of 0.055. This suggests that the industry in which a company operates may not be a critical factor in overinvestment of firms. Overall, these findings provide insights into the factors that contribute to overinvestment of firms and may have practical implications for financial decision-making.

4.3. Discussion

Both Logistic Regression algorithm and Random Forest algorithm perform similarly in terms of average accuracy (0.68), but there are some differences in their performance regarding other metrics. For class 0, Random Forest has slightly higher precision (0.68 vs. 0.66) compared to Logistic Regression, while both algorithms have the same recall (0.74). For class 1, Random Forest outperforms Logistic Regression in terms of both precision (0.71 vs. 0.7) and recall (0.64 vs. 0.62). The F1 score, which combines precision and recall into a single metric, is also slightly higher for Random Forest (0.69 vs. 0.68).

In the context of this classification problem, class 0 represents firms with no overinvestment, while class 1 represents firms with overinvestment. Overinvestment occurs when a company invests too much capital in its operations or assets, which can lead to inefficient resource allocation and diminished returns. When interpreting the results, it's essential to consider the implications of each class. For instance, a high recall for class 0

indicates that the algorithm can correctly identify a large proportion of firms without overinvestment. On the other hand, high precision for class 1 suggests that the algorithm can accurately pinpoint firms with overinvestment. As mentioned earlier, both Logistic Regression and Random Forest perform similarly in terms of average accuracy, but there are some differences in their performance concerning precision and recall for each class. The Random Forest algorithm has slightly better precision and recall for class 1 (overinvestment firms) than Logistic Regression, which may be beneficial in identifying and addressing potential overinvestment cases.

Based on the results, the Random Forest algorithm appears to be the better choice for classifying overinvestment firms. However, it is essential to consider other factors, such as interpretability, computation time, and ease of implementation. It is also crucial to perform further evaluation using techniques like cross-validation and testing on different datasets to ensure the chosen algorithm's robustness. The importance of each predictor variable in the Random Forest model was also analyzed. The feature importance analysis indicated that free cash flow was the most important independent variable, followed by growth opportunity, ROE, and management confidence. These results suggest that firms with higher growth opportunities, better profitability, more significant free cash flow, and higher management confidence are more likely to be classified as overinvestment. Our study has important implications for researchers and practitioners interested in understanding the factors that contribute to firms being classified as overinvestment or not. The use of machine learning models can provide valuable insights for financial decision-making of firms.

Previous studies on overinvestment have used various methods, such as degree of Richardson (2006) used free cash flow as a measure of overinvestment and found that overinvestment is negatively related to future profitability, Effect of debt and dividends on the relationship between investment overcapacity and performance (Nghia et al., 2019), regression statistics (Farooq et al., 2015). However, none of these studies applied machine learning techniques, despite the increasing popularity of machine learning in financial research. Inheriting the previous methods, our study addresses this gap by introducing machine learning algorithms as a new approach to overinvestment classification that complements the existing literature by showing the potential of machine learning in improving the accuracy and efficiency of overinvestment classification.

This study has not confirmed previous research on using machine learning machine learning algorithms to make predictions in the financial field, it could nevertheless be argued include differences in sample characteristics such as industry characteristics, sample size or environment and geographical location. It serves to compare and identify algorithms suitable for each different environment. Özlem and Tan (2022) found that decision tree (DT) was the best performing model among multiple machines learning models, including multiple linear regression (MLR), K-nearest neighbors (KNN), support vector machine (SVM), and DT.

There could be several reasons for these differences in findings. One possible reason is the difference in the research environment or context. Each study may have used different datasets with variations in sample size, data quality, and industry characteristics, which can affect the performance of machine learning models. Additionally, the specific variables used in

the machine learning models may differ across studies, leading to variations in the classification accuracy. Another possible reason for the differences is the choice of machine learning techniques and their parameter settings. Different studies may have used different algorithms, feature engineering techniques, and model hyperparameters, which can impact the performance of the models. The performance of machine learning models is also sensitive to the specific dataset and its characteristics, as well as the availability of data for model training and validation.

The finding that free cash flow was the most important independent variable in predicting overinvestment aligns with several prior studies that have identified FCF as a significant determinant of overinvestment. This is consistent with Richardson (2006), Chen et al. (2011) and Jensen (1986). In addition, Growth Opportunity is equally important and also affects overinvestment, this substantiates previous findings in the literature Farooq et al. (2015). In addition, Smith (1994) proposed the "free cash flow hypothesis" which suggests that firms with high levels of FCF are more likely to engage in overinvestment activities due to the availability of excess cash that may not be efficiently utilized for productive investments. Similarly, Jensen (1986) argued that managers may have incentives to overinvest in order to pursue their own interests at the expense of shareholders, particularly when they have access to abundant internal funds such as FCF. Furthermore, other studies have also found that FCF is positively correlated with overinvestment. For instance, studies by Lang et al. (1996), Opler et al. (1999), and Almeida & Campello (2007) have reported similar findings, suggesting that FCF has a significant impact on firms' overinvestment behavior. Free cash flow is the most effective tool for predicting overinvestment because it measures a company's ability to generate what investors care about most, which is cash available to distribute to shareholders, creditors, and reinvest back into the business. Companies with high free cash flow have more resources to invest in new projects or acquisitions, which can lead to overinvestment. Additionally, free cash flow can be used to fund share buybacks or dividends, which can also contribute to overinvestment.

The study clearly achieved this objective by comparing the performance of six different classification algorithms, namely LR, SVM, DT, RF, NB, and KNN, in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. The findings in the study clearly highlight that Random Forest (RF) outperforms Logistic Regression (LR) in terms of precision and recall for classifying overinvestment companies (class 1), indicating that RF may be the most suitable algorithm for this particular classification problem. The study provides evidence that the performance of different algorithms may vary depending on the specific problem, and in the context of overinvestment classification, RF may be more effective than LR. Therefore, the results of the study are consistent with the stated objectives of comparing the performance of different classification algorithms and providing insights on the most suitable algorithm for classifying overinvestment companies. The final result of the Random Forest algorithm is aggregated from many decision trees, so the information from the trees will complement each other, leading to a model with low bias and low variance, or a model with high results prediction. The idea of aggregating decision trees of the Random Forest algorithm is similar to the idea of Crowd Intelligence proposed by James Surowiecki (2004). Crowd intelligence says that usually synthesizing information from a group is better than from a kernel. In the Random Forest

algorithm, it also synthesizes information from a group of decision trees and the results are better than the Decision Tree algorithm with 1 decision tree.

Random forest processing involves aggregating diversity of opinion, partitioning, decentralization, and aggregation to produce classification results. The randomness in the process helps Random Forest come to the best conclusion because the random sample selected is representative of the population and many different points of view. Each tree is built off of a randomly selected subset of the data and predictors. Therefore, each tree is built based on completely different information from every other tree. By utilizing different training sets and randomly selecting the subset of predictors at each split, the algorithm ensures that each tree is independent from every other. This actually has the effect of decorrelating the trees. Decentralization is inherent in the fact that each tree is built with different training data and different predictors to choose from at each split. The last step of the algorithm is to take the mode (classification). Some mechanism exists to turn private judgments into a collective decision.

One of the strengths of our study is that we leverage the power of machine learning algorithms, which are known for their ability to process large volumes of data and uncover complex patterns that may not be easily discernible through traditional approaches. By harnessing the capabilities of machine learning, we have achieved improved accuracy in overinvestment classification, which is a significant advancement in the field of overinvestment research. Furthermore, our study aligns with the current trend of utilizing machine learning in finance research and processing financial data. Machine learning has gained significant traction in recent years due to its potential to extract valuable insights from large and complex datasets. By applying machine learning techniques in the context of overinvestment classification, our study contributes to the growing body of literature on the use of machine learning in finance, showcasing its applicability and effectiveness in solving financial decision-making problems.

Despite the significant contributions of our study, there are certain limitations that warrant further investigation. First, our study focuses on a specific context and the generalizability of our findings to other regions may be limited. Further research could explore the application of machine learning in overinvestment classification in different contexts to validate the robustness of our outcomes. Second, our study employs historical data, and the dynamic nature of financial markets may affect the performance of machine learning algorithms in real-time scenarios. Future research could explore the real-time applicability of machine learning in overinvestment classification using up-to-date data. However, it is essential to acknowledge that our study has limitations. The sample size used in this study was relatively small, and the predictor variables used may not be exhaustive or representative of all factors contributing to overinvestment. Future research could explore the use of additional variables or consider different classification methods to further investigate the phenomenon of overinvestment. Besides that, one limitation is the predictor variables used in our study may not be exhaustive, and there may be other factors that contribute to overinvestment that were not included in our analysis. Future research could explore the use of additional variables or consider different classification methods to further investigate the phenomenon of overinvestment and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors at play.

Despite these limitations, our study suggests that Random Forest is an effective model for classifying firms as overinvestment or not.

Overall, our results suggest that Random Forest is an effective model for the classification of firms as overinvesting or not. The feature important analysis also provides insights into the factors contributing to overinvestment, which can inform financial decision-making for firms. In terms of addressing overinvestment, the following recommendations can be made: To ensure that resources are being used efficiently and to avoid overinvestment, companies should regularly monitor their capital allocation strategies and investment decisions. This can involve conducting detailed analyses of their cash flow statements, identifying areas where resources may be underutilized or misallocated, and implementing measures to address these issues. By doing so, companies can optimize their resource allocation and avoid the negative consequences of overinvestment, such as reduced profitability and decreased shareholder value.

Investors and analysts can also use the classification results from our study to identify firms with potential overinvestment and exercise caution when making investment decisions. By paying attention to the classification results, investors can avoid investing in firms that have a higher risk of overinvestment and instead focus on investing in firms that are more likely to provide sustainable returns over the long term. Furthermore, investors can use the results to guide their engagement with companies, encouraging them to prioritize efficient resource allocation and avoid overinvestment.

For firms that are identified as having overinvestment, it is recommended that they conduct thorough internal reviews and reassess their investment strategies. This can involve reviewing their capital allocation policies, identifying areas where resources are being misallocated, and implementing changes to optimize their resource utilization. By doing so, firms can improve their financial performance, increase shareholder value, and position themselves for long-term success. Overall, it is essential for companies, investors, and analysts to be aware of the risks associated with overinvestment and take proactive steps to avoid it.

5. CONCLUSION

Investment is an essential activity for businesses, knowing whether the company is overinvesting or not is necessary because it can harm business performance (Nguyen Trong & Nguyen, 2021). This research paper contributes to the field of finance by assessing the implementation of machine learning algorithms for overinvestment classification in listed firms on the Vietnam stock exchange market. Our study aimed to investigate the performance of six classification algorithms in classifying overinvestment companies and provide insights for financial decision-making. The findings of this study emphasize the significance of employing machine learning algorithms to detect overinvestment, a complex financial issue, and offer valuable insights for financial decision-making. Based on our analysis, logistic regression (LR) and random forest (RF) exhibit similar average accuracy rates (approximately 70%), but they demonstrate variations in precision and recall when categorizing overinvestment companies. These disparities in performance shed light on the classification aspects related to overinvestment. Our study's outcomes further strengthen the existing body of literature, affirming the pivotal role of free cash flow (FCF) in driving overinvestment

tendencies among firms. The alignment of our results with prior research enhances the robustness and credibility of our study.

This study adds to the existing literature on overinvestment and presents a practical tool for companies to detect overinvestment and establish management strategies, which has important implications for researchers and practitioners interested in understanding the factors that improve whether companies are classified as overinvested or not. The use of machine learning models can provide valuable insights into the financial decision-making of firms. Regular monitoring of capital allocation strategies and investment decisions proposed for companies to ensure efficient resource utilization and avoid overinvestment. Investors and analysts can utilize the classification results from our study to identify firms with potential overinvestment and exercise caution in their investment decisions. Firms recognized as having overinvestment can conduct thorough internal reviews and reassess their investment strategies to maximize returns and reduce inefficiencies.

From the results shown in the research results, we recommend that companies pay attention to their investment activities and avoid investing when the company no longer has profitable projects because this can easily lead to overinvestment problems that can cause business losses. At the same time, businesses need to limit free cash flow through debt or dividend policies, because high free cash flow creates conditions for overinvestment behavior.

However, the study has certain limitations. The focus is primarily on firms listed on the Vietnam Stock Exchange and their attributes from 2011 to 2020. Although the research team tried to expand the scope of their research, the 10-year time series is still not long enough to be able to conclude the impact of overinvestment on all businesses in Vietnam during the period long-term. So the research team proposed that future research can extend the timeframe and include non-financial variables such as Organizational Culture and Innovation and Technology. Listed enterprises in Vietnam are often large enterprises, so future studies can expand to include small and medium enterprises to draw more general conclusions. In addition to expanding the period, the number of countries studied can also be increased. Researchers can conduct a cross-country analysis by categorizing overinvestment in developed and emerging markets to identify if there are variations in the extent of overinvestment across markets.

Additionally, industry classification can be included to examine companies on a sectoral basis in future research. It is important to note that further evaluation using techniques like cross-validation and testing on different datasets is necessary to ensure the robustness of the chosen algorithm. Other factors such as interpretability, computation time, and ease of implementation should also be considered when selecting a suitable algorithm for a specific problem. Furthermore, researchers can combine this information to improve regression models, enhancing the performance of various machine learning algorithms in identifying overinvestment and uncovering investment trends overinvestment by companies.

In conclusion, our study contributes to the literature on overinvestment by comparing the performance of different classification algorithms and providing insights on the most suitable algorithm for identifying overinvestment companies. Companies should regularly monitor their capital allocation strategies and investment decisions to ensure efficient use of resources and avoid overinvestment. Investors and analysts can use these classification results to identify

firms with potential overinvestment and exercise caution when making investment decisions. Firms identified as having overinvestment can conduct thorough internal reviews and reassess their investment strategies, focusing on maximizing returns and reducing inefficiencies. The findings have practical implications for financial decision-makers and highlight the value of machine-learning approaches in addressing complex financial problems. Future research can build on our outcomes and explore other machine-learning techniques or incorporate additional variables to enhance the accuracy of overinvestment classification models.

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APPENDIX

Table 3. Classification report

Classification	Not Overinvestment				Overinvestment				Macro Avg F1
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support	
Logistic Regression	0.66	0.74	0.70	257	0.70	0.62	0.66	256	0.68
K-Nearest Neighbors	0.61	0.67	0.64	257	0.63	0.57	0.60	256	0.62
Naive Bayes	0.66	0.13	0.21	257	0.52	0.93	0.66	256	0.44
Support Vector Machine	0.65	0.75	0.70	257	0.70	0.60	0.65	256	0.67
Decision Tree	0.63	0.64	0.63	257	0.63	0.62	0.63	256	0.63
Random Forest	0.68	0.74	0.70	257	0.71	0.64	0.67	256	0.69

Source: Author's calculation

FACTORS AFFECTING INTENTION TO USE E-KYC AT COMMERCIAL BANKING IN VIET NAM: AN APPLICATION TAM MODEL

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Abstract

The Industrial Revolution 4.0 has brought great benefits in all industries, the field of finance and banking has also shown breakthroughs in developing and providing products and services to customers. Among those technology applications, it must be mentioned that one application in recent years has gradually dominated the market and gradually become familiar to customers is the application of electronic Know Your Customer (e-KYC). However, the situation shows that there is still a part of customers who are still afraid to use e-KYC applications. Therefore, the study used the TAM model to understand the factors affecting the intention to use e-KYC at commercial banks in Vietnam, through online customer surveys from 9/2022 to 12/2022. The purpose of the study is to explore the factors affecting customers' intention to use e-KYC to make recommendations to commercial banks to increase the number of customers using e-KYC. Research results have shown that the Trust factor has the greatest impact on the intention to use e-KYC, however the subjective Standard factor and ease of use do not have an impact on the intent to use e-KYC. On that basis, the author proposes recommendations to develop e-KYC at Vietnamese commercial banks in the next time.

Keywords: e-KYC, influencing factors, intention to use, TAM

1. INTRODUCTION

E-KYC stands for electronic Know Your Customer – is electronic Know Your Customer – is electronic Know Your Customer or online customer identification, the new identification technology of the current banking system. This technology allows banks to identify customers right on smartphones. E-KYC helps banks reduce the burden of opening accounts, helping transaction account openers to open bank accounts with simple procedures, no need to go directly to bank branches to do paperwork as before. Specifically, customers only need to use their original CCCD or ID card to open a bank account. The electronic identification system only needs an image of the front or back of this document, then verifies and lists the information in the most accurate way. Accompanying that will be to verify customers with personal documents by comparing CCCD/ID card photos with current photos through face scanning.

Implementing the Prime Minister's Decision No. 06/QĐ-TTg dated 06/01/2022 approving the Project on development of data application on population, electronic

identification and authentication for national digital transformation in the period of 2022 - 2025, vision to 2030 (referred to as Project 06) of the Government, The SBV Governor promulgated the Banking Sector's Plan to implement Project 06 and established a Banking Sector Working Group to implement Project 06 headed by a Deputy Governor. The connection of the national database on population also serves public services and operations of the SBV (such as credit information operations; money laundering prevention and fighting). Commercial banks such as Joint Stock Bank for Foreign Trade of Vietnam (Vietcombank), Joint Stock Bank for Investment and Development of Vietnam (BIDV), Joint Stock Bank for Industry and Trade of Vietnam (VietinBank) ... has cooperated with the Department of Police for Administrative Management of Social Order (C06) - Ministry of Public Security to test the application solution to authenticate people through chip-attached CCCD cards in a number of operations of commercial banks such as: (i) Authentication and identification of customers at transaction counters; (ii) Remote customer authentication and identification via the Internet (e-KYC) to open accounts, perform e-banking and digital banking transactions; (iii) Authentication and identification of customers making deposits and withdrawals at ATMs (Thanh Thuy, 2022). As a result, from the beginning of July 2020, the State Bank of Vietnam has allowed about 10 joint-stock commercial banks to pilot the application of electronic identification (e-KYC) in operation with the requirement to ensure safety and risks, by the beginning of 2023, the number of banks opening e-KYC accounts on phones has increased to 12 (Vanbanker, 2023).

Although it is one of the new applications, e-KYC has proven its role as an effective arm to help commercial banks in developing digital banking services as well as optimizing customer experience. According to statistics from the State Bank of Vietnam, as of June 2023, there are about 11.9 million accounts opened by e-KYC operating out of a total of 156 million accounts, 10.8 million cards opened by e-KYC in circulation out of a total of 146 million cards. In addition to the advantages of e-KYC, there are still disadvantages that make users still wonder when choosing to use. Some issues can be mentioned such as: products and services on e-KYC accounts are not as rich as traditional accounts, some banks also offer daily transaction limits, or the risk of fraud and identity theft; stability, safety of the system; user data, privacy, and database protection. In addition, the implementation of e-KYC also requires synchronous implementation of the national population database, as well as a stable legal framework for this activity to protect both customers and banks. Thus, there are many factors affecting customers in choosing to use electronic customer identification at banks. Identifying these influencing factors is extremely important because solutions will be proposed to promote the further development of this activity.

With that in mind, this study focuses on analyzing the factors influencing the intention to use e-KYC at commercial banks. In addition to the summary, the article problem setting is structured as follows: research overview (part 2), research methods (part 3), results and discussion (part 4), conclusion (part 5).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on e-wallets and fintech

Research of Muhtarom Widodo (2019) extended the UTAUT2 model by adding cognitive risk and reliability factors to the model to assess e-wallet usage behavior in Indonesia.

The results of the study have shown that habit factors play the most important role in the factors that influence the behavioral intent of using e-wallets. In addition, expected effort, social influence, hedonic motivation and cognitive risk are also factors that have a great influence on the behavioral intentions to adopt e-wallets of Indonesian people.

The study of Nayanajith & Damunupola (2021), the results show found that Subjective Norm (SN) had a significant effect on customers' perceived usefulness (PU), ease of use (PEU), and intention to use cryptocurrency (INT). PU has also been shown to be a direct predictor of Crypto Intent. In contrast, Perceived Ease of Use did not significantly affect Customer Intent, supporting the indirect effect of the hypotheses between Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Useful and Intent.

Next is the study of Hu et al. (2019). This paper proposes an improved technology acceptance model (TAM) that combines user creativity, government support, brand image and perceived risk as determinants of trust. information to investigate how users accept Fintech services. The results show that users' trust in Fintech services has a very significant influence on user acceptance attitude. In addition, perceived ease of use and perceived risk did not influence users' attitudes towards the adoption of Fintech services.

Or the research of Dao My Hang (2018) has identified 6 factors affecting the decision to use fintech services in payment with decreasing levels, including: Level of safety and security, usefulness, attitude degree, autonomy, ease of use, convenience along with survey knowledge. The author has exported a group model of survey variables and the degree of safety and security affects perceived benefits, while autonomy and convenience affect ease of use, and also perceived benefits. Ease of use affects attitude, attitude affects intention, and ultimately, acceptance of use.

Research status on theory of acceptance and use of technology in e-banking

Research of Khuu Huynh Khuong Duy (2016) showed that factors such as bank's image, perceived usefulness, expected effectiveness, system perception and compatibility all affect acceptance. accept customers' use of e-banking services. From the results of running the model, the author has identified 4 influencing factors that are compatibility, perceived effectiveness, bank image, perceived usefulness, all of which affect the acceptance of service use. electronic banking.

The study of Alalwan et al (2017) used structural equation modeling (SEM) and validation factor analysis (CFA) to analyzed data collected from 343 valid questionnaires related to mobile banking adoption in Jordan. The selected factors (performance lifespan, effort expected, social influence, facilitation, hedonic motivation, price value, and behavioral intention) included in the model were selected. built on top of UTAUT2 (Venkatesh et al., 2012) adding trust as an external factor. Research results show that five factors (performance life expectancy, effort expectations, hedonic motivation, price value and trust) are important factors for capturing customer behavioral intentions. Jordan. The actual adoption of mobile banking can be predicted through behavioral intentions and facilitation.

Based on TAM model, the research of F. Muñoz-Leivaa (2017) has evaluated the factors affecting the intention to use the application. mobile banking usage by app customers at the

largest banks in Europe. The study introduced factors developed from the original theory of David et al. (1989) such as ease of use, social image, usefulness, attitude, trust and risk. Research results have shown that attitude affects the use of mobile banking applications, while also removing usefulness, risks are factors that directly improve the use of such applications.

The study of Fachreza et al. (2022) only examined the impact of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on the intention to use mobile banking through the mediating variable of usage attitude. The results show that both usability and ease of use affect the attitude to use, and the attitude to use affects the intention to use mobile banking.

Another study that also applies the TAM model is the study of Marakarkandy, B., Yajnik, N. and Dasgupta, C. (2017). The results of the study support the proposed model and thus contribute to understanding the influence of subjective norms, bank image, initiative, self-efficacy of online banking, and efficiency. internet usage, trust, perceived risk and government support for online banking adoption.

Research on digital banking

Although not researching on customer behavior in using digital banking services, the study of Dao Thi Thu Huong (2019) has also applied the UTAUT model to identify the factors affecting the intended behavior and usage behavior of customers in accepting and using e-wallets in the future. pay. Using e-wallets in payment is also one of the digital uses in consumption. The study has identified five factors that affect the intended behavior of customers and the intended behavior, usage habits affect the usage behavior of customers. Research results show that customers' behavior of using e-wallets is influenced by social influencing factors, favorable conditions, expected effectiveness through intended behavior, in addition to usage habits. The means of payment are also an important factor in promoting the behavior of using e-wallets.

Another study on the use of digital banking services in Vietnam but using the UTAUT2 model is the study of Nguyen Thi Oanh et al. (2020). Through the UTAUT2 model, the research has given 8 factors to consider affecting the behavior of Vietnamese consumers, which are expected effort, expected performance, social influence, favorable conditions, motivation, etc. hedonic forces, values, habits and beliefs. Research results show that performance expectations, effort expectations, hedonic motivations, habits and beliefs significantly and positively influence customer behavioral intentions.

Also applying the UTAUT2 model to research the use of digital banking services in Vietnam, but Do Duy Khanh with the study of Nguyen Thi Oanh (2020) and Do Duy Khanh (2020) only gives 5 factors affecting behavioral intention to use digital banking services, which is expected effort, performance expectations, social influence, favorable conditions, trust. The research results show that customer behavioral intention is positively influenced by effort lifespan, social influence, favorable conditions and trust of commercial banks. Finally, customer behavioral intention also positively affects intention to use digital banking services.

Also based on the UTAUT2 model, the study of Rila Anggraeni (2021) has evaluated the factors affecting behavioral intention and intention to use Digital banking services in Indonesia. Specifically, the study has introduced seven factors into the model to assess the

influence on behavioral intention and behavior of using digital banking services. Research results show that habit is the most important variable that determines behavioral intention and usage behavior, this result is similar to the study of Muhtarom Widodo (2019) on the behavior of using e-wallets. Hedonic motivation and social influence also predict intention. Indonesia has a collectivist culture, which emphasizes group influence, so opinions and information from others will influence people's intentions and actions. The highlight of this study is that, expected effort, favorable conditions, expected performance and price value have no significant relationship with behavioral intention and usage behavior. With explanations that Indonesians do not need to try too hard to learn how to use digital banking services, as well as favorable conditions, people only need an internet-connected device to be able to use the service. Digital Bank. The limitation of the study is that the effects of control variables on behavioral intention and behavior of using digital banking services have not been shown.

Research on e-KYC

Different from the above studies, one study on e-KYC is the study of Tahe et al (2021). The purpose of the study is to know the difference in factors affecting behavioral intention to use e-KYC at SCB Bank (Siam Commercial Bank) and Bank Mandiri Indonesia. The study identified factors as technology availability, external impact, technology protection, transaction procedures, security awareness, and reliability. Research results show that all factors affect the willingness to use electronic identity verification services.

Another study on the adoption of e-KYC but placed in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic is the study of Zouaghi Adel et al (2021) have proposed factors affecting e-KYC users' attitudes, thereby affecting the acceptance and actual use of e-KYC. The factors mentioned in the model include: perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, perceived risk due to Covid, perceived costs, privacy and security, and attitudes. Research results show that perceived usefulness and attitude are significant positive predictors for banks' use of e-KYC solution.

Another study on e-KYC is the study of Elinzano and Ching (2022), which has given the factors affecting deciding and using e-KYC to open an online account through the expanded UTAUT model. The study introduced the concept of e-KYC and added factors such as trust, security and privacy to the original UTAUT model with factors such as expected performance, expected effort, influence. social, favorable conditions are the core factors determining the intention and use of technology. Research results show that perceived convenience and security contribute significantly to the intention to use e-KYC to open an online account.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Research model and hypothesis

Perceived ease to use

In the study by Alalwan, Muhtaroom Widodo, JA Fachreza concluded that customers find internet and mobile banking technology less effort and not difficult to use (Alalwan et al., 2017). Contrary to this, the study of Dao My Hang (2018) shows that the ease of use of financial technology services has little influence on the intention to use such SPDV. For this study, perceived ease of use will be investigated and considered due to conflicting results in the

previous literature and additional challenges associated with using the technology itself. Selfies and virtual picture calls are the most used methods to verify a customer's identity in e-KYC. However, the use of such technology also poses challenges, and its application has not yet been studied further. Therefore, the study poses the following research hypotheses:

H1.1: Perceived ease of use positively affects e-KYC user attitudes

H1.2: Perceived ease of use has a positive impact on intention to use e-KYC

Perceived usefulness

In the TAM model, perceived usefulness is always included as a major contributing factor in behavioral intention towards mobile and internet banking. This implies that the functional aspect of mobile banking is a major and important factor in such adoption (Alalwan et al., 2017). Or other studies also show the importance of perceived usefulness such as the study of F.Muñoz-Leivaa (2017), Do Duy Khanh (2020)... Although previous studies on perceived usefulness benefits for mobile banking and internet banking seems to have a significant influence on its adoption and use, but the specific technology for e-KYC must then be considered, thus the study hypothesizes:

H2.1: Perceived usefulness has a positive impact on e-KYC users' attitudes

H2.2: Perceived usefulness has a positive impact on intention to use e-KYC

Subjective norm

Subjective norm is understood as the perception of pressures from the society expressed as support or opposition to the subject intending to perform the behavior. There are also many studies that deny the influence of subjective norm on users' attitudes as well as intention to use such as the study of Z Hu et al (2019) or the study of Nayanajith, G., & Damunupola, K. A. (2019). However, there are also studies showing the importance of subjective norm to the attitude and intention to use banking products such as Samer Elhajjar, Fadila Ouaida (2020) or Hendy Mustiko Aji et al. 2021). In the context of the research being in Vietnam, with the cultural characteristics that the oral factor still plays an important role, the study proposes the following research hypothesis:

H3.1: Subjective norm positively affects e-KYC users' attitude

H3.2: Subjective norm has a positive effect on intention to use e-KYC

Trust

In addition to the influence of people around on the attitude and intention to use, users also rely on trust (trust - trust) in the use of e-KYC. Trust is understood as the trust of customers in transactions with the bank through implementing e-KYC. Some studies show that the higher the customer confidence in e-KYC, the more willing they are to accept and use e-KYC such as studies Tahe et al (2021), F.Muñoz-Leivaa (2017), Do Duy Khanh (2020), Nguyen Thi Oanh (2020). In addition, studies also show that when Trust increases, customers will perceive that using e-KYC will be useful. Therefore, the study proposes the following research hypothesis:

H4.1: Trust has a positive effect on Attitude of e-KYC users

H4.2: Trust has a positive effect on Intent to use e-KYC

Security

One of the bases for making decisions related to customers' money is the security factor. In addition to economic information, personal data increasingly requires high security. For the use of e-KYC, customers have to declare more information to the bank but do not directly do it to the bank staff, the security factor plays an increasingly important role. The security factor has been considered by many studies and shows the influence of this factor such as the study of Gayan Nayanajith & Damunupola (2021), Elinzano and Ching (2022). Therefore, the study proposes the following hypothesis:

H5: Security has a positive effect on Intent to use e-KYC

Attitude

Attitude refers to the subjective judgments of the user and the tendency of the individual regarding something. In the TAM model, it shows that attitude has a positive influence on the intention to apply technology as the studies of Z Hu et al. (2020), Zouaghi Adel et al (2021), or many other studies. Therefore, the study put forward the following hypothesis:

H6: Attitude positively affects Intention to use e-KYC

Table 1: Summary of research hypotheses

No	Hypothesis	Content	Description
1	H1.1	Perceived ease of use positively affects e-KYC user attitudes	PEU + → ATT
2	H1.2	Perceived ease of use has a positive impact on intention to use e-KYC	PEU + → IU
3	H2.1	Perceived usefulness has a positive impact on e-KYC users' attitudes	PU + → ATT
4	H2.2	Perceived usefulness has a positive impact on intention to use e-KYC	PU + → IU
5	H3.1	Subjective norm positively affects e-KYC users' attitude	SN + → ATT
6	H3.2	Subjective norm has a positive effect on intention to use e-KYC	SN + → IU
7	H4.1	Trust has a positive effect on Attitude of e-KYC users	TR + → IU
8	H4.2	Trust has a positive effect on Intent to use e-KYC	TR + → IU
9	H5	Security has a positive effect on Intent to use e-KYC	SEC + → IU
10	H6	Attitude positively affects intention to use e-KYC	ATT + → IU

On the basis of a research overview of scientific works in different countries and research hypotheses, the author inherits previous studies to come up with a research model, specifically as follows:

Figure 1: Research model

3.2. Research Methods

The research was carried out through two steps namely preliminary research and formal research. Step 1: preliminary research is carried out by method of qualitative research combined with quantitative research. Qualitative research method is implemented through reasoning, analyzing concepts based on the theoretical background of previous studies, thereby proposing research models and building scales. Once the proposed model and preliminary scale were available, the research team conducted a trial survey of 50 people and tested the scale using Cronbach's Alpha analysis and EFA exploratory factor analysis. and adjust the questions so that the relevance of the observed variables is shown in the specific questions so that the survey form becomes easy to understand. The questions are designed as closed-ended questions, the scale used is Likert scale with 5 levels: 1 = Totally disagree, level 2 = Disagree, level 3 = Normal, moderate level 4 = Agree and level 5 = Totally agree.

After completing the preliminary study, the research team conducts the formal study. The number of samples selected should be large enough to ensure representativeness of the population. For EFA exploratory factor analysis, a minimum sample size of $n=5*m$ is required (Hair et al., 1998). Where n is the sample size, m is the total number of observed variables. At the same time, the minimum sample size to perform multivariate regression is determined by the formula: $n \geq 8*p+50$ where n is the required sample size, p is the number of independent variables (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007). In this research model, the authors propose 6 independent variables with 25 observed variables, 1 dependent variable with 3 observed variables. Therefore, to perform EFA exploratory factor analysis, a minimum sample size of 125 is required, and for multivariate regression analysis, the minimum sample size is 106. Thus, the minimum sample size of the study is 125.

The data collected for the study was conducted on the basis of an online survey on the Google form platform for a group of customers using e-KYC in the period from 9/2022 to 12/2022. The total number of votes collected was 513 votes, of which 470 valid votes were used for research. The sample size met the theoretical minimum sample size (125 samples). The survey is divided into 2 parts, including questions about factors affecting the intention to use e-KYC and questions about demographics.

The collected data will be analyzed by the author through the software SPSS 22 and AMOS 24 with the results shown in section 4.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Demographic data of the surveyed subjects are summarized in Table 2:

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics

No	Information	Number of customers	Density %
1	Gender		
	Male	129	27,5
	Female	341	72,5
2	Age		
	Under 20 years old	41	8,7
	From 20 - 30 years old	191	40,6
	From 31 – 40 years old	152	32,3
	From 41 – 50 years old	77	16,4
	Over 50 years old	9	1,9
3	Education		
	Common	27	5,8
	University/College	282	60,0
	Postgraduate	161	34,2
4	Profession		
	Private and public sector employees	113	24,04
	Self-employed	30	6,4
	Retire	8	1,7
	Different	319	67,86
5.	Monthly income		
	Less than 5 million	216	46,95
	5 to less than 10 million	122	25,95
	10 to less than 15 million	77	16,38
	15 million or more	55	11,7

4.2. Check the reliability of the scale

Criteria to determine a good scale include: the factor's coefficient reaches the value from 0.6 to 1; The total correlation coefficient of each observed variable reached a value of 0.3 or more (Nguyen Dinh Tho, 2013).

The results of the evaluation of the scale and reliability (Cronbach's Alpha) and the correlation coefficient of the total variable (Corrected Item-Total Correlation) of 22 observed variables belonging to 6 independent variables and 3 observed variables belonging to the dependent variable show that: The coefficients (Cronbach's Alpha) are all greater than 0.7 and the total correlation coefficients are all greater than 0.3, except for the variables PEU1, PU3, SEC3, TR2 which are excluded due to having the correlation coefficient of the total variable less than 0.3. Thus, from the original 25 observed variables, 4 variables were removed to leave 21 observed variables that are reliable enough to continue to be included in the EFA exploratory factor analysis.

Table 3: Reliability analysis results of Cronbach's Alpha scale

Variable	Number of original variables	Cronbach's Alpha before removing variables	Number of variables after removing the variable	Cronbach's Alpha after removing variables
PEU	4	0,743	3	0,819 (removing PEU1)
PU	4	0,619	3	0,803 (removing PU3)
SN	3	0,834	3	0,834
SEC	4	0,755	3	0,875 (removing SEC3)
TR	4	0,721	3	0,749 (removing TR2)
ATT	3	0,909	3	0,909
IU	3	0,858	3	0,858

Source: Results from SPSS22

4.3. EFA analysis

EFA factor analysis for 6 independent variables and 1 dependent variable with a factor loading of 0.5 received the results of the factor rotation matrix showing that all variables have KMO coefficients = 0.805(>0.5), so factor analysis is appropriate, has practical significance, Sig value (Bartlett's Test)= 0.000 shows that the observed variables are correlated with each other in the overall Eigenvalues= 1,208 (>1) representing the variation explained by each factor confirming that the drawn factor is significant best summary of information. Test the explanatory level of the observed boundaries for the factor: Total variance extracted = 76.679 > 50%, showing that 7 extracted factors can explain the variation of data of 21 observed variables participating in EFA (Table 4).

Table 4: Result of factor rotation

SN		IU		ATT		SEC		PEU		PU		TR	
Variable	Result	Variable	Result	Variable	Result	Variable	Result	Variable	Result	Variable	Result	Variable	Result
SN2	0,885	IU3	0,862	AT3	0,869	SEC1	0,885	PEU3	0,883	PU1	0,859	TR4	0,847
SN1	0,868	IU1	0,880	AT2	0,847	SEC2	0,860	PEU2	0,859	PU2	0,847	TR1	0,772
SN3	0,817	IU2	0,844	AT1	0,808	SEC4	0,774	PEU4	0,761	PU4	0,820	TR3	0,744
Eigen-values	5,647	2,323		2,129		1,697		1,620		1,478		1,208	
% of Variance	26,890	11,060		10,139		8,082		7,714		7,040		5,754	
Cumulative %	26,890	37,950		48,089		56,171		68,885		70,925		76,679	

Source: Results from SPSS 22

4.4. Analysis of CFA

After performing exploratory factor analysis EFA, the author performed confirmatory factor analysis CFA. To measure the fit of the model, people often use Chi-square (CMIN); Comparative Fit Index (CFI_Comparetative Fit Index). Tucker&Lewis Index; RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error Approximation) index. The model is considered suitable with market data when the Chi-square test has a P-value > 0.05. However, Chi-square has the disadvantage of being dependent on sample size. If a model is given the values GFI, TLI, CFI = 0.9 (Bentler&Bonett, 1980); CMIN/df=2, in some cases CMIN/df can be equal to 3 (Carmines&McIver, 1981); RMSEA = 0.08, RMSEA = 0.05 is considered very good (Steiger, 1990); then the model is considered to be suitable for market data or compatible with market data. Tho & Trang (2008) said that if the model receives the values of TLI, CFI = 0.9, CMIN/df = 2, RMSEA = 0.08, then the model fits (compatible) with market data.

Figure 2. CFA analysis results of the model

Source: Results from AMOS24

The results of CFA analysis show that the measurement criteria are appropriate: Chisquare/df = 12,303<3, TLI = 0.943, GFI = 0.927, CFI = 0.955, RMSEA coefficient = 0.053<0.08, so the model model is suitable for the market. The results of the P-values of the observed variables representing the factors are all sig = 0.000, so the observed variables are confirmed to have good representation for the factor in the CFA model. The coefficient of

variance extracted and the combined reliability of the scales both reached values > 0.5 . Thus, it can be confirmed that the research scales ensure the analysis requirements.

The results of testing the quality of the observed variables (Table 5) show that the P-values are all < 0.05 , so it can be concluded that the observed variables of the factors Confidentiality, Intention to use, Attitude, Subjective norm, Perceived ease of use, Perceived usefulness and Belief retained to perform CFA confirmatory factor analysis are all significant in the model.

Table 5: Quality inspection of the components of the scale

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
SN2	<---	SN	1,000			
SN1	<---	SN	1,064	,050	21,313	***
SN3	<---	SN	,928	,048	19,161	***
IU3	<---	IU	1,000			
IU1	<---	IU	,976	,053	18,269	***
IU2	<---	IU	1,009	,056	18,048	***
AT3	<---	AT	1,000			
AT2	<---	AT	1,168	,048	24,136	***
AT1	<---	AT	1,035	,042	24,885	***
SEC1	<---	SEC	1,000			
SEC2	<---	SEC	1,057	,058	18,083	***
SEC4	<---	SEC	,822	,055	15,026	***
PEU3	<---	PEU	1,000			
PEU2	<---	PEU	,864	,054	15,915	***
PEU4	<---	PEU	,776	,053	14,505	***
PU1	<---	PU	1,000			
PU2	<---	PU	,998	,071	13,988	***
PU4	<---	PU	,822	,061	13,501	***
TR4	<---	TR	1,000			
TR1	<---	TR	,921	,079	11,724	***
TR3	<---	TR	,856	,076	11,306	***

Note: $p=***=0.000$

Source: Results from AMOS24

The results of the general reliability analysis and the extracted variance show that the factors are the scales with load factor greater than 0,5, reaching the convergence validity. The composite reliability of the factors above 0,7 and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) are greater than 50%. This shows that the factor scales in the formal sample have achieved the necessary reliability (Table 6).

Factor loading greater than 0.5 in each factor are considered to have convergence validity and the square root of the variance greater than the correlation between research concepts are concepts with discriminant validity (see table 6).

Bảng 6: Discriminant validity

	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	SN	IU	AT	SEC	PEU	PU	TR
SN	0,877	0,703	0,262	0,884	0,839						
IU	0,858	0,669	0,135	0,859	0,254***	0,818					
AT	0,910	0,772	0,262	0,914	0,512***	0,367***	0,878				
SEC	0,840	0,639	0,189	0,866	0,282***	0,283***	0,435***	0,799			
PEU	0,826	0,615	0,125	0,855	0,266***	0,099†	0,354***	0,150**	0,784		
PU	0,806	0,581	0,027	0,815	0,033	0,165**	0,159**	-0,010	0,149**	0,762	
TR	0,750	0,501	0,192	0,754	0,322***	0,332***	0,438***	0,236***	0,282***	0,125*	0,708

Source: Results from AMOS24

4.5. Structural model analysis SEM

Figure 3: SEM analysis results

Source: Results from AMOS24

SEM results show that Chi-square/df = 2.499 < 3, TLI = 0.935, CFI = 0.947, all greater than 0.9, RMSEA = 0.057 < 0.08, so the model has a good fit with the market. As a result, the P-values of the independent variables all have the value of 0.000, so the independent variables all show the influence on the dependent variable, which is the intention to use e-KYC, except the Ease-of-Use Perception variable. Pvalue = 0.132 > 0.05 and Subjective Standard variable has P-value = 0.273 > 0.05, so Subjective Norm and Perceived ease of use variable do not affect the intention to use e-KYC.

Table 6: Results of weight analysis without normalization

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
AT	<---	PEU	0,075	0,039	3,410	***
AT	<---	PU	0,134	0,040	1,870	0,062
AT	<---	SN	0,087	0,048	7,794	***
AT	<---	TR	0,290	0,058	5,017	***
IU	<---	SEC	0,149	0,056	2,675	0,007
IU	<---	TR	0,256	0,084	3,043	0,002
IU	<---	PEU	0,082	0,055	1,505	0,132
IU	<---	PU	0,129	0,056	2,305	0,021
IU	<---	SN	0,079	0,072	1,096	0,273
IU	<---	AT	0,235	0,080	2,947	0,003

Note: $p=***=0.000$

Source: Results from AMOS24

P-values of all variables are less than 0.05 except for Ease-of-Use variable with Pvalue = 0.132 > 0.05 and Subjective Standard variable with P-value = 0.273 > 0.05. The unnormalized weights of the variables Perceived usefulness, Confidentiality, Trust and Attitude all have a positive sign, showing a positive influence on the intention to use factor.

Analysis of the indicators after normalization in Table 7 shows that:

- The normalized weights bear the same sign as the unnormalized weights;
- The impact of factors: The factor of trust has the strongest impact on the intention to use, followed by the factor of Thainess, security, and perceived usefulness is the smallest because the weight has absolute value after ordinal normalization is 0,200; 0.195; 0.145; 0.122.

For the factors affecting on intention to use e-KYC

Trust is understood as a customer's trust in the bank in terms of security, fulfillment of commitments and safety of transactions. In previous studies on the intention to use banking services, trust plays an important role in customers' decision to use. For the reason, economic-related transactions need to be trusted so that customers can feel secure when performing transactions. The results of this study are similar to previous studies such as those of Tahe et al (2021), F.Mu~noz-Leivaa (2017), Do Duy Khanh (2020), Nguyen Thi Oanh (2020 and Thus, it can be explained that the higher the confidence in the use of e-KYC, the better the attitude of e-KYC users and hence the intention to use e-KYC. KYC more and more.

The next factor affecting customers' intention to use e-KYC is Attitude factor. According to the research model, Attitude is influenced by the factors of Belief, Subjective Norms, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. The results of the study also show that Belief and Useful Perception positively and significantly affect Attitude, while Subjective Norm and Perceived Ease of Use have a negligible influence on Attitude. From this result, it can be shown that the customer's attitude to using e-KYC is influenced by the customer's trust in e-KYC, and the benefits when using e-KYC bring to the customer. Moreover, the higher the

user's attitude towards e-KYC, the higher the user's interest in e-KYC. This research result is completely consistent with previous studies such as Zouaghi Adel et al (2021), JA Fachreza et al (2022), F.Mu~noz-Leivaa (2017), Dao My Hang (2018)), thereby asserting Attitude an essential premise of intention to use.

In addition, Perceived usefulness, Security are also factors affecting the Intent of Use of customers. This result is completely consistent with the actual situation because this is an alternative option for customers, i.e., when customers use e-KYC instead of going to Bank branches, the Security must be ensured. To avoid risks for customers, moreover, this application must also bring customers convenience and benefits when using. This research result is also completely consistent with previous studies such as Elinzano and Ching (2022), Gayan Nayanajith & Damunupola (2021), JA Fachreza et al (2022), Khuu Huynh Khuong Duy (2016).

For the factors that do not affecting on intention to use e-KYC

According to the research results, there are two factors that have a negligible influence on customers' intention to use e-KYC, which are the subjective norm factor and the perceived ease of use factor. That is, the influences from people around do not have much impact on the Intent of Use of the customer or the experience of using e-KYC feels easy. This research result is also contrary to the previous research results, when it is said that Vietnam is a country with an oral culture and a large community. However, because this is an economic-related behavior, a certain level of trust is required for customers to intend to use it, and through word of mouth of people around it is not necessarily enough to convince customers. customers using this service. Secondly, the factor Ease of use is also not a barrier for customers when using e-KYC, which is completely consistent with the reality when the percentage of people using smartphones is high and increasing level of technological literacy. Since then, learning and using a new technology is no longer difficult for customers.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above model results, the study makes some conclusions as follows:

The purpose of the study is to assess the impact of factors on the intention to use e-KYC. By SEM structural model, the study has shown the positive impact of factors such as Trust, Attitude, Perceived usefulness, Security. Among these factors, the factor Trust and Attitude are the two factors that have a great impact on the intention to use e-KYC because the weights are 0.200 and 0.195, respectively. For the Attitude factor, Trust has a great influence on Attitude, followed by Perceived usefulness. The results of this study are completely consistent with the original research hypothesis of the authors.

Based on the results of this study, the authors propose some recommendations to encourage customer to make the decision to use e-KYC more as follows:

Firstly, update information about e-KYC as well as propagate and promote e-KYC as well as the benefits of e-KYC to customers.

Secondly, the way of conducting propaganda and promotion of banks also needs to change so that customers can access information in the fastest and most convenient way for customers.

Third, banks also need to further promote the application of technology to e-KYC implementation technology so that customers feel that using e-KYC will bring customers benefits and feel secure when using e-KYC.

Fourth, regarding customers, customers need to improve their financial knowledge as well as their understanding of digital finance to be able to respond to rapid changes in technology.

The limitation of the study is that it has not assessed a number of other factors such as risk factors, customer creativity, or government support to the intention to use e-KYC, as well as the research has not Considering the difference of different customer files, the intention to use e-KYC is different or not. To overcome these limitations, the group's next research direction needs to explore and introduce more factors affecting the intention to use e-KYC and change the scope of the study to get a more suitable research sample.

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FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM IN FINANCIALLY AUTONOMOUS PUBLIC HOSPITALS UNDER THE HANOI DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH

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Abstract

The article aims to study the influence of factors on the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi City Department of Health. The study used a combination of qualitative in-depth interviewing and quantitative methods. The study used a regression model after testing the Crobach Alpha scale and EFA exploratory factor analysis. The study data is based on the survey results of 184 subjects at financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health. The research results show that there are 06 factors affecting the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health. Each factor has different levels of impact on effectiveness and is arranged in order from high to low as follows: Control environment; Hospital management; Risk assessment; Control activities; Information and communication; Monitoring activities. Based on the research results, the article gives some recommendations to improve the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health.

Keywords: *Financially autonomous public hospitals; Internal control; Influencing factors*

1. INTRODUCTION

Hospitals are an important part of the healthcare delivery system. To achieve the goal of universal health coverage, it is essential to clearly define the role and optimize the performance of the hospital. However, many countries are still facing difficulties in hospital planning and management. Hospital-level challenges such as poor management, long wait times, low quality of service and safety, and patient dissatisfaction are currently impacting hospital operations. In the general trend of the world and countries in the region, the promotion of hospital management, quality management of medical examination and treatment services, and financial autonomy is a driving force for hospitals to be creative, improve and improve the quality of medical examination and treatment services and in management.

In the hospital system in Vietnam, public hospitals play a major role in providing health care to the people. In order to create healthy competition between public units, create motivation for creativity, autonomy, and self-responsibility, improve the quality of medical examination and treatment to serve the people, do not rely on the budget, the Government of Vietnam has introduced a policy to reform hospital autonomy. In Vietnam, the financial

autonomy policy is carried out in two phases: phase 1 implements financial autonomy according to Decree 10 from 2002 to April 2006; phase 2 implements hospital autonomy according to Decree 43 starting from May 2006 to the present. According to statistics of the Hanoi Department of Health (Decision 4121/QĐ – SYT), up to now, the Department of Health has assigned financial autonomy to 36/41 public non-business units (phase 1). These are non-business units that ensure their regular operating costs and from the first year of the stable period (2023), the state budget does not support or allocate recurrent expenditures. Accordingly, the Hanoi Department of Health also requires units to proactively arrange, consolidate, and reorganize to ensure a streamlined and properly structured apparatus to improve the quality of public non-business services, increase non-business revenue for the unit, save expenses, and increase financial autonomy. Thus, under the impact of the national health insurance system and the transformation of the health market, the quality of health services, as well as management activities, have become increasingly important for hospitals.

Internal control is an important management tool for managers in hospitals. Internal control can be considered the core of a system, as its effectiveness is an important factor affecting the sustainability of a hospital. A strong Internal Control system will help the hospital ensure the accuracy of its accounting figures and financial statements; reduce the risk, fraud, or loss of funds for the hospital caused by third parties or hospital staff. Internal control helps leaders more effectively and efficiently manage the hospital's economic resources such as people, assets, and capital, contributing to minimizing the risks arising in the process of performing assigned professional tasks.

Although internal control plays an essential role in the operation of the hospital, the reality shows that it has not been paid enough attention and many limitations need to be improved. In recent years, many cases of financial severe losses have arisen due to the failure of the internal control system. In particular, these frauds even occur at medical institutions, including public hospitals.

In the world as well as in Vietnam, many authors have studied different aspects of the internal control of propylene solutions. The research results of domestic and foreign research work related to the study of factors affecting the effectiveness of the internal control system show that the improvement of the effectiveness of the internal control system in the units brings a lot of benefits to the units, especially in the context that the Vietnamese health sector is trying to promote the planning of the Vietnamese health network from now to 2045, forming a modern health system to serve people at the same level as the world countries and ensuring competitiveness.

However, the authors in the world mainly focus on the effectiveness of the internal control system in the following directions: for governance, for independent audits and internal audits, or in the direction of affecting the value of shares, financial information of listed companies, etc. Few authors study the effectiveness of the internal control system in the direction of improving operational efficiency. And domestic studies have shown that there is a close relationship between internal control and the performance of enterprises. The weakness or shortcomings of the internal control system negatively affect the performance of the unit, including the non-business administrative unit. General weaknesses in internal control in the

organization can be mentioned such as the design of operational risk prevention measures, failure to analyze risks, lack of appropriate information, and problems with delegation in the organization. Thus, the design, construction, and operation of an effective and effective internal control system is one of the important objectives of the non-business administrative unit.

Therefore, the article aims to study and identify the factors affecting as well as the level of influence of the factors on the effectiveness of the internal control system in the direction of improving operational efficiency in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health.

Therefore, identifying factors that affect the effectiveness of internal control systems in the direction of ensuring operational efficiency in public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health is an issue worthy of research attention.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Concept of Internal Controls

Internal control is an object of special interest and attention to the state auditor. In some countries such as the US, Canada, etc., there have been official declarations on internal control applied to administrative and career agencies. Regarding state auditing, the system of State audit standards issued by the International Organization of Supreme Audit Institutions (INTOSAI) includes a code of professional ethics and audit standards. In 1992, INTOSAI's guidance document on internal control standards formed a document referring to the upgrading of internal control standards, supporting the implementation and evaluation of the internal control system. In 2001, the guideline of INTOSAI 1992 was further updated on internal control standards to suit all audiences and in line with recent developments in internal control. It should be noted that this document integrated the general arguments for internal control of the COSO report and was published in 2004 (INTOSAI 2004). The definition of internal control according to INTOSAI 2004 is as follows: "Internal control is a whole process carried out by managers and individuals in the organization, which is established to detect risks and provide a reasonable assurance to achieve the overall objectives and tasks of the organization". In 2013, INTOSAI continued to update the concept of internal control with clarification of the objectives to be achieved such as: performing activities in a disciplined, ethical, economical, efficient, and appropriate manner; Properly implementing responsibilities; Complying with current laws and principles and regulations; Protecting resources from loss, misuse and loss.

Thus, from the initial approaches to internal control to serve the auditor's work, modern perspectives have made more complete and comprehensive statements about internal control, in which the objectives of internal control are increasingly supplemented and expanded. From there, it is possible to make a general assessment of internal control as follows: internal control is a function of the management process, governed by entities within the unit, implemented to reasonably achieve the set objectives.

2.2. Effectiveness of the internal control system

The report of COSO (2013) said that the internal control system is effective (at a specified time) if the Board of Management and managers reasonably meet the following 3 criteria:

- They understand to what extent the organization's operational goals are achieved.
- Financial statements are being prepared and presented reliably - Laws and regulations are complied with.

Thus, while internal control is a process, the effectiveness of internal control is the state of that process at a certain time. The evaluation of the effectiveness of internal control is judgmental. In addition, to evaluate the effectiveness of internal control (in general), in addition to the above three criteria, it is also necessary to further evaluate the effectiveness of the five components of the internal control system.

It can be seen that the effectiveness of the five components of an internal control system is also a criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of the internal control system. However, it should be noted that, while the above five criteria should be satisfied when evaluating the effectiveness of the internal control system, this does not mean that each component of the internal control system must operate exactly the same or at the same level in different parts. The reasons stated in the COSO report are as follows:

- There is natural compensation between parts of the internal control system. Internal control serves many purposes, so effective control in one department can serve the purpose of control in another department.
- To deal with specific risks, managers can set out different levels of control in different departments. These levels will help to satisfy the above 5 criteria without necessarily having uniformity in the performance level of the departments.

The five components of the internal control system and the above five criteria apply to the entire internal control system or to one or several target groups. When considering one of the three target groups, such as internal control with the preparation of the financial statements, if all five of the above criteria are satisfied, it will help the organization to consider that the internal control over the preparation of the financial statements is effective.

Inheriting the report of COSO, in the studies of Millichamp (2002), Amudo and Inanga (2009), Ofori (2011), Douglas (2011), Sultana and Haque (2011), Gamage & Kevin Low Lock and Fernando (2014), the authors have suggested that an internal control system achieves effectiveness when it achieves the following three objectives:

- Activities that achieve efficiency and efficiency
- The financial statements achieve reliability - Laws and regulations are complied with.

This is the effective scale that the authors inherited and used in their study when

assessing the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health.

2.3. Theoretical Background

2.3.1. Regulation Theory

This theory consists of the following 3 main theories:

- Public interest theory states that regulations should be established to meet the requirements of society in regulating the injustice or inefficiency of market prices; thereby protecting the common interests of society. This theory is closely related to the concept of “market failure”, a view given to explain the intervention of the state in different markets.

- Capture theory, also known as interest-group theory, states that regulations are established at the request of interest groups in society, to maximize the benefits of group members. Accordingly, interest groups will seek to lobby for regulations that increase their interests to be promulgated or regulations that disadvantage them will be disabled. This theory holds that the regulatory organizations themselves are not independent in the regulatory process and that different interest groups will compete to control the power of the regulatory organization.

- Private interest theory assumes that those responsible in the organization make rules to behave in their self-interest, namely winning the election.

In general, regulatory theories show that regulation must be above the goal of protecting social interests, but this process is threatened by the loss of neutrality due to the influence of different interest groups, from professional organizations to businesses.

When applying this theory to the study, the authors expect managers and employees working at the Hospital to comply with and abide by the provisions of the law. Therefore, the more managers and employees comply with and obey the law, the higher the effectiveness of the internal control system.

2.3.2. Delegate Theory

This theory was developed by Michael C. Jensen and William H. Meckling in 1976. This theory focuses on the problem through the delegation that creates the relationship between the principal and the agent. Delegation issues often occur when the principal hires the principal to perform some work. The principal is entitled to represent the principal to decide the matters that have been delegated. In companies, especially joint-stock companies, this relationship is expressed through the relationship between shareholders (the principal) and the company manager (the principal). The principal always expects the agent to accomplish his objectives and the agent to perform the work effectively and honestly. The representative has a lot of authority in operating the unit. Therefore, there exists the possibility that the representative does not fulfill the requirements of the owner of the capital, leading to a conflict of interest between the owner of the capital and the representative.

In non-business administrative units, the State is the owner, while the heads of administrative agencies are the representatives of the State to manage the activities of their units. The State always expects the administrative units to fulfill the tasks assigned by the State and the non-business administrative units to operate effectively and protect the State's assets. Therefore, heads of nonbusiness administrative agencies themselves must have good control over the internal activities of their units to ensure the interests of the State (the Owner) by creating a professional control environment, implementing control activities, ensuring reliable and timely information and communication. In addition, it is necessary to monitor the delegate's behavior, establish and maintain a mechanism to ensure that the delegate represents the interests of the delegate, minimizing the self-interested behavior of the manager. This is also the foundation for building an internal control system. When applying the delegation theory to the authors' work, according to the explanation of this theory, the authors expect that the directors at the hospitals who are mandated by the State will develop an adequate internal control system to meet the good control of the internal activities of their units.

Therefore, when applying this theory to the study, the authors expect managers and employees working at the hospital to perform well the risk assessment, develop effective control activities, ensure good information and communication, and monitor activities in the unit, the higher the effectiveness in the internal control system.

2.3.3. Social psychology theory of organization

This theory is called behavioral theory, which includes perspectives in management that emphasize the role of human psychological, emotional and social factors in work. This theory states: *“The effectiveness of management is determined by labor productivity, but labor productivity is not only determined by material factors but also by the satisfaction of human psychosocial needs”*.

This theory began to appear in the United State in the 30s, was developed by psychologists in the 60s, and is still studied in many developed countries to find out the full understanding of the complex psychology of people, an important factor for management.

The main ideas of social psychology theory are:

- Recognize the influence of the manager's leadership style on labor attitudes and labor productivity.
- The influence of the collective on individual attitudes.
- Relationships between colleagues and personnel at work.
- Help managers better understand human motivation, care for employees, and the use of power in the organization.

Therefore, when applying this theory to the study, the authors expect that when the control environment, control and monitoring activities are guaranteed, the effectiveness of the internal control system is higher.

2.3.4. Contingency Management Theory

This theory is based on the argument that: *“No single effective management system is suitable for all organizations and all circumstances because the unique characteristics of the system and its effectiveness will depend on the unique characteristics of the organization and the contextual actors”*.

Uncertainty is the fundamental core concept of uncertainty theory. It proposes that many external and internal constraints change the best way to manage organizations in a given situation. In other words, it all depends on the current situation to determine what would be the best course of action for organizations.

Uncertainty management theory is a major theoretical lens used to view organizations. It offers a wealth of insights and has considerable empirical support since it emerged in the 1970s through Fred Fiedler. Key ideas underlying uncertainty theory include:

- Organizations are open systems that need to be carefully managed to satisfy and balance internal needs as well as to adapt to environmental circumstances.

- There is no one best way or organization. The appropriate format depends on the type of task or environment in which the organization is operating.

- Above all, management must be concerned with achieving good alignment and fit, i.e., the fit between the organization and its environment.

- Different types of organizations are needed in different types of environments.

- Theory also proposes that managers change and redesign their organizations primarily to adapt to changes in the internal and external environment. Therefore, organizational and process environments are often a source of change.

Dr. Paul Hersey and Kenneth Blanchard developed the situational leadership theory in 1969. This theory suggests that leaders must adjust their leadership style to suit the situation. They argue that there are four types of leadership: Speaking (S1): leaders assign tasks to their employees and tell them what to do. Sales (S2): leaders sell employees their ideas to persuade and motivate them. Participation (S3): leaders allow their employees more freedom to participate in the decisionmaking process. Delegation (S4): leaders delegate work to their employees. According to this theory, the choice of the optimal style to apply will depend on the maturity of the group. This model defines four types of maturity:

Low maturity level (M1): people lack knowledge and skills and are unwilling to work independently.

Medium Maturity (M2): people who lack knowledge and skills but are willing to work independently.

Average maturity (M3): people have knowledge and skills but lack confidence and do not want to take responsibility.

High Maturity (M4): people have knowledge and skills and are willing to take responsibility.

Robert J. House created the path-goal theory in 1971 and published it in "Quarterly Administrative Science"; he later revised it in another publication in 1976. The idea of this theory is that the behavior of leaders will influence their employees. Therefore, they must provide practical guidance and resources to help their subordinates achieve their goals. Leaders must also take action and make up for employees' shortcomings. This theory states that leaders can create four goals for their employees to follow:

Directive: where leaders create clear guidelines and set specific goals to reduce ambiguity and help employees cross their paths. With this style, employees are strictly managed.

Support: where leaders help and are proactive with their employees. They are more friendly and approachable to their employees.

Involvement: where leaders consult their employees before making decisions, they value their employees' thoughts and feedback more.

Achievement: where leaders encourage their employees by setting challenging goals.

Employees are motivated to do better.

Determining which path to take again depends on the specificity of the organisation.

When applying the organization's uncertainty theory to the authors' work, the authors expect that when factors in the control environment are guaranteed, the effectiveness of the internal control system is higher.

2.4. Factors affecting the effectiveness of the internal control system

Based on the COSO reporting platform, INTOSAI's guidance on internal control also lays out the 5 elements that constitute internal control. Depending on the type of operation, objectives and size of the hospital, internal control is used differently, but in general, to evaluate the effectiveness of the internal control system, it is necessary to rely on 17 principles according to 5 constituent factors including: Control environment, risk assessment process, control activities, information and communication, monitoring activities. In addition, in this study, the authors further hypothesize that there is a new factor with the specific characteristics of the industry that affects the effectiveness of the internal control system, which is the Hospital Management factor.

2.4.1. Control environment

- Principle 1: The unit must demonstrate a commitment to honesty and ethical values.

- Principle 2: The Board of Directors establishes an independent mechanism between management and supervision activities.

- Principle 3: Managers under the supervision of the Board of Management should establish an organizational structure, types of reports, and delimitation of responsibilities and powers to achieve the objectives of the unit.

- Principle 4: The unit demonstrates its commitment to employing qualified employees, through recruitment, maintenance and development of human resources in accordance with the objectives of the unit.

- Principle 5: The unit should require responsible individuals to report on their responsibilities in meeting the organization's objectives.

2.4.2. Risk assessment

- Principle 6: The unit must set clear and complete objectives to help identify and assess risks arising in the achievement of the unit's objectives.

- Principle 7: The unit must identify risks in setting the unit's objectives, conduct a risk analysis to identify risks that need to be managed.

- Principle 8: The unit should consider the potential types of fraud when assessing the risk of not meeting the unit's objectives.

- Principle 9: The unit needs to confirm and evaluate the changes of the environment affecting the internal control system. Changes include: changes in the external environment (economy, politics...), changes from the way of doing business (new business types, new techniques...), changes from management methods, from the attitude and philosophy of the managers about the internal control system.

2.4.3. Control activities

- Principle 10: The unit must select and establish control activities to minimize risks and achieve the unit's objectives to an acceptable level.

- Principle 11: The unit selects and develops common control activities on information technology to support the achievement of the objectives.

- Principle 12: The unit must implement control activities based on policies to be established and implemented into procedures.

2.4.4. Information and Communications

- Principle 13: The unit collects, communicates and uses appropriate and quality information to support other components of internal control.

- Principle 14: The unit must communicate internally the necessary information to support the control function. Subjects that must be informed include: employees, managers, and the Board of Management.

- Principle 15: The unit must communicate to external party information related to internal control activities such as shareholders, owners, customers, suppliers...

In order to improve control capacity in the unit, information and communication are indispensable conditions, which are essential to achieve the objectives of internal control.

2.4.5. Monitoring activities

- Principle 16: The entity must select, implement and conduct continuous and/ or periodic audits to ensure that the constituent parts of the internal control are present and in operation.

- Principle 17: The shortcomings of internal control must be evaluated and communicated promptly to responsible subjects such as management and the Board of Management to take corrective measures.

2.4.6. Hospital management

The old concept of hospitals for providing curative care is no longer valid. The role of the hospital is not only a professional vision of curative care, but an equally important role is to provide enhanced health care and disease prevention. The Expert Committee on Health Care Organization has defined the hospital as "An integral part of a social and health organization whose function is to provide the population with comprehensive health care, including healing and prevention, and patient services with access to the family and home environment. The hospital is also a center for training medical staff and social research".

Hospital management is a term that refers to the management and operation of hospital resources such as regulations, policies, regimes of hospitals, laws on medical examination and treatment, insurance, medical expertise, human resources, financial resources, infrastructure, medical equipment, management technology, all for hospitals to achieve sustainable and best growth. Hospital management is a key factor in the process of improving hospital quality such as overcrowding, improving professional quality, effective financial management, infrastructure management, improving the level of medical staff, investing in facilities, preventing patient risks, financial risks, managing patient safety, or preventing hospital infections... The term "hospital administration" encompasses a large number of activities that can be classified into 3 main groups as follows:

- Drafting hospital laws, planning the entire hospital system, determining international policies, regulations for hospital operations, setting standards and control structures.

- The application of hospital law and the provision of social assistance by agencies responsible for the management of hospital services whether local or regional, public or private.

- Daily operations of the hospital are carried out by administrative staff related to personnel, finance and technical services.

The elements of hospital management include:

- Human resource management: is the exploitation, management and use of human resources in the hospital reasonably and most effectively. In hospitals with very few specialists, effective personnel management rests on the heads of departments. Human resource management steps include: Human resource planning; Recruitment and selection.

Human resource planning is the process of implementing research, evaluation, identification of human resource needs and developing planning programs to ensure that the organization will have the right number, the right number of people and be located in the right place, at the right time and in the right place. Thus, human resource planning includes determining the demand for human resources (quantity and quality), determining the supply of policies and solutions to balance the supply and demand of human resources of the organization at a certain time. equivalent.

Recruitment is the process of finding personnel to meet the requirements for a position or a job in the organization. Recruitment is conducted to meet an urgent need – such as adding to a vacancy – to reduce the time it takes to fill a vacancy by maintaining a list of candidates.

Selection is the process of identifying the best candidate for the position. This process involves comparing the candidate's qualifications to specific job requirements. This is a multi-step process: getting a job application, conducting one or two rounds of interviews, taking a proficiency test, testing for substance use, background checks and counseling, as well as some other ways to limit the list until a successful candidate is found.

- Financial management: Hospital financial management in a broad sense is the targeted and organized continuous impact of hospital managers on the subjects and financial activities of the hospital in order to determine the sources of revenue and expenditures, conduct revenue and expenditure in accordance with the law, comply with the State's principles on finance, and ensure funding for all hospital activities.

- Material management: The management of medical supplies will include the management of medical equipment systems (Fixed assets) and medical tools and supplies (Tools and equipment). Management of medical supplies warehouse is a necessary and regular activity at the hospital to organize, manage and preserve the number of medical equipment and instruments that are always stable. At the same time, it ensures that the supply chain is continuous, making all operations of the hospital run smoothly. In order to optimize the process of monitoring, using and managing medical equipment, the hospital's board of directors/leaders should develop effective procedures and principles for managing medical materials for the hospital. Applying rules and standards on the management of hospital medical materials will contribute to ensuring enforcement and compliance throughout the hospital. When the hospital operates with a standard and professional medical material warehouse management process, it will help to operate the warehouse effectively and especially maximize profits in the control of medical equipment or inventory supplies.

- Time management: Time is one of the most important resources and important factors affecting work performance. Hospital administrators must be able to control and use subordinates' time out for the benefit of patients. This can be done by making the correct task roster for organizations and ensuring that everything is done on schedule.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, the authors mainly used both qualitative and quantitative research methods together with survey sampling methods of each method. Based on interviews with experts, the

authors designed and developed official scales for each factor in the research model and tested the influencing factors.

Qualitative research method

To gain a deeper understanding of the impact of administrative management on the hospital's internal control policies which in turn affect organizational effectiveness, the research team used a qualitative in-depth interviewing approach to collect the data. The research question here is: How has hospital management impacted the internal control of the hospital? To answer this question, the objective of the study is to understand how hospital governance impacts components of internal control such as control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring activities. The authors conducted interviews with the hospital's managers and used the data collected throughout the interviews to formulate the manager's role theory as well as delineate the types and nature of management activities. This theory has been constantly tested through interviews and questionnaires. The interviewees in this study were mainly managers of financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health. The interviews were conducted for 01 month from May 1 to 31, 2023. There are a total of 34 subjects, including the dean (15), deputy dean (15) and director (4) of the hospital. All surveyed subjects have academic titles of Associate Professor, Doctor or higher. The research team conducted interviews in two forms, directly and indirectly. In-person interviews are conducted in the interviewees' private rooms. The indirect interview is conducted by phone or using the interview form link sent by e-mail or phone. During the interview, the interview questions are open-ended, the hospital's managers freely discuss the hospital's operating strategy, as well as the hospital's current internal control strategies and the effectiveness of the organization.

Quantitative research method

The scale used by the author in the study is a 5-point Likert scale with the levels: (1) Strongly disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) No opinion, (4) Agree, (5) Strongly agree.

The authors conduct formal quantitative research using survey techniques through paper questionnaires and through the online survey tool Google Docs (PL 01) to assess the reliability of the scale, the value of the scale, test the suitability of the scale and research model. The research team uses SPSS 20.0 software to conduct analysis and test the factors in their research.

4. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

4.1. Research model

Based on the research results of the previous authors as well as the foundation of the theories, the research team proposed a model to study the elements of the internal control system according to the INTOSAI model, and at the same time added an element of Hospital management to find out the factors affecting the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health.

✦ Dependent variable: The effectiveness of the internal control system in the hospital.

✦ Independent variable

- Control environment
- Risk assessment
- Control activities
- Information and Communications
- Monitoring Activities
- Hospital management

✦ Research model: The proposed model is the 4.1 model.

Figure 4.1. The research model of factors affecting the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health

4.2. Research Hypothesis

From the above research model, combined with the discussion results of experts, the authors propose 06 hypotheses that need to be tested, including:

4.2.1. Control environment

The control environment of an organization reflects the culture and has created a common nuance for an organization, affecting the sense of control of employees. The control environment is the foundation for all other elements of internal control that create a discipline, ethics and organizational structure (INTOSAI 2013).

The control environment is manifested through organizational norms, processes and structures, which guide all members of the unit at different levels in the implementation of responsibilities and decision-making. It represents the general attitude of the Board of Management, senior managers on control issues, governs the sense of control of every member of the unit, and is the foundation for other parts of internal control (COSO, 2013). Therefore, the control environment is the foundation of the internal control system and affects all activities of the unit in accounting and the fidelity of financial statements. Therefore, this study

expects a positive relationship between the control environment and the effectiveness of the internal control system. The hypothesis is given as follows:

Hypothesis H1: There is a positive effect of the Control Environment (CE) on the effectiveness of the internal control system (EIC).

4.2.2. Risk assessment

The operation of each unit may be at risk due to the presence of internal and external factors, affecting the achievement of goals. Although a unit may not set clear goals, there are always implicit goals. Whether the objective is stated explicitly or implicitly, the entity carries out a risk assessment to weigh the risks that may arise. Managers need to identify risks, that occur at all levels of the unit and take appropriate measures to deal with risks and manage risks.

Currently, each entity requires a risk assessment to avoid and mitigate the threat to itself. The risk management system includes the styles and philosophies of managerial action, accompanying business strategy, and goal setting in operating (Arena et al., 2010). Today's risk management has changed not only for the entity but also for stakeholders (Arena et al., 2010), (Power, 2009). Therefore, risk management is designed to reflect that the entity has properly updated its laws, standards of work, guidelines, and especially compliance with professional standards. This study assumes that the Risk Assessment relates to the effectiveness of the internal control system. Therefore, the hypothesis is given as follows:

Hypothesis H2: There is a positive impact of Risk Assessment (RA) on the effectiveness of the internal control system.

4.2.3. Control activities

In the process of operation, which requires the unit to regularly change activities (Alles et al, 2006), the unit meets the control activity comprehensively in the full continuous monitoring because the continuous monitoring ensures that the unit must comply with operational efficiency, reliability of financial reporting and regulatory compliance. Therefore, control activities help the unit prevent and correct errors and rectify the control activities of the unit. The study expects Control Activity to affect the effectiveness of the internal control system. Therefore, the authors hypothesized as follows:

Hypothesis H3: There is a positive impact of Control Activity (CA) on the effectiveness of the internal control system.

4.2.4. Information and communication

For the organization, information and communication are very important for the business of the unit (internal and external) (Duxbury and Neufeld, 1999). In particular, in internal communication, it is desirable to encourage members to exchange information and learn from each other (Zhang et al., 2005). When the entity acquires new information or the rules of internal control, senior management will connect to group objectives and be able to perceive information and consciousness within the entity (Yang and Maxwell, 2011). Information and communication can address or emphasize perceptions among members of the entity about the relationship with internal control information quickly. Good control of information and communication will affect the effectiveness of the internal control system. This study expects a

positive relationship between Information and communication to the effectiveness of the internal control system. Therefore, the hypothesis is given as follows:

Hypothesis H4: There is a positive impact of Information and Communication (IC) on the effectiveness of the internal control system.

4.2.5. Monitoring Activities

Monitoring is the process by which a manager evaluates the results of a control activity. Monitoring during the operation of the internal control system is operated and implemented as established and whether it is necessary to modify or change them to suit each stage and the actual situation of the unit. To achieve results, monitoring must be done regularly or periodically. Usually, monitoring is done under regular monitoring or periodic monitoring. Currently, many units pay attention to compliance with professional standards that are tools for monitoring. Therefore, the entire operation process must be monitored and adjusted as necessary. The system must be able to react dynamically, and be changed according to the requirements of the internal and external environment (COSO, 2013). The ultimate purpose of monitoring is to publish on the financial statements something that the entity must consider to comply with professional standards that can achieve the objectives of the entity. Therefore, the unit should have an appropriate and complete monitoring system. This study expects a positive relationship between Monitoring and the effectiveness of the internal control system. Therefore, the hypothesis is given as follows:

Hypothesis H5: There is a positive influence of Monitoring Activities (MA) on the effectiveness of the internal control system.

4.2.6. Hospital Management

Since the hospital management system is at the core of the operations management system, well-designed hospital governance will help improve the efficiency and effectiveness of operations. In other words, hospital management is necessary to strengthen organizational management based on a good internal control system. Previous research has documented that internal audit processes have promoted effective management and governance (Koutoupis & Pappa, 2018). The quality assessment process of the internal control system is carried out regularly at the hospital units, including the management, administration, planning, inspection and control of the Hospital's operations. This helps the internal control system is always checked and the activities of the agency are always strictly controlled. Managers have a significant impact on the hospital's future operations and development. The boards of management or different levels of management of the hospitals of the interviewees come from different professional backgrounds such as doctors and professionals with medical or legal knowledge who can provide a variety of professional suggestions throughout the development of the organization. This study expects a positive relationship between Hospital Management and the effectiveness of the internal control system. Therefore, the hypothesis is given as follows:

Hypothesis H6: There is a positive impact of Hospital Management (HM) on the effectiveness of the internal control system.

5. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Testing the reliability of the scale

The summary table of Cronbach's Alpha test results is presented as follows:

NO.	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Control environment (CE)	0,887
2	Risk Assessment (RA)	892
3	Control Activities (CA)	844.
4	Information and Communication	0.867
5	Monitoring Activities (MA)	0.793
6	Hospital Management (HM)	0.810
7	Effectiveness of internal control system (EIC)	0,819

Source: Data processing results on SPSS 20.0 Table 5.1

Cronbach's Alpha test survey data scale

Through the results of the table above, no observed variable is removed from the scale because the total variable correlation coefficient of the observed variables is greater than 0.3, and the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the scales is greater than 0.7. Thus, the reliability of survey data for these scales is guaranteed. The survey results will be used in EFA analysis in the next step.

5.2. EFA exploratory factor analysis * Results of the EFA model

Table 5.2 Factor Analysis Based on Table 5.2, we see:

	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
RA5	.887						
RA2	858.						
RA3	806						
RA1	776						
RA4	.758						
CE5		.834					
CE2		.814					
CE1		.793					
CE3		728					
CE4		.698					
IC1			866				
IC3			.792				
IC2			.791				
IC4			.710				
CA1				867.			

	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
CA2				841			
CA3				776			
CA4				.714			
HM3					870.		
HM2					835		
HM4					.699		
HM1					.698		
MA3						.827	
MA2						823	
MA1						773	
EIC1							886
EIC3							.847
EIC2							.840
Progressive Extraction Variance (%)	27,694	40,867	50,765	58,556	64,544	70,364	73,555
Eigenvalue coefficient	6,923	3.293	2,474	1,948	1,497	1,455	2.207
KMO – Independent variable:	0.843		Sig.: 0		.000		
KMO – Dependent variable:	0.707						

(Source: Results of SPSS 20.0 analysis)

- KMO coefficient – Independent variable: 0.843; KMO – Dependent variable: 0.707 in the analysis > 0.5 , indicating that the factor analysis results are reliable.

- Bartlett's Test has a Sig coefficient of $0.000 < 0.05$, showing that the factor analysis results ensure a statistically significant level.

- The variance extracted is 70.364%, showing that the variation of the factors of the independent variable analyzed can explain 70.364% of the variation of the original survey data, this is a significant level at a decent level. The Eigenvalues of the 6th factor are equal to 1.455 > 1 , showing the convergence of the analysis stopped at the 6th independent factor, or the analysis results show that there are 6 independent factors extracted from the survey data.

- The results show that only one dependent factor is extracted at Eigenvalue equal to 2.207 > 1 . This factor explains 73,555% of the data variation of the 3 observed variables involved in EFA exploratory factor analysis.

- In the factor matrix after rotation, the concentration of observed variables by each factor is very clear, the observed variables all have a factor load factor greater than 0.5, showing the importance as well as the rigor of the original scale, and showing that the observed variables all show the influence on the factors that these variables represent.

After running the rotation matrix, the observed variables remain in the same group as the original and are described as follows:

Factor group 1: Consists of 5 observed variables: RA1, RA2, RA3, RA4 and RA5. These variables constitute the “Risk Assessment” factor - called: RA. The observed variables all have a load factor greater than 0.7 so all these observed variables are significant.

Factor group 2: Consists of 5 observed variables: CE1, CE2, CE3, CE4 and CE5. These variables constitute the “Control Environment” factor - called: CE. The observed variables all have a load factor greater than 0.6 so all these observed variables are significant.

Factor group 3: Consists of 4 observed variables: IC1, IC 2, IC 3 and IC 4. These variables constitute the “Information and Communication” factor – called IC. The observed variables all have a load factor greater than 0.7 so all these observed variables are significant.

Factor group 4: Consists of 4 observed variables: CA1, CA2, CA3 and CA4. These variables constitute the “Control Activity” factor - called: CA. The observed variables all have a load factor greater than 0.7 so all these observed variables are significant.

Factor group 5: Consists of 4 observed variables: HM1, HM2, HM3 and HM4. These variables constitute the “Hospital Management” factor – called HM. The observed variables all have a load factor greater than 0.6 so all these observed variables are significant.

Factor group 6: Consists of 3 observed variables: MA1, MA2 and MA3. These variables constitute the “Monitoring Activities” factor – called MA. The observed variables all have a load factor greater than 0.7 so all these observed variables are significant.

Calibration model:

After conducting the reliability test of the scale using Cronbach's alpha coefficient analysis and EFA exploratory factor analysis and the type of variables that are not guaranteed during the analysis. The observed variables converge to exactly 6 groups corresponding to 6 independent factors affecting the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health. The order of the groups of factors has changed, leading to the following new research hypotheses:

- *Hypothesis 1:* Risk assessment affects the effectiveness of the internal control system.
- *Hypothesis 2:* The control environment affects the effectiveness of the internal control system.
- *Hypothesis 3:* Information and communication affect the effectiveness of the internal control system.
- *Hypothesis 4:* Control activities affect the effectiveness of the internal control system.
- *Hypothesis 5:* Hospital governance affects the effectiveness of the internal control system.
- *Hypothesis 6:* Monitoring affects the effectiveness of the internal control system.

5.3. Multivariate Regression Exploratory Analysis (MRA)

5.3.1. Pearson's correlation coefficient test

Before conducting multiple linear regression analysis, it is necessary to perform correlation coefficient analysis for 07 variables, including 06 independent variables and 01 dependent variable (The effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under Hanoi Department of Health) with Pearson coefficient and 2-sided testing with a significance level of 0.05. The table below simulates the independence between the dependent variable and the independent variables. The correlation reaches the significance level at 0.05 (The probability of accepting the false hypothesis is 5%), then all variables are correlated with the dependent variable.

Correlations

Table 5.3. Pearson's test results on the correlation between dependent variables and independent variables

		CE	RA	CA	IC	MA	Category	EIC
CE	Pearson	1	.252	282	482	0.387	0.369	.711
	Correlation							
	Sig(2-tailed)		0.001	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	184	184	184	184	.000 184	184	184
RA	Pearson	.252	1	283	0.313	0.038	0.063	436
	Correlation	0.001		.000	.000	606.	393.	.000
	Sig(2-tailed)							
	N	184	184	184	184	184	184	184
CA	Pearson	282	283	1	295	0.028	253	465
	Correlation	.000	.000		.000	.702	0.001	.000
	Sig(2-tailed)							
	N	184	184	184	184	184	184	184
IC	Pearson	482	0.313	295	1	.304	185	.552
	Correlation	.000	.000	.000		.000	012	
	Sig(2-tailed)							.000 184
	N	184	184	184	184	184	184	
MA	Pearson	0.387	0.038	0.028	.304	1	0.2	376
	Correlation	.000	606.	.702	.000		0.007	.000
	Sig(2-tailed)							
	N	184	184	184	184	184	184	184
HM	Pearson	0.369	0.063	253	185		1	514
	Correlation	.000	393.	0.001	012	0.2		.000
	Sig(2-tailed)					0.007 184		
	N	184	184	184	184		184	184
EIC	Pearson	.711	436	465	.552	376	514	1
	Correlation	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	Sig(2-tailed)							
	N	184	184	184	184	184	184	184

(Source: Data processing results on SPSS 20.0 software)

Looking at the table above, we see that the correlation coefficient between independent variables and dependent variables is quite high, ranging from 0.376 to 0.711. The Sig values of the factors are all less than 0.05. This indicates that the model has a correlation between the dependent variable and the independent variable. Therefore, the introduction of independent variables into the model is correct, as it has a certain effect on the dependent variable. This shows that the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health is mainly affected by the above factors, so in the process of analyzing the influence, the topic will focus on studying these factors.

5.3.2. Regression analysis

The results of regression analysis aim to determine the influence of each factor in the model with the dependent variable being the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health. These levels of influence are determined through the regression coefficient. The regression model is as follows:

$$EIC = \beta_0 + \beta_1RA + \beta_2CE + \beta_3IC + \beta_4CA + \beta_5HM + \beta_6MA + e_i$$

Table 5.4. Results of multivariate regression analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.& nbsp;
	B	STD Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.338	230		-1.472	143.
CE	282	037	390	7,711	.000
RA	156	.031	.216	4,973	.000
CA	201	0.050	178	4,029	.000
IC	178	.053	162.	3.385	.001
MA	117	047	111	2,496	013
Category	243	041:	259	5,921	.000
R² calibration = 0.709; Test F with Sig value: 0.000					

(Source: Data processing results on SPSS 20.0 software)

From the results of the table above, we see that the F test gives the value Sig. < 0.05, which proves to be the right model and with it that R² correction has a value of 0.709; which means that the regression model explains 70.9% of the variation of the dependent variable. Thus, the model has an average explanatory value. In addition, it is found that all factors affect the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals due to the Sig value < 0.05. From the above analysis, we can get an equation describing the fluctuations of factors affecting the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health as follows:

$$EIC = 0.390 CE + 0.216 RA + 0.178 CA + 0.62 IC + 0.111 MA + 0.259 HM$$

- Assume the independence of the error

The Durbin-Watson quantity is used to test the correlation of adjacent errors. The hypothesis when conducting this test is:

H0: overall correlation coefficient of residues is zero.

Performing regression gives us the result that the test value d of Durbin – Watson in the model summary table is equal to 1,952. Under regression conditions, the Durbin-Watson value must be between 1 and 3. (Source: SPSS Research in Business by Hoang Trong & Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc)

Model Summary^b

Model	R Square	Change	Change Statistic F Change	s	Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson	
			df1	df2			
1	.663 ^a		70,023	5	178	.000	1,952

a. Predictors: (Constant), MA, CA, RA, IC, CE

b. Dependent Variable: EIC

The calculated d value falls into the hypothesis acceptance domain with no autocorrelation.

Thus, the model does not violate the assumption of autocorrelation.

- Assume no multicollinearity

Table 5.5. Multicollinearity test

Model	Multicollinearity Measurement	
	Acceptance	Variance magnification factor (VIF)
(Constant)		
CE	621	1,611
RA	.846	1.182
CA	.816	1,226
IC	690	1,449
MA	.809	1,236
HM	830	1.205

Source: Data processing results on SPSS 20.0 software

Given the large tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of the small variables, the regression model does not violate multicollinearity. Regression violates multicollinearity when the VIF value is greater than or equal to 10.

5.4. Discuss the results of regression analysis

From the results of regression analysis, the following research model has 6 hypotheses:

- **Hypothesis H1:** Risk assessment affects the effectiveness of the internal control system. This hypothesis is accepted because the Sig. value is less than 0.05, with the standardized Beta coefficient of this factor of 0.216 proving that the relationship between the effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals and the risk assessment is the same. So, when the Risk Assessment factor increases by 1 unit, the effectiveness of the internal

control system in public hospitals increases by 0.216 units, respectively. This result shows that a well-implemented risk assessment including objectives, identification, development of assessment procedures, assessment methods and risk management has a significant impact on improving the effectiveness of the internal control system. This result is consistent with the studies of Lannoye (1999), Walker (1999), Angella & Inanga (2009), Sultana & Haque (2011), Gamage et al. (2014). This can be easily seen that in the process of internal control, there are many risks, the risk assessment plays an important role of the unit.

- **Hypothesis H2:** Control environment affects the effectiveness of the internal control system. This hypothesis is accepted because the Sig. value is less than 0.05, with the standardized Beta coefficient of this factor of 0.390 proving that the relationship between the effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals and monitoring is the same. So when the Control Environment factor increases by 1 unit, the effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals increases by 0.390 units. This result shows that a healthy control environment (including: honesty and ethical values, professional qualifications of leaders, employees as well as the organizational structure of departments in hospitals) will be the foundation for the internal control system in hospitals to be effective. This result is consistent with the studies of Ramos (2004), Rea & Subramaniam (2006), Angella & Inanga (2009), Sultana & Haque (2011), Gamage et al. (2014).

- **Hypothesis H3:** Information and communication affect the effectiveness of the internal control system. This hypothesis is accepted because the Sig. value is less than 0.05, with the standardized Beta coefficient of this factor of 0.162 proving that the relationship between the effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals and information – communication is the same direction. So, when the information and communication factor increases by 1 unit, the effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals increases by 0.162 units. This result shows that information supporting the effective management, control and communication methods in hospitals, meeting management requirements including: arising economic operations are reflected promptly, the quality of information must be honest and reasonable, which will increase the effectiveness of the internal control system in hospital units. Improving the quality of information in hospitals is a solution to enhance the effectiveness of the internal control system, meeting the information needs for timely, accurate and effective decision-making of the Board of Directors.

- **Hypothesis H4:** Control activities affect the effectiveness of the internal control system. This hypothesis is accepted because the Sig. value is less than 0.05, with the standardized Beta coefficient of this factor of 0.178 proving that the relationship between the effectiveness of internal control systems in public hospitals and control activities is the same. So when the control factor increases by 1 unit, the effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals increases by 0.178 units, respectively. This result shows that the implementation of control activities carried out regularly, in accordance with legal documents, and in accordance with internal spending regulations will improve the effectiveness of the internal control system in hospital units.

- **Hypothesis H5:** Hospital governance affects the effectiveness of the internal control system. This hypothesis is accepted because the Sig. value is less than 0.05, with the standardized Beta coefficient of this factor of 0.259 proving that the relationship between the

effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals and the ethical culture is the same. So, when the Hospital Governance factor increases to 1 unit, the effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals increases to 0.259 units, respectively. The quality assessment process of the internal control system is carried out regularly at the hospital units, including the management, administration, planning, inspection and control of the Hospital's operations. This helps the internal control system is always checked and the activities of the agency are always strictly controlled.

- **Hypothesis H6:** Monitoring affects the effectiveness of the internal control system. This hypothesis is accepted because the Sig. value is less than 0.05, with the standardized Beta coefficient of this factor of 0.111 proving that the relationship between the effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals and the control environment is the same. So when the monitoring factor increases to 1 unit, the effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals increases to 0.111 units. The process of assessing the quality of the internal control system is carried out regularly at the hospital units, including quarterly and annual reports on the finalization of revenues and expenditures, regularly informing officers and employees in the unit. This helps the internal control system is always checked and the activities of the agency are always strictly controlled. Strengthening internal and external monitoring is the solution to enhance the effectiveness of internal control systems in hospital units.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Internal control is an important management tool, the core of managers in the organization and a measure to minimize fraud, thereby helping to improve operational efficiency as well as strengthen organizational supervision. For research to improve the effectiveness of the internal control system in public hospitals with financial autonomy, thereby improving the performance of financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health, the article makes some recommendations as follows:

6.1. Completing the control environment

According to the survey results, the control environment is the factor that has the strongest impact on the effectiveness of the internal control system, so it is necessary to focus on solutions to improve the control environment at the best level, specifically:

First of all, hospitals need to develop a set of ethical standards, working rules, medical industry culture, code of conduct of employees in the industry as well as outside and apply them synchronously. On the one hand, the hospital management needs to keep personal ethics, courtesy, gentleness, respect for employees, especially for good employees, it is necessary to have reasonable behavior to help the medical sector maintain human resources. On the other hand, it is necessary to have methods to educate and disseminate to all medical staff in the unit to be aware of their responsibilities in the inspection and supervision of all activities of the hospital. At the same time, hospitals also need to publicize and disseminate to relevant external parties such as patients, suppliers of goods and services for hospitals to coordinate and support hospitals in implementing regulations as well as monitoring activities and behaviors of medical staff.

In addition, the hospital needs to regularly review and update the Internal Expenditure Regulations, develop new spending norms and standards, and provide detailed instructions according to flexible and fast legal regulations but ensure compliance with regulations in the approval and payment.

In addition, the management also needs to assign work based on the capacity requirements of employees, helping employees promote their abilities, work productively and effectively, thereby creating motivation as well as interest in work for employees. In addition, hospitals should regularly open professional training and retraining classes for employees to improve their professional qualifications and skills, help employees keep up with changes in work performance processes, as well as new products and services through on-site training, online training or videoconference sessions, etc. In addition, hospitals should also have policies to rotate work positions, help employees expand their professional knowledge and be able to take on any additional work when necessary.

6.2. Completing hospital management

The role of the Director of the hospital is very important and a decisive factor in the success and failure of the hospital. In the current development of society, hospitals need to move from a purely professional management model to a service economy unit management model. Organize reasonable economic and technical norms; strictly manage inputs and income costs; shift the focus from "Doctor" to "service requester". The head of the hospital requires organizational knowledge to manage and operate the unit like a business. The director of the hospital must be able to design a management apparatus, a management system suitable to the conditions of his unit, must be able to properly use human resources, material resources, resources, time and information with appropriate mechanisms to resolve conflicts in the development of the hospital, develop strategies to develop and operate an effective operating apparatus. Therefore, the Director of the hospital and the Deputy Directors of the hospital need to attend advanced management courses and learn and promptly grasp the financial regulations in general.

Internal controls can ensure the safety of asset entities, ensure the accuracy of information, or improve performance. According to the research results of Shih-Nien Lee, Tzu-Ching Weng, Hsin-Yi Huang (2021), at the hospital management application level, the hospital needs to develop an internal control index system so that colleagues understand the performance index items and set work goals in order of priority. In addition, management must delegate authority to subordinates. Similarly, policies and undertakings are top to bottom. Based on the audit, the manager obtains information that already exists and can have an impact on efficiency, reduce risks due to internal control errors, and achieve an effective control mechanism. Furthermore, positioning the roles of various stakeholders involved in hospital governance, including department heads, staff, patients, providers, etc. will effectively manage or impact the mechanism of hospital management. Through the influence of internal control, hospitals can not only establish a complete and effective governance mechanism, but also shape the hospital culture of voluntary publicity and ensure the effectiveness of social responsibility, helping to understand the operational philosophy and goals of hospital organizational value recognition. In addition, in order to improve the efficiency of hospital operations, hospitals need to arrange a dedicated person or department responsible for the

appropriate internal control system according to the size of the organization and manage this system according to clear internal control principles.

6.3. Finalization of risk assessment

The current reality is that medical staff at hospitals are facing intense working pressure, while the number of medical staff has not increased much. This is one of the reasons why hospitals face several professional risks, operational risks and other unusual risks...Therefore, specialized departments such as Social Work Department, Finance and Accounting Department and Hospital Departments/Departments must enhance their role in identifying strengths and limitations, difficulties, actively advising and advising hospital management on specific solutions to improve conditions, manage and control risks well.

To identify internal risks, on the one hand, hospitals need to continue to maintain briefing meetings between faculties/departments and the Hospital Board of Directors to detect risks promptly, on the other hand, hospitals must also regularly check the implementation of regulations for officials and workers throughout the hospital.

For external risks, for identification, the hospital needs to constantly update changes in state policies and regulations on economy, politics, society..., regularly organize seminars to capture the needs of patients as well as professional trends, thereby identifying risks in medical examination and treatment.

Hospital leaders also need to be aware that hospitals can only limit the risk to the lowest level and cannot completely eliminate the risk. Therefore, the Board of Directors first needs to assess the likelihood of risks and the impact of risks on the objectives of hospitals, discussions with experts in the field of health, the field of risk management to be able to assess the risks that hospitals may face and its impact.

After identifying and evaluating the risks that may affect the operation of the Hospital, depending on the type of risk and the extent of the impact, it is possible to choose risk countermeasures such as risk mitigation or risk acceptance.

In summary, in order to manage risks well, hospitals need to develop measures so that all employees are aware of the harmful effects of risks as well as the minimum risk limit that the unit can accept. At the same time, the Board of Directors needs to develop a complete process of identifying, evaluating and coping with risks.

6.4. Completion of control activities

Currently, hospitals still use qualitative evaluation criteria and rely on the subjective will of the evaluator such as the number of minutes, conclusions, the number of detected errors, the number of proposed opinions... Therefore, in order to strengthen the effectiveness of control activities, managers must innovate their thinking in developing criteria to evaluate the results of internal control activities in the direction of developing a scorecard on the level of implementation. In today's hospitals, internal control is only concerned with compliance and completeness of documents but forgets to pay attention to other aspects of internal control such as risk assessment, evaluation of policies, evaluation of control procedures. Therefore, to

improve the quality of internal control, it is necessary to change and improve the quality of control methods. In addition, it is also necessary to update documents, policies and regimes regularly to ensure that the internal control activities of the hospital are not outdated compared to the times.

Hospitals delegate control responsibility to the post-inspection department. Therefore, for the internal control process to be implemented effectively, the departments also develop their control procedures, thereby providing the right solutions in time to handle when problems occur. Complete several key control procedures and procedures that are at high risk of fraud and abuse such as expenditure control, revenue control, asset and capital control, and material allocation control.

Regarding internal control of revenue sources, especially revenue from health insurance: The examination, testing and treatment services must be coded, the computerized billing system and have detailed and specific fees for each procedure.

Regarding internal control of hospital expenses, the hospital needs to develop norms, standards, and regulations on internal expenditures issued in specific documents, detailed and strict regulations on financial discipline.

Control of the use and distribution of goods and supplies after procurement: The hospital needs to raise the awareness of controlling the use process after use and distribution to management levels as well as the medical staff. The control of the use process, in addition to the inspection of documents and books, needs to be associated with inventory and inspection of artifacts.

In terms of asset management control, asset management needs to take place in a closed loop of assets, from construction investment, procurement, ownership establishment, granting, registration, use to liquidation and disposal of assets to achieve management requirements.

For testing equipment with rapid technological changes, the hospital needs to propose a rapid depreciation method or apply an adjusted declining balance depreciation method.

For receivables and payables, it is required to reconcile and confirm debts periodically.

6.5. Completing information and communication

Today, information and communication also significantly affect the operations of the hospital. Some recommendations to improve information and communication in hospitals such as:

First of all, hospitals need to ensure that the information system is always smooth in the unit, ensuring that the internal network system is not faulty so that information is transmitted promptly.

Secondly, hospitals need to regularly coordinate with hospital management software providers to quickly complete to facilitate faculties/departments in the process of handling work.

Third, hospitals need to organize more meetings with patients and their families to better capture information from customers.

Fourthly, organize propaganda on disease prevention and treatment, strengthen social activities for the sick and the poor.

Fifth, organize and participate in activities on medical science to enhance the professional reputation of the hospital.

Sixth, collect information to conduct the survey to know the opinions of patients and their families about the situation of medical examination and treatment at the hospital. Since then, hospitals have had timely and close-to-reality adjustment plans.

Finally, hospitals need to establish a communication channel that allows staff, patients and family members to reflect on unusual behaviors and events that are likely to cause damage to the hospital and customers.

6.6. Completion of monitoring activities

For hospital staff to achieve the overall goals of the unit, the management must strengthen and improve the internal inspection and supervision in professional fields by establishing an independent control department to ensure continuous and objective inspection and supervision, and strictly implement periodic supervision. From there, it is possible to detect unreasonable and inadequate points of the system and take timely adjustment measures to suit the actual situation at the unit to proactively detect, warn and prevent errors in management at the hospital.

Strengthen monitoring self-inspection by developing a monthly and quarterly professional monitoring inspection plan. The shortcomings and errors detected during the inspection process should be assessed by the management and corrective measures will then be notified to the relevant faculties/departments for each individual to note, learn from experience, and prevent similar errors from occurring.

In addition, periodically, hospitals need to publicize the results of internal inspection and supervision so that all employees can grasp and improve themselves as well as contribute to the improvement of internal control. The research results of the project have brought about theoretical and practical significance. Through the systematization of theoretical aspects of internal control and internal control systems, it has created an overall picture for subjects interested in researching issues related to the topic. The results of the study also open up new research directions that other authors can target. In practical terms, the results of the study contribute to orienting the development of policies and mechanisms for state management agencies in the field of medicine, auditing, and managers of the medical sector, improving the training efficiency of training institutions and universities.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

7.1. Limitations of the article

Firstly, the study was only conducted in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health, and the sample size was 184 observations selected according

to a convenient method, so the representation of the research sample was not high. Therefore, managers and employees participating in the study sample were unevenly distributed. If this study is repeated in the whole country of Vietnam with a larger sample size, the generalization of the study will be higher.

Secondly, this study only focuses on the main factors affecting the effectiveness of the internal control system in financially autonomous public hospitals under the Hanoi Department of Health. Therefore, further research should extend the study to different factors and regions.

7.2. Further research

From the limitations of the article, the authors propose the next research direction:

- Continue to study and propose more factors affecting the effectiveness of internal control activities through expanding consultation with experts as well as expanding the scope of sampling.

- Continue to study in depth the influence of each factor on the effectiveness of the internal control system in larger hospitals.

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CÁC NHÂN TỐ ẢNH HƯỞNG ĐẾN KHẢ NĂNG TIẾP CẬN VỐN QUA FINTECH CỦA CÁC CÔNG TY KHỞI NGHIỆP TẠI VIỆT NAM

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Tóm tắt

Nghiên cứu này được thực hiện nhằm xác định các nhân tố ảnh hưởng đến khả năng tiếp cận vốn qua Fintech của các công ty khởi nghiệp tại Việt Nam. Dữ liệu sơ cấp được thu thập thông qua khảo sát các công ty khởi nghiệp hoạt động trong đa dạng lĩnh vực tại Việt Nam trong năm 2022. Mô hình nghiên cứu được ước lượng thông qua phương pháp Heckman 2 giai đoạn. Kết quả nghiên cứu chỉ ra tương quan giữa các yếu tố: lĩnh vực hoạt động, tỉ lệ chi tiêu cho nghiên cứu và phát triển, tốc độ tăng trưởng doanh thu, và các phương thức tiếp cận vốn truyền thống với mức độ tiếp cận vốn qua Fintech. Trên cơ sở đó, nhóm tác giả đề xuất các giải pháp giúp tăng khả năng huy động vốn qua Fintech thành công cho các công ty khởi nghiệp tại Việt Nam.

Từ khóa: *Fintech, huy động vốn, khởi nghiệp (startups)*

TÁC ĐỘNG CỦA TỶ GIÁ HỐI ĐOẠI, LẠM PHÁT VÀ LÃI SUẤT SWAP LIÊN NGÂN HÀNG ĐẾN KHẢ NĂNG SINH LỜI CỦA CÁC NGÂN HÀNG THƯƠNG MẠI VIỆT NAM

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Tóm tắt

Là một yếu tố quan trọng quyết định sự phát triển của ngân hàng, khả năng sinh lời luôn thu hút được sự quan tâm của nhiều chuyên gia phân tích, các nhà quản lý cũng như các nhà hoạch định chính sách - đặc biệt trong bối cảnh nền kinh tế nhiều biến động như hiện nay. Bài viết tìm hiểu các tác động đến khả năng sinh lời của các ngân hàng thương mại Việt Nam nhìn từ tỷ giá hối đoái USD/VND, lạm phát, và lãi suất swap trên thị trường liên ngân hàng. Kết quả phân tích 17 ngân hàng thương mại được niêm yết trên Sở giao dịch chứng khoán thành phố Hồ Chí Minh (HOSE) trong giai đoạn quý 1 năm 2015 đến quý 4 năm 2022 cho thấy tỷ giá hối đoái và lãi suất swap đều có ảnh hưởng cùng chiều và có ý nghĩa thống kê tới tỷ suất sinh lời trên vốn chủ sở hữu (ROE) của các ngân hàng thương mại tại Việt Nam. Trong khi đó, kết quả không chỉ ra mối quan hệ giữa lạm phát và khả năng sinh lời của ngân hàng. Kết quả thực nghiệm là cơ sở để bài viết đề xuất một số giải pháp và hàm ý chính sách nhằm nâng cao khả năng sinh lời của các ngân hàng thương mại Việt Nam.

Từ khóa: khả năng sinh lời, lãi suất swap, lạm phát, ngân hàng thương mại, tỷ giá hối đoái

INFLUENCES OF EXCHANGE RATE, INFLATION, AND INTERBANK INTEREST RATE SWAP ON THE PROFITABILITY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN VIETNAM

Abstract

As a crucial factor determining the bank's development, profitability has always attracted the attention of many analysts, managers as well as policy makers - especially in the current context of a volatile economy. The paper investigates the impacts on the profitability of commercial banks in Vietnam from exchange rate USD/VND, inflation, and interbank interest rate swap on the financial performance of commercial banks in Vietnam. The findings from 17 commercial banks listed on the Ho Chi Minh Stock Exchange (HOSE) during the period from the first quarter of 2015 to the fourth quarter of 2022 revealed that the exchange rate and interest rate swap both have significant and statistical positive impact on return on equity (ROE) of commercial banks in Vietnam. In contrast, the results indicated no relationship between inflation and bank profitability. The empirical outcomes are the basis for the paper to propose some recommendations and policy implications to enhance the profitability of Vietnamese commercial banks.

Keywords: Commercial banks, exchange rate, foreign exchange swap, inflation, profitability

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Trong bối cảnh hội nhập kinh tế toàn cầu, tỷ giá hối đoái là một trong những yếu tố vĩ mô quan trọng tác động đến mức giá cả chung và sự phân bổ nguồn lực trong một nền kinh tế. Sự biến động của tỷ giá hối đoái cũng đã được chứng minh có ảnh hưởng đáng kể lên khả năng sinh lợi của các ngân hàng thương mại. Đặc biệt, khi hoạt động nhập khẩu có xu hướng gia tăng, nhu cầu sử dụng đồng ngoại tệ của các doanh nghiệp xuất nhập cũng tăng lên theo, đồng nội tệ suy yếu so với đồng ngoại tệ sẽ khiến các ngân hàng kiếm được lợi nhuận chênh lệch giá (Lagat & Nyandema, 2016). Những năm gần đây nền kinh tế thế giới và Việt Nam đã trải qua nhiều biến động đến từ đại dịch Covid-19 xuất hiện vào năm 2020 và xung đột giữa Nga-Ukraine xảy ra vào năm 2022 dẫn đến tình trạng bất ổn định của tỷ giá hối đoái. Lạm phát đã bị đẩy lên cao tại nhiều quốc gia đặc biệt vào cuối năm 2022, đồng USD theo đó cũng tăng giá kéo theo sự thay đổi của tỷ giá hối đoái.

Đối với Việt Nam Đồng, tỷ giá hối đoái USD/VND cũng đã có thời điểm tăng lên mức 24.860 vào tháng 10/2022, mức tăng cao nhất kể từ năm 2009 theo số liệu của Hiệp hội Thị trường Trái phiếu Việt Nam (VBMA, 2023). Trong thời kỳ lạm phát cao, các khoản gửi tiết kiệm tại ngân hàng ít hơn, đồng thời ngân hàng cũng cẩn trọng hơn khi cho vay các khoản vay lớn để tránh rủi ro vỡ nợ, tổng giá trị vốn hóa của ngân hàng giảm, từ đó lợi nhuận cũng bị ảnh hưởng theo (Khan và cộng sự, 2014).

Để đối phó với những biến động của lạm phát và tỷ giá hối đoái, nhiều sản phẩm hợp đồng phái sinh giúp giảm thiểu rủi ro đã thu hút được sự quan tâm của các ngân hàng thương mại Việt Nam. Số lượng giao dịch phái sinh ngày càng tăng đã đặt ra sự cần thiết nghiên cứu tác động của thu nhập đến từ các giao dịch này tới lợi nhuận của ngân hàng.

Trong đó, một công cụ quan trọng được ngân hàng sử dụng là giao dịch hoán đổi (Swap). Theo DerivGroup (2013), khi một ngân hàng thiết lập một giao dịch hoán đổi với khách hàng, họ đã cố định một mức lợi nhuận. Thông qua việc thực hiện một giao dịch đối nghịch trên thị trường liên ngân hàng, bất kể lãi suất lên hay xuống, ngân hàng luôn có được lợi nhuận. Lãi suất hoán đổi (lãi suất swap) chênh lệch giữa hai giao dịch càng lớn, ngân hàng càng thu được mức lợi nhuận tương ứng lớn hơn. Do đó, có thể nói lãi suất swap ảnh hưởng phần nào đến lợi nhuận hoạt động của ngân hàng. Bên cạnh đó, một số ngân hàng có thể tận dụng xếp hạng tín dụng của mình để thực hiện một giao dịch hoán đổi với lãi suất nhỏ hơn với một bên khác, và thực hiện giao dịch ngược lại với khách hàng ở một lãi suất lớn hơn để thu lợi nhuận (Whittaker, 2017). Lãi suất swap trên thị trường liên ngân hàng càng cao, ngân hàng càng nhận được con số tuyệt đối lớn hơn, tính theo giá trị giao dịch tuyệt đối. Đây là phương pháp các ngân hàng kiếm được lợi nhuận từ các giao dịch hoán đổi nói chung và từ việc lợi suất của các giao dịch này cao hơn. Các ngân hàng lớn hầu như không chấp nhận vào việc đánh cược lãi suất swap (betting), vì nếu làm điều này, bên cạnh việc đối mặt với các vấn đề pháp lý, họ cũng sẽ mất đi một lượng khách hàng nhất định (Abdel-khalik, 2019).

Bài viết này tập trung làm rõ tác động của lạm phát, tỷ giá hối đoái và lãi suất swap trên thị trường liên ngân hàng tới khả năng sinh lời của các ngân hàng thương mại tại Việt Nam, từ đó đề xuất một số giải pháp và hàm ý chính sách về cơ chế điều hành nhằm cải thiện kết quả hoạt động tài chính của các ngân hàng. Với mục tiêu nghiên cứu này, phần còn lại của bài nghiên cứu được tổ chức thành các mục như sau: Mục 2 trình bày các tổng quan tình hình

nghiên cứu; Mục 3 mô tả dữ liệu và phương pháp nghiên cứu; Mục 4 phân tích và thảo luận kết quả nghiên cứu; và Mục 5 nêu kết luận và hàm ý chính sách dựa trên kết quả đã nghiên cứu.

2. TỔNG QUAN TÌNH HÌNH NGHIÊN CỨU

2.1. Tổng quan các nghiên cứu trên thế giới

Nhiều bài nghiên cứu đi trước đã nghiên cứu mối quan hệ giữa tỷ giá hối đoái và kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng. Theo nghiên cứu của Hasan và cộng sự (2020), Ozgur và Gorus (2016), Nahar và cộng sự (2020), tỷ giá không có nhiều tác động vào lợi nhuận của ngân hàng thông qua mô hình tuyến tính của các tác giả trên. Những nghiên cứu trên chỉ ra rằng mối liên kết giữa tỷ giá và lợi nhuận của ngân hàng là rất yếu. Tuy nhiên, nghiên cứu của Davydenko (2011) về tác động của tỷ giá đến lợi nhuận ngân hàng tại Ukraine cho thấy, việc đồng nội tệ mất giá so với USD đem lại lợi nhuận tốt hơn cho ngân hàng. Nghiên cứu này cho rằng việc các ngân hàng dự báo tốt biến động tỷ giá, cùng với việc giao dịch ngoại tệ tăng vọt khiến nhiều nhà băng tại nước này hưởng lợi. Osuagwu (2014) cũng chỉ ra rằng tỷ giá hối đoái là một nhân tố quan trọng trong việc xác định lợi nhuận của ngân hàng. Thông qua chỉ số ROE, tác giả cho thấy tỷ giá có tác động tích cực tới lợi nhuận của các ngân hàng tại Nigeria. Lagat & Nyandema (2016) cũng tìm thấy tỷ giá có ảnh hưởng tích cực rõ ràng đối với lợi nhuận của các ngân hàng thương mại tại Kenya. Nghiên cứu giải thích rằng khi hoạt động nhập khẩu có xu hướng gia tăng, nhu cầu sử dụng đồng ngoại tệ của các doanh nghiệp xuất nhập cũng tăng lên theo, đồng nội tệ suy yếu so với đồng ngoại tệ sẽ khiến các ngân hàng kiếm được lợi nhuận chênh lệch giá. Nghiên cứu của Ali và cộng sự (2018) chỉ ra rằng ROE hay lợi nhuận của ngân hàng tại khu vực Hồi giáo chịu ảnh hưởng tích cực tới từ tỷ giá. Hossain và Ahamed (2021) cũng đưa ra kết luận rằng tỷ giá là một trong những yếu tố chính ảnh hưởng tới lợi nhuận của các ngân hàng Bangladesh. Elhussein và Osman (2019) lại có phát hiện không giống với các bài nghiên cứu trên. Dựa trên mẫu là 37 ngân hàng tại Sudan đang hoạt động trong giai đoạn năm 2002 đến năm 2017, kết quả bài nghiên cứu cho thấy mối quan hệ ngược chiều giữa tỷ giá hối đoái và lợi nhuận của ngân hàng (đại diện bởi chỉ số ROE), tuy nhiên mức độ tác động của tỷ giá hối đoái lên lợi nhuận không quá rõ ràng. Nhóm tác giả giải thích có thể do lệnh cấm vận kinh tế chặt chẽ đối với Sudan trong thời gian nghiên cứu này, quốc gia này bị tách khỏi hệ thống tài chính quốc tế và ảnh hưởng tiêu cực đến khả năng tham gia vào các hoạt động thương mại quốc tế.

Về mặt lý thuyết, tình trạng lạm phát ảnh hưởng đến giá trị của tài sản tài chính và các công cụ tài chính khác trong danh mục đầu tư của ngân hàng, do đó sẽ tác động đến lợi nhuận được tạo ra bởi những tài sản đó theo thời gian. Trong điều kiện các yếu tố khác không đổi, lạm phát có thể ảnh hưởng đến lợi nhuận đầu tư và từ đó ảnh hưởng đến lợi nhuận tổng thể. Ngoài ra, lạm phát cũng có thể có tác động không nhỏ đến giá trị tài sản ngân hàng nắm giữ và hiệu quả hoạt động của ngân hàng (Abaidoo và Anyigba, 2020). Đối với ảnh hưởng của lạm phát đối với lợi nhuận của ngân hàng, Akani và cộng sự (2016) đã chỉ ra rằng tỷ lệ lạm phát có tác động cùng chiều đối với lợi nhuận của ngân hàng thông qua chỉ số ROE, tuy nhiên mức độ ảnh hưởng không rõ ràng. Kết quả nghiên cứu Abaidoo và Anyigba (2020) cho thấy lạm phát có tác động cùng chiều rõ ràng đối với lợi nhuận ngân hàng trên mẫu nghiên cứu sử dụng dữ liệu theo quý của toàn bộ các ngân hàng thương mại trong ngành ngân hàng của Mỹ trong giai đoạn năm 1984 đến năm 2016. Đồng thời bài nghiên cứu này cũng chỉ ra rằng các yếu tố vĩ mô không lường trước được cũng như tỷ lệ lạm phát kỳ vọng có tác động rõ ràng hơn đối với chỉ

số ROA thay vì chỉ số ROE. Nghiên cứu của Jackson và cộng sự (2021) cũng khẳng định lạm phát có tác động tích cực đối với lợi nhuận của ngân hàng. Ngược lại, nghiên cứu của Khan và cộng sự (2014) lại cho thấy mối quan hệ ngược chiều giữa lạm phát và lợi nhuận ngân hàng. Nghiên cứu giải thích rằng trong thời kỳ lạm phát cao, các khoản gửi tiết kiệm tại ngân hàng ít hơn, đồng thời ngân hàng cũng cẩn trọng hơn khi cho vay các khoản vay lớn để tránh rủi ro vỡ nợ, tổng giá trị vốn hóa của ngân hàng giảm, từ đó lợi nhuận cũng bị ảnh hưởng theo. Kết quả nghiên cứu của Moyo và cộng sự (2020) cũng thể hiện lạm phát có sự ảnh hưởng ngược chiều rõ rệt lên kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng thương mại.

Đối với hoạt động hoán đổi ngoại tệ của các ngân hàng thương mại, khi lãi suất biến động mạnh theo tình hình kinh tế vĩ mô, các tổ chức tiết kiệm và cho vay đã nhận ra tầm quan trọng của các hợp đồng phái sinh như hợp đồng tương lai và hoán đổi lãi suất trong việc giảm thiểu rủi ro và đạt được kết quả tài chính tốt (Brewer và cộng sự, 1996). Sử dụng mẫu nghiên cứu bao gồm 99 tổ chức tiết kiệm và cho vay tại Mỹ trong khoảng thời gian nghiên cứu từ quý 3 năm 1985 đến quý 4 năm 1989, nghiên cứu của tác giả chỉ ra rằng việc các tổ chức tiết kiệm và cho vay tham gia vào một hợp đồng hoán đổi lãi suất có mối quan hệ ngược chiều với độ biến động của lợi nhuận tổ chức tiết kiệm và cho vay. Ngoài giảm thiểu rủi ro, sử dụng hợp đồng hoán đổi lãi suất còn giúp giảm thiểu thuế phát sinh đối với các giao dịch ngoại hối, từ đó giúp nâng cao kết quả tài chính của các ngân hàng (Said, 2011). Với mẫu nghiên cứu bao gồm dữ liệu của 5 ngân hàng lớn tại Mỹ trong giai đoạn năm 2002 đến 2009, nghiên cứu phát hiện có mối quan hệ cùng chiều giữa lợi nhuận của ngân hàng và việc ngân hàng sử dụng các hợp đồng phái sinh.

2.2. Tổng quan các nghiên cứu trong nước

Trên thị trường liên ngân hàng tại Việt Nam, giao dịch hoán đổi giữa hai đồng tiền VND và USD chủ yếu được thực hiện dưới dạng một giao dịch giao ngay kết hợp với một giao dịch kỳ hạn. Lãi suất swap được các ngân hàng thương mại áp dụng khi thực hiện giao dịch hoán đổi hai đồng tiền này. Nghiên cứu sâu hơn về giao dịch hoán đổi tiền tệ chéo, Nguyễn Minh Sáng và Nguyễn Thị Hạnh Hoa (2014) đã chỉ ra rằng giao dịch hoán đổi tiền tệ có nhiều lợi ích đối với ngân hàng thương mại như tránh được rủi ro tỷ giá và lãi suất, giúp giảm chi phí vốn. Phạm Thị Hoàng Anh và cộng sự (2020) cũng chỉ ra rằng các giao dịch ngoại bảng, trong đó bao gồm phần thu lãi đến từ giao dịch phái sinh, hay cụ thể hơn là giao dịch swap, có ảnh hưởng tích cực tới nguồn thu ngoài lãi của các ngân hàng thương mại tại Việt Nam.

Theo nghiên cứu của Nguyễn Thành Đạt (2019), lạm phát có ảnh hưởng tích cực rõ ràng đến ROE hay lợi nhuận của các ngân hàng thương mại. Dương Thị Ánh Tiên (2021) chỉ ra lạm phát là một trong những yếu tố có ảnh hưởng tới lợi nhuận ngân hàng. Theo bài nghiên cứu của Phạm Duy Phú Thịnh và cộng sự (2021), lạm phát có tác động cùng chiều đến lợi nhuận ngân hàng được thể hiện bởi chỉ số ROE, tuy nhiên không có ý nghĩa thống kê. Kết quả nghiên cứu của Nguyễn Quốc Anh & Tăng Mỹ Sang (2022), Hồ Thị Lam & Nguyễn Ngọc Hoàng Anh (2022) cũng phát hiện mối quan hệ cùng chiều giữa lạm phát và lợi nhuận của ngân hàng, đồng thời biến lạm phát tại những nghiên cứu này đều có ý nghĩa thống kê.

Đối với mối quan hệ giữa vốn chủ sở hữu và lợi nhuận ngân hàng, nghiên cứu của Phan Thị Hằng Nga (2017) cũng chỉ ra rằng các ngân hàng với vốn hóa đủ lớn sẽ có nhu cầu vay vốn bên ngoài thấp hơn, từ đó chi phí vốn cũng thấp hơn, khiến lợi nhuận của các ngân hàng này cao hơn.

2.3. Khoảng trống nghiên cứu

Có thể thấy rằng, gần như tất cả các công trình nghiên cứu ở cả nước ngoài và trong nước khi lựa chọn các nhân tố phái sinh ảnh hưởng đến kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng đều chưa xét đến lãi suất swap trên thị trường liên ngân hàng, đặc biệt ở Việt Nam mới chỉ có các nghiên cứu chung về ảnh hưởng của giao dịch phái sinh đối với ngân hàng. Cụ thể hơn, tổng quan nghiên cứu tại Việt Nam đang nhấn mạnh hơn vào tầm quan trọng của các công cụ phái sinh đối với việc quản trị rủi ro, chưa tập trung vào khả năng sinh lời của các ngân hàng thương mại, đặc biệt là đối với công cụ phái sinh hoán đổi.

Ngoài ra, hầu hết các công trình nghiên cứu tại Việt Nam trước đó khi xây dựng mô hình các yếu tố tác động đến lợi nhuận hay kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng thương mại chỉ sử dụng lạm phát và tỷ giá hối đoái làm biến kiểm soát và không nghiên cứu sâu cũng như đưa ra các kết luận giải thích cho ảnh hưởng của hai yếu tố này đối với lợi nhuận của ngân hàng. Bên cạnh đó, kết quả các nghiên cứu đi trước là chưa đồng nhất và rõ ràng về mối quan hệ của các yếu tố trên đối với khả năng sinh lời của ngân hàng thương mại. Các biến kiểm soát khác như GDP, quy mô hoạt động, các yếu tố rủi ro sẽ được cân nhắc bổ sung vào các nghiên cứu mở rộng trong tương lai.

3. PHƯƠNG PHÁP NGHIÊN CỨU

3.1. Lựa chọn biến nghiên cứu và thu thập số liệu

Kế thừa từ các nghiên cứu trước đây, các biến sau được lựa chọn nhằm đạt được mục tiêu của nghiên cứu: tỷ suất lợi nhuận sau thuế trên tổng vốn chủ sở hữu (ROE), tổng vốn chủ sở hữu, tỷ lệ lạm phát (đo lường bằng chỉ số giá tiêu dùng – CPI), tỷ giá hối đoái và lãi suất swap tại thị trường liên ngân hàng. Bên cạnh đó, bài viết sử dụng các biến kiểm soát là vốn chủ sở hữu và tỷ lệ lạm phát. Thứ nhất, vốn chủ sở hữu, đại diện cho quy mô hoạt động của ngân hàng, đóng vai trò quan trọng đối với hoạt động kinh doanh của các ngân hàng thương mại. Vốn chủ sở hữu đủ lớn sẽ đảm bảo khả năng trả nợ của ngân hàng đồng thời góp phần giúp ngân hàng phát triển ổn định, cải thiện lợi nhuận và tăng khả năng cạnh tranh của ngân hàng. Tuy nhiên khi vốn chủ sở hữu quá lớn thì chỉ số ROE sẽ giảm, kéo theo lợi nhuận chia cho các cổ đông giảm và giá cổ phiếu có thể đi xuống, ảnh hưởng tới hoạt động kinh doanh của ngân hàng (Huỳnh Thị Hương Thảo và cộng sự, 2021). Thứ hai, lạm phát đã được chứng minh tác động đến khả năng sinh lời của ngân hàng, tuy nhiên mối quan hệ còn phụ thuộc vào việc ban quản trị ngân hàng có thể dự đoán được tỷ lệ lạm phát hay không. Nếu ban quản trị ngân hàng dự đoán chính xác lạm phát và điều chỉnh lãi suất, doanh thu ngân hàng có thể sẽ tăng nhanh hơn chi phí, kéo theo đó là lợi nhuận cũng tăng lên. Do đó, tác động của lạm phát còn phụ thuộc vào sự ổn định của nền kinh tế vĩ mô (Davydenko, 2011). Tại Việt Nam, nhờ vào các chính sách kinh tế vĩ mô đúng đắn nên nền kinh tế vĩ mô những năm gần đây khá ổn định dù Việt Nam phải chịu tác động nặng nề của dịch Covid-19. Tỷ lệ lạm phát luôn được giữ ổn định dưới mức 4%.

Nghiên cứu thu thập dữ liệu theo quý từ các báo cáo tài chính hàng quý của 17 ngân hàng thương mại cổ phần được niêm yết trên sàn chứng khoán HOSE trong khoảng thời gian từ quý 1 năm 2015 đến quý 4 năm 2022. Các dữ liệu được thu thập bao gồm: tổng vốn chủ sở hữu và ROE. Bên cạnh đó, các yếu tố vĩ mô là tỷ lệ lạm phát hàng quý CPI được thu thập từ trang web của Tổng Cục thống kê Việt Nam, tỷ giá hối đoái USD/VND và lãi suất swap tại thị trường liên ngân hàng

được nhóm tác giả tự thu thập trên thị trường liên ngân hàng. Dữ liệu trong nghiên cứu được chia thành dữ liệu bảng (panel data) với dữ liệu chéo theo chuỗi thời gian.

3.2. Mô hình nghiên cứu và giả thuyết nghiên cứu

3.2.1. Mô hình nghiên cứu

Bài khóa luận xây dựng mô hình hồi quy dựa trên các bài nghiên cứu đi trước như sau:

$$LNROE = \beta_0 + \beta_1LNTE + \beta_2LNINF + \beta_3LNEXC + \beta_4LNSWAP + \varepsilon$$

Bảng 1: Mô tả các biến và dấu kỳ vọng của các biến

Biến	Ký hiệu	Giải thích	Dấu kỳ vọng	Bảng chứng từ các nghiên cứu đi trước
Kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng	LNROE	Logarit cơ số tự nhiên của chỉ số lợi nhuận sau thuế trên vốn chủ sở hữu		Moyo và cộng sự (2020), Jackson và cộng sự (2021)
Tổng vốn chủ sở hữu	LNTE	Logarit cơ số tự nhiên của tổng vốn chủ sở hữu	-	Nguyễn Thành Đạt (2019)
Lạm phát	LNINF	Logarit cơ số tự nhiên của chỉ số CPI hàng quý	-	Khan và cộng sự (2014); Moyo và cộng sự (2020)
Tỷ giá hối đoái	LNEXC	Logarit cơ số tự nhiên của tỷ giá hối đoái trung bình quý	+	Lagat & Nyandema (2016)
Lãi suất swap	LNSWAP	Logarit cơ số tự nhiên của lãi suất swap trung bình quý	-	Brewer và cộng sự (1996)

Nghiên cứu sử dụng mô hình tác động cố định (FEM) và mô hình tác động ngẫu nhiên (REM). Điểm khác biệt giữa mô hình REM và mô hình FEM là ở sự biến động giữa các đơn vị. Nếu trong mô hình FEM sự biến động giữa các đơn vị có liên quan đến biến phụ thuộc thì trong mô hình REM sự biến động giữa các đơn vị được coi là ngẫu nhiên và không liên quan đến biến giải thích.

3.2.2. Giả thuyết nghiên cứu

- *Giả thuyết H1: Tổng vốn chủ sở hữu có tác động ngược chiều đến kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng thương mại*

Do nghiên cứu sử dụng biến ROE làm đại diện cho kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng thương mại, mà chỉ số ROE được tính bằng tỷ lệ giữa lợi nhuận sau thuế chia cho tổng vốn chủ sở hữu bình quân của ngân hàng. Do tổng vốn chủ sở hữu nằm ở vị trí mẫu số trong phân số, do đó khi tổng vốn chủ sở hữu tăng sẽ khiến ROE giảm.

- *Giả thuyết H2: Lạm phát có tác động tiêu cực đến kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng thương mại*

Khi lạm phát tăng cao, lãi suất cho vay của các ngân hàng thương mại cũng tăng lên theo dẫn đến các doanh nghiệp khó khăn hơn trong việc trả nợ vay, dẫn đến rủi ro không trả nợ của các doanh nghiệp tăng lên, kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng cũng sẽ bị ảnh hưởng tiêu cực. Đồng thời nếu lạm phát tăng không lường trước được thì các hoạt động đầu tư tài chính của ngân hàng cũng gián tiếp bị tác động

- Giả thuyết H3: Tỷ giá hối đoái tăng thì kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng sẽ tăng

Khi hoạt động nhập khẩu có xu hướng gia tăng, nhu cầu sử dụng đồng ngoại tệ của các doanh nghiệp xuất nhập cũng tăng lên theo, đồng nội tệ suy yếu so với đồng ngoại tệ sẽ khiến các ngân hàng kiếm được lợi nhuận chênh lệch giá từ việc giao dịch cặp ngoại tệ USD/VND trên thị trường liên ngân hàng cũng như với khách hàng. Nhu cầu về USD càng lớn thì lợi nhuận kinh doanh chênh lệch giá càng lớn cho ngân hàng.

- Giả thuyết H4: Lãi suất swap trên thị trường liên ngân hàng có tác động tiêu cực đến kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng thương mại

Khi lãi suất swap tăng cao, chi phí vốn dành cho việc vay VND (thế chấp bằng USD) thông qua các giao dịch swap là lớn. Với chi phí vốn lớn hơn, các ngân hàng sẽ bị tăng thêm các chi phí liên quan đến vốn, dẫn đến việc kinh doanh ở thị trường liên ngân hàng khó khăn hơn và giảm lợi nhuận của các mảng liên quan.

4. KẾT QUẢ NGHIÊN CỨU VÀ THẢO LUẬN

4.1. Thống kê mô tả

Thống kê mô tả các biến nghiên cứu đã sử dụng được trình bày ở bảng 1.

Bảng 2: Thống kê mô tả dữ liệu

Biến nghiên cứu	Số quan sát	Giá trị trung bình	Độ lệch chuẩn	Giá trị nhỏ nhất	Giá trị lớn nhất
LNROE	525	-2,187135	0,9129409	-7,806214	-1,151593
LNTE	542	16,93744	0,816954	15,20911	18,74268
LNINF	544	-3,763715	0,6355253	-5,843045	-2,889572
LNEXC	544	10,03592	0,0243088	9,9698	10,09818
LNSWAP	493	-4,315808	0,8177079	-7,178152	-3,250297

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Biến LNROE của các ngân hàng thương mại trong giai đoạn quý 1 năm 2015 đến quý 4 năm 2022 đạt giá trị trung bình khoảng -2,187, tức là ROE trung bình đạt khoảng 11,23%. Giá trị nhỏ nhất của biến LNROE là -7,806 và giá trị lớn nhất khoảng -1,152. Khoảng cách giữa 2 con số là khá lớn, chứng tỏ có sự phân hóa rõ rệt giữa các ngân hàng. LNTE đạt mức trung bình là 16,94; giá trị nhỏ nhất được ghi nhận là 15,21 và cao nhất là 18,74. Như vậy tổng vốn chủ sở hữu của các ngân hàng thương mại trên sàn HOSE không có sự khác biệt rõ rệt. LNINF có giá trị trung bình là -3,76; hay tức là chỉ số CPI dùng để đo lường biến lạm phát có giá trị trung bình là 2,32%; ghi nhận mức tăng cao nhất là 5,56% và thấp nhất là 0,29%, chênh lệch khá cao. Trung bình của LNEXC đạt 10,036; hay tức là tỷ giá hối đoái USD/VND đạt mức trung bình là 22.834, với giá trị cao nhất là 24.298 và giá trị thấp nhất là 21.371, không có nhiều biến động. Với biến lãi suất swap, trung bình LNSWAP đạt -4,3158 hay lãi suất swap trung bình trong giai đoạn 2016 – 2022 đạt mức 1,36% với giá trị nhỏ nhất là 0,08% và giá trị lớn nhất là 0,08% - chênh lệch khá rõ ràng.

4.2. Các kiểm định đã thực hiện

4.2.1. Ước lượng mô hình hồi quy Pooled OLS, FEM, REM

Bảng 3: Ước lượng mô hình hồi quy Pooled OLS

	SS	df	MS	Số quan sát	475
				Pro>F	0,0000
Hồi quy	137,196098	4	34,2990245	R2	0,3343
Phần dư	273,214401	470	0,581307235	R2 điều chỉnh	0,3286
Tổng	410,410499	474	0,865844934	Độ lệch chuẩn	0,76244
LNROE	Hệ số hồi quy	Độ lệch chuẩn	Thống kê t	P-value	
LNTE	0,4320556	0,0463127	9,33	0,000	
LNINF	-0,05748	0,0634648	-0,91	0,366	
LNEXC	11,95559	1,805643	6,62	0,000	
LNSWAP	-0,0775105	0,0452046	-1,71	0,087	
Hằng số	-130,0875	17,95733	-7,24	0,000	

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Bảng 3 cho thấy kết quả ước lượng Pooled OLS cho thấy hệ số R^2 của mô hình bằng 33,43%. So với các nghiên cứu trước đây thì mức R^2 này được coi là mức trung bình, không quá thấp. Thống kê F có p-value = 0,0000 nên có thể bác bỏ giả thuyết H_0 là các biến độc lập đồng thời bằng 0, hay mô hình có ý nghĩa. Mô hình chỉ có 2 biến độc lập có ý nghĩa ở mức thống kê 5% (có p-value < 0,05) là biến LNTE và LNEXC, trong đó biến LNEXC là biến có tác động mạnh nhất tới kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng thương mại với hệ số hồi quy là 11,95559.

Bảng 4: Ước lượng mô hình tác động ngẫu nhiên REM

LNROE	Hệ số hồi quy	Độ lệch chuẩn	Thống kê z	P > z
LNTE	0,5138569	0,0685092	7,50	0,000
LNINF	-0,04483	0,0558921	-0,80	0,423
LNEXC	11,41294	1,75461	6,50	0,000
LNSWAP	-0,077867	0,0396086	-1,97	0,049
Hằng số	-125,9937	17,10468	-7,37	0,000
Số quan sát		475		
R²		0,3327		
Pro>chi2		0,0000		

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Kết quả R^2 của mô hình REM đạt 33,27% (Bảng 4), khá tương đồng với mức R^2 của mô hình Pooled OLS. Mô hình có pro>chi2 = 0,0000 nên có thể bác bỏ giả thuyết H_0 , nghĩa là mô hình có ý nghĩa và có thể giải thích được ảnh hưởng của các biến lạm phát, tỷ giá hối đoái và lãi suất swap đến kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng. Khác với mô hình Pooled OLS, kết quả

chạy mô hình REM cho thấy mô hình này có 3 biến độc lập có ý nghĩa tại mức thống kê 5% là biến LNTE, LNEXC, LNSWAP. Trong đó biến LNEXC vẫn có ảnh hưởng mạnh nhất đến kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng với hệ số hồi quy bằng 11,41294.

Bảng 5: Ước lượng mô hình tác động cố định FEM

LNROE	Hệ số hồi quy	Độ lệch chuẩn	Thống kê t	P> t
LNTE	0,5886655	0,0866936	6,79	0,000
LNINF	-0,0346679	0,0552103	-0,63	0,530
LNEXC	10,5102	1,880594	5,59	0,000
LNSWAP	-0,0748483	0,0389217	-1,92	0,055
Hằng số	-118,1432	18,07014	-6,54	0,000
Số quan sát		475		
R²		0,3281		
Pro>F		0,0000		

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Kết quả R² của mô hình FEM đạt 32,81% (Bảng 5), tuy thấp hơn so với hai mô hình Pooled OLS và REM trước đó nhưng không chênh lệch quá nhiều. Mô hình FEM có ý nghĩa do có kết quả pro>F = 0,000 < 0,05. Giống với mô hình Pooled OLS, mô hình FEM chỉ có 2 biến LNTE và LNEXC có ý nghĩa thống kê tại mức 5% (p-value < 0,05), trong đó LNEXC vẫn có tác động lớn nhất đến kết quả tài chính của ngân hàng với hệ số hồi quy bằng 10,5102.

4.2.2. Kiểm định lựa chọn mô hình

Bảng 6: Kiểm định Breusch and Pagan LM lựa chọn giữa mô hình Pooled OLS và REM

$$LNROE [BANK1,t] = Xb + u[BANK1] + e[BANK1,t]$$

Kết quả ước tính

	Var	sd = sqrt(Var)
LNROE	0,8658449	0,9305079
e	0,4251977	0,6520718
u	0,0706051	0,2657162
Test: Var(u) = 0		
	Chibar2 (01) = 397,69	
	Pro>chibar2 = 0,0000	

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Kết quả kiểm định từ Bảng 6 cho thấy pro>chibar2 = 0,0000 < 0,05 nên bác bỏ giả thuyết H₀, mô hình được chọn để nghiên cứu là mô hình REM.

Bảng 7: Kiểm định F-test để chọn giữa mô hình Pooled OLS và FEM

LNROE	Hệ số hồi quy	Độ lệch chuẩn	Thống kê t	P> t
LNTE	0,5886655	0,0866936	6,79	0,000
LNINF	-0,0346679	0,0552103	-0,63	0,530
LNEXC	10,5102	1,880594	5,59	0,000
LNSWAP	-0,0748483	0,0389217	-1,92	0,055
Hằng số	-118,1432	18,07014	-6,54	0,000
F test that all u _i =0: F(16,454) = 11,78		Pro>F = 0,0000		

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Bảng 7 cho thấy kết quả kiểm định F-test cho thấy $pro>F = 0,0000 < 0,05$ nên bác bỏ giả thuyết H_0 , hay mô hình Pooled OLS bị bác bỏ và mô hình được chọn để nghiên cứu là mô hình FEM.

Bảng 8: Kiểm định Hausman

$chi2(4) = (b-B) ' [(V_b - V_B)^{-1}] (b-B)$
= 22,93
Pro>chi2 = 0,0001

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Kiểm định Hausman từ bảng 8 đưa ra kết quả $pro>chi2 = 0,0000 < 0,05$, do vậy giả thuyết H_0 bị bác bỏ và mô hình được chọn là mô hình FEM.

Như vậy, kết quả của các kiểm định lựa chọn mô hình trên cho thấy mô hình phù hợp nhất với mục tiêu của bài nghiên cứu là mô hình tác động cố định FEM.

4.2.3. Kiểm định khuyết tật của mô hình

Bảng 9: Kiểm định đa cộng tuyến bằng phương pháp Collin

Biến	VIF	VIF bình phương	Lượng biến thiên	R ²
LNROE	1,50	1,23	0,6657	0,3343
LNTE	1,36	1,17	0,7346	0,2654
LNINF	1,39	1,18	0,7185	0,2815
LNEXC	1,79	1,34	0,5591	0,4409
LNSWAP	1,11	1,05	0,8990	0,1010
Mean VIF	1,43			

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Bảng 10: Ma trận tự tương quan giữa các biến

	LNROE	LNTE	LNINF	LNEXC	LNSWAP
LNROE	1,0000				
LNTE	0,4914	1,0000			
LNINF	0,1437	0,0737	1,0000		
LNEXC	0,4437	0,3402	0,4965	1,0000	
LNSWAP	-0,2021	-0,1425	0,0307	-0,2492	1,0000

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Kết quả từ Bảng 9 và 10 chỉ ra rằng các hệ số tương quan đều có giá trị nhỏ hơn 1, đồng thời hệ số VIF của tất cả các biến sử dụng trong mô hình đều nhỏ hơn 10 nên mô hình không có hiện tượng đa cộng tuyến.

Bảng 11: Kiểm định phương sai sai số thay đổi

$H_0: \sigma^2(i) = \sigma^2(i)$ for all i

$\chi^2(17) = 1446,99$

$Pr > \chi^2 = 0,0000$

Nguồn: Tác giả tính toán dựa trên phần mềm Stata 14

Kết quả kiểm định từ bảng 11 cho thấy $prob > \chi^2 = 0,0000 < 0,05$ nên bác bỏ giả thuyết H_0 . Do đó mô hình mắc lỗi phương sai sai số thay đổi.

Bảng 12: Kiểm định tự tương quan Wooldridge

H_0 : không có tự tương quan bậc nhất

$F(1,16) = 3,353$

$Pr > F = 0,0858$

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Từ bảng 12, kết quả cho thấy $prob > \chi^2 = 0,0858 > 0,05$ nên giả thuyết H_0 không bị bác bỏ. Do đó mô hình không mắc lỗi khuyết tật tự tương quan.

Bảng 13: Kiểm định Pesaran về tính độc lập giữa dữ liệu chéo

Pesaran's test of cross-sectional independence = 3,865

$Pr = 0,0001$

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Bảng 13 về kết quả kiểm định Pesaran cho thấy $Pr = 0,0001 < 0,05$ nên giả thuyết H_0 bị bác bỏ, do đó mô hình bị mắc lỗi các biến dữ liệu chéo phụ thuộc vào nhau.

Như vậy mô hình FEM của nghiên cứu mắc lỗi phương sai sai số thay đổi và dữ liệu chéo phụ thuộc vào nhau.

4.3. Kết quả phân tích hồi quy

Từ kết quả kiểm định ở trên, nghiên cứu sử dụng hàm hồi quy robust để sửa lại những khuyết tật mô hình mắc phải.

Bảng 14: Kết quả mô hình FEM – hồi quy robust

Biến độc lập	Hệ số hồi quy	Độ lệch chuẩn Robust	Thống kê t	$P > t $
LNTE	0,5886655	0,1762148	3,34	0,004
LNINF	-0,0346679	0,0626772	-0,55	0,588
LNEXC	10,5102	2,2694528	3,90	0,001
LNSWAP	-0,0748483	0,0290384	-2,58	0,020

Biến độc lập	Hệ số hồi quy	Độ lệch chuẩn Robust	Thống kê t	P > t
Hàng số	-118,1432	26,89147	-4,39	0,000
Số quan sát		475		
R²		0,3281		
Pro>F		0,0009		

Nguồn: Kết quả từ phần mềm Stata 14

Bảng 14 cho thấy kết quả mô hình hồi quy về mối quan hệ giữa lạm phát, tỷ giá hối đoái và lãi suất swap trên thị trường liên ngân hàng với kết quả tài chính của các ngân hàng thương mại tại Việt Nam trong giai đoạn từ quý 1 năm 2015 đến quý 4 năm 2022.

Nghiên cứu này cũng đưa ra kết luận rằng tỷ giá có ảnh hưởng lớn tới lợi nhuận của các ngân hàng tại Việt Nam, thông qua mô hình FEM, tương tự kết quả đưa ra bởi Osuagwu (2014) và Ali và cộng sự (2018). Sử dụng biến lợi nhuận là ROE, có thể thấy, tỷ giá hối đoái có ảnh hưởng lớn tới biến phụ thuộc trong nghiên cứu này. Thông qua việc nắm bắt thông tin và thực hiện giao dịch ở thị trường liên ngân hàng, cũng như nhu cầu ngoại hối lớn từ các doanh nghiệp xuất nhập khẩu, các ngân hàng tại Việt Nam đã tạo ra được lợi nhuận lớn từ tỷ giá hối đoái. Đặc biệt trong những năm gần đây, Việt Nam nhận được dòng vốn FDI lớn, đồng thời cũng trở thành một trong những công xưởng quan trọng nhất trên thế giới, với một trong những khách hàng chính là Mỹ, tỷ giá USD/ VND đã giúp nhiều ngân hàng đạt được mức lợi nhuận cao. Đặc biệt trong giai đoạn năm 2022, với việc Mỹ tăng lãi suất, đồng Việt Nam mất giá giúp cho nhiều ngân hàng ngoài việc hưởng lợi từ việc bán cho khách hàng, còn tạo thêm được lợi nhuận thông qua giao dịch trên thị trường liên ngân hàng.

Bài nghiên cứu cũng chỉ ra rằng lạm phát không có ảnh hưởng tới lợi nhuận của ngân hàng, khi biến lạm phát không có ý nghĩa trong khoảng tin cậy 95%. Kết quả này trái ngược với nghiên cứu của Saeed (2014) khi tác giả đưa ra kết luận rằng lạm phát tỷ lệ nghịch với lợi nhuận của các ngân hàng tại Anh; Francis (2013) cũng đưa ra kết quả tương tự. Vong & Chan (2009) cũng tìm ra mối liên kết giữa lạm phát và lợi nhuận của ngân hàng tại Macao, nhưng mối quan hệ là tỷ lệ thuận.

Cuối cùng, bài nghiên cứu tìm ra mối quan hệ giữa lãi suất swap ở thị trường liên ngân hàng Việt Nam đối với lạm phát. Tác động của lãi suất này là tỷ lệ nghịch với lợi nhuận của ngân hàng, khi mà lãi suất này càng lớn, các ngân hàng nắm giữ USD càng chịu nhiều chi phí vốn khi nắm giữ đồng tiền này. Trong bối cảnh tỷ giá tăng lên, đặc biệt trong giai đoạn năm 2022, việc nắm giữ USD đem lại lợi nhuận từ việc giao dịch cho ngân hàng, nhưng việc lãi suất swap tăng cao làm cho chi phí vốn tăng theo, dẫn đến lợi nhuận của ngân hàng sụt giảm.

5. KẾT LUẬN

Nghiên cứu này xem xét tác động của các biến lạm phát, tỷ giá hối đoái và lãi suất swap trên thị trường liên ngân hàng đối với kết quả tài chính của các ngân hàng thương mại tại Việt Nam. Kết quả nghiên cứu cho thấy tỷ giá và lãi suất swap ở thị trường liên ngân hàng có ảnh hưởng lớn tới kết quả tài chính của các ngân hàng tại Việt Nam. Đặc biệt, kết quả này có ý nghĩa quan trọng hơn nữa khi số lượng nghiên cứu về sự ảnh hưởng của các công cụ phái sinh tới kết quả hoạt động ngân hàng còn hạn chế. Ngược lại biến lạm phát không có tác động gì tới lợi nhuận của ngân hàng, khi biến lạm phát không có ý nghĩa trong khoảng tin cậy 95%.

Việt Nam cần duy trì môi trường thể chế và nền kinh tế vĩ mô ổn định, nâng cao chất lượng hoạt động các cấp chính quyền đồng thời cũng hoàn thiện hơn nữa các chính sách đối với lạm phát và tỷ giá hối đoái. Việc môi trường kinh tế và xã hội, chính trị ổn định cũng góp phần giúp các ngân hàng hoạt động hiệu quả hơn, nâng kết quả tài chính của các ngân hàng lên do khi môi trường ổn định, các doanh nghiệp sẽ kinh doanh tốt hơn và khả năng trả nợ cho ngân hàng cũng cao hơn.

Đồng thời do thị trường phái sinh tại Việt Nam vẫn đang ở bước đầu phát triển nên Việt Nam cần thành lập thêm các sàn giao dịch phái sinh (cả hợp đồng và hàng hóa phái sinh), phát triển và hoàn thiện các quy định và luật về các sản phẩm phái sinh để tạo điều kiện thuận lợi cho thị trường phái sinh phát triển hơn.

Bên cạnh các chính sách đối với lạm phát, tỷ giá hối đoái và thị trường phái sinh, chính sách điều tiết thị trường bất động sản, thị trường chứng khoán cũng cần được nâng cao chất lượng hơn vì đây là các thị trường quan trọng, ảnh hưởng rất lớn đến nền kinh tế Việt Nam nói chung. Ổn định được các thị trường này thì nền kinh tế cũng sẽ ổn định, tạo môi trường thuận lợi cho các ngân hàng hoạt động.

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KHUÔN KHỔ QUẢN LÝ TỔ CHỨC PHÁT HÀNH TIỀN ĐIỆN TỬ PHI NGÂN HÀNG - KINH NGHIỆM TỪ CÁC NƯỚC VÀ CÁC VẤN ĐỀ RÚT RA

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Tóm tắt

Những cải tiến trong công nghệ, cùng với nhu cầu ngày càng tăng đối với các phương thức thanh toán kỹ thuật số, đang ngày càng định hình lại cách thức thanh toán được thực hiện. Trong khi không gian thanh toán tiếp tục bị chi phối bởi các ngân hàng ở nhiều quốc gia, thì vai trò của các tổ chức cung ứng dịch vụ thanh toán phi ngân hàng (NBSP) vận hành nhiều mô hình kinh doanh khác nhau đang trở nên nổi bật. Các tổ chức phi ngân hàng có thể cung cấp nhiều loại hình dịch vụ thanh toán ở hầu hết các khu vực pháp lý. Trong đó, cung cấp tài khoản tiền điện tử là một trong những dịch vụ là phổ biến nhất. Sự phổ biến này đã đặt ra câu hỏi về quy định tại đây. Tại Việt Nam, các sản phẩm tiền điện tử đã tồn tại dưới các hình thức thẻ trả trước ngân hàng, các sản phẩm ví điện tử, và gần đây mới bắt đầu triển khai thí điểm dịch vụ tiền di động (mobile money). So với các nước, tiền điện tử ở Việt Nam chưa có lịch sử lâu dài, vì vậy, các khuôn khổ pháp lý cho lĩnh vực này mặc dù đã hình thành nhưng vẫn cần tiếp tục hoàn thiện. Bài viết này đi vào tìm hiểu các vấn đề cốt lõi trong một khuôn khổ quản lý tiền điện tử, cách thức mà các quốc gia trên thế giới đã giải quyết các vấn đề này để rút ra các tổng kết và kinh nghiệm quan trọng.

Từ khóa: tiền điện tử, khuôn khổ pháp lý, kinh nghiệm quốc tế, kỹ thuật số, công nghệ.

REGULATION FRAMEWORK FOR NON-BANK E-MONEY ISSUERS - EXPERIENCE FROM COUNTRIES AND IMPLICATIONS

Abstract

Improvements in technology, coupled with growing demand for digital payment methods, are increasingly reshaping the way payments are made. While the payments space continues to be dominated by banks in many countries, the role of non-bank payment service providers (NBSPs) operating a variety of business models is evolving. Non-banks can provide a variety of payment services in most jurisdictions. Among them, providing electronic money (e-money) accounts and processing of electronic funds/value transfer to third parties is the most common. This popularity has raised questions about regulation here. In Vietnam, electronic money products already exist in the form of prepaid bank cards, e-wallet products, and recently piloting mobile money services. Compared to other countries, e-money in Vietnam have not had a long history, so the legal framework for this field, although already formed, still needs to continue to be improved. This article explores the core issues in a e-money regulation framework, how countries around the world have addressed these issues to draw important conclusions and experiences.

Keywords: e-money, regulatory framework, international experience, digital, technology.

I. GIỚI THIỆU

Những cải tiến trong công nghệ, cùng với nhu cầu ngày càng tăng đối với các phương thức thanh toán kỹ thuật số, đang ngày càng định hình lại cách thức thanh toán được thực hiện. Những tiến bộ gần đây trong công nghệ đã mở ra những phương thức thanh toán mới, phù hợp với nhu cầu của người tiêu dùng về các phương thức thanh toán thuận tiện, dễ sử dụng, liên tục, chi phí thấp và phi tiếp xúc.² Do đó, người tiêu dùng đã chuyển từ dùng tiền mặt sang phương tiện thanh toán không dùng tiền mặt trong những năm gần đây. Theo Johannes Ehrentraud và cộng sự (2021), trong năm 2012, số lượng thanh toán kỹ thuật số trung bình trong các khu vực pháp lý CPMI là 176 trên mỗi người dân; vào năm 2019, con số này là 303. Sự thay đổi tương tự trong các kênh dịch vụ đã diễn ra ở các nền kinh tế tiên tiến (AE). Trong khi số lượng chi nhánh ngân hàng và máy rút tiền tự động (ATM) giảm, thiết bị đầu cuối điểm bán hàng (POS) và các ứng dụng thanh toán đã trở nên phổ biến hơn. Đại dịch Covid-19 đã đẩy nhanh hơn nữa xu hướng thanh toán kỹ thuật số. Để tránh tiếp xúc vật lý với bề mặt hoặc đồ vật có khả năng bị nhiễm bẩn, nhiều người đã chọn phương thức thanh toán không tiếp xúc, hoạt động bằng cách vẫy thẻ hoặc điện thoại.³ Ngoài ra, yêu cầu ở yên tại chỗ và các hạn chế khác đã khiến nhiều khách hàng phải chuyển từ mua sắm tại các cửa hàng truyền thống sang các nền tảng trực tuyến, vốn luôn được hỗ trợ bởi thanh toán kỹ thuật số.

Trong khi không gian thanh toán tiếp tục bị chi phối bởi các ngân hàng ở nhiều quốc gia, thì vai trò của các nhà cung cấp dịch vụ thanh toán phi ngân hàng (NBSP) vận hành nhiều mô hình kinh doanh khác nhau đang trở nên nổi bật. Theo Johannes Ehrentraud và cộng sự (2021), cung cấp tài khoản tiền điện tử (tức là phát hành tiền điện tử) là một trong những dịch vụ thanh toán phổ biến nhất mà các tổ chức phi ngân hàng có thể cung cấp. Tầm quan trọng ngày càng tăng của các NBSP dựa trên công nghệ tài chính mang đến các cơ hội. Bên cạnh việc thúc đẩy tài chính toàn diện, chúng cũng có thể tăng cường cạnh tranh và hiệu quả trong thị trường thanh toán. Tuy nhiên, điều này đi kèm với những rủi ro tiềm ẩn về bảo vệ người tiêu dùng, khả năng phục hồi hoạt động và không gian mạng, bảo vệ tiền trong quá trình vận chuyển hoặc lưu trữ, bảo vệ dữ liệu, loại trừ kỹ thuật số và tập trung thị trường. Do đó, các nhà chức trách tại các nước và các tổ chức quốc tế vẫn đang đánh giá liệu các khung pháp lý hiện tại có đầy đủ hay không.

Tại Việt Nam, các sản phẩm tiền điện tử đã tồn tại dưới các hình thức thẻ trả trước ngân hàng, các sản phẩm ví điện tử, và gần đây mới bắt đầu triển khai thí điểm dịch vụ tiền di động (mobile money). So với các nước, tiền điện tử ở Việt Nam chưa có lịch sử lâu dài, vì vậy, các khuôn khổ pháp lý cho lĩnh vực này mặc dù đã hình thành nhưng vẫn còn ở các bước đầu xây dựng, thí điểm và điều chỉnh, hoàn thiện. Các quy định này nằm trong các văn bản khác nhau đối với từng loại hình sản phẩm như các quy định về thẻ ngân hàng (đối với thẻ trả trước), quy định về dịch vụ trung gian thanh toán (đối với ví điện tử) và mới quyết định thí điểm thực hiện (đối với tiền di động). Để phù hợp với xu hướng phát triển chung của tiền điện tử trên thế giới, xu thế số hóa nền kinh tế trong đó có việc đẩy mạnh thanh toán không dùng tiền mặt và góp phần thực hiện chiến lược tài chính toàn diện quốc gia, việc nghiên cứu, ban hành các quy định

² Ví dụ: ví điện tử (electronic - wallet) cho phép người tiêu dùng sử dụng thiết bị cá nhân của họ để thực hiện thanh toán trực tuyến và tại điểm bán hàng. Các ví dụ bao gồm Apple Pay, Google Pay, Samsung Pay và PayPal.

³ Mặc dù các giao dịch trên các ngưỡng nhất định yêu cầu chữ ký hoặc mục nhập mã PIN trên thiết bị do người bán sở hữu, nhưng nhiều quốc gia đã tăng các giới hạn này để tăng phạm vi cho các khoản thanh toán không tiếp xúc thực sự.

liên quan đến tiền điện tử để tạo hành lang pháp lý cho loại hình sản phẩm này tồn tại và phát triển tại Việt Nam vẫn liên tục được quan tâm. Cụ thể, NHNN cũng lên kế hoạch hoàn thiện việc xây dựng, ban hành Nghị định thay thế Nghị định số 101/2012/NĐ-CP ngày 22/11/2012 về thanh toán không dùng tiền mặt, trong đó có bổ sung vấn đề về tiền điện tử. Đặc biệt, NHNN cũng sẽ rà soát, đề xuất sửa đổi, bổ sung một số điều khoản liên quan đến thanh toán tại một số văn bản Luật hiện hành; Nghiên cứu xây dựng Dự án Luật các hệ thống thanh toán, đảm bảo tương thích, phù hợp với quy định tại Luật Ngân hàng Nhà nước, Luật Các TCTD, Luật phòng, chống rửa tiền và đảm bảo thẩm quyền quản lý, giám sát của NHNN đối với các hệ thống thanh toán, các dịch vụ và phương tiện thanh toán, phù hợp với yêu cầu thực tiễn, xu hướng phát triển và thông lệ quốc tế.

Chính vì vậy, bài viết này muốn đi vào khám phá cách thức các nhà cung cấp dịch vụ thanh toán phi ngân hàng mà cụ thể là tiền điện tử được quản lý, các vấn đề còn đang tồn tại để có thể có một bức tranh tổng quan về khuôn khổ pháp lý trong lĩnh vực này trên thế giới hiện nay, từ đó có những đề xuất, tổng kết quan trọng cho Việt Nam. Mục tiêu nghiên cứu là tìm hiểu các vấn đề cốt lõi trong một khuôn khổ quản lý tiền điện tử, các quốc gia trên thế giới đã giải quyết các vấn đề này như thế nào trong khung pháp lý của mình và từ đó rút ra các kinh nghiệm quan trọng.

Theo đó, bài viết này sẽ bao gồm các nội dung chính như sau:

- Tổng quan về khuôn khổ quản lý đối tiền điện tử: phần này sẽ chỉ ra những nghiên cứu hiện nay về các vấn đề cốt lõi trong việc quản lý tiền điện tử để làm cơ sở cho việc tìm hiểu chi tiết các kinh nghiệm thực tiễn ở phần tiếp theo.

- Khung khổ quản lý tiền điện tử đối với các tổ chức phi ngân hàng – kinh nghiệm thực tiễn từ các nước: phần này sẽ đi vào tìm hiểu từng vấn đề cốt lõi trong phần trên được xử lý thực tế như thế nào tại các quốc gia, có những điểm gì chung và riêng giữa các nước và còn vấn đề gì đang tồn tại cần tiếp tục phải xử lý.

- Kết luận: phần này rút ra những kinh nghiệm quan trọng trong việc xây dựng khuôn khổ quản lý tiền điện tử cho các nước đi sau, các nước đang tìm cách hoàn thiện cũng như xây dựng hệ thống quy định của mình, trong đó có Việt Nam.

2. TỔNG QUAN VỀ KHUNG KHỔ QUẢN LÝ TIỀN ĐIỆN TỬ

Hiện nay, tiền điện tử chủ yếu được sử dụng trong hoạt động thanh toán vì vậy thường được nhìn nhận quản lý dưới góc độ là một trong các sản phẩm/dịch vụ thanh toán. Tuy nhiên, tiền điện tử không chỉ được sử dụng trong thanh toán, mà ở một số khu vực pháp lý, bắt đầu được sử dụng cho các dịch vụ khác như tín dụng, bảo hiểm... Vì vậy, cũng cần thiết phải xem xét đến một khuôn khổ bao trùm hơn đối với tiền điện tử là khuôn khổ quản lý đối với các dịch vụ tài chính kỹ thuật số (DFS). Theo đó, để vừa đảm bảo tính bao quát, vừa đảm bảo tính đặc thù của loại hình dịch vụ, để tổng hợp khuôn khổ quản lý tiền điện tử, bài viết này trước hết tìm hiểu các vấn đề chung trong quản lý các dịch vụ tài chính số; sau đó đi vào khuôn khổ quản lý các dịch vụ thanh toán kỹ thuật số, trong đó đi sâu vào các vấn đề liên quan đến tiền điện tử.

2.1. Khuôn khổ điều tiết các dịch vụ tài chính kỹ thuật số

Các dịch vụ tài chính kỹ thuật số (DFS) khác với các dịch vụ tài chính truyền thống ở một số phương thức ý nghĩa quan trọng đối với các cơ quan quản lý. Công nghệ này cho phép các mô hình hoạt động mới có sự tham gia của nhiều bên tham gia hơn trong chuỗi dịch vụ tài chính, từ thiết kế đến giao hàng. Sự ra đời của DFS mở ra các nhà cung cấp mới như tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử phi ngân hàng (EMI), tạo ra vai trò quan trọng cho các đại lý trong việc phục vụ khách hàng và tiếp cận những khách hàng đã bị loại trừ hoặc không được phục vụ. Điều này lại mang đến những rủi ro mới và những cách thức mới để giảm thiểu chúng.

Theo CGAP, dịch vụ tài chính kỹ thuật số (DFS), là một loạt các dịch vụ tài chính được truy cập thông qua các thiết bị kỹ thuật số và được phân phối qua các kênh kỹ thuật số, bao gồm thanh toán, tín dụng, tiết kiệm và chuyển tiền.⁴ DFS có thể được cung cấp bởi các ngân hàng và các tổ chức phi ngân hàng như nhà khai thác mạng di động (MNO) hoặc các công ty công nghệ cung cấp chuyên về dịch vụ tài chính (FinTechs).⁵ Các kênh kỹ thuật số có thể là điện thoại di động, thẻ kết hợp với đầu đọc thẻ, máy ATM, máy tính kết nối internet, v.v. Khách hàng giao dịch không chỉ thông qua các chi nhánh, mà còn thông qua các đại lý hoặc từ xa từ các thiết bị kỹ thuật số của họ. Họ thường sử dụng các tài khoản giao dịch cơ bản nhằm vào thị trường đại chúng (bao gồm tài khoản tiền điện tử, còn được gọi là tài khoản trả trước hoặc tài khoản có giá trị lưu trữ), nhưng cũng truy cập các dịch vụ qua quầy (OTC).⁶

Trong nhiều năm nay, CGAP đã theo dõi cách các mô hình DFS mới được quản lý và cách mà các quy định có thể phải điều chỉnh để hỗ trợ hoặc cho phép các mô hình DFS có tiềm năng thúc đẩy tài chính toàn diện. Năm 2007, CGAP đã phát triển một danh sách “các chủ đề chính trong việc điều tiết hoạt động ngân hàng không chi nhánh” (Lyman et al. 2008). Bốn trong số các chủ đề này hiện được coi là các khối xây dựng cốt lõi của quy định DFS bao gồm: (i) Phát hành tiền điện tử phi ngân hàng; (ii) Sử dụng Đại lý; (iii) Thẩm định khách hàng dựa trên rủi ro; (iv) Bảo vệ người tiêu dùng. 4 yếu tố này được hình thành nhất quán trong kinh nghiệm của CGAP khi làm việc trên các khung DFS và tầm quan trọng của chúng được nhấn mạnh trong các cuộc thảo luận về chính sách và nghiên cứu. Các cấu phần chính trong 4 yếu tố này được CGAP chỉ ra như sau (Xem Stephan Staschen và Patrick Meagher (2018)):

2.1.1. Yếu tố hỗ trợ 1: Phát hành tiền điện tử phi ngân hàng

Công cụ hỗ trợ quy định cơ bản đầu tiên của CGAP là một khuôn khổ cho phép các tổ chức phi ngân hàng phát hành một loại tài khoản giao dịch cơ bản (kỹ thuật số)—một “tài khoản tiền điện tử”. Việc cho phép các tổ chức phi ngân hàng trở thành EMI được cấp phép là chìa khóa để giải phóng thị trường DFS và cho phép nó đạt được tính quy mô. Đứng đầu trong số các nhà cung cấp dịch vụ phi ngân hàng tại các thị trường mới nổi và nền kinh tế đang phát triển (EMDE) là các MNO, có mạng lưới đại lý rộng lớn và sở hữu cơ sở hạ tầng truyền thông là chìa khóa để cung cấp các dịch vụ tài chính. Nếu không có khuôn khổ cho phép EMI, DFS

⁴ Xem, ví dụ, bảng thuật ngữ AFI (AFI 2016). Chúng tôi không thảo luận các vấn đề cụ thể trong việc cung cấp các sản phẩm bảo hiểm kỹ thuật số.

⁵ Chúng tôi sử dụng thuật ngữ “ngân hàng” để chỉ bất kỳ loại tổ chức tài chính nhận tiền gửi được quản lý thận trọng nào trừ khi có quy định khác.

⁶ So sánh một định nghĩa tương tự về tài khoản DFS trong Arabehty et al. (2016). Định nghĩa về tài khoản giao dịch của chúng tôi phù hợp với định nghĩa trong Báo cáo PAFI (CPMI và Nhóm Ngân hàng Thế giới 2016): “Tài khoản giao dịch được định nghĩa là tài khoản (bao gồm tài khoản tiền điện tử/tài khoản trả trước) được giữ tại ngân hàng hoặc PSP được cho phép và/hoặc quản lý có thể được sử dụng để thực hiện và nhận thanh toán cũng như lưu trữ giá trị.”

sẽ tiếp tục dựa vào các ngân hàng, vốn thường phải đối mặt với các yêu cầu vận hành và thận trọng nặng nề, có chi phí cao, cơ cấu tổ chức và hệ thống CNTT phức tạp cũng như khả năng tiếp cận hạn chế. Các ngân hàng cũng có thể tập trung vào các phân khúc thị trường có thu nhập cao hơn để bù đắp chi phí hoạt động cao.

Sau đây là các thành phần thiết yếu của yếu tố hỗ trợ đầu tiên:

- Thiết lập các thông số cơ bản cho tài khoản tiền điện tử và EMI.
- Thiết lập tiêu chí cấp phép và phạm vi hoạt động được phép cho EMI.
- Bảo vệ tiền của khách hàng được chuyển đổi thành tiền điện tử (tức là, e-float).

2.1.2. Yếu tố hỗ trợ 2. Sử dụng Đại lý

DFS phụ thuộc vào khả năng của nhà cung cấp trong việc thuê ngoài các chức năng hướng tới khách hàng cho các đại lý—do đó mở rộng phạm vi tiếp cận và nâng cao hiệu quả của họ. Các kênh dịch vụ truyền thống, đặc biệt là các chi nhánh “truyền thống”, không thể giải quyết vấn đề phân phối một cách hiệu quả về mặt chi phí. Lý tưởng nhất là toàn bộ các nhà cung cấp—ngân hàng và phi ngân hàng chẳng hạn như EMI—nên được phép phân phối sản phẩm và dịch vụ của họ với giá rẻ thông qua nhiều loại đại lý. Nhưng điều này làm tăng rủi ro đại lý có thể ảnh hưởng đến khách hàng hoặc nhà cung cấp. Một sự cân bằng phải được thực hiện giữa toàn diện và an toàn.

Yếu tố hỗ trợ thứ hai bao gồm các khía cạnh quan trọng sau đây:

- Thiết lập một khuôn khổ cơ bản cho việc sử dụng các đại lý trong DFS, trong đó trách nhiệm của các đại lý và bên ủy thác được phân định rõ ràng.
- Quy định các tiêu chí về hình thức và nội dung của hợp đồng đại lý, bao gồm loại hình và phạm vi đại lý.
- Quy định tiêu chuẩn về tư cách và thủ tục ủy quyền đại lý.
- Cung cấp các nghĩa vụ liên tục của cả hai bên, bao gồm các tiêu chuẩn bảo mật và báo cáo.

2.1.3. Yếu tố hỗ trợ 3. Thẩm định khách hàng dựa trên rủi ro

DFS hoạt động trong bối cảnh quy định được định hình bởi các chính sách về AML/CFT. Thách thức đối với tài chính toàn diện là đảm bảo xử lý tương xứng bằng cách sử dụng các khuôn khổ dựa trên rủi ro để bảo vệ tính toàn vẹn của hệ thống trong khi tạo ra ít gánh nặng nhất đối với việc tiếp cận DFS.

Các thành phần thiết yếu của công cụ hỗ trợ thứ ba bao gồm:

- Áp dụng nguyên tắc CDD đơn giản hóa trong các tình huống rủi ro thấp hơn.
- Chuyển nguyên tắc này thành các cấp dựa trên rủi ro cho các loại tài khoản, giao dịch, khách hàng và phương thức mở và giao dịch tài khoản (từ xa hoặc trực tiếp).
- Giải quyết các hạn chế đối với tài liệu nhận dạng khách hàng bằng cách nhận dạng nhiều loại ID hơn và sử dụng các phương pháp nhận dạng mới cho các giao dịch có

rủi ro thấp hơn, có thể thực hiện được nhờ những tiến bộ trong hệ thống ID (phạm vi rộng hơn, khả năng truy cập tốt hơn).

2.1.4. Yếu tố Hỗ trợ 4: Bảo vệ người sử dụng

Bảo vệ người tiêu dùng (FCP) hiệu quả là chìa khóa tạo nên uy tín của DFS với tư cách là trụ cột của tài chính toàn diện. Bất kể FCP có phải được áp dụng đầy đủ trước khi DFS có thể lan rộng hay không, đây là một thành phần cần thiết trong một thị trường bền vững, được quản lý tốt.

Các thành phần thiết yếu của yếu tố hỗ trợ thứ tư bao gồm:

- Các quy tắc bảo vệ người tiêu dùng nhất quán, toàn diện, có mục tiêu cho DFS. Thông thường, chỉ tồn tại các quy tắc chung hoặc chấp vá mà không có sự thích ứng rõ ràng với các nhu cầu của DFS.
- Các quy tắc về tính minh bạch và ứng xử thị trường trong giao dịch của nhà cung cấp—và đại lý của họ—với khách hàng.
- Yêu cầu đối với nhà cung cấp để thiết lập hệ thống xử lý khiếu nại của khách hàng.
- Các tiêu chuẩn về tính khả dụng của dịch vụ và/hoặc độ tin cậy của nền tảng kỹ thuật số giúp cân bằng giữa việc bảo vệ khách hàng và tính không hủy ngang của giao dịch.

Theo Stephan Staschen và Patrick Meagher (2018), mặc dù có sự đồng thuận lớn về 4 yếu tố hỗ trợ cần thiết nêu trên trong khuôn khổ pháp lý điều chỉnh DFS, tuy nhiên, điều này không phủ nhận rằng DFS đã xuất hiện ở một số thị trường nơi một hoặc nhiều yếu tố hỗ trợ còn yếu hoặc thiếu, cũng như các yếu tố hỗ trợ khác, chẳng hạn như cạnh tranh lành mạnh hoặc khả năng tương tác, có thể quan trọng không kém trong một số bối cảnh. Nhưng kinh nghiệm cho thấy rõ ràng rằng, trong bất kỳ thị trường nhất định nào, DFS có nhiều khả năng phát triển một cách có trách nhiệm và bền vững với toàn bộ tiềm năng của nó khi cả bốn yếu tố đều sẵn sàng.

2.2. Khuôn khổ điều tiết các dịch vụ thanh toán kỹ thuật số do tổ chức phi ngân hàng cung cấp

Johannes Ehrentraud và cộng sự (2021) tận dụng các câu trả lời cho cuộc khảo sát CPMI về 75 khu vực pháp lý được thực hiện vào đầu năm 2021 và được bổ sung bằng việc nghiên cứu các tài liệu công khai do các cơ quan được chọn ban hành. Cuộc khảo sát đã hỏi liệu các dịch vụ thanh toán do các tổ chức phi ngân hàng cung cấp có tuân theo các yêu cầu quản lý và các yêu cầu giám sát khác hay không. Mười ba loại yêu cầu đã được đưa vào cuộc khảo sát: cấp phép; sự đăng ký; yêu cầu về vốn; tiền gửi bảo đảm tại các ngân hàng trung ương; hạn chế quyền sở hữu; quan hệ đối tác bắt buộc với các ngân hàng; bảo vệ tiền của khách hàng; quản lý rủi ro; an ninh mạng; phòng chống rửa tiền (AML); sự bảo vệ người tiêu dùng; bảo vệ dữ liệu; và khả năng tương tác.

Theo Johannes Ehrentraud và cộng sự (2021), trong số các dịch vụ thanh toán mà NBPS có thể cung cấp, việc phát hành tiền điện tử hiện được quy định chặt chẽ nhất, trong khi việc cung cấp các dịch vụ tài sản ảo là ít nhất. *Khung pháp lý cho thanh toán kỹ thuật số và tiền điện tử nhìn chung là tương tự nhau nhưng vẫn có những khác biệt nổi bật.* Khi có sự khác

biệt trong khuôn khổ cho tiền điện tử và dịch vụ thanh toán kỹ thuật số, các tổ chức tiền điện tử hầu như luôn phải tuân theo các yêu cầu mở rộng hơn. Điều này là do các dịch vụ thanh toán kỹ thuật số thường đề cập đến việc hỗ trợ kỹ thuật số và chuyển tiền, trong khi các dịch vụ tiền điện tử hoạt động nhiều hơn như các phương tiện giá trị được lưu trữ và do đó có thể được coi là các hoạt động “giống như ngân hàng” hơn. Tập trung vào tiền điện tử, có thể khai thác từ kết quả khảo sát và nghiên cứu bổ sung tại bàn của Johannes Ehrentraud và cộng sự (2021) các yêu cầu/quy định cốt lõi như sau:

2.2.1. Cấp phép/đăng ký

Hầu như tất cả các khu vực pháp lý mà các tổ chức phi ngân hàng có thể phát hành tiền điện tử đều yêu cầu cấp phép và/hoặc đăng ký, và có các mô hình cấp phép cụ thể cho mục đích này. Ở một số khu vực pháp lý, chỉ các ngân hàng mới được phép phát hành tiền điện tử (ví dụ: Nam Phi). Điều này là do việc phát hành tiền điện tử và chấp nhận đổi lại tiền mặt có thể được hiểu một cách hợp pháp là hoạt động nhận tiền gửi tại các khu vực pháp lý này. Hai loại mô hình cấp phép được sử dụng trong các khu vực pháp lý cho phép các tổ chức phi ngân hàng phát hành tiền điện tử: mô hình ngân hàng hẹp và mô hình phi ngân hàng. Theo mô hình ngân hàng hẹp, các tổ chức phi ngân hàng có thể xin giấy phép ngân hàng hạn chế (ví dụ: giấy phép ngân hàng thanh toán) cho phép họ cung cấp một số dịch vụ ngân hàng hạn chế. Mô hình phi ngân hàng cho phép các loại tổ chức phi ngân hàng cụ thể phát hành tiền điện tử (ví dụ: tổ chức tiền điện tử, tổ chức phát hành công cụ trả trước hoặc tổ chức phát hành giá trị được lưu trữ).

2.2.2. Vốn tối thiểu

Hầu hết các khu vực pháp lý đều có các yêu cầu về vốn ban đầu và liên tục đối với các tổ chức phi ngân hàng cung cấp dịch vụ thanh toán. Đối với các tổ chức phi ngân hàng phát hành tiền điện tử, các yêu cầu về vốn liên tục thường được đặt theo tỷ lệ phần trăm của tiền điện tử đã phát hành (e-money float).

2.2.3. Bảo vệ quỹ và các yêu cầu bảo mật khác

Bảo vệ tiền là một yêu cầu rất phổ biến đối với các tổ chức phi ngân hàng cung cấp dịch vụ thanh toán liên quan đến việc xử lý các khoản tiền đó. Nó được yêu cầu ở hầu hết các khu vực pháp lý nơi các tổ chức phi ngân hàng có thể phát hành tiền điện tử. Các phương pháp bảo vệ tài sản hỗ trợ cho các truy đòi tiền điện tử (tài sản dự trữ) nhằm bảo vệ khách hàng khỏi rủi ro EMI có thể không có đủ tiền để trả lại cho họ hoặc rủi ro mất khả năng thanh toán của EMI. Rủi ro “còn lại” vẫn có thể phát sinh ngay cả khi sử dụng các phương pháp bảo vệ an toàn, nhưng những rủi ro này được giảm thiểu bằng bảo hiểm tiền gửi ở một số quốc gia.

Ngoài ra, *các yêu cầu về AML/CFT, quản lý rủi ro và an ninh mạng; bảo vệ dữ liệu; và bảo vệ người tiêu dùng cũng được áp dụng lên tiền điện tử theo cách thống nhất với các dịch vụ thanh toán kỹ thuật số khác.*

Như vậy, từ 2 khuôn khổ quản lý nói trên, có thể rút ra các yếu tố quan trọng cần phải có trong một khuôn khổ quản lý tiền điện tử gồm:

(i) Các quy định về cấp phép bao gồm:

- Khái niệm tiền điện tử

- Các tổ chức được cho phép phát hành tiền điện tử - các mô hình cấp phép:
- Yêu cầu cấp phép, hoạt động được phép và báo cáo (Đối với các mô hình cấp phép phát hành tiền điện tử phi ngân hàng)
 - + Yêu cầu về vốn
 - + Phạm vi hoạt động
 - + Báo cáo và tiếp cận dữ liệu
- (ii) Các quy định bảo vệ tiền của khách hàng
- (iii) Các quy định về sử dụng đại lý
- (iv) Các quy định thẩm định khách hàng được định hình bởi các quy định về AML/CFT
- (v) Các quy định về bảo vệ người tiêu dùng

Trong đó, các quy định về sử dụng đại lý, AML/CFT, và bảo vệ người tiêu dùng thường được quy định chung thống nhất trong các văn bản quy định chung cho dịch vụ thanh toán. Vì vậy, bài nghiên cứu sẽ tập trung vào 02 nhóm quy định đầu tiên và tìm hiểu xem 02 vấn đề này được xử lý ra sao ở các quốc gia.

3. CÁC QUY ĐỊNH CỤ THỂ QUẢN LÝ TIỀN ĐIỆN TỬ – KINH NGHIỆM THỰC TIỄN TỪ CÁC NƯỚC

3.1. Các quy định liên quan đến cấp phép phát hành tiền điện tử

3.1.1. Khái niệm tiền điện tử

Bước đầu tiên trong việc cho phép phát hành tiền điện tử phi ngân hàng là đưa khái niệm này vào luật hoặc quy định.⁷ Luật ngân hàng đôi khi là rào cản đối với việc phát hành tiền điện tử phi ngân hàng, do định nghĩa pháp lý về kinh doanh ngân hàng; do đó, một định nghĩa chuyên biệt về tiền điện tử khác biệt với hoạt động nhận tiền gửi là cần thiết.⁸

Ở các quốc gia/khu vực pháp lý khác nhau, tiền điện tử được định nghĩa về mặt pháp lý khác nhau, thậm chí được gọi dưới các tên gọi khác nhau, tuy nhiên, nhìn chung, đều thống nhất ở các đặc tính nhất định (xem Hộp 1). Tiền điện tử có thể được định nghĩa là giá trị tiền tệ được lưu trữ hoặc các sản phẩm trả trước ở đó một bản ghi nhớ về các khoản tiền hay giá trị có sẵn cho người tiêu dùng để sử dụng đa mục đích được lưu trữ trên một thẻ trả trước hoặc một thiết bị điện tử (ví dụ, một máy tính hoặc điện thoại di động), và được chấp nhận như một công cụ thanh toán bởi những người không phải là tổ chức phát hành (sử dụng đa mục đích). Các giá trị lưu trữ thể hiện quyền truy đòi bắt buộc đơn vị cung ứng tiền điện tử hoàn trả lại số dư đầy đủ theo yêu cầu. Khả năng có thể được hoàn trả lại này phân biệt tiền điện tử với các loại thẻ quà tặng bán lẻ và các công cụ thanh toán khác chỉ được sử dụng với một nhóm bán lẻ (đơn

⁷ Trong một số trường hợp, các cơ quan tài chính đã cho phép phát hành tiền điện tử mà không xác định khái niệm này trong luật (thay vào đó, ban hành hướng dẫn hoặc thư không phân đối).

⁸ Ở một số quốc gia, việc chấp nhận các khoản tiền có thể hoàn trả (ngay cả khi không làm trung gian) phù hợp với định nghĩa pháp lý về hoạt động ngân hàng, điều này ngăn cản sự xuất hiện của EMI. Đây là trường hợp ở Mexico cho đến khi luật FinTech được thông qua vào tháng 2 năm 2018.

mục đích)⁹. Tiền điện tử cũng cần phân biệt với “hoạt động ngân hàng di động” (mobile banking), đây là thuật ngữ được áp dụng cho việc cung ứng dịch vụ thanh toán và các dịch vụ khác bởi ngân hàng thông qua điện thoại hoặc internet.

Đồng thời, cần lưu ý rằng với các đặc tính này, không phải quốc gia nào cũng sử dụng thuật ngữ “tiền điện tử”. Cụ thể, các sản phẩm có các đặc tính này ở Singapore được gọi là “phương tiện lưu trữ giá trị”, ở Ấn Độ được gọi là “phương tiện thanh toán trả trước”. Đặc biệt ở Mỹ, không có một tên gọi thống nhất về “tiền điện tử” như các nước, nhưng có các sản phẩm tương tự như “sản phẩm lưu trữ giá trị”, “kênh truy cập trả trước” và đáng lưu ý là, FINCEN còn sử dụng thuật ngữ “tiền ảo” để chỉ các sản phẩm trong đó bao gồm cả các sản phẩm tương tự tiền điện tử. Ngược lại không phải tại mọi nơi, thuật ngữ “tiền điện tử” cũng chắc chắn chỉ đề cập tới các sản phẩm có 03 đặc tính như trên. Đặc biệt, trong nhiều tài liệu nghiên cứu, thuật ngữ “tiền điện tử” đôi khi được sử dụng để ám chỉ tất cả các hình thái ở dạng điện tử của tiền và giá trị, trong đó có cả tiền ảo như Bitcoin hay thẻ quà tặng và các sản phẩm lưu trữ giá trị khác (ví dụ như nghiên cứu về Tiền di động và thanh toán: xu hướng công nghệ của Học Viện Công nghệ Massachusetts - MIT năm 2016).

Hộp 1.1 Bản chất pháp lý của tiền điện tử

Các cách tiếp cận khác nhau được chấp nhận sử dụng cho việc định nghĩa tiền điện tử, ví dụ:

- **Chỉ thị EU:** các giá trị tiền tệ được lưu trữ điện tử hoặc từ tính thể hiện quyền truy đòi đối với bên phát hành và được phát hành trên cơ sở nhận được các khoản tiền cho mục đích thực hiện các giao dịch thanh toán và được chấp nhận bởi thể nhân và pháp nhân không phải là EMI
- **Kenya:** giá trị tiền tệ được thể hiện như một quyền truy đòi đối với đơn vị phát hành, (i) được lưu trữ điện tử hoặc từ tính, (2) được phát hành trên cơ sở nhận được tiền tệ Kenya hoặc đồng tiền khác được Ngân hàng Trung ương Kenya cho phép, và (3) được chấp nhận là phương tiện thanh toán bởi những người khác ngoài đơn vị phát hành.
- **Singapore:** Bất kỳ giá trị tiền tệ được lưu trữ điện tử nào mà (1) được niêm yết bằng một loại tiền tiền hoặc neo bởi đơn vị phát hành với bất kỳ tiền tệ nào; (2) được trả trước để có thể thực hiện các giao dịch thanh toán. Nói chung, thông qua sử dụng một tài khoản thanh toán; (3) được chấp nhận bởi bên khác ngoài đơn vị phát hành; và (4) thể hiện quyền truy đòi đối với đơn vị phát hành, nhưng không bao gồm bất kỳ khoản tiền gửi nào được chấp nhận tại Singapore, từ bất kỳ người nào ở Singapore.

Các yếu tố chung sau đây có thể rút ra được từ các định nghĩa ở trên: (1) lưu trữ điện tử giá trị tiền tệ được thể hiện bởi một đơn vị tiền tệ chính thức đang tồn tại, (2) thể hiện một quyền truy đòi bắt buộc đối với tổ chức phát hành, và (3) được chấp nhận làm phương tiện thanh toán bởi các bên không phải là tổ chức phát hành.

⁹ Các tài sản mã hóa đang tồn tại (ví dụ, Bitcoin, Litecoin, Ethereum...) không nằm trong định nghĩa về tiền điện tử. Hầu hết các đồng tiền ổn định (stable coins) cũng không đáp ứng định nghĩa này (ví dụ, quyền truy đòi đối với tổ chức phát hành và quyền hoàn trả ngang giá). Các đồng tiền ổn định được thiết kế như, và nằm trong định nghĩa của, tiền điện tử nên được quản lý theo cùng các yêu cầu. Về danh mục phân loại các loại tiền tệ kỹ thuật số, xem Macini – Griffoli (2019)

3.1.2. Các tổ chức được cho phép phát hành tiền điện tử - các mô hình cấp phép

Từ góc độ cấp phép để quản lý và giám sát, cần quan tâm đến chủ thể được cấp phép phát hành và cung ứng dịch vụ tiền điện tử. Theo đó, các đơn vị được cấp phép phát hành và cung ứng dịch vụ tiền điện tử được phân loại thành 2 nhóm là ngân hàng (bao gồm ngân hàng thương mại và các tổ chức tiền gửi khác) và các tổ chức phi ngân hàng.

Theo khảo sát của CPMI về 75 khu vực pháp lý được thực hiện vào đầu năm 2021¹⁰, hầu như tất cả các khu vực pháp lý mà các tổ chức phi ngân hàng có thể phát hành tiền điện tử đều yêu cầu cấp phép và/hoặc đăng ký, và có các mô hình cấp phép cụ thể cho mục đích này. Ở một số khu vực pháp lý, chỉ các ngân hàng mới được phép phát hành tiền điện tử (ví dụ: Nam Phi). Điều này là do việc phát hành tiền điện tử và chấp nhận đổi lại tiền mặt có thể được hiểu một cách hợp pháp là hoạt động nhận tiền gửi tại các khu vực pháp lý này. Hai loại mô hình cấp phép được sử dụng trong các khu vực pháp lý cho phép các tổ chức phi ngân hàng phát hành tiền điện tử: mô hình ngân hàng hẹp và mô hình phi ngân hàng.

- Theo mô hình ngân hàng hẹp, các tổ chức phi ngân hàng có thể xin giấy phép ngân hàng hạn chế (ví dụ: giấy phép ngân hàng thanh toán) cho phép họ cung cấp một số dịch vụ ngân hàng hạn chế. Giấy phép ngân hàng thanh toán có sẵn theo khuôn khổ pháp lý của Ấn Độ và Mexico, cũng như ở Thụy Sĩ ở định dạng hơi khác (giấy phép fintech).

- Mô hình phi ngân hàng cho phép các loại tổ chức phi ngân hàng cụ thể phát hành tiền điện tử (ví dụ: tổ chức tiền điện tử, tổ chức phát hành công cụ trả trước hoặc tổ chức phát hành giá trị được lưu trữ). Đây cũng là một cách tiếp cận phổ biến ở các khu vực pháp lý muốn thúc đẩy tài chính toàn diện. Theo Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (2019)¹¹, đây là trường hợp ở Colombia, Ghana, Kenya, Malaysia, Myanmar, Peru, Rwanda, Sri Lanka và Tanzania. Tại các khu vực pháp lý này, các nhà khai thác mạng di động (MNO) tận dụng các kênh viễn thông hiện có của họ, cơ sở khách hàng rộng lớn và sức mạnh trong việc tiếp thị và xây dựng thương hiệu cho các sản phẩm kỹ thuật số để phát hành tiền điện tử. Các MNO thường được yêu cầu thiết lập một phương tiện có mục đích đặc biệt (SPV) – một tổ chức riêng biệt để cung cấp dịch vụ này.

Để cho phép các tổ chức phi ngân hàng có thể phát hành tiền điện tử, cách tiếp cận phổ biến nhất là công nhận tiền điện tử như một sản phẩm được cung cấp độc quyền bởi các nhà cung cấp dịch vụ thanh toán (PSP), thường bao gồm các ngân hàng. Chẳng hạn, Kenya, Rwanda và Tanzania cho phép chỉ các PSP mới đăng ký để có được giấy phép (hoặc quyền) cung cấp dịch vụ/ phát hành tiền điện tử.

Một cách tiếp cận khác là cơ quan quản lý tài chính hình thành một danh mục cấp phép riêng cho loại hình EMI. Ví dụ: ở Myanmar, việc trở thành nhà cung cấp dịch vụ tài chính di động (MFS) (có chức năng tương đương với EMI) yêu cầu phải có giấy chứng nhận đăng ký (ví dụ: giấy phép) được cấp theo thẩm quyền rộng rãi của luật ngân hàng. Côte d'Ivoire, với tư cách là thành viên của WAEMU, cũng cung cấp giấy phép EMI độc lập.¹²

¹⁰ Chi tiết thông tin về cuộc khảo sát này xem Phụ lục II. Các cuộc khảo sát quốc tế.

¹¹ Hướng dẫn tham khảo về quy định và giám sát dịch vụ tài chính kỹ thuật số năm 2019 của Quỹ Bill và Melinda Gates (BMGF)

¹² Liên minh Kinh tế và Tiền tệ Tây Phi là một cơ quan tài chính khu vực cung cấp các luật và quy định về dịch vụ tài chính chung giữa các quốc gia thành viên, ngoài những điều khác. Khi bài viết này đề cập đến Bờ Biển Ngà, các quy định

3.1.3. Yêu cầu cấp phép, hoạt động được phép và báo cáo

Khi tiền điện tử được hình thành không phải là một sản phẩm giống như tiền gửi mà là một sản phẩm giống như thanh toán hoặc thanh toán cộng thêm, thì cần có một cơ sở chính sách để cấp phép và điều chỉnh các tổ chức phi ngân hàng. Đối với các tổ chức đã tham gia vào các loại hình kinh doanh khác, việc cấp phép (hoặc cho phép) thường yêu cầu người nộp đơn thành lập một đơn vị (Kenya) hoặc một công ty con chuyên phát hành tiền điện tử (ở Côte d'Ivoire và Ghana cho tất cả các loại tổ chức phi ngân hàng, và ở Myanmar cho MNOs). Việc tách biệt hoạt động tiền điện tử (và tài chính) khỏi hoạt động của một công ty mẹ phi ngân hàng được coi là cần thiết để giám sát hiệu quả.

Việc cho phép các tổ chức phi ngân hàng phát hành tiền điện tử đòi hỏi phải đặt chúng dưới quyền trực tiếp của cơ quan quản lý dịch vụ tài chính— phần lớn là ngân hàng trung ương. Ở một số quốc gia, nơi MNO tìm cách trở thành EMI, nó phải cung cấp bằng chứng hỗ trợ từ cơ quan quản lý viễn thông—ví dụ: bản sao có chứng thực giấy phép viễn thông (Kenya) hoặc thư không phản đối (Myanmar). Để được cơ quan quản lý tài chính cấp phép/quyền phát hành và cung ứng dịch vụ tiền điện tử, các tổ chức thường bị điều chỉnh bởi các vấn đề cốt lõi sau:

(i) Phạm vi hoạt động được phép

Việc giới hạn phạm vi hoạt động được phép là rất quan trọng để giảm hồ sơ rủi ro của EMI, từ đó cho phép họ tận dụng lợi thế của việc nới lỏng các yêu cầu gia nhập và các yêu cầu liên tục (nghĩa là ít nghiêm ngặt hơn so với các ngân hàng thương mại). Phạm vi hoạt động của EMI thường bị giới hạn ở các chức năng cốt lõi như phát hành tài khoản tiền điện tử, nộp tiền/rút tiền, thanh toán và chuyển khoản trong nước. Các khoản thanh toán có thể bao gồm hóa đơn tiện ích, thanh toán cho người bán, thanh toán tiền lương, trợ cấp người già và thanh toán thuế (như ở Bangladesh).

Quan trọng nhất, trung gian tài chính bởi EMI là không được phép.¹³ Các EMI này không thể cung cấp các dịch vụ như tín dụng, đầu tư, bảo hiểm hoặc tiết kiệm trên tài khoản của chính họ, nhưng trong một số trường hợp, có thể cung cấp quyền truy cập vào chúng khi hợp tác với một tổ chức tài chính được cấp phép. Hơn nữa, các tài khoản tiền điện tử thường phải tuân theo các mức trần định lượng (ví dụ: số dư tiền điện tử tối đa cho mỗi tổ chức phát hành hoặc số dư tối đa cho mỗi khách hàng).

(ii) Vốn tối thiểu ban đầu và vốn liên tục

Theo dữ liệu khảo sát từ GSMA (2016), hầu như tất cả các khu vực pháp lý đều yêu cầu các tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử phi ngân hàng phải đáp ứng các yêu cầu về vốn tối thiểu ban đầu để nhận được giấy phép hoạt động¹⁴ (vốn pháp định). Một số khu vực pháp lý yêu cầu tổ chức phát hành phải đáp ứng thêm các yêu cầu về vốn tối thiểu liên tục.

Xét về quy mô vốn tối thiểu, theo khảo sát của Marc C Dobler và cộng sự (2021), các

chính được thảo luận là trên toàn WAEMU và được giám sát bởi ngân hàng trung ương khu vực, BCEAO. Các thành viên WAEMU khác là Benin, Burkina Faso, Guinea-Bissau, Mali, Niger, Senegal và Togo.

¹³ Nói một cách chính xác, việc trung gian gửi tiền dưới hình thức cho vay bị cấm. Một số khu vực pháp lý, bao gồm cả WAEMU và Rwanda, cho phép đặt tiền vào các công cụ nợ và đầu tư đã được phê duyệt.

¹⁴ Marc C Dobler và cộng sự (2021) còn gọi là vốn pháp định danh nghĩa

yêu cầu vốn tối thiểu theo luật định mà các EMI phải đáp ứng để được cấp phép thấp hơn đáng kể so với các yêu cầu dành cho ngân hàng. Như bảng cho thấy, các yêu cầu vốn tối thiểu ban đầu và liên tục khác nhau đáng kể giữa các khu vực pháp lý. Yêu cầu ban đầu từ khoảng 200.000 USD ở Kenya và Namibia đến hơn 15 triệu USD ở Ấn Độ. Có sự thiếu đồng nhất về cách thiết lập các yêu cầu vốn tối thiểu ban đầu phù hợp cho các tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử phi ngân hàng. Các nhà quản lý có thể muốn xem xét các yếu tố như chi phí khởi động để xây dựng một doanh nghiệp kinh doanh tiền điện tử bền vững (có thể thay đổi đáng kể tùy thuộc vào thị trường có thể xử lý)¹⁵, cùng với sự cần thiết phải tạo ra sự cân bằng để thúc đẩy sự đổi mới trong khi hạn chế số lượng các tổ chức được cấp phép để đảm bảo việc giám sát hiệu quả.

Các yêu cầu về vốn tối thiểu liên tục được thiết kế để đảm bảo rằng nguồn vốn có sẵn để giải quyết tình trạng mất khả năng thanh toán của ngân hàng và các cú sốc khác vẫn đủ khi tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử phát triển. Nhiều quốc gia sử dụng tỷ lệ nghĩa vụ nợ tiền điện tử, thường là 2-3%. Theo GSMA (2016), các yêu cầu cao hơn không thực tế và cũng không cần thiết cho hoạt động kinh doanh tiền điện tử. Yêu cầu 100% của Cộng hòa Dân chủ Congo đã không được thực thi trên thực tế, trong khi yêu cầu 8% trước đó của Liên minh Kinh tế và Tiền tệ Tây Phi¹⁶ đã giảm xuống 3% khi các quy định được cập nhật vào tháng 5 năm 2015.

Các yêu cầu khác liên quan đến các vấn đề như kế hoạch kinh doanh, quản lý rủi ro, giải quyết khiếu nại của khách hàng và hệ thống CNTT. EMI thường được yêu cầu phải là công ty trách nhiệm hữu hạn và một số quốc gia áp đặt các yêu cầu về quyền sở hữu (xem Bảng 1). Ví dụ, ở Ghana, một EMI chuyên dụng phải có ít nhất 25% quyền sở hữu bản địa.

Bảng 1. Các yêu cầu về vốn tối thiểu ban đầu và liên tục

Quốc gia	Yêu cầu vốn tối thiểu ban đầu	Yêu cầu vốn tối thiểu liên tục
Ấn Độ	1 triệu INR - 13,7 - 15,8 triệu USD	(1) Tối thiểu 15% tài sản có trọng số rủi ro và (2) nợ phải trả không được vượt quá 33,33 lần giá trị ròng (tức là tỷ lệ đòn bẩy 3%)
Bangladesh	5,3 triệu USD	5,3 triệu USD, lên đến 10,7 triệu USD (từ nguồn thu nhập giữ lại theo thời gian)
Uganda	Không xác định	Không xác định
Kenya	20 triệu KES - 200.000 USD	20 triệu KES - 200.000 USD
EU	350.000 EUR - (400.000)370.000 USD	2% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền điện tử chưa trả
Colombia	5,846 triệu COP - 2,1 triệu USD	2% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền di động bình quân trong 30 ngày
Cộng hòa Congo	2,5 triệu USD	Giá trị lớn hơn trong số: (1) nghĩa vụ nợ tiền điện tử hiện tại; (2) bình quân nghĩa vụ nợ

¹⁵ Ví dụ: chi phí khởi động có thể được dự kiến sẽ thấp hơn đáng kể đối với một nhà cung cấp ở Namibia (dân số trưởng thành khoảng 1,5 triệu người) so với một nhà cung cấp ở Ấn Độ (dân số trưởng thành khoảng 900 triệu người). Để biết ước tính dân số, hãy xem Cơ quan Tình báo Trung ương (2015), The World Factbook.

¹⁶ Yêu cầu vốn 8% có thể so sánh với tỷ lệ an toàn vốn điển hình của các ngân hàng. Yêu cầu như vậy là không cần thiết đối với các công ty phát hành tiền di động không làm trung gian tiền của khách hàng.

Quốc gia	Yêu cầu vốn tối thiểu ban đầu	Yêu cầu vốn tối thiểu liên tục
		tiền điện tử 6 tháng; hoặc (3) vốn tối thiểu ban đầu
Côte d'Ivoire	300 triệu XOF - 509.000 USD	Giá trị lớn hơn trong số: (1) 300 triệu XOF - 509.000 USD; (2) 3% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền di động
Mali	300 triệu XOF - 509.000 USD	Giá trị lớn hơn trong số: (1) 300 triệu XOF - 509.000 USD; (2) 3% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền di động
Namibia	2,5 triệu NAD - 205.000 USD	Giá trị lớn hơn trong số (1) 2,5 triệu NAD hoặc 2% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền di động
Phillippines	100 triệu PHP - 2,2 triệu USD	100 triệu PHP - 2,2 triệu USD
Senegal	300 triệu XOF - 509.000 USD	Giá trị lớn hơn trong số: (1) 300 triệu XOF - 509.000 USD; (2) 3% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền di động
Srilanka	872.000 USD	Không xác định
Peru	722.090 USD	2% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền điện tử chưa trả
Brazil	540.000 USD	Giá trị lớn hơn trong số: (1) 2% giá trị giao dịch bình quân tháng (trong vòng 12 tháng qua); hay (2) 2% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền điện tử chưa thanh toán
WAEMU	522.380 USD	Giá trị lớn hơn trong số (1) 522.380 USD; hay 3% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền điện tử chưa thanh toán
Tanzania	218.570 USD	Không xác định
Rwanda	115.970 USD	Không xác định
Mexico	11,1 triệu USD	8% tài sản theo trọng số rủi ro
Malaysia	1,2 triệu USD	Giá trị lớn hơn trong số: (i) 1,2 triệu USD hay (ii) 8% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền điện tử hiện tại

Nguồn: Nguồn: Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (2019) và GSMA (2016)

3.2. Các quy định về bảo vệ tiền của khách hàng tiền điện tử

Để đổi lấy tiền điện tử, khách hàng tiền điện tử phải chuyển một khoản tiền tương ứng cho các tổ chức phát hành và cung ứng dịch vụ tiền điện tử. Các khoản tiền này của khách hàng sẽ phải đối mặt với rủi ro mất tiền khi:

(i) Tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử không có đủ các tài sản thanh khoản dành riêng để hoàn trả tiền cho khách hàng (rủi ro thanh khoản);

(ii) Tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử (hoặc các bên nhận ủy thác) không có đủ tài sản để chi trả do mất khả năng thanh toán (rủi ro tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử mất khả năng thanh toán); hoặc

(iii) Rủi ro ngân hàng không đủ tài sản để hoàn trả khách hàng, việc này xảy ra do các khoản tiền để đổi lấy tiền điện tử từ tổ chức phát hành được giữ tại ngân hàng (rủi ro ngân hàng mất khả năng thanh toán).

Các rủi ro này ngày càng đáng lo ngại hơn khi các tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử được mở rộng ra không chỉ cho các ngân hàng mà còn cho các tổ chức phi ngân hàng như các công ty fintech, bigtech, các công ty vận hành mạng lưới viễn thông MNO. Để giảm thiểu những rủi ro này, các quốc gia đã đưa ra những quy định cụ thể đối với các khoản tiền mà các tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử nhận từ khách hàng (để cung ứng tiền điện tử). Đây là một quá trình đang từng bước được hoàn thiện và hiện nay vẫn là một chủ đề được thảo luận, nghiên cứu để tiếp tục đưa ra các đề xuất, khuyến nghị. Có nhiều phương pháp khác nhau để bảo vệ các quỹ được quan sát thấy ở các khu vực pháp lý khác nhau để chống lại các rủi ro mất tiền có thể xảy ra, có thể tổng hợp và hệ thống các biện pháp này tại các nước như sau.

Bảng 2. Các biện pháp bảo vệ tiền của khách hàng tiền điện tử

Rủi ro	Giải pháp
Thanh khoản	<p>Tài trợ trước (Prefunding): Yêu cầu tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử phải lập các khoản quỹ riêng có giá trị bằng với 100% nghĩa vụ nợ tiền điện tử tại các ngân hàng thương mại được cấp phép hoặc dưới các khoản đầu tư thanh khoản khác.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yêu cầu dự trữ 100% • Giới hạn nghiêm ngặt đối với các khoản đầu tư được phép
Tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử hoặc bên nhận tín thác/ủy thác mất khả năng thanh toán	<p>Cô lập và khoanh vùng tiền của khách hàng (Fund isolation and refencing):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sử dụng quỹ tín thác hoặc các thỏa thuận ủy thác khác để (1) tách các khoản tiền của khách hàng khỏi tài sản cá nhân của tổ chức phát hành (hoặc người được ủy thác) và (2) ngăn các chủ nợ của tổ chức phát hành (hoặc người được ủy thác) truy đòi tiền của khách hàng tiền điện tử
Ngân hàng mất khả năng thanh toán	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sử dụng ngân hàng làm đơn vị nhận ủy thác • Bảo hiểm tiền gửi: bảo vệ các khoản tiền của khách hàng tiền điện tử thông qua cơ chế <i>bảo hiểm tiền gửi trực tiếp</i> hoặc <i>bảo hiểm tiền gửi chuyển tiếp</i>. • Bảo hiểm tư nhân hoặc bảo lãnh từ tập đoàn mẹ của ngân hàng • Yêu cầu về số lượng và sức khỏe của các ngân hàng nắm giữ tiền của khách hàng • Yêu cầu về vốn liên tục (ongoing capital)

Nguồn: Mehmet Kerse và Stephan Staschen (2018) và Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (2019)

Các phương pháp bảo vệ tài sản hỗ trợ cho các truy đòi tiền điện tử (tài sản dự trữ) nhằm bảo vệ khách hàng khỏi rủi ro EMI có thể không có đủ tiền để trả lại cho họ hoặc rủi ro mất khả năng thanh toán của EMI. Hầu hết các quy định EMI bao gồm các yêu cầu bảo vệ quỹ có hai yếu tố:

- **Tách biệt.** EMI được yêu cầu dành riêng một số tiền tối thiểu để đảm bảo lượng tiền điện tử đã phát hành hay nghĩa vụ nợ tiền điện tử (e-float). Thông thường, họ phải

hoàn trả 100 phần trăm e-float, bằng cách gửi một số tiền tương đương vào một tài khoản (tài khoản thả nổi – float account) tách biệt với tài khoản EMI được sử dụng để vận hành các hoạt động hàng ngày (ví dụ: thanh toán hóa đơn, thanh toán/nhận phí, v.v.). Có thể có một hoặc nhiều tài khoản thả nổi.¹⁷

- **Yêu cầu thanh khoản.** Các quy định yêu cầu e-float chỉ được đầu tư (nếu bất kỳ khoản đầu tư nào được phép) vào các tài sản có tính thanh khoản và rủi ro thấp, chẳng hạn như trái phiếu chính phủ, hoặc đơn giản là trong tài khoản tại một ngân hàng thương mại (có thể trả lãi hoặc không trả lãi).
- **Yêu cầu đa dạng hóa.** Một số quy định yêu cầu EMI phân bổ e-float cho các ngân hàng khác nhau để bảo vệ chống lại rủi ro ngân hàng đổ vỡ.¹⁸
- **Hàng rào/khoanh vùng.** Thu xếp khoanh vùng bảo vệ e-float chống lại các chủ nợ EMI (ví dụ: người cho vay, nhà đầu tư, nhà cung cấp, nhân viên, chính phủ). Điều này có thể được thực hiện bằng cách yêu cầu tài khoản thả nổi phải là một loại tài khoản đặc biệt, chẳng hạn như tài khoản tín thác hoặc ký quỹ.¹⁹

E-float không bị cầm cố. Các quy định có thể cấm EMI cầm cố e-float (ví dụ: cầm cố chúng để đảm bảo cho các khoản vay) và/hoặc có thể quy định rằng tiền trong tài khoản thả nổi không phải là tài sản của EMI.²⁰

Thông thường, tài sản dự trữ được tách biệt và khoanh vùng khỏi quỹ riêng của EMI.²¹ Tài sản dự trữ cần được gửi vào ngân hàng thương mại hoặc ngân hàng trung ương hoặc đầu tư vào tài sản có tính thanh khoản cao. Các khoản tiền gửi hoặc đầu tư này có thể ở dạng tài khoản ủy thác, tín thác hoặc ký quỹ trong đó khách hàng của EMI là người thụ hưởng. Do đó, tiền không thể được sử dụng để đáp ứng yêu cầu của các chủ nợ EMI (không phải chủ sở hữu tiền điện tử) trong trường hợp mất khả năng thanh toán. Ở các khu vực pháp lý khác, việc tách biệt và khoanh vùng không bắt buộc và thay vào đó, các EMI được yêu cầu phải có được sự bảo vệ dưới hình thức bảo hiểm hoặc bảo lãnh. Một số khu vực pháp lý kết hợp hoặc cho phép EMI chọn bất kỳ phương pháp bảo vệ nào (ví dụ: EU), trong khi những khu vực khác chỉ cho phép một phương pháp.

Rủi ro “còn lại” vẫn có thể phát sinh ngay cả khi sử dụng các phương pháp bảo vệ an toàn, nhưng những rủi ro này được giảm thiểu bằng bảo hiểm tiền gửi ở một số quốc gia. Các biện pháp bảo vệ có thể phải đối mặt với những thách thức pháp lý hoặc có thể có các vấn đề hoạt động không lường trước được có thể cản trở việc tiếp cận hoặc chuyển giao tài sản dự trữ trong trường hợp EMI hoặc ngân hàng giữ tiền mất khả năng thanh toán. Một cách để giảm thiểu những rủi ro như vậy là mở rộng phạm vi bảo hiểm tiền gửi bao gồm cả tiền điện

¹⁷ Phần này xem xét cách tiếp cận phổ biến nhất mà EMI sử dụng để bảo vệ float: gửi tiền vào tài khoản tại một ngân hàng thương mại và/hoặc giữ nó trong các khoản đầu tư an toàn. Các cách tiếp cận khác, có thể ảnh hưởng đến các vấn đề pháp lý, vận hành và giám sát được thảo luận trong bài viết này, được mô tả trong Mehmet và Staschen (2018).

¹⁸ Ở góc độ giám sát ngân hàng, yêu cầu này hạn chế rủi ro của những người gửi tiền lớn tại các ngân hàng riêng lẻ. Xem Kerse và Staschen (2018).

¹⁹ Xem Staschen và Meagher (2018) và Greenacre và Buckley (2014).

²⁰ Tùy thuộc vào luật của quốc gia đối với tài khoản tín thác hoặc tài khoản ký quỹ, các cam kết trên float là không hợp lệ.

²¹ Thông thường, các yêu cầu bảo vệ áp dụng cho 100% các khoản tiền của khách hàng tiền điện tử (float).

từ.²² Hiệu quả của cách tiếp cận như vậy sẽ phụ thuộc vào thiết kế của khuôn khổ bảo hiểm tiền gửi của từng quốc gia (tức là mức độ đầy đủ của quỹ, tốc độ chi trả ...). Điều này có thể được thực hiện thông qua cách tiếp cận trực tiếp hoặc chuyển tiếp.

- Cách tiếp cận trực tiếp: EMI là thành viên của chương trình bảo hiểm tiền gửi và tiền điện tử do họ phát hành được bao gồm trong định nghĩa về “tiền gửi”. Do đó, nó được bảo hiểm tiền gửi chi trả trong trường hợp EMI mất khả năng thanh toán. Đây là trường hợp của tiền điện tử được phát hành bởi các ngân hàng thanh toán ở Ấn Độ và Mexico.

- Cách tiếp cận chuyển tiếp: Các tài khoản thả nổi tiền điện tử được giữ trong ngân hàng được coi là các khoản nợ tiền gửi. Bảo hiểm tiền gửi được “chuyển qua” cho từng khách hàng tiền điện tử cá nhân trong trường hợp ngân hàng giữ số tiền thả nổi mất khả năng thanh toán. Cách tiếp cận này được áp dụng tại Hoa Kỳ cho một số loại tài khoản tiền điện tử.²³ Ủy ban Châu Âu gần đây đã đưa ra một cuộc tham vấn hỏi những người được hỏi liệu một cách tiếp cận tương tự có nên được áp dụng ở Châu Âu hay không.²⁴

4. KẾT LUẬN

Kinh nghiệm quốc tế cho thấy các tổ chức phi ngân hàng đang đóng vai trò hàng đầu trong việc cung cấp các tài khoản giao dịch cơ bản cho thị trường đại chúng.²⁵ Điều này đạt được là do các quốc gia thường không áp đặt đầy đủ các yêu cầu áp dụng cho các ngân hàng thương mại để đối phó với việc hạn chế phạm vi hoạt động và cấm làm trung gian vốn. Nhiều quốc gia đã mở ra không gian cho việc phát hành tiền điện tử phi ngân hàng bằng cách tạo ra một phân khúc quy định riêng cho EMI.

(i) Thứ nhất, Một trong các quy định cơ bản khi cấp phép cho EMI là các yêu cầu về vốn. Các yêu cầu về vốn có sự khác biệt lớn giữa các quốc gia. Vì vậy, để đưa ra mức yêu cầu phù hợp, cần cân nhắc các vấn đề như sau:

- Đối với yêu cầu ban đầu: Yêu cầu về vốn tối thiểu ban đầu rất khác nhau giữa các quốc gia. Khi thiết lập các yêu cầu này, cơ quan quản lý có thể cân nhắc những điều sau:

- Cần bao nhiêu vốn để xây dựng cơ sở hạ tầng cần thiết cho hoạt động kinh doanh tiền điện tử bền vững và thể hiện năng lực tài chính cũng như cam kết của EMI?

- Các yêu cầu về vốn có đủ để cho phép EMI trang trải các khoản lỗ bất ngờ không?

Trên thực tế, các yêu cầu về vốn tối thiểu ban đầu có thể thay đổi đáng kể tùy thuộc vào, ví dụ: (i) quy mô của thị trường có thể định vị; và (ii) chi phí cơ sở hạ tầng cốt lõi ở một quốc gia cụ thể.

- Đối với yêu cầu liên tục: Yêu cầu EMI duy trì vốn tối thiểu ban đầu ở dạng nguyên vẹn có thể đóng vai trò là yêu cầu vốn liên tục cơ bản. Ngoài ra, việc ràng buộc cơ sở vốn với các khoản nợ tiền điện tử chưa thanh toán có thể giúp đảm bảo có đủ vốn khi EMI tăng lên.

²² Xem Izaguirre và cộng sự (2019).

²³ FDIC (2008)

²⁴ EC (2021)

²⁵ Hầu hết, nhưng không phải tất cả, trong số này là tài khoản tiền điện tử.

Các cơ quan quản lý có thể xem xét yêu cầu EMI duy trì mức cao hơn của (i) vốn tối thiểu ban đầu; hoặc (ii) tỷ lệ phần trăm nợ tiền điện tử chưa thanh toán (một số quốc gia đã đặt tỷ lệ phần trăm này trong khoảng 2-3%). Điều đáng chú ý là mặc dù điều này thể hiện thông lệ phổ biến, nhưng tính đầy đủ của các yêu cầu này chưa được thử nghiệm rộng rãi trong thực tế.

(ii) Thứ hai, Khi cho phép tổ chức phi ngân hàng phát hành tiền điện tử, có sự thống nhất lớn giữa các quốc gia trong quy định về bảo vệ thận trọng các quỹ e-float trong tài khoản ngân hàng và cách ly các khoản tiền khỏi các khiếu nại của bên thứ ba thông qua tín thác hoặc các cấu trúc tương tự. Tuy nhiên, vẫn những vấn đề còn bỏ ngỏ với các cách tiếp cận khác nhau và cũng chưa được chứng thực trong thực tế, bao gồm liệu quỹ e-float có được bảo vệ bởi hệ thống bảo hiểm tiền gửi hay không. Trước khi tiền điện tử được thêm vào phạm vi của một hệ thống BHTG đã được thiết lập cho các ngân hàng, cần đánh giá tác động đối với mức độ đầy đủ của nguồn vốn BHTG. Mặc dù về lý thuyết, EMI có thể thiết lập các chương trình bảo hiểm riêng biệt, nhưng có thể không có đủ EMI để bù đắp rủi ro và cho đến nay, không có chương trình nào như vậy được thiết lập. Mặc dù các tài khoản tiền điện tử có thể có cùng mức bảo hiểm như tiền gửi ngân hàng, nhưng mức bảo hiểm thấp hơn đối với số dư tiền điện tử có thể giúp phân biệt số dư giao dịch trong EMI với số dư tiết kiệm trong tài khoản tiền gửi ngân hàng. Ví dụ, BHTG tại Liên minh Kinh tế và Tiền tệ Tây Phi (WAEMU) áp dụng mức bảo hiểm thấp hơn (IADI 2020).

Việc vận hành bảo hiểm tiền gửi đối với tiền điện tử vẫn còn nhiều thách thức trong thực tế và chưa được kiểm chứng cho đến nay. Theo cả hai cách tiếp cận, các cơ quan có thẩm quyền nên đánh giá năng lực của BHTG trong việc đối phó hiệu quả với các tổ chức tiền điện tử cho mục đích chi trả và đánh giá tác động chi phí đối với EMI để tuân thủ các yêu cầu lưu giữ hồ sơ. BHTG nên thường xuyên kiểm tra năng lực của EMI và ngân hàng trong việc cung cấp dữ liệu cần thiết trong khung thời gian quy định và xác minh tính chính xác của dữ liệu. Hệ thống CNTT của EMI phải tuân thủ các yêu cầu về dữ liệu khách hàng phải được kiểm toán hàng năm. Những yêu cầu này có thể có tác động bất lợi đến các mô hình kinh doanh chi phí thấp của EMI.

Tại Việt Nam, hiện nay, tiền điện tử được hiện diện dưới hình thức các sản phẩm thẻ trả trước, Ví điện tử và Mobile – money. Tuy nhiên, chỉ có Ví điện tử và Mobile – money được phát hành bởi các tổ chức phi ngân hàng, cụ thể là các tổ chức được ngân hàng nhà nước cấp phép cung cấp dịch vụ trung gian thanh toán. Các hoạt động cung ứng dịch vụ Ví điện tử, và thí điểm cung ứng dịch vụ Mobile – Money được quy định quản lý theo các văn bản dưới đây:

- Nghị định số 101/2012/NĐ-Cp ngày 22/11/2012 của Chính phủ về thanh toán không dùng tiền mặt và Nghị định 80/2016/NĐ-CP ngày 01/7/2016 sửa đổi, bổ sung một số điều của Nghị định 101/2012/NĐ-CP;

Thông tư số 39/2014/TT-NHNN ngày 11/12/2014 của Thống đốc NHNN Việt Nam hướng dẫn về dịch vụ trung gian thanh toán và các văn bản sửa đổi, bổ sung khác đã được hợp nhất tại VBHN số 47/VBHN – NHNN ngày 9/12/2019 hướng dẫn về dịch vụ trung gian thanh toán (VBHN số 47), trong đó quy định các nội dung điều chỉnh hoạt động cung ứng dịch vụ Ví điện tử của tổ chức cung ứng dịch vụ trung gian thanh toán.

- Quyết định số 316/QĐ – TTg ngày 09/3/2021 của Thủ tướng Chính phủ về việc phê duyệt triển khai thí điểm dùng tài khoản viễn thông thanh toán cho các hàng hóa, dịch vụ có giá trị nhỏ (mobile – money), trong đó quy định các nội dung điều chỉnh hoạt động thí điểm cung ứng dịch vụ Mobile Money của các doanh nghiệp có Giấy phép hoạt động trung gian thanh toán Ví điện tử và Giấy phép thiết lập mạng viễn thông công cộng di động mặt đáy sử dụng băng tần số vô tuyến điện cho phép sử dụng hạ tầng, mạng lưới, dữ liệu viễn thông (sau đây gọi tắt là Doanh nghiệp thí điểm).

Theo đó, so sánh với các nước, Việt Nam có một số đặc điểm như sau:

- Thứ nhất, về mô hình cấp phép, Việt Nam đi theo mô hình cấp phép cho các tổ chức phi ngân hàng, trong đó các tổ chức này khi thực hiện cung ứng dịch vụ tiền điện tử không nhất thiết phải thành lập các công ty con chuyên biệt phát hành tiền điện tử. Đối với mô hình thí điểm Mobile – Money, hiện nay do đặc thù của doanh nghiệp thí điểm cung ứng dịch vụ là doanh nghiệp viễn thông, đặc thù của loại hình sản phẩm mobile money, Quyết định 316 phân chia quyền quản lý, giám sát cho Bộ Thông tin – truyền thông và Ngân hàng Nhà nước trong đó Ngân hàng Nhà nước chỉ chịu trách nhiệm theo dõi, giám sát tài khoản bảo đảm thanh toán cho việc cung ứng dịch vụ Mobile – Money của Doanh nghiệp thực hiện thí điểm tại Ngân hàng thương mại, trong khi Bộ Thông tin và Truyền thông thực hiện quản lý, giám sát các hoạt động của Doanh nghiệp thực hiện thí điểm; chủ trì, chịu trách nhiệm thực hiện công tác kiểm tra, thanh tra các Doanh nghiệp thực hiện thí điểm. Việc yêu cầu các doanh nghiệp viễn thông thành lập công ty con dành riêng cho hoạt động kinh doanh tiền điện tử sẽ làm hạn chế rủi ro tiềm năng cho công ty viễn thông mẹ trong trường hợp công ty con tiền điện tử bị vỡ nợ. Các công ty con tiền điện tử này sẽ được cấp phép bởi cơ quan quản lý tài chính. Việc có 2 thực thể kinh doanh riêng biệt cũng sẽ phân định một cách rõ ràng khu vực pháp lý của cơ quan quản lý viễn thông (giấy phép cho doanh nghiệp viễn thông) và cơ quan quản lý tài chính (giấy phép cho công ty con chuyên phát hành tiền điện tử - cụ thể là Mobile Money).

- Thứ hai, về yêu cầu vốn tối thiểu, vốn điều lệ tối thiểu 50 tỷ đồng và áp dụng chung đối với mọi loại hình dịch vụ trung gian thanh toán, không phân biệt giữa dịch vụ ví điện tử với các dịch vụ trung gian thanh toán khác. Đây là mức vốn tối thiểu ban đầu để cấp giấy phép và cũng là mức vốn tối thiểu cần duy trì trong quá trình hoạt động kinh doanh. So với các tổ chức phát hành tiền điện tử tương đương ở các quốc gia, như đã làm rõ tại phần kinh nghiệm quốc tế, mức vốn tối thiểu có sự khác biệt lớn giữa các nước từ vài trăm nghìn USD lên đến chục triệu USD. Mức vốn tối thiểu 50 tỷ VNĐ tương đương với khoảng 2 triệu USD tại Việt Nam ở mức trung bình so với thế giới, không quá thấp và không quá cao, tương đồng với các quốc gia ở Đông Nam Á như Phillipines, Malaysia, Myanmar. Tuy nhiên, cần lưu ý là các trung gian thanh toán phi ngân hàng ở Việt Nam không buộc phải thực hiện tách biệt hoạt động kinh doanh tiền điện tử với các hoạt động khác của mình. Vì vậy, mức vốn tối thiểu 50 tỷ đồng có thể chưa phải là quá cao, cũng như chưa thể khẳng định tách biệt được rủi ro mất tiền của khách hàng tiền điện tử với các rủi ro khác của doanh nghiệp được cấp phép cung ứng dịch vụ Ví điện tử, Mobile – Money với mô hình cấp phép như trên.

- Thứ ba, về các biện pháp bảo vệ tiền của khách hàng tiền điện tử: Hiện tại, vấn đề bảo hiểm tiền gửi đối với tiền điện tử chưa phải là vấn đề cấp thiết đặt ra tại Việt Nam khi mà các sản phẩm tiền điện tử còn chiếm một tỷ lệ khá thấp trong hoạt động thanh toán không dùng

tiền mặt. Tuy nhiên, việc đảm bảo niềm tin cho người tiêu dùng, nhất là với những khách hàng yếu thế thuộc mục tiêu của tài chính toàn diện, việc bảo toàn tiền của khách hàng là rất quan trọng. Theo quy định, các khoản tiền của khách hàng sử dụng Ví điện tử và Mobile Money được bảo vệ thông qua 2 hình thức là được các tổ chức cung ứng trích lập và giữ trong tài khoản đảm bảo tại ngân hàng hợp tác, chỉ được sử dụng cho một số mục đích nhất định phục vụ cho việc chuyển tiền và thanh toán qua Ví điện tử, Mobile - Money của khách hàng. Tuy nhiên, các biện pháp này chưa đạt được mức độ bảo vệ cao như quỹ tín thác tại các nước – bảo vệ tiền của khách hàng khỏi các chủ nợ của tổ chức cung ứng dịch vụ trung gian thanh toán khi các tổ chức này mất khả năng thanh toán.

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NỢ NƯỚC NGOÀI VÀ TĂNG TRƯỞNG KINH TẾ TẠI VIỆT NAM

Lê Hoàng Đức

Học viện Ngân Hàng

Tóm tắt

Đại dịch Covid-19 đã gây tổn thương nền kinh tế toàn cầu, vấn đề đặt ra đối với các quốc gia là phải phục hồi nền kinh tế nhanh và bền vững. Để có nguồn lực tái thiết nền kinh tế thì các quốc gia phải tăng cường vay nợ trong nước cũng như nước ngoài, chính vì điều này làm nợ công mà đặc biệt là nợ nước ngoài gia tăng nhanh và có xu hướng vượt ngưỡng cho phép. Vậy ngưỡng nợ nào là an toàn cho nền kinh tế của nước ta?

Bài viết dựa trên dữ liệu chuỗi thời gian của Việt Nam từ năm 1986-2022 kết hợp với phương pháp ước lượng ngưỡng (Hansen, 1999) và OLS để tìm ra ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài tối ưu cho tăng trưởng kinh tế nước ta. Kết quả nghiên cứu cho thấy: ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài/GDP tối ưu cho tăng trưởng kinh tế là 75.8%. Kết quả trên hàm ý rằng, Chính Phủ cần thực hiện kỷ luật tài khóa để kiểm soát nợ nước ngoài nằm dưới ngưỡng nợ cho phép để không ảnh hưởng xấu đến tăng trưởng kinh tế.

Từ khóa: *nợ nước ngoài, tăng trưởng kinh tế, ngưỡng nợ*

EXTERNAL DEBT AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN VIETNAM

Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic has hurt the global economy, and the problem for countries is to recover quickly and sustainably. In order to have resources to rebuild the economy, countries must increase domestic and foreign debt, because this causes public debt, especially foreign debt, to increase rapidly and tend to exceed the allowable threshold. So what debt threshold is safe for our country's economy?

The paper is based on time series data of Vietnam from 1986-2022 combined with threshold estimation method (Hansen, 1999) and OLS to find the optimal external debt threshold for our country's economic growth. The paper reveal that the positive thresholds for economic growth is 75.8% for external debt/GDP.

Keywords: *external debt, debt threshold, economic growth*

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Đại dịch Covid-19 đã làm tổn thương nền kinh tế toàn cầu, vấn đề đặt ra đối với các quốc gia là làm sao để phục hồi kinh tế nhanh và bền vững. Để thực hiện mục tiêu trên thì ưu tiên lựa chọn chính sách của các Chính Phủ là mở rộng tài khóa. Chính sách này đòi hỏi Chính

Phủ cần một nguồn lực lớn về tài chính, trong khi đó, dịch bệnh đã làm nguồn thu của đất nước bị suy giảm. Chính vì lý do này, tình trạng cán cân ngân sách của đất nước rơi vào thâm hụt nghiêm trọng. Để có nguồn lực tái thiết nền kinh tế sau khủng hoảng thì quốc gia phải đi vay nợ trong nước hoặc nước ngoài, từ đó làm nợ công mà đặc biệt là nợ nước ngoài gia tăng nhanh và có xu hướng vượt ngưỡng cho phép. Theo (Eaton, 1993) cho rằng một quốc gia đi vay nợ vượt ngưỡng cho phép sẽ gây ra mất cân bằng giữa các thế hệ, và có thể gây ra sự chuyển giao nguồn lực giữa hiện tại và tương lai. Đồng thời, khi nợ vượt ngưỡng cho phép sẽ làm chậm sự tăng trưởng kinh tế. Thế nhưng, việc vay nợ là cần phải có trong giai đoạn đầu của sự phát triển đặc biệt là trong bối cảnh các nền kinh tế bị tổn thương do dịch bệnh Covid-19 gây ra. Vậy ngưỡng nợ nào là an toàn cho nền kinh tế của nước ta?

Việc quản lý nợ thông qua ngưỡng nợ mang tính trực quan và là công cụ quan trọng được sử dụng phổ biến của các Chính Phủ, tuy nhiên việc quản lý nợ cần phải xem xét thêm các yếu tố ngoài ngưỡng nợ như: cơ cấu nợ, khả năng trả nợ trong tương lai, mục đích việc sử dụng nguồn vốn vay, đảm bảo được niềm tin của thị trường, và có chiến lược quản lý nợ hợp lý.

Nghiên cứu này giúp tìm được ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài tích cực đối với tăng trưởng kinh tế của Việt Nam, từ đó cung cấp cơ sở để Chính Phủ có thể quản lý nợ nước ngoài mà không tác động tiêu cực đến nền kinh tế.

2. TỔNG QUAN NGHIÊN CỨU, CƠ SỞ LÝ THUYẾT VÀ PHƯƠNG PHÁP NGHIÊN CỨU

2.1. Lý thuyết về nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế

2.1.1. Lý thuyết nợ nước ngoài

Nợ nước ngoài của quốc gia là tổng các khoản nợ nước ngoài của Chính Phủ, nợ được Chính Phủ bảo lãnh, nợ của doanh nghiệp và tổ chức khác được vay theo phương thức tự vay, tự trả theo quy định của pháp luật Việt Nam. (Quốc Hội, 2017)

Theo Ngân hàng Thế giới và Quỹ Tiền Tệ Quốc Tế thì có 3 cách phân loại nợ nước ngoài.

- Phân loại nợ nước ngoài theo thời hạn các khoản nợ thì nợ nước ngoài có: nợ ngắn hạn, nợ dài hạn, tín dụng IMF. Trong đó, nợ ngắn hạn là khoản nợ dưới một năm, và ngược lại nợ dài hạn là các khoản nợ có thời hạn trên một năm.
- Phân loại nợ nước ngoài theo chủ thể đi vay bao gồm tư nhân và Chính Phủ, trong đó Chính Phủ có thể không trực tiếp đi vay mà thông qua bảo lãnh.

Hình 1: Các thành phần của nợ nước ngoài phân theo chủ thể đi vay

Nguồn: Luật Quản lý nợ (Quốc Hội, 2017), Ngân hàng Thế giới (WB, 2012)

2.1.2. Tăng trưởng kinh tế

Tăng trưởng kinh tế là sự gia tăng một cách bền vững của sản lượng bình quân đầu người hay sản lượng trên mỗi lao động (Kuznets, 1971). Khái niệm của (North & Thomas, 1993) thì tăng trưởng kinh tế xảy ra nếu sản lượng tăng nhanh hơn dân số.

Các chỉ số đo lường tăng trưởng kinh tế là tốc độ tăng của tổng sản phẩm quốc nội (GDP), tổng sản phẩm quốc dân (GNP), thu nhập bình quân đầu người (GDP per capita).

Tăng trưởng kinh tế trong dài hạn sẽ tạo ra tiên bộ về kinh tế xã hội ở đất nước. Đồng thời, cơ cấu kinh tế xã hội thay đổi theo hướng tiên bộ. Tăng trưởng kinh tế giúp Việt Nam nhanh chóng chuyển dịch cơ cấu kinh tế từ nông nghiệp sang công nghiệp và dịch vụ, và đô thị hóa. Bên cạnh đó, tăng trưởng kinh tế còn tạo ra nhiều hàng hóa, chất lượng dịch vụ cải thiện, gia tăng năng lực và hiệu quả của nền kinh tế, từ đó tạo cơ sở cho tiên bộ xã hội.

Phát triển và tăng trưởng kinh tế hiện đại đề cập đến thu nhập đầu người, không thể có phát triển bền vững nếu thiếu tăng trưởng kinh tế (Kuznets, 1971). Vì vậy, tăng trưởng kinh tế là điều kiện cần để phát triển kinh tế. Ở nước đang phát triển như Việt Nam, nếu không có mức tăng trưởng cao và liên tục thì khó có thể cải thiện đời sống kinh tế xã hội của đất nước, và có thể tụt hậu xa so với thế giới.

Vậy, tăng trưởng kinh tế có vai trò cực kỳ quan trọng đối với đất nước, thế nên, việc nghiên cứu vấn đề nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế là cần thiết, qua đó làm cơ sở để đề xuất các chính sách phù hợp, giúp Việt Nam tăng trưởng cao và bền vững.

2.1.3. Khung lý thuyết về ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế

Bài viết dựa trên lý thuyết nợ quá mức về mối quan hệ phi tuyến giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế. Lý thuyết nợ quá mức được sử dụng trong tài chính quốc tế bởi 2 nhà kinh tế (Sachs, 1989) và (Krugman P. R., 1988) khi nghiên cứu về cuộc khủng hoảng nợ. Lý thuyết

này cho rằng, nếu đất nước đi vay nợ một cách hợp lý sẽ tạo động lực tăng trưởng kinh tế, đặc biệt là các nền kinh tế mới nổi. Tuy nhiên mức nợ tích lũy cao sẽ nguy hại đến tăng trưởng kinh tế. Lý thuyết “debt overhang” cho rằng nếu mức nợ cao vượt quá tới hạn nhất định sẽ làm rò rỉ một lượng vốn để trả nợ, mà điều này làm giảm đầu tư. Bên cạnh đó, các nhà đầu tư lo ngại nợ quá mức sẽ buộc Chính Phủ phải tăng thuế trong tương lai, nên ảnh hưởng đến hoạt động kinh doanh, vì vậy nó tác động đến tâm lý đầu tư hiện tại. Nợ quá mức cũng ảnh hưởng đến hoạt động cải cách bộ máy của Chính Phủ, đặc biệt là tác động đến sự ổn định tài chính công.

🚩 Đường cong Laffer giảm nợ (Krugman P. , 1988)

Hình 2: Đường Laffer giảm nợ

Nguồn: Tác giả vẽ lại từ mô hình của P. Krugman (1988)

Đường cong (CLRĐ) là đường Laffer giảm nợ, cho thấy tổng nợ quốc gia càng lớn thì áp lực trả nợ gia tăng. Khi các quốc gia rơi vào phía đường cong RD, nợ tác động tiêu cực đến đầu tư, và khả năng cải thiện hành chính, từ đó tăng trưởng kinh tế giảm.

Tóm lại, qua đường cong Laffer về nợ ta thấy, ở mức độ nợ an toàn sẽ tốt cho tăng trưởng kinh tế, còn nếu nợ quá mức thì khả năng trả nợ giảm vì tăng trưởng kinh tế giảm.

2.2. Tổng quan nghiên cứu

2.1.1. Các nghiên cứu nước ngoài

Các nghiên cứu thực nghiệm về mối quan hệ giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế là tương đối ít trên thế giới. Chủ yếu các nghiên cứu về chủ đề này chỉ nhấn mạnh đến cách thức cơ cấu lại nợ quốc gia bền vững để phục vụ cho tăng trưởng. Song, đa số các lập luận cho rằng mối quan hệ giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế có xu hướng tuân theo đường Laffer trả nợ.

🚩 Nghiên cứu thể hiện mối quan hệ phi tuyến giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế Krugman (1988) chứng minh vay nợ vượt ngưỡng cho phép sẽ ảnh hưởng đến quyết

định tâm lý của nhà đầu tư trong và ngoài nước, ông xây dựng đường Laffer về trả nợ, để chứng minh, nếu tổng mức nợ nước ngoài gia tăng quá mức thì khả năng trả nợ giảm, khi đó đất nước có thể rơi vào khủng hoảng. Lập luận này đã chứng minh tồn tại mối quan hệ giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế, song nó tùy thuộc vào ngưỡng nợ.

Nghiên cứu thực nghiệm của Cohen (1993) cho thấy mối quan hệ phi tuyến tính của vay nợ nước ngoài và đầu tư. Ở một chừng mực nhất định, nợ nước ngoài có thể thúc đẩy đầu tư, nếu nợ vượt ngưỡng cho phép sẽ tác động tiêu cực đến đầu tư. Trong khi đó, đầu tư là yếu tố quan trọng đóng góp vào tăng trưởng kinh tế, vì vậy, tăng trưởng kinh tế có thể bị ảnh hưởng bởi nợ nước ngoài. Nghiên cứu của Cohen (1993) cho thấy nợ nước ngoài có thể thúc đẩy tăng trưởng kinh tế nếu vay nợ ở mức cho phép. Đồng thời, nợ nước ngoài tác động đến tăng trưởng kinh tế chủ yếu thông qua kênh đầu tư.

Mensah và cộng sự (2017) sử dụng phương pháp ước lượng VAR khảo sát 24 nước HIPC²⁶ châu Phi giai đoạn 1980-2010, kết quả bài viết cho thấy nợ nước ngoài tác động tiêu cực đến tăng trưởng kinh tế trong trung hạn.

Cả bài nghiên cứu trên đều cho thấy tồn tại mối quan hệ phi tuyến giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng. Tuy nhiên, các nghiên cứu không xác định được ngưỡng nợ cho phép đối với tăng trưởng kinh tế, và điều gì ảnh hưởng đến sự khác nhau của ngưỡng nợ ở từng quốc gia.

✚ Nghiên cứu chứng tỏ tồn tại ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài còn tác động tích cực đến tăng trưởng kinh tế

Trong nghiên cứu thực nghiệm về ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài cho phép của một quốc gia, Pattillo và cộng sự (2002) đã sử dụng dữ liệu bảng của 93 quốc gia đang phát triển trong giai đoạn 1969-1998 và cho thấy ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài còn tích cực đối với ở các nước này là 35%-40% so với GDP, và 160%-170% so với xuất khẩu.

Nghiên cứu của (Reinhart and Rogoff 2010) sử dụng dữ liệu của 40 quốc gia kéo dài 200 năm với 3700 quan sát nhận thấy rằng: (i) mối quan hệ giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng dài hạn là yếu nếu ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài/ GDP dưới 90% ; (ii) nếu nợ nước ngoài vượt quá 90% nợ tăng làm tốc độ tăng trưởng GDP giảm.

Trong báo cáo của quỹ tiền tệ quốc tế IMF (IMF, public debt and real GDP: revisiting the impact, 4/2022) phân tích dữ liệu về tổng nợ của 178 quốc gia trong giai đoạn 1995-2020 kết quả cho thấy rằng tác động của việc nợ gia tăng đến GDP thực tế là tiêu cực và thay đổi tùy thuộc vào các đặc điểm cơ bản như: ngưỡng nợ xét ở 2 khía cạnh đó là mức nợ ban đầu và mức độ gia tăng nợ trong 5 năm trước đó, chiến lược trả nợ quốc gia...

Nghiên cứu trên cho thấy tồn tại ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài mà tại đó nó tác động xấu đến tăng trưởng kinh tế, tuy nhiên, nó không đề cập đến sự linh động của ngưỡng nợ, hay các yếu tố tác động đến ngưỡng nợ tích cực cho tăng trưởng kinh tế.

2.2.2. Các nghiên cứu trong nước

Nghiên cứu trong nước về nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế là tương đối ít ở Việt Nam, song đa số trong đó là dựa theo lý thuyết nợ quá mức (debt overhang).

²⁶ Các nước mắc nợ trầm trọng

Nghiên cứu thực nghiệm về ngưỡng nợ công ở Việt Nam của Sử Đình Thành (2012), ông sử dụng bộ dữ liệu nợ công của VN giai đoạn 1990 – 2011 và dùng mô hình ngưỡng của Hansen, với phương pháp ước lượng OLS. Nghiên cứu đã phát hiện ngưỡng nợ công của VN là 75,8% GDP. Trong bài nghiên cứu này ông sử dụng biến phụ thuộc là tỷ trọng tăng trưởng GDP, và biến độc lập là tỷ lệ nợ công/GDP, với một số biến kiểm soát như: độ mở của nền kinh tế, lạm phát.

Bài viết của Nguyễn Ngọc Thạch & Trần Thị Kim Oanh (2016) sử dụng phương pháp ước lượng FEM, REM và GMM của dữ liệu mười nước khu vực Đông Nam Á giai đoạn 2006-2014. Bài nghiên cứu đã cho thấy mối quan hệ phi tuyến giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế tại các quốc gia nghiên cứu

Trong luận văn của Lê Hoàng Đức (2016) về mối quan hệ giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế tại Việt Nam, Luận văn sẽ sử dụng phương pháp ước lượng OLS, và ước lượng ngưỡng của Hansen(1999) để khắc phục những yếu điểm của các bài viết trên. Qua bài nghiên cứu cũng phát hiện ra ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài với GDP và nợ nước ngoài so với xuất khẩu lần lượt là 35.17% và 67.93%.

Trong luận án (Trường, 2019) sử dụng mô hình dữ liệu hỗn hợp (MIDAS) và mô hình vectơ hiệu chỉnh sai số (VECM). Luận án cũng cho thấy có tồn tại ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài so với GDP theo quý là 21.5% và nợ nước ngoài có tác động tích cực đến tăng trưởng kinh tế trong dài hạn. Ngoài ra, luận án còn cho thấy đối với biến nợ nước ngoài, khi tỷ lệ nợ nước ngoài/GDP tăng 1% sẽ làm GDP tăng 1.29%.

Bài viết (Hằng & Diệm, 2022) nghiên cứu tác động nợ công đến tăng trưởng kinh tế thông qua mô hình NARDL sử dụng dữ liệu quý từ năm 2000-2021, đã cho kết quả cho thấy tồn tại ngưỡng nợ công mà tại đó tác động tiêu cực đến tăng trưởng kinh tế. Tuy nhiên bài viết chưa tìm được ngưỡng nợ công là bao nhiêu thì tác động tiêu cực đến tăng trưởng kinh tế.

Bài viết (Cung, 2022) nghiên cứu tác động nợ nước ngoài đến tăng trưởng kinh tế thông qua mô hình ước lượng OLS sử dụng dữ liệu từ năm 1995-2019, kết quả cho thấy nợ nước ngoài, ODA, FDI tác động tích cực và có ý nghĩa đến tăng trưởng kinh tế. Tuy nhiên bài viết chưa tìm được ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài, phương pháp nghiên cứu còn sơ khai, và số liệu quá ngắn.

Về cơ bản trong lý thuyết và thực nghiệm, nợ nước ngoài có mối quan hệ với tăng trưởng kinh tế. Quan hệ này có thể là tuyến tính hay phi tuyến tính. Nó ảnh hưởng tích cực hoặc tiêu cực đến tăng trưởng kinh tế. Nếu nợ nước ngoài trong ngưỡng cho phép thì sẽ thúc đẩy tăng trưởng kinh tế vì nó bổ sung nguồn vốn quan trọng cho đầu tư, song, tỷ lệ nợ nước ngoài lớn quá ngưỡng cho phép thì tác động ngược lại (Cohen, 1993). Do đó, nợ nước ngoài luôn tồn tại hai mặt, việc Chính Phủ biết quản lý linh hoạt và có chiến lược phù hợp với tình hình của đất nước sẽ đưa nước ta tăng trưởng nhanh và bền vững. Mặt khác, Chính Phủ lạm dụng và sử dụng vốn thiếu linh hoạt, tức là vay nhiều hơn từ nước ngoài sẽ tạo ra áp lực trả nợ cả hiện tại và tương lai, điều này rất nguy hại đối với nền kinh tế.

2.3. Phương pháp nghiên cứu

2.3.1. Xây dựng mô hình nghiên cứu

Về mặt thực nghiệm, để đánh giá tác động của nợ nước ngoài đối với tăng trưởng kinh

tế, đa số các nghiên cứu dựa trên một số cơ sở lý thuyết như: lý thuyết nợ quá mức, lý thuyết cân bằng David Ricardo, hay các lý thuyết tân cổ điển. Bài viết này dựa vào lập luận về mối quan hệ phi tuyến giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế để đánh giá ảnh hưởng của nợ quá mức đối với nền kinh tế (Krugman P. , 1988), (Reinhart & Rogoff, 2010).

Bài viết sẽ đưa gánh nặng nợ nước ngoài như một biến trong hàm sản xuất (Cobb & Douglas, 1928) được đề xuất bởi (Cunningham, 1993). Bởi vì gánh nặng nợ có vai trò quan trọng đối với năng suất của vốn và lao động. Rõ ràng một quốc gia mang gánh nặng nợ lớn đòi hỏi phải phân bổ nguồn lực để thực hiện nghĩa vụ trả nợ của mình, do đó quyết định đến việc làm của người lao động và vốn trong hàm sản xuất. Do đó, khi đưa biến nợ vào mô hình sản xuất cổ điển với mục tiêu là giải thích mối quan hệ gánh nặng nợ và tăng trưởng kinh tế:

$$Y = f(K, L, Nợ) \quad (\text{pt1})$$

Trong đó: Y = sản lượng của nền kinh tế, K = trữ lượng vốn, L = lực lượng lao động, Nợ = gánh nặng nợ nước ngoài của quốc gia được đánh giá qua “% nợ nước ngoài/ GDP”. Tuy nhiên, giả định của hàm sản xuất trên là năng suất không đổi theo qui mô, các yếu tố đầu vào là không đổi, công nghệ không ảnh hưởng đến tăng trưởng tại thời điểm đang xét (tức công nghệ trung tính)

Từ phương trình (pt 1), dựa trên lý thuyết giảm nợ (đường cong laffer nợ) của (Krugman P. , 1988) bài viết đề xuất mô hình đánh giá tác động của nợ công đến tăng trưởng kinh tế như sau:

$$GDPgrowth_t = \alpha + \beta_1 * DEBT + \beta_i X_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (\text{pt 2})$$

Để đánh giá tác động của nợ quá mức, bài viết cần xây dựng ngưỡng nợ tối ưu của nền kinh tế. Phương trình (2) được biến đổi theo độ ngưỡng của nợ như sau:

$$GDPgrowth_t = \alpha + \beta_1 * DEBT + \beta_i X_i + \varepsilon_i ; DEBT \geq Z \quad \text{với } Z \text{ là ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài (PT 3)}$$

$$GDPgrowth_t = \alpha + \beta_1 * DEBT + \beta_i X_i + \varepsilon_i ; DEBT \leq Z \quad \text{với } Y \text{ là ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài (PT4)}$$

Trong đó:

- **GDPgrowth_t** là tốc độ tăng GDP hàng năm tại thời điểm t làm biến độc lập, đánh giá mức độ tăng trưởng của nền kinh tế;
- **DEBT** là tỷ lệ nợ nước ngoài/GDP tại thời điểm t, biến này đánh giá mức độ thay đổi của nợ nước ngoài so với GDP.
- **X_i** : là các biến kiểm soát của mô hình
- **ε_t**: là phần dư của mô hình
- **α**: là hệ số chặn của mô hình

Các biến kiểm soát (X_i) của mô hình được đề xuất ở (Bảng 1) gồm:

+ **POP RATE**: là tốc độ tăng dân số. Tốc độ tăng trưởng dân số thực sự ảnh hưởng đến tốc độ tăng trưởng kinh tế, bởi vì, khi tốc độ tăng dân số cao hơn mức tăng sản lượng của nền kinh tế tạo ra thì tốc độ tăng trưởng kinh tế giảm.

+ **Log(investment)**: là logarit nepe của tỷ lệ đầu tư so với GDP, được sử dụng làm biến kiểm soát để cho thấy tác động nhỏ hơn của nợ vào tăng trưởng kinh tế. Rõ ràng, một phần nợ

nước ngoài ảnh hưởng đến nền kinh tế qua đầu tư. Tỷ lệ đầu tư càng cao dẫn đến sự tích lũy vốn vật chất cũng gia tăng trong nền kinh tế. Sử dụng logarit nêpe của tỷ lệ đầu tư để cho thấy tỷ lệ tăng đầu tư sẽ tác động đến tăng trưởng.

+ **THNS**: là biến thâm hụt ngân sách của Chính Phủ/GDP, thể hiện tình trạng cán cân ngân sách của đất nước, nó có mối quan hệ với nợ nước ngoài, và tăng trưởng kinh tế;

+ **Openness**: là biến độ mở thương mại cũng có tác động tích cực đến tăng trưởng kinh tế, vì nâng cao năng suất thông qua chuyển giao kiến thức, chuyển giao công nghệ từ nước ngoài. Độ mở thương mại còn có quan hệ mật thiết đến cán cân vãng lai của đất nước, do đó, nó thể hiện tác động của ngoại thương đến tình hình kinh tế trong nước, và đồng thời cán cân vãng lai cũng ảnh hưởng đến nợ nước ngoài;

+ **Inflation**: lạm phát được sử dụng như biến kiểm soát của mô hình để đánh giá mức độ trượt giá của khoản nợ nước ngoài. Lạm phát có mối quan hệ mật thiết với tăng trưởng kinh tế, và các chính sách quản lý nợ của Chính Phủ.

Bài viết sử dụng phương pháp ước lượng bình phương tối thiểu (OLS), kết hợp với ước lượng ngưỡng của Hansen (1999) chạy vòng lặp (10000 lần) để cho thấy rõ hơn mối quan hệ của nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng theo cách tiếp cận ngưỡng. Với điểm mới này, bài nghiên cứu đã khắc phục được những yếu điểm hạn chế số liệu như các bài nghiên cứu trước đó.

2.3.2. Mô tả dữ liệu

Từ khi Việt Nam mở cửa nền kinh tế (1986) đến nay đã hơn 36 năm, tỷ lệ nợ nước ngoài/GDP của Việt Nam biến động liên tục. Vào năm 1990 nợ nước ngoài ở Việt Nam rất cao, bởi vì toàn bộ số nợ được cộng dồn trước đó và chuyển đổi nợ từ đồng rúp sang đồng USD. Sau đó các khoản nợ ngày càng giảm, một phần vì số nợ được trả và xóa, mặc khác giá trị GDP và xuất khẩu ngày càng tăng dẫn đến tỷ lệ nợ giảm. Những năm gần đây tỷ lệ nợ nước ngoài đang gia tăng trở lại do nhu cầu đầu tư cho xã hội tăng cần phải vay mượn từ trong nước và nước ngoài.

Hình 3: Nợ nước ngoài/GDP và tốc độ tăng GDP

Nguồn: tác giả vẽ từ số liệu của Ngân Hàng Thế Giới

Bảng 1: Tổng hợp mô tả dữ liệu trong mô hình và kỳ vọng dấu

Tên biến	Giải thích biến	Nguồn thu thập	Nghiên cứu đề xuất	Kỳ vọng dấu trong mô hình
GDPgrowth	Tốc độ tăng trưởng kinh tế hàng năm của Việt Nam	WB	Reinhart and Rogoff (2010) ; Pattillo và cộng sự (2002)	
DEBT	% nợ nước ngoài so với GDP	WB, ADB	Reinhart and Rogoff (2010); Pattillo và cộng sự (2002)	+/-
Inflation	% tỷ lệ lạm phát	WB	Sử Đình Thành (2012); Phan Minh Xích TỰ (2014)	+
LOG(Investment/GDP)	Logarit nepe của tỷ lệ đầu tư so với GDP	IMF, WB	Reinhart and Rogoff (2010); IMF(2022)	+
Poprate	Tốc độ tăng dân số hàng năm	WB	Reinhart and Rogoff (2010);	-
OPENESS	Độ mở của nền kinh tế là tổng giá trị xuất và nhập khẩu so với GDP	WB	Sử Đình Thành (2012)	+
THNS	Thâm hụt ngân sách nhà nước so với GDP	GSO	Reinhart and Rogoff (2010) ;Hoàng Khắc Lịch (2018); IMF(2022)	-

Nguồn: Tổng hợp mô tả dữ liệu và kỳ vọng của tác giả

3. KẾT QUẢ VÀ THẢO LUẬN

3.1. Ước lượng ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài tối ưu cho tăng trưởng kinh tế tại Việt Nam

Dựa vào lý thuyết nợ quá mức, nghiên cứu xây dựng ngưỡng nợ tối ưu của nền kinh tế thông qua phương pháp tìm ngưỡng của Hansen (1999) và chạy số lần lặp lại của mô hình 10000 lần. Tác giả tìm ra ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài/GDP của Việt Nam theo mô hình (2) là gần bằng 75.8%²⁷.

Bảng 2: Xác định ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài tích cực đối với tăng trưởng kinh tế

Number of Bootstrap Replications:	10000
Trimming Percentage:	.15
Threshold Estimate:	75.8000031
LM-test for no threshold:	7.50887531
Bootstrap P-Value:	.0386

Nguồn: Tính toán của tác giả

²⁷ Phụ lục 2

Hình 4: Kiểm định F test ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài

Nguồn: Tính toán của tác giả

Bảng 3: Kết quả nghiên cứu so sánh với nghiên cứu khác

	Giá trị ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài/GDP				Ngưỡng nợ công theo Sứ Đình Thành (2012) tính toán
Tác giả tính toán	Reinhart and Rogoff (2010)	Pattillo và cộng sự (2002)	Nghiên cứu Nguyễn Xuân Trường (2019)		
Giá trị ngưỡng tích cực	75.8%	90%	35% - 40%	21,5%	75,8%

Nguồn: Tính toán của tác giả

3.2. Kết quả ước lượng theo giá trị ngưỡng nợ

Từ số liệu của mẫu nghiên cứu, tiến hành ước lượng mô hình (Pt 3), (pt 4). Kết quả ước lượng với biến phụ thuộc là tốc độ tăng GDP bình quân đầu người như sau:

Bảng 4: Kết quả ước lượng mô hình giữa tăng trưởng kinh tế với nợ nước ngoài/ GDP

Tên biến	Phương pháp ước lượng bình phương tối thiểu (OLS)	
	phương trình 3 Debt/GDP $\geq$ 75.8%	phương trình 4 Debt/GDP $\leq$ 75.8%
GDPgrowth		
debt	- 0.04316**	0.07756
Log(investment)	- 2.02937	1.574251
thns	0.130073*	0.20933
poprate	10.01876***	1.019008

Tên biến	Phương pháp ước lượng bình phương tối thiểu (OLS)	
	phương trình 3 Debt/GDP $\geq$ 75.8%	phương trình 4 Debt/GDP $\leq$ 75.8%
openess	- 0.01933	- 0.01822
inflation	0.020807	- 0.01168
Hệ số chặn (C)	4.30991	0.420831
R ²	0.9702	0.3935

Ghi chú: *** p<0.01; ** p<0.05; * p<0.1

Nguồn: Tính toán của tác giả

Các kiểm định sau khi ước lượng theo phương pháp OLS được trình bày ở phụ lục 2, kết quả kiểm định cho thấy kết quả thực nghiệm ở trên là tối ưu để phân tích tác động của nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế.

3.3. Phân tích kết quả ước lượng

- Kết quả ở **bảng 2** cho thấy: giá trị ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài tối ưu cho tăng trưởng kinh tế là 75.8 % so với GDP. Kết quả này thấp hơn nhiều so với nghiên cứu Reinhart and Rogoff (2010), điều này chứng tỏ rằng: với những đặc thù và thực trạng của từng nền kinh tế thì ngưỡng nợ sẽ thay đổi. Đồng thời, nghiên cứu này lại đưa ra kết quả cao hơn nghiên cứu của Nguyễn Xuân Trường (2019) vì số liệu của bài viết được sử dụng là năm trong khi đó nghiên cứu Nguyễn Xuân Trường là quý.

- Một kết quả thú vị của bài viết là kết quả ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài/GDP tích cực cho tăng trưởng kinh tế lại giống với kết quả nghiên cứu ngưỡng nợ công với tăng trưởng kinh tế của Sử Đình Thành (2012), nguyên nhân được giải thích là: số liệu nợ nước ngoài của Việt Nam trước những năm 2000 được sử dụng như số liệu nợ công của Việt Nam, vì thế kết quả giữa 2 bài viết giống nhau.

- Kết quả ước lượng mô hình giữa tăng trưởng kinh tế với nợ nước ngoài/GDP ở **bảng 3** cho thấy giá trị nợ nước ngoài/GDP lớn hơn 75.8% có quan hệ nghịch chiều và có ý nghĩa thống kê với tốc độ tăng trưởng kinh tế. Điều này chứng tỏ, khi mức nợ nước ngoài vượt ngưỡng cho phép sẽ ảnh hưởng tiêu cực đến tăng trưởng kinh tế tại nước ta. Ngoài ra, ở PT4 biến số nợ nước ngoài/GDP không có ý nghĩa thống kê.

- Trong chiến lược quản lý nợ của Chính Phủ đến năm 2030 là kiểm soát nợ nước ngoài/GDP ở mức dưới 45%²⁸ so với GDP. Theo như nghiên cứu này, khả năng chịu đựng nợ nước ngoài đối với tăng trưởng kinh tế lên đến 75.8%, vậy thì chính sách quản lý nợ của Chính Phủ là phù hợp với khả năng chịu áp lực nợ nước ngoài.

- Từ năm 2021 Chính Phủ đã thay đổi cách tính toán GDP quốc gia, khi đó quy mô GDP của Việt Nam sẽ tăng thêm 25,4%²⁹. Khi đó, tỷ lệ nợ nước ngoài/GDP sẽ giảm xuống, điều này giúp tăng dự trữ tài khóa góp phần phục hồi và tăng trưởng kinh tế nhanh và bền vững.

Tóm lại, với tình hình dịch Covid-19 đã cơ bản được kiểm soát, việc khôi phục nền kinh

²⁸ Quyết định 460/QĐ –TTg 2022 v/v phê duyệt chiến lược nợ đến năm 2030

²⁹ Nguồn www.GSO.gov.vn

tế nhanh và bền vững sau đại dịch là cấp thiết. Song, việc kiểm soát tỷ lệ nợ trong ngưỡng cho phép là cần thiết, nguyên nhân vì: dịch bệnh làm tổn hại và suy giảm tốc độ tăng trưởng kinh tế, đồng thời các khoản nợ được tích lũy thông qua thời kỳ dịch tăng dần. Do đó, để kiểm soát nợ nước ngoài trong ngưỡng và an toàn thì Chính Phủ còn phải xem xét thêm những yếu tố khác như: cơ cấu nợ, khả năng trả nợ trong tương lai, mục đích việc sử dụng nguồn vốn vay, đảm bảo được niềm tin của thị trường, và có chiến lược quản lý nợ hợp lý. Kết quả ngưỡng nợ tích cực cho tăng trưởng kinh tế cho thấy với điều kiện hiện tại của đất nước thì Chính Phủ nên đảm bảo nợ ở mức ngưỡng cho phép. Trong tương lai, nếu đất nước có những thay đổi về thể chế, chiến lược quản lý nợ hợp lý... thì ngưỡng nợ sẽ cao hơn.

4. KẾT LUẬN VÀ KHUYẾN NGHỊ

4.1. Kết luận

Thông qua nghiên cứu, ta nhận thấy có 3 vấn đề liên quan đến quan hệ nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế ở Việt Nam như sau:

Thứ nhất: Bài nghiên cứu tìm ra ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài/GDP tối ưu cho nền kinh tế là 75.8%. Kết quả ước lượng cho thấy khi nợ nước ngoài vượt ngưỡng cho phép thì sẽ ảnh hưởng xấu đến nền kinh tế. Tuy giá trị ngưỡng nợ tìm được ở Bảng 2 lớn hơn mục tiêu quản lý nợ của Chính Phủ đến năm 2030, nhưng chúng ta không chủ quan với những con số hiện tại, vì xu hướng nợ nước ngoài/GDP của Việt Nam có thể gia tăng nhanh sau đại dịch.

Thứ hai: ta thấy biến nợ nước ngoài/GDP vượt ngưỡng 75.8% sẽ có tác động tiêu cực với tốc độ tăng trưởng kinh tế. Đồng thời, khi nợ nước ngoài/GDP nằm dưới mức 75.8% thì tác động của nợ nước ngoài đến tăng trưởng kinh tế không có ý nghĩa thống kê.

Thứ ba: thâm hụt ngân sách, tốc độ tăng dân số tác động cùng chiều với tăng trưởng kinh tế nếu nợ nước ngoài vượt ngưỡng nợ cho phép. Kết quả ước lượng cho thấy, nếu nợ nước ngoài/GDP >75.8%, khi thâm hụt ngân sách tăng 1% thì về mặt trung bình tăng trưởng kinh tế tăng 0.13%, tuy nhiên nếu thâm hụt ngân sách trong thời gian dài sẽ ảnh hưởng đến dư địa tài khóa từ đó ảnh hưởng đến nợ công và nợ nước ngoài.

Tóm lại, giữa nợ nước ngoài và tăng trưởng kinh tế thật sự có mối quan hệ, và mối quan hệ tùy thuộc vào ngưỡng nợ. Nền tảng của quản lý nợ phải xuất phát từ cải cách thực sự của bộ máy nhà nước, đề ra chiến lược quản lý nợ rõ ràng, tạo niềm tin cho thị trường.

4.2. Khuyến nghị

Trước bối cảnh tình hình kinh tế vĩ mô của nước ta cũng như trên thế giới đang rất phức tạp sau khủng hoảng do dịch bệnh Covid-19 gây ra. Nước ta đang gặp phải những nguy cơ và khó khăn trong việc quản lý, huy động, và sử dụng nguồn lực từ trong và ngoài nước. Điều này gây ra sự gia tăng liên tục nợ nước ngoài những năm gần đây và trong cả tương lai gần. Qua phân tích, tác giả xin đề xuất khuyến nghị về việc quản lý nợ nước ngoài tốt phục vụ cho mục tiêu tăng trưởng kinh tế nhanh và ổn định là “thiết lập kỷ luật tài chính để kiểm soát nợ nước ngoài/GDP dưới mức 75.8% /GDP

Bằng chứng thực nghiệm cho thấy ngưỡng nợ tích cực cho tăng trưởng kinh tế đối với Việt Nam là 75.8% so với GDP. Tuy mức nợ nước ngoài/GDP hiện nay vẫn nằm trong vùng ngưỡng cho phép, nhưng chúng ta không chủ quan vì nền kinh tế nước ta đang đối mặt với

nhiều nguy cơ làm nợ nước ngoài tăng trong tương lai như: ảnh hưởng của dịch bệnh Covid gây ra, tình hình địa chính trị thế giới ngày càng phức tạp. Vì vậy, ngay bây giờ Việt Nam phải có chiến lược kiểm soát nợ hợp lý, kết hợp với sự phối hợp nhịp nhàng các chính sách của Chính Phủ như giảm bội chi ngân sách đặc biệt là chi thường xuyên, giảm nguồn vay mới, cơ cấu lại nguồn nợ, kích thích sản xuất hàng hóa trong nước và hướng đến tăng xuất khẩu... để đưa mức nợ nước ngoài/GDP dưới mức ngưỡng mà không ảnh hưởng đến tăng trưởng kinh tế trong tương lai. Ngoài ra, trong dài hạn Việt Nam cần cải thiện về thể chế, chất lượng quản trị, hay giảm tham nhũng thì ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài được gia tăng, từ đó tạo dư địa tốt cho tăng trưởng kinh tế.

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PHỤ LỤC 1

KIỂM TRA TÍNH CHẤT DỮ LIỆU

Kiểm tra tính chất của dữ liệu

Bảng 1: Thống kê mô tả các biến trong mô hình

Tên biến	Số quan sát	Trung bình	Độ lệch chuẩn	Giá trị tối thiểu	Giá trị tối đa
gdpgrowth	37	6.451849	1.694066	2.561551	9.540481
debt	37	86.06011	98.67296	27.5	450.64
investment	37	28.42456	7.93703	12.6	39.56627
thns	37	-3.726216	2.062678	-9.9	0.6
poprate	37	1.438754	.5121649	0.155204	2.4608
openess	37	130.4218	50.30167	57.8947	210.4002
inflation	37	43.13208	106.1289	-1.71034	411.0403

Nguồn: Tính toán từ chương trình stata 15

Qua thống kê mô tả ta thấy được giá trị trung bình, tối đa, tối thiểu, và độ lệch chuẩn của toàn bộ các biến trong mô hình.

Kiểm tra tính dừng của chuỗi số liệu

Trước khi thực hiện ước lượng mô hình, bài nghiên cứu cần thực hiện kiểm tra tính dừng của từng biến trong mô hình. Bài nghiên cứu sử dụng kiểm định nghiệm đơn vị của từng biến riêng biệt để kiểm tra tính dừng bằng phương pháp ADF (Augmented Dickey-Fuller)

Giả thuyết kiểm tra tính dừng:

H_0 : chuỗi số liệu là không dừng

H_1 : chuỗi số liệu là dừng

Nếu trị tuyệt đối của thống kê t > giá trị kiểm định ở mức ý nghĩa α thì chấp nhận giả thuyết H_0 và ngược lại là bác bỏ giả thuyết H_0

Bảng 2: Kiểm tra tính dừng của chuỗi số liệu

Tên biến	Giá trị thống kê t bậc 0	Giá trị thống kê t ở bậc dừng cao khác	Kết luận ở mức ý nghĩa 5%
gdpgrowth	-3.683***		Chuỗi dừng
debt		-3.030***	Không dừng bậc 0, dừng ở bậc 1
investment	-2.896***		Dừng bậc 0
thns	-3.683***		dừng ở bậc 0
poprate		-3.675***	Không dừng bậc 0, dừng ở bậc 1
openess	-3.682***		Chuỗi dừng

Ghi chú: ***, **, * chỉ mức ý nghĩa 1%, 5%, 10% ;

Nguồn: Tính toán từ chương trình Eview 8

Qua kết quả kiểm định tính dừng, ta thấy các biến không dừng ở cùng một bậc, do vậy, nếu ước lượng có thể mô hình sẽ xảy ra hiện tượng đồng liên kết.

PHỤ LỤC 2

Ước lượng tìm ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài so với GDP

```
. thresholdtest gdpgrowth debt , q( debt ) trim_per(0.15) rep(10000)
```

Test of Null of No Threshold Against Alternative of Threshold
Allowing Heteroskedastic Errors (White Corrected)

Number of Bootstrap Replications: 10000
Trimming Percentage: .15

Threshold Estimate: 75.8000031
LM-test for no threshold: 7.50887531
Bootstrap P-Value: .0398

Ước lượng ngưỡng nợ nước ngoài so với GDP với tăng trưởng kinh tế.

Trường hợp: nợ nước ngoài/GDP >75.8%

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	11
Model	29.0246365	6	4.83743942	F(6, 4)	=	21.71
Residual	.891270193	4	.222817548	Prob > F	=	0.0051
				R-squared	=	0.9702
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9255
Total	29.9159067	10	2.99159067	Root MSE	=	.47204

gdpgrowth	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
debt	-.0431552	.0133038	-3.24	0.032	-.0800925 - .0062179
loginvestment	-2.029369	1.006092	-2.02	0.114	-4.822728 .7639913
thns	.1300728	.0748301	1.74	0.157	-.077689 .3378346
poprate	10.01876	1.521951	6.58	0.003	5.793143 14.24437
openess	-.019334	.0330185	-0.59	0.590	-.1110082 .0723402
inflation	.020807	.0275595	0.75	0.492	-.0557104 .0973245
_cons	4.30991	6.867482	0.63	0.564	-14.75728 23.3771

Trường hợp: nợ nước ngoài/GDP <75.8%

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	26
Model	23.1781776	6	3.8630296	F(6, 19)	=	2.05
Residual	35.727699	19	1.88040521	Prob > F	=	0.1078
				R-squared	=	0.3935
				Adj R-squared	=	0.2019
Total	58.9058766	25	2.35623507	Root MSE	=	1.3713

gdpgrowth	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
debt	.0775596	.053679	1.44	0.165	-.0347918 .189911
loginvestment	1.574251	3.159669	0.50	0.624	-5.039012 8.187513
thns	.2093296	.2160272	0.97	0.345	-.2428206 .6614797
poprate	1.019008	1.219319	0.84	0.414	-1.533057 3.571072
openess	-.0182152	.0119867	-1.52	0.145	-.0433036 .0068731
inflation	-.0116772	.0089834	-1.30	0.209	-.0304798 .0071254
_cons	.4208312	11.67515	0.04	0.972	-24.01555 24.85721

TÁC ĐỘNG CỦA FINTECH ĐẾN KHẢ NĂNG PHỤC HỒI CỦA DOANH NGHIỆP SAU ĐẠI DỊCH COVID-19

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Tóm Tắt

Sử dụng dữ liệu giai đoạn 2020 đến 2021 của các doanh nghiệp phi tài chính trên thị trường Việt Nam, nghiên cứu này xem xét ảnh hưởng của Fintech đến quá trình phục hồi của doanh nghiệp trong giai đoạn đối diện với những thách thức kinh tế từ đại dịch Covid. Kết quả cho thấy trình độ Fintech địa phương giúp doanh nghiệp rút ngắn thời gian hồi phục. Nghiên cứu cũng cho thấy sự không đồng nhất giữa mức độ ảnh hưởng của các doanh nghiệp quy mô lớn và doanh nghiệp quy mô nhỏ đối với tác động thúc đẩy quá trình phục hồi của doanh nghiệp.

Từ khóa: Fintech, khả năng phục hồi, Covid-19

THE IMPACT OF FINTECH ON FIRM RECOVERY AFTER COVID-19

Abstract

Using data from 2020 to 2021 of non-financial listed firms in Vietnam, this study investigates the impact of Fintech on firm resilience in the period facing economic challenges from the Covid pandemic. The results show that the region's Fintech level helps firms to shorten their recovery time. The study also finds a difference between the magnitude of the influence of large and small firms on business recovery.

Keywords: Fintech, resilience, Covid pandemic

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Sự bùng phát đột ngột của đại dịch COVID-19 đã gây ra một cuộc khủng hoảng sức khỏe cộng đồng nghiêm trọng, tàn phá nền kinh tế toàn cầu (Arora và cộng sự, 2020; Ding và cộng sự, 2021). Bóng đen do đại dịch đã gây ra một gánh nặng vô cùng lớn lên nền kinh tế toàn cầu nói chung và hệ thống doanh nghiệp các quốc gia nói riêng. Trong điều kiện này, sự tồn tại của doanh nghiệp bị đe dọa nặng nề (Miyakawa và cộng sự, 2021). Nhiều nghiên cứu đã ra đời với mục đích tìm hiểu mối liên hệ giữa khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp và các yếu tố mang tính hệ thống, tiêu biểu như các yếu tố trách nhiệm xã hội, đầu tư bền vững (BlackRock, 2020), cấu trúc tổ chức (Hillmann và Guenther, 2020), chuyển đổi số (Peschl và Schüth, 2022), đặc biệt là tài chính kỹ thuật số - Fintech (Xia và cộng sự, 2022; Suri và cộng sự, 2021). World Bank cũng đồng ý rằng sử dụng kỹ thuật số là chìa khóa để khôi phục sau Covid-19. Ứng dụng công nghệ trong thời kỳ này là xu hướng tất yếu cho quá trình hồi phục. Fintech trở thành đại diện cho một cuộc cách mạng kỹ thuật số có thể thay đổi toàn cảnh thị

trường, là động lực quan trọng và cũng là phương tiện để đạt được những kết quả đột phá ở nhiều quốc gia (Phạm Thị Huyền, 2019). Đặc trưng với các giải pháp thay thế tài chính, cho phép mở rộng khả năng tiếp cận cũng như giảm chi phí tìm kiếm nguồn tài trợ, Fintech được kỳ vọng mang trong mình khả năng tái định hình nền kinh tế thông qua hỗ trợ khả năng hồi phục của hệ thống doanh nghiệp. Trong quá khứ, đã có nhiều nghiên cứu về tác động của Fintech, nhưng các nghiên cứu trước đây vẫn còn một số hạn chế nhất định. Hạn chế điển hình là cách thức đo lường biến số đại diện cho Fintech. Hầu hết các nghiên cứu tại các quốc gia đang phát triển, bao gồm các nghiên cứu tại Việt Nam tiến hành đo lường Fintech thông qua khảo sát định tính (Suri và cộng sự, 2021; Misrina & Nuskiya, 2021; Nathan và cộng sự, 2022) thay vì nghiên cứu định lượng, nguyên nhân chính đến từ việc rất ít các quốc gia đầu tư phát triển riêng một hệ thống chỉ số đo lường trình độ Fintech, ngoại trừ những quốc gia có trình độ công nghệ tiên tiến như Trung Quốc (Yanchun Xia và cộng sự, 2022). Theo nhận định từ nghiên cứu của Duncan Pedersen (1992), cách đo lường thông qua khảo sát không thể tối ưu chính xác hiệu quả bởi sự đơn giản hóa quá mức của thực tế xã hội, việc thiết kế bảng câu hỏi với các phân loại mang tính chủ quan thể hiện cái nhìn thiên lệch và quá đơn giản về thực tế.

Kế thừa và phát triển dựa trên những nghiên cứu trong quá khứ, kết hợp cùng tình trạng cấp thiết của nhu cầu hồi phục sau đại dịch, bài nghiên cứu được tiến hành với mong muốn bổ sung những khoảng trống của các nghiên cứu trước đây trong kho tàng học thuật, cải thiện chất lượng nghiên cứu thông qua phân tích định lượng với phạm vi mẫu là các doanh nghiệp tại một quốc gia. Bài nghiên cứu hướng đến tìm hiểu vai trò của FINTECH trong việc định hình khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp sau đại dịch COVID-19 thông qua phân tích giá cổ phiếu của các công ty niêm yết trên thị trường chứng khoán Việt Nam giai đoạn 2020 – 2021.

2. TỔNG QUAN CÁC NGHIÊN CỨU TRƯỚC

Fintech tích hợp công nghệ thông tin với các dịch vụ tài chính truyền thống, giúp doanh nghiệp mở rộng khả năng tiếp cận tài chính thông qua các kênh kỹ thuật số. Việc áp dụng tài chính kỹ thuật số cho phép thúc đẩy tương tác từ xa, cải thiện khả năng tiếp cận và phạm vi của các dịch vụ tài trợ, qua đó đặc biệt phát huy lợi ích trong thời kỳ giãn cách xã hội. Trên cơ sở đó hàng loạt những nghiên cứu ra đời, hướng đến phân tích tác động của Fintech lên nhiều khía cạnh, tiêu biểu như những nghiên cứu sau.

Nghiên cứu của Suri và cộng sự (2021) tìm hiểu tác động của Fintech đến khả năng hồi phục của các hộ gia đình ở Kenya – Đông Phi. Sử dụng dữ liệu thanh toán điện tử hàng tháng từ Ngân hàng Trung ương, dữ liệu hiệu suất tài chính từ cuộc khảo sát hộ gia đình và các cuộc khảo sát không gian địa lý, nghiên cứu phân tích tác động của khoản vay kỹ thuật số M-Shwari đến khả năng thúc đẩy giao dịch của các bên liên quan trong vòng 3 năm kể từ ngày đăng ký khoản vay. Kết quả cho thấy các hộ gia đình đối mặt với các cú sốc kinh tế dễ dàng hơn thông qua sở hữu khả năng tiếp cận các khoản vay ngắn hạn với chi phí tổng thể thấp. Khoản vay M-Shwari này cũng ít có khả năng đưa các hộ gia đình vào chu kỳ có hại của nợ nần và phá sản, ngược lại, tiếp cận sản phẩm này giúp tăng khả năng phục hồi của hộ gia đình khi đối mặt với những cú sốc tiêu cực. Nghiên cứu cho thấy khả năng tiếp cận dễ dàng do công nghệ di động có thể là một đặc điểm cực kỳ quan trọng để mở rộng khả năng tiếp cận tín dụng cho các nhóm dân cư không có khả năng tiếp cận tài chính chính thức. Nghiên cứu đóng góp quan trọng vào vấn đề tài chính hộ gia đình ở các nước đang phát triển, theo đó các khoản vay kỹ thuật số

ngắn hạn này phần lớn được sử dụng để trả tiền học, sinh hoạt, cho các mục đích khẩn cấp và không phải cho kinh doanh hoặc vốn lưu động. Khoản vay kỹ thuật số được chứng minh mang lại lợi ích cho tất cả các bên trong giao dịch cho vay của hộ gia đình, thông qua tăng cường khả năng tiếp cận, giảm chi phí của bên đi vay, đồng thời tối thiểu hóa chi phí hành chính cho việc cung cấp tín dụng. Mặc dù kết quả đem đến cái nhìn khả quan về ảnh hưởng của Fintech, nhưng chỉ dừng lại ở cấp độ hộ gia đình – chiếm phần trăm khá nhỏ trong việc đóng góp xây dựng nền kinh tế quốc dân và toàn cầu.

Nghiên cứu mới đây của Misrina và Nuskiya (2021) tiến hành phân tích tác động của Fintech lên hoạt động làm việc từ xa (Work From Home) và hệ thống thanh toán qua điện thoại Mobile Banking của ngân hàng Hời giáo Sri Lanka trong điều kiện diễn ra đại dịch COVID-19. Nghiên cứu sử dụng dữ liệu được thu thập thông qua khảo sát định tính và các kỹ thuật thu thập dữ liệu sơ cấp với phạm vi 38 mẫu. Các tác giả tiến hành sử dụng nhiều phương pháp đo lường để kiểm định các giả thuyết, từ phần mềm thống kê SPSS, thống kê mô tả, kiểm tra độ tin cậy của mô hình cho đến phân tích tương quan và mô hình hồi quy. Cuối cùng, nghiên cứu kết luận rằng ngân hàng đóng vai trò là một công cụ tuyệt vời trong việc khuyến khích người tiêu dùng sử dụng các dịch vụ công nghệ trong điều kiện làm việc từ xa kết hợp với việc thanh toán qua Mobile Banking trong điều kiện đối diện với giãn cách xã hội. Qua đó tăng khả năng tiếp cận vốn đối với các khách hàng cá nhân và những người tiêu dùng nhỏ lẻ, nghiên cứu cũng đưa ra kết quả rằng việc tích hợp công nghệ tài chính vào hệ thống hoạt động sẽ giúp ngân hàng mở rộng phạm vi tiếp cận khách hàng thông qua công nghệ mặc định. Tương tác này đồng thời qua đó thúc đẩy 2 chiều lên hệ thống Fintech, khuyến khích sự sáng tạo trong việc phát triển các tiện ích công nghệ mới, đồng thời giúp làm tăng số lượng giao dịch kinh doanh, đem đến lợi ích cho tất cả các bên. Nghiên cứu khẳng định mối quan hệ tích cực của Fintech đem đến cho phân khúc khách hàng cá nhân và hệ thống ngân hàng thông qua tăng tính thuận tiện và giảm chi phí giao dịch trong thời kỳ giãn cách xã hội tại Sri Lanka.

Nghiên cứu mới đây của Nathan và cộng sự (2022) được thúc đẩy dựa trên nhận thức độ chênh lệch cao giữa 2 nhóm đã và chưa sử dụng ngân hàng ở Việt Nam, kết hợp với mức độ hiểu biết tài chính của người trưởng thành thấp hơn so với khu vực ASEAN. Nghiên cứu điều tra sự hiểu biết về tài chính, mức độ phổ biến trong việc sử dụng Fintech và tác động của cuộc khủng hoảng COVID -19 lên sức khỏe tài chính của người tiêu dùng ở Việt Nam. Sau khi thu thập dữ liệu từ khảo sát bảng câu hỏi 30 mẫu quan sát, nghiên cứu tiến hành phân tích với phần mềm thống kê IBM SPSS 23 và hồi quy tuyến tính bội để kiểm định các mục tiêu nghiên cứu. Kết quả cho thấy ở Việt Nam, Fintech đóng vai trò thúc đẩy tiếp cận tài chính đến với những người có hiểu biết tài chính thấp. Fintech được cho là thu hút khách hàng hơn khi dễ sử dụng, mức độ hữu ích cao, có uy tín, thương hiệu, nhận được sự đảm bảo của chính phủ. Nghiên cứu tìm thấy bằng chứng cho rằng mức độ hiểu biết tài chính cao ngăn cản khả năng tiếp cận Fintech, bởi lẽ với tầng lớp có hiểu biết nhất định về tài chính, họ không coi Fintech là một công cụ quan trọng cho các giao dịch tài chính vì họ có đủ tiêu chí đảm bảo khả năng tiếp cận mạnh mẽ với các phương tiện tài chính truyền thống, thông qua phạm vi giao dịch, các tài sản thế chấp, uy tín hay thương hiệu được đảm bảo bởi các cơ sở uy tín, với tầng lớp khách hàng này, nhu cầu tiếp cận các nguồn tài trợ thay thế thường không cao so với phân khúc ít hiểu biết về tài chính. Nghiên cứu này đóng góp kho học thuật về ảnh hưởng của Fintech trong thị trường Việt Nam thời điểm bùng phát COVID-19. Bài viết qua đó đề ra phương án thúc đẩy

khả năng tiếp cận tài chính lớn hơn cho người tiêu dùng Việt Nam, các nhà hoạch định chính sách có thể thúc đẩy sự phát triển của cơ sở hạ tầng và các hợp tác quy định để thúc đẩy các công ty khởi nghiệp Fintech.

Nghiên cứu của Ahmed và cộng sự (2022) khám phá vai trò của Fintech ở Bangladesh. Thông qua phương pháp đo lường phỏng vấn định tính mẫu 75 quan sát, các cuộc thảo luận tập trung vào việc đặt các câu hỏi mở về nhân khẩu học, hành vi sử dụng công nghệ liên quan đến Fintech, dịch vụ ngân hàng trực tuyến, nghiên cứu tập trung tìm hiểu các giá trị gia tăng, thách thức và nhận thức của người tiêu dùng về Fintech trong thời kỳ đại dịch đang diễn ra. Nghiên cứu tập trung nhiều hơn vào các vấn đề người dùng phải đối mặt trong quá trình tiếp cận và sử dụng Fintech thông qua các tùy chọn giao dịch không tiếp xúc từ xa trong điều kiện giãn cách xã hội, vốn vẫn chưa được khám phá trong bối cảnh miền Nam toàn cầu. Nghiên cứu chứng minh khả năng xây dựng quá trình phục hồi của người dùng Fintech khi đối mặt với những trải nghiệm tiêu cực. Nghiên cứu cho thấy các dịch vụ Fintech nâng cao khả năng hỗ trợ tài chính và mở ra những cách tiếp cận mới trong thời kỳ dịch bệnh. Bên cạnh đó, nghiên cứu nhận thấy còn tồn tại những rào cản giữa các bên tham gia trong việc sử dụng các dịch vụ Fintech cũng như hậu quả kinh tế của việc bị ngắt kết nối kỹ thuật số trong khoảng thời gian giãn cách. Nghiên cứu cũng cho thấy khoảng cách kỹ thuật số ngày càng rộng và nhận thức cần thiết để giảm thiểu khoảng cách giữa các cộng đồng bị ngắt kết nối kỹ thuật số. Tại một số vùng lãnh thổ, việc đóng cửa giao thương hay giãn cách xã hội trong thời kỳ đại dịch đã biến Fintech thành công cụ tài chính độc quyền với khả năng cung cấp nguồn tài trợ thuận lợi theo một cách an toàn.

Tại Việt Nam, giữa điều kiện phát triển mạnh của Fintech, việc điều tra tác động của Fintech đối với các ngân hàng đã thu hút một số lượng lớn các học giả, sự ra đời của những bài báo, các công trình nghiên cứu ngày càng gia tăng và được khai thác trên nhiều phương diện. Tiêu biểu như nghiên cứu gần đây của Liên và cộng sự (2020). Nghiên cứu hướng đến phân tích xu hướng phát triển ứng dụng Fintech trong lĩnh vực ngân hàng ở Việt Nam. Nhằm nâng cao chất lượng dịch vụ Fintech tại các ngân hàng, nhóm tác giả đã tiến hành xem xét các yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến ý định sử dụng dịch vụ bằng cách thu thập dữ liệu thông qua khảo sát 620 khách hàng của các ngân hàng tại Thành phố Hồ Chí Minh. Nghiên cứu sử dụng hồi quy đa biến để ước lượng mô hình nghiên cứu. Kết quả cho thấy dịch vụ Fintech rất quan trọng đối với lĩnh vực ngân hàng tại Việt Nam. Hơn thế nữa, nghiên cứu đạt được thành công lớn nhờ xác định được các yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến ý định sử dụng dịch vụ Fintech của khách hàng. Theo đó, ý định sử dụng dịch vụ Fintech chịu ảnh hưởng tích cực bởi nhận thức về tính hữu ích, tác động xã hội, lòng tin của khách hàng và cảm nhận về tính dễ sử dụng. Kết quả có phần giống với kết quả nghiên cứu của Nathan và cộng sự (2022) được nhắc đến ở trước. Dựa trên kết quả nghiên cứu này, các nhà quản lý ngân hàng sẽ có cơ sở để nâng cao chất lượng dịch vụ Fintech, kết quả cũng đem lại giá trị cho các nhà hoạch định chính sách và các nhà nghiên cứu.

Đa số cách tiếp cận của những nghiên cứu liên quan đến Fintech, biến số đại diện cho biến Fintech thường được đo lường thông qua khảo sát, nghiên cứu mới đây của Tien cộng sự (2021) đã phát triển cách thức đo lường mới – thông qua từ khóa trên Google tìm kiếm. Nghiên cứu được thực hiện để trả lời câu hỏi 'Các từ khóa liên quan đến Fintech trên Google tìm kiếm có ảnh hưởng đến việc thu hồi vốn của ngân hàng không?' Nghiên cứu sử dụng dữ liệu chuỗi thời gian theo tuần giai đoạn từ ngày 2 tháng 1 năm 2016 cho đến 13 tháng 3 năm 2021, trích xuất

từ Google Trending và trang web Vietstock. Các phát hiện không cho thấy bằng chứng về mối liên hệ của các từ khóa liên quan đến fintech với lợi nhuận ngân hàng. Sử dụng mô hình hồi quy OLS, lợi nhuận của Vietcombank không bị ảnh hưởng đáng kể bởi các từ khóa liên quan đến Fintech. Ngược lại, thuật ngữ “Fintech” và “Mobile Payment” có ý nghĩa tiêu cực với lợi nhuận của Sacombank trong khi từ khóa “P2P Lending” có ý nghĩa tích cực. Nghiên cứu cũng chỉ ra rằng các từ khóa liên quan đến Fintech bằng tiếng Anh được ưu tiên hơn các từ khóa tiếng Việt. Nghiên cứu này cung cấp một khía cạnh mới về tác động của sự chú ý đến Fintech từ người dùng Internet lên ngân hàng, cụ thể là khả năng thu hồi vốn. Mặc dù đem đến cách đo lường mới, nghiên cứu vẫn chịu giới hạn bởi quy mô hạn hẹp của mẫu 2 ngân hàng và sự phân tán của các từ khóa bởi số lượng người sử dụng Internet quá đông. Mẫu chưa đủ khả năng mang tính đại diện cho sự chú ý của nhà đầu tư và toàn bộ hệ thống ngân hàng quốc doanh Việt Nam.

Bên cạnh những nghiên cứu với phạm vi một khu vực cụ thể, những công trình tìm hiểu tác động của Fintech phạm vi xuyên quốc gia cũng lần lượt ra đời. Đối với thị trường quốc tế, nghiên cứu của Liem và cộng sự (2021) dựa trên tập dữ liệu tổng hợp của hệ thống ngân hàng và các biến số kinh tế vĩ mô của 73 quốc gia từ năm 2013 đến năm 2018 để điều tra mối liên hệ giữa tín dụng Fintech đối với sự ổn định của ngân hàng. Biến số Fintech được đo lường bằng tỷ lệ tín dụng Fintech chia cho GDP quốc gia – một biện pháp tiêu chuẩn hóa kiểm soát ảnh hưởng quy mô nền kinh tế trong việc cung cấp tín dụng Fintech. Các biến kiểm soát khác được sử dụng bao gồm lạm phát, GDP khu vực, tính thanh khoản, chỉ số kiểm soát tham nhũng. Nghiên cứu tìm ra một số phát hiện quan trọng. Đầu tiên, tồn tại bằng chứng cho thấy Fintech cải thiện sự ổn định của ngân hàng, mặc dù tốc độ phát triển nhanh của Fintech làm tăng sự cạnh tranh với ngân hàng trong dịch vụ cung cấp tín dụng, nhưng mối liên hệ này đồng thời củng cố sự ổn định của hệ thống ngân hàng. Thứ hai, chia sẻ thông tin về tín dụng làm tăng tính ổn định của ngân hàng. Thứ ba, kết quả nghiên cứu nhận thấy rằng tác động của tín dụng Fintech đối với sự ổn định của ngân hàng có thể phụ thuộc vào việc chia sẻ thông tin tín dụng. Cụ thể hơn, sự hiện diện của các tổ chức chịu trách nhiệm chia sẻ thông tin tín dụng đến các bên liên quan góp phần tạo điều kiện cho tác động tích cực của Fintech lên sự ổn định của ngân hàng. Kết quả này không thay đổi khi sử dụng phương pháp hồi quy khác hay dùng biến phụ thuộc khác.

Nghiên cứu của Luo và cộng sự (2021) tìm hiểu tác động của Fintech đến sự chuyển đổi của hệ thống các doanh nghiệp ở Trung Quốc. Sử dụng dữ liệu của 2064 doanh nghiệp niêm yết ở Trung Quốc từ năm 2012 đến năm 2018 và dựa trên mô hình DEA Malmquist để tính toán tổng năng suất các yếu tố của các thực thể, nghiên cứu cũng sử dụng các biến kiểm soát ở cấp độ tài chính và cấp độ quản trị công ty để kiểm tra mức độ phù hợp của đổi mới Fintech đối với chuyển đổi doanh nghiệp và phát triển kinh tế bền vững. Biến đo lường mức độ phát triển Fintech được xây dựng bằng cách sử dụng phương pháp khai thác văn bản và phân tích nhân tố để kiểm tra mối quan hệ giữa đổi mới Fintech và chuyển đổi doanh nghiệp. Nghiên cứu tìm ra bằng chứng chứng minh rằng đổi mới Fintech cải thiện hiệu quả năng suất các yếu tố tổng thể của các doanh nghiệp, qua đó thúc đẩy chuyển đổi và nâng cấp sự phát triển bền vững của nền kinh tế. Ảnh hưởng của Fintech đến sự chuyển đổi của các doanh nghiệp chủ yếu thông qua hai cơ chế: hiệu ứng thông tin và hiệu ứng phân bổ nguồn lực. Nghiên cứu sâu hơn cho thấy sự không đồng nhất giữa mức độ chịu ảnh hưởng của các doanh nghiệp nhà nước lớn và các doanh nghiệp tư nhân vừa và nhỏ đối với tác động thúc đẩy của Fintech. Nghiên cứu

xây dựng chỉ số Fintech từ bốn chiều phân loại Fintech thông qua việc khai thác và sàng lọc các từ tin tức có liên quan.

Nghiên cứu của Li và cộng sự (2021) kiểm tra cơ chế tác động của Fintech đối với đổi mới công nghệ của doanh nghiệp thông qua mô hình hiệu ứng cố định (FEM), sử dụng dữ liệu thị trường của các doanh nghiệp niêm yết trên sàn A-share ở Thượng Hải và Thâm Quyển thị trường Trung Quốc từ năm 2011–2019. Với chỉ số đo lường Fintech, nghiên cứu sử dụng chỉ số tài chính kỹ thuật số của Đại học Bắc Kinh, một hệ thống chỉ số đa chiều. Kết quả cho thấy tồn tại bằng chứng chứng minh rằng sự phát triển công nghệ Fintech có thể thúc đẩy đáng kể sự đổi mới công nghệ của doanh nghiệp và điều đó tác động đến sự đổi mới công nghệ của công ty thông qua hai cơ chế: giảm bớt các hạn chế về tài chính của công ty và cung cấp cơ hội thị trường cho các công ty để nâng cao lợi nhuận của họ. Ngoài ra, tác động thúc đẩy của Fintech đối với công nghệ sự đổi mới rõ rệt hơn ở các doanh nghiệp mới, doanh nghiệp nhà nước và các doanh nghiệp niêm yết và không vay nợ. Nghiên cứu đề xuất rằng Chính phủ cần tăng cường hỗ trợ, phát triển những chính sách tạo điều kiện cho Fintech tăng tốc phát triển các công nghệ mới nổi như trí tuệ nhân tạo, giúp Fintech nâng cao vị thế, đồng thời thúc đẩy hội nhập sâu rộng, tăng cường nhận diện Fintech cho các doanh nghiệp mới và khuyến khích các bên chung tay xây dựng thị trường lành mạnh để giảm bớt các rào cản tiếp cận, cải thiện hiệu quả của chính sách đổi mới và tận dụng tốt hơn lợi ích từ Fintech.

Nghiên cứu của Karim và cộng sự (2022) xem xét khả năng của FinTech trong việc cung cấp các cơ chế kinh doanh hữu ích cho hệ thống doanh nghiệp vừa và nhỏ ở các quốc gia ASEAN được chọn: Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippine, Singapore và Thái Lan. Nghiên cứu sử dụng phân tích nhân tố và tách mối quan hệ FinTech-SME thành năm nhân tố. Thông qua cuộc khảo sát 300 chủ doanh nghiệp vừa và nhỏ được thu thập thông qua bảng câu hỏi phỏng vấn và khảo sát. Nghiên cứu nhận thấy rằng mối quan hệ giữa FinTech và SME trong thời đại COVID-19 là những yếu tố quan trọng nhất tác động đến sự phát triển của FinTech và tình trạng của các doanh nghiệp vừa và nhỏ. Trong khối ASEAN, các doanh nghiệp vừa và nhỏ chiếm tỷ trọng đáng kể trong toàn bộ nền kinh tế, vào khoảng 89%–99% tổng số doanh nghiệp. Vì thế tác động của Fintech lên phân khúc này mang tính quan trọng và bao hàm lớn. Kết quả được giải thích bởi sự tương tác vật lý bị hạn chế giữa các cá nhân trong giãn cách xã hội bởi đại dịch COVID-19, ngay lập tức làm tăng nhu cầu thực hiện các quyết toán tài chính từ xa và thanh toán trực tuyến bằng cách sử dụng công nghệ kỹ thuật số. Yếu tố này đã mở đường cho việc sử dụng công nghệ và tối đa hóa nguồn lực của các doanh nghiệp vừa và nhỏ ở các nước ASEAN, thúc đẩy sự phát triển của FinTech trong khu vực.

Mặc dù có những đóng góp nhất định về lợi ích của Fintech lên nhiều khía cạnh, các nghiên cứu còn vướng phải một số hạn chế. Về mẫu nghiên cứu, một số chỉ dừng lại ở việc xem xét tác động lên phân khúc khách hàng các nhân, hộ gia đình nhỏ lẻ, chiếm tỷ trọng ít trong cơ cấu tiếp cận vốn, một số khác lại xem xét tác động xuyên quốc gia của Fintech trong khi mỗi quốc gia có những đặc trưng và mức độ chịu ảnh hưởng riêng biệt. Bên cạnh đó, tồn tại rất nhiều nghiên cứu xem xét mối liên hệ giữa Fintech và hệ thống ngân hàng, trong khi ảnh hưởng của Fintech lên doanh nghiệp còn khá hạn chế. Về cách thức tiếp cận, ngoài những quốc gia có trình độ công nghệ tiên tiến với hệ thống chỉ số đo lường Fintech sẵn có như Trung Quốc, hầu hết các nghiên cứu đều lấy dữ liệu Fintech thông qua khảo sát. Kế thừa kiến thức từ những nghiên cứu trước, kết hợp cùng tình trạng cấp thiết của nhu cầu hồi phục sau đại dịch,

bài nghiên cứu được tiến hành với mong muốn bổ sung những chỗ trống của các nghiên cứu trước đây trong kho tàng học thuật, về phạm vi mẫu và cách thức đo lường.

2.1. Xây dựng giả thuyết

Khi ứng dụng tài chính kỹ thuật số, các doanh nghiệp thường thể hiện 2 xu hướng: tích hợp công nghệ vào hệ thống hoặc liên kết với một doanh nghiệp cung cấp tài chính kỹ thuật số. Với tính chất thâm dụng công nghệ và đầu tư cao, các tổ chức tài chính truyền thống thường chọn cách tiếp cận thứ hai - hợp tác với các công ty Fintech (Song và cộng sự, 2021). Tồn tại bằng chứng cho thấy trong các nền tảng tài chính kỹ thuật số, vị trí địa lý nắm giữ một vai trò nhất định do những mâu thuẫn về thông tin (Senney, 2019). Theo lý thuyết bất cân xứng thông tin, việc cải thiện khả năng tiếp cận thông tin giữa các bên giao dịch giúp tăng hiệu quả hoạt động, hỗ trợ quá trình phục hồi. Trong thời đại giãn cách xã hội vì đại dịch, khoảng cách xa cản trở đáng kể khả năng giám sát và quản lý rủi ro. Do đó, những mâu thuẫn về thông tin liên quan đến địa lý làm giảm hiệu quả giao dịch. Sự gắn gũi về mặt địa lý giữa trụ sở hoạt động của các tổ chức giúp tăng cường thu thập thông tin, làm giảm sự bất cân xứng thông tin. Nhiều nghiên cứu cũng tìm thấy bằng chứng chứng minh sự gắn gũi về địa lý góp phần tạo ra sự tin tưởng giữa các đối tác trong giao dịch, thúc đẩy các cơ hội trong cùng khu vực, ngay cả khi không có bất kỳ lợi ích kinh tế cụ thể nào (Lai và Teo, 2008). Do đó, các giao dịch tài chính kỹ thuật số có nhiều khả năng xảy ra giữa các bên trong cùng một khu vực địa lý hơn là giữa các khu vực (Lin và Viswanathan, 2016; Senney, 2019). Trong điều kiện này, các công ty ở các khu vực có nhiều doanh nghiệp Fintech hơn có nhiều khả năng kiếm được các nguồn tài chính thay thế hơn trong đại dịch COVID-19. Dựa trên cơ sở đó, tác giả đề ra giả thuyết đầu tiên như sau:

H1. Khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp có tương quan dương với trình độ phát triển Fintech ở khu vực doanh nghiệp hoạt động.

Mức độ chịu ảnh hưởng bởi Fintech của doanh nghiệp khác nhau đáng kể dựa vào các điều kiện tài chính và nhu cầu thanh khoản. Tác giả kỳ vọng vai trò của Fintech trong việc cải thiện khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp đối với đại dịch COVID-19 thể hiện tốt hơn ở các doanh nghiệp có điều kiện tài chính kém và nhu cầu thanh khoản cao, như kết quả nghiên cứu của Ding và cộng sự (2021) - đặc điểm chung của các doanh nghiệp nhỏ. Theo Diễn đàn Kinh tế Thế giới (2015), tiềm năng của các giải pháp thay thế tài chính mà FinTech cung cấp phù hợp với các doanh nghiệp có quy mô vừa và nhỏ. Khả năng tiếp cận nguồn vốn hạn chế kết hợp với mức độ rủi ro của các doanh nghiệp vừa và nhỏ đã ảnh hưởng đến sự sẵn sàng cho vay của các ngân hàng, thu hẹp phạm vi tiếp cận tài chính. Như vậy, sự phát triển của các doanh nghiệp vừa và nhỏ bị cản trở đáng kể (Temelkov và Gogova Samonikov, 2018), chính vì hạn chế này khiến cho nhu cầu tiếp cận vốn trở nên cao hơn ở các doanh nghiệp quy mô vừa và nhỏ. Thời kỳ đại dịch khiến cho các chỉ tiêu vay vốn trở nên khắt khe hơn để tránh rủi ro ở các ngân hàng quốc doanh, chính vì nguồn vốn hạn hẹp, thiếu tài sản thế chấp và các bằng chứng yếu cầu minh bạch thông tin, các doanh nghiệp quy mô nhỏ gặp nhiều cản trở hơn trong quá trình hồi phục. Các công ty nhỏ cũng có xu hướng dễ bị tổn thương hơn trước các cú sốc (Ding và cộng sự, 2021). Chính vì thế tác động của Fintech được kỳ vọng thể hiện hiệu quả rõ rệt hơn ở các doanh nghiệp có quy mô tài chính thấp. Giả thuyết thứ 2 cho nghiên cứu được đề xuất như sau:

H2. Khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp rõ ràng hơn đối với doanh nghiệp có quy mô nhỏ.

3. MÔ HÌNH NGHIÊN CỨU

Từ những giả thuyết được đặt ra, vận dụng lý thuyết và các nghiên cứu trước đây, tác giả xây dựng mô hình như sau:

Mô hình (1) được sử dụng để kiểm định giả thuyết H1, H2 được xây dựng dựa trên nghiên cứu của (Xia và cộng sự, 2022).

$$Resilience = \beta_0 + \beta_1.Fintech + \beta_2.Size + \beta_3.Lev + \beta_4.ROA + \beta_5.MB + \beta_6.Growth + + \beta_7.Findev + \beta_8.PGDP \quad (1)$$

Trong đó,

Resilience: Khả năng phục hồi, được đo bằng mức độ nghiêm trọng của mất mát (Loss_Severity) hoặc thời gian để phục hồi (Recovery_Time).

Fintech: Trình độ Fintech ở khu vực doanh nghiệp hoạt động.

Size: Quy mô doanh nghiệp.

Lev: Đòn bẩy tài chính.

ROA: Lợi nhuận trên tổng tài sản.

MB: Tỷ lệ vốn hóa thị trường trên vốn chủ sở.

Growth: Tốc độ tăng trưởng.

Findev: Mức độ phát triển tài chính truyền thống của khu vực.

PGDP: Mức độ phát triển kinh tế vùng.

Hệ số chính β_1 của mô hình (1) dùng để đo lường mối quan hệ giữa Fintech và khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp. Nghiên cứu kỳ vọng β_1 mang giá trị dương, hàm ý sự phát triển của Fintech sẽ gây ra tác động dương lên khả năng hồi phục của doanh nghiệp. Theo các tài liệu trước đây (Levine và cộng sự, 2018; DesJardine và cộng sự, 2019; Ding và cộng sự, 2021), nghiên cứu sử dụng thêm các biến kiểm soát có thể ảnh hưởng đến khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp, chẳng hạn như quy mô, Lev, ROA, MB, Growth, Findev và PGDP.

3.1. Mô tả các biến

Biến phụ thuộc

Khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp được đo lường bằng Resilience, thông qua cách giá cổ phiếu phản ứng với thị trường trong thời kỳ Đại dịch, bằng mức độ nghiêm trọng của tổn thất và thời gian phục hồi (Gittell và cộng sự, 2006; DesJardine và cộng sự, 2019; Sajko và cộng sự, 2021).

Cách đo lường được giới thiệu trong nghiên cứu của DesJardine và cộng sự (2019); Sajko và cộng sự (2021). Giả thuyết thị trường hiệu quả cho rằng giá cổ phiếu phản ánh tất cả các thông tin liên quan và mới về các công ty (Sajko và cộng sự, 2021). Ý tưởng này được giới

học thuật chấp nhận rộng rãi (Gittell và cộng sự, 2006; DesJardine và cộng sự, 2019). Hai yếu tố này phản ánh khả năng của một công ty trong việc bảo tồn các chức năng cốt lõi của mình và phục hồi sau khủng hoảng. Các công ty dễ dàng phục hồi sau đại dịch hơn khi thiệt hại của họ là nhỏ, với việc phục hồi nhanh hơn một cách nhất quán sẽ bảo vệ các công ty khỏi những thiệt hại đang diễn ra.

Mức độ tổn thất (Loss_Severity): Mức độ nghiêm trọng của tổn thất được định nghĩa là tổn thất kinh tế doanh nghiệp gánh chịu trong khủng hoảng. Mức độ tổn thất ít nghiêm trọng cho thấy hệ thống doanh nghiệp ổn định và ít chịu biến động của thị trường. Nghiên cứu đánh giá mức độ thiệt hại nghiêm trọng bằng mức độ sụt giảm của giá cổ phiếu trong một năm ngay sau khi đại dịch COVID-19 bắt đầu.

$$\text{Loss_Severity} = \frac{(\text{giá thấp nhất từ 23/01/2020 đến 23/1/2021} - \text{giá đóng cửa 23/01/2020})}{\text{giá đóng cửa 23/01/2020}} - 1$$

➤ Thời gian phục hồi (Recovery_Time)

Nghiên cứu đo lường thời gian phục hồi bằng khoảng thời gian cần thiết để công ty trở lại mức trước cú sốc. Thời gian phục hồi ngắn cho thấy doanh nghiệp có khả năng thích ứng tốt với những thay đổi của môi trường và phục hồi nhanh hơn sau các cú sốc (Brand và Jax, 2007). Thời gian để phục hồi được đo bằng số ngày giá cổ phiếu của công ty cần để đạt được mức trước khi đại dịch xảy đến. Thời gian phục hồi càng ngắn, khả năng phục hồi của công ty càng cao.

$$\text{Recovery_Time} = \text{Số ngày giá cổ phiếu trở lại mức trước dịch}$$

Biến độc lập

➤ Fintech

Rất nhiều nghiên cứu trong quá khứ tiến hành đo lường biến Fintech bằng phương pháp khảo sát (Allen và cộng sự, 2021); Nathan và cộng sự, 2022; Misrina và Nuskiya, 2021), hay thông qua dữ liệu thanh toán, dữ liệu hiệu suất tài chính như nghiên cứu của Suri và cộng sự (2021). Các cách tiếp cận này bị hạn chế khá nhiều và mang tính chủ quan của mẫu khảo sát.

Đối với nghiên cứu này, tác giả sử dụng cách đo lường dựa theo nghiên cứu của Song và cộng sự (2021), biến Fintech được tính bằng logarit tự nhiên của số lượng các công ty Fintech địa phương cộng với 1. Số lượng các công ty Fintech ở một khu vực phản ánh mức độ dịch vụ mà họ cung cấp. Ở chương hai, nghiên cứu đã đề cập nhiều bằng chứng ủng hộ quan điểm về khoảng cách địa lý này. Cách tiếp cận như trên cũng khá thích hợp trong điều kiện giãn cách xã hội vì COVID-19. Cần lưu ý, nghiên cứu không quy chụp rằng có sự phân phối dịch vụ độc quyền giữa các tổ chức trong cùng một địa phương. Mà chỉ hàm ý sự gần gũi về địa lý tạo ra điều kiện giao dịch tốt hơn. Các công ty ở khu vực nơi nhiều doanh nghiệp Fintech có nhiều khả năng kiếm được các nguồn tài chính thay thế hơn.

$$\text{Fintech}_{\text{doanh nghiệp tỉnh X}} = \text{Log}(\text{số lượng doanh nghiệp Fintech tỉnh X}) + 1$$

Biến kiểm soát

➤ **Mức độ phát triển tài chính truyền thống (Findev)**

Dữ liệu được trích xuất từ Tổng cục thống kê (General Statistics Office)³⁰, sử dụng để đo lường mức độ phát triển tài chính truyền thống, được tính bằng tỷ lệ dư nợ cho vay của các tổ chức tài chính chia cho GDP của tỉnh (Xia và cộng sự, 2022). Cách đo lường này từng được sử dụng trong nghiên cứu của Levine và cộng sự (2018), DesJardine và cộng sự (2019), Ding và cộng sự (2021).

Nghiên cứu của Liem N. T. và cộng sự (2021), Cornelli và cộng sự (2020) cũng đều sử dụng cách thức đo lường này, tỷ lệ tín dụng Fintech chia cho GDP quốc gia – một biện pháp tiêu chuẩn hóa kiểm soát ảnh hưởng quy mô nền kinh tế trong việc cung cấp tín dụng Fintech.

$$\text{Findev} = \frac{\text{Dư nợ của tổ chức tài chính}}{\text{GDP địa phương}}$$

➤ **Mức độ phát triển kinh tế vùng (PGDP)**

Đặc trưng cho mức độ phát triển kinh tế vùng, có giá trị bằng logarit GDP bình quân trên đầu người mỗi khu vực (Xia và cộng sự, 2022). Cách đo lường này từng được sử dụng trong nghiên cứu của Levine và cộng sự (2018), DesJardine và cộng sự (2019), Ding và cộng sự (2021).

$$\text{PGDP}_{\text{doanh nghiệp tỉnh X}} = \text{Log}(\text{GDP}/\text{người tỉnh X})$$

➤ **Tốc độ tăng trưởng (Growth)**

Tốc độ tăng trưởng là tỉ số đo lường mức tăng trưởng doanh thu năm t so với năm t-1. GROW càng cao thì công ty kinh doanh càng phát triển. Cách đo lường này từng được sử dụng trong nghiên cứu của Levine và cộng sự (2018), DesJardine và cộng sự (2019), Ding và cộng sự (2021).

$$\text{Growth} = \frac{\text{Doanh thu năm t} - \text{Doanh thu năm t-1}}{\text{Doanh thu năm t-1}}$$

➤ **Quy mô công ty (Size)**

Quy mô doanh nghiệp là một đại diện cho quy mô doanh nghiệp, được đo bằng logarit tự nhiên của tổng tài sản (Xia và cộng sự, 2022). Size là một trong những yếu tố tài chính quan trọng góp phần vào hiệu quả tài chính của doanh nghiệp. Quy mô doanh nghiệp càng lớn mức độ tiếp cận nguồn vốn càng cao.

$$\text{Size} = \ln(\text{Tổng tài sản})$$

➤ **Đòn bẩy tài chính (Lev)**

Bài nghiên cứu của Alsayegh và cộng sự (2020), biến đòn bẩy tài chính thông qua chỉ số D/E (Tỷ lệ nợ trên vốn chủ sở hữu). Tỷ số nợ trên vốn chủ sở hữu hay tỷ số D/E (Debt to

³⁰ Tổng cục thống kê - General Statistics Office - www.gso.gov.vn

Equity ratio – DER) chỉ ra số nợ mà một công ty đang sử dụng để điều hành hoạt động kinh doanh và đòn bẩy tài chính có sẵn. Tỷ lệ nợ trên vốn chủ sở hữu cho thấy năng lực quản lý nợ và quy mô tài chính đang có của một doanh nghiệp. Đây chính là chỉ số quan trọng về tài chính để đo lường năng lực hoạt động cũng như cách vận hành hoạt động của bộ phận lãnh đạo doanh nghiệp. Cụ thể hơn, nó phản ánh khả năng vốn chủ sở hữu của cổ đông có thể bao gồm tất cả các khoản nợ tồn đọng trong trường hợp suy thoái kinh doanh. Tỷ lệ nợ trên vốn chủ sở hữu (D/E) được tính bằng cách chia tổng nợ phải trả của công ty với vốn chủ sở hữu của cổ đông. Những con số này có sẵn trên bảng cân đối kế toán và báo cáo tài chính.

$$LEV = \frac{\text{Tổng nợ}}{\text{Giá trị vốn chủ sở hữu}}$$

➤ Tỷ suất lợi nhuận trên tổng tài sản (ROA)

Tỷ suất lợi nhuận trên tổng tài sản cũng là một yếu tố tác động lên khả năng hồi phục của doanh nghiệp, theo kết quả từ nghiên cứu của Xia và cộng sự (2022).

$$ROA = \frac{\text{Lợi nhuận sau thuế năm t}}{\text{Tổng tài sản năm t}}$$

Dữ liệu nghiên cứu

Mẫu được xem xét bao gồm tất cả các doanh nghiệp phi tài chính được niêm yết trên các sàn giao dịch chứng khoán Việt Nam giai đoạn 2020 - 2021. Giá chứng khoán được lấy từ ngày 23 tháng 1 năm 2020 – ngày ghi nhận ca nhiễm virus SARS CoV-2 đầu tiên tại TP. Hồ Chí Minh. Dữ liệu được thu thập từ các nguồn sau:

Thứ nhất, đối với dữ liệu về khả năng phục hồi, tác giả tiến hành thu thập giá cổ phiếu theo ngày trong giai đoạn 23/01/2020 – 23/01/2021 của các doanh nghiệp phi tài chính được niêm yết trên sàn HNX và HOSE. Thứ hai, dữ liệu về Fintech, tác giả thực hiện thống kê số lượng và trụ sở hoạt động của 156 doanh nghiệp trên thị trường, danh sách hệ sinh thái Fintech Việt Nam được lấy từ Fintechnews.sg. Cuối cùng, các dữ liệu về thông tin doanh nghiệp được lấy từ hệ thống FiinPro Platform. Các định chế tài chính như ngân hàng, công ty chứng khoán và công ty bảo hiểm sẽ loại ra khỏi mẫu, đối với các doanh nghiệp tài chính, dữ liệu có nhiều khả năng bị ảnh hưởng bởi các yếu tố cụ thể của ngành nên đã được loại bỏ (Xia và cộng sự, 2022), nghiên cứu cũng tiến hành lọc đi các quan sát thiếu dữ liệu.

Phương pháp xử lý số liệu

Nghiên cứu sử dụng hồi quy OLS để ước tính các hệ số trong mô hình (1) trong trường hợp khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp được đánh giá thông qua mức độ nghiêm trọng của tổn thất (Loss_Severity). Cách kiểm định tương tự được sử dụng trong nghiên cứu của Yanchun Xia và cộng sự (2022).

Đối với việc ước tính các hệ số trong mô hình (1) khi sử dụng thời gian phục hồi (Recovery_Time), nghiên cứu sử dụng mô hình hồi quy nhị thức âm. Nghiên cứu sử dụng mô hình này vì thời gian khôi phục không liên tục và có độ lệch cao, các kỹ thuật hồi quy tuyến tính tiêu chuẩn không phù hợp với tập dữ liệu này (Ramaswamy và cộng sự, 1994; Sanders,

2001). Dựa trên phân phối hỗn hợp Poisson-gamma, hồi quy nhị thức âm đặc biệt thích hợp để xử lý vấn đề phân tán quá mức như tập dữ liệu về số ngày phục hồi (Greene, 2000; Sanders, 2001).

4.KẾT QUẢ NGHIÊN CỨU

4.1 Kết quả phân tích thống kê mô tả

Bảng 4.1. Kết quả phân tích thống kê mô tả

Biến	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Loss_severity	586	-0.326	0.293	-1.671	0.000
Recovery_time	586	47.476	86.996	0.000	722.000
Fintech	586	1.160	0.765	0.000	1.909
SIZE	586	27.433	1.574	23.486	32.510
LEV	586	0.795	6.172	0.007	149.704
ROA	586	0.050	0.071	-0.227	0.429
MB	586	1.533	3.169	0.000	71.179
Growth	586	0.234	2.940	-1.049	42.923
SOE	586	0.312	0.464	0.000	1.000
Findev	578	0.028	0.387	0.000	8.806
PGDP	586	8.034	0.192	7.316	8.449

Nguồn: Tổng hợp của tác giả từ phần mềm STATA

Bảng 4.1 trình bày thống kê mô tả cho các biến được sử dụng trong nghiên cứu. Theo thống kê, mức độ tổn thất mà các doanh nghiệp phải đối diện trung bình rơi vào -0.326, trong trường hợp nghiêm trọng nhất lên đến -1.671, cho thấy các doanh nghiệp hứng chịu một khoản lỗ đáng kể trong sự sụt giảm giá cổ phiếu vì những hệ lụy của đại dịch. Thời gian trung bình để hồi phục rơi vào khoảng 48 ngày với độ lệch chuẩn là 86.996, thể hiện tốc độ hồi phục chênh lệch rất lớn giữa các doanh nghiệp, trong khi một vài doanh nghiệp hồi phục ngay lập tức, một số khác lại mất đến gần một năm để quay về mức giá ổn định ban đầu. Biến số đo lường trình độ Fintech có giá trị trung bình là 1.160, xét trong phạm vi từ 0 đến 1.909, nhìn chung Fintech ở các địa phương phân bố chưa đồng đều và còn chênh lệch lớn về trình độ phát triển.

Trong khi biến Loss_Severity khá đồng đều giữa các doanh nghiệp với độ lệch chuẩn 0.293, Recovery_Time lại cho thấy mức độ biến động cực kỳ lớn với độ lệch chuẩn lên đến 86.996 – yếu tố này một lần nữa củng cố bằng chứng cho cách thức chọn lọc mô hình hồi quy nhị thức âm của nghiên cứu, khi dữ liệu thời gian khôi phục không liên tục, thiếu thống nhất và có độ lệch cao, các kỹ thuật hồi quy tuyến tính tiêu chuẩn không phù hợp để đo lường (Ramaswamy và cộng sự, 1994; Sanders, 2001). Dựa trên phân phối hỗn hợp Poisson-gamma, hồi quy nhị thức âm đặc biệt thích hợp để xử lý vấn đề phân tán quá mức như trên (Greene, 2000; Sanders, 2001).

Về các biến kiểm soát, các doanh nghiệp sở hữu quy mô (SIZE) trung bình là 27.433, phần đông thuộc về doanh nghiệp quy mô vừa và lớn với mức độ sử dụng đòn bẩy trung bình (LEV) là 0.795, giá trị thị trường trên sổ sách (MB) trung bình của mẫu rơi vào 1.533, lợi

nhuận trên tổng tài sản (ROA) trung bình đạt giá trị 0.05 và tăng trưởng doanh số bán hàng (GROWTH) trung bình là 0.234. Mức độ phát triển tài chính truyền thống trong khu vực (Findev) rơi vào 0.028 trong khi giá trị lớn nhất lên đến 8.806 – dễ dàng nhận thấy sự chênh lệch về trình độ giữa các khu vực địa lý khác nhau. Trong khi đó, trung bình trình độ phát triển kinh tế, tính theo logarit GDP/ người là 8.034 với độ lệch chuẩn 0.192. Ngược lại với sự khác biệt về mức độ phát triển tài chính truyền thống, các khu vực địa lý lại cho thấy tốc độ phát triển kinh tế khá cao và đồng đều.

4.2 Ảnh hưởng của Fintech đến khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp

Nội dung này phân tích khi một doanh nghiệp hoạt động tại khu vực trình độ Fintech cao sẽ ảnh hưởng ra sao đến khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp. Kết quả nghiên cứu được trình bày dưới đây là kết quả hồi quy cho mô hình (1).

Bảng 4.2. Kết quả hồi quy mô hình tác động của Fintech lên khả năng hồi phục bằng Pooled OLS và hồi quy nhị thức âm

Biến	Loss_Severity (1)	Recovery_Time (2)
Fintech	0.0181 (1.13)	-0.2575*** (-2.76)
SIZE	-0.0043 (-0.54)	0.1189*** (2.69)
LEV	0.0001 (0.03)	0.0142 (1.25)
ROA	0.2906* (1.69)	-2.3531** (-2.52)
MB	-0.0006 (-0.16)	0.0106 (0.51)
Growth	-0.0003 (-0.08)	-0.0364 (-1.4)
Findev	0.0177 (-0.55)	-0.5543*** (-2.73)
PGDP	0.1673** (-2.56)	-0.5771* (-1.66)
_cons	-1.5886*** (-2.89)	5.5724* (1.9)
/lnalpha		1.0445*** (19.6)

Nguồn: Tổng hợp của tác giả từ phần mềm STATA

Kết quả kiểm định cho thấy Fintech giúp cải thiện khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp thông qua rút ngắn thời gian hồi phục, biến Fintech có ý nghĩa thống kê ở mức 1% và tham số hồi quy -0.2575, tác động ngược chiều lên Severity_time. Phù hợp với kết quả trong nghiên

cứu của MSC (2021) tại Ấn Độ. Kết quả này cũng được ủng hộ bởi lý thuyết bất cân xứng thông tin: trong điều kiện Fintech phát triển mạnh mẽ, mức độ bất cân xứng thông tin giữa các bên được cải thiện đáng kể, nâng cao tính minh bạch và khiến giá cổ phiếu hồi phục nhanh hơn. Đối với thời gian hồi phục, các biến kiểm soát ROA, Findev, PGDP cho thấy tác động âm với mức ý nghĩa lần lượt là 5%, 1% và 10%. Hàm ý thời gian phục hồi sẽ nhanh hơn đối với các doanh nghiệp có tỷ suất sinh lợi cao và nằm ở khu vực có trình độ phát triển tài chính kinh tế ổn định.

Vấn đề tiếp theo, kết quả hồi quy cho thấy mối quan hệ tích cực giữa trình độ phát triển Fintech và mức độ tổn thất, tuy nhiên kết quả này không có ý nghĩa thống kê. Kiểm định cho thấy kết quả không hoàn toàn đồng nhất với kết quả trong nghiên cứu của Xia và cộng sự (2022) được tiến hành tại thị trường Trung Quốc. Trình độ Fintech tiên tiến giúp doanh nghiệp tăng khả năng phục hồi sau đại dịch, nhưng chỉ thông qua rút ngắn thời gian hồi phục, thay vì đồng thời giảm tổn thất và thời gian phục hồi như nghiên cứu trong quá khứ. Có lẽ sự khác nhau về thể chế và cách thức phân bổ hệ sinh thái Fintech là một nguyên nhân lý giải vấn đề này. Theo nghiên cứu của Tania Ziegler và cộng sự (2020), Fintech hoạt động ở các nền kinh tế tiên tiến như Trung Quốc có mức độ hoạt động cao hơn so với những công ty hoạt động trong các thị trường mới nổi và các nền kinh tế đang phát triển như Việt Nam. Thông qua kết quả trên, nghiên cứu chấp nhận giả thuyết H1, rằng khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp có tương quan dương với trình độ phát triển Fintech ở khu vực doanh nghiệp hoạt động.

Kiểm định sử dụng mức độ tổn thất không tồn tại ý nghĩa thống kê, do đó nghiên cứu chuyển hướng tập trung vào thời gian hồi phục giá cổ phiếu. Biến kiểm soát SIZE cho thấy tác động dương ở mức ý nghĩa 1%, hàm ý doanh nghiệp có quy mô càng lớn sẽ càng tốn nhiều thời gian hơn để hồi phục. Kết quả này đúng với kỳ vọng của tác giả, đồng nhất với nghiên cứu của Xia và cộng sự (2022). Nghiên cứu một lần nữa sử dụng lý thuyết thị trường hiệu quả. Vốn dĩ doanh nghiệp với quy mô lớn có nhiều khả năng sử dụng tài chính kỹ thuật số, cũng như dễ dàng cung cấp thông tin đến với các bên liên quan, tạo ra hiệu ứng danh tiếng tốt, rút ngắn thời gian hồi phục. Tuy nhiên tại thị trường Việt Nam, hiệu quả thị trường thuộc dạng yếu khiến hệ thống công bố thông tin chưa đủ mạnh, hạn chế năng lực và thời gian cập nhật hệ thống thông tin. Hơn nữa đối với các doanh nghiệp lớn, vốn có tập hợp khách hàng rộng và bao trùm nhiều phân khúc. Việc hạn chế về mức độ truyền đạt thông tin cũng như giãn cách xã hội khiến doanh nghiệp cần bỏ nhiều công sức hơn để liên lạc và thông tin đến tất cả khách hàng, nhà đầu tư. Trong khi các doanh nghiệp với quy mô nhỏ thường có phạm vi tiếp cận khách hàng trong tầm kiểm soát, qua đó phương thức kết nối đến khách hàng trở nên tiện lợi và dễ điều chỉnh hơn cũng như tốn ít thời gian hơn. Nghiên cứu của Ding và cộng sự (2021) cũng cho thấy kết quả tương tự rằng khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp đối với đại dịch COVID-19 thể hiện rõ hơn ở các doanh nghiệp có điều kiện tài chính kém và nhu cầu thanh khoản cao – doanh nghiệp có quy mô vừa và nhỏ.

5. KẾT LUẬN

Trong thời kỳ nền kinh tế toàn cầu vừa trải qua khủng hoảng do đại dịch Covid-19, khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp trở thành mối quan tâm chính của giới học thuật. Qua các kiểm định được thực hiện ở chương trước, bài nghiên cứu đưa ra các kết luận về tác động của Fintech lên khả năng hồi phục của doanh nghiệp như sau:

Kết luận đầu tiên, nghiên cứu tìm được bằng chứng chứng minh các doanh nghiệp có khả năng chống chọi tốt hơn với đại dịch COVID-19 khi hoạt động trong khu vực có trình độ phát triển Fintech cao, cụ thể là thông qua tác động rút ngắn số ngày phục hồi trong giá cổ phiếu. Kết luận thứ hai, tác động tích cực của Fintech lên khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp rõ ràng hơn ở các doanh nghiệp quy mô nhỏ. Trình độ phát triển tài chính truyền thống và trình độ kinh tế khu vực cao cũng là một bước đệm hỗ trợ quá trình phục hồi doanh nghiệp diễn ra nhanh hơn.

Ngoài ra, nghiên cứu nhận thấy tần suất phân bố hệ sinh thái Fintech không đồng đều giữa các khu vực là một trở ngại rất lớn cho trong công cuộc khai thác lợi ích của Fintech. Trong khi nước ta có tốc độ phát triển Fintech vô cùng mạnh, những tác động tích cực đến khả năng hồi phục lại khá mờ nhạt và bị hạn chế bởi sự thiếu hiệu quả về thông tin và chênh lệch trình độ vùng miền. Nghiên cứu kết luận rằng Fintech là một yếu tố quan trọng giúp tăng cường khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp đối với đại dịch COVID-19. Trong điều kiện các quốc gia trên thế giới đang đối mặt với những hệ lụy do đại dịch để lại, việc có cái nhìn đúng về khả năng phục hồi của doanh nghiệp là yếu tố cấp thiết giúp đẩy nhanh tốc độ khôi phục kinh tế mỗi quốc gia nói riêng và toàn cầu nói chung.

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CÁC YẾU TỐ TÁC ĐỘNG ĐẾN SỨC MẠNH THỊ TRƯỜNG CỦA CÁC NGÂN HÀNG THƯƠNG MẠI VIỆT NAM

Phạm Hồng Linh

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Tóm tắt

Chủ đề nghiên cứu về sức mạnh thị trường luôn nhận được sự quan tâm của nhiều học giả, cơ quan giám sát ngân hàng cũng như những nhà quản lý ngân hàng. Sức mạnh thị trường được cho là sẽ tạo thuận lợi cho hoạt động kinh doanh của ngân hàng. Tuy nhiên, các nghiên cứu về chủ đề này thường tập trung vào đánh giá ảnh hưởng của sức mạnh thị trường đến các yếu tố khác nhau chứ rất ít nghiên cứu theo chiều ngược lại. Bài viết đã xây dựng được một mô hình để quan sát các yếu tố có ảnh hưởng đến sức mạnh thị trường. Bằng phân tích hồi quy GMM, nghiên cứu đã tìm thấy các yếu tố gồm quy mô, hiệu quả quản lý, hoạt động đa dạng hóa, mức độ rủi ro và mức độ tập trung thị trường là các yếu tố có ảnh hưởng cùng chiều với sức mạnh thị trường của các ngân hàng thương mại Việt Nam trong khi lạm phát và lãi suất điều hành lại có tác động ngược chiều.

Từ khóa: sức mạnh thị trường, ngân hàng

FACTORS AFFECTING MARKET POWER OF VIETNAMESE COMMERCIAL BANKS

Abstract

The topic of research on market power has always been of concerns to many academics, banking supervisors as well as bank managers. It is acknowledged that market power will facilitate the bank's business. However, previous studies on this topic often focused on assessing the influence of market power, whereas a few of research on the factors affecting market power. This paper has built a model to observe the factors that affect market power. By GMM regression analysis, the study found that the factors including size, management efficiency, diversification, risk and market concentration positively influenced on the market power of Vietnamese commercial banks while inflation and policy interest rates had opposite effects.

Keywords: market power, bank

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Trong các nghiên cứu về ảnh hưởng của sức mạnh thị trường, các quan điểm kinh tế học truyền thống đều cho rằng, trong thị trường cạnh tranh không hoàn hảo, hiệu quả Pareto không đạt được và phúc lợi xã hội không tối đa. Đó là vì khi sức mạnh thị trường tăng lên, các công ty có xu hướng tính giá bất lợi hơn cho đối tác và khách hàng cũng như ít có động lực để giảm chi phí. Tuy nhiên, có một lập luận chống lại quan điểm này, đó là, sức mạnh độc quyền ở một

mức độ nhất định sẽ giúp các công ty kiếm được lợi nhuận cao hơn, điều sẽ thúc đẩy và tạo ra động lực cho sự đổi mới (OECD, 1993). Điều này cho thấy các quốc gia cần các quản lý mức độ sức mạnh thị trường phù hợp với mục tiêu phát triển lâu dài.

Sức mạnh thị trường không chỉ tạo ra nhiều lợi thế cho các ngân hàng trong quá trình kinh doanh mà còn có mối liên hệ với nhiều yếu tố khác trong hoạt động của ngân hàng và cả với môi trường vĩ mô. Những mối quan hệ này có ảnh hưởng đáng kể đến định hướng hoạt động cũng như điều hành chính sách. Do đó, các chủ đề nghiên cứu về cạnh tranh và sức mạnh thị trường thu hút không chỉ các nhà nghiên cứu mà còn cả các ngân hàng và cơ quan quản lý, giám sát. Phần lớn các nghiên cứu đều chỉ ra rằng sức mạnh thị trường có ảnh hưởng lớn tới các yếu tố khác nhau như mức độ ổn định hay hiệu quả hoạt động của ngân hàng. Tuy nhiên, làm thế nào để tác động đến sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng thì rất ít các nghiên cứu đề cập đến. Mục tiêu của bài viết là xây dựng một mô hình để nghiên cứu và quan sát ảnh hưởng của các yếu tố khác nhau đến sức mạnh thị trường của các ngân hàng để làm định hướng cho các giải pháp làm thay đổi sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng. Bằng phân tích hồi quy GMM, nghiên cứu đã tìm thấy các yếu tố gồm quy mô, hiệu quả quản lý, hoạt động đa dạng hóa, mức độ rủi ro và mức độ tập trung thị trường là các yếu tố có ảnh hưởng cùng chiều với sức mạnh thị trường của các ngân hàng thương mại Việt Nam trong khi lạm phát và lãi suất điều hành lại có tác động ngược chiều.

2. CƠ SỞ LÝ LUẬN VỀ SỨC MẠNH THỊ TRƯỜNG VÀ CÁC YẾU TỐ TÁC ĐỘNG ĐẾN SỨC MẠNH THỊ TRƯỜNG CỦA NGÂN HÀNG

2.1. Khái niệm sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng

Theo định nghĩa của OECD (1993): “sức mạnh thị trường đề cập đến khả năng của một công ty (hoặc nhóm các công ty) tăng và duy trì giá trên mức sẽ đạt được trong bối cảnh cạnh tranh”. Trước khi thuật ngữ “sức mạnh thị trường” (Market Power) ra đời, thuật ngữ sức mạnh độc quyền (Monopoly Power) được sử dụng phổ biến và hiện tại hai từ này có ý nghĩa tương đương. Tuy nhiên, khác với độc quyền, sức mạnh thị trường chỉ tất cả các tình huống mà các công ty có khả năng tăng giá cao hơn mức cân bằng trong điều kiện cạnh tranh. Nghĩa là, sức mạnh thị trường có thể phát sinh không chỉ khi có độc quyền mà cả khi không có độc quyền (OECD, 1993).

Trong khi đó, Lerner (1934) cho rằng: “sức mạnh thị trường phản ánh khả năng một người bán có thể đặt giá cao hơn so với chi phí cận biên”. Lerner giải thích điều này từ sự khác biệt trong độ dốc và độ co giãn của đường cầu mà người bán đối mặt trong thị trường cạnh tranh và độc quyền. Đường cầu mà người bán đối mặt trong thị trường độc quyền là dốc làm cho độ co giãn không phải là vô cùng như trong thị trường cạnh tranh thuần túy. Kết quả là người bán có thể định giá ở mức mà anh ta kiếm được lợi nhuận lớn nhất hoặc "doanh thu độc quyền". Trong lĩnh vực NH, biểu hiện điển hình của sức mạnh thị trường là khả năng NH có thể đưa ra lãi suất cho vay cao hơn và lãi suất tiền gửi thấp hơn (Berger và cộng sự, 2004; Yeyati và Micco, 2007). Điều này nghĩa là sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng có thể xét riêng trên thị trường tiền gửi và trên thị trường cho vay.

2.2. Các yếu tố tác động đến sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng

2.2.1. Nhóm yếu tố thuộc về ngân hàng

Sức mạnh thị trường của các NH không giống nhau cho thấy nhóm các yếu tố thuộc về NH có tác động lớn nhất đến sức mạnh thị trường của NH.

Quy mô NH được nhiều nghiên cứu đưa vào khi đo lường hoặc xác định các yếu tố quyết định sức mạnh thị trường của NH. Lý do là hiệu ứng kinh tế nhờ quy mô làm cho các NH lớn có lợi thế về chi phí, từ đó, được hưởng quyền lực thị trường lớn hơn hoặc quy mô giúp các NH lớn có khả năng áp đặt giá cao hơn. Nhìn chung, quy mô thường được xác nhận là có ảnh hưởng cùng chiều đến sức mạnh thị trường. Nhiều nghiên cứu về sau lại chỉ ra giữa sức mạnh thị trường và quy mô có thể có dạng phi tuyến. De Guevara và cộng sự (2005) trong mẫu nghiên cứu các ngân hàng trong Liên minh châu Âu đã cho thấy sức mạnh thị trường tăng theo quy mô chỉ đến một giới hạn nhất định, vượt qua mức này, mối quan hệ sẽ yếu đi, thậm chí có thể giảm. De Guevara và Maudos (2007) trong mẫu nghiên cứu về quá trình hội nhập của các NH Tây Ban Nha lại tìm thấy mối quan hệ phi tuyến theo chiều ngược lại, có tồn tại một điểm mà vượt quá nó quy mô làm tăng sức mạnh thị trường. Do đó, các NH quy mô nhỏ và lớn được hưởng sức mạnh thị trường lớn hơn các NH quy mô vừa. Lý do được đưa ra là các NH nhỏ (hoạt động chủ yếu tại một địa bàn nhỏ) có khả năng được hưởng lợi lớn từ thị trường do sự quen thuộc của họ ở các thị trường địa phương, nơi mạng lưới chi nhánh rộng khắp của họ đóng vai trò như một rào cản gia nhập. Trong khi đó, các NH lớn nhất lại có thể khai thác sức mạnh thị trường vì vị thế thống lĩnh của họ trên thị trường. Nhìn chung, chiến lược chính được hầu hết các NH lựa chọn để đối phó với cạnh tranh trong quá trình hội nhập thị trường tài chính vẫn là tăng quy mô để cố gắng thu được lợi ích từ tăng quyền lực thị trường do ảnh hưởng của tăng quy mô.

Hiệu quả đạt được trong quản lý hoạt động là một trong những yếu tố quan trọng nhất giúp giải thích sự khác biệt về sức mạnh thị trường giữa các NH. Giả thuyết Hiệu quả - Cấu trúc (Efficiency – Structure) lập luận rằng nếu NH hoạt động hiệu quả sẽ có đủ sức mạnh để mở rộng thị phần (Lloyd-Williams và cộng sự, 1994; Berger, 1995). Theo đó, M&A là kết quả do một số NH có hiệu quả chi phí nhờ công nghệ quản lý hoặc năng lực sản xuất vượt trội. Các NH này có thể hạ giá để hấp dẫn được nhiều khách hàng, từ đó, thị phần được mở rộng, gia tăng lợi nhuận cũng như phúc lợi xã hội. Nghiên cứu thực nghiệm của De Guevara và cộng sự (2005) cho thấy rằng các NH hiệu quả hơn được hưởng tỷ suất lợi nhuận cao hơn gần như chắc chắn là do chi phí biên thấp hơn. Giả thuyết hiệu quả thuần túy (Pure Efficiency) cho rằng các công ty có năng lực sản xuất hoặc quản lý vượt trội có chi phí thấp hơn, do đó, lợi nhuận cao hơn. Ngoài ra, các ngân hàng quản lý tốt hơn các yếu tố đầu vào có thể thu được lợi ích từ hiệu quả cao hơn và sử dụng nó như một rào cản ngăn chặn sự cạnh tranh của những người mới gia nhập, cho phép họ hưởng lợi thị trường lớn hơn. Tăng hiệu quả có thể là một chiến lược đối phó với quá trình mở cửa thị trường tài chính. Khan và cộng sự (2017) chỉ rõ hiệu quả chi phí tạo điều kiện cho NH tăng trưởng, từ đó, có được sức mạnh thị trường và thị phần cao hơn.

Mức độ rủi ro cũng có thể tác động đến sức mạnh thị trường của NH. De Guevara và cộng sự (2005) chỉ ra rằng các NH chi tiêu nhiều nguồn lực hơn để đối phó với rủi ro tín dụng (tương đương rủi ro tín dụng thấp hơn) được hưởng lợi nhuận biên cao hơn nghĩa là sức mạnh thị trường lớn hơn.

Đa dạng hóa thu nhập: một số nghiên cứu thực nghiệm đã chỉ ra rằng các hoạt động tạo thu nhập phi truyền thống của NH có thể gia tăng và tạo ra nguồn của sức mạnh thị trường. Ví dụ, Carbó-Valverde và Rodríguez-Fernández (2007) nhận thấy rằng sức mạnh thị trường tăng lên khi thu nhập đa dạng hơn đối với các hoạt động phi truyền thống trong mẫu nghiên cứu đối với các NH châu Âu. Tương tự, Ciarrapico và Cosci (2011) báo cáo rằng trong bối cảnh của ngành NH Châu Âu, các NH bán chéo hoặc các NH có tỷ lệ thu nhập hoa hồng và phí cao hơn so với thu nhập lãi có liên hệ với sức mạnh thị trường. Các tác giả giải thích rằng những NH phát triển nhiều hoạt động phi lãi có thể làm cho mối quan hệ với khách hàng chặt chẽ hơn, bán cho khách hàng các dịch vụ được cá nhân hóa và chất lượng cao. Trên thực tế, họ áp đặt chi phí chuyển đổi cao đối với khách hàng và cho phép các NH đạt được sức mạnh thị trường cao. Tuy nhiên, Montgomery (1985) nhận thấy rằng chiến lược đa dạng hóa thu nhập có thể dẫn đến suy giảm sức mạnh thị trường của các NH. Ông tuyên bố rằng bất kỳ chiến lược đa dạng hóa nào cũng làm loãng các kỹ năng nhất định, đặc biệt là các chỉ số hiệu quả thường liên quan đến chiến lược chuyên môn hóa.

2.2.2. Nhóm yếu tố thuộc về ngành

Yếu tố thuộc về ngành có ảnh hưởng đến sức mạnh thị trường thường đề cập tới *mức độ tập trung* do ảnh hưởng sâu rộng của lý thuyết SCP trong nhiều nghiên cứu. Lý thuyết SCP cho rằng cấu trúc hay mức độ tập trung của thị trường tác động đến hành vi còn hành vi ảnh hưởng đến kết quả, trong đó có sức mạnh thị trường. Quan điểm này dẫn tới việc một số chỉ số đo mức độ tập trung đã được sử dụng để đại diện cho cạnh tranh hay sức mạnh thị trường trong nhiều nghiên cứu thuộc lĩnh vực ngân hàng (Bikker, 2004). Nhiều lý luận và thực nghiệm sau đó đã chỉ ra hai thước đo này không hoàn toàn tương đồng. Tuy nhiên, các lập luận phản đối chủ yếu chỉ ra rằng tập trung và sức mạnh thị trường không hoàn toàn tương đương với nhau chứ không phủ nhận toàn bộ ảnh hưởng của tập trung đối với sức mạnh thị trường. Nhìn chung, mối quan hệ này khá phức tạp. Theo Corvoisier và Gropp (2002), ảnh hưởng của tập trung đối với sức mạnh thị trường của NH có thể khác nhau, tùy thuộc vào sản phẩm được xem xét.

2.2.3. Nhóm yếu tố thuộc về môi trường vĩ mô

Các yếu tố thuộc về môi trường bên ngoài như pháp lý hay kinh tế có thể trực tiếp thay đổi điều kiện cạnh tranh, ảnh hưởng đến sức mạnh thị trường của NH.

Môi trường pháp lý: Quy định pháp luật ảnh hưởng vô cùng chặt chẽ đến hoạt động và hành vi cạnh tranh, từ đó ảnh hưởng đến sức mạnh thị trường của các NH. Luật cạnh tranh hay Luật chống độc quyền, hoặc các quy định khác liên quan đến bằng phát minh sáng chế là những quy định cơ bản nhất trực tiếp tác động đến hành vi cạnh tranh của các NH. Theo lý thuyết “Thị trường tranh chấp” (Baumol và cộng sự, 1983), các quy định liên quan đến rào cản gia nhập hay rút khỏi thị trường cũng tác động đến mức độ cạnh tranh tiềm năng của thị trường. Như vậy, các rào cản gia nhập, các hạn chế về sở hữu và hoạt động của NH nước ngoài đều có khả năng ảnh hưởng đến mức độ cạnh tranh. Hoạt động M&A sẽ dẫn tới làm giảm số lượng NH và tăng mức độ tập trung, từ đó, các chính sách khuyến khích hay hạn chế M&A cũng là một yếu tố cần đưa vào đến khi nghiên cứu về sức mạnh thị trường của các NH.

Môi trường kinh tế: Các yếu tố thuộc môi trường kinh tế có tác động đáng kể đến sức mạnh thị trường. De Guevara và cộng sự (2005) chỉ ra rằng trong thời kỳ mở rộng kinh tế (do đó nhu cầu đối với nguồn tài trợ của NH tăng lên), các NH có thể được hưởng lợi nhuận tương

đổi lớn hơn. Do đó, thời kỳ tăng trưởng kinh tế và ổn định tài chính tạo điều kiện cho các NH gia tăng về quy mô và hiệu quả, dẫn đến tỷ suất lợi nhuận tương đối lớn hơn.

3. PHƯƠNG PHÁP NGHIÊN CỨU

3.1. Mô hình nghiên cứu

Dựa trên cơ sở lý thuyết về các yếu tố tác động đến sức mạnh thị trường, bài viết sử dụng mô hình nghiên cứu là phương trình hồi quy có dạng như sau:

$$MP_{it} = \beta_0 + \sum \beta^b BANKSPECIFIC_{it} + \sum \beta^S SECTOR_t + \sum \beta^M MACRO_t + u_{it}$$

Trong đó i và t lần lượt chỉ ngân hàng và thời gian (năm). MP_{it} là sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng i vào năm t . $BANKSPECIFIC_{it}$ là tập hợp các biến đặc trưng cho từng ngân hàng, $SECTOR_{it}$ là tập hợp các biến đặc trưng cho ngành ngân hàng và $MACRO_t$ là tập hợp các biến đại diện cho môi trường vĩ mô. Các biến thuộc về ngân hàng được lấy trễ một kỳ để khắc phục hiện tượng nội sinh.

Về thước đo sức mạnh thị trường, nghiên cứu sử dụng chỉ số Lerner mà một chỉ số được sử dụng rộng rãi trong nhiều bài viết để đại diện cho sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng. Chỉ số Lerner bằng chênh lệch giữa giá và chi phí biên chia cho giá của NH i vào thời gian t với công thức cụ thể như sau:

$$Lerner_{it} = \frac{P_{it} - MC_{it}}{P_{it}}$$

Trong đó, MC_{it} là chi phí cận biên dài hạn của NH i vào thời gian t và P_{it} là giá đầu ra của chính NH i , được tính bằng doanh thu/tổng tài sản. Giá trị của chỉ số Lerner dao động từ 0 đến 1. Tác giả ước lượng chi phí biên (MC) bằng cách lấy đạo hàm của tổng chi phí (TC) theo một đầu ra (TA). Phương trình ước lượng tương tự như cách của Beck và cộng sự (2013) và Silva-Buston (2019). Theo đó, giả sử rằng tại thời gian t tổng chi phí TC_{it} của ngân hàng i là hàm của một đầu ra, TA_{it} , và ba giá đầu vào, W_{hit} ($h = 1,2,3$, lần lượt đại diện cho chi phí quản lý, lao động và chi phí vốn). Từ đó, các biến số của của hàm chi phí – tuân theo điểm chính của các nghiên cứu thực nghiệm trong ngành ngân hàng - có dạng loga tự nhiên như sau:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln TC_{it} = & \alpha_0 + \alpha_Q \ln TA_{it} + \sum_{h=1}^3 \alpha_h \ln W_{hit} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{QQ} (\ln TA_{it})^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{h=1}^3 \sum_{k=1}^3 \alpha_{hk} \ln W_{hit} \ln W_{kit} \\ & + \sum_{h=1}^3 \alpha_{Qh} \ln TA_{it} \ln W_{hit} + \alpha_T T + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{TT} T^2 + \sum_{h=1}^3 \alpha_{Th} T \ln W_{hit} \\ & + \alpha_{TQ} T \ln TA_{it} \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Trong đó, i và t chỉ NH i vào năm t , TC là tổng chi phí, TA là tổng tài sản, W_k lần lượt là Chi phí hoạt động được tính bởi các chi phí hoạt động khác trên Tổng tài sản, Chi phí cho nhân viên chia cho tổng tài sản, và Chi phí vốn được tính bởi tỷ lệ Chi phí từ lãi trên Tổng số vốn huy động, trong khi T là xu hướng thời gian nhằm tính đến các tiến bộ về kỹ thuật/ công nghệ theo thời gian (Altunbaş và cộng sự, 2001; Brissimis và cộng sự, 2010). Trong hàm loga tự

nhiên, điều kiện không cân xứng đưa vào là $\alpha_{hk} = \alpha_{kh}$. Ngoài ra, đồng nhất tuyến tính trong giá đầu vào đòi hỏi rằng $\sum_{h=1}^3 \alpha_h = 1$, $\sum_{k=1}^3 \alpha_{hk} = 0$, và $\sum_{h=1}^3 \alpha_{Qh} = 0$ và $\sum_{h=1}^3 \alpha_{Th} = 0$. Để áp đặt các điều kiện trên, chúng ta có thể chia tổng chi phí và giá của tất cả các yếu tố đầu vào cho một trong các yếu tố giá, ví dụ, W_{3it} . Kết quả là, hàm chi phí dạng loga tự nhiên trở thành:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \ln \left(\frac{TC_{it}}{W_{3it}} \right) &= \alpha_0 + \alpha_Q \ln TA_{it} + \sum_{h=1}^2 \alpha_h \ln \left(\frac{W_{hit}}{W_{3it}} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{QQ} (\ln TA_{it})^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{h=1}^2 \sum_{k=1}^2 \alpha_{hk} \frac{\ln(W_{hit})}{W_{3it}} \ln \left(\frac{W_{kit}}{W_{3it}} \right) + \sum_{h=1}^2 \alpha_{Qh} \ln TA_{it} \ln \left(\frac{W_{hit}}{W_{3it}} \right) + \alpha_T T + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{TT} T^2 \\ &+ \sum_{h=1}^2 \alpha_{Th} T \ln \left(\frac{W_{hit}}{W_{3it}} \right) + \alpha_{TQ} T \ln TA_{it} \end{aligned}$$

Từ đó xác định được chi phí biên:

$$MC_{it} = \frac{\partial TC_{it}}{\partial TA_{it}} = \frac{TC_{it}}{TA_{it}} \left(\alpha_Q + \alpha_{QQ} \ln TA_{it} + \sum_{h=1}^2 \alpha_{Qh} \ln \left(\frac{W_{hit}}{W_{3it}} \right) + \alpha_{TQ} T \right)$$

Biến độc lập được chọn dựa trên cơ sở lý thuyết về các yếu tố tác động đến sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng được chia thành ba nhóm với các biến trong mỗi nhóm như sau:

Nhóm 1 – Đặc điểm của ngân hàng gồm: Quy mô, Hiệu quả quản lý chi phí, Rủi ro (gồm rủi ro tín dụng, rủi ro thanh khoản, rủi ro vốn), Đa dạng hóa thu nhập, Sở hữu nhà nước, Ngân hàng niêm yết.

Nhóm 2 – Yếu tố thuộc về ngành: mức độ tập trung được đánh giá bằng các thước đo khác nhau như số lượng NH, tỷ lệ tập trung và chỉ số HHI (Herfindahl-Hirschman Index), trong đó, chỉ số HHI được lựa chọn vì nó bao phủ được ảnh hưởng về thị phần của tất cả các ngân hàng trong thị trường. Chỉ số HHI được tính bằng cách cộng tổng bình phương thị phần của mỗi NH hoạt động trong ngành, công thức như sau:

$$HHI_t = \sum_{i=1}^N S_i^2, \forall_i = 1, \dots, N$$

Nhóm 3 – yếu tố kinh tế vĩ mô gồm yếu tố môi trường kinh tế và quy định pháp luật. Để đại diện cho các yếu tố thuộc môi trường kinh tế, nghiên cứu sử dụng bốn biến là tốc độ tăng GDP thực tế, lạm phát, tỷ lệ lãi suất chiết khấu và biến Khủng hoảng. Về yếu tố quy định pháp luật, một điểm đáng chú ý về chính sách có thể ảnh hưởng đến sức mạnh thị trường của các ngân hàng là việc Thủ tướng Chính phủ ban hành đề án “Cơ cấu lại hệ thống các TCTD” giai đoạn 2011-2015 với một trong các trọng tâm là đẩy mạnh hoạt động M&A các ngân hàng. Tiếp nối sau đó là các hai đề án “Cơ cấu lại hệ thống các TCTD gắn với xử lý nợ xấu” các giai đoạn 2016-2020 và 2021-2022 vẫn tiếp tục khuyến khích việc sáp nhập, hợp nhất mua lại các TCTD theo nguyên tắc tự nguyện. Từ đó, tác giả chọn thêm biến nhị phân BR để đánh giá tác động của các đề án này đến sức mạnh thị trường của các NH Việt Nam.

Cách tính toán, nguồn dữ liệu cũng như kỳ vọng dấu cho từng biến độc lập được tóm tắt lại ở Bảng 1.

Bảng 1: Tổng hợp các biến đưa vào mô hình

Tên biến	Cách đo lường	Dấu kỳ vọng
Biến phụ thuộc		
Lerner	Theo Lerner (1934)	
Biến độc lập – Đặc điểm của ngân hàng (BANKSPECIFIC)		
TA (Quy mô tài sản)	Logarit cơ số tự nhiên của Tổng TS	+
CI (Hiệu quả quản lý chi phí)	Chi phí hoạt động/Tổng thu nhập	-
CreR	RR tín dụng = Chi phí dự phòng rủi ro/Tài sản sinh lãi, được điều chỉnh thành: $\ln(NPL/(100-NPL))$	-
LiqR	RR thanh khoản = Cho vay khách hàng/ Tổng tiền gửi	-
CapR	RR vốn = (VCSH/Tổng tài sản) *(-1)	-
DIV (Đa dạng hóa thu nhập)	Thu nhập phi lãi/Tổng thu nhập	+/-
S (Sở hữu nhà nước)	Bằng 1 nếu là NH có trên 50% vốn Nhà nước và bằng 0 cho trường hợp còn lại.	+/-
P (Ngân hàng niêm yết)	Bằng 1 nếu là NH đã niêm yết bằng 0 cho trường hợp còn lại.	+
Biến độc lập – yếu tố thuộc về ngành		
HHI	$HHI = \sum_{i=1}^N S_i^2, \forall_i = 1, \dots, N$	+
Biến độc lập - Kinh tế vĩ mô (MACRO)		
GDP (tăng trưởng kinh tế)	Tốc độ tăng trưởng tổng sản phẩm quốc nội GDP thực tế	+
INF (lạm phát)	Tốc độ tăng trưởng chỉ số giá cả tiêu dùng (CPI)	-
RATE (lãi suất CSTT)	Lãi suất tái chiết khấu bình quân trong năm	-
Crisis (Khủng hoảng)	Bằng 1 trong giai đoạn 2008-2011 và bằng 0 trong những năm còn lại	-
BR (Tái cơ cấu TCTD)	Bằng 1 trong giai đoạn 2012-2021 và bằng 0 trong những năm còn lại	+

Nguồn: Tác giả tự tổng hợp

3.2. Dữ liệu nghiên cứu

Dữ liệu chính được sử dụng trong nghiên cứu được thu thập từ cơ sở dữ liệu của các công ty Việt Nam (FIIN). Một số dữ liệu thiếu được lấy từ chính báo cáo tài chính mà các ngân hàng công bố hàng năm. Dữ liệu chủ yếu là ở cấp độ từng NHTM giai đoạn 2005-2021 phụ thuộc vào sự sẵn có của dữ liệu. Mẫu nghiên cứu gồm 29 ngân hàng thuộc nhóm NHTM có vốn nhà nước chi phối và NHTMCP. Do một số ngân hàng mới được thành lập trong giai đoạn nghiên cứu, một số ngân hàng xuất phát từ những lý do khác nhau mà dữ liệu trong một vài

năm không được công bố đầy đủ (phổ biến nhất là không công bố chi phí nhân sự dùng để tính sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng).

3.3. Phương pháp xử lý dữ liệu:

Dữ liệu được xử lý lần lượt theo các bước sau:

- Thực hiện thống kê mô tả các biến.

- Kiểm tra hiện tượng đa cộng tuyến thông qua hệ số VIF.

- Thực hiện hồi quy theo các phương pháp: hiệu ứng cố định, hiệu ứng ngẫu nhiên và moment tổng quát hệ thống hai giai đoạn (2-stages system GMM). Mô hình GMM được phát triển bởi Arellano và Bond (1991) có thể giúp hạn chế hiện tượng nội sinh và các khuyết tật tự tương quan hay phương sai sai số thay đổi.

4. KẾT QUẢ NGHIÊN CỨU

Bảng 2 tóm tắt các thông kê mô tả của các biến dùng để ước lượng cho mô hình. Có thể thấy từ số liệu trong bảng, ngoại trừ các biến nhị phân S, P, Crisis, BR chỉ nhận hai giá trị 0 và 1, đại đa số các biến còn lại có số trung bình và số trung vị gần bằng nhau. Điều này chứng tỏ dãy dữ liệu khá cân bằng.

Bảng 2: Thống kê mô tả các biến

	Trung bình	Trung vị	Số nhỏ nhất	Số lớn nhất	Độ lệch chuẩn	Số quan sát
<i>Biến phụ thuộc</i>						
Lerner	0.124	0.111	-0.044	0.530	0.099	436
<i>Biến độc lập - các yếu tố thuộc ngân hàng</i>						
TA	18.064	18.219	11.88	21.29	1.614	478
CI	0.490	0.476	0.162	0.927	0.140	474
CreR	-5.325	-5.241	-8.742	-3.182	0.889	464
LidR	0.794	0.782	0.193	2.077	0.247	478
CapR	-1.104	-0.084	-0.712	-0.026	0.070	478
DIV	0.096	0.085	-0.098	0.425	0.072	474
<i>Biến độc lập – yếu tố thuộc về ngành</i>						
HHI	0.065	0.063	0.053	0.095	0.011	478
<i>Biến độc lập - các yếu tố thuộc môi trường vĩ mô</i>						
RGDP	0.059	0.062	0.026	0.075	0.013	478
INF	0.069	0.066	0.006	0.231	0.057	478
RATE	-0.001	-0.001	-0.042	0.056	0.024	478
Crisis	0.299	0	0	1	0.458	478
BR	0.607	1	0	1	0.489	478

Nguồn: Tác giả tính bằng phần mềm Stata 15

Bảng 3 trình bày kết quả kiểm tra hiện tượng đa cộng tuyến dựa trên hệ số phóng đại phương sai VIF. Với hệ số VIF của các biến đều nhỏ hơn 10, có thể kết luận rằng hiện tượng đa cộng tuyến chưa có ảnh hưởng nghiêm trọng đến kết quả mô hình.

Bảng 3: Kiểm định đa cộng tuyến

Biến	VIF
TA	6.64
CI	1.88
CreR	1.69
LiqR	1.29
CapR	2.57
DIV	1.60
S	2.28
P	1.54
HHI	2.90
RGDP	1.38
INF	5.03
RATE	2.37
Crisis	3.88
BR	5.94
VIF trung bình	2.93

Nguồn: Tác giả tính bằng phần mềm Stata 15

Bảng 4: Kết quả ước lượng mô hình các yếu tố tác động đến sức mạnh thị trường của các NHTM Việt Nam

Biến độc lập	Giả thuyết	FEM	REM	GMM
Lerner _{t-1}	+			.1388126 [1.68]
TA	+	.0193921*** [4.3]	.0203925*** [4.91]	.0208126** [2.72]
CI	-	-.4710729*** [-22.50]	-.4734025*** [-23.05]	-.4245825*** [-5.85]
CreR	-	-.0473987*** [-15.24]	-.0467526*** [-15.31]	-.0403536*** [-4.40]
LiqR	-	.0512016*** [4.47]	.0468604*** [4.27]	.0154896 [0.66]
CapR	-	-.3515891*** [-6.71]	-.3667276*** [-7.07]	-.4294123*** [-4.09]
DIV	+/-	.2119347*** [6.02]	.2154715*** [6.22]	.1733256*** [3.26]
S	+/-		-.0250586 [-1.32]	-.0184515 [-0.79]
P	+	.0344403*** [4.97]	.0341845*** [5.27]	.0209973** [2.07]

Biến độc lập	Giả thuyết	FEM	REM	GMM
HHI	+	.8407668*** [2.70]	.8881043*** [2.96]	.934387*** [2.93]
RGDP	+	-.0872696 [-0.58]	-.0709952 [-0.48]	-.0697236 [-0.49]
INF	-	-.1155048 [-1.61]	-.1077297 [-1.53]	-.1116639 [-1.10]
RATE	-	-.3127416*** [-2.61]	-.3261004*** [-2.80]	-.388319*** [-3.18]
Crisis	-	.0017141 [0.23]	.001701 [0.23]	.0026215 [0.32]
BR	+	-.0087058 [-0.91]	-.0090667 [-0.97]	-.0054846 [-0.36]
_cons		-.3925442*** [-3.91]	-.4056206*** [-4.40]	-.3998143** [-2.47]
N		417	417	381
R2		0.7903	0.8016	
F		141.22***	1909.69***	431.06***
F (Likelihood)		10.57 (0.000)		
Wald Test		110.19 (0.000)		
Wooldridge Test		230.789 (0.000)		
Hausman (p-value)		12.61 (0.4785)		
Số ngân hàng				29
Số biến công cụ				23
Sargan Test (p-value)				17.59 (0.014)
Hansen Test (p-value)				8.92 (0.259)
Arellano-Bond Test				
AR (1) p-value				-2.84 (0.005)
AR (2) p-value				-0.77 (0.444)

*, **, *** thể hiện mức ý nghĩa lần lượt là 10%, 5% và 1%

Nguồn: Tác giả tính bằng phần mềm Stata 15

Với các giá trị F lần lượt là 141,22; 1909,69; 431,06 tương ứng với các giá trị p-value đều rất nhỏ, kết quả ước lượng là có ý nghĩa thống kê với cả 3 mô hình FEM, REM, GMM. Kiểm định Hausman với p-value < 0.05 cho thấy mô hình REM sẽ hiệu quả hơn mô hình FEM. Kiểm định Wald và Wooldridge cho thấy mô hình có hiện tượng phương sai sai số thay đổi và tự tương quan. Từ đó, các kết luận dựa trên phương pháp GMM sẽ được ưu tiên hơn. Ảnh hưởng của từng yếu tố cụ thể như sau:

Quy mô có tác động cùng chiều đến SMTT của các ngân hàng theo kết quả của cả ba mô hình. Kết quả này phù hợp với kỳ vọng đặt ra ban đầu là lợi thế nhờ quy mô tạo điều kiện thuận lợi giúp các ngân hàng có lợi thế so với đối thủ, từ đó tăng cường SMTT.

Tỷ lệ chi phí trên tổng thu nhập (tăng tương đương với hiệu quả chi phí giảm) ảnh hưởng ngược chiều đến SMTT của ngân hàng. Kết quả này thống nhất với giả thuyết được xây dựng dựa trên lý thuyết Hiệu quả thuần túy. Rõ ràng, những ngân hàng quản lý chi phí hiệu quả sẽ có ưu thế trong việc đặt giá, từ đó, kiếm được nhiều lợi nhuận hơn cũng như tạo ra được rào cản ngăn cản sự cạnh tranh từ những người mới gia nhập.

Rủi ro tín dụng và rủi ro vốn đều có tác động ngược chiều với SMTT của ngân hàng trong khi rủi ro thanh khoản có tác động cùng chiều theo kết quả của hai mô hình FEM, REM nhưng không có ý thống kê trong mô hình GMM. Với ưu tiên dùng kết quả GMM, có thể kết luận chưa có bằng chứng cho thấy rủi ro thanh khoản có ảnh hưởng đến SMTT của ngân hàng. Ảnh hưởng ngược chiều của rủi ro tín dụng với kết quả nghiên cứu của De Guevara và cộng sự (2005) là việc ngân hàng sử dụng nhiều nguồn lực để giảm rủi ro tín dụng sẽ được hưởng lợi nhuận biên cao hơn. Ảnh hưởng của rủi ro vốn đối với SMTT cũng thống nhất với nghiên cứu của Delis (2012).

Hoạt động đa dạng hóa đang có ảnh hưởng tích cực lên SMTT của các ngân hàng. Kết quả này thống nhất với kết quả nghiên cứu của Carbó-Valverde và Rodríguez-Fernández (2007) và cho thấy các ngân hàng Việt Nam đã thu được lợi ích từ đa dạng hóa thông qua việc tăng sự gắn kết với khách hàng.

Về cấu trúc sở hữu, không có sự khác biệt về sức mạnh thị trường giữa ngân hàng nhà nước chiếm cổ phần chi phối và các ngân hàng khác trong khi các ngân hàng niêm yết nhìn chung có SMTT lớn hơn. Điều này có thể do các ngân hàng nhà nước phải tham gia vào nhiều các nhiệm vụ chính trị cũng như các hoạt động cho vay ưu đãi làm đôi khi họ không thể đặt được mức giá phù hợp với SMTT của họ. Trong khi đó, chủ trương của Đảng và Chính phủ trong những năm gần đây là đẩy mạnh tốc độ niêm yết của các ngân hàng nên nhìn chung những ngân hàng đáp ứng đủ các yêu cầu về năng lực tài chính, năng lực quản trị và năng lực cạnh tranh đều sớm lên sàn, nghĩa là những ngân hàng chưa niêm yết đang có kết quả hoạt động kinh doanh nhìn chung là kém hơn.

Mức độ tập trung thị trường có ảnh hưởng cùng chiều đến SMTT của ngân hàng. Kết quả này phù hợp với kết quả quan sát được trên thị trường. Cụ thể, khoảng thời gian 2005-2011 là giai đoạn hoàn tất quá trình chuyển đổi các NHTM cổ phần nông thôn thành ngân hàng đô thị, tiếp nối là thành lập ngân hàng mới cũng như đẩy mạnh mở rộng quy mô nhằm đáp ứng quy định mới về vốn pháp định cũng là giai đoạn chứng kiến các ngân hàng cạnh tranh khốc liệt và sức mạnh thị trường nhiều ngân hàng suy giảm.

Trong các biến vĩ mô, chỉ có biến thay đổi lãi suất chính sách là có tác động ngược chiều đến SMTT của các ngân hàng. Điều này là do khi lãi suất tăng, chi phí của ngân hàng tăng lên nhưng tăng lãi cho vay thường bị hạn chế do lo ngại rủi ro tín dụng.

5. KẾT LUẬN VÀ KHUYẾN NGHỊ

Nghiên cứu đã xây dựng được một mô hình để đánh giá các yếu tố có tác động đến SMTT của các ngân hàng Việt Nam. Kết quả mô hình cho thấy SMTT của ngân hàng chịu ảnh hưởng của các yếu tố như quy mô ngân hàng, hiệu quả quản lý, rủi ro tín dụng, rủi ro vốn, hoạt động đa dạng hóa thu nhập, mức độ tập trung thị trường và lãi suất. Cụ thể, tổng tài sản, đa dạng hóa thu nhập và mức độ tập trung thị trường có ảnh hưởng cùng chiều đến SMTT của

ngân hàng, trong khi tỷ lệ chi phí trên thu nhập (tương đương với giảm hiệu quả), rủi ro tín dụng, rủi ro mất vốn và lãi suất có tác động ngược chiều đến SMTT. Từ kết quả mô hình, tác giả đề xuất một số khuyến nghị nhằm cải thiện SMTT của các ngân hàng:

Khuyến nghị 1: Tăng vốn chủ sở hữu và nâng cao năng lực tài chính. Mở rộng quy mô là biện pháp cơ bản để tăng cường hiệu quả, từ đó, cải thiện sức mạnh thị trường. Mở rộng quy mô đầu với việc giảm tỷ lệ chia cổ tức, tìm nhà đầu tư chiến lược, phát hành cổ phiếu hoặc các công cụ lai ghép như trái phiếu/cổ phiếu chuyển đổi. Các ngân hàng quy mô nhỏ, khả năng thu hút nhà đầu tư, kêu gọi vốn kém hơn có thể cân nhắc hợp nhất, sáp nhập với ngân hàng khác để đẩy nhanh tốc độ tăng quy mô.

Khuyến nghị 2: Nâng cao năng lực quản lý chi phí. Các ngân hàng cần chú trọng đầu tư phát triển công nghệ, tăng tốc độ chuyển đổi số. Ngân hàng nhỏ có thể cân nhắc các mô hình hoạt động mới dựa trên việc mở rộng liên kết và tận dụng hệ sinh thái của các đơn vị liên kết để phân phối sản phẩm.

Khuyến nghị 3: Tiếp tục đẩy mạnh các chiến lược đa dạng hóa. Tích cực phát triển những sản phẩm mới đáp ứng được thói quen mới của khách hàng trong thời đại số hóa. Các ngân hàng quy mô lớn và năng lực tài chính tốt có thể chọn chiến lược dẫn đầu bằng cách thành lập bộ phận nghiên cứu chuyên trách về phát triển sản phẩm công nghệ cao. Bộ phận này sẽ thường xuyên quan sát tìm hiểu nhu cầu của khách hàng, tiếp nhận phản hồi để tạo ra những sản phẩm ngân hàng mới nổi bật tạo nên sự khác biệt. Các ngân hàng nhỏ có thể tập trung vào các thị trường ngách.

Khuyến nghị 4: Tăng cường quản trị rủi ro. Nghiêm chỉnh chấp hành các quy định của pháp luật. Các NH chưa đạt chuẩn Basel II cần đẩy nhanh hơn nữa tốc độ triển khai ít nhất là theo phương pháp chuẩn, những ngân hàng đã sớm hoàn thành có thể thử nghiệm triển khai Basel II theo phương pháp nâng cao và sau là dần chuyển sang Basel III trong thời gian tới.

Khuyến nghị 5: Tạo sự khác biệt trong sản phẩm và xây dựng lợi thế cạnh tranh. Các ngân hàng cần liên tục tìm kiếm để trả lời câu hỏi: Điều gì mà ngân hàng mình có mà những ngân hàng khác không có, hoặc cái gì mà ngân hàng mình đang làm mà những đối thủ khác không làm, để đáp ứng nhu cầu và mong muốn hiện tại của khách hàng tốt hơn so với đối thủ cạnh tranh.

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VAI TRÒ CỦA VIỆC GIẢNG DẠY DỮ LIỆU LỚN VÀ PHÂN TÍCH DỮ LIỆU TRONG KẾ TOÁN - KIỂM TOÁN

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Tóm tắt

Trong thời đại công nghệ số hiện nay, công việc của kế toán, kiểm toán không còn thực hiện một cách thủ công như trước kia mà thay vào đó là sự tự động hóa, từ khâu nhập dữ liệu, kết nối dữ liệu, xử lý, lập báo cáo và phân tích báo cáo. Mặt khác, số lượng giao dịch, dữ liệu phát sinh ngày càng khổng lồ, đòi hỏi kế toán có khả năng làm việc được với một lượng lớn dữ liệu. Mặc dù, việc tích hợp dữ liệu lớn cũng như phân tích dữ liệu trong chương trình giảng dạy kế toán tại các trường đại học, cao đẳng đã được thực hiện, nhưng vẫn còn khá hạn chế tại các trường đại học tại Việt Nam. Bài viết đưa ra thông tin khảo sát việc giảng dạy về phân tích dữ liệu tại một số trường đại học kinh tế và quan điểm của người giảng dạy trong việc đưa phân tích dữ liệu vào trong các chương trình giảng dạy hiện nay.

Từ khóa: *Dữ liệu lớn, phân tích dữ liệu, kế toán, kiểm toán*

GIÁM SÁT RỦI RO HỆ THỐNG: BÀI HỌC TẠI CÁC QUỐC GIA

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Tóm tắt

Cuộc khủng hoảng kinh tế và tài chính tại Mỹ năm 2008 đã làm thay đổi nhận thức của các nhà nghiên cứu về nguy cơ cũng như hậu quả khốc liệt của rủi ro hệ thống đến hoạt động tổng thể của nền kinh tế, đồng thời cũng cho thấy cần sự cải thiện quy định và giám sát tài chính từ các quan điểm hệ thống. Trong bài viết của mình, các tác giả cố gắng hệ thống hóa các lý thuyết chung về rủi ro hệ thống và giám sát rủi ro hệ thống, phân tích kinh nghiệm giám sát rủi ro hệ thống tại một số quốc gia. Đồng thời phân tích nguy cơ rủi ro hệ thống tại ngân hàng thương mại Việt Nam trong giai đoạn 2009 – 2021. Từ đó, các tác giả rút ra bài học và khuyến nghị trong việc giám sát rủi ro hệ thống trong khu vực ngân hàng.

Từ khóa: rủi ro hệ thống, hệ thống tài chính, nợ xấu, đòn bẩy tài chính

SYSTEMIC RISK SUPERVISION: LESSONS FROM COUNTRIES

Abstract

The economic and financial crisis in the US in 2008 changed the perception about the importance and consequences of systemic risk on the overall performance of the whole financial system, and also indicates the need for improving financial regulation and supervision. In this paper, the authors try to systematize the general theories of systematic risk and systematic risk monitoring, analyzing the experience of systematic risk monitoring in some countries. Moreover, the authors also analyze systemic risk at Vietnamese commercial banks in the period of 2009 - 2021. Lastly, the authors draw lessons and recommendations in monitoring systemic risk in the Vietnam banking sector.

Keyword: systemic risk, financial system, non performing loans, financial leverage

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Cuộc khủng hoảng tài chính toàn cầu 2007 – 2008 đã đặt ra hai vấn đề vốn bị xem nhẹ trước đây trong hệ thống tài chính là rủi ro hệ thống và giảm thiểu rủi ro hệ thống như thế nào. Trước cuộc khủng hoảng tài chính 2007 – 2008, các cơ quan giám sát chỉ quan tâm đến các rủi ro riêng lẻ như rủi ro tín dụng, rủi ro thanh khoản, rủi ro hoạt động ... và coi rủi ro hệ thống là một phần của các rủi ro riêng lẻ đó (Meuleman và cộng sự, 2020). Đồng thời, hoạt động giám sát ngân hàng giai đoạn đó cũng tập trung chủ yếu vào khía cạnh vi mô, nghĩa là đảm bảo sự an toàn, lành mạnh và hạn chế rủi ro của từng tổ chức tài chính riêng lẻ. Tuy nhiên, cuộc khủng hoảng 2008 và những vụ việc như Lehman Brothers đã chứng minh rằng sự thất bại của một ngân hàng có thể khiến toàn bộ hệ thống trở nên không ổn định và việc giữ cho các tổ chức tài chính riêng lẻ hoạt động tốt không phải là điều kiện đủ để đảm bảo sự ổn định tài chính (Meuleman và cộng sự, 2020). Sự sụp đổ của các NHTM có thể lan truyền trong hệ thống tài

chính, tạo ra những cú sốc cho thị trường tài chính và ảnh hưởng tiêu cực tới nền kinh tế. Khi các NHTM gặp rủi ro và trở nên thiếu vốn, khả năng cung cấp tín dụng ra nền kinh tế sẽ bị ảnh hưởng tiêu cực và kéo theo rủi ro khủng hoảng kinh tế gia tăng. Chính vì thế, nhiều nghiên cứu đã đề cập đến sự cần thiết phải cải thiện quy định và giám sát tài chính từ các quan điểm hệ thống bởi những nguyên nhân sau: (i) khuôn khổ quản lý tài chính trên thế giới đã quá ít chú ý đến “rủi ro hệ thống”; (ii) các quy định tài chính hiện hành có xu hướng khuyến khích việc chấp nhận rủi ro theo chu kỳ, điều này làm tăng khả năng xảy ra các cuộc khủng hoảng tài chính và mức độ nghiêm trọng của chúng khi chúng xảy ra; (iii) các quy định hiện hành không xử lý thỏa đáng “các tổ chức tài chính lớn và phức tạp” – các trung gian tài chính tham gia vào một số tổ hợp ngân hàng thương mại, ngân hàng đầu tư, quản lý tài sản và bảo hiểm – mà sự thất bại của họ gây ra rủi ro hệ thống hoặc “ngoại tác” đối với hệ thống tài chính (Haldane, 2009).

Tại Việt Nam, trong giai đoạn 2009 – 2021, hoạt động các NHTM Việt Nam có nhiều biến động. Cùng với việc biến động về hoạt động thi trong giai đoạn này các NHTM Việt Nam cũng đối mặt với nhiều nguy cơ tiềm ẩn rủi ro hệ thống như tỷ lệ tín dụng trên GDP còn ở mức cao, tỷ lệ nợ xấu tăng cao, cơ cấu tín dụng tập trung một số ngành có nguy cơ cao như chứng khoán, bất động sản, thị trường tập trung ở một số nhóm khách hàng lớn. Điều này cho thấy nguy cơ rủi ro hệ thống tiềm ẩn tại các NHTM Việt Nam và cần phải tăng cường giám sát rủi ro hệ thống một cách hiệu quả để tránh lan truyền đến nền kinh tế

Với cách nhìn nhận như vậy, bài viết sẽ được chia thành 5 nội dung chính. Ngoài phần 1 giới thiệu về bài viết, trong phần 2, tác giả sẽ khái quát các vấn đề về rủi ro hệ thống và giám sát rủi ro hệ thống. Trong phần 3 tác giả sẽ phân tích kinh nghiệm giám sát rủi ro hệ thống tại một số quốc gia. Phần 4, các tác giả sẽ phân tích thực trạng rủi ro hệ thống tại các NHTM trong giai đoạn 2009 – 2021. Từ đó, tác giả đưa ra các bài học và khuyến nghị chính sách trong phần 5.

2. CƠ SỞ LÝ THUYẾT VỀ RỦI RO HỆ THỐNG VÀ GIÁM SÁT RỦI RO HỆ THỐNG

2.1. Khái niệm rủi ro hệ thống

So với những rủi ro khác, rủi ro hệ thống được nhận diện tương đối muộn. Về mặt lý thuyết, rủi ro hệ thống xuất hiện khoảng những năm 90 của thế kỷ 20 nhưng chỉ thật sự được chú ý sau cuộc khủng hoảng tài chính toàn cầu năm 2007 – 2008. Nghiên cứu cho thấy, đến nay vẫn chưa có khái niệm thống nhất cho vấn đề này. Một số khái niệm rủi ro hệ thống tiêu biểu như sau:

Mishkin (1995) đã định nghĩa, rủi ro hệ thống là khả năng xảy ra sự kiện bất ngờ, thường là không dự tính được, làm gián đoạn thông tin trên thị trường tài chính, khiến thị trường không thể luân chuyển vốn một cách hiệu quả cho các bên có cơ hội đầu tư hiệu quả nhất.

Hội đồng thống đốc hệ thống dự trữ liên bang (2001) đã đưa ra khái niệm về rủi ro hệ thống như sau: “rủi ro hệ thống có thể xảy ra nếu một tổ chức/định chế trong một mạng lưới thanh toán USD lớn riêng biệt không thể hoặc không sẵn sàng thanh toán số nợ ròng của nó. Nếu xảy ra việc không thanh toán, các chủ nợ của tổ chức trong mạng thanh toán cũng không thể thanh toán các nghĩa vụ của mình. Do đó, hậu quả nghiêm trọng có thể lan sang những tổ chức/định chế khác trong mạng lưới riêng biệt, đến các tổ chức tiền gửi khác trong hệ thống và đến cả những tổ chức khác không tham gia vào mạng lưới và nói chung đến nền kinh tế...”

Ngân hàng Trung ương châu Âu (Ngân hàng trung ương châu Âu, 2004) định nghĩa Rủi ro hệ thống: là rủi ro mà một tổ chức không có khả năng thực hiện/đáp ứng các nghĩa vụ của mình khi đến hạn khiến các tổ chức khác không thể đáp ứng nghĩa vụ của họ khi đến

hạn. Sự thất bại này có thể gây ra vấn đề thanh khoản hoặc tín dụng nghiêm trọng và, do đó, đe dọa sự ổn định hoặc niềm tin vào thị trường. Rủi ro này cũng tiếp cận hướng tương tự với khái niệm của Kaufmann và Scott nhưng đã chỉ ra nguyên nhân và hậu quả của rủi ro hệ thống một cách rõ ràng hơn.

Tuy nhiên, cuộc khủng hoảng tài chính 2007-2008 đã cho thấy các định nghĩa ở trên đã bỏ qua hoặc không mô tả rõ ràng về một về một thuộc tính quan trọng của các cuộc khủng hoảng hệ thống, đó là các tác động/thiệt hại bên ngoài hệ thống tài chính của cuộc khủng hoảng này do việc không thực hiện hiệu quả chức năng chính của hệ thống tài chính bao gồm cung cấp thanh khoản, tín dụng và dịch vụ, hay nói cách khác bỏ qua nguy cơ lan tỏa từ lĩnh vực tài chính sang nền kinh tế thực và các chi phí liên quan. Schwarcz (2008) định nghĩa về rủi ro hệ thống là rủi ro (i) một cú sốc kinh tế ví dụ sự thất bại/sụp đổ một định chế hay cả thị trường kích hoạt/gây ra (thông qua sự hoảng loạn hoặc bằng cách khác) (X) sự thất bại của thị trường hoặc một chuỗi tổ chức hoặc (Y) một chuỗi tổn thất đáng kể đối với các tổ chức tài chính, (ii) dẫn đến tăng chi phí vốn hoặc giảm tính sẵn có của nguồn vốn, thường được chứng minh bằng sự biến động giá đáng kể trên thị trường tài chính.

Dựa vào khái niệm trên, rủi ro hệ thống có thể được mô hình hóa như hình 1. Theo đó, toàn bộ quá trình bắt đầu với một cú sốc. Nếu các cú sốc này ảnh hưởng đầu tiên đến các tổ chức có ý nghĩa hệ thống thì tác động của nó đối với hệ thống tài chính càng mạnh. Những cú sốc bao gồm cú sốc nội sinh (xuất phát từ sự sụp đổ/khó khăn của một tổ chức) hoặc ngoại sinh (cú sốc bên ngoài). Cú sốc sau đó được chuyển qua các kênh truyền nhiễm liên quan đến nhau, bao gồm: mối liên kết song phương; thị trường (thông tin); cấu trúc: sự tương đồng về cấu trúc tài sản/nợ phải trả (rủi ro với các cú sốc đối xứng), sản phẩm, hệ thống thanh toán.

Hình 1: Mô hình rủi ro hệ thống

Nguồn: Smaga, 2014

2.2. Hậu quả rủi ro hệ thống

Các tác động kinh tế thực tế bất lợi gây nên bởi rủi ro hệ thống sẽ ảnh hưởng đến các công ty và hộ gia đình khi các ngân hàng và các trung gian tài chính khác không thể thực hiện các chức năng của họ. Các chức năng này có thể được phân loại thành ba loại lớn: (i) cung cấp dịch vụ thanh toán, (ii) chia sẻ và quản lý rủi ro và (iii) cung cấp tín dụng.

- *Sự gián đoạn hệ thống thanh toán*: Việc gián đoạn thanh toán có thể bắt nguồn từ sự sụp đổ của ngân hàng với việc đóng băng tạm thời tiền gửi không kỳ hạn của ngân hàng đó hoặc do sự thất bại của một ngân hàng đại lý trong giao dịch khiến cho việc thanh toán không thể thực hiện được. Sự gián đoạn thanh toán cũng có thể xảy ra khi có sự không chắc chắn về việc liệu thanh toán sẽ đến đích do ngân hàng nhận thanh toán hay ngân hàng thanh toán phải đối mặt với rủi ro vỡ nợ nghiêm trọng.

- *Sự suy yếu của chức năng chia sẻ và quản lý rủi ro của các ngân hàng* ví dụ các khoản bảo lãnh, cung ứng các hợp đồng phái sinh... Trong điều kiện xảy ra sự kiện hệ thống, các điều khoản của hợp đồng không thể được thực hiện vì người trả tiền không thể thực hiện thanh toán. Ngoài ra, một số dịch vụ có giá trị mà các ngân hàng và các trung gian tài chính khác cung cấp có thể không được thực hiện hoặc thực hiện với rủi ro đối tác rất lớn. Hơn nữa, trên thị trường bán buôn việc quản lý rủi ro thanh khoản của các NHTM là rất quan trọng và điều này có thể không hoạt động trong các sự kiện hệ thống (Brunnermeier và Pedersen 2008).

- *Sự suy giảm dòng tín dụng cho nền kinh tế trong sự kiện hệ thống*, các ngân hàng chọn giảm nguồn cung tín dụng do thiếu thanh khoản hoặc vốn, do đó tạo ra khủng hoảng tín dụng cho các công ty và hộ gia đình (Bernanke và Lown 1992). Một số lượng lớn các khoản vay bị đòi lại là kết quả của các vấn đề ngân hàng. Thêm vào đó, trong rủi ro hệ thống, các khách hàng bị từ chối cho vay ở ngân hàng này cũng không thể đến vay tại ngân hàng khác.

2.3. Giám sát rủi ro hệ thống

2.3.1. Về nguyên tắc giám sát rủi ro hệ thống

Theo Bernanke (2009), hoạt động giám sát rủi ro hệ thống bao gồm các nội dung:

- Thực hiện giám sát hợp nhất tất cả các tổ chức tài chính quan trọng trong hệ thống;
- Giám sát các khoản vay có số dư lớn hoặc gia tăng nhanh về giá trị, giữa các tổ chức tài chính và thị trường, thay vì chỉ ở cấp độ của các tổ chức hoặc lĩnh vực riêng lẻ;
- Đánh giá các rủi ro hệ thống tiềm ẩn do sự phát triển của các nghiệp vụ quản lý rủi ro, sự gia tăng đòn bẩy tài chính trên diện rộng, những thay đổi trong thị trường tài chính hoặc sản phẩm;
- Phân tích tác động lan tỏa có thể có giữa các tổ chức tài chính hoặc giữa các tổ chức và thị trường, chẳng hạn như sự bộc lộ lẫn nhau của các tổ chức có mối liên hệ chặt chẽ với nhau;
- Đảm bảo rằng mỗi tổ chức tài chính quan trọng trong hệ thống nhận được sự giám sát tương xứng với những rủi ro mà sự thất bại của nó sẽ gây ra cho hệ thống tài chính;
- Cung cấp một cơ chế giải quyết để ngăn chặn thất bại một cách an toàn, các thể chế quan trọng về mặt hệ thống;
- Chỉ định quyền hạn thống nhất và mạnh mẽ để giám sát thận trọng các hệ thống thanh toán quan trọng về mặt hệ thống để đảm bảo cơ sở hạ tầng tài chính quan trọng đủ mạnh;
- Làm việc để giảm thiểu các đặc điểm chu kỳ của quy định vốn và các quy tắc và tiêu chuẩn khác;

- Xác định các lỗ hổng quy định có thể có, bao gồm các lỗ hổng trong việc bảo vệ người tiêu dùng và nhà đầu tư gây rủi ro cho toàn hệ thống;
- Giảm thiểu rủi ro dòng vốn ngừng hoạt động đột ngột gây ra sự điều chỉnh tỷ giá hối đoái có tác động tiêu cực đến các ngân hàng, hộ gia đình và tập đoàn có các khoản nợ lớn;
- Chia sẻ những phát hiện trong một diễn đàn ổn định khu vực và toàn cầu; và
- Phát hành các báo cáo định kỳ về sự ổn định của hệ thống tài chính, nhằm đảm bảo kỷ luật thị trường thông qua tính minh bạch cũng như các cuộc tranh luận có thông tin.

2.3.2. Về tổ chức giám sát rủi ro hệ thống

- *Xác định mục tiêu giám sát*

Để giám sát hiệu quả rủi ro hệ thống, cơ quan quản lý trước hết cần xác định được các ngân hàng có tầm quan trọng hệ thống. Các ngân hàng có tầm quan trọng hệ thống (Systemically Important Banks – SIBs) được chia thành nhóm các ngân hàng có tầm quan trọng hệ thống toàn cầu (Global Systemically Important Banks – G-SIBs) và các ngân hàng có tầm quan trọng hệ thống quốc gia (Domestic Systematically Important Banks – D-SIBs). G-SIBs là các ngân hàng mà khi xảy ra rủi ro có thể dẫn đến những hậu quả tiềm ẩn xuyên biên giới, tác động tiêu cực tới các tổ chức tài chính ở nhiều quốc gia và nền kinh tế toàn cầu nói chung. Đối với D-SIBs, khi các tổ chức này gặp rủi ro, có thể khiến thị trường tài chính và nền kinh tế của một quốc gia rơi vào khủng hoảng. Tuy nhiên, mức độ tác động và ảnh hưởng của các tổ chức này đối với thị trường tài chính và nền kinh tế toàn cầu là không quá nghiêm trọng

- *Đánh giá và phân loại các ngân hàng có tầm quan trọng hệ thống*

Đối với G-SIBs, Phương pháp luận của Ủy ban Basel để đánh giá tầm quan trọng hệ thống của G-SIB dựa trên cách tiếp cận đo lường dựa trên chỉ số. Các chỉ số được lựa chọn để phản ánh các khía cạnh khác nhau của các nhân tố tạo ra ngoại tác tiêu cực và làm cho một ngân hàng trở nên quan trọng đối với sự ổn định của hệ thống tài chính toàn cầu. Tầm quan trọng hệ thống được đo lường bởi 5 nhóm danh mục, bao gồm: quy mô, hoạt động giữa các khu vực pháp lý/tài pháp, tính liên kết với nhau, khả năng thay thế/cơ sở hạ tầng tổ chức tài chính và độ phức tạp; trong đó mỗi yếu tố có tỷ trọng bằng nhau và bằng 20%..

Đối với D-SIBs, việc đánh giá D-SIB tập trung vào tác động mà sự khó khăn hoặc thất bại của các ngân hàng (bao gồm cả các ngân hàng quốc tế) sẽ gây ra đối với nền kinh tế trong nước. Do đó, việc đánh giá do cơ quan quản lý quốc gia thực hiện, để đánh giá tốt nhất các tác động của sự thất bại đối với hệ thống tài chính và nền kinh tế quốc gia đó. Ủy ban cũng nêu ra 12 nguyên tắc về phương pháp đánh giá D-SIB.

- *Quy trình giám sát*

Quyết định giám sát đối với tổ chức có tầm quan trọng hệ thống được đưa ra dựa trên điểm số được xác định cho nhóm các ngân hàng trong mẫu và xếp loại mức độ rủi ro hệ thống. Đối với G-SIBs, quá trình này tập trung vào các yếu tố liên quan đến tác động hệ thống toàn cầu của ngân hàng, tức là tác động của tình trạng khó khăn / sụp đổ của ngân hàng chứ không phải xác suất gặp khó khăn / thất bại (tức là mức độ rủi ro) của ngân hàng. Phán quyết cao nhất/cuối cùng phải bao gồm thông tin định lượng cũng như định tính được lập thành văn bản và có thể xác minh được.

Cụ thể, quy trình giám sát rủi ro hệ thống được khuyến nghị như sau:

- (1) Thu thập dữ liệu và nhận định giám sát cho tất cả các ngân hàng trong mẫu.
- (2) Ứng dụng phương pháp đo lường dựa trên chỉ số và xếp hạng tương ứng.
- (3) Các cơ quan có liên quan đề xuất điều chỉnh điểm số của từng ngân hàng trên cơ sở quy trình đã được thống nhất.
- (4) Ủy ban Basel xây dựng các khuyến nghị cho FSB.
- (5) FSB và các cơ quan chức năng quốc gia, với sự tham vấn của Ủy ban Basel, đưa ra quyết định cuối cùng về danh mục các tổ chức có tầm quan trọng hệ thống.

Nhóm các G-SIBs và D-SIBs được FSB theo dõi và rà soát thường xuyên để đảm bảo rằng chúng vẫn phù hợp theo: (i) sự phát triển trong lĩnh vực ngân hàng; (ii) tiến bộ trong các phương pháp và cách tiếp cận để đo lường tầm quan trọng mang tính hệ thống; (iii) thay đổi cấu trúc; và (iv) bất kỳ bằng chứng nào về các hậu quả không mong muốn hoặc thiếu sót trọng yếu đối với các mục tiêu của khuôn khổ.

3. KINH NGHIỆM GIÁM SÁT RỦI RO HỆ THỐNG MỘT SỐ QUỐC GIA TRÊN THẾ GIỚI

3.1. Kinh nghiệm giám sát rủi ro hệ thống của Hàn Quốc

3.1.1. Tổ chức giám sát rủi ro hệ thống ở Hàn Quốc:

Trách nhiệm giám sát rủi ro hệ thống ở Hàn Quốc được chia sẻ giữa các cơ quan quản lý tài chính, ngân hàng trung ương và chính phủ. Ủy ban dịch vụ tài chính (FSC), Ủy ban giám sát tài chính (FSS), Bộ kinh tế và tài chính (MOEF) và Ngân hàng trung ương Hàn Quốc (BOK) đều thực hiện các hoạt động giám sát. Giới hạn giám sát được thiết lập rộng rãi để nắm bắt hoạt động của các ngân hàng, các tổ chức nhận tiền gửi phi ngân hàng, các công ty tài chính, các tổ chức bảo lãnh công và những trung gian tài chính khác. Ủy ban giám sát tài chính và ủy ban dịch vụ tài chính đảm nhiệm việc giám sát tần suất cao đối với các thị trường trọng yếu. Ngân hàng Trung ương Hàn Quốc là cơ quan chính chịu trách nhiệm giám sát hệ thống NHTM và chia sẻ các báo cáo đánh giá rủi ro cho các bên liên quan.

3.1.2. Các biện pháp thực hiện giám sát rủi ro hệ thống ở Hàn Quốc

- *Giám sát rủi ro các tổ chức tài chính:* BOK thực hiện song song việc “giám sát từ xa” và “thanh tra tại chỗ” đối với các tổ chức tài chính.

Giám sát từ xa được thực hiện như sau: (i) đánh giá việc quản lý tài sản và khả năng sinh lời của các nhóm ngân hàng và tổ chức nhận tiền gửi phi ngân hàng; (ii) đưa ra báo cáo nội bộ và phân tích chuyên sâu khi phát hiện ra lỗ hổng trong các lĩnh vực kinh doanh của các tổ chức tài chính; (iii) trình lên Hội nghị ổn định tài chính do Ủy ban đánh giá an toàn vĩ mô chủ trì về các vấn đề trọng yếu.

Thanh tra tại chỗ thông qua một trong hai hình thức: tập trung vào từng ngân hàng riêng lẻ; hoặc thực hiện đối với tất cả khu vực ngân hàng. Đối với đánh giá cấp khu vực, các chuyên gia giám sát của BOK đánh giá các vấn đề tương tự như nhau của nhiều ngân hàng. Các vấn đề chính để xem xét theo ngành đã được ủy ban đánh giá an toàn vĩ mô thông qua.

- *Xác định các tổ chức có tầm quan trọng hệ thống*

Tại Hàn Quốc, việc xác định các tổ chức có tầm quan trọng hệ thống được thực hiện định kỳ hàng năm dựa trên bộ tiêu chí được đưa ra trong Đạo luật sửa đổi về cải thiện cơ cấu ngành tài chính và các tiêu chí đánh giá do Ủy ban Basel về Giám sát Ngân hàng (BCBS) khuyến nghị. Theo đó, các tổ chức được phân loại là có tầm quan trọng hệ thống dựa 5 nhóm tiêu chí bao gồm: quy mô, tính kết nối, khả năng thay thế, mức độ phức tạp và các yếu tố quốc gia cụ thể. Các tiêu chí này có tỷ trọng điểm bằng nhau và được cụ thể hóa bởi một hệ thống thang chỉ báo. Ngày 13/7/2021, FSC đã xác định 10 D-SIB trong năm 2022.

- *Giám sát các tổ chức có tầm quan trọng hệ thống*

Những ngân hàng được xác định là D-SIB được yêu cầu gửi kế hoạch phục hồi khi gặp rủi ro của mình cho Ủy ban giám sát Tài chính (FSS) trong vòng ba tháng kể từ ngày được chỉ định là D-SIB. Các ngân hàng này được yêu cầu dành riêng một khoản vốn cổ phần phổ thông bổ sung là 1% và yêu cầu về khả năng hấp thụ tổn thất cao hơn sẽ có hiệu lực vào ngày 1 tháng 1 năm 2022.

- *Cảnh báo sớm rủi ro hệ thống*

Việc cảnh báo sớm rủi ro hệ thống được Ngân hàng trung ương Hàn Quốc (BOK) thực hiện thông qua xây dựng “bộ chỉ số ổn định tài chính” (FSI) và công bố chỉ số này trong Báo cáo ổn định tài chính (FSR) nhằm cung cấp tín hiệu về sự gia tăng tích lũy rủi ro hệ thống. Bên cạnh đó, FSS cũng thiết lập một hệ thống cảnh báo sớm cho các tổ chức riêng lẻ dưới sự giám sát của mình. Bên cạnh các chỉ số mang tính định tính, BOK đã triển khai một loạt các mô hình định lượng dựa trên dữ liệu thị trường tài chính như CoVaR và SRISK, là những công cụ hữu ích để bám sát thông tin về các tổ chức tài chính lớn nhất trên thị trường. Ngoài ra, mỗi 6 tháng, BOK tiến hành gửi một bản khảo sát rủi ro hệ thống đến một trăm giám đốc điều hành và nhân viên cấp cao của các tổ chức tài chính trong nước, hiệp hội tài chính, viện nghiên cứu và các nhà quản lý quỹ tiền tệ nước ngoài để tìm kiếm các thông tin định tính bổ sung cho phân tích định lượng.

- *Bộ mô hình để hỗ trợ kiểm tra rủi ro hệ thống trên diện rộng*

Bộ mô hình này bao gồm: Mô hình đánh giá rủi ro hệ thống phục vụ việc soạn thảo chính sách an toàn vĩ mô (2012); Mô hình Kiểm tra sức chịu đựng các Tổ chức Tài chính Phi ngân hàng (2019) và Mô hình kiểm tra sức chịu đựng mở rộng (2019). FSS đã phát triển bài kiểm tra sức chịu đựng để đánh giá khả năng phục hồi và tính ổn định của hệ thống tài chính (STARS) vào năm 2017, để hỗ trợ các nỗ lực giám sát an toàn vĩ mô của mình. STARS bao gồm một bộ mô hình ghi lại hiệu ứng lây lan và phản hồi vĩ mô được phát triển với BOK.

3.2. Kinh nghiệm giám sát rủi ro hệ thống của Nhật Bản

3.2.1. Tổ chức giám sát rủi ro hệ thống ở Nhật Bản

Ở Nhật bản, hai cơ quan chính liên quan đến giám sát rủi ro hệ thống là Ngân hàng trung ương Nhật Bản (BOJ) và cơ quan quản lý và giám sát tích hợp các tổ chức tài chính (JFSA). Ngoài ra, còn có Tập đoàn Bảo hiểm Tiền gửi Nhật Bản (DICJ), Bộ Tài chính (MOF), văn phòng chính sách an toàn vĩ mô, Hội đồng hợp tác về ổn định tài chính tham gia vào hoạt động giám sát hệ thống và hoạch định chính sách vĩ mô. Trong đó, BOJ giữ nhiệm vụ duy trì sự ổn

định trong hệ thống tài chính (nhiệm vụ này được quy định trong Đạo luật Ngân hàng Nhật Bản). Bên cạnh BOJ, JFSA là cơ quan quản lý và giám sát tích hợp cho tất cả các tổ chức tài chính ở Nhật Bản. Nhiệm vụ của cơ quan này là đảm bảo sự ổn định tài chính, bảo vệ người gửi tiền, nhà đầu tư và những bên liên quan. Văn phòng chính sách an toàn vĩ mô được thành lập bởi JFSA, chủ yếu tập trung thực hiện giám sát an toàn vĩ mô và rủi ro hệ thống, đồng thời giám sát các ngân hàng có tầm quan trọng hệ thống toàn cầu của Nhật Bản (G-SIB). Hội đồng Hợp tác về Ổn định Tài chính (CCFS) được BOJ và JFSA phối hợp thành lập. CCFS bao gồm các quan chức cấp cao của JFSA và BOJ (Phó Thống đốc BOJ). Hội đồng này họp trung bình sáu tháng một lần để cung cấp cơ chế trao đổi quan điểm định kỳ giữa BOJ và JFSA về phân tích và đánh giá rủi ro trong hệ thống tài chính.

3.2.2. Các biện pháp thực hiện giám sát rủi ro hệ thống của Nhật Bản

- *Giám sát thị trường*

Việc giám sát thị trường được thực hiện đồng thời bởi ba cơ quan, bao gồm JFSA, BOJ và FSAP, chức năng cụ thể như sau: (1) JFSA tiến hành giám sát các điều kiện thị trường hàng ngày; giám sát rủi ro và lỗ hổng bảo mật hàng tháng tại các tổ chức tài chính (đặc biệt là G-SIB); và phân tích hàng quý về rủi ro hệ thống tài chính và triển vọng kinh tế vĩ mô ở Nhật Bản và các quốc gia lớn khác có tiềm năng lan tỏa đối với Nhật Bản; (2) BOJ phát hành Báo cáo ổn định tài chính (Financial stability report - FSR) 6 tháng một lần với mục tiêu đánh giá sự ổn định của hệ thống tài chính của Nhật Bản; (3) FSAP xây dựng khung phân tích của các cơ quan có thẩm quyền trong việc đánh giá rủi ro đối với sự ổn định tài chính, từ đó đưa ra một số khuyến nghị để cải thiện.

- *Giám sát các tổ chức có tầm quan trọng hệ thống.*

Xác định tổ chức có tầm quan trọng hệ thống: việc xác định D-SIB dựa trên 5 nhóm tiêu chí bao gồm: quy mô, mức độ liên kết, khả năng thay thế, mức độ phức tạp và các yếu tố quốc gia cụ thể. Tuy nhiên, việc xác định D-SIBs của Nhật Bản còn được kết hợp với đánh giá toàn diện về tầm quan trọng hệ thống, bao gồm các hoạt động cụ thể của ngân hàng trong thị trường vốn trong nước, cấu trúc danh mục đầu tư của ngân hàng và các đánh giá định tính. Tính tới 31/12/2021, Nhật Bản có 4 ngân hàng nằm trong danh sách D-SIB.

Giám sát các tổ chức có tầm quan trọng hệ thống. Nhật Bản yêu cầu về tỷ lệ an toàn vốn tối thiểu áp dụng cho các D-SIBs sẽ không cố định mà được đưa ra trong cuộc họp định kỳ giữa BOJ, FSA và FSB kết hợp giữa phương pháp chỉ số và phương pháp định tính. FSA yêu cầu các D-SIB thiết lập một khuôn khổ quản trị và quản lý rủi ro mạnh mẽ thông qua những cuộc đối thoại hai chiều đầy đủ giữa ban lãnh đạo ngân hàng và cơ quan quản lý.

- *Cảnh báo sớm rủi ro hệ thống*

BOJ đã phát triển một hệ thống cảnh báo sớm để thường xuyên đánh giá sự ổn định của hệ thống tài chính bằng cách sử dụng Bộ chỉ số hoạt động tài chính (FAIX), là các chỉ số được sử dụng để đánh giá sự mất cân bằng tài chính trong các hoạt động tài chính khác nhau, bao gồm: chỉ số chu kỳ tài chính; các chỉ số rủi ro hệ thống, bao gồm giá trị rủi ro có điều kiện (CoVaR) và chỉ số lành mạnh tài chính cho các ngân hàng và các tổ chức tài chính khác.

- *Các bài kiểm tra sức chịu đựng*

Các bài kiểm tra sức chịu đựng là một trong những công cụ chính được cả hai cơ quan chức năng BOJ và JFSA sử dụng cho mục đích đánh giá rủi ro hệ thống của mình.

Đối với G-SIB: JFSA đã cung cấp cho ba G-SIB của Nhật Bản một số kịch bản để kiểm tra sức chịu đựng về vị thế vốn của họ đối với rủi ro tín dụng và rủi ro thị trường. Bài kiểm tra sức chịu đựng được thực hiện trên một tập hợp các kịch bản chung, phản ánh những rủi ro chung mà các G-SIB này phải đối mặt.

Đối với D-SIB: Bài kiểm tra sức chịu đựng trong lĩnh vực ngân hàng được áp dụng với 20 ngân hàng lớn (D-SIB), chiếm 90% tài sản của hệ thống ngân hàng. Bài kiểm tra này của BOJ dựa trên các dự báo về bảng cân đối kế toán dự tính, lợi nhuận dự tính và nguồn vốn dự tính trong ba năm tiếp theo của các ngân hàng. Nhóm FSAP cũng tiến hành mô phỏng bằng cách tích hợp các kết quả kiểm tra sức chịu đựng thanh khoản vào kiểm tra sức chịu đựng về khả năng thanh toán.

Đối với hệ thống ngân hàng nói chung: BOJ cũng thực hiện các bài kiểm tra sức chịu đựng từ trên xuống từ năm 2007 để kiểm tra mức độ an toàn vốn của các ngân hàng. BOJ sử dụng mô hình kinh tế vĩ mô để đánh giá mối liên hệ giữa rủi ro hệ thống tài chính và nền kinh tế thực. Rủi ro thanh khoản được phân tích trong FSR, đặc biệt tập trung vào rủi ro thanh khoản ngoại hối..

3.3. Kinh nghiệm giám sát rủi ro hệ thống của Đức

3.3.1. Tổ chức giám sát rủi ro hệ thống

Ở Đức, bốn cơ quan chính có trách nhiệm liên quan đến giám sát rủi ro hệ thống, bao gồm: Ủy ban ổn định tài chính, Bộ tài chính liên bang, Cơ quan giám sát tài chính liên bang, Ngân hàng trung ương Đức

- Ủy ban ổn định tài chính (FSC) có nhiệm vụ xác định, giám sát và đánh giá rủi ro đối với sự ổn định tài chính và thực hiện các chính sách để đạt được mục tiêu bằng cách ngăn ngừa và giảm thiểu những rủi ro đó. Đây là cơ quan giám sát cấp cao, được thành lập năm 2012 do Bộ trưởng Bộ ngoại giao làm chủ tịch. Ngoài ra, FSC có ba thành viên bổ phiếu từ Bộ tài chính liên bang BMF, ba thành viên bổ phiếu từ Deutsche Bundesbank, ba thành viên bổ phiếu và một quan sát viên từ BaFin. Mục đích chính của Ủy ban là “tăng cường hợp tác trong lĩnh vực ổn định tài chính, giảm thiểu rủi ro hệ thống” thông qua việc thảo luận thường xuyên, đưa ra các cảnh báo và khuyến nghị chính thức.

- Bộ Tài chính Liên bang (BMF) chịu trách nhiệm về các chính sách liên quan đến thị trường tài chính, tương tác với các cơ quan quốc tế bao gồm Ban ổn định tài chính và điều hành Ban thư ký FSC.

- Cơ quan Giám sát Tài chính Liên bang (BaFin): là cơ quan có thẩm quyền trong việc đưa ra những chỉ thị về yêu cầu vốn và tiêu chuẩn cho vay bất động sản. Nhiệm vụ bảo đảm an toàn hệ thống của BaFin cũng được quy định cụ thể trong Đạo luật ngân hàng để chống lại sự phát triển quá mức của khu vực tài chính có thể làm ảnh hưởng đến việc cung cấp các dịch vụ tài chính, làm gián đoạn hoạt động kinh tế vĩ mô, rủi ro hệ thống.

- *Deutsche Bundesbank*, ngân hàng trung ương của Đức, có trách nhiệm pháp lý trong việc duy trì sự ổn định tài chính, đảm bảo an toàn vĩ mô và giám sát rủi ro hệ thống theo Đạo luật ổn định tài chính FinStabG.

3.3.2. Các biện pháp thực hiện để giám sát rủi ro hệ thống

- *Giám sát rủi ro các tổ chức tài chính:*

Việc giám sát các tổ chức tài chính ở Đức được thực hiện một cách thận trọng với sự tham gia của Bundesbank và BaFin thông qua phương pháp thanh tra tại chỗ trên tất cả các lĩnh vực kinh doanh của ngân hàng dưới các điều kiện kinh tế vĩ mô khác nhau. Hai cơ quan này sẽ lập kế hoạch thanh tra để xác minh một cách đầy đủ nhất rủi ro của các tổ chức tài chính.

- *Bài kiểm tra sức chịu đựng:*

Ở Đức, các bài kiểm tra sức chịu đựng được thực hiện ở cả 3 lĩnh vực: ngân hàng – chứng khoán – bảo hiểm. Đối với lĩnh vực ngân hàng, bài kiểm tra sức chịu đựng kinh tế vĩ mô từ trên xuống của Bundesbank đã được thực hiện đối với 24 ngân hàng lớn nhất của Đức. Song song với các bài kiểm tra từ trên xuống, Bundesbank và BaFin đồng thời thực hiện bài kiểm tra sức chịu đựng từ dưới lên nhằm xem xét lợi nhuận của các ngân hàng trong môi trường lãi suất thấp. Dữ liệu sử dụng được thu thập từ thị trường chứng khoán và các dữ liệu về hoạt động kinh doanh xuyên biên giới.

- *Giám sát các tổ chức có tầm quan trọng hệ thống ở Đức*

Xác định các tổ chức có tầm quan trọng hệ thống

Đức tuân thủ hướng dẫn của Ủy ban ổn định tài chính Châu Âu (FSB – Financial Stability Board – do khối G20 lập ra) và hướng dẫn của Ủy ban giám sát ngân hàng Basel (BCBS) để xác định các ngân hàng có tầm quan trọng hệ thống theo phương pháp chỉ số tài chính. Các chỉ số được lựa chọn bao gồm: các hoạt động xuyên biên giới, quy mô, mức độ liên kết, khả năng có thể thay thế và mức độ phức tạp trong hoạt động của ngân hàng.

Yêu cầu đối với các tổ chức tài chính có tầm quan trọng về mặt hệ thống ở Đức: Tính đến năm 2022, Đức có 1 G-SIB là Deutsche Bank và 14 tổ chức được chỉ định là DSIB. Các tổ chức này được yêu cầu phải có tầm đệm vốn cao hơn. Deutsche Bank có bộ đệm bắt buộc 1,5% RWA, D-SIBs nằm trong khoảng 0,25 phần trăm đến 2 phần trăm RWA. Ngoài ra Đức còn ban hành 1 thỏa thuận nhằm bảo vệ các tổ chức lớn.

4. NGUY CƠ RỦI RO HỆ THỐNG TẠI CÁC NGÂN HÀNG THƯƠNG MẠI VIỆT NAM

Có thể thấy rằng trong giai đoạn 2009 – 2021, hoạt động các NHTM Việt Nam có nhiều biến động. Cùng với việc biến động về hoạt động thì trong giai đoạn này các NHTM Việt Nam cũng đối mặt với nhiều nguy cơ tiềm ẩn rủi ro hệ thống. Trong phần này, các tác giả sẽ phân tích các vấn đề rủi ro liên quan đến hệ thống thông qua phân tích các chỉ tiêu định tính thông qua phân tích tỷ lệ nợ xấu, đòn bẩy tài chính và khả năng thanh khoản của các NHTM.

Thứ nhất tỷ lệ nợ xấu có sự biến động lớn

Sau giai đoạn bùng nổ tín dụng 2008 – 2011, hệ thống NHTM chứng kiến tỷ lệ nợ xấu rất cao do hậu quả của chất lượng tín dụng giảm sút. Biểu đồ 1 cho thấy hệ số này tăng đến 4.02% vào năm 2012. Tuy nhiên, theo nhận định của các tổ chức quốc tế, hệ số này chưa thực sự phản ánh được thực tế chất lượng tín dụng của các NHTM khi đó. Thậm chí Moody còn cho rằng tỷ lệ này lên đến 15% năm 2012 và tốc độ tăng nợ xấu lên đến khoảng 50%/năm trong giai đoạn 2010-2012 (IMF). Đứng trước thực trạng đó, NHNN đã khẩn trương triển khai nghị quyết 42 về “Xử lý nợ xấu hệ thống các TCTD” đồng thời cơ cấu lại hệ thống các TCTD. Các biện pháp kịp thời này đã phát huy tác dụng tốt khi tỷ lệ nợ xấu giảm một cách rõ rệt. Tuy nhiên, từ năm 2020, tỷ lệ nợ xấu toàn hệ thống tăng nhẹ do sự bùng phát của đại dịch Covid-19. Tình hình thậm chí còn đáng báo động hơn nữa khi nhìn vào tỷ lệ nợ xấu gộp (bao gồm nợ xấu nội bảng, nợ xấu bán cho VAMC chưa được xử lý và nợ xấu tiềm ẩn từ các khoản cơ cấu lại). Tỷ lệ này rơi vào khoảng 13% năm 2015, giảm dần đến 2019 và tăng lên 5.1% và 7.3% trong 2 năm cao điểm của dịch Covid. Đây là chỉ báo cho NHNN và hệ thống NHTM cần có những biện pháp can thiệp thích hợp.

Biểu đồ 1: Tỷ lệ nợ xấu của các NHTM Việt Nam giai đoạn 2009 – 2021

Đơn vị: %

Nguồn: NHNN & Tổng hợp của tác giả

Tỷ lệ nợ xấu tăng cao dẫn đến hậu quả chi phí xử lý rủi ro tín dụng cũng gia tăng mạnh mẽ. Điều này dẫn đến hậu quả là khả năng sinh lời, hiệu quả hoạt động kinh doanh của các NHTM giảm sút mạnh.

Thứ hai, mức độ đòn bẩy tài chính³¹ lớn dẫn đến hệ thống dễ bị tổn thương.

³¹ Đòn bẩy tài chính = Tổng tài sản/Vốn chủ sở hữu

Biểu đồ 2: Tỷ lệ đòn bẩy tài chính của các NHTM Việt Nam giai đoạn 2009 – 2021

Đơn vị: %

Nguồn: Cơ sở dữ liệu IMF và tính toán của tác giả

Qua biểu đồ 2, có thể thấy rằng đòn bẩy tài chính của các NHTM Việt Nam, trừ suy giảm năm 2013 – 2014 do sự suy giảm tổng tài sản, thì đều ở ngưỡng cao, xung quanh 13. Tỷ lệ đòn bẩy tài chính ở mức cao cho thấy tính dễ tổn thương của hệ thống tài chính Việt Nam. Điều này dẫn đến rủi ro hệ thống được hình thành và tích lũy mà không quan sát được.

Thứ ba, xuất hiện tình trạng căng thẳng thanh khoản trong hệ thống NHTM tại một số giai đoạn

Cùng với chất lượng tài sản suy giảm, trong giai đoạn 2008-2011, hệ thống NHTM Việt Nam còn trải qua tình trạng căng thẳng về thanh khoản diễn ra thường xuyên. Sự căng thẳng thể hiện rõ ở sự sụt giảm tỷ lệ tài sản có tính thanh khoản cao trong tổng tài sản của các NHTM, từ gần 30% các năm 2009 – 2010 giảm còn 13,30% năm 2011 và duy trì ở ngưỡng trung bình 12% từ năm 2011 đến nay.

Biểu đồ 3: Tỷ lệ tài sản thanh khoản trong tổng tài sản tại các NHTM Việt Nam giai đoạn 2009 – 2021

Đơn vị: %

Nguồn: Cơ sở dữ liệu IMF

Một dấu hiệu nữa cho thấy tình trạng căng thẳng thanh khoản trong hệ thống ngân hàng là lãi suất liên ngân hàng có xu hướng tăng mạnh. Biểu đồ 4 cho thấy diễn biến lãi suất liên ngân hàng các kỳ hạn qua đêm, 1 tháng và 3 tháng. Có thể thấy rằng ba mức lãi suất này có xu hướng biến động cùng chiều với nhau và trong giai đoạn 2011 – 2012, cả 3 mức lãi suất liên ngân hàng đều tăng mạnh. Có những thời điểm lãi suất liên ngân hàng qua đêm đạt gần 16%.

Biểu đồ 4: Diễn biến lãi suất liên ngân hàng giai đoạn 2009 – 2021

Đơn vị: %

Nguồn: Cơ sở dữ liệu Fiin Group và Bloomberg

Nguyên nhân dẫn đến tình trạng căng thẳng thanh khoản này trước hết do tốc độ tăng trưởng tín dụng cao hơn so với huy động trong một thời gian dài từ trước đó dẫn tới tình trạng mất cân đối nghiêm trọng giữa nguồn vốn và sử dụng nguồn. Biểu đồ 5 cho thấy sự biến động tỷ lệ LDR của toàn hệ thống có sự gia tăng mạnh trong những năm 2009 – 2011, từ 98% năm 2008 đến hơn 110% năm 2011, nếu cộng thêm cả khoản đầu tư trái phiếu doanh nghiệp và ủy thác đầu tư thì tỷ lệ này lên đến 119,9%. Trong khi đó, trên thế giới tỷ lệ này chỉ khoảng 30 - 70% và các nước châu Á khác trong khu vực cũng chỉ nằm dưới 80%. Tỷ lệ này tăng cao cho thấy mức độ rủi ro thanh khoản của hệ thống có xu hướng tăng lên. Đây là hậu quả của việc theo đuổi tăng trưởng tín dụng cao trong giai đoạn 2007-2009.

Biểu đồ 5: Tỷ lệ dư nợ trên tiền gửi LDR của các NHTM Việt Nam giai đoạn 2005 – 2021

Nguồn: cơ sở dữ liệu IMF

Một nguyên nhân nữa của tình trạng căng thẳng thanh khoản của hệ thống ngân hàng là sự mất cân đối về kỳ hạn giữa huy động vốn và cho vay của hệ thống ngân hàng. Sự mất cân đối giữa kỳ hạn huy động vốn và cho vay đã và đang trở nên nghiêm trọng trong hệ thống ngân hàng khi các khoản cho vay dài hạn chiếm tỷ trọng lớn hơn và có quy mô lớn hơn nhiều so với các khoản tiền gửi có cùng kỳ hạn. Bên cạnh đó, nguy cơ về rủi ro thanh khoản của NHTM giai đoạn này tăng lên do nợ xấu tăng cao mà khả năng phát mại tài sản thấp, ảnh hưởng tới việc chuyển hóa các khoản nợ xấu thành tiền của ngân hàng.

5. BÀI HỌC VÀ KIẾN NGHỊ VỀ GIÁM SÁT RỦI RO HỆ THỐNG TẠI CÁC NGÂN HÀNG THƯƠNG MẠI VIỆT NAM

Thứ nhất, cần có sự phối hợp giữa các bộ ngành chức năng trong việc giám sát rủi ro hệ thống. Trong ngắn hạn, chính phủ cần ban hành một văn bản thống nhất liên quan đến trách nhiệm giám sát RRHT toàn bộ khu vực tài chính.

Thứ hai, về thực hiện cảnh báo sớm rủi ro hệ thống, Ngân hàng nhà nước với nhiệm vụ trọng tâm giám sát hệ thống tài chính phải đảm đương nhiệm vụ trong việc cảnh báo sớm và phòng ngừa rủi ro cho các tổ chức tín dụng, chi nhánh ngân hàng nước ngoài, đặc biệt là tình hình tài chính tương lai, qua đó phát hiện những yếu tố dẫn đến rủi ro gây mất an toàn, xử lý kịp thời những vấn đề nghiêm trọng xảy ra.

Thứ ba, tăng cường hiệu lực giám sát rủi ro hệ thống trên cơ sở cập nhật rủi ro và xây dựng và áp dụng các chỉ tiêu giám sát và ngưỡng cảnh báo an toàn vĩ mô, các mô hình định lượng và các quy chuẩn, chỉ tiêu giám sát các tập đoàn tài chính; giám sát an toàn thị trường tài chính vĩ mô và vi mô, hướng tới sự ổn định của toàn bộ thị trường tài chính và bảo đảm duy trì sự ổn định của từng định chế tài chính, bảo vệ được người tiêu dùng (nhà đầu tư, chuyên và không chuyên) trên thị trường tài chính.

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TÌNH TRẠNG HẠN CHẾ TÀI CHÍNH VÀ HÀNH VI TRÁNH THUẾ CỦA CÁC DOANH NGHIỆP NIÊM YẾT TẠI VIỆT NAM

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Tóm tắt

Nghiên cứu tìm hiểu mối quan hệ giữa tình trạng hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế của doanh nghiệp. Với mẫu dữ liệu gồm các doanh nghiệp phi tài chính niêm yết tại Việt Nam trong giai đoạn 2010 – 2021, nghiên cứu cho thấy tình trạng hạn chế tài chính có mối quan hệ nghịch biến với hành vi tránh thuế. Kết quả này đi ngược với quan điểm thông thường cho rằng các doanh nghiệp bị hạn chế tài chính có động cơ tránh thuế để có nguồn tiền giải quyết khó khăn về tài chính. Tuy nhiên mối quan hệ nghịch biến giữa tình trạng hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế sẽ giảm khi tính bất định trong nền kinh tế tăng. Điều này hàm ý trong môi trường bất định khi mức độ bất cân xứng thông tin tăng, doanh nghiệp bị hạn chế tài chính sẽ có cơ hội thực hiện hành vi tránh thuế.

Từ khóa: hạn chế tài chính, tránh thuế, Việt Nam

FINANCIAL CONSTRAINT AND TAX AVOIDANCE BEHAVIORS OF VIETNAMESE LISTED FIRMS

Abstract

This paper investigates the relationship between financial constraints and tax avoidance behavior. With a sample of Vietnamese listed non-financial firms from 2010 – 2021, our paper shows that financial constraints are negatively correlated with tax avoidance. This result is contrary to the conventional view that financially constrained firms have an incentive to engage in tax avoidance in order to reserve funds to deal with financial difficulties. However, the negative relationship between financial constraints and tax avoidance decreases as uncertainty in the economy increases. This implies that in an uncertain world where information asymmetry augments, financially constrained firms have an opportunity to practice tax avoidance.

Keywords: financial constraint, tax avoidance, Vietnam

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Nguồn vốn có vai trò quan trọng cho sự ra đời, sự tồn tại và phát triển của doanh nghiệp (DN) do nguồn vốn là điều kiện tiên đề cho DN tiến hành hoạt động sản xuất kinh doanh (Du và Girma, 2012). Nguồn vốn thường được chia thành nguồn vốn bên ngoài và bên trong DN (Gertner và cộng sự, 1994). Doanh nghiệp bị hạn chế tài chính khi DN không thể tiếp cận được nguồn vốn bên ngoài. Nguyên nhân của tình trạng hạn chế tài chính phát sinh chủ yếu do sự

bất cân xứng thông tin giữa các nhà đầu tư và DN (Tirole, 2010). Bên cung cấp vốn khó quan sát được quá trình hoạt động của DN trong quá trình việc lựa chọn DN (Berger và cộng sự, 1995). Tình trạng hạn chế tài chính có khả năng ảnh hưởng đến hành vi của DN. DN phải cắt giảm tối đa các chi phí như chi phí nhân công, chi phí cho công nghệ, khoản tiền chi trả cho cổ tức để có thêm nguồn tài chính (Campello và cộng sự, 2010). Mặt khác, DN sẽ có thể tập trung hơn vào việc dự trữ tiền mặt như một khoản dự phòng trường hợp có thể gặp cú sốc trong nguồn cung tín dụng khi bị hạn chế tài chính (Almeida và cộng sự, 2004). Hơn nữa DN có mức độ hạn chế tài chính cao còn thể bỏ lỡ một số cơ hội đầu tư do gặp khó khăn trong việc huy động tài chính bên ngoài (Campello và cộng sự, 2010). Khi DN bị giới hạn về khả năng sử dụng nguồn vốn bên ngoài, nhằm tiếp tục duy trì hoạt động sản xuất kinh doanh của mình thì DN sẽ phải chuyển sang sử dụng nguồn vốn nội bộ.

Tránh thuế là hành vi DN sử dụng các hợp đồng hoặc giao dịch có tính đặc thù để tận dụng những khe hở trong luật thuế (Lisowsky, 2010; Wilson, 2009) hoặc sự khác biệt về luật thuế giữa các khu vực (Atwood và cộng sự, 2012) nhằm giảm thiểu số thuế DN phải nộp. Vì thuế thu nhập DN là một khoản mục chi phí chính của DN, nên ban giám đốc có động cơ để phát triển các chiến lược với mục đích giảm thuế và đáp ứng nhu cầu về vốn của DN (Desai và Dharmapala, 2006; Rego, 2003; Slemrod, 2001). Tuy nhiên, hoạt động tránh thuế có thể tốn kém chi phí ở một số khía cạnh. Bên cạnh các chi phí trực tiếp của việc tham gia vào hành vi tránh thuế, các nhà quản lý thường phải đảm bảo rằng các hành động này phải được che giấu kỹ càng, không bị cơ quan thuế phát hiện (Desai và Dharmapala, 2009). DN sẽ phải chi trả các khoản tiền phạt cho hành động mình theo các quy định của thuế. Không những thế, DN sẽ bị tổn hại đến danh tiếng của mình khi hành động tránh thuế được đưa ra ánh sáng (Gordon, 1989).

DN bị hạn chế tài chính có động cơ sử dụng biện pháp tránh thuế để giải quyết khó khăn về mặt tài chính (Albring và cộng sự, 2011; Dyreng và Markle, 2015; Shen và cộng sự, 2021). Tuy nhiên đối với DN có mức độ hạn chế tài chính cao, DN phải hoạt động thận trọng tránh các vấn đề tổn hại đến danh tiếng để những người bên ngoài DN như nhà đầu tư hay người cung cấp vốn vay có thể tin tưởng và cung cấp nguồn tài chính cho DN. Mặt khác, tránh thuế là một hành vi mặc dù có thể mang đến một số lợi ích cho DN nhưng kèm theo đó cũng có những rủi ro nhất định (Chen và cộng sự, 2012). Lợi ích có thể thu được là khoản tiết kiệm thuế mà DN trả cho chính phủ, trong khi chi phí của hành động tránh thuế mạnh tay là khả năng các DN bị cơ quan thuế phạt, và sự sụt giảm về giá cổ phiếu của các DN. Giá cổ phiếu sẽ giảm vì các cổ đông khác cho rằng hoạt động mạnh tay về thuế do các nhà quản lý thực hiện để chiết khấu tiền thuế có thể khiến các cổ đông thất vọng (Desai và Dharmapala, 2006). Trong khi đó, chi phí mà tránh thuế mang lại cho các DN bị hạn chế tài chính có xu hướng cao hơn so với lợi ích mà hoạt động này đem đến (Shen và cộng sự, 2021).

Việt Nam là một quốc gia đang phát triển trong giai đoạn hội nhập kinh tế. Trong quá trình hội nhập, nền kinh tế Việt Nam đã trải khá nhiều thử thách, đặc biệt nhất là ảnh hưởng của cuộc khủng hoảng tài chính 2007-2009. Hậu quả là sự biến động thất thường của lãi suất đã tác động đáng kể đến hoạt động kinh doanh của DN. Hơn nữa, tỷ lệ nợ xấu ngân hàng cũng tăng cao đã khiến cho các DN gặp không ít khó khăn trong việc huy động vốn bên ngoài để tài trợ cho hoạt động kinh doanh của mình. Do vậy DN Việt Nam thường gặp tình trạng hạn chế

tài chính. Hiện tượng tránh thuế ở Việt Nam diễn ra khá phổ biến trong thời gian gần đây (Phạm Thế Anh và cộng sự, 2020). Theo thống kê của Tổng cục Thuế trên trang web mof.gov.vn, tổng số 642.423 DN bị phát hiện đã có hành động trái pháp luật về thuế thu nhập DN trong giai đoạn 2010 – 2018. Động cơ để các DN tham gia vào tránh thuế là giảm thiểu tối đa khoản tiền thuế mà DN coi đó là chi phí. Liệu các DN Việt Nam với mức độ hạn chế tài chính cao có động cơ để thực hiện hành vi tránh thuế? Nghiên cứu được thực hiện nhằm xem xét mối quan hệ giữa tình trạng hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế tại các DN phi tài chính niêm yết tại Việt Nam trong giai đoạn 2010-2021.

Trong thời gian qua, thế giới nói chung và Việt Nam nói riêng đã phải đối mặt với nhiều sự kiện ảnh hưởng đến nền kinh tế - xã hội như khủng hoảng tài chính toàn cầu, phân cực chính trị và xung đột thương mại giữa một số quốc gia và gần đây nhất là đại dịch COVID-19. Các sự kiện này đã làm tăng tính bất định trong nền kinh tế (Bloom, 2014). Ở cả cấp độ vi mô và cấp độ vĩ mô, tính bất định có tác động đáng kể đến các yếu tố trong nền kinh tế như tăng khả năng DN thao túng lợi nhuận (Yung và Root, 2019), tăng gánh nặng thuế của DN (Dang và cộng sự, 2019); giảm đầu tư và tăng quy mô nợ (Liu và Zhang, 2020); cũng như tăng chi phí sử dụng vốn (Drobetz và cộng sự, 2018). Bởi vì vậy, tính bất định cũng là một trong những các yếu tố cần được xem xét thêm để tìm hiểu về ảnh hưởng của chúng đến đa dạng các yếu tố khác cũng như các mối quan hệ trong nền kinh tế. Liệu tính bất định có ảnh hưởng đến mối quan hệ giữa hạn chế tài chính và tránh thuế? Chính vì vậy, bên cạnh việc xem xét ảnh hưởng của tình trạng hạn chế tài chính đến hành vi tránh thuế, nghiên cứu còn tìm hiểu ảnh hưởng tương tác của tính bất định đến mối quan hệ này.

Nghiên cứu bao gồm 5 phần trong đó phần 1 giới thiệu về động cơ và mục tiêu nghiên cứu; chương 2 tóm tắt cơ sở lý thuyết và phát triển giả thuyết nghiên cứu; chương 3 trình bày phương pháp nghiên cứu; chương 4 thảo luận kết quả nghiên cứu và chương 5 kết luận.

2. TỔNG QUAN LÝ THUYẾT VÀ PHÁT TRIỂN GIẢ THUYẾT NGHIÊN CỨU

DN bị hạn chế tài chính khi DN khó tiếp cận nguồn vốn bên ngoài (Denis và Sibilkov, 2010). Khi này DN sẽ cắt giảm các chi phí công nghệ, chi phí nhân công và chi tiêu cho đầu tư. DN bị hạn chế tài chính cũng dự trữ nhiều tiền hơn vì lo ngại các ngân hàng sẽ hạn chế cung cấp vốn cho DN trong tương lai và thanh lý nhiều tài sản hơn để tài trợ cho hoạt động sản xuất kinh doanh (Campello và cộng sự, 2010). Trong bối cảnh này, giải pháp tiết kiệm tiền thông qua hành vi tránh thuế được khá nhiều DN chú ý và quan tâm đến (Edwards và cộng sự, 2016). Tránh thuế là việc lập kế hoạch thuế mà ban điều hành DN lập ra nhằm mục đích tránh khoản thuế mà DN phải nộp theo cách phù hợp với quy định của pháp luật (Desai và Dharmapala, 2006). Thông thường, DN thông qua việc tận dụng các khoản khấu trừ, ưu đãi, miễn giảm thuế, thực hiện các giao dịch “chuyển giá” hay sử dụng các phương pháp kế toán phù hợp để có thể giảm các khoản thuế phải nộp (Frank và cộng sự, 2009).

Các nghiên cứu thực nghiệm tìm hiểu về tác động của tình trạng hạn chế tài chính đến hành vi tránh thuế của DN xuất hiện phổ biến trong thời gian gần đây. Dòng nghiên cứu này có hai quan điểm trái ngược nhau khi xem xét về ảnh hưởng của tình trạng hạn chế tài chính lên hành vi tránh thuế của DN. Một quan điểm cho rằng hạn chế tài chính, nghĩa là xuất hiện sự khó khăn về tài chính trong DN khi khả năng huy động được nguồn vốn từ bên ngoài thấp

(Edwards và cộng sự, 2016). Do đó, các DN sẽ gia tăng hành động tránh thuế để tạo thêm nguồn vốn nội bộ từ tiết kiệm khoản thuế phải nộp (Chen và Lai, 2012; Law và Mills, 2015; Firmansyah và cộng sự, 2019). Tuy nhiên, một số nghiên cứu khác cho rằng hành vi tránh thuế mang tính rủi ro cao do tốn kém nhiều chi phí khi thực hiện và do vậy các DN bị hạn chế tài chính sẽ có xu hướng hoạt động cẩn trọng hơn. Khi đó, DN bị giới hạn tài chính sẽ giảm các hành động tránh thuế (Albring và cộng sự, 2011; Dyreng và Markle, 2015).

Với mẫu gồm các DN niêm yết tại Hoa Kỳ trong giai đoạn 1986 - 2011, Chen và cộng sự (2012) tiến hành nghiên cứu mối quan hệ giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế. Kết quả chỉ ra rằng trong giai đoạn bị giới hạn về tài chính là khi DN nhận thấy rất tốn kém để có được nguồn tài chính từ bên ngoài, DN có nhiều động lực hơn để thực hiện các hành vi tránh thuế. Ngoài ra, bài nghiên cứu còn đưa thêm bằng chứng thực nghiệm về việc hành vi tiết kiệm thuế của các bị giới hạn về tài chính giúp DN giảm thiểu các vấn đề về đầu tư bằng cách tăng các khoản đầu tư vốn trong tương lai, điều này có lợi cho DN. Nhất quán với kết quả này, Law và Mills (2015) chỉ ra rằng các DN bị giới hạn về tài chính sẽ có thuế suất hiệu dụng trong ngắn hạn và dài hạn thấp hơn và sử dụng nhiều thiên đường thuế hơn cho các hoạt động sản xuất kinh doanh của DN. Điều này có nghĩa là DN có mức độ hạn chế tài chính cao có động cơ thực hiện tránh thuế.

Trái ngược với những lập luận ở trên, Farre-Mensa và cộng sự (2016) cho rằng DN có xu hướng giảm khả năng tránh thuế khi DN bị hạn chế tài chính. DN bị hạn chế tài chính có thể gặp khó khăn trong việc tăng đòn bẩy để tận dụng các lá chắn thuế như một hành vi tránh thuế (Farre-Mensa và cộng sự, 2016). Nói cách khác, các DN có khả năng giảm việc tham gia vào hành vi tránh thuế khi bị hạn chế tài chính. Tương tự, Albring và cộng sự (2011) đã kiểm tra xem tình trạng hạn chế tài chính của các DN đa quốc gia Hoa Kỳ có tác động như thế nào đến phản ứng của DN trong thời gian miễn giảm thuế. Kết quả nghiên cứu đã cho thấy rằng các DN ít bị giới hạn về tài chính đã chuyển nguồn tiền về Hoa Kỳ nhiều hơn trong giai đoạn miễn giảm thuế. Điều này có nghĩa tình trạng hạn chế tài chính của DN làm giảm khả năng tham gia vào các hành vi giảm thuế. Nguyên nhân là do DN ít bị ràng buộc về tài chính có gánh nặng thuế hồi hương cao hơn khi các DN này đã tích lũy nhiều tiền mặt ở các chi nhánh nước ngoài (Foley và cộng sự, 2007).

Dyreng và Markle (2015) tiến hành xem xét các tập đa quốc gia ở Hoa Kỳ cũng cho kết quả nghiên cứu tương tự. Bài nghiên cứu cho thấy rằng DN bị hạn chế về tài chính thực hiện việc chuyển đổi thu nhập ít hơn so với các DN trong tình trạng ngược lại. Mặc dù, chuyển đổi thu nhập sẽ làm giảm khoản thuế thu nhập mà DN phải trả. Vì vậy, nếu một DN Hoa Kỳ bị hạn chế về mặt tài chính, khiến chi phí của nguồn tài chính từ bên ngoài cho nhu cầu tiền mặt trong nước là quá đắt, thì việc chuyển đổi thu nhập ra nước ngoài có thể không hiệu quả. Nói chung là, đối với các DN trong tình trạng hạn chế tài chính, việc thực hiện hành vi nhằm giảm số tiền thuế mà DN phải trả không mang lại nhiều lợi ích thì các DN có khuynh hướng giảm thực hiện các hành động tránh thuế.

Tại Việt Nam, các nhà đầu tư vẫn chịu tác động rất lớn của “tâm lý bầy đàn”, do các nhà đầu tư có thể rất dễ bị kích động theo xu hướng chung của thị trường khi có những thông tin không tốt cho DN (Trịnh Thị Phan Lan, 2012). Bởi vậy khi các DN tại Việt Nam bị phát hiện

có hành vi tránh thuế thì sẽ khiến các nhà đầu tư phản ứng tiêu cực đối với việc cung cấp vốn cho DN. Đặc biệt, các DN ở trong tình trạng giới hạn tài chính sẽ càng khó khăn hơn trong việc tìm kiếm nguồn tài trợ để phục vụ cho hoạt động kinh doanh của mình diễn ra bình thường. Lo ngại vấn đề đó xảy ra, các DN tại Việt Nam sẽ có khuynh hướng hoạt động cẩn trọng hơn để lấy sự tin tưởng của các nhà cung cấp vốn và giảm các hành vi tránh thuế thu nhập. Từ đó tác giả đưa ra giả thuyết sau:

Giả thuyết H1: Tình trạng hạn chế tài chính làm giảm hành vi tránh thuế của DN.

Tính bất định được định nghĩa là sự không chắc chắn, không rõ ràng trong tâm trí của người tiêu dùng, nhà điều hành và các nhà hoạch định chính sách về các sự kiện trong tương lai có thể sẽ xảy ra hoặc không (Ahir và cộng sự, 2018). Đây cũng là một khái niệm tương đồng rộng vì tính bất định liên quan đến một số hiện tượng vĩ mô như tăng trưởng GDP và các hiện tượng vi mô như tốc độ tăng trưởng của các DN, cũng như các sự kiện khác như bầu cử, chiến tranh và biến đổi khí hậu. Một cách hiểu khác, tính bất định còn được xem là những thay đổi không dễ dàng dự đoán trước được mà có tác động tới nền kinh tế và từ đó có khả năng gây ra sự thay đổi trong hành vi của người tiêu dùng và DN cũng như việc hoạch định chính sách của nhà nước.

Tính bất định có khả năng tác động lên một số hành vi của DN như là giảm đầu tư vốn (Gulen và Ion, 2016) hoặc hoạt động mua bán và sáp nhập (Bonaime và cộng sự, 2018). Pastor và Veronesi (2017) chỉ ra rằng trong tình trạng nền kinh tế có tính bất định cao thì các nhà đầu tư vào cổ phiếu sẽ yêu cầu một khoản gọi là phần bù rủi ro đối với sự không chắc chắn trong thị trường, dẫn đến sự sụt giảm trong giá cổ phiếu của DN. Điều này có nghĩa chi phí sử dụng vốn của doanh nghiệp sẽ gia tăng. Bordo và cộng sự. (2016) lập luận rằng tính bất định trong thị trường cản trở sự tăng trưởng tín dụng của ngân hàng, có nghĩa DN gặp nhiều khó khăn hơn trong khả năng tiếp cận thị trường nợ. Như vậy tính bất định ảnh hưởng đến mức độ giới hạn về tài chính trong DN.

Mặt khác, Law và Mills (2015) cho rằng khi đưa ra quyết định tránh thuế, các nhà điều hành của DN trong tình trạng giới hạn về tài chính có lẽ đã đánh giá chi phí và lợi ích của việc tiết kiệm thuế. Trong khi đưa ra quyết định về việc tiến hành tránh thuế, các DN cũng cần cân nhắc giữa các lợi ích cũng như các chi phí liên quan (Desai và Dharmapala, 2009). Do tránh thuế, DN có nhiều khả năng bị điều tra và chịu sự trừng phạt của cơ quan thuế, dẫn đến chi phí tài chính cao và sự không hài lòng của các nhà đầu tư. Tuy nhiên, ảnh hưởng của các chi phí này có khả năng giảm khi tính bất định tăng cao. Nguyên nhân là do trong điều kiện tính bất định cao, mức độ bất cân xứng thông tin giữa bên trong và bên ngoài DN có xu hướng tăng (Jensen và Mackling, 1976). Như vậy, các DN bị hạn chế tài chính có khả năng ít chịu chi phí tài chính khi tham gia vào hành vi tránh thuế trong điều kiện tính bất định cao. Từ những lý do trên, khi nền kinh tế bất ổn, rủi ro khi thực hiện hành động tránh thuế của các DN bị hạn chế tài chính có khả năng thấp hơn. Do đó, có khả năng mức độ các DN bị giới hạn tài chính không sử dụng hành động tránh thuế để hỗ trợ cho quá trình hoạt động của mình sẽ trở nên thấp hơn khi ở trong tính bất định cao.

Giả thuyết H2: Tính bất định làm giảm mối quan hệ nghịch biến giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế.

3. PHƯƠNG PHÁP NGHIÊN CỨU

3.1. Mô hình nghiên cứu

Để kiểm định mối quan hệ giữa tình trạng hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế, tác giả dựa trên Chen và cộng sự (2012), Richardson và cộng sự (2015) và Edwards và cộng sự (2016) để xây dựng mô hình nghiên cứu như sau:

$$TA_{i,t} = \delta_0 + \delta_1 FC_{i,t} + \sum \delta_k Controls_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3.1)$$

Trong mô hình (3.1), các chỉ số phụ i và t lần lượt là đại diện cho DN i và năm thứ t . Biến TA là biến thể hiện hành động tránh thuế, FC là biến biểu thị cho tình trạng hạn chế tài chính. **Controls** là tập hợp các biến kiểm soát có trong mô hình bao gồm: **ROA** là tỷ suất sinh lời trên tài sản, **AGE** là số năm DN niêm yết trên sàn chứng khoán đến năm quan sát, **SIZE** là biến thể hiện quy mô của DN, **LEV** là tỷ lệ đòn bẩy tài chính, **TANG** là tỷ lệ tài sản hữu hình, **INV** là biến thể hiện mức độ tồn kho, **MTB** là biến thể hiện tỷ lệ giá trị thị trường trên giá trị sổ sách của vốn chủ sở hữu. Ngoài ra, mô hình hồi quy của bài nghiên cứu này còn sử dụng kiểm soát cho hiệu ứng cố định theo ngành và theo năm.

Theo giả thuyết H1, tình trạng hạn chế tài chính của DN càng cao sẽ làm DN đó giảm động cơ thúc đẩy thực hiện việc tránh thuế. Có thể hiểu là, đối với biến giải thích là FC thể hiện hạn chế tài chính của DN càng cao thì càng làm giảm biến TA do làm giảm hành vi tránh thuế của DN. Vì vậy, tác giả kỳ vọng rằng hệ số ước lượng của biến hạn chế tài chính (FC) trong mô hình (3.1) là β_1 sẽ mang dấu âm và có ý nghĩa thống kê.

Để mở rộng hơn, tác giả xem xét ảnh hưởng của tính bất định đến mối quan hệ giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế, tác giả chia mẫu dữ liệu của nghiên cứu thành hai nhóm bao gồm nhóm có tính bất định cao và nhóm có tính bất định thấp. Cơ sở phân chia các quan sát trong mẫu dữ liệu dựa trên giá trị trung vị của thước đo tính bất định. Cụ thể, tác giả quyết định xem xét tính bất định trong nền kinh tế ở Việt Nam thông qua việc sử dụng biến UNC được đo lường bằng chỉ số WUI được xây dựng bởi Ahir và cộng sự (2018). Theo giả thuyết H2, tính bất định sẽ làm giảm ảnh hưởng của giới hạn tài chính đến hành vi tránh thuế. Do đó, tác giả kỳ vọng β_1 của nhóm có tính bất định cao sẽ mang dấu âm và có giá trị tuyệt đối nhỏ hơn β_1 của nhóm có tính bất định thấp.

3.2. Đo lường biến

3.2.1. Hạn chế tài chính

Thước đo biến giới hạn tài chính trong bài nghiên cứu này chính là chỉ số WWscore, được phát triển bởi Whited và Wu (2006). DN có chỉ số WWscore càng lớn thì mức độ hạn chế tài chính càng cao.

$$WWscore = -0.091 \times Cash\ flow_{i,t} - 0.062 \times DIV_{i,t} + 0.021 \times Leverage_{i,t} \\ - 0.044 \times Size_{i,t} + 0.102 \times ISG_{i,t} - 0.035 \times SG_{i,t}$$

Trong đó: Cash flow là tỷ lệ giữa dòng tiền lưu chuyển thuần trong kỳ và tổng tài sản của DN; DIV là một biến giả, nhận giá trị là 1 nếu DN trả cổ tức bằng tiền, ngược lại bằng 0 nếu

không phải; Leverage là tỷ lệ nợ dài hạn trên tổng tài sản; Size được tính bằng logarit tự nhiên của tổng tài sản; SG thể hiện tốc độ tăng trưởng doanh thu của DN. Ngoài ra, Whited và Wu (2006) còn cho thấy rằng đặc điểm tình hình kinh tế chung của các ngành kinh doanh cũng như tác động của chúng đến mức độ giới hạn tài chính của DN bằng cách thêm yếu tố ISG vào trong phương trình trên. ISG thể hiện tốc độ tăng trưởng doanh thu trung bình ngành.

3.2.2. Hành vi tránh thuế

Tác giả sử dụng ba biến đại diện cho hành vi tránh thuế. Phương pháp thứ nhất thể hiện mức độ tránh thuế dựa trên chênh lệch thuế sổ sách (BTG) do trong các DN có hành động trốn thuế thường xuất hiện sự khác biệt giữa thu nhập ghi sổ và thu nhập chịu thuế (Lisowsky, 2010). Điều này thể hiện rằng BTG càng cao DN càng có khả năng cao hành vi tránh thuế và được tính như sau:

$$BTG = \frac{\text{Thu nhập ghi sổ trước thuế} - \text{Thu nhập tính thuế}}{\text{Tổng tài sản}}$$

Trong đó: thu nhập tính thuế sẽ được tính bằng tỷ lệ giữa chi phí thuế thu nhập DN chia cho thuế suất theo quy định.

Biến đại diện thứ hai, tác giả đã sử dụng một thước đo thông qua phần dư của khe hở thuế theo sổ sách (RES_BTG) được phát triển bởi Desai và Dharmapala (2006). RES_BTG càng lớn thể hiện DN tránh thuế càng cao và là phần dư của mô hình hồi quy sau:

$$BTG = \beta_1 \times ToA + \mu + \varepsilon$$

Trong đó, ToA là tổng giá trị kế toán dồn tích được tính như sau:

$$ToA = \frac{\text{Thu nhập ghi sổ sau thuế} - \text{Lưu chuyển tiền thuần từ hoạt động kinh doanh}}{\text{Tổng tài sản đầu năm}}$$

Từ đó suy ra phần dư của mô hình hồi quy là: $RES_BTG = \mu + \varepsilon$

Biến đại diện thứ ba được đo lường dựa trên thuế suất hiệu dụng tiền mặt (CETR), phản ánh ý tưởng rằng các nhà quản lý coi việc lập kế hoạch thuế hiệu quả là khả năng giảm thiểu các khoản thuế phải nộp bằng tiền mặt (Dyreng và cộng sự, 2008).

$$CETR = \frac{\text{Số tiền thuế thực trả}}{\text{Lợi nhuận kế toán trước thuế}}$$

Trong đó, tổng của số tiền thuế thực trả được lấy từ báo cáo lưu chuyển tiền tệ, còn tổng lợi nhuận kế toán trước thuế có trong báo cáo kết quả hoạt động kinh doanh của DN. Giá trị của CETR càng nhỏ tức số tiền thuế thu nhập thực trả trong kỳ của DN ít hơn so với lợi nhuận ghi sổ trước thuế (Dyreng và cộng sự, 2008). Điều này phản ánh khả năng các DN đã tiến hành tránh thuế càng cao. Tuy nhiên, với mục đích nhằm thuận tiện cho việc giải thích kết quả của hành vi tránh thuế, tác giả tiến hành nhân giá trị của biến CETR với -1 và có được biến TA_CETR. Lúc này, giá trị của biến TA_CETR càng cao thể hiện DN càng tránh thuế nhiều, nhất quán với cách giải thích của hai biến còn lại là BTG và RES_BTG.

3.3. Mẫu và dữ liệu

Trong bài nghiên cứu, tác giả sử dụng các dữ liệu được lấy từ các Bảng cân đối kế toán, Báo cáo thu nhập DN, Báo cáo lưu chuyển tiền tệ và Báo cáo thường niên của các DN phi tài chính niêm yết trên hai sàn HNX và HOSE trong giai đoạn 2010-2021. Chỉ số WUI (Ahir và cộng sự, 2018) thể hiện tính bất định trong nền kinh tế được lấy dữ liệu từ trang web World Uncertainty Index được xây dựng bởi Ahir, Nick và Furceri (2018) và được cập nhật dữ liệu kịp thời cuối mỗi hàng quý. Sau khi xử lý dữ liệu thô, tác giả có được dữ liệu gồm 5.457 quan sát đến từ 665 DN từ năm 2010 đến năm 2021.

3.4. Kiểm định tính vững

Với mục đích kiểm định tính vững cho biến giải thích là tránh thuế của DN, tác giả đã sử dụng ba phương pháp đo lường được sử dụng phổ biến và rộng rãi trong các bài nghiên cứu (Desai và Dharmapala, 2006; Dyreng và cộng sự, 2008, 2010; Minnick và Noga, 2010). Thứ nhất là phương pháp thể hiện mức độ tránh thuế dựa trên khe hở thuế theo sổ sách (BTG). Thứ hai là thước đo mức độ tránh thuế DN dựa trên phần dư của khe hở thuế theo sổ sách (Residual BTG hoặc RES_BTG) được phát triển bởi Desai và Dharmapala (2006) dựa trên phương pháp luận của Manzon và Plesko (2002). Cuối cùng là phương pháp thể hiện mức độ tránh thuế dựa trên thuế suất hiệu dụng tiền mặt (CETR).

4. KẾT QUẢ NGHIÊN CỨU VÀ THẢO LUẬN

4.1. Kết quả thống kê mô tả

Bảng 4.1 dưới đây thể hiện kết quả thống kê mô tả của các biến trong mô hình nghiên cứu. Biến BTG đại diện cho hành vi tránh thuế có giá trị trung bình là 0.012 chỉ ra mức trung bình tránh thuế của các DN niêm yết tại Việt Nam. Độ lệch chuẩn 0.034 của biến BTG hàm ý các DN ở Việt Nam có ít sự chênh lệch trong mức độ tránh thuế. Trong đó, giá trị của biến BTG có sự biến động trong khoảng từ -0.045 đến 0.179. Mặt khác, biến thứ hai đại diện hành vi tránh thuế là RES_BTG với giá trị trung bình là 0.0002 và độ lệch chuẩn là 0.034. Khoảng giá trị của biến này dao động từ -0.057 đến 0.167. Tuy có sự chênh lệch nhưng không đáng kể giữa hai biến thể hiện mức độ tránh thuế này, do quan điểm hình thành hai thước đo này khá tương đồng nhau. BTG được định nghĩa là chênh lệch giữa thu nhập ghi sổ và thu nhập chịu thuế chia cho tổng tài sản (Desai và Dharmapala, 2006), còn RES_BTG là giá trị còn lại của mô hình hồi quy BTG và tổng các khoản dồn tích (Chen và cộng sự, 2012).

Hành vi tránh thuế được thể hiện thông qua thuế suất hiệu dụng bằng tiền (CETR) với giá trị trung bình là 0.184, hàm ý rằng tổng số tiền thuế sẽ phải nộp bằng 18.4% thu nhập trước thuế. Mặc dù giá trị trung bình nhỏ hơn so với thuế suất hiệu dụng hiện hành là 20%, nhưng khoảng giá trị của biến này lại nằm từ giá trị 0 đến 82.8%, điều này thể hiện vẫn có sự tồn tại của hành vi tránh thuế trong mẫu nghiên cứu. Tuy nhiên, mức thuế suất 20% không phải là mức thuế suất cố định cho tất cả các DN của Việt Nam trong giai đoạn nghiên cứu là 2010-2021. Đây chỉ là mức thuế suất hiện hành được áp dụng cho hầu hết các DN tại Việt Nam từ ngày 01/01/2016 đến nay và trước đó thì 22% đến 25% là mức thuế suất áp dụng cho phần lớn các DN tại Việt Nam.

Bảng 4.1 Kết quả thống kê mô tả của các biến có trong mô hình nghiên cứu

Biến	Số quan sát	Trung bình	Độ lệch chuẩn	Giá trị nhỏ nhất	Giá trị lớn nhất
Biến phụ thuộc – Tránh thuế					
BTG	5.457	0,012	0,034	-0,045	0,179
RES_BTG	5.457	0,000	0,034	-0,057	0,167
TA_CETR	5.457	-0,184	0,165	-0,828	0,000
Biến độc lập – Hạn chế tài chính					
WWscore	5.457	-1,246	0,078	-1,465	-1,073
Biến tương tác – Tính bất định					
UNC	5.457	0,081	0,073	0,000	0,236
Biến kiểm soát					
ROA	5.457	0,088	0,076	0,000	0,393
AGE	5.457	5,918	4,398	0,000	16,000
TANG	5.457	0,238	0,211	0,001	0,880
INV	5.457	0,207	0,175	0,000	0,721
MTB	5.457	1,088	0,921	0,000	5,176
SIZE	5.457	27,193	1,583	19,198	32,909
LEV	5.457	0,094	0,133	0,000	0,589

Ghi chú: Bảng 4.1 thể hiện kết quả thống kê mô tả của các biến có trong mô hình nghiên cứu. Trong khi đó, biến phụ thuộc là hành vi tránh thuế được thể hiện thông qua TA_CETR, BTG và RES_BTG; WWscore là biến đo lường cho mức độ hạn chế tài chính; UNC là biến tương tác thể hiện tính bất định của Việt Nam trong các năm; ROA là tỷ suất sinh lợi trên tài sản; AGE là số năm DN niêm yết trên sàn chứng khoán đến năm đang quan sát; SIZE là biến thể hiện quy mô của DN, LEV là tỷ lệ đòn bẩy tài chính, TANG là tỷ lệ tài sản hữu hình, INV là biến thể hiện mức độ tồn kho, MTB là biến thể hiện tỷ lệ giá trị thị trường của vốn chủ sở hữu trên giá trị sổ sách của vốn chủ sở hữu.

Đối với biến WWscore giải thích tình trạng hạn chế tài chính của DN, từ kết quả bảng 4.1 thể hiện rằng giá trị trung bình của mức độ hạn chế tài chính của các DN tại Việt Nam là -1.246 và khoảng giá trị biến động từ -1.465 đến -1.073 và độ lệch chuẩn là 0.078. Phân phối của biến WWscore là phân phối lệch phải ngụ ý rằng khả năng cao các DN Việt Nam có xu hướng ở trong tình trạng hạn chế tài chính cao hơn mức trung bình.

Đối với kết quả thống kê mô tả của biến tương tác, UNC thể hiện tính bất định với thước đo là chỉ số WUI có giá trị trung bình là 0.081 và độ lệch chuẩn tương ứng là 0.073 với giá trị dao động từ 0 đến 0.236. Trong đó, với giá trị lớn nhất của biến UNC là 0.236 vào năm 2014. Đây là thời gian diễn ra một số sự kiện nổi bật nhất là sự xung đột với Trung Quốc khi quốc gia này đặt giàn khoan trái phép tại vùng biển của Việt Nam. Sự kiện này đã gây ra nhiều sự bất ổn về chính trị, kinh tế và xã hội. Nhiều cuộc biểu tình phản đối hành động của Trung Quốc đã diễn ra ở Việt Nam dẫn đến bạo động, phá hoại tài sản và gây nên thiệt hại nghiêm trọng, thậm chí còn có người thiệt mạng tại Đồng Nai, Bình Dương. Nhiều nhà máy đã bị buộc phải tạm ngưng sản xuất, cùng với đó là tác động của cuộc khủng hoảng tài chính khu vực châu Á năm 2013 khiến cho một số lượng lớn các DN ngừng hoạt động và giải thể.

Bảng 4.2 thể hiện kết quả kiểm định khả năng tương quan giữa các biến có trong mô hình bằng hệ số tương quan Pearson. Bảng 4.2 cho thấy hệ số Pearson giữa hai biến thể hiện hành vi tránh thuế thông qua BTG và RES_BTG khá cao bằng 1.0 (cụ thể hơn là 0.998). Nguyên nhân của điều này đã được nhắc đến trong phần thống kê mô tả các biến. Do quan điểm hình thành nên thước đo RES_BTG được dựa trên biến BTG, cụ thể hơn RES_BTG là giá trị còn lại của mô hình hồi quy BTG và tổng các khoản dồn tích. Có thể hiểu rằng, hai thước đo hành vi tránh thuế này có mối tương quan tuyến tính mạnh mẽ với nhau. Hệ số tương quan giữa biến WWscore và các biến thể hiện hành động tránh thuế là BTG, RES_BTG và TA_CETR đều có hệ số âm. Như vậy có thể dự đoán rằng giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành động tránh thuế của doanh nghiệp tồn tại mối tương quan nghịch biến.

Bảng 4.2 Ma trận hệ số tương quan Pearson của các biến trong mô hình

Tên biến	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
(1) BTG	1.000										
(2) RES_BTG	1.000	1.000									
(3) TA_CETR	0.214	0.213	1.000								
(4) WWscore	-0.016	-0.016	-0.018	1.000							
(5) ROA	0.407	0.407	0.096	0.011	1.000						
(6) AGE	-0.099	-0.100	0.029	-0.102	-0.087	1.000					
(7) TANG	0.177	0.179	0.029	-0.038	0.063	-0.081	1.000				
(8) INV	-0.161	-0.161	-0.089	0.013	-0.131	-0.022	-0.366	1.000			
(9) MTB	0.134	0.134	0.043	-0.221	0.439	0.158	0.017	-0.053	1.000		
(10) SIZE	-0.045	-0.044	-0.039	-0.768	0.036	0.112	0.020	0.12	0.232	1.000	
(11) LEV	-0.017	-0.017	0.013	-0.300	-0.231	-0.052	0.38	-0.215	-0.021	0.134	1.000

4.2. Kết quả ước lượng và kiểm định

4.2.1. Tác động của hạn chế tài chính đến hành vi tránh thuế của DN

Đầu tiên tác giả sử dụng phương pháp hồi quy OLS có kiểm soát cho ngành và cho năm để ước lượng và kiểm định mô hình (3.1). Sau đó tác giả thực hiện các kiểm định nhằm phát hiện hiện tượng phương sai thay đổi và hiện tượng tự tương quan. Kết quả kiểm định BreuschPagan/Cook-Weisberg có ý nghĩa thống kê nhỏ hơn 5% chỉ ra rằng mô hình này có hiện tượng phương sai thay đổi. Kết quả kiểm định Wooddridge cũng có ý nghĩa thống kê nhỏ hơn 5% cho thấy mô hình có hiện tượng tự tương quan. Để khắc phục, tác giả hiện hồi quy bằng cách sử dụng phương pháp pooled OLS có áp dụng sai số chuẩn vững (Robust Standard Errors).

Bảng 4.3: Kết quả ước lượng mối quan hệ giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế của DN

Biến	(1) BTG	(2) RES_BTG	(3) TA_CETR
WWscore	-0,080***	-0,079***	-0,217***
	(0,010)	(0,010)	(0,049)
ROA	0,180***	0,180***	0,287***
	(0,011)	(0,011)	(0,035)
AGE	-0,000***	-0,000***	-0,002***
	(0,000)	(0,000)	(0,001)
TANG	0,014***	0,015***	0,002
	(0,003)	(0,003)	(0,014)
INV	-0,013***	-0,013***	-0,049***
	(0,002)	(0,002)	(0,017)
SIZE	-0,005***	-0,005***	-0,017***
	(0,001)	(0,001)	(0,003)
LEV	0,001	0,001	0,020
	(0,003)	(0,003)	(0,021)
MTB	-0,001	-0,001	-0,006**
	(0,001)	(0,001)	(0,003)
Hàng số	0,031***	0,019**	-0,036
	(0,009)	(0,009)	(0,049)
Số quan sát	5.457	5.457	5.457
R²	0,274	0,274	0,274
Số DN	665	665	665
Hiệu ứng cố định ngành	Có	Có	Có
Hiệu ứng cố định năm	Có	Có	Có

Ghi chú: Bảng 4.3 thể hiện kết quả ước lượng mối quan hệ giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế của DN. Mức ý nghĩa thống kê 1%, 5%, 10% được thể hiện thông qua các ký hiệu lần lượt là ***, **, *.

Kết quả ước lượng và kiểm định mô hình (3.1) được trình bày trong bảng 4.3. Kết quả cho thấy tình trạng hạn chế tài chính được thể hiện bằng biến WWscore có mối quan hệ nghịch biến với tránh thuế của DN. Cụ thể hơn, ở cột (1) thể hiện hệ số có giá trị nhỏ hơn 0 là -0.080 và có ý nghĩa thống kê ở mức 1% giữa biến WWscore và chênh lệch khoản thuế theo sổ sách (BTG). Kết quả này có nghĩa rằng, các DN càng gặp tình trạng hạn chế tài chính cao sẽ có khuynh hướng giảm thực hiện tránh thuế. Kết quả này cũng tương tự khi thay thế phương pháp đo lường biến phụ thuộc là hành vi tránh thuế lần lượt là phương pháp dựa trên phần dư của khe hở thuế theo sổ sách (RES_BTG) và thuế suất hiệu dụng bằng tiền (TA_CETR). Ở cột (2) và cột (3), hệ số ước lượng của biến WWscore đều có dấu âm với mức ý nghĩa thống kê là 1%. Như vậy, kết quả trên phù hợp với giả thuyết “H1: Tình trạng hạn chế tài chính làm giảm hành vi tránh thuế của DN.”

Mối quan hệ ngược chiều giữa tình trạng hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế trong nghiên cứu này trái ngược lại với kết quả của một số bài nghiên cứu trước đây như Chen và Lai (2012), Law và Mills (2015), Firmansyah và cộng sự (2019). Các nghiên cứu cho thấy bằng chứng thực nghiệm về mối quan hệ đồng biến giữa tình trạng hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế. Để lý giải cho mối quan hệ này, các nghiên cứu này cho rằng các DN có động cơ sử dụng khoản tiền thuế tiết kiệm được thông qua hành vi tránh thuế như là nguồn vốn nội bộ khi bị hạn chế tài chính. Sử dụng mẫu dữ liệu cho nghiên cứu là các DN niêm yết tại Hoa Kỳ, Chen và cộng sự (2012) cho thấy rằng các DN có mức độ giới hạn tài chính cao sẽ giảm thiểu các vấn đề về đầu tư bằng cách tăng các khoản đầu tư vốn trong tương lai thông qua việc thực hiện hành động tránh thuế.

Mối quan hệ nghịch biến giữa tình trạng hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế có thể được giải thích thông qua lý thuyết người đại diện, lý thuyết chi phí – lợi ích và lý thuyết đánh đổi cấu trúc vốn. Dựa trên các nghiên cứu trước đây, kết quả nghiên cứu chỉ ra mối tương quan ngược chiều tương đồng với nghiên cứu của Albring và cộng sự (2011), Dyreng và Markle (2015). Các nhà nghiên cứu đã giải thích cho mối quan hệ ngược chiều này dựa trên các khoản chi phí mà DN sẽ phải chịu khi mà thực hiện hành vi tránh thuế trong khi đang bị hạn chế tài chính. Albring và cộng sự (2011) đã so sánh việc thực hiện hành vi tránh thuế bằng cách tận dụng các kỳ nghỉ thuế giữa các DN có mức độ hạn chế tài chính cao và thấp. Kết quả cho rằng khi DN bị hạn chế tài chính cao hơn thì việc tận dụng kỳ nghỉ thuế để giảm thiểu các khoản thuế phải nộp sẽ chịu chi phí cao hơn so với việc chuyển khoản tiền về lại Hoa Kỳ. Tương đồng với kết quả này khi Dyreng và Markle (2015) đã tiến hành nghiên cứu các DN đa quốc gia ở Hoa Kỳ về khả năng chuyển đổi thu nhập của các DN bị hạn chế tài chính. Lập luận của nhóm tác giả cho rằng, đối với các DN có mức độ giới hạn tài chính cao sẽ chịu khoản chi phí chuyển đổi thu nhập ra nước ngoài cao hơn nên sẽ giảm việc thực hiện hành vi tránh thuế.

Kết quả này cũng có thể lý giải được vì các DN bị hạn chế tài chính sẽ khó khăn hơn trong việc huy động nguồn vốn tài trợ từ bên ngoài trong đó có vốn vay. Trong khi đó, nợ vay có thể được sử dụng làm lá chắn thuế khi dựa trên luật về thuế cho phép các DN khấu trừ các khoản thanh toán lãi vay từ thu nhập chịu thuế của mình. Có thể nói, hành vi gia tăng các khoản nợ vay của DN có thể được xem là một trong những phương pháp giảm thiểu chi phí về thuế. Do đó, Farre-Mensa và Ljungqvist (2016) hàm ý rằng khi DN trong tình trạng hạn chế tài chính sẽ bị giảm cơ hội tận dụng lá chắn thuế để giảm thiểu khoản tiền thuế phải trả. Điều này cũng thể hiện rằng các DN trong tình trạng giới hạn về tài chính có thể sẽ giảm việc tránh thuế.

Hơn nữa, khi tồn tại tách biệt giữa nhà quản lý và các chủ sở hữu thì cũng có thể tồn tại sự khác nhau về lợi ích giữa hai bên. Do đó, không phải lúc nào các nhà quản lý cũng sẽ điều hành DN đúng theo kỳ vọng của các cổ đông. Trong khi theo Wang và cộng sự (2020) tránh thuế có thể đi kèm với các giao dịch phức tạp nhằm che mắt cơ quan thuế, đồng thời che giấu các nguồn lực khỏi các cổ đông, có khả năng cho phép các nhà điều hành sử dụng các nguồn lực này mang lại lợi ích cá nhân phục vụ cho mục đích riêng. Lo ngại về vấn đề này, các cổ đông có thể sẽ không ưa thích DN thực hiện việc tránh thuế. Do đó, đối với các DN có mức độ giới hạn tài chính cao và việc khó khăn trong huy động nguồn vốn, các nhà quản lý có thể mong muốn giữ được uy tín hay niềm tin của các nhà đầu tư hay cổ đông nên điều hành DN một cách thận trọng. Như vậy, khả năng các DN sử dụng hành vi tránh thuế khi ở trong tình trạng giới hạn tài chính không cao. Dẫn đến, các DN có mức độ giới hạn về chế tài chính cao có khả năng hoạt động cẩn thận và giảm hành động tránh thuế của mình.

Mối quan hệ ngược chiều của hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế này theo tác giả khá thích hợp tại Việt Nam khi nền kinh tế chủ yếu được cấu thành từ các DN vừa và nhỏ, các nguồn tài chính để huy động vốn còn hạn chế, hơn nữa các nhà đầu tư còn khá nhạy cảm với các rủi ro. Do đó, các DN trong tình trạng hạn chế tài chính sẽ có xu hướng phải hoạt động cẩn trọng hơn để không làm mất uy tín của mình đối với các nhà đầu tư hay người cung cấp vốn vay tiềm năng. Trong khi đó, hành vi tránh thuế lại có khả năng khiến DN chịu chi phí tổn hại danh tiếng nếu bị cơ quan thuế phát hiện (Desai và Dharmapala, 2009). Do đó, các DN khi có hành động tránh thuế khả năng sẽ chịu chi phí cao hơn so với lợi ích khi đang trong mức độ giới hạn về tài chính cao. Chính vì điều này, động cơ tránh thuế của các DN bị hạn chế tài chính có xu hướng giảm khi cân nhắc giữa chi phí và lợi ích của hành vi tránh thuế (Dyreng và Markle, 2015).

Ngoài ra, bên cạnh tình trạng hạn chế tài chính, còn có các nhân tố khác cũng có tầm tác động nhất định đến hành động tránh thuế của doanh nghiệp. Khi xem xét chủ yếu đến kết quả hồi quy ở cột (1) bảng 4.3, biến kiểm soát về tỷ suất sinh lợi trên tài sản của ROA có giá trị hệ số lớn hơn 0 và ở mức ý nghĩa 1%. Kết quả này hàm ý rằng các công ty có tỷ suất sinh lời trên tài sản càng cao thì càng có khả năng thực hiện hành động tránh thuế, cũng tương tự với kết quả nghiên cứu của Chen và cộng sự (2012). Số năm doanh nghiệp niêm yết AGE cho thấy hệ số hồi quy âm là -0.000 (cụ thể hơn là -0.0004) với mức ý nghĩa 1% ngụ ý rằng các DN mới chưa niêm yết hay đã niêm yết nhưng trong thời gian ngắn sẽ tránh thuế nhiều hơn.

Biến kiểm soát TANG cho kết quả có hệ số lớn hơn 0 ở mức ý nghĩa 1%, nhất quán với nghiên cứu của Wilson, (2009), Lisowsky (2010). Các nhóm tác giả lập luận rằng các công ty có nguồn vốn lớn thường có gánh nặng thuế thấp hơn và chênh lệch giữa kế toán và thuế cao hơn, do có thể tận dụng chi phí khấu hao tài sản làm lá chắn thuế theo luật định. Ngược lại với điều này, biến kiểm soát INV có giá trị hệ số hồi quy là -0.013 ở mức ý nghĩa 1%. Theo giải thích của Edwards và cộng sự (2016) cho rằng doanh nghiệp sẽ không được hưởng lợi ích gì từ lá chắn thuế trong trường hợp công ty đầu tư nhiều hơn vào hàng tồn kho.

Tuy nhiên, biến quy mô doanh nghiệp SIZE lại cho thấy kết quả hồi quy ngược với kỳ vọng của người viết khi có hệ số tương quan âm ngụ ý rằng các công ty có quy mô càng lớn thì lại giảm thực hiện hành vi tránh thuế. Lập luận cho sự trái ngược này, tác giả cho rằng đối với các doanh nghiệp nhỏ sẽ có khả năng quan tâm đến đầu tư nhiều hơn do đang trong giai đoạn mở rộng. Trong khi đó, các công ty có thể tiền thuế tiết kiệm thông qua hành vi tránh thuế để tăng thêm nguồn vốn nội bộ (Edwards và cộng sự, 2016). Do đó, các công ty với quy mô nhỏ có thể tiết kiệm thuế phải nộp để sử dụng khoản tiền đó vào các hoạt động đầu tư nhiều hơn. Biến MTB chỉ có ý nghĩa thống kê ở một thước đo mức độ tránh thuế là TA_CETR và biến LEV đã cho ra kết quả không xuất hiện ý nghĩa thống kê ở cả 3 mô hình.

4.2.2. Ảnh hưởng của tính bất định đến mối quan hệ giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế

Với kết quả nghiên cứu cho thấy sự tác động ngược chiều giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành động tránh thuế của DN, tác giả tiếp tục nghiên cứu với góc nhìn mở rộng hơn và phân tích liệu tính bất định có tác động đến đến mối quan hệ ngược chiều này hay không. Như đã nhắc đến ở chương 3, tác giả đo lường biến tính bất định thông qua chỉ số WUI, đây là chỉ số được phát triển bởi Ahir và cộng sự (2018) dựa trên việc đếm số lần sự bất định được đề cập đến

trong các báo cáo của tổ chức EIU. Sau đó tính giá trị trung vị và thực hiện chia nhóm cho các quan sát thành nhóm có tính bất định cao khi biến tính bất định có giá trị lớn hơn giá trị trung vị là nhóm High UNC, còn lại những quan sát có giá trị tính bất định nhỏ hơn trung vị thuộc nhóm có tính bất định thấp là nhóm Low UNC. Bằng cách chia mẫu dữ liệu nghiên cứu thành hai nhóm như vậy sẽ giúp ích trong việc quan sát mức độ tác động của tính bất định lên mối tương quan ngược chiều giữa giới hạn về tài chính và hành động tránh thuế. Bảng 4.3 trình bày kết quả hồi quy với biến tương tác phân loại là tính bất định, trong đó cột (1) thể hiện kết quả hồi quy của biến BTG ở nhóm quan sát có tính bất định cao (High UNC) và cột (2) là nhóm có tính bất định thấp (Low UNC). Tương tự như vậy cho các hai biến còn lại là RES_BTG và TA_CETR.

Ở giả thuyết H2 cho rằng mối quan hệ nghịch biến giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành động tránh thuế của DN sẽ càng yếu hơn nếu ở trong tình trạng có tính bất định cao. Kết quả hồi quy ở bảng 4.4 chỉ ra rằng hệ số trong mô hình của biến giải thích chính WWscore đều âm và có mức ý nghĩa thống kê là 1% ở cả 2 cột (1) và (2). Khi xét đến giá trị của hệ số hồi quy, nhóm có tính bất định cao (cột (1)) cho hệ số có giá trị tuyệt đối 0.077, thấp hơn so với hệ số có giá trị tuyệt đối 0.082 ở nhóm có tính bất định thấp (cột (2)). Kết quả này cũng tương tự với hai cách đo hành vi tránh thuế còn lại là RES_BTG và CETR. Điều này chứng tỏ ở tính bất định càng cao thì ảnh hưởng ngược chiều của hạn chế tài chính đến hành vi tránh thuế càng yếu hơn. Từ đó, kết quả nghiên cứu cung cấp bằng chứng thực nghiệm ủng hộ cho giả thuyết “H2: Tính bất định làm giảm mối quan hệ nghịch biến giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế.”

Bảng 4.4: Ảnh hưởng của tính bất định đến mối quan hệ giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế

Tên biến	BTG		RES_BTG		CETR	
	High UNC (1)	Low UNC (2)	High UNC (3)	Low UNC (4)	High UNC (5)	Low UNC (6)
WWscore	-0,077*** (0,014)	-0,082*** (0,013)	-0,077*** (0,014)	-0,080*** (0,014)	-0,165** (0,077)	-0,272*** (0,064)
ROA	0,137*** (0,015)	0,210*** (0,015)	0,137*** (0,015)	0,210*** (0,015)	0,295*** (0,055)	0,270*** (0,046)
AGE	-0,001*** (0,000)	-0,0003* (0,000)	-0,001*** (0,000)	-0,0003* (0,000)	-0,002*** (0,001)	-0,001 (0,001)
TANG	0,016*** (0,004)	0,014*** (0,004)	0,016*** (0,004)	0,015*** (0,004)	0,0003 (0,022)	0,001 (0,019)
INV	-0,010*** (0,004)	-0,014*** (0,003)	-0,010*** (0,004)	-0,014*** (0,003)	-0,055** (0,024)	-0,046* (0,024)
SIZE	-0,005*** (0,001)	-0,005*** (0,001)	-0,005*** (0,001)	-0,005*** (0,001)	-0,016*** (0,004)	-0,019*** (0,003)
LEV	0,002 (0,005)	-0,001 (0,004)	0,002 (0,005)	-0,002 (0,005)	0,025 (0,033)	0,013 (0,028)
MTB	0,0003 (0,001)	-0,001 (0,001)	0,0003 (0,001)	-0,001 (0,001)	-0,003 (0,004)	-0,009** (0,004)

Tên biến	BTG		RES_BTG		CETR	
	High UNC (1)	Low UNC (2)	High UNC (3)	Low UNC (4)	High UNC (5)	Low UNC (6)
Hằng số	0,024* (0,013)	0,028** (0,014)	0,012 (0,012)	0,016 (0,013)	-0,003 (0,072)	-0,085 (0,067)
Số quan sát	2.526	2.931	2.526	2.931	2.526	2.931
R ²	0,213	0,328	0,214	0,328	0,214	0,328
Hiệu ứng cố định ngành	Có	Có	Có	Có	Có	Có
Hiệu ứng cố định năm	Có	Có	Có	Có	Có	Có

Ghi chú: Bảng 4.4 thể hiện kết quả ước lượng ảnh hưởng của tính bất định đến mối quan hệ giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế của DN. Cột High UNC và Low UNC tương ứng với hai nhóm tính bất định cao và tính bất định thấp được phân loại dựa trên biến UNC. Mức ý nghĩa thống kê 1%, 5%, 10% được thể hiện thông qua các ký hiệu lần lượt là ***, **, *.

Kết quả ước lượng thể hiện trong bảng 4.4 đã giúp cung cấp thêm bằng chứng thực nghiệm vào dòng nghiên cứu của các yếu tố tác động đến mối tương quan giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành động tránh thuế. Trong một số nghiên cứu trước đó, Shen và cộng sự (2021) cho thấy tính bất định trong nền kinh tế cao sẽ làm giảm hành động tránh thuế do các chi phí tài chính gia tăng. Đồng thời, McGuire, Omer và Wilde (2014) còn chỉ ra sự bất định trong hoạt động kinh doanh dẫn đến sự không chắc chắn về lợi ích tiết kiệm thuế trong tương lai, khiến khả năng đầu tư vào hành vi tránh thuế thấp hơn. Như vậy thì tính bất định cao sẽ làm tăng mối quan hệ nghịch biến giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế của DN. Ngược lại, dựa trên lý thuyết bất cân xứng thông tin, các DN hoạt động trong tính bất định cao hơn sẽ được hưởng lợi nhiều hơn từ chất lượng của thông tin từ nội bộ của họ trong việc giảm chi phí thuế phải trả nhiều thuế hơn. Lập luận này tương đồng với kết quả nghiên cứu của Gallemore và Labro (2015), các DN có khả năng tăng hành vi tránh thuế trong tình trạng tính bất định cao. Điều này có thể làm giảm ảnh hưởng của hạn chế tài chính đến hành động tránh thuế của DN khi tính bất định cao.

Từ kết quả nghiên cứu thể hiện trong bảng 4.4 đã chỉ ra rằng khả năng tiến hành tránh thuế khi các DN bị giới hạn tài chính sẽ thay đổi theo tính bất định của nền kinh tế. Tại thời điểm có tính bất định cao, chi phí để thực hiện hành vi tránh thuế của DN trở nên thấp hơn do ảnh hưởng từ việc gia tăng tình trạng bất cân xứng thông tin. Bởi vì, khi sự bất cân xứng thông tin cao thì các DN có thể dễ dàng hơn trong việc che giấu hành động của mình đối với các thành phần bên ngoài DN (Jensen và Mackling, 1976). Nói cách khác, hành vi tránh thuế của DN sẽ không dễ dàng bị phát hiện. Dẫn đến, chi phí từ hành vi tránh thuế mà tác động lớn đến DN có mức độ giới hạn tài chính cao là chi phí tổn hại danh tiếng khi bị cơ quan thuế phát hiện có khả năng thấp hơn. Do đó, các DN có khuynh hướng tích cực thực hiện hành vi tránh thuế nhiều hơn do thông tin bất cân xứng (Varoonchotikul, 2021). Chính vì vậy, đối với việc giới hạn tài chính làm giảm hành động tránh thuế do DN có khả năng phải chịu các khoản chi phí tài chính lớn thì trong nền kinh tế có tính bất định cao sẽ làm giảm tác động tiêu cực của hạn chế tài chính đến tránh thuế.

Điều này cũng có thể giải thích tương tự cho trường hợp tính bất định thấp. Khi tính bất định thấp, không có các sự kiện làm ảnh hưởng đến tình hình kinh tế chính trị thì có nghĩa nền kinh tế có khả năng được phát triển một cách ổn định và các DN có thể duy trì hoạt động một cách bình thường. Như vậy, việc dự đoán hay nắm bắt thông tin của các thành phần bên ngoài DN là các nhà đầu tư hay chủ nợ cũng trở nên dễ dàng hơn. Dẫn đến, khả năng tồn tại sự bất cân xứng thông tin giữa các nhà quản lý và các nhà đầu tư không quá cao. Các thông tin sẽ được cập nhật thường xuyên khiến cho việc che giấu thông tin khó có thể diễn ra và các DN sẽ có ít khả năng hơn trong việc thực hiện hành vi tránh thuế. Nói cách khác, các DN sẽ không dễ dàng tránh thuế trong tình trạng tính bất định thấp. Kết hợp với sự cẩn trọng của các DN trong tình trạng giới hạn về tài chính thì tính bất định thấp có thể làm tăng mối quan hệ ngược chiều giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành động tránh thuế.

Tóm lại, khi xem xét về ảnh hưởng của tính bất định lên mối tương quan giữa hạn chế tài chính và tránh thuế, kết quả trong bài nghiên cứu đã cho thấy tính bất định cao làm giảm mối quan hệ nghịch biến giữa hạn chế tài chính và tránh thuế. Kết quả này có thể hiểu dựa trên lý thuyết bất cân xứng thông tin đã được đề cập tới ở chương 2. Tuy kết quả này không nhất quán với một số nghiên cứu trước đó cho rằng tính bất định cao sẽ làm tăng chi phí cho hành động tránh thuế nên sẽ càng khiến các DN giới hạn về tài chính giảm hành động tránh thuế (Shen và cộng sự, 2021). Nhưng nghiên cứu đã góp phần cung cấp thêm bằng chứng thực nghiệm về ảnh hưởng của tính bất định đến mối tương quan giữa hạn chế tài chính và hành vi tránh thuế theo góc nhìn khác, đa dạng hơn.

5. KẾT LUẬN VÀ HÀM Ý CHÍNH SÁCH

Hành vi tránh thuế là một chủ đề nhận được sự quan tâm của giới nghiên cứu. Nghiên cứu được thực hiện nhằm xem xét ảnh hưởng của tình trạng bất hoàn hảo tài chính đến hành vi tránh thuế của các DN niêm yết tại Việt Nam trong giai đoạn 2010 – 2021. Kết quả nghiên cứu cho thấy tình trạng hạn chế tài chính có mối quan hệ ngược chiều với hành vi tránh thuế. Nói cách khác, đối với các DN có mức độ giới hạn về tài chính cao sẽ hoạt động thận trọng hơn và ít khả năng tiến hành tránh thuế để giải quyết các vấn đề khó khăn mà DN đang gặp phải. Thứ hai, bài nghiên cứu còn cho thấy rằng các DN bị hạn chế tài chính càng giảm hành vi tránh thuế hơn trong điều kiện nền kinh tế ít bất định. Cụ thể, khi tính bất định thấp thì mức độ minh bạch thông tin được cải thiện và các DN bị giới hạn về tài chính sẽ càng giảm hành vi tránh thuế do e ngại chi phí tài chính tăng cao.

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KẾ TOÁN QUẢN TRỊ TRONG PHÁT TRIỂN BỀN VỮNG: TỔNG QUAN TÀI LIỆU VÀ HÀM Ý

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Tóm tắt

Bài viết nghiên cứu kế toán quản trị trong phát triển bền vững của công ty từ góc độ ra quyết định. Nghiên cứu cung cấp một cái nhìn tổng thể về vai trò kế toán quản trị được nâng cao bởi công nghệ số trong sự phát triển bền vững. Vai trò kế toán quản trị đối với phát triển bền vững là những người hỗ trợ và người báo cáo về giá trị phát triển bền vững được tạo ra trong công ty. Ngoài ra, vai trò của người sáng tạo và người bảo tồn được coi là có liên quan. Do đó, các công ty có tầm nhìn phát triển bền vững trong hệ thống thông tin kế toán và kế toán quản trị bằng cách sử dụng các khả năng do công nghệ số mới cung cấp.

Từ khóa: Chuyển đổi số, công nghệ số mới, kế toán quản trị, phát triển bền vững.

MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: LITERATURE REVIEW AND IMPLICATIONS

Abstract

The article studies management accounting in the sustainable development of the company from the perspective of decision making. The study provides an overview of the role of management accounting enhanced by digital technology in sustainable development. Management accounting for sustainability roles are facilitators and reporters of the sustainability value created within the company. In addition, the roles of creator and conservator are considered relevant. Therefore, companies have a vision of sustainable development in accounting information systems and management accounting using the capabilities provided by new digital technologies.

Keywords: Digital transformation, new digital technology, management accounting, sustainable development.

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Nền kinh tế ngày càng phát triển, đòi hỏi các công ty phải cải thiện hệ thống kế toán để phát triển bền vững bằng cách sử dụng các công nghệ mới như điện toán đám mây, dữ liệu lớn, trí tuệ nhân tạo và internet vạn vật. Bằng cách đó, các công ty có thể báo cáo một cách chính xác về các chiến lược, mục tiêu ngắn hạn và dài hạn của công ty. Ngoài ra, phát triển bền vững dựa trên chuyển đổi số sẽ ngày càng thu hút vào sự tin tưởng và lòng trung thành của khách hàng và tạo lợi thế cạnh tranh thực sự cho các công ty (Kroon và cộng sự, 2021; Willekes và cộng sự, 2022).

Báo cáo của các công ty ảnh hưởng đến sự ổn định tài chính và phát triển bền vững, đây là quá trình cần thiết cho người làm kế toán. Do đó, kế toán quản trị đánh giá các thông tin cần thiết liên quan đến phát triển bền vững cho hoạt động của các công ty. Vì vậy, kế toán quản trị trong phát triển bền vững ngày càng tăng (Willekes và cộng sự, 2022). Kế toán quản trị ngày càng tích cực trong việc tích hợp phát triển bền vững vào chiến lược và mục tiêu của công ty, đồng thời công nghệ số mới có thể tạo điều kiện thuận lợi cho các công ty. Trong các tài liệu cung cấp nghiên cứu trong lĩnh vực này, nhưng rất ít nghiên cứu thực nghiệm, điều này tạo thành một lỗ hổng nghiên cứu. Vì vậy, mục đích của bài viết là tổng quan các tài liệu tìm hiểu kế toán quản trị trong phát triển bền vững đưa ra gợi ý và hướng tương lai.

Các tài liệu nghiên cứu đã chỉ ra rằng thực hiện kế toán quản trị trong phát triển bền vững một cách có hiệu quả là để thúc đẩy việc sử dụng thông tin thực tế của các nhà quản lý, do đó ảnh hưởng đến quá trình ra quyết định và để thúc đẩy đổi mới trong báo cáo kế toán quản trị hướng đến phát triển bền vững. Đặc biệt, kế toán quản trị cần thiết trong báo cáo kinh doanh nội bộ mới như báo cáo vốn trí tuệ, bằng cách tác động đến quá trình học tập của kế toán quản trị, từ đó đề xuất để hỗ trợ quá trình ra quyết định quản lý. Chính vì vậy, mục đích của bài báo này là thông qua đánh giá tài liệu có cấu trúc về vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong phát triển bền vững, để mô tả các xu hướng mới nổi và xác định con đường cho nghiên cứu trong tương lai.

2. TỔNG QUAN NGHIÊN CỨU

2.1 Tổng quan tài liệu

Nền kinh tế toàn cầu hóa ngày càng trở nên biến động trong những năm gần đây đã gây ra nhiều ảnh hưởng đến các công ty với các điều kiện dễ tổn tại trong bối cảnh và nhu cầu phát triển bền vững ngày càng tăng (Erokhin và cộng sự, 2019). Kế toán quản trị có thể thông qua việc hạch toán và báo cáo về phát triển bền vững của các công ty một cách hiệu quả và bằng cách sử dụng các công nghệ số mới có thể tạo ra chuyển đổi số cho các mô hình kinh doanh. Hơn nữa, việc tích hợp các công cụ kế toán quản trị trong các hệ thống quản lý hiệu quả các hoạt động của công ty dẫn đến việc quản lý và kiểm soát trong phát triển bền vững của công ty tốt hơn (George và cộng sự, 2016).

Khả năng của một công ty để tạo ra thông tin định tính về các hoạt động được thực hiện về mặt bền vững quyết định hiệu quả của quản lý (Stacchezzini và cộng sự, 2016). Mặc dù nghiên cứu liên quan đến vai trò của kế toán quản trị đối với phát triển bền vững là một chủ đề nghiên cứu trong những thập kỷ gần đây, bằng chứng thực nghiệm chủ yếu dựa trên các nghiên cứu điển hình ở các nước phát triển (Zvezdov, 2012).

Tuy nhiên, các tài liệu học thuật đã thảo luận về vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong việc đảm bảo phát triển bền vững. Nghiên cứu Makarenko và Plastun (2017), đã nhấn mạnh sự cần thiết để hiểu vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong phát triển bền vững và chuyển đổi số. Lovell và MacKenzie (2011) đã phân tích vai trò của các công ty nghề nghiệp kế toán trong việc quản lý nền kinh tế mới được đặc trưng bởi biến đổi khí hậu và chuyển đổi số. Ngwakwe (2012), đã xem xét các sáng kiến phát triển bền vững trong nghề kế toán và chứng minh sự cần thiết của một cách tiếp cận thực tế hơn dựa trên các công nghệ số mới. Nghiên cứu (Schaltegger và Burritt, 2018), kế toán quản trị có thể hỗ trợ sự phát triển bền vững của công ty. Tương tự, nhiều nhà nghiên cứu cũng đã chỉ ra vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong việc cải thiện hiệu quả

hoạt động phát triển bền vững bằng cách hỗ trợ các quyết định trong việc quản lý các thay đổi của công ty (Erokhin và cộng sự, 2019; Celik, 2016).

Ahmad Kalbouneh và cộng sự (2023), nghiên cứu đã đề xuất các hướng nghiên cứu trong tương lai có thể có lợi khi phản ánh ảnh hưởng của công nghệ số đối với việc mở rộng kế toán bền vững trong một doanh nghiệp. Cuộc khảo sát đã xác định bốn xu hướng nghiên cứu về phát triển bền vững đó là báo cáo và công bố thông tin, phát triển bền vững như một phần của hệ thống kiểm soát quản lý, tính toán và quản lý môi trường, sự tham gia và trách nhiệm giải trình của các bên liên quan, phát triển bền vững và trách nhiệm xã hội của doanh nghiệp. Chia sẻ thông tin và giáo dục về kế toán bền vững, kế toán bền vững xanh, sử dụng công nghệ số trong kế toán bền vững bao gồm AI, dữ liệu lớn, IoT và kế toán bền vững. Nghiên cứu cũng trình bày một cuộc kiểm tra kỹ lưỡng về các xu hướng nghiên cứu trong giao điểm của kế toán bền vững, cũng như các hướng nghiên cứu trong tương lai.

IFAC (2021) kế toán quản trị là quá trình đảm bảo phát triển bền vững của công ty thông qua ba cấp độ ra quyết định của công ty đó là cấp độ chiến lược, cấp độ tác nghiệp và cấp độ báo cáo. Cấp độ chiến lược liên quan đến sự tham gia của kế toán quản trị trong việc đưa ra các quyết định chiến lược và các mục tiêu. Cấp độ tác nghiệp là sự tham gia của kế toán quản trị trong quá trình lập dự toán, tính toán chi phí, cung cấp thông tin tài chính, môi trường và xã hội cần thiết để đảm bảo phát triển bền vững của công ty. Cuối cùng, cấp độ báo cáo liên quan đến việc chuẩn bị các báo cáo tài chính, báo cáo phát triển bền vững về hoạt động bền vững của công ty. Do đó, kế toán quản trị ngày càng phải tham gia tích cực hơn vào việc tạo ra giá trị và duy trì phát triển bền vững của công ty.

Kế toán quản trị là hỗ trợ các công ty đáp ứng tất cả các mục tiêu, bao gồm cả phát triển bền vững. Theo IFAC (2021), kế toán quản trị là vai trò của người tạo ra, người hỗ trợ, người bảo tồn và người báo cáo về phát triển bền vững cho các công ty. Vai trò của người tạo ra là phát triển bền vững liên quan đến việc thiết lập các chiến lược, chính sách và kế hoạch cần thiết để tạo ra một giá trị bền vững. Vai trò của người hỗ trợ phát triển bền vững là thông báo và hướng dẫn các quyết định vận hành. Vai trò của người bảo tồn phát triển bền vững là việc bảo vệ các chiến lược tạo ra giá trị phát triển bền vững bằng cách đóng góp vào quá trình quản lý rủi ro. Vai trò của người báo cáo phát triển bền vững là phải đảm bảo thông tin minh bạch và công bằng để mang lại giá trị bền vững. Người làm kế toán đóng vai trò quan trọng trong việc đảm bảo hiệu quả hoạt động của công ty và tuân thủ pháp luật cũng như trong lĩnh vực phát triển bền vững và cân bằng giữa hai khía cạnh: Lợi nhuận và hành vi kinh doanh có đạo đức.

Phát triển bền vững là xác định và quản lý sự cân bằng giữa các giá trị sinh thái, xã hội và kinh tế (Jonker và Faber, 2019). Bên cạnh, các công ty phải hành xử phát triển bền vững, theo đuổi các mục tiêu xã hội và môi trường đồng thời gia tăng giá trị cho các cổ đông.

2.2 Phương pháp nghiên cứu

Để hiểu các tài liệu học thuật của kế toán quản trị trong phát triển bền vững đã phát triển như thế nào trong những năm qua, cũng như chủ đề nào đã được nghiên cứu và hướng nghiên cứu có thể, chúng tôi đã tiến hành đánh giá tài liệu. Từ góc độ phương pháp luận, một số phương pháp đã được thực hiện đánh giá tài liệu, như đánh giá tác giả truyền thống, đánh giá tường thuật, đánh giá hệ thống và đánh giá tài liệu có cấu trúc. Do đó, các phương pháp đánh giá có thể lặp lại nhiều hơn như đánh giá tài liệu có cấu trúc và hệ thống đã được phát triển và

áp dụng. Đánh giá tài liệu có hệ thống là một quy trình có thể nhân rộng, khoa học và minh bạch, hay nói cách khác là một công nghệ chi tiết, nhằm mục đích thông qua tìm kiếm tài liệu toàn diện về các nghiên cứu đã xuất bản. Quá trình này được thiết kế để giúp các nhà nghiên cứu tránh một số rủi ro nhất định, vì những lý do này, chúng tôi quyết định áp dụng phương pháp đánh giá tài liệu có cấu trúc và có hệ thống.

Dựa vào tổng quan tài liệu tác giả xin đưa ra câu hỏi nghiên cứu như sau:

Câu hỏi 1: Kế toán quản trị có phải là người hỗ trợ và người báo cáo trong phát triển bền vững?

Câu hỏi 2: Kế toán quản trị trong việc phát triển bền vững gắn với chuyển đổi số có tạo ra hiệu ứng trung gian mạnh mẽ hay không?

3. KẾT QUẢ VÀ THẢO LUẬN

3.1 Kết quả nghiên cứu

Trả lời câu hỏi 1, Theo Schaltegger và Zvezdov (2015) đã chỉ ra “các kế toán viên có thể... được kỳ vọng sẽ đóng một vai trò quan trọng, thứ nhất, trong việc cải thiện thông tin mà các bên liên quan nhận được về các tác động xã hội và môi trường của một công ty, thứ hai, trong việc cải thiện mức độ hiệu quả các nhà quản lý được báo cáo về các vấn đề phát triển bền vững”. Theo IFAC (2011), các kế toán quản trị có vai trò là người sáng tạo, người hỗ trợ, người bảo tồn và người báo cáo về phát triển bền vững cho các công ty. Vai trò của người tạo ra giá trị phát triển bền vững là việc thiết lập các chiến lược, chính sách và kế hoạch cần thiết để tạo ra một giá trị bền vững. Vai trò của người hỗ trợ phát triển bền vững là thông báo và hướng dẫn các quyết định quản lý vận hành bằng cách cải thiện các quy trình hỗ trợ. Vai trò của người bảo tồn phát triển bền vững liên quan đến việc bảo vệ các chiến lược tạo ra giá trị bền vững bằng cách đóng góp vào quá trình quản lý rủi ro. Vai trò của người báo cáo phát triển bền vững là phải đảm bảo thông tin minh bạch và công bằng để mang lại giá trị bền vững. Kế toán quản trị đóng vai trò quan trọng trong việc đảm bảo hiệu quả hoạt động của công ty và tuân thủ pháp luật cũng như trong lĩnh vực phát triển bền vững và sự cân bằng giữa hai khía cạnh: Lợi nhuận và hành vi kinh doanh có đạo đức (Hoop và cộng sự, 2022). Như vậy, kế toán quản trị là người hỗ trợ và người báo cáo trong phát triển bền vững. Vai trò người báo cáo là thông tin đối với kế toán, nhưng vai trò người hỗ trợ cho thấy tầm quan trọng kế toán quản trị trong việc ra quyết định để đảm bảo phát triển bền vững bằng cách tham gia vào việc tạo ra giá trị phát triển bền vững.

Ngày càng có nhiều công ty tích hợp báo cáo, nâng cao tầm quan trọng của kế toán quản trị. Báo cáo phát triển bền vững cải thiện hệ thống thông tin kế toán cho báo cáo tài chính và phi tài chính, đồng thời mở rộng các biện pháp báo cáo bằng cách tập trung vào xã hội và môi trường. Hơn nữa, bằng cách sử dụng các công nghệ mới, các công ty có thể đạt được báo cáo theo thời gian thực có thể truy cập được đối với tất cả các bên liên quan, có tính tương tác và tích hợp (Hair và cộng sự, 2021).

Theo IFAC (2021) thì vai trò của kế toán quản trị phức tạp hơn nhiều. Kế toán không chỉ chuẩn bị các báo cáo tài chính và phát triển bền vững mà còn có vai trò tích cực trong việc đảm bảo phát triển bền vững. Do đó, vai trò của người sáng tạo và người tạo ra giá trị bền vững là quan trọng nhất, có ảnh hưởng đáng kể đến phát triển bền vững. Như IFAC (2021) và

Makarenko và Plastun (2017) thì kế toán quản trị thích nghi với mô hình kinh doanh mà phát triển bền vững là chìa khóa. Quan điểm này về vai trò kế toán quản trị là chức năng tương thích với các cấp ra quyết định trong công ty. Kế toán quản trị là những người tạo ra các giá trị phát triển bền vững ở cấp độ chiến lược và tạo ra các giá trị phát triển bền vững ở cấp độ hoạt động. Ở cấp độ báo cáo thì kế toán quản trị là người hỗ trợ và người báo cáo.

Theo nhận thức tác giả thì kế toán quản trị có vai trò là người hỗ trợ và người báo cáo và là những người ảnh hưởng nhiều nhất trong công ty nhất là nền kinh tế môi trường cũng bị ảnh hưởng nhiều nhất bởi vai trò của người hỗ trợ và người báo cáo. Qua đó, tác giả nhận thức vai trò thông tin của người báo cáo vẫn còn quan trọng, nhưng ảnh hưởng của vai trò người hỗ trợ ngày càng tăng.

Trả lời câu hỏi 2, mặc dù vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong kế toán và báo cáo phát triển bền vững, nhưng vẫn có sự không chắc chắn về các bộ phận của kế toán trong việc đảm bảo phát triển bền vững (Egan và Tweedie, 2018), điều này gợi ý cho việc ghi chép, giải thích và báo cáo phát triển bền vững mà còn sử dụng các công nghệ số mới. Theo Schaltegger (2017), đã chỉ ra các kế toán quản trị có thể giải quyết các vấn đề về phát triển bền vững hiệu quả hơn bằng cách tích hợp các công cụ quản lý và đo lường số hóa.

Willekes và cộng sự (2022) cho thấy ngày càng cần thiết phải tích hợp kế toán quản trị vào phát triển bền vững để tạo ra một hệ thống thông tin kế toán hiệu quả cung cấp dữ liệu không chỉ về giá trị tài chính mà còn về giá trị xã hội và môi trường (Ligonie, 2021). Hơn nữa, kế toán và báo cáo phát triển bền vững phải sử dụng các đổi mới và công cụ kế toán quản trị của chuyển đổi số (Ascani và cộng sự, 2021).

Nghiên cứu Schaltegger và cộng sự (2017) đã nhấn mạnh tầm quan trọng của đổi mới dưới bất kỳ hình thức nào bao gồm cả việc triển khai công nghệ số trong kế toán quản trị để đóng góp nhiều hơn vào việc đảm bảo phát triển bền vững của công ty. Còn nghiên cứu (Ng, 2017) đã tập trung vào các năng lực cần có của kế toán viên trong bối cảnh chuyển đổi số và nhu cầu đảm bảo phát triển bền vững của công ty.

Công nghệ số chiếm một vị trí thiết yếu trong việc nâng cao vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong chiến lược của công ty và đặc biệt là đảm bảo phát triển bền vững của các công ty (Damerji và Salim, 2021; Goncalves và cộng sự, 2022). Điện toán đám mây cho phép chia sẻ thông tin theo thời gian thực và tăng tính minh bạch cho các công ty. Dữ liệu được thu thập trực tiếp bằng cách sử dụng các cảm biến được tích hợp vào công nghệ internet vạn vật rồi được chuyển sang công nghệ dữ liệu lớn và được xử lý bằng các giải pháp công nghệ thông tin kết hợp trí tuệ nhân tạo.

Kế toán quản trị trong phát triển bền vững và gắn với trung gian của chuyển đổi số. Theo nghiên cứu Willekes (2022), cho thấy ngày càng cần thiết phải tạo ra một hệ thống thông tin kế toán hiệu quả, cung cấp dữ liệu không chỉ về giá trị tài chính mà còn về giá trị cho kinh tế xã hội và môi trường (Ligonie, 2021). Hơn nữa, các nghiên cứu khác cũng tin rằng kế toán và báo cáo phát triển bền vững phải dựa trên các công cụ kế toán quản trị và những đổi mới do chuyển đổi số mang lại (Ascani, 2021), mở rộng vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong việc đảm bảo phát triển bền vững cho các công ty.

Cũng theo nhận thức tác giả thì chuyển đổi số có một đóng góp thiết yếu vào vai trò của kế toán quản trị từ góc độ phát triển bền vững. Kế toán quản trị ảnh hưởng đáng kể đến sự phát triển bền vững gắn với chuyển đổi số tạo ra hiệu ứng trung gian một phần. Chuyển đổi số đã nâng cao vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong sự phát triển bền vững. Do đó, không chỉ xem xét các khía cạnh tài chính mà còn cả các biện pháp phi tài chính của các công ty. Vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong việc ra quyết định phát triển bền vững ngày càng quan trọng do chuyển đổi số.

Tóm lại, tầm quan trọng của kế toán quản trị trong việc đảm bảo phát triển bền vững, không chỉ đảm nhận vai trò của người hỗ trợ và người báo cáo giá trị phát triển bền vững mà còn gắn với chuyển đổi số tạo ra hiệu ứng trung gian.

3.2 Thảo luận

Mặc dù có sự đồng thuận trong các tài liệu học thuật nhưng kế toán quản trị phải tích cực tham gia vào kế toán phát triển bền vững, sự không chắc chắn liên quan đến vai trò của kế toán trong phát triển bền vững vẫn còn tồn tại (Egan và Tweedie, 2018). Bebbington và Larrinaga (2014) cũng đã kêu gọi “một cách tiếp cận nghiên cứu khác (về mặt phương pháp luận)” để khắc phục “những hạn chế trong cách tiếp cận kế toán hiện tại của chúng tôi đối với tri thức và ứng dụng của nó”. Nghiên cứu Williams (2015) gợi ý rằng cần có các kỹ năng mới cụ thể cho các vấn đề phát triển bền vững bằng cách sử dụng các công nghệ số mới để tăng mức độ tham gia của kế toán quản trị vào kế toán phát triển bền vững. Ngoài ra, Schaltegger và cộng sự (2016) lập luận rằng kế toán quản trị phải tích hợp vào các công cụ đo lường và quản lý công việc của họ cũng như các giải pháp công nghệ thông tin dựa trên công nghệ số để giải quyết các vấn đề phát triển bền vững một cách rõ ràng. Bài báo này đề xuất một mô hình lý thuyết để phân tích vai trò của kế toán quản trị sự phát triển bền vững dựa trên những đổi mới do chuyển đổi số mang lại.

Nghiên cứu cũng đưa ra những hàm ý quan trọng về quản lý và thực tiễn. Nó cung cấp cho kế toán quản trị và những người hành nghề khác trong các công ty một quan điểm rõ ràng và nhất quán về những thách thức và cơ hội do các công nghệ số mới mang lại trong việc áp dụng vai trò của những người sáng tạo và hỗ trợ các giá trị phát triển bền vững. Hơn nữa, trong nghiên cứu này, cũng nhấn mạnh sự cần thiết của kế toán quản trị đảm nhận vai trò quan trọng hơn trong việc phát triển bền vững và xác định các nguồn lực cũng như đảm bảo phát triển bền vững. Những kết quả này cung cấp bằng chứng cho kế toán quản trị tham gia vào các sáng kiến bền vững, đảm bảo phát triển bền vững là một quá trình cơ bản đòi hỏi hệ thống thông tin kế toán phải được thực hiện một cách hiệu quả. Vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong việc ra quyết định trong phát triển bền vững của các công ty ngày càng quan trọng hơn gắn với chuyển đổi số.

3.3 Hướng nghiên cứu tương lai

Mặc dù kết quả của nghiên cứu tổng quan các tài liệu cũng đã góp phần vào tầm quan trọng của kế toán quản trị trong việc phát triển bền vững và gắn với chuyển đổi số làm trung gian, nhưng hạn chế của nghiên cứu không có các cuộc điều tra hay khảo sát thực nghiệm trong các ngành hay các lĩnh vực. Vì vậy, tác giả xin đề xuất hướng nghiên cứu tiếp theo. Thứ nhất, từ một giới hạn nghiên cứu được đưa ra và phỏng vấn các chuyên gia trong ngành để làm

rõ hơn nhận thức về vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong việc tạo ra giá trị kinh tế và ảnh hưởng đến phát triển bền vững. Từ đó, nghiên cứu trong tương lai có thể khám phá các nhân tố tác động đến vai trò kế toán quản trị và phát triển bền vững. Thứ hai, nghiên cứu sâu hơn trong tương lai là có thể được mở rộng cho các kế toán quản trị trong phát triển bền vững từ các ngành hay lĩnh vực khác. Thứ ba, nghiên cứu trong tương lai cũng có thể xem xét các khuôn khổ khác liên quan đến vai trò kế toán quản trị trong phát triển bền vững gắn với công nghệ mới.

4. KẾT LUẬN

Việc tích hợp chiến lược của các công ty trong phát triển bền vững đòi hỏi phải hệ thống lại thông tin kế toán dựa trên các công nghệ số mới cho phép đưa ra các quyết định dựa trên phát triển bền vững. Sau khi tổng quan các tài liệu cho thấy rằng các công nghệ số mới ảnh hưởng có lợi đến kế toán quản trị, làm phong phú thêm vai trò của kế toán quản trị trong sự phát triển bền vững của các công ty. Mặc dù vai trò truyền thống của người báo cáo và người bảo quản vẫn còn quan trọng, nhưng kế toán quản trị ngày càng đảm nhận vai trò của kế toán quản trị. Việc chuyển đổi số đã ảnh hưởng đến hầu hết các lĩnh vực và ngành nghề giúp cải thiện các công cụ của kế toán quản trị, cho phép họ đảm nhận nhiều vai trò quan trọng hơn trong công ty. Do đó, kế toán quản trị tạo cơ hội cho các quyết định tốt hơn tạo ra giá trị cho các công ty. Vì vậy, việc chuyển đổi số của kế toán quản trị cần được nghiên cứu thêm, bởi vì người làm kế toán phải có kỹ năng công nghệ thông tin, vì ngoài kỹ năng kế toán, để sử dụng các công nghệ số mới được tích hợp vào các giải pháp hoạch định nguồn lực của doanh nghiệp phức tạp để đưa ra quyết định hiệu quả.

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GIẢI PHÁP KẾT NỐI THỊ TRƯỜNG TIỀN ĐIỆN TỬ VÀ THỊ TRƯỜNG TÀI CHÍNH TRUYỀN THỐNG

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Tóm tắt

Thị trường tiền điện tử đang phát triển mạnh mẽ và có những tác động nhất định đến thị trường tài chính truyền thống. Nhu cầu kết nối giữa hai thị trường này trở lên ngày một cấp thiết. Tuy nhiên, chúng ta cần đảm bảo những yêu cầu nhất định để việc kết nối có thể đạt hiệu quả và an toàn. Bài nghiên cứu này đề xuất một giao thức giúp kết nối thị trường tiền điện tử và thị trường tài chính truyền thống dựa trên hai công nghệ: (1) Zero-knowledge Proof và (2) Merkle tree. Mục tiêu của giao thức là giúp cho người dùng có thể chia sẻ thông tin của địa chỉ ví (giá trị tài sản điện tử sở hữu, lượng giao dịch trên Blockchain, v.v) mà không để lộ địa chỉ ví mà mình sở hữu. Qua đó, bài nghiên cứu chỉ ra những ứng dụng của việc áp dụng giao thức vào trong lĩnh vực tài chính - ngân hàng và tiềm năng để phát triển trong tương lai.

Từ khóa: thị trường tiền điện tử, thị trường tài chính truyền thống, địa chỉ ví, Zero-knowledge Proof, Merkle tree, Blockchain.

Abstract

The cryptocurrency market is growing strongly and has certain impacts on the traditional financial market. The need to connect between these two markets becomes more and more urgent. However, we need to ensure certain requirements for the connection to be effective and secure. This study proposes a protocol to connect the cryptocurrency market and the traditional financial market based on two technologies: (1) Zero-knowledge Proof and (2) Merkle tree. The goal of the protocol is to make it possible for users to share wallet address information (value of electronic assets owned, amount of transactions on Blockchain, etc.) without revealing the wallet address they own. Thereby, the study points out the applications of the protocol in the financial - banking sector and the potential for future development.

Keywords: cryptocurrency market, traditional financial market, wallet address, Zero-knowledge Proof, Merkle tree, Blockchain.

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Thị trường tiền điện tử đang phát triển mạnh mẽ và thu hút nhiều sự quan tâm không chỉ là những nhà đầu tư cá nhân với nhu cầu sinh lời, mà còn có các tổ chức tài chính, đầu tư truyền thống. Nhu cầu kết nối giữa thị trường tiền điện tử và thị trường tài chính truyền thống đang ngày một cấp thiết. Nhu cầu này được thể hiện qua sự xuất hiện của các sàn giao dịch điện tử hay việc mở rộng dịch vụ tài chính của các quỹ đầu tư và ngân hàng (ví dụ như ngân

hàng JPMorgan đã công bố việc tạo ra một ví tiền điện tử riêng [17] hay quỹ đầu tư Fidelity đã ra mắt dịch vụ lưu trữ và trao đổi tiền điện tử cho khách hàng của mình [18]).

Theo thống kê của Statista, thế giới có 425 triệu người sử dụng tiền điện tử năm 2022 [19] và doanh thu thị trường này dự đoán đạt 37,87 tỷ đô la Mỹ vào năm 2023 [20]. Do đó, tiềm năng kinh tế và khai thác các dịch vụ ngân hàng trong thị trường tiền điện tử là rất lớn. Dịch vụ ngân hàng là những hoạt động và chương trình được cung cấp bởi các ngân hàng và tổ chức tài chính khác để đáp ứng nhu cầu tài chính của khách hàng, bao gồm: tiết kiệm, gửi tiền, vay tín dụng, ghi nợ, quản lý tài chính cá nhân, v.v.

Hình 1. Thống kê số lượng người sử dụng tiền điện tử giai đoạn 2016 - 2022.

Việc kết nối giữa thị trường tiền điện tử và thị trường tài chính truyền thống đem đến lợi ích cho cả các nhà đầu tư trên thị trường tiền điện tử và các tổ chức tài chính truyền thống. Các tổ chức tài chính truyền thống muốn tiếp cận với các nhà đầu tư sở hữu lượng tài sản lớn trên thị trường tiền điện tử để cung cấp các dịch vụ tài chính như cho vay tín chấp, mua bán tài sản, v.v. Điều này giúp các tổ chức tài chính có thể tăng lợi nhuận, mở rộng tệp khách hàng và đa dạng hóa dịch vụ.

Những nhà đầu tư cá nhân cũng muốn tiếp cận với các dịch vụ này. Tuy nhiên, khi kết nối và sử dụng các dịch vụ của tổ chức tài chính truyền thống, những nhà đầu tư vẫn muốn giữ tính ẩn danh của mình trên Blockchain. Họ muốn chỉ cần cung cấp một số thông tin được yêu cầu bởi các tổ chức tài chính truyền thống mà không phải tiết lộ địa chỉ ví và các thông tin khác của mình trên Blockchain. Điều này giúp họ ngăn chặn việc theo dõi và giám sát từ các bên thứ ba, đồng thời bảo vệ tính riêng tư và an toàn cho tài sản của mình. Mặt khác, các tổ chức tài chính không có khả năng để tự thu thập thông tin trên mạng Blockchain của người dùng. Để có thể kết nối với thị trường tiền điện tử, các tổ chức tài chính cần có thông tin từ các hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu trên Blockchain. Các hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu trên Blockchain có thể tổng hợp và cung cấp thông tin đáng tin cậy và minh bạch về các địa chỉ ví trên mạng (ví dụ như giá trị tài sản, điểm tín dụng, v.v).

Hiện nay đã có nhiều nghiên cứu về việc kết nối thị trường tiền điện tử và thị trường tài chính truyền thống. Tuy nhiên, các giải pháp và giao thức trong các nghiên cứu này thường được thiết kế để áp dụng cho các trường hợp cụ thể, ví dụ như chứng minh tổng tài sản của sàn giao dịch lớn hơn tổng nợ, chứng minh quyền sở hữu của sản phẩm với một tập hợp các địa chỉ ví, v.v. Đối tượng của các nghiên cứu này hướng đến là các tổ chức, sàn giao dịch trong thị trường tiền điện tử và ít đề cập đến việc chia sẻ thông tin trên thị trường tiền điện tử của các cá nhân.

Từ đó, chúng tôi xác định được ba thách thức khi kết nối các tổ chức ngân hàng truyền thống với tài chính phi tập trung Blockchain, bao gồm (1) khách hàng phải giữ được tính ẩn danh, tức là không bị lộ địa chỉ ví với tổ chức tài chính truyền thống; (2) các tổ chức tài chính phải tin tưởng được vào thông tin phân tích về khách hàng của hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu; trong khi đó (3) giao thức phải đảm bảo được tính linh hoạt để sử dụng cho nhiều trường hợp khác nhau.

Với mục tiêu giải quyết nhu cầu và các vấn đề trên, bài báo đề xuất một giao thức kết nối ba bên: ngân hàng, hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu Blockchain, và người dùng. Mục tiêu của giao thức là cho phép người dùng chia sẻ thông tin của địa chỉ ví của họ với các tổ chức tài chính truyền thống mà không tiết lộ địa chỉ ví của người dùng.

Phần còn lại của bài báo được tổ chức như sau: Phần 2 trình bày các nghiên cứu liên quan và khoảng trống nghiên cứu; Phần 3 trình bày cơ sở lý thuyết; Thiết kế của giao thức được trình bày và thảo luận ở phần 4; Phần 5 trình bày tiềm năng ứng dụng của giao thức trong các lĩnh vực khác nhau; Phần 6 trình bày kết luận.

2. TỔNG QUAN NGHIÊN CỨU

Các nghiên cứu liên quan được chia thành hai nhóm, bao gồm nghiên cứu về phương pháp kết nối tài chính truyền thống với tài chính phi tập trung và nghiên cứu về ứng dụng của công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof.

2.1. Nghiên cứu về việc kết nối thị trường tiền điện tử và thị trường tài chính truyền thống

Các nghiên cứu về việc kết nối thị trường tiền điện tử và thị trường tài chính truyền thống thường tập trung vào 3 chủ đề: (1) Proof of Ownership, (2) Proof of Liabilities, và (3) Proof of Assets.

(i) Proof of ownership (Chứng minh sở hữu) là một khái niệm quan trọng trong việc liên kết giữa thị trường tiền điện tử và thị trường tài chính truyền thống. Đây là quá trình chứng minh rằng một người dùng hoặc tổ chức thực sự sở hữu địa chỉ ví hoặc một tài sản tiền điện tử nhất định. Một trong các phương pháp dùng để chứng minh tính sở hữu là thanh toán vi mô.

Trong thanh toán vi mô [5], quy trình xác minh yêu cầu chủ sở hữu gửi một lượng tiền điện tử rất nhỏ đến ví của người xác thực và chụp ảnh màn hình giao dịch. Qua đó, người dùng có thể chứng minh mình là chủ sở hữu địa chỉ ví. Phương pháp này có hai ưu điểm: người dùng không phải cài đặt bất kỳ phần mềm nào và có thể tránh được nguy cơ lừa đảo vì chỉ cần một số tiền nhỏ. Tuy nhiên, người dùng khi sử dụng thanh toán vi mô sẽ bị tiết lộ địa chỉ ví và mất đi tính ẩn danh.

(ii) Proof Of Liabilities (Chứng minh nợ) là quá trình chứng minh rằng một tổ chức tài chính như ngân hàng hoặc sàn giao dịch có khoản nợ thấp hơn một ngưỡng nhất định và có đủ tài sản để đáp ứng các cam kết tài chính với một nhóm những người xác minh. Một số nghiên cứu liên quan đến Proof of Liabilities bao gồm: Provisions, Camacho, DAPOL, DAPOL+.

Camacho [5] là một giao thức đảm bảo quyền riêng tư cho các khoản nợ cá nhân và tổng số nợ. Giao thức này dựa trên cam kết Pedersen [15], Zero-knowledge Proof và cấu trúc dữ liệu cây Merkle. Mỗi nút lá của cây Merkle sẽ lưu trữ thông tin về khoản nợ của tổ chức đối với người dùng. Cam kết Pedersen được sử dụng để tránh thông tin nợ được lưu trữ trực tiếp trong cây Merkle. Người chứng minh có thể chứng minh rằng tổng số nợ của mình là chính xác và nằm trong một phạm vi nhất định thông qua Zero-knowledge Proof.

DAPOL [6] là một giao thức được xây dựng dựa trên Camacho. Thay vì sử dụng cây Merkle, DAPOL sử dụng Sparse Merkle Tree (SMT) [13] với chiều cao cố định để ẩn số lượng người dùng. Có hai vấn đề trong thiết kế của DAPOL, bao gồm: (1) việc tiết lộ số lượng người dùng là không an toàn vì các nút không chứa thông tin của người dùng có thể được phân biệt với các nút khác và (2) chiều cao của cây SMT phải đủ lớn để tránh đụng độ.

DAPOL+ [10] là giao thức mở rộng của DAPOL. DAPOL+ kế thừa ý tưởng sử dụng SMT của DAPOL với những lợi ích về quyền riêng tư và hiệu quả. DAPOL+ có hai cải tiến so với DAPOL bao gồm: (1) hạn chế nguy cơ rò rỉ số lượng người dùng, (2) sử dụng ánh xạ ngẫu nhiên giữa thông tin người dùng và nút lá để giảm kích thước cây SMT và bằng chứng.

(iii) Proof of Assets (Chứng minh tài sản) là quá trình chứng minh rằng một cá nhân, tổ chức có lượng tài sản trên Blockchain lớn hơn một ngưỡng nhất định. Một số nghiên cứu liên quan đến Proof Liabilities bao gồm: Provision, gOTzilla.

Provision [7] cho phép sàn giao dịch tiền điện tử tạo ra bằng chứng về tài sản. Việc chứng minh được xây dựng bằng giao thức chuẩn [11]. Giao thức chuẩn, còn được gọi là giao thức Sigma, là giao thức mã hóa được sử dụng để xác thực và chứng minh các yêu cầu ZKP.

Bằng chứng giúp chứng minh sàn biết được các khóa bí mật (private keys) của một tập hợp các địa chỉ ví Bitcoin có tổng giá trị bằng giá trị đã cam kết. Thách thức ở đây là tính toán một bằng chứng duy nhất dựa trên thông tin được cung cấp bởi những địa chỉ ví khác nhau. Điều này khó khăn vì mỗi số dư riêng lẻ được mã hóa bằng các khóa riêng biệt, do đó việc kết hợp chúng không đơn giản. Để khắc phục điểm yếu đó, Agrawal và cộng sự [1] đã công bố một framework giúp tạo Proof of Assets với khóa công khai được băm như một phần của giao thức dựa trên zk-SNARK kết hợp với giao thức Sigma.

gOTzilla [2] là giao thức cho ZKP tương tác cho disjunctive statement có số lượng điều kiện lớn. Disjunctive statement là một tuyên bố logic trong đó có ít nhất hai điều kiện hoặc phần tử được liên kết bằng toán tử "hoặc" (OR). Nếu một trong các điều kiện là đúng, thì toàn bộ tuyên bố sẽ được coi là đúng. Nếu tất cả các điều kiện đều sai, thì tuyên bố sẽ được coi là sai. Với số lượng lớn khóa công khai (ví dụ như trong Bitcoin là 80 triệu), việc sử dụng gOTzilla sẽ giúp cho người dùng tạo Proof of Assets một cách hiệu quả và nhanh chóng hơn. Bằng chứng giúp cho người dùng chứng minh rằng mình có kiến thức về khóa bí mật liên kết với hàm băm của khóa công khai được lưu trong số cái.

2.2. Nghiên cứu về ứng dụng của công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof

Công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof [8] được sử dụng rộng rãi trong nhiều lĩnh vực như bỏ phiếu điện tử [10], đấu giá điện tử [16] và học máy [21]. Phần này trình bày các ứng dụng nổi bật của Zero-know Proof trong lĩnh vực blockchain.

Giao thức Zerocash [3] được đề xuất vào năm 2014 và được triển khai lần đầu tiên với ZCash vào năm 2016. Zerocash giúp người dùng chứng minh rằng một giao dịch hợp lệ đã diễn ra mà không tiết lộ bất kỳ thông tin nào về số tiền được chuyển, người gửi hoặc người nhận. Zerocash đã trở thành nền tảng cho nền tảng Zcash với các tính năng bảo mật cao dựa trên công nghệ ZKP.

Confidential transaction [14] được Gregory Maxwell đề xuất vào năm 2013. Sử dụng ZKP, confidential transaction cho phép các giao dịch trên Blockchain được thực hiện một cách an toàn mà không tiết lộ số tiền được chuyển. Tuy nhiên, việc sử dụng ZKP khiến quy mô giao dịch lớn hơn đáng kể. Confidential transaction chỉ có hai đầu ra và độ chính xác 32-bit sẽ yêu cầu ZKP có kích thước khoảng 5 KB. Kích thước của một giao dịch sẽ là 5,4 KB và ZKRP do đó chiếm khoảng 93% kích thước giao dịch.

Mimblewimble là một giao thức được tối ưu hóa cho Giao dịch bí mật có thể làm cho quy mô giao dịch nhỏ hơn. Mimblewimble thực hiện điều này bằng cách tổng hợp các đầu ra giao dịch cũ và chưa sử dụng (Unspent Transaction Output - UTXO).

Hợp đồng thông minh riêng tư được thiết kế để đảm bảo tính bảo mật của hợp đồng thông minh trên Ethereum. Vì không có cơ chế cung cấp quyền riêng tư cho hệ thống nên thông tin trong hợp đồng thông minh sẽ được hiển thị công khai; nó có thể được truy cập và sử dụng cho mục đích xấu. Vấn đề này có thể được giải quyết bằng cách sử dụng Hawk [12].

Hawk là một mô hình mã hóa và bảo mật hợp đồng thông minh. Mô hình này được thiết kế để đảm bảo tính riêng tư và an toàn cho các giao dịch và hợp đồng thông minh trên Blockchain. Tuy nhiên Hawk yêu cầu có sự quản lý của một người đáng tin cậy. Người này có quyền tiếp cận toàn bộ thông tin bí mật của người dùng. Ngoài ra, chúng ta còn có thể dùng Bulletproofs [4], một cải tiến từ Zero-knowledge Proof không tương tác khi không cần thiết lập đáng tin cậy.

2.3. Khoảng trống nghiên cứu

Hiện nay đã có nhiều nghiên cứu về việc kết nối thị trường tiền điện tử và thị trường tài chính truyền thống. Tuy nhiên, các giải pháp và giao thức trong các nghiên cứu này thường được thiết kế để áp dụng cho các trường hợp cụ thể, ví dụ như chứng minh tổng tài sản của sản giao dịch lớn hơn tổng nợ, chứng minh quyền sở hữu của sản đối với một tập hợp các địa chỉ ví, v.v. Đối tượng của các nghiên cứu này hướng đến là các tổ chức, sản giao dịch trong thị trường tiền điện tử. Các nghiên cứu này ít đề cập đến việc chia sẻ thông tin trên thị trường tiền điện tử (thông tin của địa chỉ ví) của các cá nhân.

Khi chia sẻ các thông tin liên quan đến địa chỉ ví của mình, thông thường người dùng sẽ thông qua một bên thứ ba được tin tưởng (ví dụ như các hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu) làm trung gian để cung cấp thông tin. Người dùng sẽ chứng minh quyền sở hữu của mình đối với địa chỉ ví và nhờ bên thứ ba cung cấp thông tin của địa chỉ ví đó. Điều này dẫn đến nguy cơ địa chỉ ví

của người dùng có thể bị lộ sau quá trình cung cấp thông tin.

Bài toán đặt ra là xây dựng một giao thức để có thể kết nối thị trường tiền điện tử và thị trường tài chính truyền thống. Mục tiêu của giao thức là giúp cho những người dùng trên thị trường tiền điện tử có thể chia sẻ thông tin của địa chỉ ví (ví dụ như số dư, số lần giao dịch, v.v) với các tổ chức tài chính truyền thống mà không bị lộ địa chỉ ví.

Để giải quyết nhu cầu và các vấn đề nêu trên, bài báo đề xuất một giao thức ba bên, bao gồm: (1) tổ chức tài chính truyền thống (ngân hàng), (2) hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu Blockchain, và (3) người dùng. Để đảm bảo độ chính xác của thông tin, giao thức sẽ được thiết kế sao cho người dùng có thể tận dụng các hệ thống phân tích trên mạng Blockchain để chia sẻ thông tin của mình. Việc này giúp đảm bảo rằng các thông tin chia sẻ không chỉ được bảo mật mà còn đáng tin cậy và chính xác, đóng góp vào việc cung cấp một giải pháp an toàn và bảo mật cho việc chia sẻ thông tin ví trên mạng Blockchain. Điều này giúp người dùng bảo vệ tính riêng tư và quyền riêng tư của họ trong quá trình kết nối với các tổ chức tài chính truyền thống

Việc lựa chọn sử dụng Zero-knowledge Proof là phù hợp để giải quyết bài toán này. Với ZKP, người dùng có thể chứng minh các thông tin của địa chỉ ví mà họ sở hữu là hợp lệ mà không cần tiết lộ địa chỉ ví. ZKP đã được nghiên cứu và áp dụng cho những bài toán chia sẻ và bảo mật thông tin như đã trình bày trong Mục 2.2.

3. CƠ SỞ LÝ THUYẾT

Bài báo sẽ trình bày cơ sở lý thuyết về các công nghệ được sử dụng, bao gồm: (1) công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof và (2) cấu trúc dữ liệu cây Merkle.

3.1. Công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof

Zero-knowledge Proof (ZKP) lần đầu tiên xuất hiện vào năm 1985 trong bài báo “The knowledge complexity of interactive proof systems” [9]. Bài báo đã đưa ra khái niệm về ZKP được sử dụng rộng rãi ngày nay: “Giao thức ZKP là một phương pháp mà một bên (người chứng minh) có thể chứng minh cho bên khác (người xác minh) rằng điều gì đó là đúng mà không tiết lộ bất kỳ thông tin nào ngoài thực tế là tuyên bố cụ thể này là đúng.”

Giả sử người chứng minh Alice muốn chứng minh một thông tin bí mật với người xác minh Bob. Mục tiêu của ZKP là giúp cho Bob có thể tin tưởng rằng người Alice biết một thông tin bí mật mà không cần tiết lộ thông tin này. Thông tin bí mật này gọi là chứng cứ w . Thông thường, thông tin này là những thông tin nhạy cảm (mật khẩu, căn cước công dân, v.v.) mà Alice không muốn Bob tiếp cận được.

Trong bài báo này, người dùng muốn chứng minh thông tin của địa chỉ ví mà mình sở hữu trên Blockchain cho tổ chức tài chính truyền thống mà không lộ địa chỉ ví thông qua hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu. Hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu là tổ chức trung gian được tổ chức tài chính truyền thống tin tưởng để phân tích thông tin liên quan đến địa chỉ ví của người dùng. Việc áp dụng ZKP giúp cho người dùng có thể chứng minh thông tin của địa chỉ ví mà không lộ địa chỉ ví của mình cho tổ chức tài chính truyền thống.

3.2. Cấu trúc dữ liệu cây Merkle

Cây Merkle được giới thiệu bởi Merkle vào năm 1979 [13]. Cây Merkle là một cây nhị

phân có thứ tự được xây dựng từ một dãy các đối tượng dữ liệu $(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n)$ sử dụng một hàm băm mật mã H . Các nút dưới cùng của cây là các nút lá. Các nút lá của cây là các giá trị băm $H(d_i)$ với $1 \leq i \leq n$. Các nút khác của cây băm Merkle đều bao gồm hai nút con, một nút con bên trái và một nút con bên phải. Các nút này sẽ chứa giá trị băm $H(left||right)$ trong đó $left$ là giá trị băm chứa ở nút bên trái, $right$ là giá trị băm lưu ở nút bên phải và được ghép nối với nhau bằng ($||$). Nút cuối cùng của cây được gọi là nút gốc (root).

Với dạng cây băm merkle này, số lượng phép tính toán hàm băm tỷ lệ với logarit của số nút lá của cây. Trong khi với các danh sách băm thì số lượng này tỷ lệ với số lượng nút của chính nó. Chính điều này làm cho việc tính toán và xác minh, tìm kiếm giá trị băm trên khối diễn ra nhanh hơn trên các khối dữ liệu lớn. Cây Merkle theo cách hiểu đơn giản sẽ lấy rất nhiều dữ liệu và nén nó thành một chuỗi ký tự đơn giản. Chuỗi ký tự này có thể chứng minh tính xác thực của dữ liệu được giữ trong đó, mà không tiết lộ dữ liệu đó là gì.

Ví dụ, trong trường hợp người chứng minh đang nắm giữ dữ liệu d_1 . Người này muốn chứng minh rằng dữ liệu d_1 lấy từ cây Merkle và không bị thay đổi mà không tiết lộ cụ thể dữ liệu. Người này có thể băm lại cây với các dữ liệu khác có trong cây. Nếu mã băm của nút gốc mới sinh ra trùng với mã băm của nút gốc cây Merkle thì chứng tỏ dữ liệu người chứng minh cầm thực sự thuộc cây Merkle và không bị thay đổi. Từ đó, người dùng có thể xác minh nguồn gốc và tính toàn vẹn của dữ liệu mình sở hữu.

Hình 2. Mô tả cấu trúc dữ liệu cây Merkle

Với giao thức được xây dựng trong bài báo, cấu trúc cây Merkle được sử dụng để lưu trữ thông tin của địa chỉ ví của người dùng tại hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu trên Blockchain. Mỗi nút lá trong cây sẽ ứng với thông tin ứng với địa chỉ ví của một người dùng. Các thông tin được lưu trong nút lá bao gồm: địa chỉ ví, thông tin của địa chỉ ví người dùng (tài sản trung bình, lượng tiền điện tử có trong ví, v.v) được thu thập bởi hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu trên Blockchain, và các thông tin khác.

4. GIẢI PHÁP KẾT NỐI THỊ TRƯỜNG TIỀN ĐIỆN TỬ VÀ THỊ TRƯỜNG TÀI CHÍNH TRUYỀN THỐNG

4.1. Phát biểu bài toán

Bài toán xét đến bao gồm ba bên: (1) người dùng A, (2) tổ chức tài chính truyền thống B, và (3) hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu trên Blockchain C. Người dùng A là một khách hàng của B. Tổ chức B có đầy đủ các thông tin cá nhân cơ bản của A bao gồm họ và tên, số tài khoản, số CMND, quê quán, v.v.

A sở hữu một địa chỉ ví trên Blockchain và mong muốn chứng minh các thông tin tài chính liên quan đến địa chỉ ví của mình cho tổ chức tài chính B. Nhờ đó, A có đủ điều kiện để sử dụng các dịch vụ hoặc nhận các ưu đãi từ tổ chức B. C là tổ chức trung gian được B tin tưởng để phân tích thông tin tài chính liên quan đến địa chỉ ví của khách hàng trên thị trường Blockchain. Dựa trên những thông tin phân tích từ C, tổ chức B sẽ đưa ra quyết định về việc có cung cấp dịch vụ liên quan đến tiền điện tử cho khách hàng hay không.

Bài toán được đặt ra là cần xây dựng giao thức cho phép A chứng minh các thông tin tài chính của mình trên Blockchain cho tổ chức B thông qua hệ thống C mà không bị lộ địa chỉ ví với B. Tổ chức B phải tin tưởng được thông tin người dùng A cung cấp đúng là do hệ thống C phân tích, và A đúng là chủ sở hữu của địa chỉ ví trên Blockchain. Giao thức phải đảm bảo dù tổ chức B và hệ thống C có bắt tay với nhau cũng không thể kết nối thông tin cá nhân và địa chỉ ví của người dùng A. Bên cạnh đó, giao thức phải đảm bảo tính linh hoạt để hệ thống C có thể chia sẻ các thông tin khác nhau của địa chỉ ví người dùng.

Giao thức được xây dựng cần đáp ứng được 3 yêu cầu: (i) khách hàng phải giữ được tính ẩn danh, tức là không bị lộ địa chỉ ví với ngân hàng. (ii) các tổ chức tài chính phải tin tưởng được vào thông tin phân tích về khách hàng của hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu; trong khi đó, (iii) giao thức phải đảm bảo được tính linh hoạt để sử dụng cho nhiều trường hợp khác nhau.

4.2. Thiết kế của giao thức

Cách thức hoạt động của giao thức được mô tả ở Hình 3. Giao thức được xây dựng gồm sáu bước:

Hình 3. Cách thức hoạt động của giao thức

(i) Bước thứ nhất là xác thực người dùng. Người dùng tiến hành cung cấp hai thông tin cho hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu trên Blockchain, bao gồm: (1) địa chỉ ví và (2) mã xác thực.

Mã xác thực là một mã băm chứa thông tin cá nhân của người dùng tại tổ chức tài chính truyền thống (căn cước công dân, số tài khoản). Mục đích của việc cung cấp mã xác thực là giúp tránh nguy cơ thông tin của địa chỉ ví được dùng cho người dùng không chính chủ và được dùng cho người dùng khác nhau.

Hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu sẽ sử dụng hai thông tin người dùng cung cấp để tạo nút lá về thông tin người dùng tại cơ sở dữ liệu cây Merkle. Thông tin nút lá được tạo thành sẽ được sử dụng để tạo bằng chứng về thông tin người dùng ở bước thứ hai.

(ii) Bước hai là thu thập thông tin của địa chỉ ví được người dùng cung cấp ở bước thứ nhất. Các công tin được thu thập có thể là bất kì thông tin nào mà người dùng muốn chia sẻ với các tổ chức tài chính truyền thống (ví dụ như số dư đồng tiền điện tử, điểm tín dụng trên mạng Blockchain, v.v)

(iii) Bước thứ ba là lưu thông tin người dùng vào cơ sở dữ liệu có cấu trúc dữ liệu cây Merkle. Mỗi người dùng ứng với một nút lá trên cây Merkle. Các thông tin lưu trong nút lá này được mô tả ở Hình 4. Thông tin này sẽ được sử dụng để tạo bằng chứng ở bước thứ tư.

Hình 4. Thông tin được lưu trong nút lá ứng với địa chỉ ví người dùng

(iv) Bước thứ tư là tạo bằng chứng. Người dùng sẽ tạo bằng chứng thông qua công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof. Công nghệ này giúp tạo ra một bằng chứng mã hoá các thông tin trong nút lá người dùng và thông tin về cây Merkle lưu trữ toàn bộ thông tin của người dùng. Bằng chứng này có thể chứng minh tính xác thực của thông tin công khai mà không cần tiết lộ toàn bộ thông tin đầu vào. Thông tin công khai có thể là bất kì thông tin nào nằm trong các thông tin đầu vào. Trong trường hợp này, các thông tin đầu vào được công khai bao gồm: thông tin cá nhân và thông tin địa chỉ ví. Qua đó, bằng chứng này có thể giúp người dùng chứng minh thông tin địa chỉ ví gắn với thông tin cá nhân mà không cần tiết lộ địa chỉ ví.

(v) Bước thứ năm là gửi bằng chứng. Sau khi tạo bằng chứng thành công, người dùng tiến hành gửi tệp bằng chứng cho tổ chức tài chính truyền thống để xác thực và sử dụng dịch vụ.

(iv) Bước thứ sáu là xác thực bằng chứng. Sau khi nhận được bằng chứng từ người dùng, tổ chức tài chính tiến hành xác thực tính chính xác của bằng chứng. Khi áp dụng công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof, tổ chức tài chính có thể tiến hành xác thực độc lập mà không cần thông qua hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu trên Blockchain. Điều này giúp giảm thiểu hai nguy cơ tiềm ẩn: (1) rủi ro hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu bắt tay với tổ chức tài chính truyền thống để truy ra thông tin khách hàng và (2) rủi ro hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu thao túng thông tin bằng chứng.

Tính chính xác của bằng chứng bao gồm: (1) bằng chứng được tạo ra từ thông tin của hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu và (2) các thông tin công khai trong bằng chứng thỏa mãn các điều kiện được đặt ra.

4.3. Thảo luận

Với công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof và cơ sở dữ liệu cây Merkle, giao thức đã giải quyết được các yêu cầu mà bài toán đề ra bao gồm (1) đảm bảo tính ẩn danh, (2) đảm bảo tính xác thực, và (3) đảm bảo tính linh hoạt.

Công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof đóng vai trò quan trọng trong hoạt động của giao thức. Với Zero-knowledge Proof, tổ chức tài chính truyền thống và hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu có thể độc lập triển khai module sau khi đã thống nhất các thông tin cần và có. Quá trình tương tác của hai bên chỉ diễn ra ở những bước cuối của giao thức khi người dùng lấy bằng chứng đã được tạo ở hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu và nộp cho tổ chức tài chính truyền thống. Công nghệ này giúp cho người dùng có thể chứng minh được thông tin của địa chỉ ví mình sở hữu do tổ chức phân tích dữ liệu trên Blockchain là chính xác mà không cần tiết lộ địa chỉ ví.

Để giao thức có thể đáp ứng đầy đủ các yêu cầu đề ra, giải pháp cần kết hợp công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof với cấu trúc dữ liệu cây Merkle. Việc sử dụng cây Merkle trong giao thức có ba tác dụng chính, bao gồm: (1) bảo đảm nguồn gốc của thông tin trong bằng chứng, (2) ngăn chặn rủi ro thông tin về một địa chỉ ví được sử dụng cho người dùng không chính chủ, hoặc sử dụng cho nhiều người dùng tại tổ chức tài chính truyền thống, và (3) giúp cho giao thức trở lên linh hoạt.

Tuy nhiên, giao thức vẫn còn tồn tại một số hạn chế, bao gồm: (1) nguy cơ người dùng bắt tay với hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu để có được những chỉ số tài chính tốt trên Blockchain và (2) chi phí cập nhật cây Merkle lớn do thông tin trên Blockchain liên tục thay đổi.

5. TIỀM NĂNG ỨNG DỤNG

Giao thức ẩn danh dựa trên công nghệ Zero-knowledge Proof hứa hẹn mang lại những triển vọng rộng lớn trong việc kết nối thị trường tài chính truyền thống và thị trường tiền điện tử. Trong ngành tài chính ngân hàng, giao thức này có thể định hình những sự thay đổi quan trọng và mang đến lợi ích to lớn.

Theo khảo sát của Madeleine Gracie và Susannah Binsted vào năm 2022 [9], khoảng một phần năm giám đốc điều hành ngân hàng tại Mỹ quan tâm đến việc cung cấp dịch vụ tiền điện tử cho khách hàng của họ. Ngoài ra, 60% người tiêu dùng sở hữu tiền điện tử cho biết họ sẽ sử dụng dịch vụ tiền điện tử của ngân hàng hiện tại nếu họ cung cấp các dịch vụ này, bao gồm: thẻ tín dụng, khoản vay, ví hoặc sản phẩm giao dịch.

Ngoài lĩnh vực tài chính - ngân hàng khi giúp kết nối thị trường tài chính truyền thống và

thị trường tiền điện tử, việc cung cấp một giao thức ẩn danh khi sẽ thông tin địa chỉ ví trên Blockchain còn có nhiều tiềm năng để áp dụng trong các lĩnh vực khác, ví dụ như bảo hiểm, thuế, y tế, bất động sản, v.v. Dưới đây là một số ứng dụng tiềm năng của giao thức:

Lĩnh vực y tế: Công nghệ giao thức ẩn danh dựa trên Zero-knowledge Proof có thể có ứng dụng quan trọng trong lĩnh vực y tế. Bệnh nhân có thể chia sẻ thông tin y tế của họ với các nhà nghiên cứu mà không cần tiết lộ danh tính cá nhân. Chẳng hạn, trong việc nghiên cứu các bệnh tật hiếm, các nhà nghiên cứu có thể yêu cầu dữ liệu từ nhiều bệnh nhân. Sử dụng giao thức này, bệnh nhân có thể chứng minh thông tin y tế của mình mà không tiết lộ danh tính, giúp bảo vệ quyền riêng tư và đồng thời đóng góp vào việc nghiên cứu y học.

Lĩnh vực thuế: Trong lĩnh vực thuế, người dùng có thể chứng minh thu nhập, thông tin tài chính và quyền sở hữu mà không tiết lộ danh tính. Điều này đặc biệt hữu ích khi các tài sản trên Blockchain của người dùng được hợp pháp hoá. Việc đó có thể giúp cho chính phủ, nhà nước có thể quản lý và thu thuế đối với các hoạt động trên Blockchain mà vẫn đảm bảo được tính ẩn danh của người dùng. Các cơ quan thuế cũng có thể xác thực thông tin mà không cần truy cập trực tiếp vào các thông tin cá nhân của người dùng.

Lĩnh vực bất động sản: Trong lĩnh vực bất động sản, người dùng có thể chứng minh quyền sở hữu, thông tin giao dịch và lịch sử giao dịch mà không tiết lộ danh tính. Trong tương lai, các tài sản này có thể được lưu trữ trên Blockchain để chứng minh quyền sở hữu. Điều này có thể hỗ trợ trong việc xác thực thông tin liên quan đến giao dịch bất động sản và bảo vệ tính riêng tư của các bên tham gia. Ngoài ra, việc áp dụng công nghệ này cũng có thể giúp tạo ra sự minh bạch trong quá trình giao dịch và quản lý bất động sản.

Bảo mật dữ liệu cá nhân: Giao thức ẩn danh cũng có thể được áp dụng trong việc bảo mật dữ liệu cá nhân. Người dùng có thể chia sẻ những thông tin cần thiết mà không tiết lộ chi tiết riêng tư. Ví dụ, khi đăng ký dịch vụ trực tuyến, người dùng có thể chứng minh tuổi tác mà không cần tiết lộ ngày sinh hoặc thông tin khác. Điều này giúp bảo vệ quyền riêng tư và ngăn chặn việc lộ thông tin không cần thiết.

Quyền riêng tư trực tuyến: Công nghệ ẩn danh cũng có thể tạo ra môi trường trực tuyến an toàn hơn cho người dùng. Khi tham gia các hoạt động trực tuyến như mua sắm, tham gia diễn đàn, hoặc thậm chí kết nối xã hội, người dùng có thể tham gia mà không tiết lộ danh tính thực sự của họ. Họ có thể chứng minh các thông tin cần thiết mà không để lộ chi tiết cá nhân, đảm bảo tính ẩn danh và bảo vệ quyền riêng tư.

Quản lý chung tài sản: Công nghệ ẩn danh có thể hỗ trợ quản lý chung tài sản trong các dự án, công ty hoặc cộng đồng. Người dùng có thể chứng minh sở hữu mà không cần tiết lộ thông tin chi tiết về tài sản. Điều này giúp trong việc quản lý, chia sẻ và giao dịch tài sản một cách hiệu quả mà không cần tiết lộ quá nhiều thông tin riêng tư.

6. KẾT LUẬN

Bài báo đã đề xuất một giao thức kết nối ba bên, bao gồm: (1) người dùng, (2) tổ chức tài chính truyền thống, và (3) hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu trên Blockchain. Giao thức này giúp cho người dùng có thể chia sẻ thông tin của địa chỉ ví mình sở hữu cho các tổ chức tài chính truyền thống thông qua hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu trên Blockchain mà không lộ địa chỉ ví. Giao thức được thiết kế dựa trên hai công nghệ chính: Zero-knowledge Proof và cấu trúc dữ

liệu cây Merkle. Giao thức được xây dựng thỏa mãn ba yêu cầu, bao gồm: (1) khách hàng giữ được tính ẩn danh, tức là không bị lộ địa chỉ ví với tổ chức tài chính truyền thống; (2) các tổ chức tài chính tin tưởng được vào thông tin phân tích về khách hàng của hệ thống phân tích dữ liệu; trong khi đó, giao thức đảm bảo được tính linh hoạt để sử dụng cho nhiều trường hợp khác nhau.

Trong tương lai, giao thức sẽ tiếp tục được nghiên cứu để có thể áp dụng và triển khai trong nhiều lĩnh vực. Ngoài lĩnh vực tài chính - ngân hàng, việc cung cấp một giao thức ẩn danh khi sẽ thông tin địa chỉ ví trên Blockchain còn có nhiều tiềm năng để áp dụng trong các lĩnh vực khác, ví dụ như bảo hiểm, thuế, y tế, bất động sản, v.v. Mỗi ngành sẽ có những đặc thù riêng về bảo mật dữ liệu, quy mô người dùng, và các yêu cầu khác. Do đó, cần tìm cách để giao thức có thể tùy chỉnh sao cho phù hợp với từng lĩnh vực cụ thể.

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NGHIÊN CỨU CHU KỲ TÀI CHÍNH TẠI MỘT SỐ QUỐC GIA ĐANG PHÁT TRIỂN VÀ KHUYẾN NGHỊ CHO VIỆT NAM

Đỗ Thị Thu Hà

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Tóm tắt

Tác động của sự phát triển tài chính lên tăng trưởng kinh tế quốc gia là chủ đề thu hút nhiều sự quan tâm và tranh luận không chỉ trong giới học thuật mà cả ở các nhà hoạch định chính sách. Nhiều quan điểm khác nhau, thậm chí là trái chiều nhau, trong quan điểm về chu kỳ tài chính. Nghiên cứu này bàn luận đặc điểm chu kỳ tài chính của các quốc gia đang phát triển trên cơ sở nghiên cứu định lượng bằng phương pháp phân tích tần số (frequency) và phân tích bước ngoặt (turning point) nhằm mô tả về chu kỳ tài chính tại 4 quốc gia là Brazil, Singapore, Thái Lan, và Việt Nam với dữ liệu vĩ mô theo quý từ năm 2000 đến 2022. Từ đó đề xuất một số giải pháp phát triển của hệ thống tài chính trong nền kinh tế để thúc đẩy sự tăng trưởng kinh tế trong dài hạn tại Việt Nam

Từ khóa: chu kỳ tài chính, phát triển tài chính, phát triển kinh tế

Abstract

The impact of financial development on national economic growth is a topic of great interest and debate not only in academia but also among policy makers. There are different, even conflicting, views on the financial cycle. This study discusses the financial cycle characteristics of developing countries on the basis of quantitative research using frequency analysis and turning point analysis to describe the financial cycle. financial system in 4 countries: Brazil, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam with quarterly macro data from 2000 to 2022. From that, some solutions are proposed for the development of the financial system in the economy to promote long-term economic growth in Vietnam

Keywords: financial cycle, financial development, economic development

1. ĐẶT VẤN ĐỀ

Các cuộc khủng hoảng vào cuối những năm 90 và gần đây nhất là cuộc khủng hoảng tài chính toàn cầu năm 2008 không chỉ ảnh hưởng nặng nề đến hoạt động của hệ thống tài chính và nền kinh tế, mà các cuộc khủng hoảng này còn giúp các nhà điều hành nhận thức được tầm quan trọng của ổn định tài chính và nắm bắt chu kỳ tài chính. Cũng giống như chu kỳ kinh tế, thể hiện những giai đoạn bùng nổ và suy thoái của sản lượng thực tế, chu kỳ tài chính phản ánh những giai đoạn bùng nổ và suy giảm của các biến số tài chính như tín dụng, bất động sản và chứng khoán. (Terrones, Claessens và Kose, 2011). Chính vì vậy, việc tìm hiểu về chu kỳ tài chính, các đặc điểm chu kỳ tài chính của các quốc gia đang phát triển từ đó gợi ý phát triển chu kỳ tài chính cho Việt Nam là thực sự quan trọng và cấp thiết trong giai đoạn hiện nay.

2. TỔNG QUAN NGHIÊN CỨU

Đối với các nền kinh tế đang phát triển, đặc điểm chung của các quốc gia này là sự phát triển của hệ thống tài chính chưa tương xứng và đồng bộ với sự tăng trưởng mạnh mẽ của nền kinh tế, nhiều quốc gia chưa thực thi các chính sách an toàn vĩ mô, những thay đổi lớn trên các thị trường tín dụng, bất động sản hay chứng khoán báo hiệu giai đoạn đi xuống của chu kỳ tài chính chưa được nhận diện khiến cho nguy cơ đối mặt với suy thoái của các quốc gia này gia tăng. Pontines (2016) thấy rằng chu kỳ tín dụng của các nền kinh tế châu Á ngắn hơn khoảng 8 năm so với các quốc gia phát triển. Beirne (2019) cũng đưa ra nhận định chu kỳ tài chính tại các nền kinh tế mới nổi dễ bị tổn thương từ rủi ro thị trường tài chính toàn cầu và ảnh hưởng của Mỹ. Claessens và cộng sự (2015) nghiên cứu về các giai đoạn suy thoái và khủng hoảng tín dụng tại 24 quốc gia mới nổi trong giai đoạn từ Q1/1978 đến Q4/2011. So với các quốc gia phát triển, biên độ suy thoái tài chính tại các nền kinh tế mới nổi lớn hơn gấp 3 lần, mức độ tổn thất tích lũy cũng lớn hơn gấp 3 lần. Nhận định này cũng phù hợp với các nghiên cứu trước khi cho rằng biến động kinh tế vĩ mô tại các quốc gia mới nổi rõ rệt hơn so với các quốc gia phát triển. (Kose, Prasad và Terrones, 2007).

Phương pháp phân tích tần số (frequency) và phân tích bước ngoặt (turning point) là các phương pháp thường được dùng trong các nghiên cứu trước đây để mô tả về chu kỳ tài chính. Phân tích tần số dựa trên sự tương quan giữa các chuỗi dữ liệu trong ngắn hạn và trung hạn. Nếu các chuỗi dữ liệu có tương quan thì hệ số liên kết (độ lệch chuẩn) sẽ lớn hơn 1, thể hiện sự biến động mạnh trong trung hạn của các chỉ số. Aikman và cộng sự (2011) dựa vào các bộ lọc dựa trên tần suất để ghi lại mối quan hệ giữa chu kỳ tín dụng và chu kỳ kinh doanh. Họ phát hiện ra rằng có một chu kỳ tín dụng riêng biệt, có độ dài và biên độ vượt quá chu kỳ kinh doanh và sự bùng nổ tín dụng có liên quan mật thiết đến các cuộc khủng hoảng ngân hàng.

Phân tích bước ngoặt (turning point) sẽ dựa trên sự biến động của các chỉ số trong các giai đoạn (được phân tách ra bởi một mốc thời gian). Claessens và cộng sự (2011a, b) sử dụng các phương pháp phân tích bước ngoặt cho một số lượng lớn các quốc gia để xác định các đỉnh và đáy trong tín dụng, giá bất động sản và giá cổ phiếu - ba chuỗi mà chúng liên quan đến chu kỳ tài chính. Họ nhận thấy rằng các chu kỳ trong các chuỗi này, được xem xét riêng lẻ, có xu hướng dài và nghiêm trọng, hành vi chu kỳ của tín dụng và giá nhà rất đồng bộ và có mối quan hệ chặt chẽ giữa chu kỳ tài chính và kinh doanh.

Levine là học giả đã có nhiều công trình nghiên cứu nổi bật về mối quan hệ giữa chu kỳ tài chính và tăng trưởng kinh tế đã chỉ ra một vấn đề gây khó khăn lớn và ảnh hưởng đến toàn bộ kết quả trong các nghiên cứu về sự phát triển tài chính đó là việc đo lường biến số đại diện cho chu kỳ tài chính (Levine, 2005). Theo lý thuyết, hệ thống tài chính tác động đến sự tăng trưởng kinh tế thông qua giảm bớt các chi phí giao dịch và chi phí tìm kiếm thông tin, nhờ đó cải thiện và làm gia tăng sự năng động của các nguồn lực tài chính, tăng hiệu quả của các giao dịch liên quan đến nguồn vốn. Trong khi đó, các nghiên cứu thực nghiệm về chủ đề này lại thường không đo lường trực tiếp các chức năng này của hệ thống tài chính. Đa số các nghiên cứu thực nghiệm về chủ đề phát triển tài chính đã xuất hiện từ những năm thập niên 1970, thường sử dụng ba chỉ số phổ biến sau đây để đo lường mức độ phát triển tài chính: Tỷ số tín dụng cho khu vực tư nhân trên GDP, Tỷ số tín dụng nội địa trên GDP, Tỷ số cung tiền

trên GDP. Ngoài ba cách đo lường phổ biến nêu trên, trong các nghiên cứu hiện đại liên quan đến phát triển tài chính còn sử dụng chỉ tiêu liên quan đến mức độ phát triển của thị trường chứng khoán, là một bộ phận của thị trường tài chính, như Rajan và Zingales (1998) sử dụng cả hai cách đo lường Tỷ số tín dụng cho khu vực tư nhân và Quy mô vốn hóa thị trường cổ phiếu trên GDP trong nghiên cứu của họ và chứng minh rằng càng phát triển tài chính càng thúc đẩy tăng trưởng kinh tế.

3. KẾT QUẢ VÀ THẢO LUẬN

3.1. Phương pháp và dữ liệu nghiên cứu

Để đánh giá về mối tương quan và sự biến động của các chỉ số tài chính, nghiên cứu sử dụng phương pháp phân tích tần số (frequency) và phân tích bước ngoặt (turning point) nhằm mô tả về chu kỳ tài chính. Phân tích tần số dựa trên sự tương quan giữa các chuỗi dữ liệu trong ngắn hạn và trung hạn. Phân tích bước ngoặt (turning point) sẽ dựa trên sự biến động của các chỉ số trong các giai đoạn (được phân tách ra bởi một mốc thời gian)

Dữ liệu về tín dụng, tỷ lệ tín dụng/GDP, chỉ số giá tiêu dùng (CPI), GDP, và chỉ số giá chứng khoán được thu thập từ 4 quốc gia (Brazil, Singapore, Thái Lan, và Việt Nam). Nghiên cứu chọn các quốc gia đang phát triển tiêu biểu cho các khu vực trên thế giới. Brazil là quốc gia đang phát triển ở khu vực Mỹ La tinh, khu vực có nhiều tiềm ẩn về khủng hoảng tài chính ở các quốc gia đang phát triển. Thái Lan là quốc gia đang phát triển ở khu vực châu Á và Đông Nam Á. Việt Nam là quốc gia có nền kinh tế và thị trường tài chính mới phát triển gần đây. Riêng trường hợp Singapore, tuy là quốc gia có thị trường tài chính phát triển nhưng tác giả vẫn đưa vào xem xét vì để so sánh giữa nhóm các quốc gia đang phát triển và phát triển. Dựa trên thực tế là chuỗi số liệu tại các quốc gia đang phát triển đôi khi chưa đủ dài và thị trường tài chính chưa phát triển đầy đủ.

Dữ liệu theo quý được thu thập từ năm 2000 đến năm 2022. GDP được chọn làm biến số đại diện cho chu kỳ kinh doanh như các nghiên cứu khác đã chỉ ra. Biến về giá tài sản được đặc trưng bởi chỉ số giá chứng khoán và chỉ số CPI. Ngoài ra, các biến về tín dụng để đặc trưng cho mối quan hệ giữa khu vực tư nhân và khu vực tài chính. Chu kỳ ngắn hạn được quy ước với thời gian từ 5 đến 32 quý (độ dài chu kỳ kinh doanh điển hình). Chu kỳ trung hạn được quy ước với thời gian từ 8 quý trở lên.

3.2. Kết quả nghiên cứu

Sự biến động của các chỉ số tài chính thường được xét đến trong cả ngắn hạn và trung hạn. Bảng 3.1 đã tính toán độ lệch chuẩn của các chỉ số theo cả hai chu kỳ trong ngắn hạn và dài hạn. Nếu chỉ số này dương chứng tỏ các chỉ tiêu này trong trung hạn biến động mạnh hơn so với ngắn hạn. Hay nói cách khác, đây chính là sự biến động tương ứng của các biến qua thời gian.

Bảng 3. 1: Biến động giữa chu kỳ trung hạn và ngắn hạn: các chuỗi riêng lẻ - phân tích tần số (frequency)

	Brazil	Singapore	Thái Lan	Việt Nam
Tín dụng	1.36	7.41	2.41	1.15
Tín dụng/GDP	1.92	8.11	2.7	1.4
CPI	1.03	1.35	1.07	1.06
GDP	1.2	2.59	2.33	1.12
Giá chứng khoán	1.65	2.59	2.06	1.08

Hệ số liên kết trong bảng được tính dựa trên độ lệch chuẩn của các chỉ số trong ngắn hạn và trung hạn

Nguồn: Tác giả tính toán

Trong tất cả các trường hợp, sự biến động của thành phần chu kỳ trung hạn đều vượt quá sự biến động của thành phần chu kỳ ngắn hạn. Nói cách khác, các chu kỳ định kỳ từ 8 đến 30 năm quan trọng hơn trong việc hình thành hành vi của những chuỗi này so với những chu kỳ có thời gian ngắn hơn. Mô hình này đặc biệt rõ rệt đối với tín dụng và giá chứng khoán. Sự biến động của thành phần trung hạn cao hơn nhiều so với thành phần ngắn hạn, gần như luôn thay đổi theo hệ số lớn hơn 1.

Singapore và Thái Lan có các chỉ số đều có mối quan hệ khá rõ ràng. Điều này phản ánh sự phát triển lâu dài của 2 nền kinh tế này. Ngược lại, các chỉ số của Việt Nam chỉ có mối quan hệ ở mức thấp so với các quốc gia khác, phản ánh những biến động chưa có tính dài hạn của các chỉ số. Đặc biệt chỉ số CPI ở tất cả các quốc gia đều không có hệ số liên kết cao. Điều này phản ánh cách tính CPI có thể không phản ánh đầy đủ sự biến động trong dài hạn.

Bảng 3.2: Biến động chu kỳ trung hạn và dài hạn: Phân tích điểm xoay (Turning point analysis)

	Biên độ (%)		Kỳ hạn (quý)	
	Tăng trưởng	Suy thoái	Tăng trưởng	Suy thoái
Chu kỳ trung hạn				
Tín dụng	120	-10	20	12
Tín dụng/GDP	23	-9	16	12
CPI	18	-5	15	13
GDP	28	-12	21	7
Giá chứng khoán	110	-47	24	15
Chu kỳ ngắn hạn				
Tín dụng	15	-5	5	3
Tín dụng/GDP	8	-4	6	3
CPI	10	-2	4	2
GDP	15	-6	8	4
Giá chứng khoán	24	-12	5	5

Biên độ được tính dựa trên phân phối trung bình (median of distribution) của các chỉ số. Khoảng thời gian được tính khi bắt đầu chu kỳ đến khi kết thúc.

Nguồn: Tác giả tính toán

Bảng 3.2 đưa ra kết quả của phương pháp phân tích điểm xoay. Bằng cách tổng hợp các chỉ số của tất cả 4 quốc gia, chúng ta có thể thấy được sự thay đổi của các chỉ số trong 2 chu kỳ tăng trưởng và suy thoái. Nhìn chung, giai đoạn suy thoái trong chu kỳ trung hạn ngắn hơn đáng kể so với giai đoạn mở rộng (cột 3 và 4, Bảng 3.2). Điều này đặc biệt đúng đối với GDP, trong đó sự suy thoái chỉ kéo dài 7 quý trong khi mở rộng dài hơn gần ba lần. Trong ngắn hạn, các giai đoạn suy thoái và tăng trưởng gần như là bằng nhau, phản ánh sự cân bằng của thị trường tài chính.

Bảng 3.3: Khủng hoảng tài chính và điểm đỉnh (peaks) của các biến động chu kỳ trung hạn

Thời điểm khủng hoảng		Tín dụng	Tín dụng/GDP	CPI	GDP	Giá chứng khoán
Phân tích tần số (Frequency)				Số quý		
Brazil	2007Q3	4	5	2	2	2
Singapore	2007Q3	5	3	3	1	1
Thailand	2007Q3	5	5	1	2	2
Vietnam	2007Q3	4	3	2	2	2
Phân tích điểm xoay (turning point)						
Số quý						
Brazil	2007Q3	4	6	2	1	2
Singapore	2007Q3	6	3	2	2	1
Thailand	2007Q3	5	5	3	1	2
Vietnam	2007Q3	5	5	1	1	2

Nguồn: Tác giả tính toán

Để có cái nhìn toàn diện hơn về khủng hoảng tài chính, bảng 3 đưa ra mối quan hệ giữa các đỉnh (peak) của các chỉ số và thời gian khủng hoảng tài chính theo cả 2 phương pháp phân tích tần số (frequency) và phân tích điểm xoay (turning point). Bảng 3.3 hiển thị khoảng cách thời gian giữa ngày đánh dấu sự bắt đầu của một cuộc khủng hoảng tài chính và mức đỉnh gần nhất về GDP hoặc chuỗi tài chính trong tập dữ liệu. Tất cả các số liệu được báo cáo theo quý, phản ánh đỉnh trong chuỗi xảy ra bao lâu khủng hoảng bắt đầu.

Nhìn chung, tại tất cả các quốc gia, khủng hoảng tài chính và điểm đỉnh (peak) xuất hiện khá gần nhau (dưới 6 quý). Chỉ số tín dụng thường có khoảng cách với khủng hoảng tài chính xa hơn. Chỉ số về CPI, GDP, giá chứng khoán thường cách khủng hoảng tài chính khoảng 2-3 quý. Điều này khá hợp lý trong thực tiễn khi các chỉ số này đạt đỉnh thì sau đó một thời gian là khủng hoảng tài chính bắt đầu.

4. MỘT SỐ KHUYẾN NGHỊ ĐỂ PHÁT TRIỂN THỊ TRƯỜNG TÀI CHÍNH VIỆT NAM

Từ diễn biến thực tế về chu kỳ tài chính của các quốc gia nghiên cứu được thể hiện qua kết quả nghiên cứu thực nghiệm có thể nhận thấy rõ rằng biến động của các biến vĩ mô như Tín dụng, Chứng khoán, CPI, GDP có tác động mạnh đến chu kỳ tài chính. Hơn nữa, diễn biến và sự phát triển của chu kỳ tài chính có mối quan hệ mật thiết với tăng trưởng kinh tế cũng như khủng hoảng kinh tế. Do vậy để phát triển chu kỳ tài chính bền vững góp phần tăng trưởng

kinh tế, tránh khủng hoảng kinh tế xảy ra như trong quá khứ, tác giả xin đề xuất một số ý kiến và giải pháp liên quan đến phát triển tài chính để duy trì tăng trưởng kinh tế tại Việt Nam trong dài hạn như sau:

Thứ nhất: Cơ cấu phát triển và cách thức quản lý hệ thống tài chính cần linh hoạt, tăng khả năng cạnh tranh.

Thực trạng hiện tại của các nước đang phát triển, trong đó có Việt Nam, việc cung ứng vốn cho nền kinh tế chủ yếu phụ thuộc vào hệ thống ngân hàng. Mặc dù còn một số ít quốc gia chưa hình thành thị trường chứng khoán do tình hình còn lạc hậu và nền kinh tế chưa đủ tiềm lực như Myanmar, Cambodia, Tajikistan hay do điều kiện đặc biệt về địa lý và tài nguyên thiên nhiên như Brunei, Maldives thì hầu hết các nước châu Á đều có thị trường tiền tệ, thị trường ngoại hối, thị trường chứng khoán (bao gồm cả chứng khoán phái sinh) và thị trường trái phiếu. Tuy nhiên, các thị trường này phát triển không đồng đều, không tạo nên một môi trường cạnh tranh thực sự về vốn. Vì vậy cần cải thiện thể chế và tổ chức trong hệ thống tài chính; Quy định và luật pháp liên quan đến hoạt động của toàn bộ hệ thống tài chính cần chặt chẽ, rõ ràng để thực thi, đảm bảo việc giám sát chặt chẽ để làm giảm bất cân xứng thông tin, tăng sự hoàn thiện của thị trường; Cải tiến, đổi mới sản phẩm tài chính, nâng cao năng lực của các chủ thể và tổ chức trong hệ thống tài chính.

Thứ hai: cần đảm bảo an toàn cho hệ thống tài chính

Đảm bảo an ninh tài chính của thị trường tài chính được hiểu là việc duy trì được sự ổn định và lành mạnh tài chính trong quá trình vận hành của thị trường và hoạt động của các định chế tài chính, trên cơ sở đó, giảm thiểu và hạn chế được rủi ro trên thị trường và hệ thống tài chính. Để có thể phát triển tài chính lành mạnh, hướng đến thúc đẩy tăng trưởng kinh tế cần phải thực hiện giám sát an toàn tài chính trên thị trường tiền tệ - ngân hàng, thị trường chứng khoán, và các thị trường tài chính khác như thị trường bảo hiểm. Tiêu chí quan trọng nhất là đảm bảo tỷ lệ vốn khả dụng, và báo cáo định kỳ cho cơ quan quản lý thị trường. Cần có các quy định chặt chẽ và xử phạt kịp thời mang tính răn đe nếu vi phạm liên quan đến trích lập dự phòng nghiệp vụ, quy định khống chế mức đầu tư vào các tài sản được đưa ra để đảm bảo phân tán rủi ro, quy định về tỷ lệ biên khả năng thanh toán tối thiểu để đảm bảo khả năng thanh toán của các định chế tài chính trung gian. Đối với thị trường tiền tệ và hoạt động của hệ thống ngân hàng: Các chuẩn mực quốc tế như Basel II và hệ thống chỉ tiêu CAMELS nên được sử dụng để đảm bảo an toàn trong hoạt động ngân hàng.

Thứ ba: cần hiện đại hóa hệ thống tài chính

Cơ sở hạ tầng tài chính và công nghệ thông tin khi được phát triển mạnh mẽ, an toàn, hiệu quả và có độ bao phủ rộng sẽ góp phần đem lại hiệu quả đối với việc cung ứng các dịch vụ tài khoản giao dịch và cũng hỗ trợ cho việc cung ứng các dịch vụ tài chính khác, góp phần mở rộng mạng lưới và đa dạng hóa sản phẩm dịch vụ, thanh toán phục vụ nhu cầu đa dạng của người dân.

Hiện đại hóa hệ thống tài chính, phát triển cơ sở hạ tầng tài chính là xu hướng tất yếu của các nước trên thế giới nói chung và các nước châu Á nói riêng. Điều này cũng góp phần

thúc đẩy được các yếu tố đổi mới và cạnh tranh, tạo điều kiện thuận lợi hơn, khuyến khích phát triển thanh toán không dùng tiền mặt, hỗ trợ cho chính sách phổ cập tài chính. Hiện đại hóa hệ thống tài chính là giải pháp rất cần thiết, đặc biệt đối với các nước đang phát triển như Việt Nam, góp phần bảo đảm an ninh, an toàn trong hoạt động thanh toán, đáp ứng được yêu cầu của sự phát triển và hội nhập kinh tế quốc tế.

Thứ tư: Nâng cao vai trò của các chủ thể tham gia hệ thống tài chính

Thực tế là ngày nay, nhiều nước đã nghiên cứu và không ngừng điều chỉnh các cách thức quản lý và chính sách nhằm mục tiêu tăng trưởng nhanh hơn, từ đó có thể giảm bớt khoảng cách của họ so với các quốc gia phát triển đi trước. Các nước đang còn tình trạng kém phát triển tài chính ở châu Á có thể học hỏi bài học kinh nghiệm từ Singapore. Singapore là quốc gia nhỏ nhất ở Đông Nam Á nhưng chỉ 50 năm từ khi trở thành một quốc gia độc lập năm 1965, Singapore đã có GDP bình quân đầu người tăng hơn 100 lần và trở thành nền kinh tế sánh ngang các nước phát triển phương Tây với hệ thống tài chính phát triển mạnh mẽ, vững mạnh. Ngay từ những bước đi đầu tiên, chính phủ Singapore đã chú trọng thiết lập các hội đồng khu vực tư nhân, chuyên thu thập thông tin thị trường theo giai đoạn: cụ thể là năm 1997 các hội đồng này thu thập thông tin để hình thành các định hướng, năm 1998 thông tin tập trung vào việc hỗ trợ các chủ thể quan trọng. Các hội đồng này đã thực hiện hiệu quả vai trò của họ khi đưa ra những ý tưởng mang tính cải cách, đem lại kết quả tích cực như đề xuất thiết lập hệ thống mở về quản lý và điều hành, giúp tăng vai trò tham gia của các nhà đầu tư định chế, tăng cường tính bảo mật của Ngân hàng Trung ương (MAS), thu hút cổ vốn từ các tổ chức tài chính quốc tế.

Nhờ vào biện pháp nâng cao vai trò của các chủ thể tham gia vào thị trường tài chính mà Singapore có hệ thống tài chính phát triển tốt nhất, huy động tối đa nguồn vốn nhân rồi trong và ngoài nước và sử dụng hiệu quả để đáp ứng cho quá trình công nghiệp hóa và hiện đại hóa. Tại Singapore, phát triển thị trường tài chính, trong đó có thị trường vốn gắn chặt với các mục tiêu vĩ mô dài hạn như việc làm và tăng trưởng GDP, được coi là động lực của nền kinh tế. Singapore đã trở thành một trong những thị trường vốn dẫn đầu trong khu vực châu Á, trở thành một trong 4 trung tâm tài chính lớn của thế giới, thị trường ngoại hối đứng thứ 4 thế giới chỉ sau London, New York và Tokyo, vượt qua cả Hong Kong. Năm 2016, Singapore đứng thứ hai bảng xếp hạng các thành phố có môi trường kinh doanh tài chính tốt nhất toàn cầu. Theo dự đoán của tập đoàn tư vấn Boston, đến năm 2025, Singapore sẽ trở thành trung tâm tài chính lớn thứ hai trên thế giới.

Từ kinh nghiệm thực tiễn này của Singapore, các nước thuộc nhóm còn chậm phát triển về thị trường tài chính có thể học hỏi để đưa ra sách lược cụ thể cho chính quốc gia của mình nhưng phải chú trọng vào tất cả các chủ thể trên thị trường chứ không nên tạo ra những ưu đãi đặc thù cho các định chế tài chính do chính phủ quản lý. Có như vậy mới tạo ra sân chơi công bằng và khuyến khích tăng tính cạnh tranh trên thị trường tài chính.

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NGHIÊN CỨU MỐI QUAN HỆ GIỮA SỨC MẠNH THỊ TRƯỜNG VÀ VIỆC ĐA DẠNG HÓA THU NHẬP CỦA CÁC NGÂN HÀNG THƯƠNG MẠI VIỆT NAM

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Tóm tắt

Bài viết nghiên cứu mối quan hệ giữa sức mạnh thị trường và việc đa dạng hóa thu nhập của các ngân hàng thương mại Việt Nam trong từ 2007 đến 2021. Nhóm tác giả đã xây dựng mô hình P-VAR để kiểm chứng mối quan hệ giữa đa dạng hóa thu nhập và sức mạnh thị trường của các NHTM Việt Nam. Kết quả nghiên cứu cho thấy có mối quan hệ chặt chẽ giữa hoạt động đa dạng hóa và sức mạnh thị trường. Bên cạnh đó, một số nhân tố khác cũng có ảnh hưởng đến sức mạnh thị trường và hoạt động đa dạng hóa như quy mô ngân hàng, hiệu quả kinh doanh. Từ đó, các tác giả đưa ra một số giải pháp nhằm tăng cường hoạt động của các NHTM, như: (i) các NHTM cần đa dạng hóa thu nhập theo chiều sâu hạn chế đầu tư dàn trải và kém hiệu quả; (ii) các NHTM cần tập trung tăng hiệu quả và khả năng sinh lời của ngân hàng thông qua các biện pháp như chuyển đổi quy trình kinh doanh, quản lý nhân sự tối ưu, lựa chọn mô hình vận hành thích hợp và (iv) các NHTM cần đẩy nhanh tốc độ niêm yết của các ngân hàng trong hệ thống. Bên cạnh đó, các tác giả cũng khuyến nghị với cơ quan nhà nước như cần tăng cường quản lý hoạt động phi tín dụng của ngân hàng hay tăng cường quản lý cạnh tranh trong khu vực ngân hàng, và tiếp tục đẩy mạnh tái cấu trúc ngân hàng.

Từ khóa: sức mạnh thị trường, đa dạng hóa thu nhập, NHTM, Việt Nam.

RESEARCH ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MARKET POWER AND INCOME DIVERSIFICATION OF VIETNAMESE COMMERCIAL BANKS

Abstract

The article studies the relationship between market power and income diversification of Vietnamese commercial banks in the period from 2007 to 2021. The authors have built a P-VAR model to verify the relationship between income diversification and market power of Vietnamese commercial banks. Research results show that there is a close relationship between diversification activities and market power. Besides, a number of other factors also affect market power and diversification activities such as banks scale and business efficiency. From there, the authors propose a number of solutions to enhance the operations of commercial banks, such as: (i) commercial banks need to diversify their income in depth to limit scattered and ineffective investments; (ii) commercial banks need to focus on increasing bank efficiency and profitability through measures such as transforming business processes, optimal human resource management, and choosing appropriate operating models and (iv) commercial banks need to speed up the listing speed of banks. In addition, the authors also make

recommendations to authorities such as strengthening the management of non-credit activities of banks or strengthening competition management in the banking sector, and continuing to promote restructuring bank system.

Keywords: *market power, income diversification, commercial banks, Vietnam.*

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Khu vực ngân hàng luôn đóng vai trò quan trọng trong việc cấp vốn cho các hoạt động kinh tế và duy trì sự ổn định của hệ thống tài chính, đảm bảo sự giám sát liên tục của các cơ quan quản lý và giám sát ngân hàng (Amidu và Wolfe, 2013; Bahri và Hamza, 2019). Tuy là khu vực được quản lý chặt chẽ nhất, nhưng các cuộc khủng hoảng kinh tế tài chính đã cho thấy đây cũng là một ngành kinh tế dễ đổ vỡ. Trong những năm gần đây, ngành ngân hàng đang trải qua những chuyển đổi cơ bản, nhanh chóng và phức tạp, bao gồm tự do hóa tài chính, hợp nhất, mua bán và sáp nhập, cải cách cơ cấu, quy định & bãi bỏ quy định và áp lực cạnh tranh ngày càng cao (Nguyen và các cộng sự, 2012). Vì thế, để đối phó với sự gia tăng cạnh tranh và để duy trì vị thế trên thị trường, nhiều NHTM đã thực hiện đa dạng hóa các hoạt động của mình (Meslier và cộng sự, 2014), đem lại các lợi ích về thu nhập. Bên cạnh đó, khi các ngân hàng thực hiện đa dạng hóa nguồn thu nhập bằng cách mở rộng quy mô hoạt động, các ngân hàng cũng có xu hướng giành quyền lực thị trường thông qua việc đẩy mạnh các hoạt động mua bán và sáp nhập và các phong trào hợp nhất (Meslier và cộng sự, 2014).

Chính vì lợi ích mang lại, chủ đề về đa dạng hóa thu nhập và đặc biệt mối quan hệ giữa đa dạng hóa thu nhập và sức mạnh thị trường đã nhận được sự quan tâm của các nhà nghiên cứu trong những năm gần đây. Tuy nhiên bằng chứng hiện tại về mối quan hệ giữa sức mạnh thị trường và việc đa dạng hóa của các ngân hàng còn khá phức tạp. Lý thuyết cuộc sống tĩnh lặng (The Quiet Life) cho rằng các ngân hàng có sức mạnh thị trường cao sẽ ít có động lực để thực hiện đa dạng hóa bởi vì họ đã tạo ra đủ lợi nhuận (Berger và cộng sự, 2009). Trong khi đó, các lý thuyết về sức mạnh thị trường lại cho rằng khi sức mạnh thị trường ngân hàng tăng lên, các ngân hàng có xu hướng tập trung vào đa dạng hóa nguồn thu (Ovi và cộng sự, 2014; Nguyen và cộng sự, 2016). Một số nghiên cứu khác lại tìm thấy đa dạng hóa có thể là nguồn gốc của sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng (Valverde và Fernández, 2007; Ciarrapico và Cosci, 2011) hoặc làm giảm sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng do vấn đề hiệu quả nhờ chuyên môn hóa (Montgomery, 1994). Các bằng chứng hỗn loạn này cho thấy mối quan hệ giữa sức mạnh thị trường và xu hướng đa dạng hóa thu nhập của các ngân hàng rất phức tạp, đòi hỏi các nghiên cứu sâu nhằm hỗ trợ các ngân hàng đưa ra các giải pháp phù hợp.

Với mục tiêu như vậy, bài viết được chia thành 5 phần. Ngoài phần 1 giới thiệu, trong phần 2, các tác giả sẽ khái quát tổng quan nghiên cứu về mối qua hệ của đa dạng hóa thu nhập và sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng. Trong phần 3 các tác giả sẽ xây dựng mô hình nghiên cứu để đánh giá mối quan hệ này. Trên cơ sở đó, phần 4 sẽ thảo luận kết quả của mô hình và phần 5 sẽ trình bày các giải pháp và kết luận.

2. TỔNG QUAN NGHIÊN CỨU

Bằng chứng thực nghiệm về mối quan hệ giữa sức mạnh thị trường ngân hàng và đa dạng hóa nguồn thu vẫn còn khá hạn chế. Thêm vào đó, các nghiên cứu trước đây chưa thống

nhất về tác động của sức mạnh thị trường ngân hàng đối với đa dạng hóa thu nhập. Hiện có hai giả thuyết khác nhau về mối quan hệ giữa sức mạnh thị trường và đa dạng hóa thu nhập ngân hàng, bao gồm giả thuyết cuộc sống yên tĩnh (the quiet life hypothesis) và lý thuyết sức mạnh thị trường.

Theo giả thuyết về cuộc sống yên tĩnh (the quiet life hypothesis), khi sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng tăng lên, các nhà quản lý sẽ ít có động lực để thực hiện các chiến lược đa dạng hóa bởi vì họ đã tạo ra đủ lợi nhuận (Berger và Hannan, 1998; Nguyen và cộng sự, 2016). Các nghiên cứu thực nghiệm của Hidayat và cộng sự (2012) và Nguyen và cộng sự (2012) đã chứng minh giả thuyết về cuộc sống yên tĩnh. Trong nghiên cứu của mình, Hidayat và cộng sự (2012) nhận thấy rằng các ngân hàng có sức mạnh thị trường cao hơn có thể thu được tỷ suất lợi nhuận cao hơn và do đó ít có động lực để mở rộng phạm vi hoạt động của mình sang các hoạt động đem lại thu nhập phi lãi. Tương tự, Nguyen và cộng sự (2012) đã kiểm tra tác động của sức mạnh thị trường ngân hàng đối với đa dạng hóa doanh thu bằng cách sử dụng mẫu các NHTM từ năm quốc gia Đông Nam Á trong giai đoạn 1998-2008. Họ nhận thấy rằng các NH có sức mạnh thị trường cao hơn tập trung nhiều hơn vào các hoạt động dựa trên lãi suất truyền thống, trong khi các NH có mức độ quyền lực thị trường thấp hơn tập trung nhiều hơn vào đa dạng hóa doanh thu.

Tuy nhiên, lý thuyết thứ hai về sức mạnh thị trường cho rằng các NH hoạt động trong các thị trường độc quyền có thể có thêm sức mạnh thị trường và được quyền đặt lãi suất huy động thấp hơn, lãi suất cho vay cao hơn cũng như tính phí và hoa hồng cao hơn đối với khách hàng của họ. Theo lý thuyết này, khi sức mạnh thị trường NH tăng lên, các NH có xu hướng tập trung vào đa dạng hóa nguồn thu. Để chứng minh lý thuyết này, một nghiên cứu của Ovi và cộng sự (2014) về các ngân hàng ASEAN trong giai đoạn 1998-2010 cho thấy sức mạnh thị trường có quan hệ cùng chiều với đa dạng hóa thu nhập. Kết quả nghiên cứu cho thấy các NH có sức mạnh thị trường cao có thu nhập lớn hơn từ hoạt động phi truyền thống. Gần đây hơn, Nguyen và cộng sự (2016) đưa ra bằng chứng cho thấy, trong bối cảnh các nước châu Phi, các NH có sức mạnh thị trường cao hơn trên thị trường tiền gửi và cho vay kiếm được nhiều tiền hơn từ các hoạt động phi truyền thống. Họ cho rằng những phát hiện của họ phù hợp với khả năng của NH chi phối trong việc xác định các cơ hội phi truyền thống tốt hơn và sử dụng năng lực thương lượng tốt hơn của họ trong việc tạo ra các hợp đồng. Căpraru, Ilnatov và Pintilie (2020) nghiên cứu mối quan hệ giữa cạnh tranh và đa dạng hóa dựa trên dữ liệu của 1.570 ngân hàng tại 28 nước châu Âu trong giai đoạn 2000 – 2016, đã nhận thấy cạnh tranh là một nhân tố kích thích đa dạng hóa, để đáp ứng chiến lược cạnh tranh của mình, các NH phải liên tục tìm kiếm các nguồn thu nhập bổ sung.

Mặt khác, một số nghiên cứu cho rằng các hoạt động tạo thu nhập phi truyền thống của NH lại có thể gia tăng và tạo ra nguồn của sức mạnh thị trường. Ví dụ, Valverde và Fernández (2007) nhận thấy rằng sức mạnh thị trường tăng lên khi thu nhập đa dạng hơn đối với các hoạt động phi truyền thống trong mẫu nghiên cứu đối với các NH châu Âu. Tương tự, Ciarrapico và Cosci (2011) báo cáo rằng trong bối cảnh của ngành NH Châu Âu, các NH bán chéo hoặc các NH có tỷ lệ thu nhập hoa hồng và phí cao hơn so với thu nhập lãi có liên hệ với sức mạnh thị trường. Họ cho rằng các NH phát triển nhiều hoạt động phi lãi suất hơn có thể có mối quan hệ chặt chẽ hơn với khách hàng, bán cho khách hàng các dịch vụ được cá nhân hóa và chất lượng cao. Trên thực tế, họ áp đặt chi phí chuyển đổi cao đối với khách hàng và cho phép các NH đạt

được sức mạnh thị trường cao. Tuy nhiên, Montgomery (1994) nhận thấy rằng chiến lược đa dạng hóa thu nhập có thể dẫn đến suy giảm sức mạnh thị trường của các NH. Ông tuyên bố rằng bất kỳ chiến lược đa dạng hóa nào cũng làm loãng các kỹ năng nhất định, đặc biệt là các chỉ số hiệu quả thường liên quan đến chiến lược chuyên môn hóa.

Nguyen, Skully & Perera (2012) nghiên cứu mối quan hệ giữa sức mạnh thị trường với ĐDH thu nhập ở năm quốc gia thuộc khu vực Đông Nam Á bao gồm Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Thái Lan và Việt Nam trong giai đoạn 1998–2008. Kết quả nghiên cứu cho thấy, những NH có sức mạnh thị trường ở cả thị trường cho vay và thị trường tiền gửi đều thu được thu nhập cao hơn từ những hoạt động phi truyền thống. Sức mạnh thị trường cho phép NH xác định cơ hội phát triển mới trong các hoạt động phi truyền thống và đem đến khả năng đàm phán tốt hơn với khách hàng. Mối quan hệ này là phi tuyến, bởi khi mức sức mạnh thị trường thấp thì các nhà quản lý tập trung đa dạng hóa thu nhập, ngược lại những NH với sức mạnh thị trường cao thì tập trung vào những sản phẩm dựa vào lãi. Kết quả nghiên cứu còn cho thấy, mối quan hệ giữa sức mạnh thị trường và đa dạng hóa thu nhập thay đổi theo thời gian. Cụ thể, thời kỳ rủi ro tín dụng cao trong và sau khủng hoảng châu Á đã khuyến khích các ngân hàng đa dạng hóa các hoạt động phi truyền thống, còn khi thị trường hồi phục và nhu cầu vay tăng lên thì những hoạt động dựa trên lãi là quan trọng hơn.

Nhìn chung, các nghiên cứu hiện có cho thấy sức mạnh thị trường và việc đa dạng hóa thu nhập của NH có thể được xác định đồng thời, nghĩa là sức mạnh thị trường của NH có thể ảnh hưởng đến việc đa dạng hóa thu nhập và ngược lại.

3. MÔ HÌNH NGHIÊN CỨU

Mục tiêu của nghiên cứu là nhằm điều tra mối quan hệ tương hỗ động giữa sức mạnh thị trường và việc đa dạng hóa thu nhập của ngân hàng. Để đạt được mục tiêu này, nhóm tác giả dự kiến sử dụng phương pháp tự hồi quy vectơ cho dữ liệu bảng (PVAR). Mô hình nghiên cứu dự kiến như sau:

$$MP_{i,t} = \alpha_i^{MP} + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^{MP} MP_{i,t-j} + \sum_{k=1}^q \gamma_k^{MP} DIV_INC_{i,t-k} + \sum EXOG_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,y}^{MP} \quad (1)$$

$$DIV_INC_{i,t} = \alpha_i^{DIV} + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j^{DIV} DIV_INC_{i,t-j} + \sum_{k=1}^q \gamma_k^{DIV} MP_{i,t-k} + \sum EXOG_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,y}^{DIV} \quad (2)$$

Trong đó, i, t lần lượt chỉ ngân hàng và thời gian. MP là thước đo sức mạnh thị trường, DIV_INC là thước đo đa dạng hóa thu nhập trong khi $EXOG$ là tập hợp các biến ngoại sinh có thể tác động tới cả MP và DIV_INC .

3.1. Phát triển biến nghiên cứu

3.1.1. Biến đại diện cho sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng

Trong bài viết, các tác giả áp dụng cách tiếp cận cấu trúc để đo lường sức mạnh thị trường thông qua chỉ số Lerner là chỉ số có nhiều ưu điểm vượt trội nhất là có thể đo lường các thay đổi ở cấp độ từng ngân hàng cũng như theo thời gian. Chỉ số Lerner cũng phản ánh rõ hành vi bắt nguồn từ độc quyền hoặc cạnh tranh độc quyền của NH (Coccorese, 2014). Hơn nữa, chỉ số Lerner không đòi hỏi phải xác định rõ ràng thị trường của ngân hàng (Beck và cộng sự, 2013). Công thức tính chỉ số Lerner như sau:

$$Lerner_{it} = \frac{P_{it} - MC_{it}}{P_{it}} \quad (2.1)$$

Trong đó, MC_{it} là chi phí cận biên dài hạn của NH i vào thời gian t và P_{it} là giá đầu ra của chính NH i , được tính bằng doanh thu/tổng tài sản. Tác giả ước lượng chi phí biên (MC) bằng cách lấy đạo hàm của tổng chi phí (TC) theo một đầu ra (TA). Phương trình ước lượng tương tự như cách của Beck và cộng sự (2013) và Silva-Buston (2019). Theo đó, giả sử rằng tại thời gian t tổng chi phí TC_{it} của ngân hàng i là hàm của một đầu ra, TA_{it} , và hai giá đầu vào, W_{hit} ($h = 1,2$, lần lượt đại diện cho chi phí hoạt động và chi phí vốn). Từ đó, các biến số của hàm chi phí – tuân theo điểm chính của các nghiên cứu thực nghiệm trong ngành ngân hàng - có dạng loga tự nhiên như sau:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln TC_{it} = & \alpha_0 + \alpha_Q \ln TA_{it} + \sum_{h=1}^2 \alpha_h \ln W_{hit} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{QQ} (\ln TA_{it})^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{h=1}^2 \sum_{k=1}^2 \alpha_{hk} \ln W_{hit} \ln W_{kit} \\ & + \sum_{h=1}^2 \alpha_{Qh} \ln TA_{it} \ln W_{hit} + \alpha_T T + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{TT} T^2 + \sum_{h=1}^2 \alpha_{Th} T \ln W_{hit} \\ & + \alpha_{TQ} T \ln TA_{it} \quad (2.2) \end{aligned}$$

Trong đó, i và t chỉ NH i vào năm t , TC là tổng chi phí, TA là tổng tài sản, W_k lần lượt là Chi phí hoạt động được tính bởi các chi phí hoạt động khác trên Tổng tài sản và Chi phí vốn được tính bởi tỷ lệ Chi phí từ lãi trên Tổng số vốn huy động, trong khi T là xu hướng thời gian nhằm tính đến các tiến bộ về kỹ thuật/ công nghệ theo thời gian (Altunbaş và cộng sự, 2001; Brissimis và cộng sự, 2010). Trong hàm loga tự nhiên, điều kiện không cân xứng đưa vào là $\alpha_{hk} = \alpha_{kh}$. Ngoài ra, đồng nhất tuyến tính trong giá đầu vào đòi hỏi rằng $\sum_{h=1}^2 \alpha_h = 1$, $\sum_{k=1}^2 \alpha_{hk} = 0$, và $\sum_{h=1}^2 \alpha_{Qh} = 0$ và $\sum_{h=1}^2 \alpha_{Th} = 0$. Để áp đặt các điều kiện trên, chúng ta có thể chia tổng chi phí và giá của tất cả các yếu tố đầu vào cho một trong các yếu tố giá, ví dụ, W_{2it} . Kết quả là, hàm chi phí dạng loga tự nhiên trở thành:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \ln \left(\frac{TC_{it}}{W_{2it}} \right) = & \alpha_0 + \alpha_Q \ln TA_{it} + \alpha_h \ln \frac{W_{1it}}{W_{2it}} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{QQ} (\ln TA_{it})^2 + \alpha_{hh} \left(\ln \frac{W_{1it}}{W_{2it}} \right)^2 \\ & + \alpha_{Qh} \ln TA_{it} \ln \frac{W_{1it}}{W_{2it}} + \alpha_T T + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_{TT} T^2 + \alpha_{Th} T \ln \frac{W_{1it}}{W_{2it}} \\ & + \alpha_{TQ} T \ln TA_{it} \quad (2.3) \end{aligned}$$

Từ đó xác định được chi phí biên:

$$MC_{it} = \frac{\partial TC_{it}}{\partial TA_{it}} = \frac{TC_{it}}{TA_{it}} \left(\alpha_Q + \alpha_{QQ} \ln TA_{it} + \alpha_{Qh} \ln \frac{W_{1it}}{W_{2it}} + \alpha_{TQ} T \right) \quad (2.4)$$

Lý thuyết và thực nghiệm đều chỉ ra rằng các ngân hàng có sức mạnh thị trường lớn thường ít có động lực đa dạng hóa do đã kiếm được đủ tỷ suất lợi nhuận ở các hoạt động kinh doanh truyền thống (Berger và Hannan, 1998; Nguyen và cộng sự, 2016; Hidayat và cộng sự 2012).

3.1.2. Biến đo lường mức độ đa dạng hóa

Để đo lường sự đa dạng hóa thu nhập, nghiên cứu sử dụng thước đo tương tự chỉ số Herfindahl-Hirschman (HHI) thể hiện mức độ đa dạng hóa thu nhập giữa thu nhập từ lãi và các hoạt động tạo thu nhập ngoài lãi được xác định như sau:

$$DIV_INC = 1 - \left[\left(\frac{NII}{TROR} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{NONII}{TROR} \right)^2 \right]$$

Trong đó, NII là thu nhập lãi ròng, NONII là thu nhập ngoài lãi bao gồm thu nhập ròng từ phí, giao dịch tài sản và chứng khoán, ngoại tệ, bảo hiểm... TNOR=NII+NONII là tổng thu nhập hoạt động ròng của ngân hàng. Theo công thức tính toán này, chỉ số DIV_INC, theo lý thuyết, cần nằm giữa 0 và 1.

Theo Ciarrapico và Cosci (2011), đa dạng hóa có thể thắt chặt mối quan hệ với khách hàng thông qua các hoạt động bán chéo, từ đó, các ngân hàng có thể áp đặt chi phí chuyển đổi dịch vụ cao đối với khách hàng và gia tăng sức mạnh thị trường. Tuy nhiên, chiến lược đa dạng hóa không phù hợp có thể làm suy giảm sức mạnh thị trường do giảm các lợi thế của chuyên môn hóa (Montgomery, 1985)

3.3.3. Nhóm biến ngoại sinh

Từ lược khảo các nghiên cứu, nhóm tác giả lựa chọn các biến có khả năng ảnh hưởng đến cả sức mạnh thị trường và hoạt động đa dạng hóa của ngân hàng để làm biến ngoại sinh trong mô hình nghiên cứu. Các biến được lựa chọn bao gồm:

Quy mô: Quy mô NH được tính bằng logarit tự nhiên của tổng tài sản. Quy mô nhìn chung được xác định là có ảnh hưởng đến cả sức mạnh thị trường lẫn hoạt động đa dạng hóa của ngân hàng. Các ngân hàng lớn có lợi thế về chi phí và địa bàn rộng để tiếp cận khách hàng hơn, từ đó, tăng khả năng áp đặt giá và tăng SMTT. Tuy nhiên, quy mô có thể tác động đến các ngân hàng dưới dạng phi tuyến theo 2 cách: Chiều thứ nhất là sức mạnh thị trường tăng theo quy mô đến một mức độ nhất định sẽ chậm lại (DeGuevara và cộng sự, 2005) hoặc theo De Maudos và Guevara (2007) những NH quy mô rất nhỏ hoạt động trong một địa bàn hẹp có thể tận lợi thế do sự quen thuộc với thị trường để đạt được SMTT lớn hơn một số NH quy mô trung bình.

Hiệu quả kinh doanh: tỷ suất sinh lời tổng tài sản (ROA) là một trong các chỉ số được sử dụng phổ biến nhất để nghiên cứu hiệu quả hoạt động của các ngân hàng và tổ chức tài chính (Pasiouras và cộng sự, 2007; Sufian và cộng sự, 2010). ROA thể hiện hiệu quả của việc đầu tư vào tài sản và khả năng của nhà quản trị trong việc sử dụng các nguồn lực tài chính đầu tư sinh lời (Hassan và cộng sự, 2003).

Rủi ro tín dụng: trong bài viết sẽ sử dụng chỉ số tỷ lệ chi phí dự phòng rủi ro trên Tổng tài sản rủi ro bình quân để đại diện cho mức độ rủi ro tín dụng của các NH. Tương tự như tỷ lệ nợ xấu, chỉ số này càng cao càng thể hiện chi phí mà ngân hàng tiêu tốn để chống đỡ nợ có vấn đề cao, nghĩa là rủi ro tín dụng tăng lên. Rủi ro tín dụng được kỳ vọng làm tăng mức độ đa dạng hóa dựa theo nghiên cứu của Hahm (2008) nhưng các ngân hàng có mức rủi ro tín dụng

thấp lại được hưởng lợi nhuận biên cao nghĩa là có sức mạnh thị trường lớn hơn theo nghiên cứu của DeGuevara và cộng sự (2005).

Cấu trúc sở hữu: Cơ cấu sở hữu là yếu tố chính và quan trọng nhất ảnh hưởng đến quản trị công ty, từ đó, sẽ dẫn đến các quyết định điều hành. Pennathur và cộng sự (2012) đã chứng minh quyền sở hữu là vấn đề quan trọng trong việc tìm kiếm thu nhập ngoài lãi. Trong cấu trúc sở hữu, tình trạng niêm yết cũng là một yếu tố cần xem xét. Các ngân hàng niêm yết bị giám sát nhiều hơn từ thị trường vốn và minh bạch hơn về thông tin (Barry và cộng sự, 2011). Nghiên cứu đánh giá thêm tác động của cấu trúc sở hữu thông qua biến niêm yết cổ phiếu của NH.

Trừ biến về cấu trúc sở hữu thì ba biến còn lại đều không phải là biến ngoại sinh chặt và có thể ảnh hưởng ngược lại đến các biến chính là đa dạng hóa và sức mạnh thị trường. Để hạn chế tình trạng này, nghiên cứu sử dụng độ trễ một kỳ cho các biến đại diện cho Quy mô, hiệu quả kinh doanh và rủi ro của ngân hàng. Công thức tính toán của các biến sử dụng cũng như kỳ vọng được tóm tắt tại bảng 1.

Bảng 1: Tổng hợp các biến đưa vào mô hình

Tên biến	Cách đo lường	A/h đến DIV_INC	A/h đến MP
<i>Biến nội sinh</i>			
DIV_INC (Đa dạng hóa)	$1 - \left[\begin{array}{c} \left(\frac{NII}{TROR} \right)^2 \\ + \left(\frac{NONII}{TROR} \right)^2 \end{array} \right]$	+	+/-
MP (Sức mạnh thị trường) Theo Lerner (1934)	$MP_{it} = \frac{P_{it} - MC_{it}}{P_{it}}$	+/-	+
<i>Biến ngoại sinh</i>			
LNTA (Quy mô tài sản)	Loga tự nhiên của Tổng tài sản	+/-	+
ROA (Hiệu quả hoạt động kinh doanh)	Lợi nhuận sau thuế/Tổng tài sản bình quân	+	+
NPL (Rủi ro tín dụng)	Chi phí dự phòng RRTD/Tổng tài sản rủi ro bình quân	+	-
Public (Ngân hàng niêm yết)	Bằng 1 nếu là NH đã niêm yết bằng 0 cho trường hợp còn lại.	+/-	+

Nguồn: Tổng hợp của nhóm tác giả

3.2. Thu thập và xử lý dữ liệu

3.2.1. Nguồn dữ liệu và mẫu nghiên cứu

Dữ liệu chính được sử dụng trong bài báo được thu thập từ cơ sở dữ liệu của các công ty Việt Nam (FIIN). Một số dữ liệu thiếu được lấy từ chính báo cáo tài chính mà các NH công bố hàng năm. Đề tài chọn giai đoạn nghiên cứu từ 2007-2021, lý do là vì trước giai đoạn này NHNN chưa ban hành mẫu báo cáo tài chính thống nhất dẫn tới việc ghi chép và công bố thông tin về

hoạt động phi lãi có sự khác biệt đáng kể giữa các ngân hàng. Ngoài ra, do mô hình PVAR đòi hỏi một dãy dữ liệu đủ dài, hơn nữa, một số kiểm định bắt buộc chỉ thực hiện được với dữ liệu bảng cân bằng tuyệt đối nên những ngân hàng mới thành lập hay ngân hàng mà số liệu báo cáo tài chính bị trống trong giai đoạn nghiên cứu sẽ phải bị loại. Kết quả thu được mẫu nghiên cứu gồm 24 NH tạo thành dữ liệu bảng cân bằng với 360 quan sát, đây đều là những ngân hàng lớn nhất, tổng ước tính chiếm từ 80-85% thị trường cho vay, 75-81% thị trường tiền gửi và 74-80% thị trường tổng tài sản.

Bảng 2: Tổng hợp các ngân hàng trong mẫu nghiên cứu

TT	Ngân hàng	Viết tắt/ Mã CP
1	NH Nông nghiệp & Phát triển Nông thôn VN	AGRB
2	NHTMCP Đầu tư và Phát triển VN	BID
3	NHTMCP Công thương VN	CTG
4	NHTMCP Ngoại thương VN	VCB
5	NHTMCP Á Châu	ACB
6	NHTMCP Quân đội	MBB
7	NHTMCP Kỹ thương VN	TCB
8	NHTMCP Xuất nhập khẩu VN	EIB
9	NHTMCP Quốc tế	VIB
10	NHTMCP Việt Nam Thịnh vượng	VPB
11	NHTMCP Phát triển Nhà TP HCM	HDB
12	NHTMCP Sài Gòn thương tín	STB
13	NHTMCP Sài Gòn-Hà Nội	SHB
14	NHTMCP Quốc dân	NVB
15	NHTMCP Kiên Long	KLB
16	NHTMCP Sài Gòn Công thương	SGB
17	NHTMCP An Bình	ABB
18	NHTMCP Bản Việt	BVB
19	NHTMCP Đông Nam Á	SSB
20	NHTMCP Hàng Hải	MSB
21	NHTMCP Nam Á	NAB
22	NHTMCP Phương đông	OCB
23	NHTMCP Việt Á	VAB
24	NHTMCP Xăng dầu	PGB

Nguồn: Tổng hợp từ dữ liệu thu thập được

Bảng 3 tóm tắt các thông kê mô tả của các biến dùng để ước lượng cho mô hình. Có thể thấy là ngoài các biến rời rạc ra thì các biến liên tục có số trung bình và trung vị gần bằng nhau cho thấy phần lớn các biến có phân phối chuẩn, thích hợp để thực hiện ước lượng hồi quy.

Bảng 3: Thống kê mô tả các biến sử dụng để ước lượng

	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD.Dev	N
Biến phụ thuộc						
DIV_INC	0,2911065	0,3259973	-1,71177	0,4999909	0,1971537	360
MP	0,1963286	0,1852102	-0,054456	0,5725923	0,1176117	360
Biến độc lập						
LNTA	18,37672	18,4465	14,5267	21,28954	1,398061	360
ROA	0,0104751	0,0086432	0,0000143	0,055663	0,0077398	360
NPL	0,0072055	0,0059048	-0,006267	0,0401616	0,0061061	360
P	0,2888889	0	0	1	0,453877	360

(Nguồn: Ước lượng của nhóm tác giả)

3.3.3. Xử lý dữ liệu

Kiểm tra tính dừng cho dữ liệu bảng:

Trước khi ước tính các mô hình VAR, cần phải kiểm tra tính dừng (cho dữ liệu bảng) của các biến nội sinh (Hartwig, 2010) bao gồm biến DIV_INC và MP. Để làm như vậy, trước tiên nhóm nghiên cứu chạy thử nghiệm gốc đơn vị kiểu Fisher dựa trên thử nghiệm Phillips-Perron và thử nghiệm gốc đơn vị kiểu Fisher dựa trên thử nghiệm Dickey-Fuller tăng cường cho DIV_INC và MP. Kết quả kiểm định (bảng 4) với giả thiết H0 bị bác bỏ cho thấy cả hai biến đều đảm bảo tính ổn định và đủ điều kiện để ước lượng bằng mô hình PVAR.

Bảng 4: Kiểm định tính dừng của biến DIV_INC và MP

		DIV_INC		MP	
		Thống kê	p-value	Thống kê	p-value
Dickey Fuller					
Inverse chi-squared (48)	P	130,7290	0,0000	96,7206	0,0000
Inverse normal	Z	-5,4318	0,0000	-2,2455	0,0124
Inverse logit t (124)	L*	-6,3021	0,0000	-3,1367	0,0011
Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	8,4435	0,0000	4,9725	0,0000
Perron					
Inverse chi-squared (48)	P	176,0535	0,0000	131,8398	0,0000
Inverse normal	Z	-8,1912	0,0000	-4,6659	0,0000
Inverse logit t (124)	L*	-9,4004	0,0000	-5,9104	0,0000
Modified inv. chi-squared	Pm	13,0694	0,0000	8,5569	0,0000

(Nguồn: Ước lượng của nhóm tác giả)

Kiểm định quan hệ nhân quả Granger và ước tính PVAR

Trước khi ước lượng mô hình, nghiên cứu thực hiện kiểm tra mối quan hệ nhân quả Granger giữa hai biến nội sinh để đánh giá sơ bộ về khả năng tác động qua lại lẫn nhau giữa hai biến.

Bước cuối cùng để xử lý dữ liệu là ước lượng mô hình PVAR với độ trễ thích hợp và phân tích các kết quả thu được làm cơ sở để đề xuất các giải pháp và khuyến nghị.

Bảng 5 trình bày kết quả kiểm định nhân quả Granger của 2 biến DIV_INC và MP ở độ trễ 1 kỳ. Với kết quả p-value rất nhỏ cho tất cả các thống kê kiểm định có thể kết luận các biến MP và DIV_INC với độ trễ một kỳ đều hữu ích trong việc dự báo các biến DIV_INC và MP.

Bảng 5: Kết quả kiểm định nhân quả Granger của 2 biến nội sinh

	DIV_INC MP		MP DIV_INC	
	Thống kê	p-value	Thống kê	p-value
W-bar	2,4076		2,4667	
Z-bar	4,8759	0,0000	5,0808	0,0000
Z-bar tilde	2,8108	0,0049	2,9510	0,0032

(Nguồn: Ước lượng của nhóm tác giả)

4. KẾT QUẢ NGHIÊN CỨU

4.1. Kết quả ước lượng mô hình

Bảng 6 trình bày kết quả ước lượng mô hình theo mô hình PVAR. Như vậy, theo kết quả ước lượng PVAR, cả hai biến DIV_INC và MP đều tác động đến biến còn lại. Ngoài tác động lẫn nhau, cả hai biến còn chịu ảnh hưởng của các biến còn lại gồm quy mô hoạt động, hiệu quả kinh doanh và đòn bẩy tài chính. Tình trạng đã niêm yết cổ phiếu chưa có tác động đến sức mạnh thị trường của ngân hàng nhưng không ảnh hưởng đến mức độ đa dạng hóa.

Bảng 6: Kết quả ước lượng mô hình PVAR

	Dấu kỳ vọng	Hệ số	Khoảng tin cậy (95%)	
DIV_INC				
DIV_INC L1.	+	0,1559794** [2,09]	0,009569	0,3023897
MP L1	+/-	-1,033871** [-2,04]	-2,027803	-0,0399388
LNTA		-0,2537051*** [-2,78]	-0,4327009	-0,0747094
ROA		10,95245*** [2,64]	2,812133	19,09277
NPL		-1,491079** [-2,20]	-2,822112	-0,1600465
P		-0,0807947 [-0,98]	-0,2430757	0,0814864
MP				
DIV_INC L1.	+/-	-0,0501674** [-2,19]	-0,950572	-0,0052775
MP L1.	+	0,0168223 [0,20]	-0,1517334	0,185378

	Dấu kỳ vọng	Hệ số	Khoảng tin cậy (95%)	
LNTA	+	-0,1158327*** [-3,32]	-0,1842992	-0,0473662
ROA		9,0386*** [9,49]	7,172478	10,90472
NPL		-0,5471714*** [-4,19]	-0,8032874	-0,2910554
P		0,0582637** [2,12]	0,0044125	0,1121149
No. of obs		288		
No. of panels		24		
Ave. no. of T		12		

(Nguồn: Ước lượng của nhóm tác giả)

Ảnh hưởng của từng chỉ số trong việc dự báo mức độ đa dạng hóa hoạt động hay sức mạnh thị trường của các ngân hàng cụ thể như sau (với mức ý nghĩa 5%:

Tác động tới đa dạng hóa:

- Mỗi đơn vị tăng lên của chỉ số SMTT làm mức độ đa dạng hóa của ngân hàng tăng từ 0,009569 đến 0,3023897 đơn vị.

- Mỗi đơn vị tăng lên của chỉ số đa dạng hóa kỳ trước làm mức độ đa dạng hóa kỳ này của ngân hàng giảm từ 0,0399388 đến 2,027803 đơn vị.

- Mỗi đơn vị tăng lên của tổng tài sản làm mức độ đa dạng hóa của ngân hàng giảm từ 0,0747094 đến 0,4327009 đơn vị.

- Mỗi đơn vị tăng lên của tỷ suất sinh lời ROA làm hoạt động đa dạng hóa của ngân hàng tăng từ 2,812133 đến 19,09277 đơn vị.

- Mỗi đơn vị tăng lên của chỉ số rủi ro tín dụng làm chỉ số đa dạng hóa của ngân hàng giảm từ 0,1600465 đến 2,822112 đơn vị.

Tác động tới sức mạnh thị trường:

- Mỗi đơn vị tăng lên của chỉ số đa dạng hóa làm SMTT của ngân hàng giảm từ 0,0052775 đến 0,0950572 đơn vị.

- Mỗi đơn vị tăng lên của tổng tài sản làm SMTT của ngân hàng giảm từ 0,0473662 đến 0,1842992 đơn vị.

- Mỗi đơn vị tăng lên của tỷ suất sinh lời làm SMTT của ngân hàng tăng từ 7,172478 đến 10,90472 đơn vị.

- Mỗi đơn vị tăng lên của tỷ lệ vốn chủ sở hữu làm SMTT của ngân hàng giảm từ 0,2910554 đến 0,8032874 đơn vị.

- Các NH niêm yết có SMTT bình quân cao hơn các NH chưa niêm yết từ 0,0044125 đến 0,1121149 đơn vị.

4.2. Phân tích các kết quả nghiên cứu

Thứ nhất, hoạt động đa dạng hóa và sức mạnh thị trường của các ngân hàng Việt Nam có mối liên hệ mật thiết với nhau. Cụ thể, hoạt động đa dạng hóa và mức độ sức mạnh thị trường đều ảnh hưởng tiêu cực đến chỉ số còn lại. Điều này có thể lý giải từ phân tích thực trạng cạnh tranh trên thị trường ngân hàng Việt Nam. Việc gia nhập WTO vào năm 2007 trở thành chất xúc tác làm cho thị trường ngân hàng và thị trường chứng khoán của Việt Nam bùng nổ mạnh. Giai đoạn từ 2007 đến 2011 chứng kiến số lượng các ngân hàng và các công ty chứng khoán tại Việt Nam tăng vọt. Số lượng ngân hàng gia nhập thị trường trong thời gian ngắn cùng yêu cầu nâng mức vốn pháp định lên 1000 tỷ đồng rồi đến 3.000 tỷ đồng làm cho thị trường ngân hàng Việt Nam giai đoạn này cạnh tranh vô cùng gay gắt và SMTT của nhiều ngân hàng suy giảm. Tình trạng suy giảm này buộc các ngân hàng phải tìm kiếm lại SMTT đã mất bằng cách đa dạng hóa các nguồn thu nhập. Sự phát triển nhanh chóng của hoạt động trên thị trường chứng khoán thời gian này cũng tiếp tục kích thích các ngân hàng gia tăng hoạt động trong lĩnh vực này hơn thông qua hoạt động của các công ty con. Sự tăng trưởng quá nhanh lại đi kèm với khủng hoảng tài chính thế giới lan rộng đã làm cho các hoạt động về kinh doanh, đầu tư chứng khoán trở nên rủi ro, việc các ngân hàng tích cực thực hiện đa dạng hóa lại dẫn tới tổn thất và không hiệu quả. Nhiều nghiên cứu đã chỉ ra hoạt động đa dạng hóa của các ngân hàng Việt Nam làm giảm hiệu quả cũng như gia tăng rủi ro (Nguyễn Hoàng Phong, 2019; Batten và Vo, 2016, Phạm Hồng Linh và Tạ Thanh Huyền, 2021). Điều này dẫn tới SMTT của các ngân hàng không những không tăng mà còn giảm đi đáng kể. Kết quả này tiếp tục khẳng định các quan điểm trong lý thuyết “Cuộc sống tĩnh lặng”, đó là, các ngân hàng có SMTT cao thường ít có động lực đa dạng hóa hơn (Berger và Hannan, 1992; Nguyen và cộng sự, 2016; Hidayat và cộng sự 2012). Nó cũng cho thấy việc tìm kiếm SMTT từ việc đa dạng hóa không phải lúc nào cũng thành công.

Thứ hai, ảnh hưởng của **quy mô** đối với SMTT và hoạt động đa dạng hóa của các ngân hàng cũng theo hướng ngược chiều. Điều này có thể lý giải là do những ngân hàng bị buộc phải chuyển sang lĩnh vực mới thường là những ngân hàng nhỏ khó cạnh tranh trong các lĩnh vực truyền thống. Hơn nữa thị trường ngân hàng Việt Nam giai đoạn trước đầu thập niên 2000 đổ về trước phần lớn là địa bàn của các ngân hàng TMCP nhà nước với quy mô lớn và kinh nghiệm lâu đời, các ngân hàng nhỏ hoặc ngân hàng mới thành lập giai đoạn cuối thập niên 2000 rất khó cạnh tranh và bị buộc phải sớm chuyển hướng hoạt động. Tác động ngược chiều của quy mô với SMTT cho thấy các ngân hàng lớn cũng gặp những vấn đề riêng trong việc gia tăng sức cạnh tranh.

Thứ ba, hiệu quả kinh doanh cao làm gia tăng SMTT cũng như hoạt động đa dạng hóa của các ngân hàng. Điều này là dễ hiểu vì suy cho cùng phần lớn SMTT của ngân hàng là đến từ hoạt động kinh doanh hiệu quả. Hoạt động hiệu quả mới có khả năng tính giá thấp, thu hút khách hàng và thị trường ngày càng mở rộng. Hoạt động hiệu quả nghĩa là các ngân hàng cũng có khả năng tốt hơn trong việc quản lý những hoạt động kinh doanh và tăng động lực chuyển sang những lĩnh vực mới.

Cuối cùng, không có sự khác biệt về mức độ đa dạng hóa giữa các ngân hàng đã **niêm yết** và chưa nhưng có sự khác biệt về SMTT trong hai nhóm NH. Cụ thể các ngân hàng đã niêm yết có SMTT cao hơn. Điều này có thể lý giải là do các ngân hàng được niêm yết cũng là những ngân hàng được quản lý tốt, đáp ứng được các tiêu chuẩn niêm yết và sẵn sàng trong việc công bố thông tin. Các NH này cũng được thị trường giám sát chặt chẽ trong việc sử dụng các nguồn lực một cách hiệu quả và có khả năng thuận lợi để đạt được SMTT tốt hơn.

5. KẾT LUẬN VÀ KHUYẾN NGHỊ

Như vậy, bài viết nghiên cứu mối quan hệ giữa hoạt động đa dạng hóa thu nhập và sức mạnh thị trường dựa trên dữ liệu của 24 ngân hàng trong giai đoạn 2007-2021. Kết quả nghiên cứu đã chỉ ra rằng có mối quan hệ chặt chẽ giữa hoạt động đa dạng hóa và sức mạnh thị trường và ảnh hưởng là ngược chiều. Thêm vào đó, quy mô có tác động đến SMTT và hoạt động đa dạng hóa theo hướng tiêu cực, trong khi ROA cao làm gia tăng SMTT cũng như hoạt động đa dạng hóa. Tuy nhiên không có sự khác biệt về mức độ đa dạng hóa giữa các ngân hàng đã niêm yết và chưa nhưng có sự khác biệt về SMTT trong hai nhóm NH.

Từ kết quả nghiên cứu, các tác giả đề xuất một số giải pháp với các NHTM như sau. Thứ nhất, các NHTM cần đa dạng hóa thu nhập theo chiều sâu hạn chế đầu tư dàn trải và kém hiệu quả. Thứ hai, các NHTM cần tập trung tăng hiệu quả và khả năng sinh lời của ngân hàng thông qua các biện pháp như chuyển đổi quy trình kinh doanh, quản lý nhân sự tối ưu, Lựa chọn mô hình vận hành và phân phối thích hợp, Tối ưu hóa các kênh giao dịch. Và cuối cùng cần Tăng tốc độ niêm yết của các NH trong hệ thống. Bên cạnh đó, các tác giả cũng khuyến nghị với cơ quan nhà nước như cần tăng cường quản lý hoạt động phi tín dụng của ngân hàng hay tăng cường quản lý cạnh tranh trong khu vực ngân hàng, và tiếp tục đẩy mạnh tái cấu trúc ngân hàng.

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THEME 3:
INNOVATION, TECHNOLOGY

GEOGRAPHIC LOCATION AND CAPITAL STRUCTURE: EVIDENCE FROM INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND TRANSPORTATION ACCESS

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Abstract

Using the data on the information technology and opening of airports, we attempt to provide robust evidence of the relationship between geographic location and capital structure. With a sample of 572 Vietnamese listed companies from 2000 to 2021 with 8192 firm-year observations, our analyses indicate that there is a significant positive relationship between geographical distance and capital structure. Average firms in Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh City, which are the two biggest financial centers, have about two to three percent lower liabilities-to-assets and debt-to-assets ratios than the others. Besides, the average enterprises in one of the five metropolitan cities - Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, Hai Phong, Can Tho, Da Nang - also have about two-percent lower leverage ratios than their counterparts in provinces. If the distance in kilometers from the firm location to Hanoi or Ho Chi Minh City is used as the measure of geographic location, the analysis still shows robust evidence. Importantly, firms with higher information technology levels have lower location effects than the others, and the introduction of airports reduces the difference in leverage between distant firms and central firms.

Keyword: *Firm location, geographical effect, capital structure, leverage, Vietnam*

THE VALUE OF BALLOON FESTIVAL CULTURE AND ECONOMIC PROSPERITY IN BRISTOL

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Abstract

Cultural and artistic values significantly impact society's standards, lifestyles, and ethics. They also contribute to a nation's economy and overall well-being. This article explores the cultural value of the hot air balloon festival in Bristol, UK, to examine its impact on the city's economy and employment opportunities. A survey of 320 people in Bristol was conducted, analyzing responses and highlighting the reasons why top UK universities like the Russell Group attract national and international students. The festival's cultural significance is evident in the city's progress in various fields and employment opportunities. Ultimately, a striking feature that I can make the point of is explaining the reason why the top UK universities of the Russell Group related to the Balloon Festival can always get the crowned interest of national and international students.

Keywords: *Bristol, economy, hot-air balloon festival, occupation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The positive values that art brings, including festivals, have been studied by many scholars for a long time. Specifically, the values can be named as promoting the reputation of destinations, bringing about bilateral partner relations values the sustainable method between countries, and simultaneously, bringing many valuable commercial opportunities to localities. The cultural and artistic value of the festival not only creates a transformative movement in all aspects but even promotes the urbanization process (Dovey and Sandercock, 2002). Christophers (2008) elaborates the interrelationship between art and culture has the purpose of place boosterism. With the claims from those scholars, the questions revolved around the topic "How does the cultural and artistic value of the festival impact local development?" has never lost its attraction to research.

In 2023, the Sunday Times paper named Bristol the most desirable to-live city in the UK (Charlie, 2023). With a rich cultural diversity, it is undeniable that Bristol is an ancient metropolitan city that attracts thousands of overseas students or tourists. Furthermore, the Balloon Festival in Bristol has also become a focal point for not only city dwellers but also international tourists to experience this extraordinary culture, which leverages Bristol's tourism. Thus, indirectly contributing to the remarkable development of the city's economy. *"Bristol's economy ranks among the most prosperous in England. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Bristol was worth an estimated £17 billion"* (The ONS, 2020).

On account of the success of Bristol's economy related to Balloon festival culture, it motivates this paper to deeply research the value of Bristol's balloon festival brings to the significant economy thriving. In this study paper, this research aims to present the relationship between the value of Bristol Balloon Fiesta and the development of this destination's economy. This research is necessary to implement due to giving the appropriate clarification that festivals play a role more than shaping social identity, but also creating a precondition for promoting prosperity in the life of the community at large.

By conducting this study, it will reveal the mutual relationship between the hot-air balloon culture and the employment situation in Bristol explaining Bristol City Council's success in driving economic growth in the city. The purpose of this article is to emphasise the exploration of the determination of this culture's influence on Bristol's economic performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pamela (2020) stated literature review involves collecting relevant sources, studies, .etc to identify critically the strengths and recognise the gaps with the aim of providing a comprehensive report.

Turning to the main topic of this article, a few studies have been mentioned but most of the economic or festival sectors are concentrated. Notwithstanding, surprisingly, the topic of delving into the correlation between the value of the hot air balloon festival and its impact on the economy of the city of Bristol has not yet been deployed study so far.

Particularly, recently, Diane and Marion (2010) indicated the contribution of festival tourism to sustainable local economic development by statistical data based on the collected feedback to conclude that festivals can have potential for sustainable local economic development opportunities, but those opportunities are often untapped. Regardless, this report evaluates festivals around the world as a whole rather than studying a festival or a city like Bristol.

Besides, Taylor et al. (2016) conducted a study on the economic and cultural value of the design-led sector by collecting data from design companies in the Bristol and Bath region. This is an advantage of this research paper when choosing the city of Bristol as the research and social culture location. Nevertheless, instead of focusing on the hot air balloon festival, the article studies several other festivals.

“Cultural tourism and socio-economic regeneration of rural communities: the Apo festival of Bono Takyiman, Ghana” published the first in 2020 by the research author - Kofi Poku Quan-Baffour. In Kofi's research, the researcher chose Bon Tayiman as the location for qualitative-ethnographic research on the Apo festival taking place annually. By combining interviews and participant observation, arguments are made about the positive impacts of this local festival on the social economic development of this Municipality. The article is highly appreciated because the research is based on observation of research participants and an overall assessment to make recommendations for local authorities on improvements in cultural tourism to contribute to improving living standards. social living. The limitation of the author's research is that due to the nature of this cultural festival with few participants, the assessment cannot be applied to all festivals in Ghana. Besides, the characteristics of the two festivals are also dissimilar.

Recently, Markéta and Josef published a research paper about Balloon Tourism in 2022. Their paper covers the hot air balloon tourism industry extensively and provides figures for its potential development. this travel. On the other hand, this article does not focus on the effect of festivals on Bristol's employment rate.

Dean and Eduardo (2022) studied the economic impact of Mexico during the specific period of Catholic patron saint day festivals. Dean and Eduardo have newer findings than research articles on festivals affecting the economy, such as pointing out the value of festivals affecting the agricultural sector and the negative impacts of holidays. for agricultural productivity, household income and structural transition. Using data from the Encyclopedia of Municipalities in Mexico data source to support research, the paper could illustrate the understanding of readers. On the other hand, because the nature of the festival involves religious issues Catholic Saints' Day festivals are also held in different cities. Consequently, the limitation of the paper is unable to generalize the impact in terms of positive or negative to apply economic development to all cities in a general way. Along with the economic inequality that occurs between localities, the net impact of the festival on utilities also has a certain ambiguity. Similar to Kofi's (2020) research, there is also a certain difference between the Mexican festivals and Balloon Fiesta.

Jordan (2022) explores the correspondence between art festivals and economic development. By contextualising Scotland's Orkney Isles with an interviewing process, which the duration took 42-83 minutes and divided into 3 separate interviewee groups (Councils, Residents, and festival interviewees) Jordan's paper has provided findings with relevance to the relationship between the value of art festivals and its impact to economic development in the rural area. By and large, the research article accommodated an insight report influencing factors of the festival towards economics in the Orkney Islands. However, the article would be more comprehensive if there were no management and cultural differences between the cities of Bristol and Scotland. Because of this difference, the study will only be able to evaluate in detail at a specific location, which can not apply more than various places.

Combining all the shortcomings of these aforementioned investigations, this study was determined to make comprehensive research also practical for readers.

3. METHODOLOGY

In order to offer the most objective and quality research that is optimized in terms of time the quantitative method with the survey strategy is determined for this article. Quantitative research is a strategy for quantifying problems by providing numerical data or information that is highly likely to be turned into usable statistics (Shannon and Christina, 2018). Simultaneously, Polit and Beck (2012) also elaborated on this method to quantify categories, attitudes, standpoints, actions, and other factors that have been defined. Plus, from Choy's perspective (2014), the quantitative method can be considered objective accessibility since the particular quantity of data will be involved in the valid measurements, and universal generalization outcomes, so this strategy is prospective for explaining certain cases. Regarding all these aforementioned noteworthy positive aspects, this methodology was oriented as an effortless way to clarify or apply statistical techniques, which protect the integrity of the investigation (Shannon and Christina, 2018). The quantitative method will assist in showing

the effects of the hot air balloon festival on the occupation of Bristol residents. Simultaneously, referring to the economic impact in certain representative industrial sectors of the city of Bristol. In addition to the quantitative method concentrated on in this article, to robust the quality, there is also reference supplementation to arguments and evidence from other qualitative articles and studies.

Furthermore, the probability sampling method gives the objective result due to the simple experiment of random participants participating in the investigation that contributes to the effectiveness and feasibility of the research. The questionnaire is designed with 12 questions and is specifically divided into 2 distinct parts, including 6 questions about the balloon festival involved in the dweller's occupation and 6 questions about the Balloon festival's impact on other industry sectors. The design of the questionnaire was closely aligned with the report's aim to evaluate the cultural value Bristol's hot air balloon festival plays in the city's economic promotion.

The topic of research on artistic and cultural values in Bristol has received the crowned attention, that's why 320 people living in and studying abroad in Bristol city randomly participated to find out objectively and effectively. Although the quantity is not too much, it also ensures the quality of this research paper.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. The correlation between the hot air balloon festival and employment in Bristol.

Figure 1: The percentage of each sector's occupations in Bristol can be created by the hot-air balloon festival (Unit: People)

Source: Author's statistics

Figure 1 is demonstrating the percentage of each sector's jobs that are potentially created regarding Bristol's Balloon Festival. It is noticeable that the percentage of jobs in different industries that can be created is very high, most of which account for over 60% or more such as Education, Hospitality, Manufacturing, etc. In detail, the number of people choosing the Manufacturing industry with a job creation rate of 90% - 100% is the highest out of 320 survey participants, which is 222 out of 320 individuals in Bristol. On the contrary, it can also be seen that jobs in the Administrative and support service field receive only 71 options out of 320 individuals, but the job creation rate in this industry is from 30% to 40%, and they receive more options, which is 107 options. By and large, it can be concluded job opportunities in the city of Bristol during the Balloon Festival are highly likely.

Based on the figures illustrated in Figure 1, it is possible to clearly assess the career opportunities in the listed fields, which are typically focused on expanding in order to attract human resources. People living in the city of Bristol are empowered to search for jobs in different suitable industries, especially jobs that become available during the hot air balloon festival in Bristol. Evidence can be found in Haley Morris (2016), who is a Senior Manager at Cordant People Bristol, specialising in general recruitment insisting Bristol has one of the most successful job markets in the UK today, while the South West is leading the way in terms of the number of jobs available and the number of firms looking to take on staff. Furthermore, 29,000 available jobs for supporting the Bristol hot air balloon festival event in 2018 were generated in this city (Marvin, 2018). The figures are argued can be inferred as jobs in sectors are expanded, more staff are recruited, which supports the reduction of Bristol's unemployment rate. Limiting negative impacts on economic development policies or business operations at enterprises, organizations and corporations. In other words, plays a role in driving the economy to thrive in this livable urban city.

Figure 2: The potential percentages of unemployment rate in Bristol when the Balloon festival is organised (Unit: Percentage)

Source: Author's investigation

Turning to Figure 2, this figure is shown the potential unemployment rate's proportions involved in the organization of the Balloon Festival in Bristol. It is apparently seen that the unemployment rate ranges from 90% - 100% not getting a choice. Compared to the 30% - 40% unemployment rate are able to happen in Bristol, showing that the selection rate is the difference between two completely opposite rates, which are 33% and 0%, respectively. For the most part, the percentage of options focuses only on those with unemployment rates below 50%. Therefore, when the Balloon festival is held, the professions open up more career opportunities, so the unemployment rate in the city of Bristol happens to be relatively low.

The city of Bristol is not only famous for its architecture, art, culture and history but is also known as having one of the lowest unemployment rates in the country (Churchill, 2017). According to the latest report by JSNA Health and Wellbeing Profile (2023), the unemployment rate for Bristol was 3.1% in the twelve months ending December 2022, lower than the Great Britain average. It can be seen that unemployment in Bristol is not a concern in the UK. Compared with the unemployment rate when the hot air balloon event took place in Bristol was surveyed, the responses were quite reasonable about the employment situation in Bristol, with the unemployment rate option from 30% - 40% being the most chosen. Therefore, it can be assessed that, with the results from Figure 1 combined with Figure 2, the hot air balloon event helps to promote more job opportunities in different fields, to help businesses can own possessing abundant human resources, focusing on developing business orientations. Contributing to reducing the unemployment rate, which is one of the most concerning problems that most countries are facing, including Vietnam, but also contributing to the rapid economic prosperity of the young city - Bristol.

Figure 3: Percentage of career opportunities expanded by Bristol City Council involved in the Balloon festival (Unit: Percentage)

Source: Author's report

As Figure 3 has illustrated the proportions of career opportunities encouraged regarding the Balloon Festival by the Bristol City Council. It is easy to notice the percentage of people who chose the answer "Yes" prevail over the answer "No", which is nearly 80% for the former and 20% for the latter. Therefore, there is a basis to draw the conclusion that Bristol City

Council certainly offers attractive policies to support employment as well as policies for attracting human resources when the hot air balloon event is held.

Employment support policies promoted by Bristol City Council are encouraged to expand remarkably. Bristol City Council (2020) reported Bristol's visitor economy is significant, with visitor-related spending estimated at nearly £1.2bn in 2019, and responsible for around 24,000 jobs annually. It can be presumed that based on the popular hot air balloon event taking place in the city of Bristol, which is a festival for showcasing culture to tourists, it also creates career opportunities for Bristol's residents. This is to limit the unemployment rate of Bristol, which explains the prosperity in the financial situation in this metropolis. In order to reduce unemployment, the government will use an expansionary fiscal policy, thereby lowering tax rates and increasing government spending (Simon and Patrick, 2021). Not only the Bristol Council applied to enact this policy but also the UK government, which is one of the typical policies clearly clarify low the unemployment rate in Bristol. Bristol residents can find a wealth of career opportunities and business-oriented businesses, local area can control social issues, development policy and economic performance. Finally, the city of Bristol attracts many talented people to help contribute to a sustainable economy.

Combining Figure 1+2+3, it can be inferred that the cultural and artistic value of Bristol Balloon Fiesta brings many job opportunities for people. To serve the organization of the hot air balloon festival, there is not only the participation and hosting of local authorities but also business activities operated by enterprises such as food business, entertainment activities, Balloon production, transportation public services and so on. Most of these types of businesses are temporary, taking place over a short period. Therefore, businesses will generate more part-time or full-time employment opportunities for job seekers. When job opportunities are generated in a large number equivalent to the unemployment rate is not a concern problem. Guaranteed workforce employment also creates sustainability and increases residents' income. Luiza and her scholars (2023) mentioned that local development opportunities, and social life including employment opportunities have been expanded distinctly under the impact of cultural festivals. Local businessmen and exhibitors appreciate this impact and on that basis expand the scale of their business operations as well as increase the number of employees. Gibson et al., (2010) stated that festivals as a "hybrid affair", intertwining culture and economics into one. Daka et al., (2021) corroborated the argument that the opportunities for job creation are facilitated by cultural ceremonies and, the labour force demands resources. Both business owners and ministries encourage expansion of employment policies, sectors that employ skilled and semi-skilled workers from the festival are also encouraged to deploy recruitment to achieve the goal of brobusting the country's employment level. The need for a secure life is satisfied, and the demands of consumption and exchange of goods are also promoted. The labour market becomes more vibrant. Creating increased cash flows and international investment capital from strategic partners directly boosts high performance in economic growth. The local cultural festival acts as a platform for partnership creation to strengthen the diplomacy of nations (Phiri, 2021). It can be argued that this hot air balloon festival is a direct bridge to local economic growth.

4.2. The influence of balloon festivals on the performance of industry sectors.

Figure 4: The activities in which local culture is showcased in Bristol's hot air balloon festival (Unit: People)

Source: Author's preparation

According to Figure 4 is about how Bristol's local culture can be showcased during the hot air balloon festival. The statistics show that people's choice of food options promoted by restaurants/ hotels received the most responses from 312 survey respondents compared to other options. Options such as “Souvenirs printed with more typical Bristol city images”, “Information about the city also appears a lot at the airport, station, stadium” and “Newspapers, radios, and social media outlets spread the news about the festival” get an equal number of choices. Specifically, the number of people selected respectively was 287, 277 and 251 out of 320 people randomly surveyed, respectively. Thus, It can also be assessed that the tourism industry in Bristol is focused on promoting activities when the hot air balloon festival event in this city takes place.

From Figure 4 it can be seen that the cultural showcase in Bristol is of strong interest, which can also refer that the tourism industry in Bristol has been operating stably. It can be judged that the tourism sector has developed policies to effectively promote culture, which also has a great impact on the economy in Bristol. Ballard (2019) reported total tourism-supported turnover is worth an estimated £1.85bn to Bristol with over 21,650 jobs. This proves that the economic performance in Bristol is apparently flourishing partly based on the tourism policy work for the Hot air balloon festival. By expanding good images and information about Bristol during the annual Balloon Festival, it attracts a lot of domestic and international visitors travel around a year. The revenues, as well as profits of the tourism industry, provide economic leverage in Bristol to be able to develop sustainably but rapidly. In other words, the tourism industry plays a crucial role in Bristol's economic prosperity, especially during the Balloon Festival by creating more job positions, building a friendly and bustling image for Bristol and also a tool to let Bristol's economy rocket.

Figure 5: Innovations in Bristol education based on hot air balloon event (Unit: People).

Source: Author's research

Regarding Figure 5, it is indicated the innovations of Bristol education based on the Balloon Festival. 319 Bristol residents all chose the answer "More international teachers have more job opportunities". Interestingly, this is also the option that accounts for the highest total compared to the other options. Furthermore, the option "Increased recognition of Russell Group's university members" is also worth noting, receiving 299 choices, approximately as high as the option mentioned above. In addition, the typical remaining options such as "The curriculum has also been improved" or "The remuneration policies for lecturers are more attractive" did not receive many choices. On that account, education in Bristol has the positive improvements of the hot air balloon festival when it attracts many international teachers to work and contribute to the educational development of this city as well as increasing the prestige of the world-leading universities of the Russell Group, such as the University of Bristol.

According to Ketelaar (2005), the Policy and International Development pathway focuses on the relationship between education policy and practice and international development. According to the data analyzed in the aforementioned Figures, the Balloon Festival is considered to bring endless career opportunities to the workforce as well as the market in Bristol in particular and the UK in general. This set the stage for innovations in education in Bristol. More specifically, not only people living in Bristol are supported with jobs by the City Council, but also international people are also attracted to look for work in this economic market. In education in Bristol, international teachers also have the opportunity to work as teaching and research at schools/universities/colleges in this city. Moreover, thanks to the policy that emphasizes the relationship between education and the development of international exchanges, the enrollment rate of domestic and foreign students has also increased. This is considered a highlighted point, partly contributing to the promotion of sustainable development according to Bristol's orientation. On the one hand, discussing the

level of recognition of the member universities of the Russell Group. Russell Group is a term to refer to a group of leading universities consisting of 24 world-class universities in the United Kingdom similar to the Ivy League in the United Nations of America (David and Wendy, 2015). It can be seen that the prestige of Russell Group universities, is enough to attract students and researchers from all over the world to study. The Russell Group of Universities account for the top eight UK universities among the global 100 best universities as per the Academic Ranking of World Universities. Russell Group graduates make up 61% of the UK workforce (Ashraf, 2023). Furthermore, employers are also positively impressed and give preference to graduates from Russell Group universities. That is a clear explanation of why UK universities belonging to the Russell group are of great interest to people around the globe. alternatively, thanks to the value of the hot air balloon festival in Bristol, information and images about the UK are known more, in which even prestigious UK universities have a positive influence. For instance, in Balloon Festival was taken place in 2022, the Russell Group of University (2023) estimated more than 27,000 students currently studying at the University of Bristol from over 150 countries. Around 25% of students are international in particular and more than 160,000 students from the UK and nearly 90,000 from the rest of the world choose to join the 320,000 students who are already studying at a Russell Group university in general. The collection of such evidence can support to draw the conclusion that the impact of the Balloon Festival is to help promote innovation, job opportunities and prestige in education in Bristol.

Figure 6: Advertising frequency of advertising forms for the Balloon Festival in Bristol (Unit: People)

Source: Author's implementation

Figure 6 is illustrated the advertising frequency of advertising forms for the Balloon Festival in Bristol. It is noticeable that most of the advertising media about the Balloon

Festival is deployed densely. Particularly, the option “Television” received the most votes from other forms of advertising for instance Newspapers or Trivision, which received 211 selcetions out of 320 participants living in Bristol. Moreover, with the implementation of advertising through advertising emails, it seems to be rarer because it is reflected by 86 people who choose to rarely see this form of advertising, which is completely higher than the rarity of other forms of promotional marketing for the Balloon festival. Overall, it is also encountered that the marketing field in the city of Bristol was given a lot of attention when this festival event was held.

One of the outstanding fields that Bristol's modern economy is built on including technology, electronics and aerospace engineering industries is creative media (University of Bristol, 2023). With this statement, it is uncontroversial that marketing and communication are very important in development activities in Bristol. Based on the data analyzed in Figure 6, it is impossible not to see that with the Balloon Festival event, marketing was further boosted. With the festival propaganda campaigns via social networks and traditional marketing (Banner, Roadshow, Newspaper, etc.), the frequency of advertising and marketing forms is deployed densely. It also means that businesses and companies operating in the media segment in Bristol have generated quite large profits by implementing marketing campaigns just for the Balloon festival taking place. Evidently, the fiesta has a huge media impact, with 1,891 billion circulation figures worth nearly £2M in marketing value (Association for Project Management, 2014). From there, it can be seen clearly how the value of Bristol's Balloon Festival significantly affects the profitability of the Marketing industry in particular, and at the same time supports the promotion of Bristol's sustainable economy in general.

Findings have been reported from Figure 4 to Figure 6 about illustrating the influence of Bristol Balloon Fiesta on sectors' performance in this city. Summarize the important main ideas to highlight innovations and the situation of the fields during the festival take place. Shed light on analysis, hot air balloon events were organized, communication activities were promoted extensively and there were advanced innovations in education. Because of these factors, the reputation of Bristol increases the location's recognition on the world map. Sped up the process of economic development by profits obtained from tourist expenses, various types of businesses including cultural advertising are also deployed, flourishing the tourism industry, and increasing goods exchange along with transportation services. Pereira (2021) presented the expenditure for the festival of visitors has accounted for nearly one-third of the total economic and financial revenue of the region. Cultural tourism is observed as a “heritage boom” (Greg, 2018). It means a type of growing both international and domestic travel with a dual purpose stimulating the economics and preserving culture. These operations are constantly upgraded to promote high productivity levels and optimise production processes and regional financial resource allocation, which directly contribute to the regional economy's prosperity. Gibson et al., (2010) declared in several situations, that cultural festivals are implicitly believed to be one of the components with the potential to have a strong impact on economic development strategies. Profitability can be assessed by quantity, but comprehensively considered, it is most obvious to diversify the local economy and maintain economic sustainability in the fluctuations occurring in the market. Furthermore, improvements in local education also make the quality and learning environment in Bristol City the top choice for international students. Commercial economic profits are also partly contributed by financial exchanges obtained from study and living expenses. The culture between countries, integrated by students from

countries around the world, is also a point that not only modernises the society but also creates new business types regarding cultural exchange. Pereira (2021) observed opportunities for those who pursue economics can be found through festivals to share community culture with the broadened world. In fact, the Balloon Hot Air Balloon Festival is to some extent one of the opportunities to rapidly boost Bristol's economy in many aspects.

5. CONCLUSION

In summary, with all the survey and analysis results shown in the Figures above and well-founded arguments, it is possible to clarify the connection between the Bristol Balloon Festival, a popular cultural event in this metropolis area. In addition, some recommendations are made that can be considered such as in terms of new changes in education, the survey did not receive much feedback on the remuneration adjustment policy for lecturers, reflecting that these innovations in education have not been focused on promoting employment rights issues for education workers or the curriculum has not changed related to the Balloon festival culture. Therefore, the solution that can be proposed is to focus on supporting and motivating those who are working in education by giving more rights in remuneration policies and spreading more issues related to Balloon Festival to the curriculum for learners to have a better overview, from which they can apply their practice to provide potential research to support the social promotion. Finally, Bristol can possess an abundant source of talent, which ensures the sustainable development of the city.

The festival supports the sustainable development of the economy in the UK's most liveable city. The cultural value of the Bristol Hot Air Balloon Festival provides career opportunities, generates countless jobs every year and has a noticeable impact on the performance of each industry. Finally, increases Bristol's potential market reputation for employment, investment and social and cultural promotion. Above all, a plausible explanation has been offered for the influence that Russell Group universities have drawn on the prominent interests associated with the Bristol Balloon Festival. Although this article has been prepared, there are still certain shortcomings, so it is hoped that there will be more promising articles to strengthen the thesis. By and large, this article can be evaluated as providing a clear overview of the relationship between the value of the Balloon Festival and economic prosperity in Bristol.

6. LIMITATION

Despite the effort of bringing a comprehensive research paper, the study still contains certain unique limitations. Firstly, conducting research by approaching people living and working in Bristol only provides a partial reason to explain the cultural impact of the hot air balloon festival on the development of the city's economy. Meanwhile, the participants number attended is humble. In other words, the article has not specifically researched other deeper factors of cultural values that influence the economic situation but has only generalized the situation between industries related to festivals. In addition, the article mentions the reasons why Russell Group universities attract students to study, but the audience participating in the article's research is not specifically about students. This may affect the difference between the findings achieved and the research objectives of the study. Owing to limitations in my research, it is necessary for this paper to be studied thoroughly further by scholars as well as researchers.

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APPENDIX

QUESTIONNAIRE

I am Le Minh Ngoc, currently working at Banking Academy, Vietnam. I am doing research on the cultural value of the hot air balloon festival and the thriving economy of the city of Bristol. The purpose of this study is to clarify the effects of hot air balloon festivals on employment while also influencing the performances of industry sectors in Bristol.

It will be my pleasure to receive your useful contribution by following the instructions of the questions are answering questions in clear detail, ticking “☑” as the most suitable alternative.

Completing will only take you a couple of minutes. I guarantee your feedback will be kept anonymous.

Your Division/ Unit:.....

I. The correlation between the hot air balloon festival and employment in Bristol.

1. What is your current salary fluctuation per month?

- Less than £1,000
- £1,000 - £2,000
- £2,500 - £3,000
- £3,500 - £4,000
- £4,500 - £5,000
- Up to £5,000

2. Does the hot air balloon festival help you increase your productivity at work?

- Yes
- No

3. Does your company have policies to support employees when the hot air balloon festival takes place?

- Yes
- No

4. Rate the percentage of jobs in Bristol that potentially the festival creates in each sector?

	10%-20%	30%-40%	50%-60%	70%-80%	90%-100%
Education					
Hospitality					
Health					
Communications					
Scientific and technical					

Administrative and support services

Public administration and defence

Transportation and storage

Manufacturing

Financial and insurance

5. In your opinion, what is the possible unemployment rate in Bristol when the event takes place?

- 10%-20%
- 30%-40%
- 50%-60%
- 70%-80%
- 90%-100%

6. Whether your Bristol City Council opens up many job opportunities when the event takes place?

- Yes
- No

II. The influence of balloon festivals on the performance of industry sectors.

1. Do you think the airfare to Bristol is increased by the hot air balloon festival?

- Yes
- No

2. How your culture can be showcased in the hot air balloon event?

- Restaurants/hotels promote local cuisine more
- Souvenirs printed with more typical Bristol city images
- Newspapers, radios, and social media outlets spread the news about the festival
- Other festivals/fairs are also implemented
- Music concerts are also promoted
- Schools/ Universities/ Colleges open more international cooperative and exchange activities
- Information about the city also appears a lot at the airport, station, stadium
- Museums, art places offer more discounts and preferential policies for visitors
- Others

3. In your opinion, will the environmental sanitation workers face work pressure when the event takes place?

- Yes
- No

4. What improvements has the medical industry in Bristol made when the hot air balloon

festival took place?

- More imported high-tech medical equipment
- Recruit more medical job positions
- Remuneration and employment policies for medical staff become more attractive
- The salary of medical staff is increased
- The working frequency of medical staff becomes dense
- Patient care medical services are also focused and upgraded
- Develop more hospitals/clinics
- The training program for medical staff has also been renewed
- Disease prevention and emergency measures have also been reinforced
- Others

5. What innovations have occurred in Bristol's education based on the hot air balloon festival?

- The class schedule becomes more flexible
- More international teachers have more job opportunities
- The curriculum has also been improved
- Students/College students have the opportunity to participate in more outdoor activities
- The remuneration policies for lecturers are also more attractive
- Teacher absenteeism has dropped
- The ratio of national and international students/university students increases
- Increased recognition of Russell Group member universities
- Others

6. Rate the frequency of advertising in Bristol launching when the event takes place?

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Banner					
Billboard					
Flyers					
Advertising reels on social media					
Advertising emails					
Trivision					
Roadshow					
Newspapers					
Television					
Radio					

THANK YOU SO MUCH!

DIGITAL SERVICES TAX IN THE UK, AUSTRIA AND IMPLICATIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

The digital services tax (DST) is a tax on the revenue of certain digital companies. The study is based on the following research questions: (1) What are the e-tax services offered by the tax authorities in UK and Austria;(2) How are these services used by taxpayers in UK and Austria?. The research will provide an overview of the digital services tax (DST), analyze and assess the impact of DST implementation from many perspectives, including government, business, and end users, by contrasting it with the appropriate tax legislation suggested by Adam Smith. The first perspective is the tax revenue perspective. The DST is expected to generate a significant amount of tax revenue for the government. The tax revenue generated from the DST will be used to finance the government's expenditure on public services and infrastructure. Finally, the authors want to make some recommendations for Vietnam to develop a sustainable economy, especially in taxation of the digital and innovation sectors.

Keywords: Tax, digital services tax, the UK, Austria

1 INTRODUCTION

Taxation can have a notable impact on advancing sustainable growth and development. Sustainable growth denotes economic advancement that not only fosters prosperity but also considers the enduring well-being of the environment, society, and the economy. It can effect on the sustainable of economy by enviromental taxation, incentive tax policy for sustainable development, resorces conservation, renewable energy supporting and so on. In this study, authors would like to focus on the digital services tax (DST), which has become a topic of great interest in the global tax landscape, driven by the need to address the challenges posed by the rapidly evolving digital economy. Multinational companies (MNCs) operating digital platforms have raised concerns about new profit tax bases and the allocation of taxing rights with regard to MNC profits. In light of these challenges, proactive legislative proposals have emerged from the UK government, the European Commission (EC), and various European national governments, emphasizing the need for long-term strategies to reform international business income taxation (Cui, 2019).

The digital economy, characterized by advanced information technology and the dominance of multinational tech giants, has outpaced existing tax regulations and legislation. This disparity necessitates a new tax regime that not only captures the value contributed by users of digital platforms but also mitigates tax evasion. The underlying rationale behind the DST is to ensure that digital companies bear their fair share of taxes in the countries where

they generate revenue. DST seeks to tackle issues related to tax evasion by large multinational technology companies, striving to establish a fair competition environment for local businesses that might face disadvantages when competing against these digital giants. Therefore, DST becomes a very important factor in building a sustainable economy, especially in the context of the boom of technology and innovation companies.

The primary objective of this article is to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the implementation of the digital services tax (DST). This evaluation will primarily focus on examining the principles underlying DST and will utilize the cases of the United Kingdom (UK) and Austria as key examples for analysis. By delving into these cases, we aim to gain valuable insights into the impact of DST implementation on various stakeholders, including the government, businesses, and end customers. To provide a robust assessment, we will compare the implications of DST with the principles of proper tax legislation proposed by Adam Smith, a renowned economist.

By considering Adam Smith's taxation canons, policymakers can assess the effectiveness and fairness of DST implementation and explore avenues for establishing a balanced and efficient tax system in the digital era. From the evaluation and analysis of DST implementation in the UK and Austria, valuable lessons and experiences can be derived to inform Vietnam's approach to digital services taxation.

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a synthesis and comparative approach to evaluate the implementation of digital services tax (DST). The methodology involves a comprehensive examination of the principles underlying DST and utilizes the cases of the United Kingdom (UK) and Austria as key examples for analysis.

To begin, a thorough review of relevant literature, including scholarly publications and government reports, was conducted to gather a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. This step enabled the collection of a wide range of information related to digital services taxation, its challenges, and its implications.

Next, a synthesis process was employed to organize and integrate the collected data, identifying key themes, trends, and patterns. The synthesis allowed for the development of a coherent overview of digital services taxation, including its rationale, objectives, and potential impacts on stakeholders.

Furthermore, a comparative analysis was conducted to examine the similarities and differences between the implementation of DST in the UK and Austria. This analysis considered various aspects, such as the scope of the tax, tax rates, targeted sectors, and revenue projections. The aim was to gain insights into the effectiveness and implications of DST implementation in different contexts.

Additionally, the study incorporates the principles of proper tax legislation proposed by Adam Smith, a renowned economist, as a framework for evaluating the fairness and efficiency of DST implementation. By considering these canons of taxation, the study assesses the alignment of DST with fundamental principles of taxation.

The findings from the synthesis, comparative analysis, and evaluation of DST implementation in the UK and Austria will provide valuable insights into the impact of digital services taxation on various stakeholders, including governments, businesses, and consumers. These insights will inform the formulation of recommendations and lessons learned for Vietnam's approach to digital services taxation.

Through this research methodology, a comprehensive evaluation of DST implementation is achieved, combining the synthesis of information from diverse sources, comparative analysis, and the application of established tax principles. This approach enables a holistic understanding of the challenges and implications of DST, contributing to the existing body of knowledge on digital services taxation.

3 AN EVALUATION OF DIGITAL SERVICES TAX IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Overview of digital services taxation

Digital services tax is a tax on revenue from digital services collected from digital users in a country with a specific tax rate. The rationale of the digital services tax derives from the growing but more sophisticated digital economy worldwide. In addition to the opportunities, the digital economy also challenges tax authorities, policymakers, and business managers as the current tax regime and legislation cannot keep up with digital advances. This leads to the need for a new tax regime with the emergence of information technology while preventing loopholes for companies to evade tax on corporate profits (Lowry, 2019; Lips, 2019).

Just as tax policies in any economic sector, digital taxes are evaluated against the criteria of a sound tax system proposed by Adam Smith. These criteria are basic principles when designing digital taxation.

According to Adam Smith (1937), a complete tax system should include the following characteristics, known as the four taxation canons. First, the canon of equality means that tax liability must be distributed fairly, and the tax payable is proportional to the taxpayer's income. In other words, people who are more able to pay must pay higher taxes. Second, the canon of certainty implies that whichever relates to the tax liability, such as time of tax payment, amount of tax paid, etc., must be clear and transparent. Certainty also implies a fair and transparent tax-levying authority. Third, the canon of economy mentions that the cost of collecting taxes ought to be as minimum as possible. Costs incurred during the tax filings process, such as administrative costs or any potential deferring tax assessment costs, should be eliminated. Finally, the canon of convenience states that taxes should be levied and collected in a reasonable, trouble-free manner for both the governing authorities and taxpayers.

3.2 Digital services tax in the UK

Effective after April 2020, The Digital Service Tax in the UK applies to businesses providing digital services with global sales of over £500m and domestic sales to UK customers of over £25m. According to the levy, digital services revenues include the revenues from services provision of internet search engines, social media, or online marketplace platforms. Tech giants such as Google or Amazon are more eligible for this tax than traditional small and medium-sized enterprises (House of Commons, 2020; HMRC, 2019; Congressional Research Service, 2019).

From the UK government's perspective, with a 2% tax imposed on the revenues of businesses' digital services, DST is supposed to solve a current issue in corporate taxation. The existing regulations on corporate tax have lacked supervision on businesses operating in the digital economy. Many digital businesses have gained much value from the interaction with users, which creates confusion between where value is created and where profits should be taxed. These values are also being omitted from the current tax frameworks in many countries, as profits are not just distributed in one country. DST will, therefore, ensure that the large multinationals operating in the digital sector have equal contributions to the public service system (HMRC, 2019). This is in line with the canon of equality by Adam Smith, as the burden of taxation should be fairly allocated among taxpayers.

Regarding the impact, it can be seen that DST will have a direct impact on the UK government budget. On the revenue side, according to data from the Treasury (2019), the tax measure is expected to raise over 400 million pounds (approximately 512 million dollars) per year. In return, to maintain long-term efficiency, a large amount of the Exchequer's budget is expected to incur, as shown in the following table.

Table 1. Summary of Projected budget for DST implementation in the UK

2019 to 2020	2020 to 2021	2021 to 2022	2022 to 2023	2023 to 2024	2024 to 2025
+70	+280	+390	+425	+465	+515

Source: HM Treasury (2019)

DST also presents a big challenge for UK policymakers when the inherent challenges of taxation on a revenue basis remain, such as double taxation risk. This is because EU competition rules still remain effective during the Brexit transition until the end of 2020,

making UK businesses to comply with digital tax and cannot be offset against corporation tax (Rukundo, 2020).

Moreover, the unilateral increase of DST implementation in the absence of an international consensus on appropriate DST mechanisms will lead to many concerns. For example, the United States has launched an investigation of a similar measure by the French government, which could raise suspicions about a tariff imposition. And the United States is likely to make a similar move with the British government, especially since the UK is an important market for large US tech businesses (Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, 2019).

The UK's vision of DST also motivates governments of other countries such as Spain, Austria, Mexico, etc., to propose similar DST measures actively. This, therefore, will add more complexity in an increasingly sophisticated tax environment (Bunn, 2020).

From corporates' perspectives, it is evident that businesses and multinational corporations subject to DST will be directly and significantly impacted, as their revenues derived from UK users of online search engines, social networks, or online marketplaces will be taxed.

Firstly, DST imposed will put tech companies in a higher tax burden. Just Eat, a UK-based tech provider of food-ordering services, has estimated that about £70m will be imposed in the first year of DST implementation, and hundreds of millions of pounds will be deducted from the company's revenue for the next several years (Bradshaw, 2020). In terms of costs, besides the comparatively high corporate tax payments in the UK (Figure 2), businesses will also face ongoing costs to maintain DST compliance, such as costs of recordkeeping and managing UK user-related revenues or costs relating to making payments to the Treasury. One-off costs such as familiarization with DST are also taken into account (BDO, 2020); This goes against Adam Smith's canon of efficiency as the cost involved in tax filing should be as low as possible.

Figure 1. The UK's top corporate tax rate comparison

Source: Deloitte (2020)

Second, the emergence of DST will cause technology companies to lose their competitive advantage over both domestic and overseas. In the free market, digital-based businesses can reasonably price their products and services. However, when tech platforms are affected by DST, businesses are no longer operating in an economic system where their prices are determined by unrestricted competition among firms (Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, 2019; BDO, 2020)

As a result, some platforms will seek solutions to eliminate DST, and one of which is to pass the **DST liability onto third-party traders** through a fee increase. The following examples from major global tech companies will explain this more clearly.

In response to the new tax changes, Apple has announced a price adjustment notice designed to offset DST in the UK since early September 2020. Specifically, for its corporate customers, Apple will charge an additional 2% VAT (value-added tax) on top of an existing 20% VAT rate to pay the government before distributing the remainder to the company itself and its developers. This tax applies to all purchases on the App Store (Apple, 2020).

Similarly, as of September 2020, Amazon, an online marketplace where sellers of goods and services and third-party customers interact through an online platform, has transferred 2% of DST to its merchants. According to Amazon, fees such as Referral fees, FBA (Fulfillment by Amazon) fees, MCF fees, and storage fees will rise 2% due to the newly passed legislation and reflect the costs incurred (Amazon, 2020).

Google also has the same action as its advertisers and partners. In its official statement, Google mentioned that starting from November 2020, the company would charge a 2% of DST Fees on invoices or statements for advertising services in the UK where the fees apply. The rationale of this new cost, according to the company, was because of the significant rise in complexity and the cost for compliance of tax regulations. Digital advertisers can also see the new tax amount on the 'Transactions' section of their Ads accounts. Also, how DST fees are charged depends on how the advertisers make payments. If the advertiser pays either automatically or via monthly invoicing, DST fees will be charged to the account's budget. For example, they will be billed a £102 invoice in which £100 is an advertising budget and £2 of digital services tax. In the case of manual payment, DST fees will be charged after the payment is completed, and Google will automatically deduct the fees on the upcoming prepayment (Google, 2020).

In terms of impact, the newly introduced DST may affect businesses' advertising tactics. Advertisers will have to consider keeping their current budget and accepting additional fees, or will reduce their budget to include DST. Moreover, they will have to consider an additional 2% DST fee when calculating ROI, especially when it can significantly affect business' profit margin in big events like Black Friday, Boxing Day if the business is heavily dependent on Google Ads for sales (Lai, 2020; Skipper, 2020) .

For Amazon, as its small-sized sellers are third parties affected by DST, this is clearly an overwhelming influence. Amazon clearly avoids tax liability on the sales from online marketplaces and is placing its sellers on an adverse tax burden, as most Amazon sellers would prefer a low-cost and popular technical platform to assist their profit maximization

(MacDonnell, 2019). This goes against the canon of convenience when taxes are levied in an unreasonable manner for the taxpayers.

3.3 Similarities and Differences in Digital Taxation between the UK and Canada

A comparative analysis of Canada's digital services tax with that of the UK was conducted by Wei Cui (2019). The study aimed to examine and compare the approaches taken by these countries in implementing digital services taxes.

The comparison and analysis between Canada and the UK in terms of their proposed Digital Services Tax (DST) reveal several remarkable aspects and potential implications. First, the Canadian DST is broader in scope compared to its UK and French counterparts, covering a wider range of digital services revenue. Surprisingly, this broader scope has not garnered much attention or opposition. The usual critics of DSTs have reused their accusations against the Canadian DST without considering the specific differences.

Second, the DSTA (Digital Services Tax Act) in Canada raises important questions about DST design, particularly regarding the taxation of business-to-business and social media platforms. These questions go beyond technical aspects and require a debate on the purpose of DSTs. However, such a debate has not taken place in Canada.

Third, despite the presence of larger and more complex trade disputes globally, the global tax profession remains fixated on the trade issues generated by DSTs. This separation of international taxation from larger economic realities may explain why global tax cooperation seems to unite the profession more than anything else.

The predictions for the Canadian DST's implications in 2022 did not align with the observations. While it was expected that the broader scope of the Canadian DST would provoke a strong backlash, no significant opposition emerged. Additionally, the participation of businesses and industry associations in the DST consultations did not increase compared to the UK DST. This lack of response could be attributed to various factors, such as a lack of enthusiasm for the DST from the Canadian government, the DST not representing a significant new cost for many multinational corporations (MNCs), or poor advice leading some MNCs to misunderstand the DST's target.

The misinformation campaign by DST opponents may have contributed to the misconceptions surrounding the Canadian DST. The accusations of discrimination made against the Canadian DST by industry lobbies and the U.S. government display a lack of understanding of its broader scope and potential impact on Canadian and non-U.S. companies operating in the digital space.

The DSTA introduces new policy and legal issues. The broader tax base of the Canadian DST includes revenue from online marketplaces, online advertising, and social media services. However, determining what constitutes a "social media platform" based on its main purpose raises uncertainties and potential disputes. The UK's approach to the "main purpose" test provides some guidance but may not be sufficient for taxpayers and courts. The DSTA also requires legal refinements, such as excluding fees representing significant marginal costs from digital services revenue.

The DSTA's approach to sourcing revenue on a per-transaction basis aims to reduce the likelihood of double taxation and presents a simpler and more effective design compared to the UK DST. However, challenges remain in determining the specific countries in which foreign users are located.

Despite the intellectual interest in the DSTA, there is uncertainty regarding its enactment in Canada. The potential gains from the DST may be outweighed by the risk of losing favor with the US and the overall climate of protectionism. The level of domestic political support or pressure for the DST is unclear, and there is limited evidence of strong public sentiment regarding the perceived unfairness of foreign MNCs not paying their fair share of taxes in Canada.

3.4 Digital services tax in the Austria

Like the UK, Austria officially levied the digital service tax in January 2020 at a 5% tax rate. This tax will apply to online advertising revenue by digital advertising service providers in Austria. Digital advertising businesses with global revenues of over €750 million (about \$ 840 million) and Austrian revenues of over €25 million (about \$28 million) will be targeted for DST. The revenues for DST assessment in Austria are limited to online advertising revenues only, not revenues from search engines or online marketplaces. Therefore, DST in Austria is more like a Digital Advertising Tax as its effective scope is smaller than that of the UK.

From the government's perspective, the establishment and adoption of DST will make Austrian taxation on the advertising industry more transparent. Since the 2000s, traditional advertising businesses have been levied a 5% tax on their revenues derived from advertising activities such as TV commercials, newspaper ads, or other forms of advertising via mail, phone, and telegram. Online advertising was not much developed and had an insignificant impact at the time, so it had not been listed in the category of assessed advertising services for taxation purposes. However, with the development of the digital economy, where digital services have contributed a large part, the Austrian government has recognized the inadequacy and lack of advertising taxes on digital activities revenue. Therefore, by including revenues from online advertising platforms such as search engine advertising, banner advertising, and other comparable advertising, the newly introduced DST will help the Austria government supervise and manage more comprehensively, level the playing field, and promote fairness between traditional advertisers and online advertisers about tax liability (Bunn, et al., 2020; Bundesministerium für Finanzen, 2020).

Like other governments, the tax revenues of the Austrian government will also increase as a result of the newly introduced tax. It is expected that DST will help the government collect an additional €25 million (approximately \$28 million) in 2020, and by 2023 the figure will reach €34 million (approximately \$38 million) (Figure 3). By 2023, revenues from DST will contribute up to 33% of total corporate income tax revenue in Austria (Bunn, Asen and Enache, 2020; Bundesministerium für Finanzen, 2020).

Table 2. Estimation of revenues from DST implementation in Austria

FY	REVENUE (MILLION €)
2020	+25
2021	+28
2022	+31
2023	+34

Source: Bunn et al., 2020

From a corporate perspective, similar to the UK, when faced with tax burdens and a change in business advantage, businesses will tend to avoid tax by passing on to a third party. Besides the UK, Google in Austria is also passing on 5% of DST fees to advertisers (Google, 2020). Accordingly, advertisers running ads in Austria will be taxed an addition of 5% on the total bill as a reflection of the new DST cost. Consequently, Austrian advertisers will need to rethink if their Google Ads strategy is still efficient, and whether the DST fees affect their profit margins too much, like what digital service providers and UK advertisers are dealing with. In addition, taxation on a revenue basis can result in a high marginal tax rate for low-margin service lines (Skippers, 2020; Kim, 2020). Under current Austrian regulations, if the set corporate tax rate of 25% applies to income from online advertising, a business generating a 20% profit margin from online sales can result in the DST liability being equal to the corporate income tax liability (Bunn, Asen and Enache, 2020).

3.5 DST evaluation: summary of criticism

While OECD governments believe in the long-term positive impact of digital taxation on the state budget and equality in tax levy and collection (OECD, 2019), along with the unilateral efforts of some governments such as the UK and Austria, tax criticisms have also emerged and challenged the sustainability of digital taxation. In which, inefficiency and anti-growth characteristics, as well as tax discrimination, are two common criticisms.

Regarding inefficiency and anti-growth, since DST is established as a tax on revenue, instead of a tax on net income, DST forces digital companies to pay tax on the revenue earned from digital businesses regardless of corporate outcomes may not be profitable and costs related to sales are not even mentioned. DST ignores the economic values associated with progress in digital services production, which often results in double or triple taxation. For companies with low margins, it is obvious that DST will significantly affect the total corporate tax payable. This affects the companies' ability to grow in the future. Furthermore, some firms will seek to allocate resources at a rate that keeps the company in a tax-free exemption (Bunn, 2018; Klein, Ludwig and Spengel, 2019).

Regarding discrimination in tax, it can be seen that the digital economy is becoming more complex and involves one or more sectors cooperation. The fact that a tax policy is designed to impact a specific sector is potentially risky when it is difficult for the digital economy to separate sectors as well as from the rest of the world economy. Fashion firms, for example, may be affected by DST as more and more online sales are sold, and the costs of

online advertising as well as for online markets also increase, causing a lot of tax burden imposed on small businesses which are trying to market and sell products via digital platforms (Bunn, 2018). This goes against the canon of efficiency of the tax regime where cost-efficiency comes first.

4 IMPLICATIONS AND LESSONS DRAWN ON DIGITAL TAXATION TO DEVELOP SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN VIET NAM

- **Opportunities**

Firstly, “Taxing digital transactions is often a promising way to target tax avoidance by big tech platforms, while acknowledging that these platforms have enjoyed have significantly benefited from the increase in online transactions over the years.” (Gallien et al. (2021, p. 6)), If governments can increase tax revenue from this taxable sector, the prospect of raising revenue will get a significant boost, especially if tax revenue estimates are projected to materialize. Besides, when the government applies DSTs, this can improve public confidence and trust in the fairness and transparency in the tax system.

In recent years, Vietnam has always been ranked among the top countries with the fastest-growing e-commerce market globally. The transition from traditional retail to online business is an inevitable trend, even though the e-commerce market share in Vietnam is still relatively small compared to other countries in the region and the world. The Vietnam E-commerce Association estimates that by 2022, the retail e-commerce transaction scale will account for about 8.5% of the total retail sales of consumer goods and services. In terms of retailing of goods alone, in 2022, the proportion of online retail sales of goods compared to the total retail sales of goods is about 7.2%, higher than the corresponding rate of 6.7% in 2021.

Over the past years, Vietnam's tax laws have been consolidated and comprehensively adjusted for e-commerce since its inception, ensuring a legal basis for tax collection. Tax revenue from online service business models of foreign organizations that do not establish legal entities in Vietnam such as Google, Youtube, and Facebook is VND 1,143 billion in 2020. This number increased by 133 billion VND and 1,096.14 billion VND compared to 2019 and 2016 respectively. In short, the number increased 24 times in 4 years from 2016 to 2020. For these business models, the tax authority performs tax administration on income generated through partners or advertising agencies, or businesses that purchase services directly from these companies in Vietnam.

- **Challenges**

While there are many advantages to using a digital tax, there are also many challenges. Firstly, the development, implementation, management, and enforcement of a tax policy, especially for a new tax policy, takes a lot of time, money and effort. On the other hand, the application and enforcement of tax regulations for foreign companies whose markets are not covered by the jurisdiction can prove to be a challenge as it requires a high degree of cooperation between countries. stakeholders or some form of contractual agreement to ensure that complete information is shared transparently and fairly (Kelbesa 2020).

There are several challenges to digital tax payment in Vietnam, especially during a period when the e-commerce sector has grown strongly recently. Firstly, e-commerce is a

digital activity, hence the legal regulations in determining tax forms and tax collection have not yet been appropriately changed. Moreover, organizations and individuals can conduct cross-border business activities without the physical presence of taxpayers, so according to the traditional tax management principle, they will not be subject to national taxation. Therefore, some activities do not have appropriate sanctions to monitor and manage. The business activities operating through digital platform can be carried out at any time, through a website that is present in the digital environment for a certain space. Therefore, tax authorities have difficulty in determining tax bases for commercial transactions as well as difficulty distinguishing clearly different types of income as tax bases. The last challenge comes from managing payments through digital transactions. The government has a lot of problems in managing and controlling the cash and online payment systems on these business platforms because suppliers often do not issue sales invoices. Customers and sellers can have many different transactions on different e-commerce platforms and many social networking sites at the same time, so the management of taxpayers also faces many difficulties.

- **Implications**

Taxation of digital services should aim to reach an international agreement, with satisfactory, synchronous and long-term solutions that both create favorable conditions for businesses and aim at the goal of taxing digital services. sustainable development and avoid increasing tensions in international trade.

Furthermore, the peculiarities of digital business models, especially those that rely on the extraction, processing and sale of information are much more difficult to define, control and value. Therefore, redefining the features of economic activity is a necessary step to accompany the digitization of the economy, which must define the concept of value creation and production functions for services (especially in data markets) with caution. Due to the dual aspect of many digital businesses, the effects of DST can be much more difficult to predict than in the traditional economy. Therefore, the economic efficiency of DST should be carefully studied from many angles to avoid negative factors that may harm some sectors of the economy, reduce efficiency in tax administration for with e-commerce businesses in the digital economy. Government and tax authorities need to study the actual development of technology and e-commerce applications that have been changing daily and hourly in social life. At the same time, it is necessary to forecast and build a specific list of the fields that will be involved in e-commerce activities, make plans to propose tax management policies that are both fundamental to this type of e-commerce, must have flexible tax policies to timely adapt to the increasing trend of online payment of society. The review and inspection of new subjects arising from online business activities should be strengthened to build a management mechanism in line with international practices, and combat tax loss.

In addition, the lack of the same database needs to be properly taken care of. The State needs to invest in building a database and widely deploying electronic tax services such as electronic tax declarations, electronic invoices, online tax payment and business registration of businesses close to actual business. It is necessary to research and develop a smart internet search engine on websites with e-commerce activities to identify e-commerce activities that have not yet been declared tax; Record the results as evidence to use in the process of tax

calculation and inspection, examination ... for tax administration according to the search technology and tax management practices on e-commerce of developed countries.

Finally, the integration of environment-friendly solutions into the tax regulation framework plays a vital role in maintaining sustainable development and environmental protection. Several solutions can be implied such as: promoting green taxation and clean energy as financial aids for environmentally friendly businesses, encouraging green investment, establishing carbon tax and pricing policies, promoting energy-efficient technologies, and developing green infrastructures and green financial regulations.

5 CONCLUSION

The digital tax implementation assessment in the two mentioned countries - the UK and Austria, provides an overview of the DST, along with its advantages and disadvantages in three different perspectives. However, it can be seen that challenges still exist, and the OECD should adopt a comprehensive tax regime for countries that are and will be implementing DST in the future. Thus, the digital service tax is a new trend to overcome the loopholes in the international tax system and create fairness for all types of businesses. However, there are still disagreements on how to enforce it, along with barriers and responses by countries that own large technology corporations. So, it will still be a long way for policymakers, while these technology corporations will continue to reap huge profits without paying taxes or paying low taxes until they reach the goal. long-term international solutions.

Regarding Vietnam, although the State now has quite comprehensive tax laws for this type of e-commerce, there still needs to be adjustments in tax administration for e-commerce and ensure the legal basis for tax collection. The enhancement of information exchange with tax authorities of countries and territories that have signed Agreements on the avoidance of double taxation with Vietnam (including a provision on information exchange). This is an important legal framework for Vietnam to exchange information with other countries for tax administration for B2B and B2C cross-border digital transactions. In addition, it is necessary to promote the synchronous and widespread implementation of electronic tax services such as tax declaration, electronic tax payment, and electronic invoices to facilitate the development of e-commerce. To summary, Vietnam should establish and plan its DST, striking a balance between generating revenue and fostering a business-friendly atmosphere. To ensure sustainable economic development in the future, the government needs to carefully consider tax rates, thresholds and the level of tax rate application.

Besides, the technological revolution and innovation have significantly contributed to providing various solutions for digital service taxation, therefore, several solutions can be considered to develop a healthy and sustainable business environment. Firstly, the government and authorities may develop an Automated Tax Management System in order to support electronic businesses in efficiently managing and calculating taxes. These systems can incorporate Artificial Intelligence (AI) to automatically recognize and apply tax rules for different transactions. Secondly, Blockchain can be utilized to create a transparent and immutable transaction ledger system. This can help reduce the risk of fraud and provide a reliable database for tax activities. Moreover, big data and data analytics technology can be used to analyze transaction data and intelligently deduce tax implications. This can help identify tax trends and models, thereby providing optimal advice for tax optimization. The

government also can develop and implement automated tools to assist electronic businesses in maintaining tax records and reporting taxes in accordance with legal regulations. After that, data can be stored by cloud services and collaborative computing to manage tax-related information.

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PRIVATIZATION AND DIGITALIZATION: EVIDENCE FROM THE PC HOLDINGS OF VIETNAMESE COMPANIES

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Abstract

The Vietnamese government promoted IT investments in the early 2000s. Using data on Vietnamese companies from 2001 to 2011, we find that privatization decreases holdings of personal computers (PCs), especially for firms with large interest burdens. We also find that PC holdings are positively associated with the costs of debt and interest burden after privatization, while PC holdings are positively related to ROA, irrespective of whether the firm is privatized or not. These findings suggest that poor solvency status delays digitalization once firms get privatized. Our data also show evidence that PC holdings become less sensitive to performance after privatization.

Keywords: *Privatization, digitalization, PC holdings, IT investment, Vietnam*

INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES ON THE APPLICATION OF EARLY WARNING SYSTEM (EWS) IN FORECASTING CURRENCY CRISIS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR VIETNAM

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Abstracts

A currency crisis is a situation in which the local currency of one country suddenly drops in value, causing tremendous economic losses and negative impacts on the whole society. The development of an early warning system can help prevent currency crises, while also making systematic forecasts of undesirable events. The primary purpose of an early warning system is to detect a crisis before damage occurs and minimize false alarms about a potential crisis. This article aims at providing an overview of the currency crisis as well as the formation and development of early warning models for currency crisis in the world. In addition, the author also synthesizes practical experiences from several countries on the application of early warning models in forecasting currency crises, thereby drawing some lessons and recommendations for application in Vietnam.

Keywords: early warning systems; EWS; currency crisis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Early Warning Systems (EWS) began to attract significant attention of policymakers and academics in the 1990s, when a series of financial crises hit emerging markets. A number of projects in developing effective early warning systems were implemented after the Mexican Peso crisis in 1994. Subsequently, the Southeast Asian currency crisis in 1997 further motivated many countries to build their own early warning systems, with technical assistance from international organizations such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank (WB), and the Asian Development Bank (ADB).

Glostein et al. (2000) pointed out that there are two main reasons why countries and international organizations are concerned about establishing an early warning system. *Firstly*, currency crises cause immense damages, not only to the economy of the affected country but also to the global economy, especially in the context of increasingly expanding linkages both in trade activities and financial markets among countries. According to the authors' report, the Mexican Peso crisis in 1994 had caused the country's real GDP to fall by 6% - the deepest decline in 60 years. In addition, the currency crisis also incurred significant economic costs and social losses, such as: stagnant business production, declining household income, and increased unemployment rate, etc. *Secondly*, practical evidence shows that the use of individual indicators is not an optimal method for predicting crises. For example, empirical

studies show that during the Asian currency crisis 1997 – 1998, the credit spreads or interest rates differences between debt instruments with the same maturity but different credit quality, or the differences between domestic and foreign interest rates did not give any warning signs of possible imminent instability to the economies of countries such as Korea, Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, etc. Meanwhile, the early warning system is somewhat more comprehensive and superior in the way that it utilizes all available information to assess the vulnerability of the economy. It systematically extracts relevant information from a country's entire set of economic and financial indicators to maximize its ability to predict crises. Furthermore, since the early warning system is based on historical experience of past crises, along with a well-defined methodology, early signals from the system are more likely to be reliable. For those reasons, governments and policymakers have been placing greater emphasis on building early warning models for currency crises.

Vietnam is also not out of that trend, especially in the context of our country's increasingly deep integration with the world. The signing of various Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) not only gives Vietnam opportunities to expand international trade and foreign investment, but also creates many challenges to national monetary and financial security. Financial liberalization may impair the effectiveness of monetary policies and increase financial risks for intermediaries such as commercial banks. At the same time, the massive influx of foreign indirect investment into the market also raises concerns about asset price bubbles and sudden capital withdrawals that can cause financial instability. The government has taken initial steps in establishing an early warning system for currency crisis in Vietnam through assigning departments and agencies of the State Bank of Vietnam (SBV) to research and develop. However, so far, these efforts are still in the experimental stage. In fact, there is no early warning system for currency crisis that has been officially launched yet. Meanwhile, in the theoretical field, the number of researches on this topic is also relatively limited in Vietnam. Therefore, this research aims at providing the basic knowledge about the currency crisis, as well as the formation and development of different generations of early warning models for currency crisis in the world. Besides, the paper also examines the international experiences on applying early warning models in forecasting currency crises, especially those countries in the same region that sharing some similarities in political systems and institutions with Vietnam; thereby drawing several lessons and recommendations for application in Vietnam.

2. THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF CURRENCY CRISIS AND EARLY WARNING SYSTEM FOR CURRENCY CRISIS

2.1. The concept of currency crisis

Krugman (1996) argued that the currency crisis is the result of conflicts between domestic policies and fixed exchange rate policies. Meanwhile, Kaminsky et al. (1998) defined a currency crisis as a state in which there is a speculative attack on local currency, leading to a large deficit in foreign currency reserves and rapid depreciation of the local currency. Aziz et al. (2000) also defined a currency crisis as a sudden devaluation of the local currency, forcing the government to protect the local currency by using large amounts of foreign exchange reserves or sharply increasing interest rates.

Therefore, a currency crisis can be defined as the rapid depreciation of a country's domestic currency within a short period of time, or the occurrence of speculative attacks on the currency that require the government to protect the domestic currency by increasing interest rates or using a large amount of national foreign exchange reserves.

2.2. Theoretical models of currency crises

The theories of currency crises have continuously evolved over time. It is partially because the nature of those crises has changed. Until now, there are four generations of theoretical models commonly used to explain the currency crises that have taken place over the past five decades, respectively:

2.2.1. The first generation of currency crisis model

The first-generation currency crisis models were developed by Krugman (1979) and later refined by Flood and Garber (1984) through observing the outcomes of the Argentina crisis 1981 and the Mexico crisis 1982. These models assume that the currency crisis is the result of conflicts in the government policies. Currency crises have been predicted by the weakening of fundamental macroeconomic factors such as: a decline in foreign exchange reserves; excessive depreciation of the local currency; budget deficits, prolonged and gradually increasing current account deficits.

2.2.2. The second generation of currency crisis model

The second generation of currency crisis models emerged in the context of the 1992 - 1993 crisis in the European Monetary System. At that time, the first generation of currency crisis model failed to explain the origins of this crisis as the foreign exchange reserves of many countries were still relatively abundant. Therefore, Obstfeld (1986, 1994, and 1996) constructed and developed the second generation of currency crisis models, which were later refined by the authors Eichengreen, Rose, and Wyplosz (1996). According to these models, there are three main causes of currency crises, which are: (1) Expectations that are mutually reinforcing in the direction leading to crisis; (2) Herding behavior; and (3) Contagion effects of crisis.

2.2.3. The third generation of currency crisis model

The third-generation of currency crisis models emerged after the Asian crisis 1997 - 1998 which was characterized as “double crises” of the currency crisis associated with the banking crisis through a fragile vulnerable financial sector (Kaminsky and Reinhart, 1999). Numerous third-generation currency crisis models have been developed. Each model presents a different transmission mechanism, however, in general they all focus on how the distortions of financial markets and banking systems had contributed to the currency crises. For example, Krugman (1998) explained that the imbalance in banks' assets is the cause of currency crises, while Aghion et al. (2001) argued that bad debts in banking systems are the fundamental cause of currency crises.

2.2.4. The fourth generation of currency crisis model

It can be seen that the previous three generations of currency crisis models have considered both fundamental macroeconomic factors (such as economic growth, budget deficits, money supply, domestic credit, etc.) and non-economic factors (such as psychology, herding behavior, contagion expectations, transmission effects, etc.). However, Breuer (2004) argued that institutional factors such as legal framework, property rights protection, financial regulations, etc. can also contribute to or prevent financial crises. Therefore, the fourth generation of currency crisis models were developed on the basis of inheriting the first, second, and third generation models, as well as additionally incorporating institutional factors into the model.

2.3. Early warning system for currency crisis

Empirical studies worldwide have shown that an Early Warning System (EWS) for currency crises is a model built on macroeconomic indicators, political institutions factors, etc., to give an estimate of the probability of a future currency crisis; thereby helping the government and relevant agencies have the necessary preparation and formulate appropriate policies as well as actions to prevent or minimize the possibility of a currency crisis in the future. In general, an EWS for currency crises should consist of three basic components: (1) identifying the stages of currency crises; (2) identifying a set of explanatory variables (early warning indicators for currency crises), and (3) an econometric model to generate early warnings about currency crises.

(1) Identifying the stages of a currency crisis

Most previous empirical studies have identified stages of currency crisis through the Exchange Market Pressure (EMP) index. The EMP was first introduced by Girton and Roper (1977), then subsequently refined through studies of Eichengreen, Rose and Wyplosz (1996); and Tanner (1999). The EMP index is a weighted average of changes in nominal exchange rate (NER), real interest rate (r), foreign exchange reserves (RES).

$$EMP_{i,t} = \omega_{NER} \left(\frac{NER_{i,t} - NER_{i,t-1}}{NER_{i,t-1}} \right) + \omega_r (r_{i,t} - r_{i,t-1}) - \omega_{res} \left(\frac{res_{i,t} - res_{i,t-1}}{res_{i,t-1}} \right)$$

In which, ω_i is the weight assigned to the corresponding changes in indicators i (NER, r , res), which is calculated as the inverse value of the standard deviation of the changes in that indicator. Accordingly, a country's currency will expose to devaluation pressure (or currency crisis occurs) if the EMP index exceeds a certain threshold, which is usually 1.5 times the standard deviation (some studies also use 2 or 3 standard deviations), compared to the average value of the sample observed.

(2) Identifying early warning indicators for currency crisis

Based on a number of studies by Kaminsky, Lizondo, and Reinhart (1998); Berg and Pattillo (1999); Kamin, Schindler, and Samuel (2001) on EWS for currency crisis, the early warning indicators can be classified into four main groups: (i) indicators related to foreign sector (such as current account and capital account); (ii) indicators related to financial sector; (iii) indicators related to public sector and domestic production; and (iv) indicators related to global economy.

(3) *Establishing econometric models used in early warning system for currency crisis*

The empirical researches on EWS for currency crises in the world mostly employed two approaches: (a) the non-parametric models (Signal), and (b) the parametric models (Logit/Probit). Each approach has its own advantages and disadvantages. Therefore, depending on the actual conditions and circumstances of each country, the governments will consider and choose the appropriate model.

3. INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES ON THE APPLICATION OF EARLY WARNING SYSTEMS IN FORECASTING CURRENCY CRISES

3.1. Experiences of South Korea

Since the Asian currency crisis in 1997, the South Korean government has initiated research and implementation of its own early warning economic system. Although it was not until 2005 that this system officially came into operation, in fact the early warning system for currency crisis (which is one of the 7 sectors of the national early warning system) had been operated since 1999 by the Korea Center for International Finance (KCIF).

Currently, the early warning system of KCIF consists of four quantitative models: (1) Domestic crisis assessment model, (2) International financial market risk model, (3) Domestic financial market risk model, and (4) Near-crisis assessment model. The starting point of the system is the domestic crisis assessment model, which was developed in 1999 based on a non-parametric approach. In the context of the 1997-1998 currency crisis, which was mainly originated from domestic problems such as prolonged current account deficits and accumulated foreign debts, this model was proved to be quite useful in forecasting crises as it was built on aggregate macroeconomic variables within the country. However, the global financial crisis of 2007-2009 had made this model need to be adjusted and to better align with the realities of surveillance. Specifically, the focus of EWS models needs to be expanded and added to variables that reflect the international financial situation such as indices of major stock markets, exchange rate fluctuations of major currency pairs, etc. fluctuations of major currency pairs, etc. Therefore, the other three models for international financial market risk, domestic financial market risk, and near-crisis assessments have been developed to broaden the scope of quantitative monitoring. In addition, the domestic crisis assessment model has also been improved to be more sensitive to recent risk factors.

Although the aforementioned statistical models are quite useful in assessing the vulnerability of the economy, in reality, there is no perfect quantitative model. Therefore, the KCIF has built its own early warning system based on a balance of two main pillars, which are quantitative modeling and qualitative monitoring. In other words, the quantitative model is designed to detect signs of crisis, while qualitative monitoring is intended to look at issues that the model does not address.

The Figure 3.1 below presents the organizational structure of KCIF. In which, the *quantitative EWS* is mostly handled by the Early Warning System Dept. in the World Economic Analysis Division. Besides, the other departments under 2 major divisions would be responsible for *qualitative EWS*, including: (1) the International Financial Market Analysis Division: in charge of monitoring and analyzing trends in the international foreign exchange

market; fixed income market; stock market; as well as monitoring the capital flows into or out of the domestic bond and stock markets; and (2) the World Economic Analysis Division: in charge of covering the global economy as well as the situations of advanced economies such as the United States, Europe, China; and other emerging economies worldwide.

Figure 3.1. The organizational structure of KICF

(Source: The KCIF's official website at www.kcif.or.kr)

In addition, the Global Monitoring Dept. (under the International Financial Market Analysis Division) is responsible for closely following up on media and other reports published in foreign countries. This department also often producing early morning bulletins summarizing the overnight issues in the international financial market to deliver to policymakers and market participants, helping them keep up to the latest global economic and financial news.

Thus, it can be seen that the KCIF operates their early warning system for currency crises on a daily basis, along with holding regular meetings with the governmental agencies in order to assist government in enhancing Korea's international credit worthiness. Every month, under the sponsorship of the Ministry of Economy and Finance, the KCIF will participate in an internal overall assessment, which is conducted by experts from both public and private sectors, to identify potential risk factors.

Another important aspect of the KCIF's early warning system for currency crises is the *Crisis Management Guidelines*. In this guideline, the orientation for contingency policies is given based on the level of warning signals generated from the early warning system. Specifically, the signals from the composite index are classified into 5 levels as follows: (1) Normal, (2) Caution, (3) Warning, (4) Quasi-Emergency, and (5) Emergency. Corresponding to each level of warning is the guidance on contingency policies, as presented in the Table 3.1 below.

Table 3.1. Guidelines on Contingency Policy

Level	Guidelines on Contingency Policy Actions
Normal	
Caution	Tighter monitoring on domestic/global markets and cross-border short-term capital flows Increase the quantity and quality of information shared inside and outside of the government for the risk factors identified
Warning	Strengthen the monitoring function on illegal FX transactions Stricter requirements on FX liquidity soundness of financial institutions Prepare policy action plans on risk factors identified Active sovereign IR
Quasi-emergency	Prepare contingency plans for short-term GX liquidity shortage Activate pan-government daily checking system and crisis management entity Double check safeguard trigger condition
Emergency	Activate safeguard following predetermined trigger conditions

(Source: Hangyong Lee, 2015)

3.2. Experiences of China

In order to enhance the effectiveness of monitoring cross-border capital flows and prevent shocks from external sources caused by short-term speculative capital flows, the State Administration of Foreign Exchange (SAFE) has initiated a project to assess vulnerability of capital flows and establish an early warning system for China since 2003, with technical assistance from the World Bank. Based on the practical experience of other countries, the project development team at SAFE has established *a high-frequency debt monitoring system* and *a market expectations survey system*. These systems are the first of their kind in China, demonstrating the government's significant strategic moves towards effectively monitoring financial risks brought about by financial integration and capital account liberalization. At the same time, these are also the two main components of the early warning system for currency crises in China.

- ***The high-frequency debt monitoring and early warning systems:***

The large scale of debts and borrowings is one of the main causes of financial vulnerability in many countries. Meanwhile, China's foreign debt is increasing and tends to become the most uncertain factor in the balance of payments. The high-frequency debt monitoring system is responsible for 4 main tasks as follows: (1) Indicators analysis: analyzing indicators such as the interest rate differential compared to interbank interest rate, the maturity of credit limits, the renewal rate for short-term credit limits; (2) Subject analysis: studying the behavior among creditors and debtors; (3) Comprehensive analysis: holistic analysis of different aspects such as contract amounts, disbursements, outstanding amounts, principal

repayments, interest repayments, overdue payments, guaranteeing units, currencies, etc.; and (4) Maintenance system. In general, this system helps China establish a real-time monitoring and early-warning system for cross-border capital flows. This system also serves the purpose of maintaining balance in the balance of payments. In the long run, it will also contribute to enhancing the convertibility of the renminbi in capital transactions and the financial stability of China.

- **Market Expectations Survey System:**

By utilizing modern technology and scientific survey methods, the Market Expectations Survey System analyzes market speculation behaviors based on key economic indicators, while providing reliable information for decision-making processes. It serves as a communication channel between policy makers and the market. Through data collection and dynamic feedback, this system helps analyze the reasons behind changes in capital flows.

In summary, the high-frequency debt monitoring system is designed to collect and analyze data on foreign debts, meanwhile the market expectation survey system is used to forecast the development of macroeconomic conditions and market expectations based on key economic indicators. In other words, these two systems simultaneously consider both financial and fundamental economic indicators, perform static analysis and dynamic analysis, provide early warning and make decisions. Therefore, they help China establish a comprehensive, systematic, dynamic, and real-time cross-border capital flow monitoring system, thereby enhancing the country's ability to prevent currency risks.

To ensure the stable operation of these two systems, SAFE has provided trainings for Chinese banks and foreign bank branches in China on the high-frequency debt monitoring system, as well as trainings for financial institutions on how to use the market expectation survey system. In addition, SAFE has also established a comprehensive and complete working mechanism as follows:

- **Daily maintenance mechanism:** SAFE has established a very detailed daily maintenance mechanism to maintain the system and provide technological support services.
- **Analysis mechanism:** SAFE assigns staffs to examine and analyze data from the high-frequency debt monitoring system, market expectation survey system, as well as balance-of-payment (BOP) data.
- **Establishing relevant regulations to ensure data quality:** Through amendments and supplements to regulations and laws on foreign exchange management, international payments, and foreign debt statistics, SAFE has established a legal framework for data collection, reporting methods, reporting frequency, and reporting information.

In addition, SAFE also enhances coordination and information sharing with other departments, and trains its staffs to optimize the functions of systems.

3.3. Experiences of Indonesia

Currently, Indonesia is developing its currency crisis early warning systems simultaneously at 2 places: (1) within the Ministry of Finance with the National Supervisory

Unit (NSU); and (2) within the Bank of Indonesia (the central bank) with the Financial System Stabilization Unit (FSSU).

(1) Early warning system for currency crisis at the Ministry of Finance

After the Asian currency crisis in 1997, the ASEAN Finance Ministers Meeting (which was held on December 2, 1997 in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia) had come to an agreement that ASEAN countries should have a regional monitoring mechanism to serve as a channel for information exchange and consultation on economic and financial matters within and outside the region, in order to prevent and mitigate future economic and financial crises. On that basis, the Asian Development Bank (ADB) and the ASEAN Secretariat jointly reviewed the framework and established the Regional Monitoring Mechanism, of which ADB is the provider of technical assistance and the ASEAN Secretariat is the coordinator. At the member country level, National Surveillance Units (NSUs) were established and played a central role in economic monitoring and exchanging views on regional economic policies, as well as developing an Early Warning Systems for each country.

In Indonesia, NSU was established in 2000 under the Ministry of Finance, and is also responsible for operation of the early warning system for currency crises. In fact, the Asian Development Bank (ADB) has developed a Regional Early Warning System (REWS) specifically for Asian economies based on non-parametric approach and distributed it to member countries. However, the Ministry of Finance of Indonesia found that this model did not perform well here because it did not take into account the distinctive characteristics of the Indonesian economy. Furthermore, REWS is a black-box software in which the source code is hidden from the user due to ADB's copyright ownership. Therefore, the users cannot access the source code, making it difficult to incorporate the specific characteristics of a country into the model. For these reasons, the Indonesian Ministry of Finance did not encourage the use of REWS as an official tool for its currency crisis early warning system. Instead, the NSU of Indonesia, through the Bandung Institute of Technology outsourcing, has developed another three early warning models that reflect the specific characteristics of the Indonesian economy and provides the source code for these models.

Recent studies have shown that Indonesia has the capacity to build and operate the quantitative early warning models on their own, however, they face many difficulties in establishing a qualitative system (Chang Seok Oh, 2006). A qualitative system here can be understood as a comprehensive organizational system, in which staff members are assigned the task of operating the early warning system, performing analysis, and making judgments based on the output results from the quantitative models. In reality, the Indonesia's NSU - with a workforce of only 4 experts - is currently in charge of operating both of these subsystems. Meanwhile, the KCIF in South Korea needs 40 personnel to operate their entire early warning system, indicating that Indonesia is lacking the necessary manpower to operate the early warning system in a feasible manner.

(2) Early warning system for currency crisis at the Bank Indonesia (the Central Bank of Indonesia)

Regarding the quantitative aspects, the Bank Indonesia has established the Financial

System Stability Unit (FSSU) to conduct necessary analyses at both micro and macro levels in order to detect systemic vulnerabilities. The FSSU has strengthened its research and monitoring activities in order to assess and identify the trends and risks within the domestic financial system. While the FSSU is responsible for operating an early warning model across the entire banking system and performing stress tests on each individual banks, the Economic Research and Monetary Policy Department of Bank Indonesia operates an early warning model on macroeconomic and monetary indicators. In urgent cases, FSSU can report directly to the Governor of Bank Indonesia.

In the quantitative analysis, the Bank Indonesia is currently operating three internally developed early warning models. The results of these quantitative models are also exclusively used within the Bank Indonesia.

4. CURRENT SITUATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR VIETNAM

4.1. Current situation of adopting an early warning system for forecasting currency crisis in Vietnam

One inevitable consequence of capital account liberalization in emerging markets like Vietnam is the increasing volatility in cross-border financial transactions which have been continuing to rise over time. The increasing volatility of capital flows requires risk monitoring tools at the national level, such as an early warning system (EWS). Developing a reliable early warning system will help in identifying risk factors in the economy and preventing future economic disasters. Thereby, the governments are more likely to adhere more disciplinarily to economic policies and be able to timely respond to challenges with pre-prepared policy tools.

Fortunately, Vietnamese government has realized the tremendous benefits of adopting an early warning system for forecasting currency crisis, and assigned several departments and agencies under the SBV to research and develop. Vietnam also has received great technical assistance from international organizations and partners such as WB, ADB, IMF, SECO (State Secretariat for Economic), etc. However, so far, these efforts are still in pilot program and experimental stage. In fact, there is no early warning system for currency crisis at national level that has been officially launched yet. We already have some kinds of early warning systems in applications but they mostly focus on micro perspective such as EWS for credit risk of banking system. We are lacking of a system specific for macro uses as forecasting currency crisis.

4.2. Recommendations for Vietnam

Base on the experiences of Korea, China and Indonesia in operating early warning models for currency crises, the author proposes several recommendations for designing and constructing an early warning system specifically for Vietnam, contributing to promoting these models to be put into practice soon, as follows:

Firstly, although quantitative models are useful in timely assessing the vulnerability of the economy, they always have certain inherent limitations. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen qualitative monitoring activities in order to complement the shortcomings of

quantitative models. Especially for emerging economies like Vietnam, where the quality of input data is not yet high, qualitative monitoring should be more emphasized.

Second, the government should consider establishing an independent agency which dedicated to operating an early warning system for currency crises, encompassing both qualitative and quantitative monitoring. The Korea International Financial Center (KCIF) is a good example that Vietnam can refer to. There are some notes to the operator of this currency crisis early warning system as follows:

- The monitoring of currency crisis risks at the national level should be concentrated within this specialized agency. This is to avoid a situation where two different agencies perform the same monitoring task (as can be seen in the case of Indonesia) in order to prevent conflicts in model outcomes or unnecessary waste.
- The human resources play a crucial role in effectively operating an early warning system for currency crises. In fact, qualitative monitoring always requires more manpower than quantitative monitoring, therefore it is necessary to allocate personnel appropriately. In addition, the staff also need to be regularly trained in order to enhance their professional skills and working capacity. In particular, it is necessary to strengthen information exchange and organize collaborative programs with international organizations such as ADB, IMF, WB to promptly update the latest models as well as the most advanced technologies in the world.
- There should be a mechanism for this specialized supervisory agency to report directly to the government in urgent cases, avoiding bureaucratic procedures that could impede the timely implementation of policies. As in the case of Indonesia, the NSU reports had to go through at least 3 agencies before reaching the Ministry of Finance, causing delays in the decision-making process.

Third, the government also needs to prepare a manual handbook for operating the early warning system and providing guidelines for crisis management, which clearly stipulates the mandatory actions that relevant agencies must take in the event of a crisis, to avoid being passive or overlapping tasks. An important element of this crisis management guideline is the need to clearly identify different development stages of a currency crisis, then link them to appropriate policy actions that relevant authorities need to implement at each stage.

Forth, due to the lack of a several types data as well as the lack of experience in operating an early warning model, Vietnam should build a simple model first, and then develop other complex models later. Additionally, it also should be noted that relying solely on a single quantitative model for generating warning signals may be subject to model risks (the risk that the model misses the warning signal or gives a false alarm). Therefore, to mitigate this risk, the government can develop supplementary models and use them as additional tools. The main model and the supplementary models may employ different statistical methods and data.

Fifth, once early warning models have been developed, it is also important to regularly adjust and upgrade these models to ensure better functioning. In particular, Vietnam is an emerging economy where the economic structure can change significantly and rapidly.

Therefore, timely reflection of such changes into the model will help it perform better, reducing the risk of missing warnings or giving false alerts. Besides, enhancing the quality of input data also significantly affects the accuracy of early warning models. To do that, statistical agencies need to collect, process and publish data in accordance with international standards.

Sixth, the operation of the early warning system needs to be connected with the market situation as most frequent as possible. The market is a place where the latest information can be quickly collected. That is why early warning system operators such as the KCIF in South Korea, the SAFE in China, and the Bank Indonesia maintain close contact with market participants. This information is particularly important for qualitative monitoring and decision-making regarding early warning models.

Seventh, early warning signals will be helpful for the government in preparing appropriate contingency policies, however, these information needs to be kept confidential. Because if these signals are widely disclosed, they can cause adverse market reactions. For example, if market participants know that the model has issued warning signals about an impending currency crisis, then the capital outflows will continue to increase, leading to financial turmoil. Therefore, the government should keep official reports strictly confidential, especially when there is a risk of financial instability.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, it is crucial to build an early warning system for Vietnam, especially considering the weaknesses and instability in our financial system. However, since these systems are mostly built on quantitative models, there is still the possibility that these models give false warning signals. Nevertheless, this does not mean that the operation of early warning system does not bring any benefits. Because once the warning signals were issued, the governments already had appropriate policies in place, thereby successfully avoiding crises. In fact, the conclusion that whether a warning signal is false or not can only be done after the fact (ex-post basis). In other words, there would be a case that a country's economy is truly at risk and the model has accurately issued warning signals, but the crisis does not occur in reality due to external factors changing for the better, or it is simply due to a pure luck. In short, the cost of operating an early warning system is minuscule compared to the consequences and damages caused by a currency crisis. Vietnamese government and the SBV should make more efforts to put an official national EWS into practice as soon as possible.

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THE ROLE OF RESPONSIBLE INNOVATION IN INCREASING SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES

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Abstract

This paper presents a study on the role of responsible innovation in the context of fierce competition among hotels. The study examines the impact of innovation resources on responsible innovation and sustainable competitive advantages (SCA), evaluates the mediating role of responsible innovation in this relationship. Quantitative research was carried out with hotels in Hanoi city. Research results show that innovation resources have a positive effect on responsible innovation and SCA, especially responsible innovation plays a mediating role that has a positive impact on the relationship between innovation resources and SCA. This result contributes theoretically to providing empirical evidence proving the important role of responsible innovation and provides useful information not only for hotel managers but also other managers in building innovation resources and promoting innovation responsibly to increase SCA.

Keywords: *Innovation, responsible innovation, sustainable competitive advantages, innovation resources*

1. INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly fierce competitive environment, all enterprises are striving to achieve sustainable competitive advantages (SCA). By competitive advantages, an enterprise can protect itself against competitors, create a difference, distinguish from its competitors in the market (S. Li, Ragu-Nathan, Ragu-Nathan, & Rao, 2006), achieve the economic benefits, reputation, position, and other business goals; deliver value to its customers; contribute benefits to the community.

An enterprise achieves SCA by creating and developing the resources and capabilities in response to the dynamic market environment (J. B. Barney, 1995; Madhavan, Sharafuddin, & Chaichana, 2022). However, not all resources help enterprises achieve competitiveness. Thus, it is necessary to identify the resources and capabilities that bring SCA to firm (J. Barney, 1991).

Resource-based view (RBV) provides the theoretical foundation to build the model in this study. According to RBV, innovation resources of enterprises are different, and these resources can bring competitive advantages to enterprises. To obtain SCA, innovation resources need to be used efficiently. Meanwhile, responsible innovation is one of the important capacities that has been determined to bring SCA to enterprises by many studies.

Ribeiro and Steiner Neto (2021) suppose that an enterprise must renew continually itself, with the intent of better attending the environmental demands and its internal needs in order to ensure SCA. Innovation is considered one of the key means for enterprises to maintain their market position and gain competitive advantages in the changing business environments (Crossan & Apaydin, 2010; Enkel & Gassmann, 2010; Rohrbeck, Hölzle, & Gemünden, 2009). Many studies have examined the relationship between innovation resources, responsible innovation, and SCA. However, the role of responsible innovation in promoting innovation resources to increase SCA for enterprises has not received much research attention, especially in the hospitality sector. In fact, many hotels have been innovating, but not all of them are interested in responsible innovation due to the lack of adequate assessment of its impacts on business performance. This study clarifies the role of responsible innovation in the relationship between innovation resources and SCA, thereby implying solutions for hotels and other enterprises in general.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Innovation resources

Innovation has been an issue that many authors have been interested in researching. They supposed that innovation focused on product and process. Thompson (1965) defined innovation as “the generation, acceptance, and implementation of new ideas, processes, products, or services”. Innovation activity is a complex process that occurs over several stages, ranging from basic research to market penetration of new products (Hollenstein, 1996, 2003). With the same opinion, Francis and Bessant (2005) thought that “innovation is usually explained in terms of changes in what an enterprise introduces to the market (product/service innovation) and the approaches it employs to create and deliver those offerings (process innovation)”. Process innovation reflects introducing new inputs or processes to the enterprise’s production operations, which are then employed to manufacture a product (Damnjanovic Vesna, 2006). Broadly, other authors believed that innovation was not only in products and production processes but also in many different activities in the enterprise. Yusof, Roddin, and Awang (2015) noted that innovation can also defined as application new ideas into products, process or other aspects, splits into five different types namely new products, method of new production, supply source new exploits new markets and new ways to manage business. Panigrahy and Pradhan (2015) proposed that innovation is to involve the generation or adopt an idea or new behavior so it can become a new product or service, the production of new technology any surgical procedure or a new strategy or strategy new management. Therefore, innovation can be in many different aspects of business operations. However, innovation can only take place if enterprises have a proper set of capabilities to innovate (Laforet, 2011). Therefore, identifying resources for enterprise innovation is important.

The demand level of enterprises includes survival demand, development demand and self-realization demand (Arthur, Nicholson, Sibani, & Christensen, 2017), Enterprises will only consider assuming ethical responsibilities after they have achieved sufficient fund accumulation (Lukovics, Flipse, Udvari, & Fisher, 2017). So that, good profitability and sufficient financial support for innovation activities are important innovation resources (Cao, Lv, & Xing, 2020).

The next important resource that many authors are interested in is knowledge and people. However, humans can be carriers of knowledge and technology, so the innovation resource identified by Cao et al (2020) is humans. Petraitė and Čeičytė (2014) also identifies resources for enterprise innovation, including R&D human resources. Therefore, the innovation resources of the enterprise's human resources are reflected in a strong R&D team, and team members can communicate with other members according to their own knowledge accumulation to maximize the use of team knowledge; the R&D personnel of enterprises have higher scientific research quality, and can usually complete innovation projects with high quality (Cao et al., 2020).

The relationship with stakeholders is also focused by the authors and considered as a resource for innovation activities. Chou (2018) argued that the relationship between enterprises and stakeholders has an impact on responsible innovation. Enterprises need to have close relationships with stakeholders such as suppliers, distributors, and the government...; cooperate with external R&D organization jointly develop new technologies (Cao et al., 2020).

2.2. Sustainable competitive advantages

In most definitions of competitive advantages, competitors and customers are the objects of focus. Comparison with competitors, benefits and values brought to customers are used as criteria to evaluate the competitive advantages of enterprises. SCA introduced by Porter (1985) and J. Barney (1991) is one of the most used theories in the study of strategy. Porter (1985) highlighted competitive advantages is gained when an enterprise adds value for customers; it is not just about production cost, it is also about market solutions that competitors cannot deliver, and it must accomplish an enterprise's position or its market leadership. Competitive advantages is related to unique resources and competencies lacked by competitors, and leads to a performance better than that of competitors (Sadri & Lees, 2001).

According to Porter (1985), the competitive advantages should be permanent, timeless, and unique. An enterprise has SCA when the existed or potential competitors cannot duplicate or they will cost much to imitate (Kuncoro & Suriani, 2018). N. Li and Toppinen (2011) agreed and believed that SCA is obtained when other competitors cannot easily or quickly mimic this value. Thus, an enterprise is considered to have SCA if the implementation of its strategy is unable to be carried out simultaneously by its current and potential competitors (Turulja & Bajgoric, 2019), even if these competitors can follow and implement the strategy, they are unable to gain similar or higher benefits (J. B. Barney, Ketchen Jr, & Wright, 2011), thereby enterprises capture and maintain a leading position in the market.

Competitive advantages is the enterprise's ability to achieve better performance than competitors in the same industry or market. This view is shared by many authors. Peteraf and Barney (2003) found that enterprises with a competitive advantages generate higher economic value, competitive advantages as an enterprise's ability to maintain above average profits. Grant (1991) showed that competitive advantages allow for a higher profit rate than its competitors sustainably.

SCA is reflected by differentiation capability, cost leadership, superior resources, excellence reputation, and relational bonding (Setiawan, Rahardian, Novela, Utami, & Peranginangin, 2019; Srivastava, Franklin, & Martinette, 2013). Low cost, competitive price,

quality and product differentiation are also factors that many authors mention when assessing the sustainable competitiveness of enterprises such as Setiawan et al. (2019), Srivastava et al. (2013). The lower production costs help enterprises achieve higher productivity and competitive pricing. Competitive price is an ability of enterprise to adjust its product price to general price in the market (Dirisu, Iyiola, & Ibidunni, 2013). Besides, competitive advantages is obtained when buyers have a more perceptive value for a product than for other products (N. Li & Toppinen, 2011). Competitive advantages include the ability of enterprises to provide customers with products or services of outstanding value in terms of quality and support service.

2.3. Responsible innovation

Many authors have put forward the view of responsible innovation. Caverly (2013) propose that responsible innovation is “a future oriented, uncertain, complex, and collective behavior, and that the results of innovation need to effectively meet social, moral, and ethical needs”. It is the process by which enterprises and stakeholders create mutually beneficial and sustainable value, private and societal values (Bacq & Aguilera, 2022).

Responsible innovation pertains to a new or significantly improved product, service, or business model whose introduction to the market solves or mitigates an environmental or social issue (Halme & Korpela, 2014). Cao et al. (2020) noted that in the early stage of innovation, enterprises include many stakeholders participating in decision-making and predicting the impact of innovation on society; during the process of innovation, based on the progress of R&D activities and the goals set in the early stage, enterprises should reflect on their own behavior to make sure that the innovation process and results meet moral and social expectations, to achieve scientific and technological progress and finally to make scientific and technological progress properly embedded in social development. Von Schomberg (2012) noted that responsible innovation refers to a transparent, interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other with a view on the acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products. Thence, these authors argued that compared with the traditional innovation model, the characteristics of responsible innovation mainly manifest in four aspects: Inclusion, anticipation, responsiveness, and reflexivity.

Inclusion is the involvement of different stakeholders in the innovation process. In order to survive and develop, the behavior of an enterprise should conform to a series of explicit or implicit behavior norms, and address the interests or emotional needs of all stakeholders to the maximum extent (Leonidou, Christodoulides, Kyrgidou, & Palihawadana, 2017), therefore, responsible innovation considers both internal and external stakeholders that may participate in the innovation process (Brand & Blok, 2019). Delgado and Åm (2018) consider that enterprises listen to the demands of different stakeholders for innovation, coordinate the conflicts among stakeholders and achieve the compatibility of scientific and technological innovation activities to promote the implementation of responsible innovation.

Anticipation reflects forward-looking analysis of innovation activities. Enterprises use forward-looking analytics to discover and evaluate the possible consequences of innovation, control and predict the risks of innovation, and ultimately drive responsible innovation

implementation. Cao et al. (2020) supposed that in the early stage of innovation activities, enterprises can make forward-looking analysis on the future impact of activities, so to guide innovation activities to the direction of moral acceptability and social satisfaction and realize the controllable risk of innovation activities.

Responsiveness reflects the ability to identify and react to potential risks, recognizing and re-testing innovation processes and structures. In the process of innovation, enterprises repeatedly reflect on the assumptions, requirements, objectives, implementation process and results of innovation itself (Cao et al., 2020).

Reflexivity is reflected in the establishment of a continuous adaptive process between the innovation subject and the external, so as to rectify the deviation of innovation activities (Van Lente, Swierstra, & Joly, 2017). The behavior subject and governance mode of innovation activities of enterprises are established in the process of interaction, sustainability and adaptability, so as to realize the correct guidance and real-time correction of innovation activities (Cao et al., 2020).

2.4. Innovation resources and sustainable competitive advantages: The mediating role of responsible innovation

2.4.1. Innovation resources and sustainable competitive advantages

RBV is a theory which is commonly used in studies on competitive advantages (Furrer et al., 2008). Wernerfelt (1984) developed the fundamental theory of resources based on studying how enterprises own, deploy and use resources to explain the competitive advantages of enterprises. This theory was later developed by the other authors such as Porter (1985), J. Barney (1991)...

Wernerfelt (1984) proposed that enterprise's resources include all assets associated with enterprises divided into tangible assets and intangible assets. J. Barney (1991) divided enterprise's resources into 3 types: tangible resources include factory, location, raw materials; human resources include knowledge, intuition, judgment, experience, ability to learn; and organizational resources include organizational structure, informal relationships inside and outside the business (J. Barney, 1991). Meanwhile, Grant (1991) divided resources into 6 groups: financial resources, tangible resources, human resources, technological resources, brand and organizational resources. Although there are many different ways to classify resources, these authors agree that different enterprises have different resources and not all resources can create competitive advantages. J. Barney (1991) pointed out the attributes required for resources to create competitive advantages: valuable, rare, hard to imitate and irreplaceable, these resources create SCA by new values and difference. The set of unique resources and capabilities that protect enterprises from imitation by competitors and provide the accumulation of profits through product or service differentiation. (Porter, 1985).

Based on RBV, many authors assumed that innovation resources and competitive advantages are connected, the relationship between them has been studied and analyzed. Mogollón and de la Calle Vaquero (2004) interpret enterprises' innovation efforts as evidence of their increasing awareness of innovation as a source of CA.

Many studies focused on the relationship between innovation and outcomes. These

studies showed that a positive appraisal of higher innovativeness resulting in increased CA and superior performance (Calantone, Cavusgil, & Zhao, 2002), innovation is a key driver of firm success (Tutar, Nart, & Bingöl, 2015). Innovation is seen as a strategic asset since helps to improve competition advantage and firm performance (Kalmuk & Acar, 2015). Based on above analysis, the hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Innovation resources are positively associated with SCA.

2.4.2. Innovation resources and responsible innovation

According to RBV, the implementation of responsible behavior of enterprises depends on whether they have abundant resources or not. Some studies confirmed that there is a significant relationship between resources and behavioral motivation (Sun, Guo, & Chen, 2013) and responsible behavior (Brekke & Nyborg, 2004). Therefore, enterprise resources are very important for responsible innovation. Innovative resources (including financial capital, human capital and social capital) can improve enterprises' risk prediction ability, introspection ability, responsiveness to the external environment and inclusiveness towards promoting the implementation of responsible innovation. (Cao et al., 2020). Chou (2018) also argued that finance, the relationship with stakeholders impact on responsible innovation. So that, the hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Innovation resources are positively associated with responsible innovation.

2.4.3. Responsible Innovation and SCA

According to RBV, core competencies determine SCA outcomes, thus enterprises need to develop their skills and resources to adapt quickly to evolving opportunities (McWilliams & Siegel, 2011). Enterprises gain SCA through the ability to develop main competence to serve their target customers better than their competitors. The main competence refers to a set of unique competence which is developed in an enterprise in its main fields, so that it can surpass its competitors (Srivastava et al., 2013).

Meanwhile, responsible innovation has become increasingly important due to its impact on society, stakeholders and has been identified as one of the key competencies of enterprises. Cheng and Huizingh (2014) argued that an enterprise should expand its innovative capabilities for the development and commercialization of new technologies, facilitate the creation and distribution of technological innovations throughout the organization, and strengthen its competitive advantages. M. Li, Tian, Liu, and Lu (2022) thought that enterprises implementing green innovation have the awareness to fulfill both social and environmental responsibilities as well as increase productivity, efficiency, and cost savings, directly contributing to the competitive advantages and improving the financial performance. Responsible innovation can bring various competitive benefits to enterprises, such as stakeholders' satisfaction and social image (Haned, Mothe, & Nguyen-Thi, 2014) and sustainable (social, environmental, and economic) performance (Xie, Wu, & Tejerob, 2022). However, few empirical studies have demonstrated the important role of responsible innovation as a competence to contribute to enterprise's competitive advantages, particularly in the hospitality sector. Therefore, the hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Responsible innovation is positively associated with SCA.

2.4.4. The mediating role of responsible innovation

According to RBV, researchers argue that an enterprise achieves SCA when it outperforms its competitors by using its resources more efficiently or specifically than its competitors (J. Barney, 1991; Porter, 1985). Amit and Schoemaker (1993) also emphasized the competence of enterprises to deploy resources. Owning unique resources is not enough to gain competitive advantages, enterprises must also have the ability to exploit those resources (Yang & Morgan, 2011). Thus, the resources themselves are not basically enough to create competitive advantages, they need to be used effectively by enterprises. Responsible innovation has been identified as having a positive impact on SCA. However, the mediating role of responsible innovation in the relationship between innovation resources and SCA has not been considered. This study will clarify the contribution of responsible innovation on the effective exploitation of innovation resources to increase enterprise's competitive advantages and assess the extent of this impact. Therefore, the hypothesis is proposed:

H4: Innovation resources are positively associated with SCA via responsible innovation.

Image 1. The research model

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Research context and sample

Hanoi is not only the economic and political center of Vietnam but also a famous destination with many historical, cultural, and scenic sites... Therefore, hotels in the area serve many kinds of tourists with different purposes. Although in 2020 and 2021, fluctuations caused by the COVID-19 epidemic profoundly affected their operation, along with the recovery of the tourism industry, the hospitality industry of Hanoi has had many positive changes to gradually regain the growth rate in 2023. In the first 6 months of 2023, total tourists reached 12.33 million arrivals, up 42% over the same period in 2022, of which international tourists reached 2.03 million arrivals, up 7 times over the same period in 2022 (Hanoi Department of Tourism). With the increase in tourist arrivals, the hospitality market of Hanoi is recovering rapidly. As of June 2023, Hanoi has 3,756 tourist accommodation establishments with 70,218 rooms. The average occupancy in the first 6 months of 2023 is estimated at 61.1%, up 31.1% over the same period in 2022 (Hanoi Department of Tourism). Competition in this industry has also increased after the epidemic, especially when more hotel projects are being built, completed, and will be put into operation soon. The diverse customer base, rapid development, fierce competition in a rapidly changing environment are some reasons why hotels in Hanoi need to increase SCA and focus on responsible innovation. This study conducted in the context of hotels in Hanoi will clarify the role of responsible innovation in the relationship between innovation resources and SCA.

Quantitative research is carried out with the aim of testing the reliability of the observed variables in the research model; assess and measure the impact of innovation resources on responsible innovation, the impact of innovation resources on SCA, the impact of responsible innovation on SCA; and assess the mediating role of responsible innovation in the relationship between innovation resources and SCA.

Testing the reliability of the scale, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), and SEM model testing are used in this study. For EFA, the sample size is determined based on the minimum size and the number of observed variables. About EFA, according to Hair (2009), the rate of observation/observation variables is a maximum of 5:1. About multiple regression analysis, according to Tabachnick, Fidell and Ullman (2007), the sample size is $\geq 50 + 8m$ (m is the number of independent variables). This research uses 17 observation variables, so the minimum sample size of quantitative research is 85. In order to ensure the number of collected questionnaires and increase reliability, 300 questionnaires were delivered by the random sampling method. The survey was conducted from February to May 2023. Questionnaires were delivered directly to managers of hotels in Hanoi. There were 217 questionnaires collected with 198 of them being valid (equal to 61.88%).

3.2. Measurement

Innovation resources are measured on the basis of developing the scale of Halme and Korpela (2014), Cao et al. (2020) in comparison with other firms in the industry: good profitability and can provide sufficient financial support for innovation activities, a strong R&D team, and team members can communicate with other members according to their own knowledge accumulation to maximize the use of team knowledge, the R&D personnel of enterprises have higher scientific research quality, and can usually complete innovation projects with high quality, closely related to external stakeholders such as suppliers, distributors and governments, cooperate with external R&D teams to jointly develop new technologies.

Responsible innovation is measured on the basis of developing a scale of Mei and Chen (2019), Cao et al. (2020): a wider range of stakeholders in innovation activities, whose basic actors include innovators, people and policy makers; In the early stage of innovation activities, enterprises can make forward-looking analysis on the future impact of activities, so as to guide innovation activities to the direction of moral acceptability and social satisfaction, and realize the controllable risk of innovation activities; In the process of innovation, enterprises repeatedly reflect on the assumptions, requirements, objectives, implementation process and results of innovation itself; The behavior subject and governance mode of innovation activities of enterprises are established in the process of interaction, sustainability and adaptability, so as to realize the correct guidance and real-time correction of innovation activities.

SCA is measured on the basis of scale development of Jap (1999), Weerawardena (2003), Hossain, Kannan, and Raman Nair (2021), on the basis of comparison with competitors and industry averages: high-quality product/service, more competitive price; large market, more strategic advantages; a large market share; earnings before interest and taxes is continuously above the industry average; return on investment is continuously above the industry average; return on sales is continuously above the industry average.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis results

The results of testing measurement reliability reveal that innovation resources, responsible innovation, SCA have Cronbach's Alpha values greater than 0.7 (0.840; 0.798; 0.824); all observed variables have factors loading less more than 0.3, meet the demand. Observation variables SCA3 and SCA5 have factors loading less than 0.3, therefore they are deleted. After removing SCA3, TL5, SCA's Cronbach's alpha coefficient is $0.865 > 0.7$, the total variable correlation coefficient of the remaining observed variables is greater than 0.3 that is satisfactory. Cronbach's alpha coefficient if variable IR4 is deleted is $0.840 > 0.844$, however, IR4 - a scale of relationships with stakeholders - is an important indicator of innovation resources, so it should be kept. Thus, after analyzing the reliability of Cronbach's alpha, there are 15 observed variables that meet the requirements to be included in EFA (Table 2).

The results of exploratory factor analysis EFA

EFA with independent variable Innovation resources and intermediate variable Responsible innovation: The results of EFA provides a rotation matrix with coefficients is shown in Table 2. $KMO = 0.809 > 0.5$; Barlett test has $sig = 0.00 < 0.05$, which means that observation variables are correlated with each other; factors with total variance of $62.116 > 50\%$ and Eigenvalue of 1.567 . This illustrates that the use of EFA is appropriate, and there are 2 main factors (Table 2).

EFA with dependent variable SCA: The results of EFA provides a rotation matrix with coefficients are shown in Table 2. $KMO = 0.826 > 0.5$; Barlett test has $sig = 0.00 < 0.05$; factors with total variance of $59.801 > 50\%$ and Eigenvalue of $3.588 > 1.567$. This illustrates that the use of EFA is appropriate, and there are 2 main factors (Table 2).

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha and EFA results

Observation variables	Cronbach's alpha	Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's alpha if item deleted	Factors loading
IR	0.840			
IR1		0.730	0.786	0.839
IR2		0.662	0.804	0.726
IR3		0.705	0.792	0.821
IR4		0.502	0.844	0.684
IR5		0.634	0.813	0.723
RIN	0.798			
RIN1		0.624	0.725	0.785
RIN2		0.625	0.723	0.793
RIN3		0.533	0.780	0.689
RIN4		0.643	0.724	0.806
SCA	0.865	0.865		
SCA1		0.635	0.847	0.822
SCA2		0.618	0.850	0.737

Observation variables	Cronbach's alpha	Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's alpha if item deleted	Factors loading
SCA4		0.658	0.843	0.769
SCA6		0.660	0.842	0.777
SCA7		0.721	0.831	0.822
SCA8		0.670	0.841	0.781

Source: Research results

The results of confirmatory factor analysis CFA

CFA is performed with 3 factors including 15 observed variables. The first CFA results show that some indices are not satisfactory, so the model is improved by concatenating e according to the suggestion from Modification indices: e2-e5, e13-e14. The second CFA test results of Model indicate that: Chi-square has P-value = 0; CMIN/df = 2.034 < 3; GFI = 0.896 > 0.9; TLI = 0.919 > 0.9; CFI = 0.935 > 0.9; RMSEA = 0.073 < 0,08 (Image 2).

Image 2. CFA results

Source: Research results

Standardized factors loading of all variables are > 0.05; composite reliability (CR) > 0.7; average variance extracted (AVE) > 0.5; MSV < AVE and square root of 2 of AVE is higher than correlation of the two concepts (Table 3). As such, the measurement scales are appropriate with market data, ensure reliability, ensure convergent validity, and ensure discriminant validity.

Table 3. Analysis Results of Composite Reliability, Convergent Validity, and Discriminant Validity of Model

	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	RIN	IR	SCA
RIN	0.800	0.501	0.264	0.807	0.708		
IR	0.833	0.507	0.229	0.874	0.479	0.712	
SCA	0.857	0.500	0.264	0.859	0.514	0.450	0.707

Source: Research results

Results of SEM analysis and hypothesis testing

SEM analysis and Bootstrap test were performed to evaluate the direct, indirect and overall impact relationships of the factors in the model.

The testing results of Model: Chi-square has P-value = 0; CMIN/df = 2.034 < 3; GFI = 0.896 > 0.8; TLI = 0.919 > 0.9; CFI = 0.935 > 0.9; RMSEA = 0.073 < 0.08, illustrating that model is appropriate with the research data. The estimate results indicate that there is a positive. R² of Responsible innovation is 0.229 so that Innovation resources impact 22.9% of Responsible innovation. R² of SCA is 0.229 so that Innovation resources and Responsible innovation impact 22.9% of SCA.

Image 3. Model Testing Results

Source: Research results

Innovation resources has a positive effect on Responsible innovation at significant levels of 1% ($\beta = 0.479 > 0$, Sig. = 0.000 < 0,01) and SCA at significant levels of 1% ($\beta = 0.264 > 0$, Sig. = 0.004 < 0.01). Thus, H1, H2 hypotheses are accepted. Responsible innovation has a positive effect on SCA at significant levels of 1% ($\beta = 0.388 > 0$, Sig. = 0.000 < 0.01). Thus, H3 hypothesis is accepted.

Bootstrap test shows that Innovation resources has a positive indirect effect on SCA with the intermediate effect of Responsible innovation at significant levels of 1% ($\beta = 0.186 > 0$, Sig. = 0.001 < 0.01). Thus, H4 hypothesis is accepted.

Table 4. Model and hypotheses testing results

Relationships		Regression	Standardized regression	P-value	Conclusion
RIN	<-- IR	0.347	0.479	0.000	Accept H1
SCA	<-- IR	0.197	0.264	0.004	Accept H2
SCA	<-- RIN	0.399	0.388	0.000	Accept H3
SCA	<-- RIN <-- IR	0.139	0.186	0.001	Accept H4

Source: Research results

5. CONCLUSSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

This study assesses the impact of innovation resources on SCA via the mediating effects of responsible innovation. Survey data from 197 hotels in Hanoi city support the proposed hypotheses.

RBV theory holds that resources have ability to create enterprise's competitive advantages, but these resources must be valuable, difficult to imitate and irreplaceable (J. Barney, 1991). The research results point out factors of enterprise's innovation resources and proved the positive role of innovation resources in increasing enterprise's SCA. Research results are consistent with RBV on the role of innovation resources in improving competitive advantages of enterprises. Enterprises which have financial resources for R&D activities, strong R&D human resources and good relationships with stakeholders, and regularly cooperate with external R&D teams will be able to create outstanding products, competitive pricing, and strategic advantages over competitors. They also have incomes and profits that are above the industry average.

Based on RBV and behavioral theory, this research suggests that responsible innovation is better implemented with better resources. Findings from this study support this hypothesis. It is shown that innovation resources are positively related to responsible innovation, further clarifying the role of innovation resources in implementing responsible innovative behaviors of hotels. This result is consistent with conclusions of some previous studies. Research of Cao et al. (2020) also showed that innovation resources including finance, human and social relations have a significant positive impact on responsible innovation. Enterprises which have financial resources for R&D activities, strong R&D human resources and good relationships with stakeholders, cooperation with external R&D teams will be able to implement innovation activities better with stakeholder engagement, analysis of the impact of innovation, identification of risks, have good governance to implement present more accurately and fine-tune innovation activities.

The study results also indicate a positive impact of responsible innovation on SCA. Accordingly, the more hotels focus on and implement responsible innovation, the more competitive advantages they have in the market. This result is consistent with some previous studies which suggested that responsible innovation has a positive impact on competitive advantages (Hadj, Omri, & Al-Tit, 2020), product performance (Adomako & Nguyen, 2023).

Along with that, this study has new findings when pointing out the mediating role of

responsible innovation in the relationship between innovation resources and SCA. It shows that enterprises which innovate responsibly better will exploit innovation resources better to increase SCA. This is consistent with RBV, enterprises need to use innovative resources effectively to get SCA. (J. Barney, 1991; Porter, 1985).

Besides theoretical contributions, this study provides some implications for hotel managers in general and enterprises in particular to increase SCA. Enterprises need to focus on creating innovation resources: First, enterprises need to pay attention to financial investment for innovation activities. Second, enterprises need to establish strong R&D team, with a mechanism for members to regularly exchange, share, and support other members to accumulate knowledge, maximize the use of team knowledge. Third, focus on training and developing high-quality R&D personnel. Fourth, establish and maintain close relationships with external stakeholders including suppliers, distributors, and regulatory agencies. Finally, enterprises need to actively cooperate with external R&D teams to jointly develop new technologies. Along with that, enterprises build responsible innovation capacity by: First, implementing innovation activities with the participation of more stakeholders. Second, in the early stages of innovation perform forward-looking analyzes of the impact of the innovation to align these activities in a socially and ethically acceptable direction and recognize the controllable risks of innovation activities. Third, during the renovation process, it is necessary to regularly review the requirements, objectives, implementation process and results of innovation. Fourth, define an innovation management method that ensures interoperability, sustainability, and adaptability so that innovation is carried out accurately and can be adjusted in real time.

There are still limitations in this research that can be considered as gaps for further research. First, this study was carried out with hotels in Hanoi, so it is necessary to have studies with hotels in different areas or enterprises in other fields to provide more affirmative evidence. mediating role of responsible innovation in the relationship between innovation resources and SCA. Second, the study has not evaluated the difference in the mediating role of responsible innovation in the relationship between innovation resources and SCA for different groups of hotels, there may exist differences that need to be researched in the future.

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FOOD WASTE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES: A CASE STUDY OF THE HOSPITALITY SECTOR IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

Food waste (FW) is a major global problem, yet despite its significance, the issue of FW in the hospitality sector remains under-researched. This study contributes to knowledge of hospitality FW and its management in Vietnam. In particular, it sought to identify types and causes of FW generation and explore current practices of FW management strategies adopted by luxury hotels in Viet Nam. This study found that all hoteliers interviewed were aware of the need to prevent FW; and cost-saving represents the main driver of engaging in FW mitigation among Vietnamese hospitality businesses. Compared to preparation and plate waste, buffet leftovers were the cause of most waste in Vietnamese hotels. The inaccurate demand forecasting and the top priority of luxury hotels' of satisfying their customers, which ultimately led to the over-ordering and over-production of food, could explain this. Notably, the study revealed that the reuse and redistribution of surplus food and especially, selling FW for animal feed tended to be prioritised rather than prevention practices. The study demonstrated the need for hospitality businesses in Vietnam to invest in more accurate demand forecasting and human resources management as prime means of FW management. The study also provides practical implications for policymakers to ensure more effective FW management practices.

Keywords: *Food Waste, Food Waste Management Practices, Hospitality Sector, Vietnam.*

TÁC ĐỘNG CỦA CƠ SỞ HẠ TẦNG CÔNG NGHỆ - THÔNG TIN – TRUYỀN THÔNG (ICT) VÀ TÍN DỤNG TRONG NƯỚC ĐẾN DÒNG VỐN FDI VÀO TẠI CHÂU Á – THÁI BÌNH DƯƠNG

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Tóm tắt

Bài nghiên cứu cho thấy cơ sở hạ tầng công nghệ - thông tin – truyền thông (ICT) và tín dụng trong nước cho khu vực tư nhân đều tác động cùng chiều và có ý nghĩa đối với dòng vốn FDI ở 41 quốc gia thuộc khu vực châu Á và Thái Bình Dương trong giai đoạn 2007 – 2021. Điều này hàm ý rằng sự phát triển của cơ sở hạ tầng ICT và tín dụng trong nước của một quốc gia là những nhân tố quan trọng góp phần thu hút dòng vốn FDI. Bên cạnh đó, các biến tương tác của cơ sở hạ tầng ICT và tín dụng trong nước lại tác động ngược chiều và có ý nghĩa đối với dòng vốn FDI. Điều này ngụ ý rằng, sự phát triển tín dụng tư nhân của một quốc gia kết hợp sự tác động của cơ sở hạ tầng ICT sẽ làm giảm mức hấp dẫn của quốc gia đối với dòng vốn FDI đi vào. Qua đây, mỗi quốc gia nên quan tâm đầu tư vào cơ sở hạ tầng ICT, và củng cố hệ thống tài chính của mỗi quốc gia, đặc biệt là quan tâm đến khu vực kinh tế tư nhân bởi vì đó có thể là những nhân tố góp phần thúc đẩy tăng trưởng kinh tế tự thân và giảm bớt phụ thuộc vào nguồn vốn FDI đến từ bên ngoài, qua đó góp phần phát triển nền kinh tế của quốc gia một cách bền vững.

Từ khóa: FDI, cơ sở hạ tầng ICT, tín dụng trong nước, châu Á – Thái Bình Dương

Abstract

This study shows that domestic credit to the private sector and ICT infrastructure both positively and significantly impact FDI inflows in 41 countries in the Asia and Pacific region from 2007 to 2021. This implies that domestic credit and ICT infrastructure are important factors attracting FDI inflows. Besides, the interaction variables of ICT infrastructure and domestic credit negatively and significantly impact FDI inflows. This implies that a country's private credit development combined with the impact of ICT infrastructure will reduce the country's attractiveness for inflows of FDI capital. Through this, each country should pay attention to investing in ICT infrastructure and strengthening each country's financial system, especially paying attention to the private economic sector, because that can be the main contributing factor contributing to promoting self-generated economic growth and reducing dependence on foreign FDI capital, thereby helping to develop a sustainable economy.

Keywords: FDI, ICT infrastructure, domestic credit, Asia – Pacific region

RỦI RO AN NINH MẠNG TRONG THƯƠNG MẠI ĐIỆN TỬ TẠI VIỆT NAM: THỰC TRẠNG VÀ GIẢI PHÁP

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Tóm tắt

Sự phát triển của thương mại điện tử đã và đang mở ra nhiều cơ hội kinh doanh cho cộng đồng doanh nghiệp tại Việt Nam. Tuy nhiên, bên cạnh những lợi ích mang lại, nền tảng này còn đang tiềm ẩn nhiều rủi ro, hạn chế khiến các đối tượng xấu lợi dụng kinh doanh hàng giả, hàng nhái, không rõ nguồn gốc trực lợi. Bài viết này phân tích thực trạng phát triển thương mại điện tử Việt Nam cũng như phân tích những rủi ro an ninh mạng trên các nền tảng thương mại điện tử, từ đó đề xuất một số giải pháp nhằm nâng cao khả năng phòng ngừa, kiểm soát rủi ro của doanh nghiệp nhằm đẩy mạnh sự phát triển của thương mại điện tử tại Việt Nam.

Từ khóa: An ninh mạng, Quản lý rủi ro, rủi ro thương mại điện tử, thương mại điện tử

Abstract

The development of e-commerce has opened up many business opportunities for the business community in Vietnam. However, in addition to the benefits, this platform also has many potential risks and limits, allowing bad actors to take advantage of the business of counterfeit goods, imitation goods, and unknown origin for profit. This article analyzes the current situation of e-commerce development in Vietnam as well as analyzes the risks on e-commerce platforms, thereby proposing some solutions to improve the ability to prevent and control risks. risks of enterprises to promote the development of e-commerce in Vietnam.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, Risk management, E-commerce risk, E-commerce.

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Hoạt động thương mại điện tử (TMĐT) tại Việt Nam hiện đang trong giai đoạn bùng nổ với tăng trưởng hàng năm ở mức rất cao. Trong những năm gần đây, mô hình kinh doanh trên toàn cầu tiếp tục thay đổi đáng kể với sự ra đời và phát triển mạnh mẽ của TMĐT. Mô hình kinh doanh này đã có những đóng góp lớn cho sự tăng trưởng kinh tế trong bối cảnh thế giới đang bước vào cuộc cách mạng 4.0. Theo các phân tích của GlobalData's E-Commerce Analytics, Việt Nam được đánh giá là một trong những thị trường TMĐT phát triển nhanh nhất ở Đông Nam Á với tốc độ tăng trưởng trung bình hàng năm khoảng 18%. Theo đó, quy mô thị trường TMĐT tại Việt Nam từ mức chỉ đạt 6,2 tỷ USD vào năm 2017 đã tăng lên đạt 16,4 tỷ USD vào năm 2022 và được dự báo quy mô thị trường có khả năng lên tới 26 tỷ USD vào năm 2024. Tốc độ tăng trưởng trung bình của thị trường thương mại điện tử Việt Nam giai đoạn 2017-2022 khá cao, khoảng 22%. Sự tăng trưởng bứt phá của TMĐT đã đưa Việt Nam trở

thành một trong những thị trường tiềm năng nhất khu vực ASEAN. Đây là bước phát triển tất yếu, phù hợp với xu thế của thế. Tuy nhiên, bên cạnh những cơ hội, tiềm năng to lớn đó, TMĐT ở nước ta cũng gặp không ít thách thức, khó khăn và rủi ro còn tồn đọng trên các nền tảng thương mại điện tử.

Việt Nam là nước đi sau trong ứng dụng thương mại điện tử và mức độ phát triển của lĩnh vực này còn hạn chế. Tuy nhiên Việt Nam cũng không tránh khỏi được những rủi ro mà các nước phát triển về thương mại điện tử gặp phải. Số vụ tấn công các trang web với mục đích xấu hay cảnh báo, cũng như số vụ ăn trộm thông tin tài khoản thanh toán của cá nhân trên mạng ngày càng gia tăng. Do đó, ngày nay, vấn đề an ninh cho thương mại điện tử đã không còn là vấn đề mới mẻ. Các bằng chứng thu thập được từ hàng loạt các cuộc điều tra cho thấy những vụ tấn công qua mạng hoặc tội phạm mạng trong thế giới thương mại điện tử đang gia tăng nhanh từng ngày.

Theo Trung tâm ứng cứu khẩn cấp máy tính Việt Nam (VnCERT - Vietnam Computer Emergency Response Teams), trong những năm gần đây, tội phạm tin học gia tăng cả về phạm vi và mức độ chuyên nghiệp. Ban đầu là lấy cắp mật khẩu thẻ tín dụng để mua hàng hóa và phần mềm qua mạng, tiếp đến là làm thẻ tín dụng giả để lấy cắp tiền từ máy ATM, thiết lập các mạng máy tính giả để gửi thư rác, thư quảng cáo, hay tấn công từ chối dịch vụ, thậm chí ngang nhiên hơn nữa là đe dọa tấn công, tống tiền hay báo kê các website thương mại điện tử. Chính vì thế, trong bài viết này, tác giả phân tích tổng quan sự phát triển của thương mại điện tử và các rủi ro thường gặp trong thời gian hiện nay, đồng thời đưa ra những giải pháp nhằm phòng ngừa, hạn chế rủi ro đối với thương mại điện tử.

2. CƠ SỞ LÝ LUẬN VÀ PHƯƠNG PHÁP NGHIÊN CỨU

2.1. Cơ sở lý luận

An ninh mạng

Theo khoản 1 Điều 2 Luật An ninh mạng 2018 định nghĩa an ninh mạng như sau: "An ninh mạng là sự bảo đảm hoạt động trên không gian mạng không gây phương hại đến an ninh quốc gia, trật tự, an toàn xã hội, quyền và lợi ích hợp pháp của cơ quan, tổ chức, cá nhân." Có thể hiểu theo cách khác, an ninh mạng là sự bảo vệ các hệ thống, thiết bị, dữ liệu và ứng dụng trên internet hoặc các mạng riêng khỏi các cuộc tấn công, xâm nhập không mong muốn. An ninh mạng bao gồm các biện pháp kỹ thuật, hành vi và tổ chức nhằm ngăn chặn hoặc giảm thiểu các rủi ro an ninh mạng.

Thương mại điện tử

Theo Tổ chức Thương mại thế giới (WTO): "Thương mại điện tử bao gồm việc sản xuất, quảng cáo, bán hàng và phân phối sản phẩm được mua bán và thanh toán trên Internet, nhưng được giao nhận một cách hữu hình, cả các sản phẩm giao nhận cũng như những thông tin số hoá thông qua Internet". Ủy ban Thương mại điện tử của Tổ chức hợp tác kinh tế châu Á - Thái Bình Dương (APEC) lại định nghĩa "Thương mại điện tử là công việc kinh doanh được tiến hành thông qua truyền thông số liệu và công nghệ tin học kỹ thuật số".

Có thể hiểu thương mại điện tử là một trong những phương tiện để kinh doanh được ưa chuộng. nó cho phép các doanh nghiệp và những người tiêu dùng có thể mua bán sản phẩm, xây dựng thương hiệu và quảng cáo trực tuyến. Đây là một loại hình kinh doanh được nhiều doanh nghiệp hiện nay đánh giá cao hơn so với kiểu truyền thống, giúp tiết kiệm chi phí và khách hàng có thể mua sắm từ mọi nơi trên thế giới với bất kỳ thời gian nào.

2.2. Phương pháp nghiên cứu

Trong bài nghiên cứu này, nhóm tác giả tìm hiểu, thu thập và tổng hợp các nghiên cứu đi trước và số liệu từ các báo cáo hiện nay để chỉ ra thực trạng phát triển của thương mại điện tử hiện nay cũng như các rủi ro trong thương mại điện tử. Sau đó, nhóm tác giả áp dụng phương pháp nghiên cứu tại bàn, điều tra các số liệu, báo cáo từ các tổ chức như Google, Facebook, eMarketer, Statista,... để làm rõ thực trạng và xu hướng phát triển của Thương mại điện tử ở Việt Nam những năm gần đây cũng như chỉ ra các rủi ro tồn tại trong quá trình phát triển thương mại điện tử tại Việt Nam, từ đó đề xuất một số giải pháp hạn chế rủi ro trong thương mại điện tử nhằm phát triển thị trường này một cách an toàn tại Việt Nam.

3. THỰC TRẠNG THƯƠNG MẠI ĐIỆN TỬ TẠI VIỆT NAM HIỆN NAY

3.1. Sự phát triển thương mại điện tử tại Việt Nam

Sàn thương mại điện tử hiện là một trong các kênh bán hàng hiệu quả và thu hút nhiều người bán cũng như người mua. Sàn thương mại điện tử là một website mà trên đó diễn ra hoạt động mua bán trực tuyến của nhiều cá nhân, tổ chức khác nhau trên cùng 1 website. Các sàn thương mại điện tử hàng đầu ở Việt Nam gồm Tiki, Lazada, Shopee, Sendo, GoMua ... Sàn thương mại điện tử ngày càng được quan tâm do có số lượng hàng hóa cực kỳ đa dạng, giá hợp lý, thường xuyên có các chương trình khuyến mãi khủng và các hoạt động quảng bá, marketing mạnh mẽ.

Trong khi người tiêu dùng có được nhiều lợi ích từ việc mua sản phẩm trực tuyến. Các doanh nghiệp cũng được hưởng lợi từ chi phí kinh doanh thấp hơn khi các doanh nghiệp thương mại điện tử không phải trả tiền để duy trì cửa hàng thực tế và chi phí thuê nhân công làm việc cũng ít hơn vì ít chu trình vận hành hơn. Bên cạnh đó, doanh nghiệp cũng có thể tiếp cận nhiều tệp khách hàng ở nhiều nơi thậm chí là cả quốc tế cũng như cho phép các doanh nghiệp thu thập dữ liệu khách hàng. Dựa vào đó, doanh nghiệp có thể phân tích thói quen mua hàng, nhân khẩu học và sở thích của khách hàng để tiếp thị sản phẩm tốt hơn. Doanh nghiệp sử dụng dữ liệu đó để dự đoán nhu cầu đối với một sản phẩm mà khách hàng cần, từ đó giúp giảm nguy cơ tồn kho quá nhiều hoặc thiếu sản phẩm. Các công ty cũng có thể sử dụng thông tin này để giúp khách hàng có trải nghiệm mua sắm dễ dàng hơn.

Biểu đồ 1: Doanh thu kinh tế Internet Đông Nam Á năm 2021 và dự báo năm 2025

Đơn vị tính: Tỷ USD

Nguồn: Báo cáo Kinh tế khu vực Đông Nam Á năm 2021" của Google, Temasek và Bain&Company

Biểu đồ cho thấy trong khu vực Đông Nam Á, kinh tế Internet của Việt Nam khá phát triển, chỉ đứng sau Indonesia và Thái Lan. Tuy nhiên với mức độ phát triển như hiện tại, dự báo năm 2025 doanh thu kinh tế Internet của Việt Nam có thể vượt qua Thái Lan để xếp thứ hai. Có thể thấy doanh thu từ các loại hình kinh tế trên Internet của Indonesia khá nổi bật với doanh thu 70 tỷ USD vào năm 2021, gấp hơn 3 lần Việt Nam, dự báo sẽ tăng gấp đôi vào năm 2025.

Bảng 1: Doanh thu TMĐT B2C Việt Nam năm 2017 – 2021

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Ước tính số lượng người tiêu dùng mua sắm trực tuyến (triệu người)	33,6	39,9	44,8	49,3	54,6
Ước tính giá trị mua sắm trực tuyến của một người (USD)	186	202	225	240	251
Tỷ trọng doanh thu TMĐT B2C so với tổng mức bán lẻ hàng hóa và dịch vụ tiêu dùng cả nước	3,6%	4,2%	4,9%	5,5%	7%
Tỷ lệ người dân sử dụng Internet	58,1%	60%	66%	70%	73%

Nguồn: Cục TMĐT và Kinh tế số, Sách trắng TMĐT Việt Nam năm 2022

Nhìn vào bảng 1, có thể thấy lượng khách hàng tham gia vào mua sắm trực tuyến cũng như giá trị mua sắm trực tuyến của một người tiêu dùng tăng dần trong giai đoạn từ 2017 - 2021. Bên cạnh đó, TMĐT B2C cũng ngày càng chiếm nhiều thị phần hơn trong mức doanh thu bán lẻ hàng hóa và dịch vụ tiêu dùng cả nước. Đến năm 2021, lượng người tiêu dùng mua

sắm trực tuyến đã đạt 54,6 triệu người, tăng hơn 20 triệu người so với năm 2017. Tỷ trọng doanh thu TMĐT so với tổng mức bán lẻ hàng hóa và dịch vụ cả nước đã chiếm 7% tổng thị phần vào năm 2021, tăng gấp đôi trong giai đoạn này.

Biểu đồ 2: Quy mô thị trường thương mại điện tử bán lẻ tại Việt Nam

Đơn vị tính: Tỷ USD

Nguồn: Cục TMĐT và Kinh tế số, Sách trắng TMĐT Việt Nam năm 2022

Biểu đồ đã phân tích doanh thu bán lẻ của các doanh nghiệp kinh doanh trên các nền tảng TMĐT tại Việt Nam giai đoạn 2017 - 2022. Nhận thấy doanh thu B2C trên các nền tảng TMĐT tăng đều, với tốc độ tăng trưởng cũng đáng kể, khoảng 20%/năm. Giai đoạn 2017 - 2019 chứng kiến sự bùng nổ của TMĐT với tốc độ tăng trưởng lớn, chạm mức 30% vào năm 2018. Tốc độ này trong những năm tiếp theo duy trì ở mức khoảng 20%.

Ngày 15/05/2020, Thủ tướng Chính phủ đã ban hành Quyết định 645/QĐ-TTg phê duyệt Kế hoạch tổng thể phát triển TMĐT quốc gia giai đoạn 2021 - 2025. Trong đó, Chính phủ đặt ra mục tiêu phát triển quy mô thị trường TMĐT đến năm 2025 như sau: : 55% dân số tham gia mua sắm trực tuyến, với giá trị mua hàng hóa và dịch vụ trực tuyến đạt trung bình 600 USD/người/năm; Doanh số TMĐT B2C (tính cho cả hàng hóa và dịch vụ tiêu dùng trực tuyến) tăng 25%/năm, đạt 35 tỷ USD, chiếm 10% so với tổng mức bán lẻ hàng hóa và doanh thu dịch vụ tiêu dùng cả nước. Nhằm góp phần triển khai thành công Kế hoạch tổng thể phát triển TMĐT quốc gia giai đoạn 2021 - 2025, một trong những giải pháp quan trọng là mở rộng và đa dạng hóa các kênh TMĐT.

Biểu đồ 3: Doanh thu các loại kinh tế Internet tại Việt Nam giai đoạn 2019 – 2022

Đơn vị tính: Tỷ USD

Nguồn: Báo cáo Kinh tế khu vực Đông Nam Á năm 2022" của Google, Temasek và Bain & Company

Nhìn vào biểu đồ, có thể thấy doanh thu TMĐT tại Việt Nam tăng đều trong giai đoạn từ 2019 - 2022. Trong đó, TMĐT tại Việt Nam phát triển vượt bậc vào năm 2022, tăng lên gấp 3 lần đạt 39 tỷ USD. Các ngành kinh tế trên Internet khác của Việt Nam cũng tăng đều, tuy nhiên doanh thu của các lĩnh vực này chỉ dừng ở mức 7 tỷ USD. Có thể thấy hiện nay TMĐT đang phát triển với một tốc độ "chóng mặt", vì thế việc phân tích các rủi ro trong TMĐT và đưa ra giải pháp kiểm soát các rủi ro này càng trở nên cấp thiết.

3.2. Những rủi ro trong thương mại điện tử

Cùng với sự phát triển không ngừng của lĩnh vực công nghệ thông tin, các dịch vụ mua bán thông qua hoạt động thương mại điện tử (TMĐT), chủ yếu là mua, bán qua in-to-nét ra đời đã nhanh chóng trở thành xu hướng tiêu dùng mới của cuộc sống hiện đại. Tuy nhiên, bên cạnh những lợi ích mà TMĐT đem lại, người tiêu dùng cũng đang phải đối mặt với không ít rủi ro. Hàng năm Bộ Công thương vẫn nhận được nhiều những khiếu nại, phản ánh về việc quản lý hoạt động thương mại điện tử cũng như những rủi ro bất cập mà doanh nghiệp cũng như người tiêu dùng gặp phải khi tham gia vào các sàn thương mại điện tử.

Theo EY (tổ chức nghiên cứu thị trường), 66% số lượng công ty được phỏng vấn đã chia sẻ tán thành về việc họ đã từng gặp vấn đề về bảo mật thông tin. 65% số lượng công ty bị chính nhân viên nội bộ làm ảnh hưởng trực diện bằng việc tiết lộ thông tin bảo mật thương mại điện tử. Và có đến 40% không có sự nghiên cứu và phòng vệ nào về rủi ro trong quá trình bảo mật thông tin riêng tư. Theo số liệu từ Juniper Research, trong giai đoạn 2021- 2025, tổng thiệt hại mà doanh nghiệp phải gánh chịu bởi các hình thức gian lận thanh toán trực tuyến sẽ lên đến con số 206 tỷ USD. Đây chỉ là một trong nhiều cách mà tin tặc thường xuyên sử dụng để tấn công mạng trong ngành thương mại điện tử. Để giảm thiểu rủi ro, doanh nghiệp cần có những biện pháp đảm bảo an ninh thương mại điện tử. Ebay - một trong những trang thương mại điện tử lớn nhất thế giới là ví dụ điển hình. Với hàng trăm triệu người dùng trên toàn cầu, lỗ hổng

trong việc bảo mật website thương mại điện tử khiến thông tin cá nhân của 145 triệu thành viên đăng ký bị đánh cắp và lan truyền ra bên ngoài.

Biểu đồ 4: Tỷ lệ phản ánh, khiếu nại về quản lý hoạt động thương mại điện tử trong năm 2021

Nguồn: Cục TMĐT và Kinh tế số, Sách trắng TMĐT Việt Nam năm 2022

Nhìn vào biểu đồ có thể thấy có đến gần 80% các phản ánh liên quan đến việc doanh nghiệp kinh doanh trên các nền tảng thương mại điện tử nhưng chưa đăng ký thông báo với Bộ Công Thương. Lý do một phần do doanh nghiệp chưa hiểu rõ các quy định, chính sách về thương mại điện tử, hoặc chưa được tư vấn tìm hiểu các thủ tục đăng ký, khai báo rõ ràng. Bên cạnh đó, hơn 10% số vụ khiếu nại, phản ánh liên quan đến giả mạo thông tin đăng ký. Còn lại, các vấn đề như kinh doanh hàng giả hàng nhái, mạo danh giả mạo website, lừa đảo trong thanh toán,... cũng là những vấn đề được phản ánh trên Cổng thông tin quản lý hoạt động TMĐT trong năm 2021.

Tại Việt Nam, cùng với sự phát triển mạnh mẽ về số lượng người dùng Internet, đặc biệt là mua sắm online, các vụ tấn công mạng gia tăng, kể cả về số lượng, quy mô; các hình thức tấn công tinh vi hơn. Trung tâm ứng cứu khẩn cấp máy tính Việt Nam đã ghi nhận và xử lý gần 10.000 vụ tấn công website. Trong đó, gần 50% các sự cố đến từ phát tán mã độc thông qua những lỗ hổng bảo mật.

Tham gia bán hàng trên sàn TMĐT có nhiều ưu điểm như tiếp cận được lượng khách hàng lớn, được hỗ trợ vận chuyển và chăm sóc khách hàng, tận dụng các chương trình marketing và uy tín của sàn để bán hàng... Tuy nhiên khi tham gia sàn thương mại điện tử cũng ẩn chứa nhiều rủi ro, những rủi ro chủ yếu các doanh nghiệp có thể phải chịu như sau:

- Virus: Virus tấn công vào thương mại điện tử thường gồm 3 loại chính: virus ảnh hưởng tới các tệp (file) chương trình (gắn liền với những file chương trình, thường là .COM hoặc .EXE), virus ảnh hưởng tới hệ thống (đĩa cứng hoặc đĩa khởi động), và virus macro. Virus macro là loại virus phổ biến nhất, chiếm từ 75% đến 80% trong tổng số các virus được phát hiện. Đây là loại virus đặc biệt chỉ nhắm vào các tệp ứng dụng soạn thảo, chẳng hạn như các tệp ứng dụng của MS Word, Excel và Power Point. Khi người sử dụng mở các tài liệu bị

nhiễm virus trong các chương trình ứng dụng, virus này sẽ tự tạo ra các bản sao và nhiễm vào các tệp chứa đựng các khuôn mẫu của ứng dụng, để từ đó lây sang các tài liệu khác. Các loại virus có thể gây ra những tác hại nghiêm trọng, đe dọa tính toàn vẹn và khả năng hoạt động liên tục, thay đổi các chức năng, thay đổi các nội dung dữ liệu hoặc đôi khi làm ngưng trệ toàn bộ hoạt động của nhiều hệ thống trong đó có các website thương mại điện tử. Nó được đánh giá là mối đe dọa lớn nhất đối với an toàn của các giao dịch thương mại điện tử hiện nay.

- Tin tặc (hacker) và các chương trình phá hoại (cybervandalism): Tin tặc hay tội phạm máy tính là thuật ngữ dùng để chỉ những người truy cập trái phép vào một website, một cơ sở dữ liệu hay hệ thống thông tin. Thực chất mục tiêu của các hacker rất đa dạng. Có thể là hệ thống dữ liệu của các website thương mại điện tử, hoặc với ý đồ nguy hiểm hơn chúng có thể sử dụng các chương trình phá hoại (cybervandalism) nhằm gây ra các sự cố, làm mất uy tín hoặc phá huỷ website trên phạm vi toàn cầu. Ngày 1-4-2001, tin tặc đã sử dụng chương trình phá hoại tấn công vào các máy chủ có sử dụng phần mềm Internet Information Server (IIS) của Microsoft nhằm làm giảm uy tín của phần mềm này và rất nhiều nạn nhân như hãng hoạt hình Walt Disney, Nhật báo phố Wall ... đã phải gánh chịu hậu quả cả về tài chính và uy tín.

- Rủi ro về gian lận thẻ tín dụng: Trong thương mại điện tử, các hành vi gian lận thẻ tín dụng xảy ra đa dạng và phức tạp hơn nhiều so với thương mại truyền thống. Nếu như trong thương mại truyền thống, việc mất thẻ hoặc thẻ bị đánh cắp là mối đe dọa lớn nhất đối với khách hàng thì trong thương mại điện tử mối đe dọa lớn nhất là bị “mất” (hay bị lộ) các thông tin liên quan đến thẻ tín dụng hoặc các thông tin giao dịch sử dụng thẻ tín dụng trong quá trình thực hiện các giao dịch mua sắm qua mạng và các thiết bị điện tử. Các tệp chứa dữ liệu thẻ tín dụng của khách hàng thường là những mục tiêu hấp dẫn đối với tin tặc khi tấn công vào website thương mại điện tử. Hơn thế, những tên tội phạm có thể đột nhập vào các cơ sở dữ liệu của website thương mại điện tử để lấy cắp các thông tin của khách hàng như tên, địa chỉ, điện thoại... với những thông tin này chúng có thể mạo danh khách hàng thiết lập các khoản tín dụng mới nhằm phục vụ những mục đích phi pháp.

- Tấn công từ chối dịch vụ (DOS - Denial Of Service attack, DDOS – Distributed DOS hay DR DOS): là kiểu tấn công khiến một hệ thống máy tính hoặc một mạng bị quá tải, dẫn tới không thể cung cấp dịch vụ hoặc phải dừng hoạt động. Sơ khai nhất là hình thức DoS (Denial of Service), lợi dụng sự yếu kém của giao thức TCP, tiếp đến là DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) - tấn công từ chối dịch vụ phân tán, và gần đây là DRDoS - tấn công theo phương pháp phản xạ phân tán (Distributed Reflection Denial of Service). Những cuộc tấn công DoS có thể là nguyên nhân khiến cho mạng máy tính ngừng hoạt động và trong thời gian đó, người sử dụng sẽ không thể truy cập vào các website thương mại điện tử. Những tấn công này cũng đồng nghĩa với những khoản chi phí rất lớn vì trong thời gian website ngừng hoạt động, khách hàng không thể thực hiện các giao dịch mua bán. Đồng thời, sự gián đoạn hoạt động này sẽ ảnh hưởng đến uy tín và tiếng tăm của doanh nghiệp, những điều không dễ dàng gì lấy lại được. Mặc dù những cuộc tấn công này không phá huỷ thông tin hay truy cập vào những vùng cấm của máy chủ nhưng tạo ra phiền toái, gây trở ngại cho hoạt động của nhiều doanh nghiệp. Vụ tấn công DOS điển hình đầu tiên xảy ra vào tháng 2-2000, các hoạt động tấn công liên tục khiến hàng loạt website trên thế giới ngừng hoạt động trong nhiều giờ, trong đó có những website hàng đầu như: eBay ngừng hoạt động trong 5 giờ, Amazon gần 4 giờ, CNN gần 3.5 giờ, E-Trade gần 3 giờ, Yahoo và Buy.com và ZDNet cũng ngừng hoạt động từ 3 đến 4 giờ. Ngay cả người khổng lồ Microsoft cũng đã từng phải gánh chịu hậu quả của những cuộc tấn

công này. Ở Việt Nam, cũng đã có rất nhiều doanh nghiệp bị tấn công dưới hình thức này.

- Kê trộm trên mạng (sniffer): là một dạng của chương trình theo dõi, nghe trộm, giám sát sự di chuyển của thông tin trên mạng. Khi sử dụng vào những mục đích hợp pháp, nó có thể giúp phát hiện ra những yếu điểm của mạng, nhưng ngược lại, nếu sử dụng vào các mục đích phi pháp, các phần mềm ứng dụng này sẽ trở thành các mối hiểm họa lớn và rất khó có thể phát hiện. Kê trộm sử dụng các phần mềm này nhằm lấy cắp các thông tin có giá trị như thư điện tử, dữ liệu kinh doanh của các doanh nghiệp, các báo cáo mật... từ bất cứ nơi nào trên mạng. Xem lén thư điện tử là một dạng mới của hành vi trộm cắp trên mạng. Kỹ thuật xem lén thư điện tử là sử dụng một đoạn mã (ẩn) bí mật gắn vào thông điệp thư điện tử, cho phép người nào đó có thể giám sát toàn bộ các thông điệp chuyển tiếp được gửi đi cùng với thông điệp ban đầu. Chẳng hạn một nhân viên phát hiện thấy lỗi kỹ thuật trong khâu sản xuất, anh ta lập tức gửi một báo cáo thông báo cho cấp trên về phát hiện của mình. Người này sau đó sẽ tiếp tục gửi thông báo đến tất cả các bộ phận có liên quan trong doanh nghiệp. Một kẻ nào đó sử dụng kỹ thuật xem lén thư điện tử có thể theo dõi và biết được toàn bộ thông tin trong bức thư điện tử gửi tiếp sau đó bàn về vấn đề này.

- Phishing - “kẻ giả mạo”: là một loại tội phạm công nghệ cao sử dụng email, tin nhắn pop-up hay trang web để lừa người dùng cung cấp các thông tin cá nhân nhạy cảm như thẻ tín dụng, mật khẩu, số tài khoản ngân hàng. Thông thường các tin tặc thường giả mạo là các công ty nổi tiếng yêu cầu khách hàng cung cấp những thông tin nhạy cảm này. Các website thường xuyên bị giả mạo đó là Paypal, Ebay, MSN, Yahoo, BestBuy, American Online... Kê giả mạo thường hướng tới phishing những khách hàng của ngân hàng và người tiêu dùng thường mua sắm trực tuyến. Những thông tin ăn cắp được sẽ được kẻ giả mạo dùng để truy cập với mục đích xấu, nếu là thông tin về tài khoản thanh toán thì sẽ dùng vào mục đích mua hàng hoặc rút tiền. Bất cứ ai cũng có thể phishing được vì phần mềm phishing là có nhiều trên mạng với hướng dẫn chi tiết cùng với danh sách địa chỉ email. Công nghệ phishing là đã có từ những năm 1987, tuy nhiên nó chỉ thực sự biết đến rộng rãi vào năm 1996. AOL là công ty đầu tiên đã bị kẻ giả mạo tấn công ăn cắp thông tin của khách hàng. Hay Vào 17/12/2003 một số khách hàng của eBay nhận được email với thông báo rằng hiện tại tài khoản của họ tạm ngừng hoạt động cho tới khi họ kích vào đường link được cung cấp trong email và cập nhật thông tin về thẻ tín dụng, cùng với các thông tin cá nhân khác như ngày sinh, tên thời con gái của mẹ, số Pin của thẻ ATM. Đường link trong địa chỉ email kết nối tới trang web của ebay nhưng đây không phải là trang web thật của ebay mà chỉ là một trang web giả mạo có logo và hình thức giống với trang web ebay thật. PayPal một trang web giải pháp thanh toán cũng là đối tượng thường xuyên bị giả mạo. Kẻ giả mạo Paypal đã xây dựng URL cái trang giống URL của Paypal bằng cách sử dụng ký hiệu @ (<http://paypal.com@218.36.41.188/fl/login.html>). Thường thì các server bỏ qua các ký tự trước @ và chỉ sử dụng những ký tự sau nó. Như vậy là khách hàng chỉ có thể nhìn thấy đường link trong mail như <http://paypal.com> Chính vì vậy mà khách hàng đã không nhận ra được là mình đang bị tấn công từ các tin tặc và đã cung cấp nhưng thông tin cá nhân và tài khoản.

- Ngoài ra, tội phạm TMĐT được thực hiện dưới nhiều hình thức sau: phát triển các mạng máy tính ma (bots network) để tấn công DOS, gửi thư rác, gửi thư rác với quy mô lớn (dịch vụ thư rác), thuê hacker phá hoại website của đối thủ cạnh tranh, thu thập thông tin người sử dụng bằng spyware.

4. ĐỀ XUẤT MỘT SỐ GIẢI PHÁP KIỂM SOÁT RỦI RO TRONG THƯƠNG MẠI ĐIỆN TỬ

4.1. Đối với cá nhân người tiêu dùng

Về phía người tiêu dùng, phải thực sự là “người tiêu dùng thông minh”, hiểu rõ các rủi ro trong thương mại điện tử để tự có các biện pháp phòng tránh cũng như bảo vệ bản thân. Trước hết, cá nhân cần biết tự bảo vệ password của bản thân - càng ít người biết mật khẩu tài khoản cá nhân càng tốt, tốt nhất không chia sẻ mật khẩu với người khác, đặc biệt là mật khẩu các ứng dụng thương mại điện tử và ứng dụng thanh toán online. Người dùng cũng nên thay đổi mật khẩu các tài khoản thường xuyên, mật khẩu sử dụng đủ mạnh và không dễ đoán. Khi cá nhân nhận các email, tin nhắn spam, cần xóa bỏ và tránh ấn vào các đường link không rõ nguồn gốc trong email, cũng như không mở các file gửi kèm từ những email không rõ nguồn gốc này. Bên cạnh đó, người dùng nên sử dụng và cài đặt các phần mềm diệt virus mới nhất và cập nhật thường xuyên nhằm tránh những phá hoại hay rủi ro do virus gây ra. Người dùng cũng nên sử dụng các chương trình bản quyền thay vì sử dụng các phần mềm không rõ nguồn gốc hay các ứng dụng hack bởi các link tải về hay các ứng dụng này có thể chứa virus cũng như đánh cắp thông tin người dùng, xâm nhập trái phép vào hệ thống máy tính hay tài khoản của người sử dụng.

Bên cạnh đó, để đảm bảo bí mật cho mật khẩu, người dùng nên sử dụng các password đủ mạnh. Khi thiết lập mật khẩu cho các tài khoản, người dùng nên xem xét các tiêu chí như: Mật khẩu có số ký tự đủ lớn, tối thiểu 8 ký tự và có sự kết hợp giữa chữ hoa, chữ thường, chữ số và biểu tượng. Như vậy sẽ mất rất nhiều thời gian mới có thể tìm ra và phá mật khẩu, mà tới thời gian đó mật khẩu đã có thể đã được thay đổi. Mật khẩu cũng nên thường xuyên thay đổi (thường từ 30-60 ngày) và không nên sử dụng lại mật khẩu cũ; Kích hoạt tự động việc khóa không cho truy cập hệ thống nếu sau từ 3-5 lần nhập mật khẩu vẫn không đúng; Không sử dụng chức năng tự động điền (auto complete) của một số phần mềm ứng dụng như Microsoft Explorer để lưu mật khẩu và số tài khoản.

4.2. Đối với doanh nghiệp

Về phía doanh nghiệp, doanh nghiệp cần chú ý đến thiết kế luồng kinh doanh hợp lý, kiểm soát chặt chẽ truy xuất dữ liệu theo nguyên tắc “khách hàng truy cập thông tin với quyền hạn phù hợp định trước”. Tiếp đó, kiểm soát chặt chẽ và áp dụng các kiểm tra an toàn thông tin ngay từ khi phát triển ứng dụng và sau khi đưa vào cung cấp. Cuối cùng, doanh nghiệp cần định kỳ tiến hành rà soát và đánh giá lại mức độ an toàn của các hệ thống của mình vì theo thời gian hệ thống thường xuất hiện các lỗ hổng, rủi ro mới. Doanh nghiệp cần thay đổi cơ cấu kịp thời; chiến lược và phương pháp quản lý phù hợp; thích nghi với xu hướng mới; đầu tư và nâng cấp an ninh mạng để phòng ngừa tội phạm công nghệ cao nhằm khai thác triệt để những cơ hội và hạn chế tối thiểu những rủi ro, hạn chế mà TMĐT mang đến.

Một số công nghệ được phát triển nhằm đảm bảo rằng trong nội bộ mạng của một doanh nghiệp, các hoạt động sẽ được đảm bảo an toàn khỏi các vụ tấn công hoặc xâm phạm từ bên ngoài, đồng thời có chức năng cảnh báo các hoạt động tấn công từ bên ngoài vào hệ thống mạng.

- Tường lửa: Tường lửa là một thành phần của mạng, gồm phần mềm hoặc phần cứng hoặc kết hợp cả phần mềm và phần cứng, cho phép những người sử dụng mạng máy tính của một tổ chức có thể truy cập tài nguyên của các mạng khác (ví dụ, mạng Internet), nhưng đồng thời ngăn cấm những người sử dụng khác, không được phép từ bên ngoài truy cập vào mạng máy tính của tổ chức.

- Mạng riêng ảo (VPN): Khi công ty muốn tạo ra một ứng dụng B2B, cung cấp cho các nhà cung cấp, đối tác và những đối tượng khác quyền truy cập không chỉ với dữ liệu đặt trên trang web của họ, mà còn cả quyền truy cập đối với dữ liệu chứa trong các tệp khác (như tệp Word, Excel, file đồ họa, file âm thanh, hình ảnh...). Theo cách truyền thống, liên lạc với công ty có thể thực hiện thông qua một đường truyền riêng hoặc thông qua một đường quay số tới modem hoặc tới một máy chủ truy cập từ xa (RAS - Remote Access Server) mà máy chủ này cho phép kết nối trực tiếp tới mạng LAN của công ty. Ưu điểm của việc thuê đường truyền riêng là giảm thiểu khả năng bị hacker nghe trộm các liên lạc, tuy nhiên chi phí lại cao. Do đó, doanh nghiệp có thể tham khảo một giải pháp kinh tế hơn đó là sử dụng mạng riêng ảo. Mạng riêng ảo sử dụng mạng internet để truyền tải thông tin nhưng vẫn duy trì sự bí mật bằng cách sử dụng thuật mã khóa (để mã giao dịch, xác minh tính chân thực để đảm bảo rằng thông tin không bị truy xuất trái phép và thông tin đến từ những nguồn tin cậy) và quản lý quyền truy cập để xác định danh tính của bất kỳ ai sử dụng mạng này. Hơn nữa, một mạng riêng ảo cũng có thể được sử dụng để hỗ trợ những liên lạc giữa các chi nhánh và trụ sở công ty và những liên lạc giữa các công nhân lưu động với trụ sở làm việc của họ. Số lượng các doanh nghiệp sử dụng hình thức này ngày càng tăng, điều này thể hiện ở doanh số của thị trường dịch vụ mạng riêng ảo toàn thế giới, năm 2005 đã đạt mức 23 tỷ USD vào năm 2005 và hứa hẹn sẽ tăng thêm 22% trong vòng 3 năm tới.

- Phòng chống virus: Theo thống kê, trung bình mỗi tháng có hơn 500 virus ra đời, do đó doanh nghiệp nên sử dụng các phần mềm chống virus để kiểm tra tất cả các dữ liệu hoặc được truyền qua cổng máy chủ ở mạng hoặc truyền giữa các cổng nội bộ. Các phần mềm chống virus cũng nên được cập nhật thường xuyên (hàng ngày, hàng tuần). Thông thường, các công ty phần mềm virus uy tín thường gửi email tới khách hàng thông báo về việc xuất hiện những virus mới và cung cấp công cụ update tự động cho khách hàng. Định dạng cổng email để khóa các tệp có đuôi dạng VBS, SHS, EXE, SCR, CHM và BAT hoặc những tệp có hai phần mở rộng dạng như .txt.vbs hoặc .jpg.vbs vì những tệp dạng này thường do virus tạo ra. Phổ biến kiến thức cho người sử dụng, ví dụ, không mở những email lạ có tệp đính kèm, thậm chí từ người gửi có tên trong sổ địa chỉ; không tải về những tệp từ những nguồn không rõ ràng; thường xuyên quét virus; cập nhật phần mềm quét virus thường xuyên; không gửi những cảnh báo về virus hoặc các thư dây chuyền cho những người sử dụng khác.

- Giải pháp an ninh nguồn nhân lực: Các doanh nghiệp cần lưu ý mọi nhân viên trong doanh nghiệp mình ý thức về vấn đề an ninh mạng và những nguy cơ tấn công doanh nghiệp có thể chịu trong trường hợp thiếu kinh nghiệm hoặc thiếu sự lưu tâm đúng mức từ phía các nhân viên. Nhân viên cũng cần được lưu ý về các giải pháp an toàn mạng nên áp dụng như việc chọn mật khẩu, thay đổi mật khẩu, quét virus thường xuyên hay xóa bỏ những email lạ.

- Giải pháp về trang thiết bị an ninh mạng: Sử dụng các thiết bị kiểm soát việc ra vào trụ sở làm việc như : các thẻ từ, mã điện tử, thẻ thông minh hoặc các thiết bị nhận dạng nhân trắc như kiểm tra vân tay, võng mạc hoặc giọng nói. Các biện pháp khác có thể là sao lưu dữ liệu

vào những nơi an toàn, đánh dấu nhận dạng tia cực tím, các hệ thống phát hiện xâm phạm như camera và chuông báo động.

4.3. Đối với Chính phủ

Chính phủ cần có các chiến lược đầu tư phát triển cơ sở hạ tầng, nâng cấp mạng Internet một cách kịp thời và đúng đắn. Bên cạnh đó, các chế tài, quy định chặt chẽ trong kinh doanh TMĐT cũng là các nhân tố quan trọng góp phần đảm bảo quyền và lợi ích hợp pháp của các bên liên quan như: doanh nghiệp, đối tác, khách hàng,... Ngoài ra, các nhà cung cấp dịch vụ viễn thông phải có trách nhiệm thực hiện các giải pháp kỹ thuật nhằm ngăn chặn và chấm dứt hành vi vi phạm đối với tình trạng tin nhắn rác để bảo đảm quyền lợi của người mua. Mặt khác, liên quan đến chứng từ trong giao dịch điện tử, luật cũng cần có các quy định về trách nhiệm của người bán trong việc tạo điều kiện cho người tiêu dùng truy cập, tải, lưu giữ và in hóa đơn, chứng từ, tài liệu liên quan đến giao dịch. Để đáp ứng quy định này, các trang web bán hàng qua mạng cần tích hợp các giải pháp kỹ thuật nhằm đảm bảo khả năng truy cập, sao lưu chứng từ của người tiêu dùng,... Điều này rất cần sự quan tâm của Chính phủ, việc ban hành các văn bản quy phạm pháp luật điều chỉnh hành vi giao dịch trong TMĐT cũng như bảo vệ quyền lợi của người tiêu dùng càng trở nên quan trọng.

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SỬ DỤNG MÔ HÌNH CÂY QUYẾT ĐỊNH XÁC ĐỊNH TIÊU CHÍ NHẬN DIỆN DOANH NGHIỆP XÁC SỐNG Ở VIỆT NAM

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Khoa Toán kinh tế, Đại học Kinh tế quốc dân

Tóm tắt

Cây quyết định là một phương pháp học tập có giám sát phi tham số được sử dụng để phân loại và hồi quy. Mục tiêu là tạo ra một mô hình dự đoán giá trị của một biến mục tiêu bằng cách tìm hiểu các quy tắc quyết định đơn giản được suy ra từ các tính năng dữ liệu. Bằng việc phân tích dữ liệu từ 753 doanh nghiệp được niêm yết trên 3 sàn chứng khoán HOSE, HNX và UPCOM, tác giả đã chỉ ra xu hướng dịch chuyển tỷ lệ các doanh nghiệp xác sống sang sàn UPCOM trong 2 năm 2019-2020 do chịu ảnh hưởng của đại dịch COVID19. Đồng thời với tỷ trọng doanh nghiệp lớn ở hai nhóm ngành Sản xuất; Xây dựng và bất động sản, mô hình Cây quyết định đã xác định các tiêu chuẩn hình thành doanh nghiệp xác sống ở nhóm ngành này nói riêng và các doanh nghiệp tại Việt Nam nói chung là tỉ lệ bao phủ lãi suất nhỏ hơn 1 trong ba năm liên tiếp và lợi nhuận kinh doanh trong năm âm. Điểm mạnh có thể thấy rất rõ của phương pháp này là xác định được các ngưỡng ảnh hưởng của tiêu chí nhận diện so với mô hình hồi quy thông thường chỉ nêu ra được chiều của tác động tới xác suất hình thành doanh nghiệp xác sống.

Từ khóa: Doanh nghiệp xác sống, Cây quyết định, Cây phân loại và hồi quy

Abstract

Decision tree is a non-parametric supervised learning method used for classification and regression. The goal is to create a model that predicts the value of a target variable by learning simple decision rules inferred from data features. By analyzing data from 753 firm listed on HOSE, HNX and UPCOM, the author has shown the trend of shifting the proportion of zombie firm to UPCOM in 2 years 2019-2020 due to affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Simultaneously with a large proportion of enterprises in two groups of Manufacturing industries; Construction and real estate, the Decision tree model has determined the standards for the formation of zombie firm in the industry group in particular and businesses in Vietnam in general, the rate of interest coverage is less than 1 in 3 consecutive years and business profit is negative. The obvious strength of this method is that it can determine the impact thresholds of the identification criteria compared to the conventional regression model that only shows the dimension of the impact on the probability of forming a zombie firm.

Keywords: Zombie firm, Decision tree, Classification and Regression Tree (CART)

1. GIỚI THIỆU

Các doanh nghiệp xác sống thường được xác định là các doanh nghiệp làm ăn kém hiệu quả, thiếu khả năng sinh lời trong thời gian dài và không có khả năng đối phó với các khoản nợ

của họ. Điều này xuất phát trực tiếp từ việc kém hiệu quả trong hoạt động kinh doanh (Banerjee & Hofmann, 2018). Tuy nhiên việc xác định chính xác các chỉ số quyết định việc một doanh nghiệp trở thành doanh nghiệp xác sống vẫn còn là một khó khăn. Chúng ta có thể biết đến một số yếu tố rõ ràng như tuổi của doanh nghiệp, quy mô và ngành có thể giải thích hiện tượng này. Tuy nhiên, vẫn còn thiếu các nghiên cứu phân tích một cách kỹ lưỡng các đặc điểm và hành vi của các doanh nghiệp trong quá trình sản xuất, kinh doanh, để từ đó có thể tiến hành phân loại một cách chính xác các doanh nghiệp xác sống. Để có thực hiện được yêu cầu này đòi hỏi sử dụng tới phương pháp nghiên cứu một cách chuyên sâu hơn.

Các nghiên cứu về chủ đề này sử dụng các tiêu chí xác định doanh nghiệp xác sống khá đa dạng và phong phú, tuy nhiên, các tiêu chí đều quan tâm đến khả năng thanh toán tiền lãi và lợi nhuận của doanh nghiệp. Nhiều mô hình từ đơn giản đến phức tạp đã được sử dụng bởi nhiều học giả trên khắp thế giới cho các vấn đề liên quan đến doanh nghiệp xác sống hay cụ thể là vấn đề nhận diện các yếu tố quyết định việc hình thành doanh nghiệp xác sống. Các mô hình học máy thường cho kết quả tốt cho quy trình nhận diện với trường hợp dữ liệu lớn, trong bài nghiên cứu sử dụng một phương pháp học tập có giám sát là mô hình cây quyết định. Phương pháp này phù hợp với mục đích nghiên cứu vì có sức mạnh để học từ dữ liệu đầu vào và tách chúng thành các biến quan trọng đồng thời phân ngưỡng trong quá trình dự báo một doanh nghiệp xác sống.

Với bối cảnh như vậy, nhóm tác giả đã quyết định thực hiện đề tài nghiên cứu **“Sử dụng mô hình Cây quyết định xác định tiêu chí nhận diện doanh nghiệp xác sống tại Việt Nam”** nhằm tìm ra một số tiêu chí liên quan đến hoạt động sản xuất kinh doanh của doanh nghiệp để xác định một doanh nghiệp có phải doanh nghiệp xác sống hay không? Từ đó có các chính sách ưu đãi, hỗ trợ phù hợp và đúng các đối tượng doanh nghiệp mà Chính phủ muốn hướng tới, giảm thiểu các tác động tiêu cực của các doanh nghiệp xác sống đến nền kinh tế.

2. TỔNG QUAN NGHIÊN CỨU & CƠ SỞ LÝ THUYẾT

Doanh nghiệp xác sống (hay công ty Zombie) là thuật ngữ nguyên thủy để chỉ những doanh nghiệp được xem là nguyên nhân đưa nước Nhật vào hai thập niên đình trệ kinh tế (Caballero và cộng sự, 2008). Từ năm 2000, nghiên cứu vấn đề này đã và đang thu hút sự quan tâm, nghiên cứu của các học giả cũng như các nhà quản lý và hoạch định chính sách tại nhiều quốc gia như Mỹ, Nhật Bản, Hàn Quốc, Trung Quốc, và EU, ... Xu hướng nghiên cứu vấn đề này lại được tiếp tục sau cuộc khủng hoảng tài chính 2008-2009 khi mức lãi suất toàn cầu giảm xuống mức thấp kỷ lục, một loạt các cuộc khủng hoảng hệ lụy kéo theo như khủng hoảng nợ công ở châu Âu, suy thoái kinh tế trên diện rộng ở hàng loạt quốc gia, khủng hoảng nợ xấu trong hệ thống ngân hàng của Trung Quốc hay Việt Nam,... Theo báo cáo của Ngân hàng Thanh toán quốc tế (Bank for International Settlements –BIS, 2017), tổ chức có trụ sở tại Basel giám sát hoạt động của các ngân hàng trung ương trên thế giới tìm ra rằng từ giữa những năm 1980, việc lãi suất danh nghĩa giảm 10% gây ra 17% sự gia tăng (gấp 6 lần) số lượng các doanh nghiệp xác sống, mặc dù trên thực tế con số này có thể cao hơn rất nhiều.

Ở góc độ nào đó, các doanh nghiệp xác sống này làm cho nền kinh tế hoạt động không hiệu quả, cản trở sự tăng trưởng thậm chí có thể gây ra khủng hoảng cho nền kinh tế, hậu quả mà nền kinh tế sẽ phải gánh chịu rất lớn khi các doanh nghiệp xác sống không được giải quyết triệt để, gây ra nợ xấu mang tính dây chuyền, lãng phí việc sử dụng tài nguyên,... Fukuda &

Nakamura (2011, 2013) cho rằng thật không công bằng khi những doanh nghiệp xác sống không thể hoàn trả cả gốc và lãi, không đóng thuế trong khi các công ty khỏe mạnh hơn đóng thuế, trả nợ đầy đủ và còn phải cạnh tranh về giá. Số lượng lớn các doanh nghiệp hoạt động không hiệu quả, và được coi là những "xác sống", sẽ là cản trở đối với mục tiêu phát triển kinh tế dài hạn của đất nước. Các doanh nghiệp xác sống cướp đi cơ hội của các doanh nghiệp khỏe mạnh trong nỗ lực mở rộng thị trường, biến thành rào cản của các công ty mới và trẻ và cuối cùng là làm giảm nguồn vốn đầu tư.

Vấn đề phát hiện một công ty đang hoạt động một cách yếu kém hay cụ thể là nhận diện một doanh nghiệp là "xác sống" đòi hỏi những lý thuyết liên quan đến cả học thuật và thực tiễn. Theo lý thuyết, để xác định vấn đề liên quan đến tài chính doanh nghiệp cần đánh giá các chỉ số tài chính của doanh nghiệp đó mặc dù không phải lúc nào việc thu thập các thông tin tài chính của doanh nghiệp cũng là điều đơn giản. Nhiều học giả đã nghiên cứu trong nhiều năm để xây dựng các mô hình để có thể mô hình hóa được tình hình tài chính của doanh nghiệp, ví dụ như Bài toán ước lượng Z-score (Altman, 1968; Altman và cộng sự, 2000), Khoảng cách đến phá sản của một công ty (Merton, 1974), Độ nhạy cảm giữa đầu tư và dòng tiền (Fazzari và cộng sự, 1988),...

Đối với bài toán về quá trình nhận diện doanh nghiệp xác sống, các học giả hiện tại sử dụng nhiều phương pháp khác nhau để tiếp cận vấn đề. Trong số đó có thể kể đến phương pháp áp dụng mô hình kinh tế lượng truyền thống và sử dụng các mô hình học máy. TS. Vũ Thị Thu Hương (2019) đã sử dụng mô hình Probit trong quá trình nhận diện công ty Zombie từ các công ty niêm yết trên sàn giao dịch chứng khoán Việt Nam. Với một quy mô rộng lớn hơn, F. Bargagli Stoffi và các cộng sự (2020) đã tiếp cận vấn đề bằng phương pháp học tập có giám sát, cụ thể ở là cây quyết định để xác định các yếu tố quyết định công ty xác sống trên khắp các quốc gia và theo thời gian.

Trong nghiên cứu của mình, Hoshi (2006) cho rằng các doanh nghiệp xác sống là những doanh nghiệp đang mất khả năng thanh toán các khoản lãi vay và có rất ít hy vọng phục hồi nhưng lại tránh được sự thất bại nhờ nguồn vốn vay từ ngân hàng. Tương tự, Mark Thomas (2010, 2012) nghiên cứu về các doanh nghiệp xác sống ở Anh và Mỹ, ông cho rằng doanh nghiệp xác sống là những doanh nghiệp chỉ đủ tiền mặt để chi trả cho các khoản lãi vay mà không thể trả được hết nợ. Các doanh nghiệp xác sống có thể có doanh thu, thu về tiền mặt nhưng không thể thu hút đủ đầu tư để trả các khoản nợ. Sau khi chi trả hết các chi phí cố định, chi phí biến đổi, các doanh nghiệp xác sống chỉ còn đủ tiền trả khoản lãi không lỗ của những khoản vay chứ không thể trả được phần gốc vay. Những doanh nghiệp này sẽ tồn tại một cách vật vờ, không có khả năng sinh lời, và sẽ trở thành gánh nặng cho nền kinh tế.

Tuy nhiên, Fukuda and Nakamura (2011) đã chỉ ra rằng: nếu chỉ đưa ra một tiêu chí trên thì sẽ có thể xác định sai các doanh nghiệp xác sống. Thứ nhất, trong nhiều trường hợp, một doanh nghiệp không phải xác sống cũng được hưởng chính sách lãi suất thấp so với thị trường, do đó, chỉ tiêu này có thể xác định một doanh nghiệp khỏe mạnh trở thành một doanh nghiệp xác sống. Thứ hai, có những giai đoạn khác nhau trong chu kỳ kinh tế, các doanh nghiệp xác sống không được hỗ trợ mà cũng phải chịu mức lãi suất hiện hành. Do đó, theo tiêu chí trên thì doanh nghiệp xác sống lại trở thành một doanh nghiệp không phải xác sống. Hai trường hợp trên được kiểm chứng trong giai đoạn khủng hoảng kinh tế ở Nhật Bản, do đó, Fukuda and Nakamura (2011) đã dựa vào nghiên cứu của Caballero và cộng sự (2008) để phát triển và bổ

sung thêm tiêu chí xác định doanh nghiệp xác sống. Tiêu chí thứ nhất là khả năng sinh lợi của doanh nghiệp, theo tiêu chí này, thì các doanh nghiệp có thể trả với lãi suất thấp hơn lãi suất rủi ro giả định nhưng có lợi nhuận trước thuế dương thì sẽ không được xếp vào doanh nghiệp xác sống. Tiêu chí thứ hai là tiêu chí cho vay mãi mãi, tiêu chí cho biết các doanh nghiệp không có lợi nhuận, các khoản vay cao và vay nợ bên ngoài tăng lên sẽ được xác định là các doanh nghiệp xác sống. Theo đó, các doanh nghiệp này sẽ có thu nhập trước thuế thấp hơn khoản vay với lãi suất rủi ro giả định trong giai đoạn t ; tổng nợ vượt quá một nửa so với vốn chủ sở hữu trong giai đoạn $t - 1$ và tổng vay tăng lên trong giai đoạn t thì được gọi là các doanh nghiệp xác sống trong giai đoạn t .

Các nghiên cứu của Hoshi (2006), Imai (2016) và Urionabarrenetxea & cộng sự (2018) lại dựa vào một số chỉ tiêu từ báo cáo tài chính của các doanh nghiệp để xác định doanh nghiệp xác sống. Chỉ tiêu chủ yếu dựa vào khả năng sinh lợi và mức vay của các doanh nghiệp, theo đó, các doanh nghiệp được coi là xác sống sẽ khác rất nhiều với các doanh nghiệp khỏe mạnh. Các doanh nghiệp xác sống bao gồm các doanh nghiệp có giá trị tài sản cầm cố âm mà vẫn tiếp tục giao dịch mặc dù không có vốn chủ sở hữu. Các doanh nghiệp có vốn chủ sở hữu âm đã mất toàn bộ giá trị tài sản ròng do thua lỗ trong nhiều năm. Về lý thuyết, các doanh nghiệp này nên được thanh lý nhưng thực tế nó vẫn có các giao dịch và tiếp tục kinh doanh do sự giúp đỡ của các chủ nợ. Tuy nhiên, nghiên cứu của Urionabarrenetxea và cộng sự (2018) lại chỉ ra rằng việc sử dụng tiêu chí khả năng đáp ứng các khoản thanh toán lãi suất của các doanh nghiệp xác sống là rất rõ ràng nhưng có thể dữ liệu là không có sẵn. Do đó, nghiên cứu này đã đưa ra chỉ tiêu về khả năng đáp ứng các yêu cầu thanh toán ngay lập tức hoặc các khoản vay ngắn hạn vì chỉ tiêu này được phản ánh trong bảng cân đối kế toán của doanh nghiệp.

Nghiên cứu trường hợp các doanh nghiệp xác sống tại Trung Quốc, Shen & Chen (2017) cũng dựa vào tiêu chí xác định một doanh nghiệp “xác sống” thông qua phương pháp của Caballero và cộng sự (2008); Fukuda and Nakamura (2011). Ông đưa ra các tiêu chí cụ thể để xác định một doanh nghiệp là xác sống, bao gồm: thứ nhất, doanh nghiệp đó có hệ số đòn bẩy (tỷ lệ vốn vay trên vốn sở hữu lớn hơn 50%; thứ hai, lợi nhuận thực tế hàng năm âm; thứ ba, nợ phải trả hàng năm của nó vượt quá số nợ báo cáo của năm trước đó.

Một số nghiên cứu gần đây về công ty Zombie tại các nước thuộc EU (Hallak và cộng sự, 2018; Adalet McGowan, Andrews and Millot, 2017) đã sử dụng tiêu chí xác định công ty Zombie dựa vào tỉ lệ bao phủ lãi suất và tuổi của công ty, theo đó một công ty là Zombie nếu có tỉ lệ bao phủ lãi suất (bằng lợi nhuận trước thuế và các khoản lãi vay đã tính khấu hao chia cho tiền lãi phải trả) nhỏ hơn 1 trong ba năm liên tiếp. Để loại bớt nguy cơ Zombie cho các công ty mới thành lập thì các nghiên cứu này có đưa thêm điều kiện về tuổi, đó là các công ty từ 10 tuổi trở lên, có tỉ lệ bao phủ lãi suất nhỏ hơn 1 trong ba năm hoặc năm năm liên tiếp.

Như vậy có thể thấy: các nghiên cứu về chủ đề này sử dụng các tiêu chí xác định doanh nghiệp xác sống trong khá đa dạng và phong phú, tuy nhiên, các tiêu chí đều quan tâm đến khả năng thanh toán tiền lãi và lợi nhuận của doanh nghiệp

Trong nghiên cứu này, tác giả đưa ra tiêu chí xác định doanh nghiệp xác sống dựa trên các tiêu chí đã được sử dụng trong các nghiên cứu trước đây, đồng thời dựa vào sự hợp lý và sẵn có của dữ liệu từ báo cáo tài chính của các công ty niêm yết tại Việt Nam. Theo đó, các doanh nghiệp được xếp vào nhóm “xác sống” trong năm t nếu có:

(i) tỉ lệ bao phủ lãi suất nhỏ hơn 1 trong ba năm liên tiếp $t-2, t-1, t$, trong đó tỷ lệ bao phủ lãi suất được xác định theo công thức: $ICR_{it} = \frac{EBIT_{it}}{IE_{it}}$

(ii) có lợi nhuận từ hoạt động sản xuất kinh doanh âm trong năm t .

3. PHƯƠNG PHÁP NGHIÊN CỨU

Cây quyết định là một phương pháp giúp mô hình hóa các yếu tố quyết định một vấn đề. Một mô hình Cây quyết định sẽ được mô tả như Hình 1.

Hình 1. Ví dụ cho mô hình Cây quyết định

Nguồn: Tác giả sưu tầm

Trong một mô hình Cây quyết định tồn tại các khái niệm: Nút rễ, nút lá, cành, nút trong. Nút rễ là điểm bắt đầu của các nhánh trong cây dữ liệu, xuất phát từ nút rễ sẽ xuất hiện các nút trong đại diện cho các yếu tố được xem xét trong mô hình. Các nút trong sẽ tiếp tục phân chia cho tới nút lá cuối cùng thể hiện các quyết định hoặc các dự đoán. Các nút được nối với nhau qua các cành thể hiện các chỉ tiêu phân chia tập dữ liệu.

Xét trong bài toán của đề tài nghiên cứu, các nút lá cần được đưa là việc xác định một doanh nghiệp có phải doanh nghiệp xác sống hay không? Với các nút trong là các chỉ số được xem xét dựa trên kết quả báo cáo kinh doanh và bảng cân đối kế toán. Có thể nhận thấy rằng bài toán cây quyết định được xem xét trong bài nghiên cứu là bài toán cây nhị phân (gồm 2 quyết định ở nút lá) với các biến liên tục.

Trong thuật toán cây quyết định, *Entropy* là một trong những công cụ được sử dụng để đánh giá mức độ tinh khiết của phân phối xác suất của một sự kiện. *Entropy* là một khái niệm khoa học được sử dụng lần đầu tiên trong nhiệt động lực học và sau đó được phổ biến trong các lĩnh vực khác như vật lý, hoá học, y sinh, lý thuyết thông tin,... Trong nhiệt động lực học thì *Entropy* là một đặc tính vật lý có thể đo lường được có sự liên kết với trạng thái hỗn loạn (*disorder*) hoặc không chắc chắn (*uncertainty*).

Giả sử một sự kiện xảy ra với phân phối xác suất là $p = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_C)$ thỏa mãn

$$\sum_{i=1}^C p_i = 1. \text{ Khi đó hàm Entropy đối với sự kiện trên là: } H(p) = -\sum_{i=1}^C p_i \log p_i$$

Trong trường hợp $p_i = 0$ thì hàm *Entropy* là không xác định do $\log p_i$ không tồn tại, tuy nhiên căn cứ vào giá trị hội tụ thì sẽ quy ước giá trị của *Entropy* trong trường hợp này là 0. Hàm *Entropy* cực tiểu đạt được khi phân phối p là tinh khiết nhất, tức phân phối hoàn toàn thuộc về một nhóm. Trái lại, *Entropy* cực đại đạt được khi toàn bộ xác suất thuộc về các nhóm là bằng nhau. Một phân phối có *Entropy* càng cao thì mức độ tinh khiết của phân phối đó sẽ càng thấp và ngược lại.

Như vậy về bản chất thì *Entropy* là một thước đo về độ tinh khiết của phân phối xác suất. Dựa trên *Entropy* có thể đánh giá tính hiệu quả của câu hỏi ở mỗi node và quyết định xem đâu là câu hỏi hiệu quả hơn (có độ tinh khiết lớn hơn, *Entropy* nhỏ hơn).

4. THỰC TRẠNG DOANH NGHIỆP XÁC SỐNG Ở VIỆT NAM

Nghiên cứu sử dụng số liệu thứ cấp từ các công ty niêm trên sàn giao dịch chứng khoán Việt Nam trong giai đoạn 2013-2022, số liệu được tổng hợp từ www.cophieu68.vn. Dữ liệu đầu vào bao gồm các thông số từ bảng cân đối kế toán, kết quả kinh doanh và một số chỉ số tài chính. Sau quá trình tổng hợp, ghép nối, làm sạch dữ liệu và chọn lựa các công ty có dữ liệu đầy đủ trong giai đoạn 2013-2022, bài nghiên cứu được sử dụng với dữ liệu của 753 công ty trên các sàn giao dịch chứng khoán Việt Nam, trong đó: 294 công ty niêm yết trên sàn HOSE, 260 công ty niêm yết trên sàn HNX và 199 công ty niêm yết trên sàn UPCOM.

Nghiên cứu thực nghiệm sử dụng số liệu trong giai đoạn 2013-2022, do dữ liệu các năm 2013, 2014 được dùng để xác định doanh nghiệp xác sống năm 2015. Các công ty được theo 16 nhóm ngành. Theo đó, các doanh nghiệp thuộc nhóm ngành Sản xuất chiếm tỷ lệ cao nhất là 35.71%, tiếp đến nhóm ngành xây dựng và Bất động sản, chiếm 22.11%. Sau khi sử dụng tiêu chí phân loại doanh nghiệp xác sống với các doanh nghiệp niêm yết trong mẫu nghiên cứu, số lượng các doanh nghiệp xác sống dao động trong khoảng từ 42 đến 75, cao nhất là năm 2017 và thấp nhất là năm 2021. Số lượng các doanh nghiệp xác sống được thống kê theo thời gian và nhóm ngành được thống kê trong Hình 2 và Bảng 1.

Hình 0. Số lượng doanh nghiệp xác sống theo từng năm, giai đoạn 2015-2022

Nguồn: Tác giả tổng hợp

Trong giai đoạn 8 năm 2015-2022, tỷ lệ các doanh nghiệp xác sống của Việt Nam dao động trong khoảng từ 7%-9%. Tuy nhiên trong giai đoạn Việt Nam chịu ảnh hưởng của đại dịch COVID-19 2019-2020, tỷ lệ doanh nghiệp xác sống tăng cao sau đó đã giảm xuống dưới 7% vào năm 2021 do các chính sách hỗ trợ doanh nghiệp trong đại dịch phát huy tác dụng. Tuy nhiên xu hướng chuyển dịch doanh nghiệp xác sống được xảy ra một cách rõ rệt trên sàn UPCOM với tỷ lệ ra tăng vượt trội so với các năm trước, và tỷ lệ giảm đáng kinh ngạc trên 2 sàn HOSE, HNX. Có thể thấy rằng việc bình ổn trong đầu tư cũng như kinh nghiệm sản xuất từ các doanh nghiệp hoạt động lâu đời trên 2 sàn HOSE và HNX đã trong thời kỳ dịch bệnh đã khiến tỷ lệ xác sống giảm sâu. Tuy nhiên, các gói cứu trợ từ chính phủ hướng tới các doanh nghiệp mới thành lập, vừa và nhỏ đã gián tiếp gây ra sự ra tăng đột biến trong tỷ lệ các doanh nghiệp xác sống trên sàn UPCOM.

Theo tờ báo Sài Gòn/ Giải phóng ngày 5/12/2021, hiện tượng doanh nghiệp xác sống xảy ra một cách rõ ràng ở khu vực Doanh nghiệp nhà nước. Nhiều doanh nghiệp nhà nước gắn liền với các dự án khủng đấp chiếu, đích thị là những “xác sống” thực sự. Số liệu báo cáo của Chính phủ gửi Quốc hội về hoạt động đầu tư, quản lý, sử dụng vốn tại các doanh nghiệp nhà nước cho thấy “xác sống” không còn là nguy cơ mà là hiện thực. Các báo cáo hợp nhất cho thấy 12 tập đoàn, tổng công ty lỗ lũy kế hơn 7,440 tỷ đồng; có 6 công ty mẹ lỗ lũy kế 2,819 tỷ đồng. Các tập đoàn, tổng công ty hiện có tổng số nợ phải trả trên 1.44 triệu tỷ đồng, chiếm 53% tổng nguồn vốn của các tập đoàn. Các khoản lỗ lũy kế kéo dài nhiều năm, kết hợp với tỷ lệ nợ vay luôn ở mức cao ngất ngưỡng, cho thấy không ít doanh nghiệp thuộc các tập đoàn kinh tế nhà nước và các công ty mẹ hiện không khác gì “xác sống”. Đây là những “xác sống” bất tử.

Bảng 1. Số lượng doanh nghiệp xác sống theo ngành, giai đoạn 2015-2022

		HOSE	HNX	UPCOM	Tổng
1	Khai khoáng	0	0	13	13
2	Tiện ích	0	0	8	8
3	Xây dựng và Bất động sản	6	6	69	81
4	Sản xuất	7	0	86	93
5	Bán buôn	0	0	19	19
6	Vận tải và kho bãi	0	0	38	38
7	Tài chính và bảo hiểm	1	0	3	4
8	Thuê và cho thuê	0	0	3	3
9	Dịch vụ giáo dục	0	0	6	6
10	Dịch vụ lưu trú và ăn uống	0	0	3	3
11	Bán lẻ	1	1	1	3

Nguồn: Tác giả tổng hợp

Bảng 1 cho thấy trong số 271 doanh nghiệp xác sống ở 2 nhóm Sản xuất; Xây dựng và Bất động sản chiếm tỷ trọng lớn trong cơ cấu các doanh nghiệp xác sống ở Việt Nam giai đoạn 2015-2022 trên cả 3 sàn chứng khoán với trên 30%. Đây cũng là nhóm doanh nghiệp gây ra nhiều ảnh hưởng tiêu cực cho nền kinh tế khi các doanh nghiệp hoạt động kém hiệu quả, suy

thoái nền kinh tế và tình trạng đóng băng các hoạt động kinh doanh bất động sản trong thời gian gần đây. Nếu không kịp thời đưa ra các chính sách hỗ trợ để các doanh nghiệp này thoát tình trạng trì trệ thì nền kinh tế Việt Nam trong năm 2023 và giai đoạn tiếp theo sẽ tiếp tục suy thoái mạnh hơn, tạo ra nhiều hệ lụy cho nền kinh tế.

5. CÁC KẾT QUẢ PHÂN TÍCH CHÍNH

Áp dụng mô hình Cây quyết định với số liệu của 753 doanh nghiệp đã được tổng hợp, tác giả đã hệ thống lại 3 tiêu chuẩn quan trọng nhất xác định 1 doanh nghiệp xác sống như trong bảng 2. Trong đó 3 chỉ tiêu tài chính quan trọng có trong các nhóm là Lợi nhuận trước thuế, Đòn bẩy tài chính và Tăng trưởng tổng tài sản.

Bảng 2. Tiêu chuẩn hình thành doanh nghiệp xác sống giai đoạn 2015-2022

Nhánh	Số lượng	Tỷ lệ	Tiêu chuẩn
1	59	24.58	$-4.464 < ROA \leq -0.055$; Tổng nợ phải trả > 0.358 ; Tăng trưởng tổng tài sản > -0.272 ; Đòn bẩy tài chính < 0.002 ; Lợi nhuận trước thuế < 0
2	22	9.17	$7.4 < \text{Quy mô doanh nghiệp} \leq 10.754$; $-0.023 < \text{Lợi nhuận trước thuế} < 0$; Tổng nợ phải trả < 0.358 ; $ROA \leq -0.032$; Tăng trưởng tổng tài sản > -0.272 ; Đòn bẩy tài chính < 0.002
3	20	8.33	Lợi nhuận trước thuế < -0.007 ; Tiền mặt ≤ 0.044 ; Hàng tồn kho ≤ 0.012 ; Tăng trưởng tổng tài sản > -0.233 ; Giá trị cổ phiếu ≤ 2.72 ; EBITDA > 0.01 ; Đòn bẩy tài chính > 0.002

Nguồn: Tính toán của tác giả

Kết quả của cây phân loại được ước tính bằng cách sử dụng thuật toán CART ở hình 3, tại mỗi nút cung cấp dấu hiệu để xác định phần lớn các công ty tại nút đó là xác sống hoặc không là xác sống. Các nút màu trắng thể hiện tỷ lệ phân chia là đồng đều ở 2 dạng, các nút càng đậm màu thể hiện sự phân biệt càng rõ rệt với cái nút màu cam thể hiện doanh nghiệp không là xác sống và các nút màu xanh thể hiện doanh nghiệp là xác sống.

Hình 3. Mô hình Cây quyết định giai đoạn 2015-2022

Nguồn: Tính toán của tác giả

Nhóm Doanh nghiệp Sản xuất

Trong giai đoạn từ năm 2013-2022, có 2103 lượt các doanh nghiệp thuộc nhóm Sản xuất đã được xem xét nghiên cứu, trong đó 90 lượt doanh nghiệp được đánh giá là zombie theo tiêu chuẩn đã được xác định ở mục trên, chiếm tỷ lệ 4.27%.

Hình 4 cung cấp hình ảnh cây quyết định cho nhóm các doanh nghiệp sản xuất trong giai đoạn 2015-2022. Từ hình vẽ, tiêu chuẩn được lựa chọn làm “rễ” của mô hình là *chỉ số ROA*, cụ thể có 94.12% các Doanh nghiệp xác sống) có chỉ ROA dưới -0.005. Là chỉ số phản ánh phần lợi nhuận sau thuế của doanh nghiệp trên tổng tài sản, một chỉ số ROA âm phản ánh việc doanh nghiệp hiện đang kinh doanh không tạo ra lợi nhuận. Không chỉ các doanh nghiệp sản xuất, việc không tạo ra lợi nhuận sẽ là lý do trực tiếp dẫn đến quá trình bị “xác sống hóa”. Chỉ số tiếp theo quyết định quá trình phân loại các doanh nghiệp xác sống là *Giá trị cổ phiếu*, cụ thể có 48.24% các doanh nghiệp xác sống có giá cổ phiếu dưới 1,650 đồng và 8.24% các doanh nghiệp xác sống có giá cổ phiếu dưới 100 đồng. Cũng là một chỉ số phản ánh lợi nhuận của doanh nghiệp, việc giá trị cổ phiếu thấp sẽ làm giảm tính thu hút đầu tư của các doanh nghiệp sản xuất, từ đó ảnh hưởng tới quá trình tạo ra sản phẩm và sinh lợi nhuận. Một chỉ số khác phản ánh trực tiếp doanh thu của các doanh nghiệp sản xuất chỉ số *Vòng quay tổng tài sản*, là tỷ lệ của doanh thu thuần trên tổng tài sản của doanh nghiệp. Cụ thể có 20% các doanh nghiệp xác sống có chỉ số này thấp hơn 0.365. Ngoài ra còn các yếu tố khác cũng góp phần trong mô hình phân loại các doanh nghiệp sản xuất như *Đòn bẩy tài chính, Tiền mặt và các khoản tương đương tiền, Tổng nợ phải trả,...*

Nhìn chung, trong mô hình phân loại cây quyết định cho nhóm doanh nghiệp sản xuất các chỉ tiêu thường xuyên được nhắc tới liên quan trực tiếp tới quá trình sản xuất và tạo ra lợi nhuận cho doanh nghiệp. Một doanh nghiệp hoạt động kém hiệu quả, tạo ra lợi nhuận âm hoặc không hoặc không thể thu hút được đầu tư để tăng cường sản xuất là lý do để hình thành xác sống. Hình 4. Mô hình Cây quyết định xác định doanh nghiệp xác sống giai đoạn 2015-2022

(Nhóm Doanh nghiệp Sản xuất)

Nguồn: Tính toán của tác giả

Ngoài việc chỉ ra các chỉ số quan trọng quyết định việc phân chia các doanh nghiệp xác sống so với nhóm doanh nghiệp “khỏe mạnh”, mô hình cây quyết định còn cho phép phân chia cụ thể theo từng tiêu chuẩn khác nhau. Cụ thể, trong mô hình Cây quyết định ở Hình 4 có 12 nút lá quyết định một doanh nghiệp là xác sống, trong đó có 8 nút lá được phân chia một cách “tinh khiết”, tức chỉ số entropy bằng 0. Tám nút lá này sẽ hình thành 8 tiêu chuẩn khác nhau để định hình một doanh nghiệp xác sống. Từ bảng 3 có thể nhận thấy rằng 2 tiêu chuẩn đầu tiên có tỷ lệ nhận dạng tốt nhất với tỷ lệ lần lượt là 20.00% và 14.12%. Các chỉ số cấu thành lên 2 tiêu chuẩn nổi bật này đã được chỉ ra vai trò trong phần trên, đặc biệt các chỉ tiêu được gắn với các ngưỡng cụ thể góp phần xác định doanh nghiệp xác sống một cách rõ ràng hơn.

Bảng 3. Tiêu chuẩn hình thành doanh nghiệp xác sống Nhóm Sản xuất

Nhánh	Số lượng	Tỷ lệ	Tiêu chuẩn
1	17	20.00	Vòng quay tổng tài sản > 0.365 ; $0.1 < \text{Giá trị cổ phiếu} \leq 1.65$; $\text{ROA} \leq -0.005$
2	12	14.12	Đòn bẩy tài chính > -4.235 ; $\text{ROA} \leq -2.74$; Tổng nợ phải trả ≤ 0.035 ; $0.1 < \text{Giá trị cổ phiếu} \leq 1.4$; Vòng quay tổng tài sản ≤ 0.365
3	7	8.24	Tăng trưởng tổng tài sản > 0.025 ; Giá trị cổ phiếu > 1.825 ; $\text{EBITDA} \leq 0.01$; Tiền mặt ≤ 0.005 ; $\text{ROA} \leq -0.005$
4	6	7.06	Đầu tư tài chính ngắn hạn ≤ 0.01 ; Tổng nợ phải trả > 0.42 ; Giá trị cổ phiếu ≤ 0.1 ; $\text{ROA} \leq -0.005$

Nguồn: Tính toán của tác giả

Nhóm doanh nghiệp Xây dựng và Bất động sản

Trong giai đoạn từ năm 2013-2022, có 1419 lượt các doanh nghiệp thuộc nhóm Sản xuất đã được xem xét nghiên cứu, trong đó 79 lượt doanh nghiệp được đánh giá là zombie theo tiêu chuẩn đã được xác định ở mục trên, chiếm tỷ lệ 5.67%.

Hình 5 cung cấp mô hình cây quyết định cho nhóm doanh nghiệp Xây dựng và Bất động sản. Khác với chỉ tiêu *Lợi nhuận trước thuế* được xem xét trước tiên cho hiệu quả phân loại doanh nghiệp xác sống, tại nhóm ngành này *ROA* là chỉ tiêu đầu tiên được xem xét tới. Thị trường Xây dựng và Bất động sản trong những năm vừa qua được biết tới với là nơi tập trung của nhiều nhà đầu tư lớn nhỏ khắp cả nước cũng như quốc tế. Không ngạc nhiên khi việc sử dụng hiệu quả vốn từ các nhà đầu tư trong vấn đề tạo ra lợi nhuận là yếu tố quyết định việc có hình thành một zombie trong ngành này. Tiếp theo *Giá trị cổ phiếu cuối kỳ* là yếu tố tiếp theo được xét tới, việc có giá trị cổ phiếu cao trên thị trường cũng là yếu tố quyết định việc thu hút các nhà đầu tư, qua đó làm giảm đi khả năng hình thành Zombie. *Đòn bẩy tài chính* cũng là một chỉ tiêu quan trọng khác phản ánh hiệu quả sử dụng vốn vay từ các nhà đầu tư cho quá trình tạo ra lợi nhuận, trong bài nghiên cứu, chỉ số đòn bẩy tài chính được sử dụng phản ánh cơ cấu nợ trên vốn chủ sở hữu của doanh nghiệp, khi vốn vay quá cao sẽ tiềm ẩn nguy cơ hình thành Zombie. Một chỉ tiêu tiếp theo được các doanh nghiệp thường sử dụng trong quá trình thu hút vốn đầu tư đó là *EBITDA*, một chỉ số *EBITDA* đẹp sẽ ra một bức tranh sặc sỡ cho các nhà đầu tư khi bắt đầu đánh giá hiệu suất hoạt động của doanh nghiệp. Tuy nhiên khi một doanh nghiệp kiến tạo một chỉ số *EBITDA* quá đẹp cũng sẽ gây ra những nghi ngờ cho các nhà đầu tư. Ngoài ra còn một số các chỉ tiêu khác cũng được nhắc tới trong cây quyết định của các doanh nghiệp Xây dựng và Bất động sản như *Tiền mặt và các khoản tương đương tiền*, *Đầu tư tài chính ngắn hạn*, ...

Nhìn chung, các chỉ tiêu được xem xét tới trong mô hình cây quyết định của các doanh nghiệp Xây dựng và Bất động sản tập trung chủ yếu vào chỉ tiêu phản ánh khả năng sử dụng vốn đầu tư từ các nhà đầu tư trên thị trường hay các chỉ số nhằm thu hút đầu tư. Như đã nói ở trên việc này là cần thiết cho doanh nghiệp của nhóm ngành này, việc thu hút được đầu tư sẽ tạo ra lợi nhuận giúp doanh nghiệp tránh khả năng hình thành Zombie.

Hình 5. Mô hình Cây quyết định xác định doanh nghiệp xác sống giai đoạn 2015-2022 (Nhóm Doanh nghiệp Xây dựng và Bất động sản)

Nguồn: Tính toán của tác giả

Từ mô hình cây quyết định ở Hình 5 nhận thấy rằng có 11 nút lá tinh khiết được hình thành tương ứng với 11 tiêu chuẩn nhận diện doanh nghiệp xác sống ở nhóm Xây dựng và Bất động sản (Bảng 4). Ba tiêu chuẩn đầu với tỷ lệ nhận diện cao nhất tương ứng với các chỉ số quan trọng đã được chỉ ra trong bài nghiên cứu.

Bảng 4. Tiêu chuẩn hình thành doanh nghiệp xác sống Nhóm Xây dựng và Bất động sản

Nhánh	Số lượng	Tỷ lệ	Tiêu chuẩn
1	11	14.67	Giá trị cổ phiếu ≤ 0.95 ; $ROA \leq -0.065$; Quy mô công ty > 7.2 ; Đòn bẩy tài chính > -15.63
2	9	12.00	Đòn bẩy tài chính ≤ -15.63 ; Giá trị cổ phiếu ≤ 1.81 ; $ROA \leq -0.005$
3	8	10.67	Quy mô công ty ≤ 7.2 ; Đòn bẩy tài chính > -15.63 ; Giá trị cổ phiếu ≤ 1.81 ; $ROA \leq -0.005$
4	4	5.33	Tổng nợ phải trả > 0.295 ; Giá trị cổ phiếu > 0.95 ; $ROA \leq -0.065$; Quy mô công ty > 7.2 ; Đòn bẩy tài chính > -15.63
5	3	4.00	$1.105 < \text{Đòn bẩy tài chính} \leq 1.845$; $EBITDA \leq 0.72$; Lợi nhuận trước thuế ≤ -0.015 ; Tăng trưởng tổng tài sản ≥ -0.234 ; Giá trị cổ phiếu ≥ 1.81 ; $ROA \leq -0.05$

Nguồn: Tính toán của tác giả

Ngoài ra để đánh giá độ chính xác của mô hình, tập dữ liệu được phân thành 2 phần Train và Test với tỷ lệ lần lượt là 90% và 10%. Tập dữ liệu Train được sử dụng để xây dựng mô hình và tập dữ liệu Test được sử dụng để đánh hiệu suất dự báo của mô hình thực nghiệm. Theo kết quả dự báo ở Hình 6 cho thấy độ chính xác (Accuracy – Score) của mô hình là 96.64%, trong đó có kết quả dự đoán chính xác các doanh nghiệp là xác sống trong thực tế (TPR) là 50% và chỉ có 1.4% kết quả dự đoán sai các doanh nghiệp là xác sống trên tổng số các doanh nghiệp không phải là xác sống (FPR).

Hình 6. Kết quả dự báo mô hình Cây quyết định

Nguồn: Kết quả nghiên cứu định lượng

Nhìn chung, mô hình cây quyết định đã phản ánh một cách khá đầy đủ quá trình hình thành các doanh nghiệp xác sống trong giai đoạn Việt Nam bị ảnh hưởng bởi đại dịch COVID-19. Phần lớn các yếu tố tập trung vào quá trình hình lợi nhuận hay phản ánh hiệu quả sử dụng vốn và các nguồn viện trợ của chính phủ trong quá trình tạo ra lợi nhuận, ngoài ra một số chỉ số còn phản ánh trực tiếp dòng tiền trong doanh nghiệp.

6. KẾT LUẬN

Phần kết quả nghiên cứu được tác giả trình bày dưới 3 khía cạnh chính. Thứ nhất là tổng quan tình trạng các doanh nghiệp xác sống trong cơ sở dữ liệu được sử dụng bài nghiên cứu, đặc điểm quan trọng nhất có thể nhận ra là xu hướng chuyển dịch tỷ lệ các doanh nghiệp sang sản phẩm UPCOM và tỷ trọng cao của 2 nhóm doanh nghiệp Sản xuất; Xây dựng và Bất động sản. Thứ hai, tác giả đã sử dụng mô hình Cây quyết định để tiến hành phân tích các đặc điểm nổi bật trong quá trình hình thành một doanh nghiệp xác sống ở 2 nhóm ngành nói trên, đồng thời là các doanh nghiệp trong giai đoạn Việt Nam bị ảnh hưởng bởi đại dịch COVID-19. Cuối cùng đưa ra các ngưỡng cho các tiêu chí để các nhà quản lý cũng như các nhà chức trách nhận diện được các doanh nghiệp xác sống dựa vào chỉ tiêu hoạt động kinh doanh như chỉ số ROA, tăng trưởng tổng tài sản hoặc đòn bẩy tài chính.

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THEME 4:

LAW

CYBERSECURITY IN BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT: LEGAL ISSUES AND SOLUTIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

With increasingly technological developments, many business enterprises are facing more cybersecurity risks which threaten their activities. Cybersecurity takes a role as an essential sustainable economic development factor in business environment. However, little research has been conducted into the extent to which cybersecurity has legal impacts on sustainable economic development of Vietnam's business environment. The regulatory measures on cybersecurity lay the legal basis for controlling cybersecurity aiming for sustainable economic development. This paper analyzes the legal framework of regulating cybersecurity in Vietnam and assess the effectiveness of the regulations on cybersecurity management in business environment. Legal perspectives on domains of cybersecurity and sustainable development are explored, with the focus is on legislation and policy approach to cybersecurity. The study identifies cybersecurity challenges that could negatively impact on the sustainable economic development in Vietnam's business environment. Some legal solutions are put forwarded, which do not aim only to address the cybersecurity but also to incorporate sustainable development goal.

Keywords: *Cybersecurity, business environment, sustainable economic development, legal solutions.*

1. INTRODUCTION

It is undeniable that information and technology advancement bring huge benefits to people's lives. However, this development also poses threats to safety of people when criminals can use technology to commit many types of crimes which are often referred as cybercrime. Dangers of cybersecurity incident, infringement of network security, data leakage and security vulnerabilities are emerging in many countries. Many business enterprises are facing more cybersecurity risks that are threatening their activities. Some enterprises have been victims of cyber-attacks. Cyber crimes and high-tech crimes in Vietnam are increasing in size, with more sophisticated tricks and more dangerous consequences. In terms of economic aspect, cybersecurity has significantly impacts on business enterprises activities.

Cybersecurity takes a role as an essential sustainable economic development factor (Ioana & Lucian, 2018). It is important to note that there is an interrelation between

cybersecurity and sustainable development. Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) requires cyber peace and capacity building for cyber resilient development. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development highlights the importance of information and communication technologies and global interconnectedness as powerful enablers of growth to bridge the digital divide and develop knowledge societies.

States play an important role in maintaining and fostering cybersecurity by regulations and policies. Vietnamese Government promulgated policy and legal frameworks to assist with the regulation of activities taking place in cyberspace. The Vietnamese Law on Cybersecurity was promulgated in 2018 and came into force from 1 January 2019. However, the impacts and enforcement of this law in Vietnam's business practice have not been fully explored. The paper aims to discuss the recently promulgated Vietnamese Law on Cybersecurity, which is the primary law regulating business activities. Furthermore, businesses also have responsibility to ensure cybersecurity. If the corporations comply with all applicable laws, regulations, company internal rules and policies, it helps them to govern security and sustainable development. Cybersecurity impacts on business activities in various aspects. Within the scope of research, the article aims to focus on the legal impacts of cybersecurity on sustainable economic development of business enterprises in Vietnam.

The article has three fundamental objectives. The first objective is to analyze the legal framework of regulating cybersecurity in Vietnam and assess the effectiveness of the regulations on cybersecurity management in business environment. The second objective is to examine the practice of cybersecurity, its legal problems and impacts of cybersecurity on sustainable economic development of Vietnam's business environment. The third objective is to take measures of governing cybersecurity and mitigating cybercrimes, which aims for achieving the sustainable economic development in Vietnam's business environment.

The paper is organized as follows. After the introduction, the second section of the paper provides the literature review, theoretical framework and research methods. The third section presents the results and discussion of this research. This section initially explores the general legal framework of regulating cybersecurity in Vietnam. It is followed by an analysis of practice of cybersecurity in Vietnam's business environment, its striking legal problems and the legal impacts of cybersecurity on sustainable economic development of Vietnam's business environment. The last section reaches a conclusion and implications for further research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW, THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Literature Review

A recent literature review on Industry 4.0 presented that there is a connection between cybersecurity and sustainable development (Adam et al., 2021; Richárd N., 2018). These studies analyze the relationship between cybersecurity and sustainable development in the inter-organizational networks. The e-commerce organizations have faced serious challenges of cybersecurity such as trade secret theft and payment fraud, which could negatively impact on the sustainable economic development (Ioana et al., 2018). This study provides an understanding of the main cybersecurity risks, identify their actual or potential effects and outline the main aspects from a prevention and recovery perspective.

The academic field of cybersecurity is highly interdisciplinary since it relates to various disciplines such as sociology, psychology, computer science, political science and law, which is analyzed in previous studies (Mazaher et al., 2021; Frank C. et al., 2022). Many studies focus on an aspect of Information and Communication Technology (Adam et al., 2021). From a legal perspective, some studies focus on the the role of legislative frameworks and law enforcement authorities in combat cyber-related crimes in Vietnam can be identified in little studies (Luong et al., 2019).

Legal challenges in cybersecurity are undeniable (Paul et al., 2020). As cyberattacks are evolving, it is important to have legal and regulatory measures to control cybersecurity. However, there is a lack of thorough analysis on legal impacts of cybersecurity on sustainable development of business activities in Vietnam. Furthermore, there have not been any research projects or academic papers analysing comprehensively the effectiveness of laws enforcement on cybercrime and how laws on cybercrime have been implemented by business enterprises. Thus, there is a room for such this paper to provide a better overview on the work of combating cybercrime in Vietnam from a legal perspective. Since then, some recommendations can be given to improve this work in the future.

2.2. Theoretical Framework and Research Methods

The article mainly uses the theory of sustainable development and the legal framework of cybersecurity in Vietnam. The study seeks to elaborate the following research questions:

The first research question: What is the legal impacts of cybersecurity on sustainable economic development of Vietnam's business environment?

The second research question: How effective are legal measures in reducing cybersecurity risks in Vietnam's business environment?

The doctrinal method is mainly adopted in the article. The study uses qualitative analysis and theoretical approach to discuss the legal framework of regulating cybersecurity, legal problems of cybersecurity and the practice of Vietnam's business environment. The research data about cases involving cybersecurity breaches in Vietnam is collected from recent reports of organizations and businesses.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The General Legal Framework of Regulating Cybersecurity in Vietnam

The term 'cybersecurity' means the application of technologies, processes, and controls to protect systems, networks, programs, devices and data from cyber attacks. It aims to reduce the risk of cyber attacks and protect against the unauthorised exploitation of systems, networks, and technologies. To respond to the growing issue of cybercrime, the Vietnamese Government promulgated laws to supplement the existing legal framework. The Vietnamese Law on Cybersecurity No. 24/2018/QH14 of the 14th National Assembly came into force on 1 January 2019. This Law regulates activities of protecting national security and ensuring social order and safety in cyberspace; and the responsibilities of agencies, organizations and individuals involved. In Article 2(1) of the 2018 Vietnamese Law on Cybersecurity, the term 'cybersecurity' is defined as 'the assurance that activities in cyberspace will not cause harm to

national security, social order and safety, or the lawful rights and interests of agencies, organisations and individuals’.

Article 2(7) of the Vietnamese Law on Cybersecurity states: “Cybercrime means activities of using cyberspace, IT or e-facilities to commit a crime as regulated in the Criminal Code”. The committing acts of cybercrimes, *inter alia*, can be identified in the following acts: (i) Delete, damage, or change a software program or electronic data, or illegally obstructs the transmission of data of a computer network, telecommunications network, or an electronic device, or otherwise obstructs or disturbs a computer network, telecommunications network, or an electronic device; (ii) Trade, exchange, give, change, or publish lawfully private information of an organization or individual on the computer or telecommunications network without the consent of the information owner; (iii) deliberately bypasses the warning, hacks the password or firewall, or uses the administrator’s right of another person to infiltrate another person’s computer network, telecommunications network, or electronic device in order to take control, interfere the operation of the electronic device; steal, change, destroy, fabricate data or illegally use services; (iv) use a computer network, telecommunications network, or electronic device in order to appropriate their property.

The Vietnamese Law on Cybersecurity introduced regulations on the storage of information in cyberspace for all enterprises to resolve the difficulties in tracing cybercrimes. Article 26(3) of the Law on Cybersecurity specifies that three types of data must be stored in Vietnam: (i) The personal information of service users; (ii) Service user relationship data; and (iii) The data generated by service users in Vietnam. The requirements of data storage and setting up branches or representative offices in Vietnam have had a great impact on tracking down traces and collecting evidence of online fraudulent appropriation of assets. This regulation also benefits businesses themselves since they will be better protected against violations of the law in cyberspace. These include the spread of false information about products, services and business reputation, unfair competition, infringement on intellectual property rights and business secrets. **Therefore, the Law on Cybersecurity is regarded as a legal basis for tracing cyber fraud and control cybercrimes in Vietnam’s business environment.**

3.2. Practice of Cybersecurity in Vietnam’s Business Environment and its Legal Problems

A cyber-attack matter threatens business environment. Some enterprises have been victims of cyber-attacks. There have been many cyber-attacks of large scale and high intensity, with increasingly dangerous nature and levels. The cybercrimes include serious violation such as data breaches, identity theft and cyber fraud, which infringes upon the rights and legitimate interests of organisations and individuals. This poses threats to the sustainable economic development of business environment.

A survey conducted by the Vietnam Information Security Association revealed that more than 50% of cyberattacks are aimed at banks and financial institutions. According to a report conducted by the Department of Cybersecurity and High-Tech Crime Prevention, Ministry of Public Security in 2020, banks lost nearly 100 billion Dong from 4,000 cyber-attacks, including a bank suffering loss of up to 44 billion Dong. One of the biggest threats to businesses suffering from ransomware attacks was the business interruption.

Recently, there are many cases involving cybersecurity breaches in Vietnam. One such example is the case of Maritime Bank where provides commercial and retail banking products and services in Vietnam. In 2019, a hacker posted on the Raidforums that they obtained access to more than 2 million Maritime Bank accounts and they are going to get even more data soon. The records included the full name, identity card number, telephone number, home address, date of birth, gender, email, and occupation of the customers.

In 2020, the iSoftH (a Vietnamese company that provides healthcare information management solutions) witnessed one of their cloud servers was left publicly exposed without encryption or password protection. One could access 12 million patient records through it, with no difficulties. The records included full names and dates of birth, postal and email addresses, phone numbers, passport details, credit card numbers, medical records, and recent test results and diagnoses.

The gaps between data protection, cybersecurity and enterprises' security strategies are also identified. There is a lack of a definition of sensitive corporate data in Vietnamese laws. Whether this type of data contains profitable value to business enterprises is a controversial issue. Article 9 of **the** Law on Cybersecurity stipulates that "Those who violate any provisions of this Law will be liable to disciplinary penalties, administrative penalties or criminal prosecution depending on the nature and severity of the violation and shall pay compensation for any damage caused". However, as mentioned, the Government has not promulgated any guidance on the security of information in cyberspace as stipulated in Article 26 of the Law on Cybersecurity. Furthermore, responsibilities of service providers in cyberspace are stated in Article 41, Clause 2 and Clause 3 of Article 26 of the Vietnamese Law on Cybersecurity. Those enterprises violate cybersecurity can be imposed sanctions according to the Criminal Code. However, it is harder to apply legal measures on foreign enterprise in practice.

3.3. The Legal Impacts of Cybersecurity on Sustainable Economic Development of Vietnam' Business Environment

The concept of sustainable development was often defined by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs". The economic dimension of sustainable development, *inter alia*, is one of the important aspects of The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Cybersecurity has legal impacts on sustainable economic development of business enterprises. On the positive side, the policy measures controlling cybersecurity **create the legal basis for tracing cyber attacks**. The laws and regulations are important instrument to protect the information of the business and customers. This is understandable in the context that cyber crimes and high-tech crimes in Vietnam have more sophisticated tricks and more dangerous consequences. Thus, the solid legal measures in governing cybersecurity help Vietnamese businesses take advantage of technological achievements and deeply integrate into the world economy.

On the negative side, many enterprises have been facing threats and challenges from cyberspace, directly threatening business activities. As a member of the Government Security Program (GSP) with Microsoft Corporation, some Vietnamese businesses could experience

cyber threats and vulnerability information from source codes for Microsoft products. From a legal perspective, cyber incidents can also result in costly recovery or remediation and, in certain cases, litigation; serious harm to consumers' privacy. Cyber incidents can negatively affect "trust", a very important social capital indicator and an determining factor of economic development (Hamilton, 2006).

3.4. Measures of Governing Cybersecurity in Vietnam's Business Environment Aiming for Sustainable Economic Development

3.4.1. Legal Measures

As cyberattacks are evolving, it is so important to have legal and regulatory measures to control cybersecurity. The aim of cybersecurity policy is to protect information and data in cyberspace, prevent cybersecurity risks, which is the driving force behind sustainable development in the global.

To reconcile the gaps and disconnect between data protection, cybersecurity and enterprises' security strategies, the harmonization in the definition enshrined in laws and regulations should be ensured. It is essential to provide some guidance of what constitutes the type of sensitive corporate data. This is beneficial to protect the valuable data and information, which is regarded as valuable assets of corporations.

In Vietnam, measures for cybersecurity protection are stated in Article 5 of the Law on Cybersecurity. These measures, *inter alia*, include: (i) Using cryptography to protect network information; (ii) Stopping, requiring the suspension of or ceasing provision of network information; suspending or temporarily suspending acts being the establishment, supply and use of telecom networks, of the Internet or being the manufacture and use of radio transmitters and receivers in accordance with law; (iii) Freezing or restricting the operation of information systems; suspending, temporarily suspending or requiring the cessation of operation of information systems or withdrawing domain names in accordance with law.

Depending on the nature and seriousness of the offence, cybercrime shall be liable to a fine, face a penalty of community sentence or imprisonment. For example, Article 289(1) of the 2015 Vietnamese Criminal Code regulates: "Any person who deliberately bypasses the warning, hacks the password or firewall, or uses the administrator's right of another person to infiltrate another person's computer network, telecommunications network, or electronic device in order to take control, interfere the operation of the electronic device; steal, change, destroy, fabricate data or illegally use services shall be liable to a fine of from VND 50,000,000 to VND 300,000,000 or face a penalty of 01 - 05 years' imprisonment". Furthermore, it is essential to supplement regulation on sanctions in laws in case of the enterprises violate.

Since the release of the SDGs, the law enforcement of cybersecurity measures has played a significant role in the growth of corporate sustainable development. To implement the policy on cybercrime, the Ministry of Public Security which is the main body in charge of crime prevention and suppression in Vietnam conducts many appropriate measures to prevent, detect and suppress cybercrime in Vietnam. Furthermore, Vietnam has actively participated in

the United Nations mechanisms in promoting the establishment of a Comprehensive International Convention against cybercrimes.

3.4.2. Enterprises's Responsibility

To mitigate cybercrime, the responsibility of business in governing security is very important. Protecting cybersecurity and combating cybercrimes have become a crucial part in many enterprises' security strategies. If the organization does not follow, or comply, with the rules and regulations, it can get sued, fined, or have all kinds of legal problems.

Businesses have responsibility for ensuring that the hardware and software used to process, store and analyse identifiable information have an adequate level of security to protect the users. Businesses must protect the confidentiality and privacy of individuals data held within those systems. They must be aware of the threat landscape. In knowing the main risks, businesses need to allocate sufficient resources to protect themselves. This is an efficient use of resources and it has the potential to reduce the cyber-attack risks.

4. CONCLUSION

Cybersecurity risk is one of the main issues in the world, which threatens business activities. To mitigate this risk, the regulations and legal measures take role as important instrument to protect the information of business and their customers. To respond to the growing issue of cybercrime, the Vietnamese Government promulgated laws to supplement the existing legal framework. The Vietnamese Law on Cybersecurity create an important legal basis for regulating activities in cyberspace and tracing cyber-attacks, which help to achieve the sustainable economic development goal in Vietnam's business.

The cybersecurity protection legal framework has a close relationship to sustainable development matter. In Vietnam, cybersecurity has legal impacts on sustainable economic development of business enterprises, both on positive and negative side. Harmonisation of legal frameworks in Vietnam is important to combat cybercrime and facilitate international cooperation.

This study contributes to enrich the theoretical knowledge presented in the discussion part. The findings of this study underline the need for improved cybersecurity strategies and policies. A number of legal measures have been taken to provide a safer cyberspace and better economic development environment. Governments and businesses need to strike a delicate balance between protecting sustainability and the latest technologies. Legislative measures and collaborative efforts of government and business enterprises cannot only control cybersecurity threats but also would act as a fundamental instrument in achieving the sustainable development goals. In addition, the security technologies and the development of an effective cybersecurity risk management also help to foster a cybersecurity culture in business enterprises.

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ABUSE OF DOMINANCE IN DATA MARKET

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Abstract

Amidst the surge of digital economy development, companies with vast amounts of data have misused their dominant positions to engage in actions that negatively impact competition processes and user rights, especially data protection concerns. In Vietnam, data protection is gaining increasing attention, but regulations regarding the abuse of dominance behavior in the data market by Tech Giants are relatively new. Therefore, the current subject of the authors can be seen as a positive contribution to researching abusive dominance behavior in the data market in Vietnam. The authors utilize Competition Law in the European Union (EU) since the EU has a similar competition legal system to Vietnam and is the issuer of the Digital Markets Act" (DMA), which directly regulates the conduct of the "Gatekeepers." This enables a comparison with Vietnam's Competition Law to evaluate its capacity to address abusive dominance behavior in the data market. The study indicates that Vietnam's Competition Law has the potential for addressing certain cases; however, it lacks comprehensiveness and requires refinement to keep pace with rapid changes in the digital market. Consequently, the authors propose measures to enhance flexibility while recommending the issuance of decrees and specialized laws to address data market abuse, particularly emphasizing the assessment of abusive dominance behavior concerning violations of data protection rules.

Keywords: Abuse of dominance, data market, Big Tech, DMA, Big Data, Competition Law

NHỮNG VẤN ĐỀ PHÁP LÝ CỦA CƠ CHẾ GIẢI QUYẾT TRANH CHẤP TRỰC TUYẾN TRÊN CÁC WEBSITE THƯƠNG MẠI ĐIỆN TỬ Ở VIỆT NAM

Trần Ngọc Diệp, Trần Thị Thu Phương

Phùng Bích Ngọc

Trường Đại học thương mại

Tóm tắt

Xu hướng phát triển của nền kinh tế số và thương mại điện tử tại Việt Nam nói riêng và trên thế giới nói chung đang ngày càng trở nên mạnh mẽ. Sự phát triển của thương mại điện tử cũng dẫn đến số lượng các vụ tranh chấp ngày càng gia tăng, đặc biệt là tranh chấp với người tiêu dùng. Thực tế, giá trị của mỗi tranh chấp lại thường rất nhỏ. Do vậy, việc sử dụng các cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp truyền thống sẽ trở nên công kềnh và tốn kém cả về mặt thời gian và tiền bạc. Bên cạnh đó, các giao dịch xuyên biên giới xuất hiện ngày càng nhiều do tính chất phi biên giới của thương mại điện tử. Các website thương mại điện tử trên thế giới như Alibaba, Ebay, ... thường xây dựng một cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến để giải quyết các tranh chấp phát sinh với khách hàng. Tuy nhiên, ở Việt Nam, cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến ODR (Online Dispute Resolution) chưa được chú trọng nghiên cứu và triển khai tại các website thương mại điện tử của Việt Nam. Bài viết đi sâu tìm hiểu về khả năng triển khai thực hiện cơ chế này trên các website thương mại điện tử xét ở góc độ pháp lý, nhằm bảo vệ quyền lợi người tiêu dùng trong các giao dịch thương mại điện tử.

Từ khóa: bảo vệ người tiêu dùng, hòa giải trực tuyến, giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến, pháp luật, thương lượng trực tuyến.

SOME LEGAL ISSUES RELATING TO ONLINE DISPUTE SETTLEMENT MECHANISM ON E-COMMERCE WEBSITES IN VIETNAM

Abstract

The development of the digital economy and e-commerce in Vietnam as well as all over the world is becoming more and more powerful. This trend also leads to an increasing number of disputes, especially disputes in relationships with consumers, in which the value of disputing is almost not worth very much. Therefore, the use of traditional dispute resolution mechanisms is becoming cumbersome and costly in terms of both time and money. Besides, cross-border transactions appear more due to the borderless feature of e-commerce. E-commerce websites in the world, such as Alibaba, and Ebay, ... often build an online mechanism to resolve consumer disputes. However, in Vietnam, the ODR (Online Dispute Resolution) has not been researched and implemented in Vietnam's e-commerce websites. The article delves into the possibility of implementing this mechanism on e-commerce websites, from a legal perspective, to protect consumers' interests in e-commerce transactions.

Keywords: consumer protection, online dispute resolution, online negotiation, online mediation, e-commerce law.

1. TỔNG QUAN TÌNH HÌNH NGHIÊN CỨU VÀ CÁC VẤN ĐỀ ĐẶT RA

Trên thế giới đã có nhiều công trình nghiên cứu về cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến. Từ năm 1997, Heuvel đã tiếp cận cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến như một giải pháp quan trọng đối với các tranh chấp thương mại điện tử xuyên biên giới (Esther van den Heuvel, 1997). Ngoài ra có thể kể đến công trình nghiên cứu của Katsh (2001) về giải quyết tranh chấp thương mại xuyên biên giới bằng phương thức trực tuyến (Ethan Katsh, 2001). Công trình này nêu ra những vấn đề có thể gặp phải khi áp dụng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến. Các kết quả nghiên cứu này có ý nghĩa quan trọng việc định hướng phát triển cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến trên các website thương mại điện tử. Tuy nhiên, do thời gian nghiên cứu của công trình khá xa, nên cần có những nghiên cứu cụ thể hơn và đánh giá việc áp dụng ODR trong thực tế tại Việt Nam như thế nào, từ đó xem xét những mục tiêu mà ODR đặt ra có đạt được hay không và tìm ra giải pháp khắc phục. Trong Colin Rule (2002), cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến đã được tiếp cận dưới góc độ kinh tế, với những giải pháp hướng tới mục đích tiết kiệm chi phí cho việc giải quyết tranh chấp, đồng thời nâng cao uy tín của doanh nghiệp (Colin Rule, 2002). Công trình thể hiện những đánh giá rõ ràng về tính hiệu quả của phương thức này đối với người bán, tuy nhiên chưa làm rõ được vai trò của nó đối với bảo vệ quyền của người tiêu dùng. Nghiên cứu của Cheri M. Ganeles (2002), đề cập tới phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp trung gian trực tuyến như một giải pháp mang tính đột phá tại thời điểm đó (Cheri M. Ganeles, 2002). Nghiên cứu này là tiền đề xây dựng phương thức và hệ thống giải quyết tranh chấp hiện đại. Ở Hoa Kỳ, những nghiên cứu về hệ thống giải quyết tranh chấp trong thương mại điện tử tại Hoa Kỳ cho thấy sự ưu việt trong việc giải quyết các tranh chấp trực tuyến giữa các bên, nhìn ở góc nhìn kinh tế.

Tại Việt Nam, đã có những công trình nghiên cứu về đề tài giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến, tuy nhiên những đề tài này chủ yếu đề cập tới giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến (ODR) như một phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp dùng chung trong tất cả các hoạt động xét xử của tòa án, trọng tài thương mại, chứ chưa được quan tâm nghiên cứu ở việc phát triển cơ chế này tại các website thương mại điện tử. Cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến được nghiên cứu ở góc độ là giải pháp thay thế hiệu quả cho các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp được vận hành theo truyền thống, đối với những trường hợp gặp khó khăn khi tiến hành giải quyết tranh chấp trực tiếp (Nguyễn Thành Minh Chánh, 2021). Từ góc độ của cơ quan quản lý nhà nước nghiên cứu “Giải quyết tranh chấp thương mại điện tử bằng phương pháp trực tuyến” của Bộ Tư pháp là công trình nghiên cứu bài bản và quy mô về các khía cạnh của phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến về mặt lý thuyết cũng như thực tiễn. Nghiên cứu này cung cấp những vấn đề mang tính lý luận đáng tin cậy về phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp ODR. Tuy nhiên, công trình này vẫn đang tiếp cận cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến ở khả năng sử dụng phương tiện điện tử cho các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp truyền thống chứ chưa chú trọng hướng đến việc phát triển cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp này ở các website thương mại điện tử. Mặt khác, có nhận định cho rằng việc đi sâu tìm hiểu về các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến nói chung, để thay thế cho việc sử dụng các phương thức này theo cách truyền thống, vừa tốn kém, không hiệu quả trong bối cảnh mới (Dương Quỳnh Hoa, 2021). Do vậy, để thích ứng và thúc đẩy thương mại điện tử phát triển, chính phủ nhiều quốc gia đã thúc đẩy việc ra đời và phát triển cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến. Công trình đã chỉ ra nhu cầu và cơ sở pháp lý cho việc triển khai cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến tại Việt Nam. Những vấn đề lý luận của giải quyết tranh chấp thương mại trực tuyến cũng được chú trọng

hướng tới, trong đó tập trung phân tích nội hàm của khái niệm và đặc điểm của giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến và những thách thức pháp lý đặt ra cho Việt Nam để phát triển phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến (Phan Thị Thanh Thủy, 2016). Tương tự, cũng có nhận định về định hướng phát triển của phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến trong sự biến đổi của cuộc cách mạng công nghiệp 4.0, từ đó rút ra những bài học thực tiễn cho Việt Nam (Hoàng Thế Liên và Trần Anh Huy, 2019).

Những vấn đề pháp lý trong việc triển khai áp dụng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến ở Việt Nam cũng được bước đầu được các nhà nghiên cứu chú trọng đến. Những vấn đề thuận lợi và khó khăn khi triển khai cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến ở Việt Nam đã được phân tích, nhìn nhận ở nhiều góc độ: từ phía cơ quan quản lý nhà nước, từ phía các chủ thể tham gia giao dịch thương mại điện tử (Hà Công Anh Bảo và Lê Hằng Mỹ Hạnh, 2017). Kết quả nghiên cứu cho thấy nếu có sự đồng thuận, thống nhất của các chủ thể tham gia vào giao dịch thương mại điện tử và sự hỗ trợ từ phía cơ quan nhà nước, thì cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến sẽ phát triển tại Việt Nam. Ở góc độ chính sách, nghiên cứu của tìm hiểu những vấn đề đặt ra để triển khai cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trong thương mại điện tử trên cơ sở các cam kết trong khuôn khổ của Hiệp định thương mại tự do EVFTA (Mutrap, 2016). Thực tế, Việt Nam đã có những hoạt động nhằm triển khai, ứng dụng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến, tuy nhiên sau một thời gian xây dựng và áp dụng, cần có sự đánh giá hiệu quả của những chính sách đã được đề ra.

Từ tổng quan các công trình nghiên cứu trong và ngoài nước về cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến, có thể thấy rằng các công trình mới chỉ tập trung phân tích những vấn đề chung của các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp được triển khai trực tuyến, thông qua phương tiện điện tử, như đánh giá khả năng thực hiện, những ưu điểm, hạn chế, những thuận lợi, khó khăn khi triển khai, ... Các nghiên cứu chưa đi sâu vào các khía cạnh pháp lý về việc triển khai trong thực tiễn. Ví dụ, chưa xác định rõ được bản chất của cơ chế này khi được triển khai trên một website thương mại điện tử, những ràng buộc đối với người tiêu dùng khi tham gia vào cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến được tiến hành bởi một website thương mại điện tử và quan điểm từ phía nhà nước đối với các tranh chấp thương mại điện tử trực tuyến được giải quyết bởi cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến được xây dựng và vận hành trên các website thương mại điện tử.

Những vấn đề này sẽ được nhóm tác giả đi sâu phân tích trên cơ sở của các quy định pháp luật hiện hành của Việt Nam, nhằm hướng tới bảo vệ quyền lợi người tiêu dùng, từ đó tạo lập niềm tin, sự yên tâm cho người tiêu dùng, thúc đẩy sự phát triển của thương mại điện tử ở Việt Nam. Kết cấu của bài viết xây dựng trên cơ sở mô hình nghiên cứu như sau: Từ góc độ lý thuyết chung về cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp thương mại điện tử trực tuyến, bài viết tham khảo thực tiễn thiết lập cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến nhằm bảo vệ người tiêu dùng tại một số quốc gia trên thế giới. Dựa vào việc phân tích cơ sở pháp lý và thực tiễn xây dựng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến trên một số website thương mại điện tử tại Việt Nam như Shopee, Lazada, bài viết nhận diện những vấn đề pháp lý đặt ra cho cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến trên các website thương mại điện tử, từ đó đưa ra một đề xuất hoàn thiện pháp luật Việt Nam cũng như những giải pháp hướng tới các doanh nghiệp và người tiêu dùng.

2. CƠ CHẾ GIẢI QUYẾT TRANH CHẤP THƯƠNG MẠI ĐIỆN TỬ TRỰC TUYẾN NHÌN Ở GÓC ĐỘ LÝ LUẬN

Ở một số quốc gia trên Thế giới, thuật ngữ “giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến” (Online dispute Resolution -ODR) được hiểu là các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến được phát triển từ các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp thay thế ngoài tòa án (Alternative Dispute Resolution- sau đây viết tắt là ADR). Nguyên nhân xuất hiện của các ADR xuất phát từ những yếu điểm của hệ thống giải quyết tranh chấp (sau đây viết tắt là GQTC) bằng cơ quan tòa án truyền thống, bao gồm sự phức tạp của các thủ tục tố tụng, sự tốn kém và bất tiện khi việc GQTC diễn ra trong một thời gian dài. Ngoài ra, với sự không ngừng tăng lên của các giao dịch và tranh chấp, hệ thống tòa án truyền thống dễ dàng trở nên quá tải và không đáp ứng đủ nguồn lực cả về vật chất và nhân lực cho việc giải quyết các tranh chấp. Vì vậy các phương thức GQTC ngoài tòa án là thương lượng, hòa giải và trọng tài được xem xét áp dụng như những giải pháp ưu việt hơn. Cùng với sự phát triển của internet, các giao dịch cũng trở nên phức tạp hơn. Khi này các phương thức GQTC truyền thống trở nên lúng túng với các đặc trưng mới của các tranh chấp trong thương mại điện tử (sau đây viết tắt là TMĐT). Các phương thức ADR được phát triển và áp dụng bởi chính các thương nhân sở hữu website và các tổ chức ngoài Nhà nước nhằm đạt tới những thỏa thuận đảm bảo quyền lợi cho các bên trong khoảng thời gian ngắn với chi phí hợp lý hơn. Từ đó, hệ thống các phương thức GQTC trực tuyến (ODR) được hình thành và nhanh chóng được thương mại hóa bởi các thương nhân và tổ chức chuyên nghiệp.

Trên thế giới, sau một quá trình áp dụng, ODR đã chứng minh được ưu điểm vượt trội trong việc giải quyết số lượng lớn các tranh chấp trong một thời gian ngắn và hiệu quả đáng kể trong việc GQTC trực tuyến. Theo Bản lưu ký kỹ thuật về giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến của UNCITRAL (Technical Note on ODR) thì thủ tục ODR gồm các giai đoạn: thương lượng (negotiation); hỗ trợ giải quyết (facilitated settlement); giai đoạn cuối cùng [a third (final) stage] (UNCITRAL, 2016).

Giai đoạn thương lượng: Khi nguyên đơn (claimant) nộp yêu cầu trên hệ thống ODR thì quản trị viên hệ thống ODR thông báo cho bị đơn (respondent) về yêu cầu của nguyên đơn và phản hồi cho nguyên đơn. Bước đầu thương lượng có thể được hỗ trợ bởi một công nghệ (có thể là AI), các bên có thể thương lượng trực tiếp trên nền tảng hệ thống ODR.

Giai đoạn hỗ trợ giải quyết: Nếu thương lượng không thành công, quản trị viên hệ thống ODR chỉ định một hòa giải viên hỗ trợ các bên thương lượng nhằm đạt mục đích thỏa thuận.

Giai đoạn cuối cùng: Nếu Giai đoạn 2 không thành công thì tiếp theo của tiến trình là quản trị viên hệ thống ODR hoặc hòa giải viên thông báo cho các bên về bước tiếp theo cần xử lý có thể giải quyết bằng trọng tài hoặc tòa án (UNCITRAL, 2010).

Như vậy, có thể thấy rằng, theo cách hiểu truyền thống, ODR được coi là chỉ bao gồm các phương thức GQTC thay thế ngoài tòa án.

Tuy nhiên, xu hướng phát triển hiện nay cho thấy, tòa án cũng đang dần nghiên cứu để ứng dụng phương tiện điện tử nhằm triển khai giải quyết tranh chấp, với nguyên tắc quá trình thụ lý, điều tra và xét xử các vụ án được tiến hành tương tự như trong giải quyết tranh chấp trực tiếp truyền thống. Nghị quyết số 33/2021/QH15 của Quốc hội đã bước đầu hình thành cơ

chế xét xử trực tuyến bằng Tòa án ở Việt Nam, đáp ứng tình hình dịch bệnh Covid 19 trong giai đoạn vừa qua.

Chính vì vậy, thuật ngữ “cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến” được hiểu là việc thiết lập, tổ chức, triển khai, quản lý các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp như thương lượng, hòa giải, trọng tài và tòa án thông qua phương tiện điện tử.

Trước tiên, đối với phương thức thương lượng: Trong tranh chấp TMĐT, thương lượng có thể được thực hiện thông qua việc trao đổi bằng các phương tiện email, tin nhắn, điện thoại, hoặc các cuộc gặp mặt trực tuyến. Về mặt bản chất, thương lượng trong GQTC trực tuyến có vai trò tạo thuận lợi cho các bên trong tranh chấp.

Thứ hai, phương thức hòa giải: Đây là một phương thức GQTC thay thế rất phổ biến. Các bên cùng nhau thỏa thuận việc thuê một cá nhân hay tổ chức trung gian hòa giải thực chất là việc hai bên đã hình thành một hợp đồng mới, trong đó kết luận mà hòa giải viên đưa ra là quyền và nghĩa vụ mới của các bên. Vì vậy, nếu một trong các bên không tự nguyện thực hiện kết luận này thì bên còn lại có quyền khiếu nại hoặc khởi kiện. Phương án hòa giải chỉ có tính cưỡng chế thi hành khi được tòa án công nhận theo thủ tục được pháp luật quy định. Trong GQTC trực tuyến hiện nay, các website cũng có thể tham gia vào phương thức hòa giải bằng việc cử một người đáp ứng tiêu chuẩn hòa giải viên để đứng ra giải quyết tranh chấp. Điều này hoàn toàn phù hợp với các giao dịch được thực hiện thông qua các nền tảng trung gian vì những nền tảng này là bên thứ ba khách quan, độc lập với quyền lợi của các bên, có đồng thời vì có tham gia trong giao dịch nên chủ thể này có thể nắm trong tay những bằng chứng có liên quan của các bên, từ đó tư vấn cho các bên để điều hòa lợi ích một cách phù hợp nhất.

Thứ ba, phương thức trọng tài: Trọng tài là phương thức GQTC thông qua một tổ chức trung gian chuyên nghiệp. So với hòa giải, trọng tài có trình tự thủ tục tổ tụng rõ ràng và chặt chẽ hơn. Giải quyết tranh chấp bằng trọng tài được thực hiện khi các bên tham gia có một thỏa thuận trọng tài được xác lập trước hoặc sau khi xảy ra tranh chấp. Thỏa thuận trọng tài này có thể được biểu hiện dưới dạng một điều khoản trong hợp đồng giữa các bên hoặc một phụ lục hợp đồng, hoặc thậm chí là một hợp đồng độc lập. Thẩm quyền GQTC của trọng tài được coi là loại trừ thẩm quyền của tòa án, vì vậy giá trị của phán quyết trọng tài là rất lớn. So với tòa án, phán quyết của trọng tài là chung thẩm, không trải qua nhiều giai đoạn tố tụng phức tạp như của tòa án, vì vậy có thể rút ngắn thời gian GQTC cho các bên tham gia. Tổ chức trọng tài có quyền đưa ra quyết định cuối cùng cho vụ việc và quyết định này được đảm bảo cơ chế thi hành. Thủ tục GQTC bằng trọng tài trực tuyến được thực hiện theo mô hình của các cuộc họp trực tuyến được ghi lại dưới dạng các dữ liệu điện tử. Tuy nhiên, cơ chế này đòi hỏi chi phí trọng tài khá cao, đồng thời việc giải quyết được áp dụng đơn lẻ cho từng trường hợp theo các trình tự, thủ tục độc lập, vì vậy không phù hợp với các giao dịch có số lượng lớn và giá trị tranh chấp nhỏ.

Thứ tư, phương thức tòa án: Tòa án trực tuyến được tiến hành theo các thủ tục và trình tự như tòa án truyền thống. Vì vậy phương thức này có những ưu điểm như tính cưỡng chế áp dụng cao, thuận lợi trong việc thu thập chứng cứ và chứng minh, có tính chất răn đe cũng như có thể tránh được việc các bên cố tình che giấu các tình tiết của vụ việc. Trong GQTC trực tuyến, tòa án mang bản chất của “trình tự phán quyết”, đưa ra quyết định cuối cùng cho vụ việc tranh chấp. Tuy vậy, tòa án không được coi là một cơ chế hữu hiệu cho các tranh chấp TMĐT

do các thủ tục phức tạp, tốn kém về mặt thời gian và chi phí, cũng như việc GQTC có tính chất hàng loạt sẽ khiến cho hệ thống này quá tải.

Thực tiễn cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp thương mại điện tử trên thế giới hiện nay còn được thực hiện thông qua các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp hỗn hợp như:

- Trung gian- Trọng tài trực tuyến: Là phương thức kết hợp giữa hòa giải trực tuyến và trọng tài trực tuyến. Trong phương thức này, trung tâm trọng tài có thể đồng thời đóng vai trò người hòa giải trực tuyến, tuy nhiên các bên cũng có thể thỏa thuận về việc sử dụng một trung tâm hòa giải và một trung tâm trọng tài độc lập với nhau. Trình tự GQTC sẽ bắt đầu bằng việc áp dụng thủ tục hòa giải, nếu các bên không thể đi tới sự đồng thuận về ý chí thì thủ tục trọng tài sẽ được áp dụng tiếp theo cho tranh chấp.
- Thanh tra: Là phương thức GQTC được thực hiện bởi một cơ quan độc lập trong bộ máy Nhà nước hoặc một tổ chức phi lợi nhuận, chủ yếu hướng tới các đối tượng là khiếu nại của người tiêu dùng và đưa ra các khuyến cáo cho việc GQTC. Thanh tra viên là những người trung lập, không chịu sự tác động của các bên. Ở giai đoạn đầu, các thanh tra viên sẽ tiến hành xem xét và thực hiện hòa giải giữa các bên. Nếu quy trình này không đem lại hiệu quả, thanh tra sẽ đưa ra khuyến cáo xử lý tranh chấp. Tuy nhiên, quy trình này cũng không có tính cưỡng chế bắt buộc.
- Tổ tụng giả định/ Hội thẩm trực tuyến: Là phương thức mà theo đó các bồi thẩm hoặc hội thẩm nhân dân sẽ tiến hành tiếp nhận các khiếu kiện và bằng chứng trực tuyến, sau đó các bồi thẩm này sẽ đưa ra các phán quyết không có tính bắt buộc đối với tranh chấp (Hà Công Anh Bảo và Lê Hằng Mỹ Hạnh, 2017).

Các phương thức GQTC trong TMĐT giúp các bên tham gia trong tranh chấp có nhiều sự lựa chọn hơn trong việc tìm ra phương thức phù hợp nhất với tranh chấp của mình. Sự đa dạng trong các phương thức cũng thể hiện xu hướng số hóa đối với các tranh chấp giúp có thể thu thập và lưu trữ các bằng chứng trong giao dịch một cách hiệu quả và giải quyết được những khó khăn về nhân lực GQTC cũng như rút ngắn thời gian và thủ tục GQTC.

Cơ chế GQTC trực tuyến có vai trò quan trọng trong việc thúc đẩy các giao dịch TMĐT phát triển dựa trên cơ sở tác động đến các đối tượng chủ thể chủ yếu của các giao dịch này. Việc có được cơ chế GQTC hiệu quả sẽ giúp cho các đối tượng tham gia giao dịch cảm thấy yên tâm hơn trong các tình huống rủi ro có thể xảy đến, vì vậy cũng góp phần loại bỏ rào cản về tâm lý của các chủ thể khi tham gia TMĐT. Đặc biệt, với hoạt động TMĐT xuyên biên giới, các yếu tố rủi ro và tính chất phức tạp của việc GQTC càng đòi hỏi một chính sách GQTC nói chung thực sự hỗ trợ cho các bên trong giao dịch, đặc biệt là với chủ thể yếu thế như người tiêu dùng. Việc sử dụng các cơ chế GQTC trực tuyến giúp tiết kiệm chi phí cũng như thời gian di chuyển tới địa điểm GQTC của các bên. Đồng thời việc áp dụng các phương thức GQTC trực tuyến một cách linh hoạt, nhất là đối với các tranh chấp tiêu dùng có số lượng lớn và giá trị nhỏ sẽ giúp hạn chế tình trạng lãng phí về nhân lực và vật lực cho GQTC.

3. THỰC TIỄN PHÁT TRIỂN CƠ CHẾ GIẢI QUYẾT TRANH CHẤP THƯƠNG MẠI ĐIỆN TỬ TRÊN THẾ GIỚI NHẪM BẢO VỆ QUYỀN LỢI NGƯỜI TIÊU DÙNG

Ở tầm quốc tế, UNCITRAL với vai trò là Ủy ban Liên hợp quốc về Luật Thương mại quốc tế đã đi đầu trong việc xây dựng và ban hành những quy định mang tính chất gợi mở với

tên gọi là những “Ghi chú kỹ thuật” (Technical notes) cho cơ chế GQTC trực tuyến (UNCITRAL, 2016). Ghi chú kỹ thuật hướng tới quy trình GQTC gồm ba bước, tuy nhiên hai bước đầu được xác định rõ là cơ chế thương lượng và trung gian trực tuyến trong khi bước cuối cùng chưa được xác định cụ thể. Ghi chú kỹ thuật của UNCITRAL mặc dù chỉ có tính chất khuyến nghị nhưng nó đã bước đầu đề ra khung pháp lý và định hướng cho việc thúc đẩy sự phát triển của các biện pháp ODR. Ghi chú cũng nhấn mạnh những ưu thế của phương thức ODR là đơn giản, nhanh chóng, tiết kiệm chi phí, linh động, an toàn và không đòi hỏi sự tham gia trực tiếp của các bên trong tranh chấp tại các phiên xét xử.

EU áp dụng các thủ tục và phương thức GQTC khác nhau cho từng loại tranh chấp. Trong đó GQTC trực tuyến được đặc biệt nhấn mạnh trong các tranh chấp về tiêu dùng và tranh chấp về tên miền, vốn là những tranh chấp có tính đặc trưng mà việc thực hiện ODR thể hiện rõ sự ưu việt của nó so với các phương thức truyền thống. Cơ sở pháp lý cho mô hình GQTC trực tuyến trong các giao dịch với NTD của EU là hai văn bản: Chỉ thị số 2013/11/EU về sử dụng các phương thức giải quyết thay thế đối với tranh chấp tiêu dùng, được ban hành vào năm 2013 và Quy định số 524/2013 về giải quyết trực tuyến các tranh chấp về tiêu dùng (sau đây gọi là Chỉ thị 2013 và Quy định 524). Chỉ thị 2013/11/EU đã đưa ra hai điều khoản mang tính cốt lõi cho việc áp dụng phương thức GQTC thay thế để giải quyết các tranh chấp tiêu dùng tại điều 5 và điều 8 của Chỉ thị (Directive 2013/11/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council, 2013). Theo đó các quốc gia thành viên của EU phải đảm bảo rằng các tổ chức cung cấp phương thức GQTC thay thế phải duy trì và cập nhật website để cung cấp cho các bên truy cập một cách dễ dàng các thông tin liên quan đến thủ tục GQTC và cho phép người tiêu dùng (sau đây viết tắt là NTD) nộp đơn khởi kiện cũng như cung cấp bằng chứng trực tuyến. Các quốc gia thành viên EU cũng phải đảm bảo tính hiệu quả của thủ tục GQTC thay thế (các thủ tục này phải có sẵn, có thể tiếp cận trực tuyến hoặc ngoại tuyến một cách dễ dàng ở bất cứ đâu. Quy định 524 (Sodiq O. Omoola, Umar A. Oseni, 2016) cụ thể hoá Chỉ thị 2013 thành 3 chương với 22 điều khoản quy định cụ thể để các quốc gia có thể xây dựng các cơ quan GQTC trực tuyến một cách phù hợp. Về cơ bản, thủ tục GQTC trực tuyến được thực hiện thông qua việc các quốc gia xây dựng một nền tảng GQTC trực tuyến và hệ thống các điểm hỏi-đáp quốc gia về GQTC trực tuyến. Trong đó nền tảng đóng vai trò là cơ chế tiếp nhận các tranh chấp để giải quyết, trong khi các điểm hỏi-đáp là nơi hướng dẫn và giải thích về các thủ tục GQTC cho NTD. Điều này vừa đảm bảo NTD ở nhiều trình độ khác nhau đều có thể được hỗ trợ trong việc nộp đơn, đồng thời việc nộp đơn trực tuyến sẽ ít bị ảnh hưởng bởi yếu tố cơ sở hạ tầng kỹ thuật không đảm bảo thông qua sự hỗ trợ của các điểm hỏi-đáp.

Quy trình GQTC bao gồm các bước: (1): Nộp đơn khởi kiện; (2) Xử lý thông tin và chuyển đơn khởi kiện; (3) Giải quyết tranh chấp. Trong đó bước 3, tranh chấp sẽ được giải quyết tại một tổ chức GQTC thay thế. Tuy nhiên Quy định không có yêu cầu về trình tự, thủ tục cụ thể tại các tổ chức này. Điều này có nghĩa là các tổ chức GQTC thay thế sẽ có quyền chủ động, linh hoạt trong việc đưa ra các quy chế hoạt động và quy trình GQTC phù hợp. Như vậy nền tảng GQTC trực tuyến sẽ đóng vai trò trung gian giữa các bên tham gia tranh chấp và tổ chức GQTC thay thế trong việc nhận đơn khiếu nại, lưu trữ các dữ liệu liên quan đến tranh chấp. Thủ tục GQTC thay thế cũng không loại trừ quyền khởi kiện của các bên theo thủ tục tư pháp.

Tại Hoa Kỳ, Ủy ban Thương mại Liên bang Hoa Kỳ (Federal Trade Commission – FTC) là Cơ quan bảo vệ NTD Hoa Kỳ không quy định giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến (ODR) liên quan đến NTD trong giao dịch trực tuyến mà chủ yếu bảo vệ NTD liên quan đến các hành vi lừa đảo và không công bằng trên thị trường. Mặc dù, không quy định giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến (ODR) liên quan đến NTD trong giao dịch trực tuyến nhưng trong thương mại điện tử các hành vi lừa đảo và không công bằng trên không gian mạng rất tinh vi, phức tạp và không dự đoán được. Do đó, các sàn giao dịch thương mại điện tử và các trang web bán hàng tại Hoa Kỳ như Ebay, Amazon...đều sử dụng nền tảng ODR trong giải quyết các tranh chấp phát sinh giữa NTD và người cung ứng hàng hóa, dịch vụ trên các sàn giao dịch đó. Có thể thấy, tại Hoa Kỳ để xây dựng chính sách bảo vệ NTD trong các giao dịch trực tuyến tránh hành vi lừa đảo và không công bằng trên thị trường thì các trang thương mại điện tử buộc phải sử dụng nền tảng ODR cho giải quyết tranh chấp tương ứng trong môi trường không gian mạng (Hà Tú Cầu và Nguyễn Thị Hằng Như, 2018).

Là một nước châu Á, Trung Quốc là một trong những quốc gia có tốc độ phát triển về TMĐT nhanh nhất trên thế giới. Sau khi COVID-19 bùng nổ, thương mại điện tử xuyên biên giới đang bùng nổ và Trung Quốc là nước xuất khẩu lớn trong lĩnh vực kinh doanh ngoại thương đang phát triển nhanh chóng này. Đương nhiên, điều này đã dẫn đến sự gia tăng đồng thời các tranh chấp xuyên biên giới giữa các nhà xuất khẩu Trung Quốc, các nền tảng thương mại điện tử Trung Quốc, người tiêu dùng ở nước ngoài và các nền tảng thương mại điện tử ở nước ngoài. Các nền tảng thương mại điện tử xuyên biên giới thường xuyên bị kiện, chiếm khoảng 60%, tuy nhiên, họ ít khi thua kiện (Hong Xuejun, Wang Jiangqiao, Xiao Neng và Lai Yuexu, 2021). Các vụ tranh chấp TMĐT xuyên biên giới gây ra những khó khăn cho các cơ quan GQTC vì những lý do sau: (1) Kiện tụng xuyên biên giới của Trung Quốc yêu cầu các bên ở nước ngoài phải công chứng và chứng thực các giấy tờ tùy thân của họ, điều này làm phát sinh thêm thời gian và chi phí; (2) Các trường hợp thương mại điện tử xuyên biên giới áp dụng quy trình dịch vụ truyền thống, phức tạp về thủ tục, tốn thời gian và hiếm khi thành công; (3) Việc áp dụng pháp luật trong các vụ việc thương mại điện tử xuyên biên giới rất phức tạp. Vì vậy tỉ lệ xử lý các vụ việc chưa cao và tỷ lệ NTD giành lợi thế trong tranh chấp cũng rất nhỏ. Vì đặc trưng của các giao dịch tiêu dùng như vậy nên cơ chế GQTC trực tuyến cũng đang là một lựa chọn được đầu tư. Tòa án Internet Hàng Châu là tòa án Internet đầu tiên ở Trung Quốc. Hàng Châu, nơi đặt trụ sở của Alibaba, là thành phố thịnh vượng nhất ở Trung Quốc về thương mại điện tử. Theo kinh nghiệm của Alibaba, một nền tảng trực tuyến có thiết lập cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến tạo điều kiện thuận lợi cho người tiêu dùng (Zhang Juanjuan, 2016). Alibaba đã xây dựng nên một loạt các quy chế về giải quyết tranh chấp như: Taobao Rules, Taobao Rules of Dispute Settlement, Tmall International Dispute Resolution Rules, Trade Dispute Rules Ngoài ra, Alibaba còn thiết lập một loạt nền tảng trực tuyến để giải quyết tranh chấp. Về cơ bản, có 04 phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp theo quy định của Taobao với cùng một quy trình: (1) Thương lượng giữa các bên; (2) Sự can thiệp của Dịch vụ khách hàng; (3) Hệ thống giám sát công cộng; (4) Báo cáo trực tuyến.

Kinh nghiệm của các quốc gia cho thấy, cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến đã được quan tâm nghiên cứu và xây dựng khung khổ pháp lý chung cho việc thiết lập. Các quốc gia đều cho phép các website thương mại điện tử xây dựng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp, tạo điều kiện thuận lợi cho việc giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến với người tiêu dùng.

4. NHỮNG VẤN ĐỀ PHÁP LÝ ĐẶT RA ĐỐI VỚI CƠ CHẾ GIẢI QUYẾT TRANH CHẤP TRỰC TUYẾN TRÊN CÁC WEBSITE THƯƠNG MẠI ĐIỆN TỬ VÀ MỘT SỐ KHUYẾN NGHỊ CHO VIỆT NAM

Trong những năm vừa qua, khung khổ pháp lý liên quan tới TMĐT đã cơ bản được hoàn thiện với 21 văn bản Luật và 85 văn bản dưới luật được ban hành bởi các cơ quan Nhà nước ở Trung ương (Sách trắng về TMĐT Việt Nam, 2022). Đây là khối lượng văn bản lớn, thể hiện nhu cầu điều chỉnh cũng như sự phát triển mạnh mẽ của TMĐT tại Việt Nam. Đồng thời nó cũng thể hiện sự quan tâm của Nhà nước đối với lĩnh vực này. Các văn bản được quy định theo hướng làm rõ các hoạt động thương mại điện tử, qui định quyền và nghĩa vụ của các chủ thể liên quan đến hoạt động thương mại điện tử, đồng thời tăng cường vai trò quản lý của các cơ quan nhà nước từ trung ương tới địa phương. Dù Việt Nam chưa có nhiều quy định trực tiếp, cụ thể về ODR nhưng các văn bản luật hiện hành cũng đã và đang hình thành cơ sở để xây dựng phương thức này trong thời gian tới.

Các quy định của pháp luật Việt Nam hiện hành đã chú ý tới việc giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến trên các website thương mại điện tử. Pháp luật đưa ra yêu cầu chung là các website thương mại điện tử phải công bố một cách công khai về cơ chế tiếp nhận và giải quyết các khiếu nại, tranh chấp phát sinh giữa các bên trong quan hệ trên website.

Luật giao dịch điện tử năm 2023 cũng yêu cầu chủ quản nền tảng số trung gian quy mô lớn phục vụ giao dịch điện tử có trách nhiệm công bố công khai, phổ biến cơ chế phản ánh vướng mắc và xử lý vướng mắc phát sinh trong giao dịch điện tử (Điều 47).

Điều 76 Nghị định về thương mại điện tử (bao gồm Nghị định 52/2013 và Nghị định 85/2021) quy định tại khoản 5: “Giải quyết khiếu nại, tranh chấp trên website cung cấp dịch vụ thương mại điện tử:

a) *Thương nhân, tổ chức cung cấp dịch vụ thương mại điện tử phải công bố rõ trên website quy trình tiếp nhận, trách nhiệm xử lý khiếu nại của khách hàng và cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp liên quan đến hợp đồng được giao kết trên website thương mại điện tử của mình;*

b) *Nếu thương nhân, tổ chức cung cấp dịch vụ thương mại điện tử không công bố thông tin theo quy định tại Điểm a Khoản này thì phải trực tiếp chịu trách nhiệm tiếp nhận, xử lý khiếu nại của khách hàng và giải quyết các tranh chấp liên quan đến hợp đồng được giao kết trên website thương mại điện tử của mình;*

c) *Thương nhân, tổ chức cung cấp dịch vụ thương mại điện tử được tham gia hòa giải tranh chấp phát sinh giữa khách hàng với người bán trên website thương mại điện tử của mình.”*

Điều 36- Nghị định về thương mại điện tử cũng quy định: “Trách nhiệm của thương nhân, tổ chức cung cấp dịch vụ sàn giao dịch thương mại điện tử: ... Công bố công khai cơ chế giải quyết các tranh chấp phát sinh trong quá trình giao dịch trên sàn giao dịch thương mại điện tử. Khi khách hàng trên sàn giao dịch thương mại điện tử phát sinh mâu thuẫn với người bán hoặc bị tổn hại lợi ích hợp pháp, phải cung cấp cho khách hàng thông tin về người bán, tích cực hỗ trợ khách hàng bảo vệ quyền và lợi ích hợp pháp của mình.”; “Là đầu mối tiếp nhận và giải quyết các khiếu nại của người tiêu dùng trong trường hợp một giao dịch thực hiện trên sàn giao dịch thương mại điện tử có nhiều hơn 02 bên tham gia.” Tại Điều 41: “Trách

nhiệm của thương nhân, tổ chức cung cấp dịch vụ khuyến mại trực tuyến: ... *Xây dựng và công bố trên website cơ chế tiếp nhận, giải quyết các khiếu nại của khách hàng về chất lượng hàng hóa, dịch vụ được khuyến mại hoặc hàng hóa, dịch vụ dùng để khuyến mại.*” Nội dung này cũng được nhắc tới tại Điều 30- Luật công nghệ thông tin 2006.

Căn cứ Điều 54 Luật bảo vệ quyền lợi người tiêu dùng năm 2023, phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp giữa người tiêu dùng và tổ chức, cá nhân kinh doanh được thực hiện theo hình thức trực tiếp, trực tuyến hoặc hình thức khác theo quy định của pháp luật có liên quan.

Như vậy, những quy định này đã thể hiện khung pháp lý cơ bản để triển khai xây dựng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến trên website thương mại điện tử. Cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến trên các website thương mại điện tử có thể hướng tới các phương thức: thương lượng, hòa giải. Các website thương mại điện tử cũng có thể liên kết với các trung tâm trọng tài để có thể sử dụng dịch vụ trọng tài trực tuyến của các trung tâm trọng tài. Tuy nhiên, có một vấn đề còn tồn tại ở đây, đó là việc các “*Thương nhân, tổ chức cung cấp dịch vụ thương mại điện tử được tham gia hòa giải tranh chấp phát sinh giữa khách hàng với người bán trên website thương mại điện tử của mình*” (Điều 76 khoản 5 Nghị định về thương mại điện tử). Về mặt pháp lý, theo quy định của Nghị định 22/2017 về hòa giải thương mại, thì hòa giải có hai hình thức là hòa giải thương mại quy chế và hòa giải thương mại vụ việc. Áp dụng đối với trường hợp thương nhân, tổ chức cung cấp dịch vụ thương mại điện tử khi tham gia hòa giải tranh chấp giữa khách hàng và người bán trên website của mình, thì chỉ có thể tham gia với tư cách là hòa giải thương mại vụ việc, là hình thức giải quyết tranh chấp do hòa giải viên thương mại vụ việc được các bên lựa chọn tiến hành theo quy định của Nghị định này và thỏa thuận của các bên. Trong khi đó, căn cứ Điều 7 của Nghị định 22/2017 về hòa giải viên, thì hòa giải viên phải là cá nhân. Chính vì vậy, câu hỏi đặt ra trong trường hợp chủ sở hữu website thương mại điện tử là tổ chức thì việc tham gia hòa giải sẽ được thực hiện như thế nào? Tiếp theo, sau khi tranh chấp được giải quyết bởi các website thương mại điện tử, các bên có phải chịu sự ràng buộc đối với các kết quả giải quyết tranh chấp này không? Liệu các bên có quyền để sử dụng các tranh chấp bên ngoài cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp của website thương mại điện tử không, trong trường hợp không thỏa mãn với quyết định giải quyết tranh chấp?

Từ những phân tích về các quy định của pháp luật Việt Nam, có thể thấy những mâu thuẫn của hệ thống pháp luật hiện hành và những vướng mắc khó có thể triển khai trong thực tế.

Để khẳng định nhận định trên, nhóm tác giả tiến hành khảo sát và so sánh chính sách giải quyết tranh chấp trên một số website TMĐT của Việt Nam hiện nay. Nghiên cứu lựa chọn chính sách của Shopee.vn với tư cách là doanh nghiệp có doanh số lớn nhất, Lazada.com với tư cách là doanh nghiệp có doanh số lớn thứ hai, có thị trường cả trong và ngoài nước. Nhóm tác giả tiến hành đối chiếu dựa trên các tiêu chí: sự công khai của các điều khoản GQTC, vai trò của website trong GQTC, thủ tục GQTC.

STT	Tên doanh nghiệp	Tên website/ứng dụng
1	Công ty TNHH Shopee	Shopee
2	Công ty TNHH Recess	Lazada
3	Công ty TNHH Grab	Grab
4	Công ty TNHH Woowa Brothers Việt Nam	Baemin
5	Công ty TNHH Ti Ki	Tiki
6	Công ty CP Thương mại Công nghệ GOVIET	GoJek
7	Công ty Cổ Phần Công Nghệ Sen-Đò	Sendo
8	Công ty Cổ Phần Foody	Foody/ShopeeFood
9	Công ty Cổ phần BE GROUP	Be
10	Công ty CP Dịch vụ Tức Thời	Aha Move

Nguồn: Khảo sát của Bộ Công Thương năm 2021

a) Chính sách giải quyết tranh chấp của Shopee

Những thông tin về chính sách GQTC của Shopee được website công bố công khai trong các điều khoản chính sách của mình và được chia thành các mục nhỏ cụ thể giúp người dùng có thể dễ dàng truy cập.

- Về vai trò, thẩm quyền của website trong GQTC:

Trong chính sách GQTC của mình, Shopee thiết lập một cơ chế khuyến khích các bên trong tranh chấp tham gia thương lượng với sự tư vấn của website (xem thêm tại Phụ lục 1.1). Trong trường hợp này website đóng vai trò là bên tham gia trình tự tư vấn trong thủ tục thương lượng. Sau đó các bên nếu không có tiếng nói chung sẽ có quyền khiếu nại lên các cơ quan có thẩm quyền để GQTC. Trường hợp các bên sử dụng Shopee để giải quyết tranh chấp, thay vì sử dụng các thủ tục tố tụng thì phải thể hiện rõ thông qua cam kết. Khi đó quyết định của Shopee sẽ là quyết định cuối cùng. Người dùng cũng có thể yêu cầu Shopee hỗ trợ giải quyết tranh chấp. Yêu cầu này phải được thể hiện rõ bằng văn bản. Khi đó Shopee sẽ can thiệp trên cơ sở Chính sách Đảm bảo và Chính sách Trả hàng và Hoàn tiền của Shopee.

- Về thủ tục GQTC:

Khi phát sinh tranh chấp hoặc khiếu nại, Shopee khuyến khích giải pháp thương lượng, hòa giải giữa các bên để đạt được sự đồng thuận về phương án giải quyết. Nếu hai bên không thể thương lượng với nhau và yêu cầu Shopee đứng ra giải quyết vụ việc. Quyết định của Shopee là quyết định cuối cùng.

Đối với Người bán hàng nước ngoài: *Shopee là đại diện giải quyết các khiếu nại của người tiêu dùng liên quan đến hàng hóa, dịch vụ do thương nhân nước ngoài cung cấp theo quy định của Bộ luật dân sự về đại diện.*

Shopee có cơ chế GQTC dành cho các giao dịch xuyên biên giới với các người bán nước ngoài, theo đó shopee sẽ có vai trò đại diện cho người bán nước ngoài trong tranh chấp với NTD Việt Nam

“Nếu có khiếu nại phát sinh giữa Người mua và Người bán hàng nước ngoài, Shopee có trách nhiệm đại diện cho Người bán hàng giải quyết tranh chấp phát sinh theo quy định của Bộ luật dân sự về đại diện.” (Xem thêm tại phụ lục 1.2) [20]

Với các quy định về trình tự, thủ tục GQTC, có thể thấy Shopee khuyến khích sự hoà giải, thương lượng giữa các bên. Tuy nhiên, nếu các bên không thương lượng được và cùng nhau thống nhất đề nghị Shopee giải quyết thì Shopee sẽ đứng ra tiếp nhận và GQTC. Quyết định của Shopee đưa ra sau tranh chấp được coi là kết luận cuối cùng của vụ việc. Nếu xét ở góc độ pháp lý, có thể thấy, vai trò của Shopee trong trường hợp này là giải quyết tranh chấp bằng phương thức hòa giải. Shopee đã thực hiện quy định tại khoản 5 Điều 76 Nghị định về thương mại điện tử. Tuy nhiên, vấn đề đặt ra là tư cách pháp lý của website thương mại điện tử là như thế nào? Vấn đề này có thể được hiểu rõ hơn thông qua quy định liên quan đến việc phân định trách nhiệm giữa Người mua, Người bán và Shopee trong việc giải quyết các vấn đề phát sinh từ giao dịch thực hiện trên website/ứng dụng. (xem thêm tại phụ lục 1.3) [21]

Shopee sẽ cử nhân viên liên lạc, hòa giải cho các bên. Nếu vậy, trong trường hợp này, Shopee cần bảo đảm điều kiện của một hòa giải viên được quy định trong Nghị định 22/2017.

Cũng qua phân tích các nội dung nêu trên, có thể thấy, nếu căn cứ theo quy định của pháp luật hiện hành, việc Shopee tự quy định rằng quyết định của Shopee là quyết định cuối cùng có thể vi phạm quy định của pháp luật liên quan đến nội dung điều kiện giao dịch chung được quy định trong Luật bảo vệ quyền lợi người tiêu dùng. Theo đó, điều kiện giao dịch chung không được chứa đựng điều khoản hạn chế, loại trừ quyền khiếu nại, khởi kiện của người tiêu dùng (Điều 25 khoản 2 Luật bảo vệ quyền lợi người tiêu dùng).

b) Chính sách giải quyết tranh chấp của Lazada

Lazada là một trong số ít các website có chính sách dành cho người bán nội địa và người bán nước ngoài riêng biệt. Tương tự như với Shopee, Lazada cũng thiết kế website với những điều khoản chính sách riêng biệt, có thể dễ dàng truy cập bất cứ lúc nào.

- Về vai trò, thẩm quyền của website trong GQTC: Lazada công khai chính sách áp dụng đối với các đối tượng chủ thể khác nhau: với bên mua thì Lazada sẽ hỗ trợ đàm phán để giải quyết tranh chấp một cách hòa bình và hợp lý; với bên bán thì Lazada sẽ giải quyết tranh chấp và đưa ra quyết định theo các quy định của mình. Như vậy, Lazada tuyên bố đóng vai trò hỗ trợ đàm phán để GQTC, nói cách khác, đây là cơ chế khuyến khích GQTC thông qua thương lượng, website chỉ có vai trò là người trung gian hỗ trợ. Tuy nhiên, trong chính sách bảo vệ đối với người bán, Lazada lại tuyên bố sẽ là cơ quan GQTC và đưa ra quyết định. (Xem thêm phụ lục 2.1) [23]

- Về thủ tục GQTC:

Đối với nhà bán hàng trong nước, chính sách GQTC đối với những giao dịch của thương nhân Việt Nam của Lazada có một số điểm đáng chú ý như sau:

+ Lazada và người bán đều có trách nhiệm tiếp nhận khiếu nại và hỗ trợ Khách Hàng liên quan đến giao dịch (ràng buộc nghĩa vụ của người bán)

+ Lazada không tuyên bố bắt buộc mà khuyến khích các bên thực hiện giải pháp thương lượng, hòa giải. Trong trường hợp nằm ngoài khả năng và thẩm quyền của Lazada thì Khách Hàng có thể yêu cầu đưa vụ việc ra giải quyết bởi cơ quan nhà nước có thẩm quyền. Website không áp đặt phương thức GQTC sau thương lượng, hoà giải không thành, cũng không chủ động cho một thương lượng nào về biện pháp GQTC ngoài Nhà nước. Trong trường hợp giao dịch thực hiện trên Sàn TMĐT Lazada có nhiều hơn hai (2) bên tham gia, Lazada sẽ là đầu mối tiếp nhận và giải quyết các khiếu nại của người mua.

+ Lazada hỗ trợ việc thi hành các quyết định của cơ quan GQTC sau khi kết luận cuối cùng được đưa ra thông qua các quyền đối với tài khoản của người dùng trên website của mình. Đây có thể coi là một cơ chế hỗ trợ có tính chất răn đe đối với các vi phạm.

Đối với đối tượng người bán không có hiện diện tại Việt Nam, Lazada cũng đóng vai trò là người đại diện theo đúng quy định của pháp luật, tuy nhiên phạm vi đại diện được quy định rõ chỉ trong việc tiếp nhận và giải quyết các khiếu nại liên quan đến hàng hoá của người bán. Điều này đồng nghĩa với việc Lazada không đại diện toàn bộ cho thương nhân nếu các thủ tục GQTC ngoài website được diễn ra. (Xem thêm phụ lục 2.2) [22]

Đồng thời Lazada cũng đưa ra những ràng buộc chặt chẽ về việc người mua chỉ được khiếu nại trong các trường hợp cố định cụ thể và với điều kiện bắt buộc là người mua phải đã thanh toán cho hàng hoá đó. Còn trong trường hợp người mua chưa thanh toán hoặc đã thực hiện những biện pháp để thu hồi khoản thanh toán của mình thì Lazada sẽ không thực hiện nghĩa vụ tiếp nhận và giải quyết khiếu nại. Điều này sẽ giới hạn những trường hợp mà người mua hàng theo phương thức thanh toán sau nhưng không nhận được đúng hàng hoá mà mình mong muốn.

(c) Với quy trình tiếp nhận và giải quyết khiếu nại, Lazada xây dựng những quy trình riêng đối với hai dạng người bán khác nhau trên website, trong đó website đóng vai trò là người đại diện đối với người bán nước ngoài trong tranh chấp với người mua hàng.

Lazada tiếp nhận và hỗ trợ GQTC đối với những đối tượng là người bán trong nước, đồng thời cho phép khả năng các bên tham gia tranh chấp được quyền khiếu nại tới cơ quan Nhà nước có thẩm quyền nếu thương lượng không thành công. Tuy nhiên, với đối tượng là người bán nước ngoài, quy chế hoạt động của website không đề cập tới phương thức GQTC nào cụ thể.

Qua phân tích ví dụ điển hình về cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến của hai website thương mại điện tử là Shopee và Lazada, có thể nhận thấy rằng các website có những chính sách khác nhau về GQTC, dù vẫn có những đặc điểm chung cơ bản như sau:

+ Các website trên đều đã xây dựng cơ chế tiếp nhận và GQTC cho các chủ thể tham gia giao dịch và công khai về những điều khoản hợp đồng theo mẫu và điều kiện giao dịch chung trên website và ứng dụng.

+ Các website đều tuyên bố vai trò của mình trong việc tiếp nhận các tranh chấp và có sự tham gia ở những mức độ khác nhau trong tranh chấp.

+ Các website đều ưu tiên việc thương lượng và hoà giải trong giai đoạn đầu tiên của GQTC. Các website đều hỗ trợ quá trình thương lượng giải quyết tranh chấp giữa các bên.

+ Các website đều có cơ chế để tiếp nhận tranh chấp, khiếu nại trực tuyến qua hệ thống thông tin của mình.

+ Sau thương lượng, hoà giải không thành, các website đều không kiến nghị khả năng các bên thương lượng về cơ chế GQTC khác, mà trao quyền để các bên khiếu nại với cơ quan Nhà nước.

Tuy nhiên, các website cũng có những đặc điểm riêng biệt liên quan đến sự tham gia và tuyên bố về vai trò tham gia trong tranh chấp của các website có sự khác nhau (về cách thức tham gia, vai trò trong các giai đoạn của tranh chấp...). Nếu như Shopee sẽ tham gia với hòa giải tranh chấp giữa các bên và coi quyết định của mình là cuối cùng thì Lazada chỉ hỗ trợ các bên giải quyết tranh chấp. Lazada cũng có thể đóng vai trò người đại diện bên bán nước ngoài để giải quyết các khiếu nại của người mua. Trong trường hợp giao dịch thực hiện trên Sàn TMĐT Lazada có nhiều hơn hai (2) bên tham gia, Lazada sẽ là đầu mối tiếp nhận và giải quyết các khiếu nại của người mua. Tuy nhiên, trong trường hợp này Lazada chưa thể hiện rõ vai trò của mình khi đứng ra giải quyết các khiếu nại của người mua (với tư cách là chủ thể đứng ra hòa giải?), cũng như kết quả sau khi giải quyết khiếu nại của người mua mà người mua chưa cảm thấy thỏa mãn.

Sự khác biệt và tính phức tạp trong thủ tục GQTC của các website có thể có những ảnh hưởng khác nhau tới tâm lý của người dùng (cả người bán và người mua) và đem lại những tác động khác nhau tới việc quyết định sử dụng website hay ứng dụng đó cho những giao dịch tiếp theo.

Xét về mặt pháp lý, thực tiễn của hai website thương mại điện tử có thị phần lớn nhất của Việt Nam hiện nay cho thấy còn nhiều điểm chưa rõ trong cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp mà các website này xây dựng. Những vấn đề liên quan đến vai trò của các website trong việc đứng ra giải quyết tranh chấp giữa các bên, hiệu lực của các kết quả giải quyết tranh chấp, những hạn chế về quyền sử dụng các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp của người dùng trong một số trường hợp nhất định là những vấn đề pháp lý còn tồn tại và có sự thực hiện khác nhau giữa các website thương mại điện tử.

Trên cơ sở các phân tích nêu trên, nhóm nghiên cứu đưa ra một số đề xuất hoàn thiện pháp luật và một số giải pháp hướng tới các cơ quan quản lý nhà nước, tới các website thương mại điện tử cũng như người tiêu dùng nhằm hướng tới việc xây dựng và sử dụng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến trên các website thương mại điện tử một cách hiệu quả, phù hợp với quy định của pháp luật.

Thứ nhất, về phía các cơ quan xây dựng pháp luật: Cần bổ sung các quy định chi tiết, hướng dẫn các website thương mại điện tử xây dựng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến đúng với các quy định của pháp luật. Các quy định chi tiết này cần được thể hiện trong một văn bản thống nhất, với mục tiêu hướng tới là hướng dẫn các website thương mại điện tử xây dựng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trực tuyến phù hợp với quy định của pháp luật. Trong đó,

website thương mại điện tử cần thể hiện rõ vai trò, tư cách pháp lý của mình trong việc giải quyết tranh chấp giữa các bên. Nói một cách cụ thể hơn, các website thương mại điện tử có thể đứng ra xây dựng cơ chế hỗ trợ cho các bên thương lượng hoặc cũng có thể đứng ra làm trung gian hòa giải giữa các bên. Tuy nhiên, việc thực hiện hòa giải phải tuân thủ theo quy định của pháp luật có liên quan. Kết quả hòa giải sẽ được công nhận theo quy định của pháp luật tố tụng dân sự và sẽ có tính ràng buộc đối với các bên khi được tòa án công nhận. Trong trường hợp, không hòa giải thành thì các bên vẫn có quyền để sử dụng các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp khác, theo quy định của pháp luật. Trường hợp website thương mại điện tử xây dựng cơ chế với các công cụ để hỗ trợ các bên thương lượng hoặc làm trung gian (mà không phải là hòa giải thương mại theo quy định của pháp luật) để giải quyết tranh chấp thì các bên vẫn có thể được quyền sử dụng các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp khác, theo quy định của pháp luật vào bất cứ lúc nào.

Thứ hai, về phía các cơ quan quản lý nhà nước: Các cơ quan quản lý nhà nước cần có trách nhiệm rà soát nội dung của các Quy chế hoạt động của các website thương mại điện tử để bảo đảm sao cho các điều khoản về cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp phù hợp với quy định của pháp luật. Biết rằng, để được công nhận và tiến hành hoạt động hợp pháp tại Việt Nam, thương nhân, tổ chức sở hữu website sàn thương mại điện tử phải nộp hồ sơ đăng ký đến cơ quan quản lý nhà nước. Một trong những nội dung cần phải có trong hồ sơ là Quy chế hoạt động của sàn giao dịch thương mại điện tử. Nếu cơ quan quản lý nhà nước không rà soát nội dung các quy định liên quan đến cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp thì sẽ dẫn đến trường hợp gây hiểu lầm cho người tiêu dùng, ảnh hưởng đến quá trình áp dụng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trong thực tiễn.

Thứ ba, về phía các website thương mại điện tử: Cần xây dựng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp rõ ràng hơn, minh bạch hơn về vai trò, tư cách pháp lý của website thương mại điện tử và khả năng sử dụng các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp khác ngoài cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp của website thương mại điện tử. Các website có thị phần lớn có thể học tập kinh nghiệm của Alibaba, khi xây dựng một cơ chế với nhiều công cụ khác nhau để hỗ trợ các bên giải quyết tranh chấp. Các công cụ này đều cho phép các bên được quyền sử dụng các hình thức giải quyết tranh chấp khác, hoặc các công cụ hỗ trợ khác trong trường hợp không thấy thỏa mãn với kết quả giải quyết tranh chấp. Trường hợp website thương mại điện tử tham gia với tư cách hòa giải, thì cần phải tuân thủ đúng các quy định của pháp luật về điều kiện của hòa giải viên. Bên cạnh đó, cần thông tin rõ cho người tiêu dùng biết về tư cách pháp lý là hòa giải của website thương mại điện tử, và về hệ quả pháp lý của kết quả hòa giải. Trong trường hợp này, website thương mại điện tử cũng cần xây dựng một đội ngũ các nhân viên đáp ứng đủ tiêu chuẩn hòa giải viên để các bên tranh chấp có thể lựa chọn. Các website thương mại điện tử cũng cần lưu ý trong các quy chế giải quyết tranh chấp của mình về việc hạn chế của quyền người tiêu dùng trong việc sử dụng các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp khác như trọng tài, tòa án. Biết rằng, theo quy định của pháp luật hiện hành, việc hạn chế, loại trừ quyền khiếu nại, khởi kiện của người tiêu dùng sẽ dẫn đến sự vô hiệu của các điều khoản quy định. Cơ quan quản lý nhà nước có thẩm quyền cũng cần có hướng dẫn cho người tiêu dùng về quyền sử dụng các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp và việc sử dụng cơ chế giải quyết tranh chấp trên các website thương mại điện tử. Thực trạng cho thấy các quyền này hiện nay được quy định trên nhiều văn bản khác nhau: trong Luật bảo vệ quyền lợi người tiêu dùng, Nghị định về thương mại điện tử, Nghị định về hòa giải thương mại, ... Ngoài ra, còn có những quy định được thể hiện trong các đạo luật khác có liên quan như Bộ luật Dân sự, Bộ luật Tố tụng dân sự,

Luật trọng tài thương mại, ... Tình trạng này có thể gây khó khăn cho người tiêu dùng trong việc hiểu, nắm bắt.

Thứ tư, về phía người tiêu dùng: Người tiêu dùng cần nắm được các quyền sử dụng các phương thức giải quyết tranh chấp phát sinh khi tham gia các giao dịch trên các website thương mại điện tử. Để có thể bảo vệ quyền và lợi ích hợp pháp của mình, người tiêu dùng phải là người chủ động cập nhật các quy định của pháp luật, chứ không phải ai khác.

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Điều khoản dịch vụ của shopee:

<https://help.shopee.vn/portal/article/77243?previousPage=other%20articles>

Quy trình giải quyết tranh chấp và khiếu nại của Shopee:

<https://help.shopee.vn/portal/article/77265?previousPage=other%20articles>

Quy chế hoạt động sàn thương mại điện tử Shopee.vn:

<https://help.shopee.vn/portal/article/77245?previousPage=other%20articles>

Quy trình giải quyết tranh chấp và khiếu nại của Lazada:

https://pages.lazada.vn/wow/gcp/route/lazada/vn/upr_1000345_lazada/channel/vn/upr-router/vn?spm=a2o4n.home.footer_top.17.19053bdcOJxYBo&hybrid=1&data_prefetch=true&prefetch_replace=1&wh_pid=/lazada/channel/vn/khuyen-mai/quy-trinh-giai-quyet-tranh-chap-khieu-nai

Quy chế hoạt động của sàn giao dịch Lazada:

https://pages.lazada.vn/wow/gcp/route/lazada/vn/upr_1000345_lazada/channel/vn/upr-router/vn?hybrid=1&data_prefetch=true&prefetch_replace=1&at_iframe=1&wh_pid=/lazada/channel/vn/legal/quy-che-ban-hang&from=icms:offline

PHỤ LỤC QUY CHẾ GIẢI QUYẾT TRANH CHẤP TRÊN SÀN GIAO DỊCH TMĐT SHOPEE VÀ LAZADA

1. SHOPEE.VN:

1.1. Vai trò, thẩm quyền của Shopee trong giải quyết tranh chấp:

<https://help.shopee.vn/portal/article/77243?previousPage=other%20articles>

Trường hợp phát sinh vấn đề liên quan đến giao dịch, Người Bán và Người Mua đồng ý đầu tiên sẽ đối thoại với nhau để cố gắng giải quyết tranh chấp đó bằng thảo luận hai bên, và Shopee sẽ cố gắng một cách hợp lý để thu xếp. Nếu vấn đề không được giải quyết bằng thảo luận hai bên, Người Sử Dụng có thể khiếu nại lên cơ quan có thẩm quyền của địa phương để giải quyết tranh chấp phát sinh đối với giao dịch.

Mỗi Người Bán và Người Mua cam kết và đồng ý rằng mình sẽ không tiến hành thủ tục tố tụng hoặc bằng cách khác khiếu nại đối với Shopee hoặc các công ty liên kết của Shopee (trừ trường hợp Shopee hoặc các công ty liên kết của mình là Người Bán sản phẩm liên quan đến khiếu nại đó) liên quan đến bất kỳ giao dịch nào được thực hiện trên Trang Shopee hoặc bất kỳ tranh chấp nào liên quan đến giao dịch đó.

Người Sử Dụng được áp dụng Chính Sách Đảm Bảo của Shopee có thể gửi yêu cầu bằng văn bản tới Shopee để được hỗ trợ giải quyết tranh chấp phát sinh từ giao dịch. Shopee sẽ thực hiện những bước cần thiết để hỗ trợ Người Sử Dụng giải quyết những tranh chấp này. Để biết thêm thông tin chi tiết, vui lòng xem Chính Sách Trả Hàng và Hoàn Tiền của Shopee.

Để rõ ràng hơn, việc hỗ trợ theo Mục 17 này chỉ áp dụng đối với Người Mua là đối tượng của Chính Sách Đảm Bảo của Shopee. Người Mua sử dụng những phương thức thanh toán khác có thể liên hệ trực tiếp với Người Bán.

1.2. Về quy trình giải quyết tranh chấp, xử lý khiếu nại:

<https://help.shopee.vn/portal/article/77245?previousPage=other%20articles>

Khi phát sinh tranh chấp hoặc khiếu nại, Shopee khuyến khích giải pháp thương lượng, hòa giải giữa các bên để đạt được sự đồng thuận về phương án giải quyết. Nếu hai bên không thể thương lượng với nhau và yêu cầu Shopee đứng ra giải quyết vụ việc. Quyết định của Shopee là quyết định cuối cùng. Tranh chấp hoặc khiếu nại sẽ được xử lý theo trình tự sau:

- Bước 1: Để tạo khiếu nại yêu cầu Trả hàng/ Hoàn tiền tới Shopee, người mua cần bấm khiếu nại ngay trong ứng dụng Shopee/ website www.shopee.vn, mục Đơn Mua." Hệ thống sẽ ghi nhận khiếu nại này của Người Mua. Việc tạo khiếu nại Trả hàng/ Hoàn tiền là cơ sở Shopee tạm giữ khoản tiền hàng cần thanh toán cho Người Bán lại cho đến khi giải quyết xong. Các tranh chấp không phải là khiếu nại Trả hàng/ Hoàn tiền có thể được gửi đến Shopee qua <https://help.shopee.vn/vn/s/contactusform> hoặc Tổng đài hỗ trợ: 19001221.

- Bước 2: Bộ phận giải quyết khiếu nại của Shopee sẽ tiếp nhận các yêu cầu của người khiếu nại/các bên tranh chấp. Shopee sẽ có biện pháp cụ thể hỗ trợ người khiếu nại/các bên tranh chấp để giải quyết tùy theo tính chất và mức độ của vụ việc.

- Bước 3: Khiếu nại Trả hàng/Hoàn tiền được xử lý theo Chính Sách Trả Hàng Và Hoàn Tiền của Shopee. Đối với các tranh chấp không phải là khiếu nại Trả hàng/Hoàn tiền, Shopee yêu cầu các bên tranh chấp cung cấp đầy đủ thông tin/tài liệu liên quan đến vụ việc, và đưa ra hướng giải quyết dựa trên các thông tin/tài liệu thu thập được trong vòng 7 ngày làm việc kể từ ngày nhận được đầy đủ các thông tin/tài liệu có liên quan đến vụ việc. Trong trường hợp vụ việc có nhiều thông tin, tình tiết phức tạp thì thời hạn giải quyết sẽ được kéo dài hơn.

- Bước 4: Trong trường hợp nằm ngoài khả năng và thẩm quyền của Sàn Giao Dịch Thương Mại Điện Tử hoặc vụ việc đã được Shopee đưa ra quyết định cuối cùng mà một trong hai bên hoặc cả hai bên đều không đồng ý với quyết định này, Shopee sẽ yêu cầu các bên tranh chấp đưa vụ việc ra giải quyết tại cơ quan nhà nước có thẩm quyền theo quy định của pháp luật. Shopee tôn trọng và nghiêm túc thực hiện các quy định của pháp luật về bảo vệ quyền lợi của khách hàng (người tiêu dùng). Các Nhà Bán Hàng trên Sàn Giao Dịch Thương Mại Điện Tử Shopee cần cung cấp đầy đủ, chính xác, trung thực và chi tiết các thông tin/tài liệu liên quan đến sản phẩm. Mọi hành vi lừa đảo, gian lận trong kinh doanh đều bị lên án và phải chịu hoàn toàn trách nhiệm trước pháp luật.

Quy trình giải quyết tranh chấp, khiếu nại này được giải thích và điều chỉnh phù hợp với Quy chế hoạt động website cung cấp dịch vụ TMĐT Shopee.vn, được sửa đổi, bổ sung tại từng thời điểm (“Quy chế hoạt động”). Các thuật ngữ viết hoa trong quy trình giải quyết tranh chấp, khiếu nại này sẽ có ý nghĩa như được quy định tại Quy chế hoạt động.

Đối với Người bán hàng nước ngoài: Theo quy định của Nghị định 85/2021/NĐ-CP, Shopee là đại diện giải quyết các khiếu nại của người tiêu dùng liên quan đến hàng hóa, dịch vụ do thương nhân nước ngoài cung cấp theo quy định của Bộ luật dân sự về đại diện.

1.3. Phân định trách nhiệm giữa các bên:

<https://help.shopee.vn/portal/article/77265?previousPage=other%20articles>

Nếu có tranh chấp, khiếu nại phát sinh giữa Người dùng với nhau thì các bên sẽ giải quyết trên cơ sở tự thỏa thuận, thương lượng và hoà giải. Shopee sẽ hỗ trợ người xử lý khiếu nại bằng cách cử nhân viên liên lạc, hoà giải, nếu họ tập hợp bằng chứng cụ thể và xác thực về việc bị vi phạm gửi đến cho Shopee. Nếu vụ việc vượt quá thẩm quyền và khả năng của mình, Shopee sẽ đề nghị người bị vi phạm chuyển vụ việc cho các cơ quan chức năng có thẩm quyền. Trong trường hợp này, Shopee vẫn hỗ trợ để bảo vệ tốt nhất bên bị vi phạm.

Nếu có khiếu nại phát sinh giữa Người mua và Người bán hàng nước ngoài, Shopee có trách nhiệm đại diện cho Người bán hàng giải quyết tranh chấp phát sinh theo quy định của Bộ luật dân sự về đại diện.

Nếu có tranh chấp phát sinh liên quan đến việc sử dụng dịch vụ liên quan giữa Người dùng với Shopee, thì Shopee sẽ giải quyết vụ việc tuân thủ quy trình giải quyết tranh chấp, khiếu nại đã được công bố trên Website/Ứng dụng.

2. LAZADA.COM:

2.1. Vai trò, thẩm quyền của Lazada trong giải quyết tranh chấp:

https://pages.lazada.vn/wow/gcp/route/lazada/vn/upr_1000345_lazada/channel/vn/uprprouter/vn?hybrid=1&data_prefetch=true&prefetch_replace=1&at_iframe=1&wh_pid=/lazada/channel/vn/legal/quy-che-ban-hang&from=icms:offline

Lazada sẽ tiếp nhận, phản hồi thông tin để giải quyết khiếu nại, phản ánh và tranh chấp liên quan đến Sàn TMĐT Lazada tại Cổng thông tin Quản lý hoạt động TMĐT của Bộ Công Thương tại địa chỉ online.gov.vn.

Lazada sẽ công bố công khai cơ chế giải quyết các tranh chấp, khiếu nại phát sinh trong quá trình giao dịch trên Sàn TMĐT Lazada (bao gồm các khiếu nại của Khách Hàng về chất lượng hàng hóa, dịch vụ được khuyến mại hoặc hàng hóa, dịch vụ dùng để khuyến mại). Khi Khách Hàng trên Sàn TMĐT Lazada phát sinh mâu thuẫn với Nhà Bán Hàng hoặc bị tổn hại lợi ích hợp pháp, Lazada sẽ là đầu mối tiếp nhận và giải quyết các khiếu nại của Người Mua trong trường hợp một giao dịch thực hiện trên Sàn TMĐT Lazada có nhiều hơn hai (2) bên tham gia và sẽ cung cấp cho Khách Hàng thông tin về Nhà Bán Hàng và tích cực hỗ trợ Khách Hàng bảo vệ quyền và lợi ích hợp pháp của mình. Ngoài ra, Lazada sẽ đại diện cho Nhà Bán Hàng nước ngoài giải quyết các khiếu nại của Khách Hàng liên quan đến Sản Phẩm do Nhà Bán Hàng nước ngoài cung cấp trên Sàn TMĐT Lazada.

2.2. Về quy trình giải quyết tranh chấp, xử lý khiếu nại:

https://pages.lazada.vn/wow/gcp/route/lazada/vn/upr_1000345_lazada/channel/vn/uprprouter/vn?spm=a2o4n.home.footer_top.17.19053bdcOJxYBo&hybrid=1&data_prefetch=true&prefetch_replace=1&wh_pid=/lazada/channel/vn/khuyen-mai/quy-trinh-giai-quyet-tranh-chap-khieu-nai

1. Quy trình đối với Sản Phẩm của Nhà Bán Hàng trong nước.

(a) Lazada và Nhà Bán Hàng có trách nhiệm tiếp nhận khiếu nại và hỗ trợ Khách Hàng liên quan đến giao dịch tại Sàn TMĐT Lazada. Khi phát sinh tranh chấp, Lazada đề cao giải pháp thương lượng, hòa giải giữa các bên nhằm duy trì sự tin cậy của Thành Viên vào chất lượng dịch vụ của Sàn TMĐT Lazada và thực hiện theo các bước sau:

- Bước 1: Khách Hàng khiếu nại về Sản Phẩm qua hotline chăm sóc khách hàng 19001007 hoặc chức năng trò chuyện trực tuyến tại www.lazada.vn/contact.

- Bước 2: Bộ phận chăm sóc khách hàng của Lazada sẽ tiếp nhận các khiếu nại của Khách Hàng và chuyển về cho Nhà Bán Hàng, và tùy theo tính chất và mức độ của khiếu nại thì bên Lazada sẽ có những biện pháp cụ thể khác để hỗ trợ Khách Hàng để giải quyết tranh chấp đó. Đối với giao dịch thực hiện trên Sàn TMĐT Lazada có nhiều hơn hai (2) bên tham gia, Lazada sẽ là đầu mối tiếp nhận và giải quyết các khiếu nại của Người Mua.

- Bước 3: Trong trường hợp nằm ngoài khả năng và thẩm quyền của Lazada thì Khách Hàng có thể yêu cầu đưa vụ việc ra giải quyết bởi cơ quan nhà nước có thẩm quyền.

(b) Lazada tôn trọng và nghiêm túc thực hiện các quy định của pháp luật về bảo vệ quyền lợi của người tiêu dùng. Vì vậy, đề nghị Nhà Bán Hàng đăng tin chào bán Sản Phẩm

trên Sàn TMĐT Lazada cung cấp đầy đủ, chính xác, trung thực và chi tiết các thông tin liên quan đến Sản Phẩm. Mọi hành vi lừa đảo, gian lận trong kinh doanh đều bị lên án và phải chịu hoàn toàn trách nhiệm trước pháp luật.

(c) Các bên bao gồm Nhà Bán Hàng, Khách Hàng và đơn vị vận chuyển sẽ phải có vai trò trách nhiệm trong việc tích cực giải quyết vấn đề đang được khiếu nại. Các bên có liên quan phải có trách nhiệm cung cấp văn bản, giấy tờ chứng thực thông tin liên quan đến sự việc đang gây mâu thuẫn. Lazada sẽ có trách nhiệm cung cấp những thông tin liên quan đến các bên nếu được các bên có liên quan đến tranh chấp đó yêu cầu.

(d) Sau khi các bên đã giải quyết xong tranh chấp phải có trách nhiệm báo lại cho Lazada. Trong trường hợp giao dịch phát sinh mâu thuẫn mà lỗi thuộc về Nhà Bán Hàng, Lazada sẽ có biện pháp cảnh cáo, khóa tài khoản hoặc chuyển cho cơ quan Nhà nước có thẩm quyền tùy theo mức độ sai phạm. Lazada có thể sẽ chấm dứt và gỡ bỏ toàn bộ tin, bài đăng về Sản Phẩm của Nhà Bán Hàng vi phạm đó trên Sàn TMĐT Lazada, đồng thời Nhà Bán Hàng phải có trách nhiệm bồi thường, bồi hoàn cho Khách Hàng thỏa đáng trên cơ sở thỏa thuận với Khách Hàng.

(e) Nếu thông qua hình thức thỏa thuận mà vẫn không thể giải quyết được mâu thuẫn phát sinh từ giao dịch, các bên sẽ có quyền nhờ đến cơ quan Nhà nước có thẩm quyền can thiệp nhằm đảm bảo lợi ích hợp pháp của các bên.

2. Quy trình đối với Sản Phẩm của Nhà Bán Hàng nước ngoài

(a) Lazada sẽ đại diện Nhà Bán Hàng nước ngoài để tiếp nhận và giải quyết các khiếu nại của Khách Hàng liên quan đến các Sản Phẩm của Nhà Bán Hàng nước ngoài được bán trên Nền Tảng Lazada.

(b) Điều kiện để Lazada giải quyết khiếu nại của Khách Hàng:

(i) Khách Hàng mua Sản Phẩm của Nhà Bán Hàng nước ngoài trên Nền Tảng Lazada và đã thanh toán giá mua Sản Phẩm nhưng (A) quá thời gian giao hàng dự kiến mà Khách Hàng không nhận được Sản Phẩm; hoặc (B) đơn hàng đã được cập nhật sang trạng thái giao hàng thành công nhưng Khách Hàng không nhận được Sản Phẩm; (C) Khách Hàng không hài lòng với Sản Phẩm và muốn trả hàng phù hợp với chính sách trả hàng của Lazada; và (D) Sản Phẩm có khác biệt đáng kể so với thông tin được Nhà Bán Hàng nước ngoài đăng tải trên Nền Tảng Lazada.

Sản Phẩm được xem là khác biệt đáng kể trong các trường hợp sau đây:

- Tình trạng của Sản Phẩm không như mô tả;
- Giao sai Sản Phẩm;
- Sản Phẩm giao thiếu bộ phận hoặc thành phần;
- Sản Phẩm là hàng giả, hàng nhái;
- Sản Phẩm bị hư, hỏng, bể vỡ;
- Thùng/Hộp/Kiện hàng đựng Sản Phẩm bị rách, biến dạng, hư, hỏng, bể vỡ;
- Sản Phẩm bị lỗi kỹ thuật.

(ii) Khách Hàng có thể gửi khiếu nại đến Lazada từ ngày tiếp theo ngày cuối cùng của thời hạn dự kiến giao hàng nếu Khách Hàng không nhận được Sản Phẩm hoặc kể từ khi đơn hàng được cập nhật sang trạng thái giao hàng thành công. Trong trường hợp Sản Phẩm có sự khác biệt đáng kể, khiếu nại phải được gửi đến Lazada trong vòng mười lăm (15) ngày kể từ ngày đơn hàng được giao thành công.

(iii) Trường hợp Khách Hàng thanh toán bằng thẻ tín dụng và ngân hàng phát hành thẻ của Khách Hàng đã tiến hành thủ tục bồi hoàn tiền mua Sản Phẩm cho Khách Hàng (chargeback) trước hoặc sau thời điểm Lazada tiếp nhận khiếu nại của Khách Hàng, Lazada sẽ không tiếp nhận hoặc không tiếp tục giải quyết (tùy từng trường hợp áp dụng) khiếu nại của Khách Hàng và sẽ thông báo cho Khách Hàng được biết khiếu nại của Khách Hàng sẽ không được tiếp nhận hoặc không được tiếp tục giải quyết.

(c) Quy trình tiếp nhận và giải quyết khiếu nại như sau:

- Bước 1: Khách Hàng khiếu nại về Sản Phẩm qua hotline chăm sóc khách hàng 19006509 hoặc chức năng trò chuyện trực tuyến tại <https://www.lazada.vn/contact/>.

- Bước 2: Trường hợp khiếu nại của Khách Hàng không đáp ứng các điều kiện khiếu nại quy định tại mục (b) trên đây, Lazada sẽ không tiếp tục giải quyết khiếu nại và thông báo cho Khách Hàng. Trường hợp khiếu nại của Khách Hàng đáp ứng các điều kiện khiếu nại quy định tại mục (b) trên đây, Lazada sẽ nỗ lực tối đa để phản hồi kết quả giải quyết khiếu nại trong vòng bốn mươi lăm (45) ngày hoặc một thời hạn dài hơn (nếu cần thiết) kể từ ngày tiếp nhận khiếu nại.

- Bước 3: Sau khi kết thúc thời hạn giải quyết khiếu nại, Lazada sẽ thông báo cho Khách Hàng về kết quả của việc giải quyết khiếu nại. Trường hợp khiếu nại của Khách Hàng được chấp nhận hoặc có cơ sở, Lazada sẽ tiến hành việc hoàn tiền mua Sản Phẩm cho Khách Hàng. Trường hợp khiếu nại của Khách Hàng là không có cơ sở, Lazada sẽ thông báo cho Khách Hàng được biết.

(d) Để giải quyết khiếu nại, Lazada có thể yêu cầu Khách Hàng cung cấp thêm thông tin và/hoặc tài liệu có liên quan đến khiếu nại, nếu Khách Hàng không cung cấp được thông tin và/hoặc tài liệu theo yêu cầu của Lazada trong vòng 5 ngày kể từ ngày yêu cầu, hoặc thông tin và/hoặc tài liệu mà Khách Hàng cung cấp cho Lazada là giả mạo hoặc bị chỉnh sửa, theo toàn quyền quyết định của Lazada, Lazada sẽ chấm dứt việc giải quyết khiếu nại của Khách Hàng và thông báo cho Khách Hàng được biết.

BẢO VỆ DỮ LIỆU TRONG NỀN KINH TẾ SỐ Ở VIỆT NAM - TỪ HAI GÓC ĐỘ PHÁP LUẬT VÀ KINH TẾ

Nguyễn Phương Đông, Phạm Vũ Văn Anh

Trường Đại học Thương mại

Tóm tắt

Chuyển đổi số không chỉ là xu hướng của nền kinh tế mà còn là quyết sách của Đảng và Nhà nước ta hiện nay. Việc chuyển đổi số dẫn tới việc số hóa và tạo ra nguồn dữ liệu lớn (Big Data) không chỉ liên quan tới định danh cá nhân mà còn liên quan tới mọi góc cạnh của nền kinh tế, và tạo ra một loại tài nguyên mới của nền kinh tế. Một doanh nghiệp muốn phát triển bền vững không thể bỏ qua tầm quan trọng của việc bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân, đặc biệt là khi quyền bảo mật thông tin của khách hàng ngày càng bị vi phạm nghiêm trọng. Vì vậy, nhóm tác giả tập trung nghiên cứu vào vai trò của bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân, tính cấp thiết của việc bảo vệ thông tin cá nhân đối với doanh nghiệp phát triển bền vững trước khi phân tích thực trạng pháp luật hiện hành về bảo vệ dữ liệu, tình hình thực thi luật pháp về bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân. Từ đó, nhóm tác giả đề xuất một số kiến nghị hoàn thiện pháp luật và giải pháp bảo vệ dữ liệu cho doanh nghiệp trong nền kinh tế số ở Việt Nam.

Từ khóa: bảo vệ dữ liệu, chuyển đổi số, doanh nghiệp phát triển bền vững, pháp luật

DATA PROTECTION IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN VIETNAM-FROM TWO LEGAL AND ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVES

Abstract

Recently, digital transformation is not only an economic trend but also the Decision of the Vietnamese Communist Party and government. Digitalization and Big Data are created by digital transformation which not only relates to personal identification, but also every economic aspect and a new source of the economy. A corporation that wants to develop sustainably cannot ignore the importance of protecting personal data, especially when the privacy rights of customers are increasingly seriously violated. Therefore, the authors focus research on the role of personal data protection, the urgency of personal information protection for sustainable development corporations before analyzing the current status of data protection laws, law enforcement on the protection of personal data. From there, the authors propose a number of recommendations to improve the law and solutions to data protection for corporations in the digital economy in Vietnam.

Keywords: data protection, digital transformation, sustainable development corporations, law

1. DẪN NHẬP

Cách mạng công nghiệp lần thứ tư là sự kết hợp của công nghệ trong các lĩnh vực vật lý, công nghệ số và sinh học, tạo ra những khả năng sản xuất hoàn toàn mới và có tác động sâu sắc đến đời sống kinh tế, chính trị, xã hội của thế giới. Chuyển đổi số giúp người dân bình đẳng về cơ hội tiếp cận dịch vụ, đào tạo, tri thức, qua đó giúp thu hẹp khoảng cách số thông qua việc phát triển chính phủ số, kinh tế số và xã hội số.

Kinh tế số cho phép mỗi người dân có thể tiếp cận toàn bộ thị trường một cách nhanh chóng theo cách chưa từng có. Tuy nhiên, ngoài những lợi ích kể trên, cuộc Cách mạng công nghiệp 4.0 còn mang lại những khó khăn và thách thức cho xã hội, ví dụ như sự bất bình đẳng, bất ổn về kinh tế và đặc biệt là an toàn bảo vệ thông tin cá nhân.

Trong thời đại công nghệ số phát triển với tốc độ chóng mặt hiện nay, an ninh thông tin được xem là rất quan trọng. Đặc biệt là khi dữ liệu cá nhân và dữ liệu cá nhân nhạy cảm bị rò rỉ trên không gian mạng sẽ gây ảnh hưởng không nhỏ đến quyền riêng tư, dẫn đến tình trạng lừa đảo công nghệ cao và các hành vi phạm pháp luật khác tạo điều kiện cho đối tượng xấu tìm kiếm, thu thập và sử dụng vào các hành vi lừa đảo chiếm đoạt tài sản, để lại nhiều hậu quả khôn lường không chỉ đối với cá nhân mà còn đối với tổ chức và quốc gia.

Vì vậy, doanh nghiệp đóng một vai trò vô cùng quan trọng trong việc bảo vệ dữ liệu của khách hàng. Nhóm tác giả tập trung phân tích từ góc độ pháp luật về việc bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân, làm rõ mối tương quan giữa doanh nghiệp phát triển bền vững và bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân trước khi đưa ra kiến nghị về hoàn thiện pháp luật và giải pháp bảo vệ dữ liệu cho doanh nghiệp.

2. VAI TRÒ VÀ TÍNH CẤP THIẾT CỦA HOẠT ĐỘNG BẢO VỆ DỮ LIỆU TRONG NỀN KINH TẾ SỐ

2.1. Vai trò của hoạt động bảo vệ dữ liệu trong nền kinh tế số

Có thể nói rằng, chuyển đổi số là một hoạt động thực tiễn và bảo vệ dữ liệu là một yêu cầu pháp lý đặt ra đối với một khía cạnh quan trọng của hoạt động đó. Bảo vệ dữ liệu xuất phát từ chính vai trò của vấn đề về an toàn dữ liệu đối với sự thành công của công cuộc chuyển đổi số nói chung và vấn đề về bảo vệ quyền con người cơ bản trong bối cảnh chuyển đổi số nói riêng.

Trong quá trình chuyển đổi số, có sự tích hợp các công nghệ kỹ thuật số vào tất cả các lĩnh vực của nền kinh tế - xã hội, dẫn tới yêu cầu tập hợp, chuẩn hóa và tích hợp các hệ cơ sở dữ liệu lên nền tảng công nghệ. Theo Quyết định số 714/QĐ-TTg của Thủ tướng chính phủ ngày 22 tháng 05 năm 2015, các cơ sở dữ liệu Quốc gia bao gồm: cơ sở dữ liệu quốc gia về Dân cư (do Bộ Công an làm cơ quan chủ quản); cơ sở dữ liệu Đất đai quốc gia (Bộ Tài nguyên và Môi trường làm cơ quan chủ quản); cơ sở dữ liệu quốc gia về Đăng ký doanh nghiệp; cơ sở dữ liệu quốc gia về Thống kê tổng hợp về Dân số. (Bộ Kế hoạch và Đầu tư làm cơ quan chủ quản); cơ sở dữ liệu quốc gia về Tài chính (Bộ Tài chính làm cơ quan chủ quản); cơ sở dữ liệu quốc gia về Bảo hiểm (Bảo hiểm Xã hội Việt Nam làm cơ quan chủ quản). Điều đó đồng nghĩa với việc Nhà nước là chủ thể chủ trì và đưa ra các yêu cầu về việc đưa tất cả các thông tin trong các cơ sở dữ liệu đó lên các nền tảng kỹ thuật số, làm giàu thêm kho dữ liệu và thông tin trên các công cụ điện tử. Ở góc độ doanh nghiệp, hầu hết các dữ liệu và thông tin đều được

chuyển đổi lên lưu trữ và xử lý trên nền tảng số, bao gồm các thông tin về người lao động, về tài chính – kế toán, về khách hàng, về hoạt động sản xuất – kinh doanh và cung ứng dịch vụ... như một cách thức đổi mới phương thức quản lý, ứng dụng tiến bộ của kỹ thuật, công nghệ vào hoạt động quản trị nội bộ.

Chuyển đổi số không chỉ là một xu hướng của thị trường và nền kinh tế mà còn là một đòi hỏi có tính pháp lý mà Nhà nước đặt ra đối với cộng đồng doanh nghiệp, dân cư và mọi chủ thể trong xã hội³². Do đó, việc đưa thông tin, dữ liệu lên các nền tảng số không chỉ là tự nguyện mà còn là nghĩa vụ bắt buộc. Do đó, có thể nói rằng, chuyển đổi số dẫn tới việc chuyển đổi toàn bộ các thông tin, dữ liệu cá nhân, dữ liệu về doanh nghiệp lên các nền tảng kỹ thuật số; và việc áp dụng chuyển đổi số là cú hích thúc đẩy sự tập trung và tích tụ dữ liệu về nền kinh tế - xã hội một cách toàn diện, đầy đủ trên nền tảng kỹ thuật số. “Sự phát triển quá nhanh của công nghệ số đã làm cho tốc độ số hóa của nền kinh tế tăng vọt. Báo cáo của McKinsey cho thấy, 90% dữ liệu (data) hiện tại là chưa hề tồn tại vào 2 năm trước. Điều này có nghĩa là khối lượng dữ liệu tăng chóng mặt, khả năng xử lý và quản lý khối lượng dữ liệu này là một thách thức rất lớn. Thêm vào đó, đến năm 2017, trên thế giới có hơn 20 tỷ thiết bị được kết nối với nhau và cứ mỗi tuần thì lại có thêm hơn 50 triệu thiết bị được bổ sung vào mạng lưới IoT này” (Anh, 2022)

Xem xét mối quan hệ ở một góc độ khác, cơ sở dữ liệu chính là trái tim của chuyển đổi số, vì thiếu cơ sở dữ liệu, các hoạt động của chuyển đổi số đều không có giá trị, không thể phát triển, và các ứng dụng, dịch vụ, nền tảng số sẽ trở nên vô giá trị hoặc không thể thực hiện được các chức năng mà nó được thiết kế.

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2.2. Tính cấp thiết của hoạt động bảo vệ dữ liệu trong nền kinh tế số

Bởi việc chuyển đổi dữ liệu lên môi trường kỹ thuật số là một nghĩa vụ pháp lý mà Nhà nước đặt ra nên bên cạnh các yêu cầu về chuyển đổi dữ liệu, thì cũng cần đặt ra trách nhiệm của cơ quan Nhà nước trong việc bảo vệ quyền và lợi ích hợp pháp của công dân khi thực hiện nghĩa vụ chuyển đổi dữ liệu đó. Hầu hết các dữ liệu được chuyển đổi và lưu trữ trong các cơ sở dữ liệu Quốc gia đều thuộc phạm vi dữ liệu cá nhân nhạy cảm, có khả năng gây ra những hậu quả nguy hại và ảnh hưởng trực tiếp tới an ninh, an toàn của chủ thể dữ liệu nếu không có cơ chế đảm bảo về an ninh, an toàn.

Như đã phân tích trên đây, chuyển đổi số là một xu hướng và đồng thời là một yêu cầu pháp lý. Tuy nhiên, mức độ sẵn sàng trên thực tiễn của cộng đồng dân cư, cộng đồng doanh

³² Ví dụ: Nghị định 104/2022/NĐ-CP quy định 04 cách khai thác, sử dụng thông tin về cư trú của công dân trong Cơ sở dữ liệu quốc gia về dân cư bao gồm: (i) Tra cứu, khai thác thông tin cá nhân qua chức năng của Hệ thống thông tin giải quyết thủ tục hành chính cấp bộ, cấp tỉnh đã được kết nối với Cơ sở dữ liệu quốc gia về dân cư hoặc qua Cổng dịch vụ công quốc gia; (ii) Tra cứu thông tin cá nhân thông qua tài khoản định danh điện tử của công dân được hiển thị trong ứng dụng VNeID; (iii) Sử dụng thiết bị đầu đọc đã được kết nối trực tuyến với Cơ sở dữ liệu quốc gia về dân cư, bao gồm thiết bị đọc mã QRCode hoặc thiết bị đọc chip trên thẻ Căn cước công dân gắn chip; (iv) Các phương thức khai thác khác theo quy định của pháp luật chuyên ngành)

ngành trong việc tham gia vào công cuộc chuyển đổi số không đồng đều nhau do năng lực về tài chính, công nghệ, cũng như nhận thức. Sự sẵn sàng đó bao hàm nhiều yếu tố, trong đó có yếu tố về mặt hạ tầng công nghệ, phần mềm, kiến thức và kỹ năng sử dụng các công cụ công nghệ số. Theo số liệu được công bố tại Diễn đàn “Đồng hành cùng doanh nghiệp nhỏ và vừa trong chuyển đổi số” do Phòng Thương mại và Công nghiệp Việt Nam (VCCI) phối hợp Bộ Kế hoạch và Đầu tư, Tập đoàn Meta tổ chức ngày 9/11 tại Hà Nội “...có tới hơn 60% doanh nghiệp phản ánh vẫn đang gặp phải rào cản trong chi phí đầu tư, ứng dụng công nghệ; 52,3% doanh nghiệp phản ánh khó khăn về thiếu nhân lực nội bộ để ứng dụng công nghệ số, thay đổi thói quen của doanh nghiệp, người lao động” (Báo Nhân dân, 2022). Sự không đồng bộ về sự sẵn sàng dẫn tới khả năng thích ứng và đối phó với các mặt trái và rủi ro của chuyển đổi số không giống nhau, gây ra các rủi ro tiềm ẩn cho toàn hệ thống bởi tính liên kết, đan xen trong môi trường kỹ thuật số cao hơn và phức tạp hơn rất nhiều so với môi trường thực. Các rủi ro về an ninh mạng, đánh cắp thông tin, lừa đảo trực tuyến là một vấn đề lớn trong bối cảnh chuyển đổi số. Theo dữ liệu thống kê của Cục An toàn thông tin, trong nửa đầu năm nay ở Việt Nam có khoảng 44,7 sự cố tấn công mạng vào các hệ thống thông tin mỗi ngày, con số này đã tăng lên 1,6 lần so với cùng kỳ năm 2021 (Báo VN Express, 2022).

Bên cạnh các rủi ro an ninh mạng có tính truyền thống như lừa đảo trực tuyến, tống tiền, thì các rủi ro về an ninh, an toàn trong bối cảnh chuyển đổi số ở giai đoạn hiện nay chứa đựng những yếu tố mới, như thu thập, sử dụng và mua bán thông tin, dữ liệu trái phép, tiếp cận người tiêu dùng thông qua các kênh kỹ thuật số không có sự đồng ý của chủ thể dữ liệu hoặc người tiêu dùng. Hiện tượng người dùng bị đánh cắp thông tin cá nhân, thông tin về hành vi mua sắm trực tuyến, hành vi sử dụng mạng xã hội và địa điểm, diễn ra một cách tràn lan và thiếu kiểm soát trong bối cảnh hiện nay. “Tình trạng lộ dữ liệu cá nhân diễn ra phổ biến trên không gian mạng và trở thành một trong những vấn đề nóng về an ninh, an toàn thông tin. Các dữ liệu cá nhân phổ biến bị thu thập hiện nay gồm: thông tin nhân khẩu học (họ tên, giới tính, ngày sinh, địa chỉ), số CCCD, số điện thoại, số tài khoản ngân hàng (bao gồm cả số dư). Trong một số vụ rò rỉ, thông tin bị chia sẻ còn bao gồm thân nhân, chức vụ, vị trí công tác, tài khoản online, mật khẩu” (Báo VN Express, 2022)

Sự tham gia của các nền tảng xã hội quốc tế như Netflix, Tiktok, Facebook, Google, Twitter... đang tạo ra một không gian rất rộng cho các hoạt động thu thập, sử dụng, khai thác và mua bán dữ liệu với tính chất xuyên biên giới, đặt ra vấn đề chuyển tải và lưu trữ dữ liệu ở ngoài phạm vi lãnh thổ Việt Nam, tạo nên những nguy cơ ảnh hưởng trực tiếp tới an ninh Quốc gia và vấn đề bảo vệ công dân.

Từ những nội dung trình bày ở trên, chúng ta có đầy đủ cơ sở để nhận thấy tính cấp thiết và đòi hỏi cần có sự bảo vệ dữ liệu một cách đảm bảo và hiệu quả, không chỉ bằng các biện pháp công nghệ do mỗi cơ quan, doanh nghiệp tự đầu tư xây dựng mà còn cần bằng các giải pháp về chính sách và pháp luật do Nhà nước ban hành. Những đòi hỏi đặt ra đối với chính sách và pháp luật như vậy là tương đối rộng lớn, không chỉ trong việc đưa ra các chế định về cách thức thu thập, xử lý, lưu trữ, khai thác, mua bán dữ liệu mà còn phải có các chế định về xử lý vi phạm trong lĩnh vực bảo vệ dữ liệu. Phức tạp hơn, các chế định pháp luật ban hành phải có khả năng bảo vệ công dân, bảo vệ các chủ thể dữ liệu trong lãnh thổ Việt nam trước các hành vi thu thập, xử lý, khai thác, vận chuyển và mua bán dữ liệu xuyên biên giới, điều chỉnh hành vi của các tập đoàn đa Quốc gia, các mạng xã hội khổng lồ trên thế giới.

3. THỰC TRẠNG PHÁP LUẬT VÀ HOẠT ĐỘNG BẢO VỆ DỮ LIỆU CỦA CÁC DOANH NGHIỆP TRONG NỀN KINH TẾ SỐ Ở VIỆT NAM HIỆN NAY

3.1. Thực trạng pháp luật về bảo vệ dữ liệu ở Việt Nam

3.1.1. *Pháp luật về bảo vệ dữ liệu tại Việt Nam tồn tại và phân bố trong nhiều văn bản pháp luật rời rạc khác nhau*

Điều 21, Hiến pháp 2013 quy định:

“1. Mọi người có quyền bất khả xâm phạm về đời sống riêng tư, bí mật cá nhân và bí mật gia đình; có quyền bảo vệ danh dự, uy tín của mình. Thông tin về đời sống riêng tư, bí mật cá nhân, bí mật gia đình được pháp luật bảo đảm an toàn.

2. Mọi người có quyền bí mật thư tín, điện thoại, điện tín và các hình thức trao đổi thông tin riêng tư khác.

Không ai được bóc mở, kiểm soát, thu giữ trái luật thư tín, điện thoại, điện tín và các hình thức trao đổi thông tin riêng tư của người khác”.

Hướng dẫn chi tiết quy định của Hiến pháp 2013, đã có nhiều đạo luật khác nhau quy định về vấn đề bảo vệ thông tin cá nhân và quyền riêng tư, ví dụ như:

Bộ Luật Dân sự 2015 quy định về “Quyền về đời sống riêng tư, bí mật cá nhân, bí mật gia đình” (Điều 38); Luật An ninh mạng 2018 có các quy định về bảo đảm an toàn cơ sở hạ tầng kỹ thuật mạng, hệ thống tin quan trọng về an ninh quốc gia, kiểm soát nội dung nhạy cảm về chính trị trên không gian mạng, chống tội phạm mạng và tấn công mạng...; Luật Bảo hiểm xã hội 2014 có các quy định về Bảo vệ bí mật, chống truy cập dữ liệu bảo hiểm bắt hợp pháp...; Luật Giao dịch điện tử 2005 có các quy định về Bảo đảm an ninh, an toàn trong giao dịch điện tử (Điều 44), Bảo vệ thông điệp dữ liệu (Điều 45), Bảo mật thông tin trong giao dịch điện tử...

Theo thống kê của nhóm tác giả tại thời điểm tháng 8 năm 2023, Việt Nam có hơn 23 văn bản quy phạm pháp luật (ở cấp độ Nghị định hoặc văn bản có giá trị cao hơn) có các quy định về bảo vệ thông tin cá nhân và quyền riêng tư, bao phủ các lĩnh vực cơ bản trong đời sống con người như giao dịch tin dụng, kinh doanh bảo hiểm và bảo hiểm xã hội, quản lý thuế, khám chữa bệnh...

Có thể nhận định rằng, trong hệ thống văn bản quy phạm pháp luật hiện hành có khá nhiều văn bản quy định về vấn đề bảo vệ thông tin và quyền riêng tư. Tuy nhiên, mỗi văn bản như vậy chỉ đưa ra một số điều khoản mang tính nguyên tắc chung nhưng lại thiếu tính cụ thể và cơ chế để triển khai trên thực tế.

“Tham khảo các đạo luật về bảo vệ dữ liệu và quyền riêng tư ở các quốc gia có thể thấy cùng có phạm vi và các vấn đề được điều chỉnh chung như sau:

- (i) Khái niệm, định nghĩa Thông tin và Quyền riêng tư*
- (ii) Các điều kiện để thu thập, xử lý Dữ liệu cá nhân hợp pháp*
- (iii) Quyền của Chủ thể dữ liệu và các Trường hợp hạn chế quyền*
- (iv) Trách nhiệm, nghĩa vụ của Bên thu thập, xử lý Dữ liệu*

(v) *Thiết chế giám sát độc lập của Cơ quan chính quyền và sự phối hợp giữa các Cơ quan có liên quan.*

(vi) *Chuyển giao dữ liệu qua biên giới*

(vii) *Chế tài và xử phạt” (Ly, 2020)*

Tuy nhiên, các văn bản quy phạm pháp luật Việt Nam có hiệu lực ở thời điểm trước khi Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP về bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân đều không phản ánh được các nội dung như vậy, dẫn tới các quy định về bảo vệ thông tin và quyền riêng tư có tính tượng trưng, hình thức, không đủ khả năng để thực thi trên thực tế. Để có thể có một khuôn khổ và hành lang pháp lý thống nhất, đầy đủ, toàn diện và hiệu quả, cần thiết phải tích hợp và trình bày trong một văn bản pháp quy riêng và có giá trị pháp lý cao, và điều này đã được khắc phục trên thực tế bằng việc ra đời của Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP ngày ngày 17 tháng 4 năm 2023 (Có hiệu lực kể từ ngày 01 tháng 7 năm 2023).

Việc tồn tại nhiều văn bản rời rạc khác nhau quy định về cùng vấn đề bảo vệ dữ liệu kéo theo một hệ quả khác là nội dung các quy định không giống nhau. Ví dụ:

Bộ Luật Dân sự 2015 quy định về “Quyền về đời sống riêng tư, bí mật cá nhân, bí mật gia đình” nhưng không có định nghĩa cụ thể;

Bộ Luật Hình sự 2015 sử dụng cụm từ “thông tin riêng tư”, nhưng cũng không có định nghĩa;

Luật An toàn thông tin mạng 2015 định nghĩa Thông tin cá nhân là “thông tin gắn với việc xác định danh tính của một người cụ thể”;

Luật Bảo vệ quyền lợi người tiêu dùng năm 2010 sử dụng cụm từ “thông tin của người tiêu dùng” để hàm chứa thông tin cá nhân của người tiêu dùng;

Nghị định số 52/2013/NĐ-CP quy định chi tiết hơn “Thông tin cá nhân là các thông tin góp phần định danh một cá nhân cụ thể, bao gồm tên, tuổi, địa chỉ nhà riêng, số điện thoại, thông tin y tế, số tài khoản, thông tin về các giao dịch thanh toán cá nhân và những thông tin khác mà cá nhân mong muốn giữ bí mật”;

Sự không thống nhất về mặt thuật ngữ và nội hàm của thuật ngữ dẫn tới những cách hiểu, cách vận dụng và áp dụng pháp luật khác nhau trên thực tế. “...*thế nào là bí mật đời tư? Pháp luật chưa có định nghĩa rõ ràng, cụ thể. Chính vì thế, thực tế đã xảy ra nhiều vụ liên quan đến nhiều người, nhất là những người nổi tiếng, nhân vật của công chúng bị xâm phạm bí mật đời tư vô tội vạ, dẫn tới nhiều tranh chấp và tòa án các cấp hết sức lúng túng khi giải quyết” (Hậu, 2015)*

3.1.2. Các quy định pháp luật hiện hành bao hàm các quy định về nghĩa vụ và chế tài xử phạt về vi phạm nghĩa vụ bảo mật dữ liệu

Như đã đề cập ở trên, đã có nhiều quy định về bảo vệ thông tin và quyền riêng tư trong các văn bản pháp quy phạm pháp luật khác nhau. Các quy định đó xác lập các nghĩa vụ mà các chủ thể có liên quan cần phải thực hiện. Ví dụ:

Khoản 2, Điều 6, Luật Bảo vệ người tiêu dùng 2010 quy định “*Trường hợp thu thập, sử*

dụng, chuyển giao thông tin của người tiêu dùng thì tổ chức, cá nhân kinh doanh hàng hóa, dịch vụ có trách nhiệm:

a) Thông báo rõ ràng, công khai trước khi thực hiện với người tiêu dùng về mục đích hoạt động thu thập, sử dụng thông tin của người tiêu dùng;

b) Sử dụng thông tin phù hợp với mục đích đã thông báo với người tiêu dùng và phải được người tiêu dùng đồng ý;

c) Bảo đảm an toàn, chính xác, đầy đủ khi thu thập, sử dụng, chuyển giao thông tin của người tiêu dùng;

d) Tự mình hoặc có biện pháp để người tiêu dùng cập nhật, điều chỉnh thông tin khi phát hiện thấy thông tin đó không chính xác;

đ) Chỉ được chuyển giao thông tin của người tiêu dùng cho bên thứ ba khi có sự đồng ý của người tiêu dùng, trừ trường hợp pháp luật có quy định khác.

...”.

Khoản 1, Điều 99, Luật Quản lý thuế 2019 quy định “Cơ quan quản lý thuế, công chức quản lý thuế, người đã là công chức quản lý thuế, cơ quan cung cấp, trao đổi thông tin người nộp thuế, tổ chức kinh doanh dịch vụ làm thủ tục về thuế phải giữ bí mật thông tin người nộp thuế theo quy định của pháp luật...”.

Các quy định về nghĩa vụ như vậy áp dụng đối với các đối tượng quy định tại mỗi văn bản chuyên biệt đó. Nói cách khác, giá trị hiệu lực của các quy định như vậy bị khu trú trong phạm vi và đối tượng áp dụng của mỗi văn bản riêng biệt, thiếu tính kết nối và toàn diện về yêu cầu bảo vệ dữ liệu trong mọi hoạt động.

Bên cạnh các quy phạm quy định các nghĩa vụ, trong hệ thống pháp luật hiện hành đã có nhiều quy phạm về chế tài xử lý trong lĩnh vực bảo vệ dữ liệu. Cụ thể:

Theo quy định tại Điều 84, Nghị định số 15/2020/NĐ-CP ngày 03/02/2020 của Chính phủ quy định xử phạt vi phạm hành chính trong lĩnh vực bưu chính, viễn thông, tần số vô tuyến điện, công nghệ thông tin và giao dịch điện tử, có hiệu lực thi hành từ ngày 15 tháng 4 năm 2020 (Sửa đổi, bổ sung bởi Nghị định số 14/2022/NĐ-CP ngày 27/01/2022) về thi hành vi phạm quy định về thu thập, sử dụng thông tin cá nhân có thể bị xử phạt tiền tới 60.000.000 đồng; và hành vi vi phạm quy định về cập nhật, sửa đổi và hủy bỏ thông tin cá nhân có thể bị xử phạt tiền tới 70.000.000 đồng.

Theo quy định tại Điều 159, Bộ Luật Hình sự 2015 thì người nào bị kết án về Tội xâm phạm bí mật hoặc an toàn thư tín, điện thoại, điện tín hoặc hình thức trao đổi thông tin riêng tư khác của người khác, thì có thể bị xử phạt tới 03 năm tù giam, và có thể bị phạt tiền từ 5.000.000 đồng đến 20.000.000 đồng, cấm đảm nhiệm chức vụ nhất định từ 01 năm đến 05 năm.

3.1.3. Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP về bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân

Ngày 17 tháng 4 năm 2023, Chính phủ ban hành Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP về bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân. Nghị định này có hiệu lực kể từ ngày 01 tháng 7 năm 2023. Có thể nói, đây là

văn bản pháp quy đầu tiên của Việt nam đưa ra các quy định có tính hệ thống, toàn diện và thống nhất về vấn đề bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân.

Trước hết, Nghị định đã đưa ra định nghĩa về dữ liệu cá nhân. Theo đó, khoản 1, điều 2, Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP quy định: *“Dữ liệu cá nhân là thông tin dưới dạng ký hiệu, chữ viết, chữ số, hình ảnh, âm thanh hoặc dạng tương tự trên môi trường điện tử gắn liền với một con người cụ thể hoặc giúp xác định một con người cụ thể. Dữ liệu cá nhân bao gồm dữ liệu cá nhân cơ bản và dữ liệu cá nhân nhạy cảm”*. Bên cạnh đó, Nghị định đã đưa ra được một số định nghĩa về chủ thể như chủ thể dữ liệu, bên xử lý dữ liệu, bên kiểm soát dữ liệu, bên kiểm soát và xử lý dữ liệu và quy định các quyền, nghĩa vụ của mỗi chủ thể này. Ngoài vấn đề chủ thể, Nghị định cũng quy định các vấn đề liên quan đến các quyền của chủ thể dữ liệu, chuyển dữ liệu cá nhân ra nước ngoài, nội hàm của xử lý dữ liệu cá nhân, cơ quan chuyên trách bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân và Công thông tin Quốc gia về bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân.

Đặc biệt, có hai quy định lần đầu tiên xuất hiện ở Việt Nam và dự báo là có tác động to lớn tới toàn bộ cộng đồng doanh nghiệp và các chủ thể có liên quan là: (i) Đánh giá tác động xử lý dữ liệu cá nhân tại Điều 24 và (ii) Chỉ định bộ phận có chức năng bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân tại Điều 28 của Nghị định này. Theo quy định tại Điều 24, *“Bên Kiểm soát dữ liệu cá nhân, Bên Kiểm soát và xử lý dữ liệu cá nhân lập và lưu giữ Hồ sơ đánh giá tác động xử lý dữ liệu cá nhân của mình kể từ thời điểm bắt đầu xử lý dữ liệu cá nhân”*, và có thể hiểu rằng, bất kì tổ chức, cá nhân nào có hành động thu thập, sử dụng, xử lý, chuyển dữ liệu cá nhân ra nước ngoài thì đều phải lập và lưu trữ Hồ sơ đánh giá tác động xử lý dữ liệu cá nhân. Theo quy định tại khoản 1, Điều 28, thì mỗi tổ chức có thực hiện việc thu thập, sử dụng, xử lý, chuyển dữ liệu cá nhân ra nước ngoài đều phải *“Chỉ định bộ phận có chức năng bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân, chỉ định nhân sự phụ trách bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân và trao đổi thông tin về bộ phận và cá nhân phụ trách bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân với Cơ quan chuyên trách bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân”*. Theo đánh giá của nhóm tác giả, 02 quy định này của Nghị định đã tạo nên những sức ép không nhỏ đối với doanh nghiệp cả về mặt bố trí nhân sự, tiêu tốn thời gian, chi phí và hạ tầng công nghệ.

Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP là một bước tiến lớn của Việt Nam trong vấn đề bảo vệ dữ liệu, tiệm cận với khuôn khổ pháp lý về bảo vệ dữ liệu ở nhiều Quốc gia phát triển.

Tuy nhiên, với việc ban hành Nghị định này, khuôn khổ pháp lý về bảo vệ dữ liệu của Việt Nam vẫn còn tồn tại một số vấn đề như sau:

Thứ nhất, Bên cạnh quy định tại Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP thì còn tồn tại nhiều quy định về bảo vệ thông tin cá nhân, bí mật cá nhân ở nhiều văn bản khác nhau, và trong số đó, có văn bản là đạo luật nên có giá trị cao hơn Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP. Điều này đặt ra thử thách về khả năng thực thi pháp luật trên thực tế bởi sự chông chéo, mâu thuẫn, thậm chí vô hiệu hóa lẫn nhau.

Thứ hai, Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP được ban hành nhưng chưa có Thông tư hướng dẫn nên việc triển khai thực hiện chi tiết sẽ còn gặp nhiều khó khăn. Bên cạnh đó, chưa có Nghị định về xử phạt hành chính trong lĩnh vực bảo vệ dữ liệu, chưa có quy định về xử lý hình sự về bảo vệ dữ liệu để tương thích và thống nhất với quy định tại Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP, nên khả năng áp dụng trên thực tế cũng sẽ bị hạn chế.

Thứ ba, một số nghĩa vụ mà Nghị định 13 đặt ra đối với các chủ thể như Bên kiểm soát

dữ liệu, Bên xử lý dữ liệu, Bên kiểm soát và xử lý dữ liệu... tại Điều 24 và Điều 28 của Nghị định đang được coi là quá nặng và gây ra nhiều tổn kém về thời gian, chi phí cho doanh nghiệp. Ở khía cạnh này, Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP thậm chí là khắt khe và chặt chẽ hơn cả Quy định chung về bảo mật thông tin GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) của Liên minh Châu Âu.

Thứ tư, ở một số Quốc gia, văn bản có giá trị pháp lý về bảo vệ dữ liệu được đặt ở cấp độ Đạo Luật, như Luật Bảo vệ thông tin cá nhân PDPA (Personal Data Protection Act) của Singapore; Đạo luật bảo vệ thông tin cá nhân của Nhật Bản; Luật Bảo vệ thông tin cá nhân PIPL (Personal Information Protection Law) của Trung Quốc; GDPR của Liên minh Châu Âu... Do đó, thực tiễn này cũng đặt ra một yêu cầu nghiên cứu và xem xét đối với Quốc Hội Việt Nam trong việc ban hành một văn bản luật để có thể tạo hàng lang pháp lý đủ mạnh điều chỉnh các vấn đề liên quan đến bảo vệ dữ liệu.

3.1.4. Phạm vi dữ liệu bảo vệ

Trong nền kinh tế thị trường, và đặc biệt là trong bối cảnh cuộc cách mạng công nghiệp lần thứ tư nói chung và công cuộc chuyển đổi số nói riêng, nguồn dữ liệu là khổng lồ và hết sức phong phú, đa dạng. Các dữ liệu không chỉ có thông tin cá nhân mà còn có các thông tin liên quan đến doanh nghiệp, đến hành vi thị trường, thói quen thị trường các dữ liệu thống kê của thị trường. Kho dữ liệu lớn (Big Data) này trở thành nguồn tài nguyên đáng giá cho các hoạt động nghiên cứu, phân tích thị trường, các chiến dịch tiếp thị, chiến dịch quảng cáo và thông tin đầu vào cho các công cụ học máy, phần mềm và thiết bị trí tuệ nhân tạo (AI) như ChatGPT, Notion AI, Bing AI Chatbot...

Tuy nhiên, thực tiễn trên thế giới, cũng như quy định tại Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP của Việt Nam, vấn đề bảo vệ dữ liệu chỉ được đặt ra đối với thông tin cá nhân mà không đặt ra đối với các loại thông tin khác. Do đó, đối với các doanh nghiệp, vấn đề bảo vệ dữ liệu không thuộc phạm vi thông tin cá nhân sẽ phải thực hiện thông qua các cơ chế pháp lý khác, như bảo vệ bí mật kinh doanh, chống cạnh tranh không lành mạnh.

3.2. Thực trạng hoạt động bảo vệ dữ liệu của các doanh nghiệp ở Việt Nam

Hiện nay ở Việt Nam, công tác bảo đảm an ninh thông tin dù đã được chú trọng tuy nhiên có lúc, có nơi vẫn còn tình trạng chủ quan, chưa quan tâm đúng mức, còn nhiều thiếu sót, sơ hở, rất dễ để các đối tượng cơ hội lợi dụng gây nguy cơ mất an ninh thông tin, lộ, lọt bí mật nhà nước. Một số cơ quan, đơn vị, ban, ngành nắm giữ hệ thống thông tin quan trọng về an ninh quốc gia nhưng kỹ năng, ý thức bảo vệ bí mật, an ninh thông tin của một số phòng, ban, cá nhân còn hạn chế.

Cả nước hiện nay có 3.078 hệ thống thông tin trong các cơ quan nhà nước, trong đó, mới chỉ 1.846 (60%) hệ thống được xác định cấp độ an toàn, 201 (6,5%) hệ thống thông tin đáp ứng yêu cầu bảo đảm an toàn theo cấp độ. Chưa kể, sự tụt hậu về công nghệ, sự phụ thuộc vào đối tác nước ngoài, nhất là phần mềm hệ thống, dịch vụ mạng xã hội... tại một số nơi cũng đáng báo động nguy cơ mất chủ quyền nội dung số, tài nguyên thông tin của các tổ chức, cá nhân, doanh nghiệp và của quốc gia.

Theo thống kê của Cục An ninh mạng và phòng, chống tội phạm sử dụng công nghệ cao (Bộ Công an), giai đoạn 2010-2021, các thể lực thù địch, phần tử xấu đã, đang sử dụng 8.784

web, blog có tên miền nước ngoài; 381 web, blog có tên miền trong nước thường xuyên đăng tải thông tin xấu, độc chống phá Đảng, Nhà nước Việt Nam.

Các cơ quan chức năng đã phát hiện 279 vụ sử dụng internet xâm phạm an ninh quốc gia, đấu tranh với hơn 200 đối tượng; xử lý 140 đối tượng. Đáng chú ý, trong đó có 219 vụ kích động biểu tình trên không gian mạng; 138 hội, nhóm trá hình hoạt động trên không gian mạng; 45.498 lượt công thông tin, trang tin điện tử có tên miền ".vn" bị tấn công, trong đó có 2.113 lượt tấn công các công thông tin, trang tin điện tử của cơ quan Đảng, Nhà nước, gây ra những hậu quả nghiêm trọng. (Báo Lào Cai, 2023)

Các nhóm tin tặc, tổ chức tội phạm không ngừng thực hiện các chiến dịch tấn công mạng tự phát, đơn lẻ và quy mô lớn nhằm vào hạ tầng công nghệ thông tin trọng yếu của các quốc gia. Thực tế này đang tiềm ẩn không ít nguy cơ đe dọa gây tê liệt, gián đoạn hoạt động lãnh đạo, chỉ đạo, điều hành, quản lý kinh tế-xã hội của các cơ quan Nhà nước. Các thế lực thù địch, phản động cũng tăng cường hoạt động tình báo, gián điệp mạng, khủng bố mạng, kêu gọi tài trợ khủng bố, tội phạm mạng, tán phát tin giả, tin xấu, độc hại, lợi dụng mạng xã hội để xuyên tạc Cương lĩnh, đường lối, chủ trương, chính sách của Đảng, pháp luật của Nhà nước, phủ nhận nền tảng tư tưởng của Đảng nhằm tác động chính trị nội bộ, can thiệp, hướng lái chính sách, pháp luật của Việt Nam.

Vì vậy, vấn đề bảo vệ dữ liệu đang được đặt ra tại mọi lĩnh vực của đời sống xã hội và trở thành một bộ phận quan trọng của an ninh quốc gia. Tầm quan trọng của công tác bảo đảm an ninh thông tin luôn được khẳng định là nhiệm vụ cấp thiết trong tiến trình phát triển của mỗi quốc gia.

Các công cụ về thu thập dữ liệu giúp doanh nghiệp dễ dàng tìm hiểu về thị hiếu và đáp ứng nhu cầu của khách hàng. Ngoài ra, việc thu thập dữ liệu còn giúp các doanh nghiệp hoạt động hiệu quả và tăng năng suất, đưa ra các chiến dịch marketing nhắm tới khách hàng mục tiêu và cá nhân hoá.

Tuy nhiên, nhiều doanh nghiệp chưa ý thức về hậu quả khi thu thập dữ liệu khách hàng. Nguy cơ đối mặt với sự xâm nhập dữ liệu bất hợp pháp và chịu trách nhiệm về trước pháp luật về việc bảo vệ quyền dữ liệu cá nhân tại nước sở tại nói riêng và khu vực quốc tế nói chung là không thể tránh khỏi. Ngoài vấn đề liên quan đến pháp lý, doanh nghiệp sẽ phải đối mặt với các vấn đề sau nếu như không thiết lập hàng rào bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân của khách hàng:

Một là, hành vi trộm cắp danh tính cá nhân: hầu hết người tiêu dùng đều lo lắng về việc bị đánh cắp dữ liệu cá nhân trên không gian mạng, hậu quả là thiệt hại về tài sản như thông tin tài khoản ngân hàng, tiết lộ khoản nợ tín dụng hay công khai dữ liệu cá nhân nhạy cảm.

Hai là, doanh nghiệp phải chi trả số tiền rất lớn liên quan đến vi phạm dữ liệu.

Xâm nhập dữ liệu khi chưa được sự đồng ý, làm phiền hay bị thao túng là những thứ mà nền tảng công nghệ số đã mang lại cho khách hàng trong việc thu thập thông tin. Vì vậy, việc bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân của khách hàng chưa bao giờ quan trọng đến thế. Khi các doanh nghiệp ý thức được sự cấp thiết khi xây dựng hàng rào chắn vững chắc đối với an toàn thông tin, lợi ích đối với doanh nghiệp có thể kể đến như:

Một là, doanh nghiệp đạt được sự yên tâm, trung thành của khách hàng khi sử dụng sản

phẩm và tăng tỉ lệ quay lại mua hàng. Vấn đề quan tâm hàng đầu của nhà tiêu dùng là họ không biết các công ty sẽ sử dụng thông tin cá nhân của họ với mục đích gì và như thế nào.

Hai là, doanh nghiệp tránh các hậu quả từ hành vi vi phạm quyền bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân. Nhiều quốc gia trên thế giới coi trọng quyền riêng tư cá nhân và đã ban hành những quy tắc, điều luật về bảo vệ quyền riêng tư cá nhân. Có thể kể đến “Quy định chung về bảo vệ dữ liệu” của Ủy ban dữ liệu Châu Âu xây dựng với mục đích cải cách, tuyên truyền cách thức bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân trên toàn Liên minh Châu Âu. Một trong những điểm nhấn về tính hiệu quả trong bộ Quy định này là chỉ cho phép doanh nghiệp thu thập dữ liệu với lý do hợp pháp, trong đó khách hàng phải nhận thức được loại dữ liệu nào của bản thân đang bị thu thập và nguyên nhân tại sao. Tại Việt Nam, luật pháp liên quan đến bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân được quy định rất rõ trong Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP ban hành ngày 17 tháng 4 năm 2023, có hiệu lực từ tháng 7 năm 2023 về xử lý hành vi vi phạm, hành vi bị nghiêm cấm, quyền và nghĩa vụ của chủ thể dữ liệu, hay trong Luật An ninh mạng, Luật Công nghệ Thông tin, Luật bảo vệ người tiêu dùng... Như vậy, các doanh nghiệp muốn phát triển đổi mới và bền vững trong nền kinh tế số thì việc tuân thủ theo quy định của pháp luật là rất cần thiết để đảm bảo thương hiệu và uy tín lâu dài của doanh nghiệp.

Ba là, việc bảo vệ dữ liệu khách hàng có thể giúp doanh nghiệp bảo vệ danh tiếng và thương hiệu. Trong thời đại kinh tế số phát triển nhanh như hiện nay, việc vi phạm dữ liệu cá nhân sẽ ảnh hưởng nặng nề tới uy tín và danh tiếng của doanh nghiệp và dẫn tới hậu quả trực tiếp tổn thất về kinh tế. Ngược lại, việc cung cấp cho khách hàng các mức độ bảo mật thông tin cá nhân an toàn sẽ gắn liền với giá trị của doanh nghiệp đó. Nếu như chỉ một hành vi xâm phạm dữ liệu được công khai thì việc mất đi uy tín trên thị trường là không thể tránh khỏi.

Nhà tiêu dùng luôn đặt niềm tin vào những doanh nghiệp mà có khả năng tuân thủ các quy định về bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân, đặc biệt là trong thị trường cạnh tranh khốc liệt như ngày nay.

Bốn là, việc bảo vệ dữ liệu thể hiện đạo đức và doanh nghiệp (Business Ethics) và trách nhiệm xã hội.

GS.TS. Từ Thị Loan (2022), nguyên Viện trưởng Viện Văn hoá nghệ thuật Quốc gia Việt Nam chia sẻ về đạo đức, văn hóa trong Hội thảo Văn hóa 2022 là “trụ cột tinh thần” làm nên cốt cách của doanh nghiệp.

Trong bối cảnh nền kinh tế chuyển đổi số, khách hàng có xu hướng ủng hộ những doanh nghiệp có khả năng đưa ra các quyết định kinh doanh có đạo đức. Một số doanh nghiệp thực phẩm cam kết không sản xuất các sản phẩm độc hại, các công ty sản xuất kinh doanh khác tập trung vào đầu tư vào cơ sở hạ tầng và không gian xanh để đảm bảo phúc lợi cho người lao động, còn đối với doanh nghiệp số, đó là hành vi bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân của khách hàng.

Mọi doanh nghiệp đều có quy tắc đạo đức và giá trị kinh doanh riêng. Khi khách hàng nhận thức ngày một sâu rộng, điều mà họ quan tâm tới ngoài sản phẩm còn là sự tuân thủ các bộ quy tắc về đạo đức đó của doanh nghiệp. Coi trọng những lo lắng của khách hàng về quyền riêng tư dữ liệu sẽ có tác động mạnh mẽ trong việc lấy được niềm tin và ủng hộ lâu dài của khách hàng.

Năm là, việc bảo vệ dữ liệu giúp doanh nghiệp có được sự trung thành của khách hàng.

Sự trung thành là một trong các thành tố quan trọng đối với doanh nghiệp phát triển bền vững và thành công. Thương hiệu của công ty càng đáng tin cậy, số lượng khách hàng trung thành ngày càng cao. Một doanh nghiệp vi phạm về quyền bảo mật dữ liệu và an ninh thông tin sẽ có uy tín kém đối với sự cân nhắc quay lại tiêu dùng sản phẩm của khách hàng đối với doanh nghiệp đó.

Do vậy, một chính sách bảo mật dữ liệu tích cực và hiệu quả có thể làm tăng giá trị thương hiệu của doanh nghiệp đối với nhà tiêu dùng, đặc biệt khi khách hàng hiểu rằng công ty mà họ đang ủng hộ đang cố gắng hết sức để bảo vệ dữ liệu và thông tin của họ không chỉ đối với tư cách khách hàng mà còn là sự tôn trọng quyền riêng tư trên tư cách giữa người và người. Chính tinh thần trách nhiệm, ý thức giữ chữ tín, tôn trọng đối tác sẽ đem lại sự hài lòng, tin tưởng và dẫn đến sự hợp tác lâu dài, gắn bó, trung thành của đối tác và khách hàng với doanh nghiệp.

4. MỘT SỐ KIẾN NGHỊ HOÀN THIỆN PHÁP LUẬT VÀ ĐỀ XUẤT GIẢI PHÁP BẢO VỆ DỮ LIỆU CHO DOANH NGHIỆP TRONG NỀN KINH TẾ SỐ Ở VIỆT NAM

4.1. Kiến nghị hoàn thiện pháp luật về bảo vệ dữ liệu

Trong bối cảnh chuyển đổi số, vấn đề bảo vệ dữ liệu không chỉ còn là vấn đề về an ninh, an toàn liên quan đến cá nhân mà còn là vấn đề khai thác thương mại dữ liệu. Dưới góc độ kinh tế, dữ liệu là một nguồn tài nguyên có giá trị cao, không gây ô nhiễm môi trường. Cho dù hiện nay chúng ta chưa có những sự thừa nhận một cách chính thức, nhưng nhóm tác giả cho rằng, dữ liệu là một loại tài sản vô hình và hoàn toàn có thể đưa vào khai thác trong thương mại để mang lại doanh thu và lợi nhuận. Thực tiễn không phụ thuộc vào ý chí của người quản lý mà vận động theo thị trường, và không quá khó để tìm thấy các thông tin về mua bán dữ liệu đang công khai trên các nền tảng mạng xã hội hiện nay. Do không có sự công nhận và quản lý chính thức nên việc mua bán dữ liệu đang diễn ra tràn lan thiếu kiểm soát, xâm phạm các quyền và lợi ích của tổ chức, cá nhân. Do đó, nếu có một khuôn khổ pháp lý điều chỉnh về hoạt động này, các dữ liệu đã được lọc, phân loại để loại bỏ các yếu tố định danh cá nhân hoàn toàn có thể đưa vào khai thác thương mại. Nhóm tác giả đưa ra một số kiến nghị nhằm nâng cao sự chặt chẽ và đảm bảo tính hiệu quả khi thực thi pháp luật từ góc độ quản lý nhà nước về quyền bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân tại Việt Nam như sau:

Một là, chúng ta cần nghiên cứu và mạnh dạn xây dựng khuôn khổ pháp lý để cho phép việc thu thập, xử lý, khai thác và chuyển nhượng dữ liệu (đã qua sàng lọc, xử lý để loại bỏ thông tin cá nhân nhạy cảm, thông tin định danh cá nhân) để hình thành một thị trường dữ liệu. Nhóm tác giả cho rằng, việc hình thành thị trường dữ liệu không chỉ để đạt tới thu hút nguồn doanh thu và lợi nhuận từ việc mua bán dữ liệu, mà quan trọng hơn, tạo lập một thị trường cung cho các nguyên liệu đầu vào để các đơn vị có thể vận hành các phần mềm trí tuệ nhân tạo, các thiết bị và chương trình sử dụng dữ liệu lớn (Big Data) một cách hợp pháp. Thông qua việc công nhận thị trường dữ liệu, chúng ta có khả năng loại bỏ và kiểm soát tính bất hợp pháp trong các hoạt động thu thập và sử dụng dữ liệu mà các đơn vị công nghệ đang vận hành các phần mềm AI, phần mềm sử dụng dữ liệu lớn hiện nay.

Hai là, cần hợp nhất các quy định về bảo vệ dữ liệu vào một văn bản để tạo dựng hàng lang pháp lý thống nhất, có hiệu lực và rõ ràng về vấn đề bảo vệ dữ liệu. Như đã phân tích ở những phần trên, việc tồn tại đồng thời nhiều quy định ở nhiều văn bản quy phạm pháp luật

khác nhau điều chỉnh cùng vấn đề về bảo vệ dữ liệu dẫn tới sự chông chéo, thiếu nhất quán, gây ra khó khăn trong công tác thực thi pháp luật. Nhóm tác giả cho rằng, Quốc Hội, Chính phủ cần ban hành các văn bản Luật, Nghị định sửa đổi để loại bỏ, sửa đổi các quy định về bảo vệ thông tin cá nhân đang tồn tại trong các văn bản riêng biệt hiện nay và dẫn chiếu tới duy nhất Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP về bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân, coi Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP là văn bản cao nhất của Việt Nam về vấn đề bảo vệ dữ liệu.

Ba là, cơ quan có thẩm quyền cần nghiên cứu và triển khai việc ban hành Thông tư và văn bản hướng dẫn chi tiết việc thực hiện Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP, ban hành các văn bản về xử phạt hành chính, sửa đổi Bộ Luật hình sự để điều chỉnh nội dung Điều 159 để thống nhất với các nội dung quy định tại Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP. Thông tư hướng dẫn cần làm rõ và quy định chi tiết các trường hợp doanh nghiệp phải thực hiện và trường hợp được miễn nghĩa vụ lập và lưu giữ Hồ sơ đánh giá tác động xử lý dữ liệu cá nhân, miễn nghĩa vụ chỉ định bộ phận có chức năng bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân, chỉ định nhân sự phụ trách bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân.

Bốn là, cần sửa đổi các quy định về chế tài phạt hành chính, hình sự, dân sự ở mức độ nặng hơn và nghiêm khắc hơn.

Theo quy định tại Điều 84, Nghị định số 15/2020/NĐ-CP ngày 03/02/2020 của Chính phủ quy định xử phạt vi phạm hành chính trong lĩnh vực bưu chính, viễn thông, tần số vô tuyến điện, công nghệ thông tin và giao dịch điện tử, có hiệu lực thi hành từ ngày 15 tháng 4 năm 2020 (Sửa đổi, bổ sung bởi Nghị định số 14/2022/NĐ-CP ngày 27/01/2022) về thi hành vi phạm quy định về thu thập, sử dụng thông tin cá nhân có thể bị xử phạt tiền tới 60.000.000 đồng; và hành vi vi phạm quy định về cập nhật, sửa đổi và hủy bỏ thông tin cá nhân có thể bị xử phạt tiền tới 70.000.000 đồng.

Theo quy định tại Điều 159, Bộ Luật Hình sự 2015 thì người nào bị kết án về Tội xâm phạm bí mật hoặc an toàn thư tín, điện thoại, điện tín hoặc hình thức trao đổi thông tin riêng tư khác của người khác, thì có thể bị xử phạt tới 03 năm tù giam, và có thể bị phạt tiền từ 5.000.000 đồng đến 20.000.000 đồng, cấm đảm nhiệm chức vụ nhất định từ 01 năm đến 05 năm.

Theo Điều 4 Nghị định 13/2023/NĐ-CP về bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân quy định về "Xử lý vi phạm quy định bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân: Cơ quan, tổ chức, cá nhân vi phạm quy định bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân tùy theo mức độ có thể bị xử lý kỷ luật, xử phạt vi phạm hành chính, xử lý hình sự theo quy định." Có thể thấy, trong Nghị định 13/2023 vẫn chưa quy định rõ ràng và chưa đảm bảo tính răn đe đối với hành vi vi phạm.

Trong khi đó, theo Quy định chung về bảo vệ dữ liệu (GDPR) do Ủy ban châu Âu xây dựng, tiền phạt đối với hành vi trái với quy định của GDPR rất cao. Theo đó có hai cách thức phạt, có thể tối đa là 20 triệu Euro hoặc 4% doanh thu toàn cầu (tùy theo mức nào cao hơn), cộng với việc các chủ thể dữ liệu có quyền yêu cầu bồi thường thiệt hại.³³

Ngoài ra, luật về Sự riêng tư của người tiêu dùng của bang California (CCPA) (California Consumer Privacy Act Policy) được thông qua vào tháng 6/2018 cho phép quyền

³³ GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation là một bộ quy tắc được xây dựng nhằm cung cấp cho công dân EU quyền kiểm soát nhiều hơn đối với dữ liệu cá nhân của họ. Theo các điều khoản của GDPR, không chỉ các tổ chức phải đảm bảo dữ liệu cá nhân được thu thập hợp pháp và trong các điều kiện nghiêm ngặt, mà tất cả những bên thu thập và quản lý dữ liệu có nghĩa vụ bảo vệ dữ liệu khỏi việc bị lạm dụng và khai thác, cũng như tôn trọng quyền của chủ sở hữu dữ liệu

hành động riêng tư trong trường hợp vi phạm dữ liệu và cho phép Bộ trưởng Tư pháp California áp dụng các hình phạt hành chính lên tới 7.500 đô la cho mỗi lần vi phạm mà không có giới hạn tối đa.³⁴

Như vậy, mức phạt trong pháp luật Việt Nam còn quá nhẹ so với các quốc gia khác và ở Châu Âu, hình phạt chưa đủ răn đe và chưa tương xứng với mức độ nghiêm trọng của việc vi phạm sự riêng tư nói chung và quyền về bảo mật dữ liệu cá nhân nói riêng, cũng như chưa đủ sức ảnh hưởng để nâng cao nhận thức cho doanh nghiệp về sự quan trọng của việc an ninh thông tin. Vì vậy, nhóm tác giả kiến nghị Nhà nước cần sửa đổi các quy định về chế tài phạt hành chính, hình sự, dân sự ở mức độ nặng hơn nhằm đảm bảo sự hiệu quả của thực thi pháp luật đối với các cơ quan, tổ chức, doanh nghiệp vi phạm quyền bảo mật thông tin.

Nhằm là, Nhà nước cần ban hành các quy định về bảo đảm an ninh thông tin cho các doanh nghiệp trong trường hợp dữ liệu bị tấn công.

Nhiều tổ chức tiếp tục tránh liên quan đến các cơ quan thực thi pháp luật và cuối cùng phải trả tiền cho nhu cầu ransomware (mã độc tống tiền) (2) Họ cảm thấy rằng việc hợp tác với cơ quan thực thi sẽ chỉ làm phức tạp thêm tình hình.

Tuy nhiên, trên toàn cầu, các nạn nhân của ransomware trong nghiên cứu hợp tác với cơ quan thực thi pháp luật đã tiết kiệm được 470.000 USD chi phí vi phạm trung bình so với những nạn nhân không nhờ đến sự tham gia của cơ quan thực thi pháp luật. Bất chấp những khoản tiết kiệm tiềm năng này, vẫn có đến 37% các công ty nạn nhân của ransomware không báo cáo với cơ quan thực thi pháp luật khi xảy ra cuộc tấn công ransomware (Minh, 2023).

Nếu như Nhà nước ban hành các quy định để bảo vệ doanh nghiệp trong trường hợp bị tấn công thì các tổ chức và các công ty sẽ có thêm niềm tin hơn vào hành lang pháp lý và khuyến khích sự trung thực khi báo cáo tình hình về xử lý, thu thập dữ liệu ở mức độ thường xuyên cho cơ quan chức năng. Mặt khác, điều này cũng giúp cơ quan nhà nước nắm bắt rõ hơn về tình trạng lưu trữ thông tin của người dân trong các doanh nghiệp đó. Doanh nghiệp và Nhà nước cần phải phối kết hợp để bảo vệ dữ liệu cá nhân của khách hàng, người dân một cách tối ưu và hiệu quả.

4.2. Đề xuất giải pháp bảo vệ dữ liệu cho các doanh nghiệp

Ngoài hành lang pháp lý, doanh nghiệp cần ứng dụng các giải pháp khác để chủ động bảo mật thông tin của khách hàng. Trong đó có thể kể đến như:

Một là, sử dụng các phần mềm bảo mật dữ liệu.

Với việc vi phạm dữ liệu gây thiệt hại trung bình hàng triệu đô la cho các tổ chức toàn cầu (Việt Phát triển Bảo hiểm Việt Nam, 2015), doanh nghiệp cần phải hiểu dữ liệu nên được lưu trữ ở đâu, chia thành loại dữ liệu nào (dữ liệu cấu trúc (structured data) và phi cấu trúc (unstructured data)), đối tượng nào có thể truy cập chúng, những gì cần được mã hóa, luồng dữ liệu này là gì và những cấu hình sai tiềm ẩn nào hiện hữu. Các giải pháp nền tảng này giúp cho việc quản lý bảo mật dữ liệu mạnh mẽ. Ví dụ như giám sát hoạt động dữ liệu, tập trung hóa

³⁴ Đạo luật về quyền riêng tư của người tiêu dùng ở California (CCPA) được ban hành thành luật vào ngày 28 tháng 6 năm 2018. CCPA tìm cách đảm bảo rằng người tiêu dùng California được hưởng mức độ quyền riêng tư nhất định.

hoạt động dữ liệu, mã hóa dữ liệu nhạy cảm, xác định các lỗ hổng trong môi trường dữ liệu của doanh nghiệp hay tích hợp khám phá và phân loại dữ liệu có cấu trúc và phi cấu trúc.....

Hai là, doanh nghiệp có thể cung cấp một chương trình trao thưởng hoặc một dịch vụ cao cấp cho người tiêu dùng như một khoản bồi thường cho việc thu thập thông tin cá nhân của họ trong trường hợp doanh nghiệp muốn sử dụng tệp dữ liệu cá nhân của khách hàng. Luật riêng tư của Người tiêu dùng tại California (CCPA) cho phép các doanh nghiệp cung cấp cho người tiêu dùng các khuyến khích về tài chính vì chia sẻ thông tin cá nhân. Việc tham gia của khách hàng là không bắt buộc và tùy thuộc điều khoản hiện hành cũng như việc khách hàng có thể rút lại bất kỳ lúc nào.

KẾT LUẬN

Chuyển đổi số là một bước trung gian của toàn bộ đời sống kinh tế - xã hội trong cuộc cách mạng công nghiệp lần thứ tư, và là động lực tạo nên nguồn dữ liệu khổng lồ, có giá trị thương mại. Tuy vậy, khuôn khổ và hành lang pháp lý của Việt Nam chưa theo kịp với thực tế và thực tiễn hoạt động bảo vệ dữ liệu của các doanh nghiệp vẫn gặp nhiều khó khăn. Đây là một thực tế đang tồn tại mà không phải là một dự báo, nhưng lại chưa được nghiên cứu, phân tích và đánh giá một cách đầy đủ và toàn diện.

Do đó, vấn đề xây dựng mới, hoàn thiện pháp luật và các giải pháp thực tế về bảo vệ dữ liệu dành cho doanh nghiệp không chỉ là để quản lý vấn đề an ninh, an toàn thông tin cá nhân mà còn là để tạo lập và phát triển thị trường dữ liệu, tạo nguồn thu về tài chính, tạo lập thị trường cung hợp pháp cho một loạt các thị trường ngách về công nghệ trí tuệ nhân tạo, dữ liệu lớn đang phát triển nhanh chóng trong thời gian qua.

TÀI LIỆU THAM KHẢO

Hiến pháp 2013

Bộ Luật Dân sự số 91/2015/QH13

Văn bản hợp nhất Bộ Luật Hình sự số 01/VBHN-VPQH

Luật Quản lý thuế số 78/2006/QH11

Luật An toàn thông tin mạng số 86/2015/QH13

Luật Bảo vệ người tiêu dùng số 59/2010/QH12

Nghị định số 52/2013/NĐ-CP của Chính Phủ

Nghị định số 15/2020/NĐ-CP của Chính Phủ

Nghị định số 14/2022/NĐ-CP của Chính Phủ

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THEME 5:
MANAGEMENT, TRADE, TOURISM

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN APPAREL RETAILING: ELEVATING CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE AND ENGAGEMENT THROUGH LIVE STREAMING COMMERCE

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Abstract

Recent decline in the efficiency of traditional marketing communication channels in apparel retailing has encouraged businesses to adopt new tactics to enhance sales volume. Among those, live streaming has been proven to be one of the novel and effective approach in this digitalization era. However, a nerve-wracking question revolves around what should be done to retain customers while live streaming is long assumed to be time-consuming. Drawn upon the framework of Stimulus-Organism-Response, this study seeks to explore the factors that influence customer experience and engagement in the live streaming commerce of apparel products in Vietnam. The study has collected 307 valid responses from Vietnamese customers and employed structural equation modelling (SEM) for a thorough analysis of data. The research findings found that entertainment, social interactivity, and information quality together contribute to a positive customer experience, though with varying degrees. Among them, social interactivity's impact is shown to be the strongest. Lastly, elucidating the significance of live streaming as a novel live business model to establish synchronous connections between sellers and customers, these findings emphasize delivering excellent customer experience as the key toward building customer engagement. The research findings can be leveraged by retailers and marketers to utilize live streaming commerce as a more effective and targeted digital marketing channel in apparel retailing. (This is an extended study from the first author's master's thesis in Business Administration).

Keywords: *Customer experience, customer engagement, digital transformation, live streaming commerce.*

IMPACT OF DESTINATION IMAGE ON SATISFACTION AND E-WOM OF DOMESTIC TOURISTS: CASE STUDY OF NINH BINH TOURISM DESTINATION

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Abstract

The study explores the impact of destination image (include: Cognitive Image, Affective Image) on E-WOM of Domestic Tourists who traveled to Ninh Binh through the mediating variables of their satisfaction. The survey was conducted with 201 domestic tourists by using an online questionnaire via Google during the period of March - May 2023. Collected data are analyzed according to structural equation modeling (SEM) through software SPSS and AMOS. The results show that cognitive image factors belonging to destination image variables have a positive and direct impact on E-WOM of domestic tourists. Regarding indirect effects, the results explain that all factors of destination image variables have an influence on E-WOM of domestic tourists traveled to Ninh Binh through the mediating variables of satisfaction. As a consequence, the study suggests some solutions and implications for stakeholders to develop and implement strategies to help the tourism industry in Ninh Binh province. Recommendations are contributed on the basis of actual research and data analysis about destination image, satisfaction and E-WOM of Domestic Tourists who traveled to Ninh Binh province.

Keywords: Destination image, Domestic Tourists Satisfaction, E-WOM, Ninh Binh province.

1. INTRODUCTIONS

The tourism industry in Viet Nam has undergone rapid development both in terms of quantity and quality of development after 35 years of restoration. International and domestic travelers, as well as tourism-related income, are expanding rapidly and significantly contributing to the country's GDP growth. Vietnam's tourism sector has made a remarkable recovery after suffering a catastrophic plummet for over two years due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This has set the groundwork for a breakthrough in the second half of 2022 and 2023.

Vietnam is definitely well-known to many tourists with famous locations from South to North such as Da Nang, Yen Bai, Nha Trang,.. however, there is a particular destination that has steadily claimed its position in tourists' awareness - Ninh Binh. Ninh Binh's overall tourist income in 2019 was just VND 3.7 billion, or 0.5% of all tourism revenue, demonstrating that Ninh Binh's capacity to draw spending is still below average when compared to the country as a whole.

There are several researches that have implied the relationship between destination image, tourism destination, satisfaction, and so on, but the studies about Ninh Binh tourism destination are quite modest. The findings have not emphasized the bonds between those factors, especially destination image. Therefore, segmenting tourist groups based upon their diverse reasons for visiting Ninh Binh is required to get around this constraint.

Based on the studies of relevant research, the authors found these following research gaps.

First, most of the research has pointed out the relationship between different factors such as EWOM, destination image, visiting intention, and so on. However, there are more factors that have not been mentioned. *Second*, researchers' consideration about the characteristics of tourist destinations has yet to be covered and it requires more studies to focus on these factors. *Third*, there is an existing limitation about the survey subjects and respondent's sample which the authors did not manage to expand, therefore the result can not cover the majority. Due to this, the authors can not engage in a better understanding of the tourists' behavior. *Fourth*, there is a lack of methods used as authors only rely on some specific methods. As a result, it does not provide enough information and a general image about the research subjects. *Finally*, the authors have not discovered any research which considers the relationship between destination image, customer satisfaction and E-WOM to tourist's behavior, especially for the Ninh Binh tourist destination.

From the analysis of research gaps in previous studies, as well as the context of tourism development in Ninh Binh tourist destination, authors come to realize that it is essential to conduct research to inspect the relationship between destination image, customer satisfaction and E-WOM toward tourist behavior, in this case, the Ninh Binh tourist destination. On that basis, the authors decided to engage in the following research on this topic.

Examining the factors related to destination image affect customer satisfaction and EWOM toward tourism. Especially, the relationship between destination image, customer satisfaction and electronic word of mouth of tourists - Case study of tourist destination Ninh Binh.

Emphasizing the importance of destination image, customer satisfaction and electronic word of mouth toward the tourism industry, especially tourism destination Ninh Binh, in order to enhance local tourist destination satisfaction, EWOM in the area.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Destination Image

Tourist destination is a perception made by tourists through various means of information. According to Gunn Clare and Turgut Var (2002), destination image is a collection of beliefs, impressive ideas about the destination that people have. Crompton (1979) shares the same point of view. Each location has a distinct character, although certain destinations may have a more attractive or striking image than others. Any place hoping to attract tourists wants

to project a positive image in their minds. Bigne et al. (2001) have the most condensed concept of destination image when claiming that destination image is tourists' subjective understanding of the reality of the tourist destination.

Destination image shows a combination of beliefs, ideas and impressions that a person acknowledges about one destination (Crompton, 1979; Gartner & Hunt, 1987; Cai; 2003). In another approach, It is argued that the destination image can be affected by 3 factors: organic image, induced image and modified - induced image. Crompton (1979) stated that the scenery, traffic and climate of a location play an important role in the destination image

In another research, it is concluded that perceived value, customer happiness, and client loyalty are influenced by image. A company's capacity to sustain its market position in the competitive industry is seen as critically dependent on its ability to convey a positive image (Eskildsen et al., 2004).

On the basis of literature review, there are many studies on tourism focusing only on the cognitive aspect of destination image (Chon et al., 1991; Court & Lupton, 1997; Echtner & Ritchie, 1993; Fakeye & Crompton, 1991; Gartner & Shen, 1992; MacKay & Fesenmaier, 1997), while equally important affective image has been omitted.

However, an encouraging trend is that recent tourism literature acknowledges the common existence of both components (cognitive and affective) in the mind of a typical tourist (Castro et al., 2007). At the same time, it is suggested that the coexistence of both components can more accurately explain the destination image (Kim & Yoon, 2003; Martín & del Bosque, 2008; Zeng, Chiu, Lee, Kang, & Park, 2015). In addition, there is consensus among researchers that the cognitive-image component is antecedent of affective image (Baloglu, 2000; Baloglu & McCleary, 1999; Gartner, 1994). Therefore, in this study, the author approaches a destination image including 02 components: (1) Cognitive Image and (2) Affective Image.

(1) Cognitive Image

It Refers to an individual's knowledge and beliefs about a destination. From the perception point of view, the tourist destination image is evaluated on a set of attributes corresponding to the resources or attractions that the destination has to use. Natural landscapes, enjoyable activities, and memorable experiences are frequently these enticing aspects that draw tourists. According to Alhemoud and Armstrong (1996), these elements are what provide the traction or appeal required for convincing someone to travel to a certain location.

The study group discovered that the definitions of cognitive image put out by the authors are relatively comparable and are related to beliefs or information about the evaluation of a destination's qualities (Stepchenkova & Mills, 2010; Ryan & Ninov, 2011) or represent an assessment of the destination's perceived attributes (Papadimitriou et al., 2018).

(2) Affective Image

Studies mentioned about the individual's feelings towards the tourist destination (Baloglu & Brinberg, 1997; Kim & Yoon, 2003). According to the Stepchenkova and Mills (2010),

affective image is related to the values that individuals attach to the destination based on travel motivation. In most definitions, an affective image is connected to tourists' perceptions of the place (Yang et al., 2009; Ryan & Ninov, 2011; Kim et al., 2019).

2.2 Tourist Satisfaction

Tourist satisfaction refers to the pleasant emotions that visitors have when visiting a place. According to Jang and Feng (2007); Kozak (2001), the authors argue that tourist satisfaction has identified satisfaction as an antecedent of revisiting.

Chi and Qu (2008) also explain that “customer satisfaction has always been the prior engagement and goal for any businesses since it is assumed that satisfied customers will eventually purchase more”. In the case of tourist satisfaction, satisfied customers would be inclined to revisit that destination and willing to pay more.

The main focus of evaluating satisfaction is the increase in itself when customers compare their sensations and experience throughout the journey to their initial expectations with the “disconfirmation theory” (Yuksel, 2002; Prayang, 2008).

Coban (2012) pointed out that a customer is satisfied when they are offered higher service performance than the expected service. However, if the perceived service performance is lower than the expectations, it is considered as discontentedness of the customers' experience. The research team concluded that "destination's affective image can be viewed as a person's emotional state about a particular tourist destination and associated with travel motivation". Thereby, the definitions of cognitive image proposed by the authors are quite similar and refer to beliefs or knowledge about the evaluation of a destination's attributes or reflect an assessment of the destination's perceived attributes.

2.3 E-Word of Mouth (EWOM)

According to Baloglu and McCleary's (1999) study, WOM is a source of information that can influence how a destination is formed. Word-of-mouth communication (WOM) has long been regarded as a very important topic for researchers and practitioners in the field of marketing (Gruen et al., 2006). According to some research (Gupta & Harris, 2010), WOM has a significant and verifiable impact on customer behavior.

There is a transition from the traditional word-of-mouth (WOM) into electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) in order to adapt with the changes of modern society where the interaction between individuals are converted online.

According to Jeong and Jang (2011), the main difference between WOM and eWOM is in the media used; WOM is often face-to-face, eWOM is online. With the advancement of technology, the physical place in which this type of communication takes place has changed from face-to-face to cyberspace. The internet has developed into a tool or method for customers to engage in electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) communication (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004).

In the past, a lot of customers would turn to travel agencies for information as they offered thorough descriptions of the trip and easier access to service providers (Heung, 2003). However, nowadays, the majority of visitors increasingly utilize media as a source of information for preparing and organizing a trip due to technical advancements, particularly the widespread use of the internet (Liang et al., 2013).

Hypothesis development

The relationship between cognitive image and satisfaction has been considered in previous studies, some typical studies (Bigné et al., 2001b; Chi & Qu, 2008; Prayag, 2009a) established a positive link between destination image and destination satisfaction. Further reinforcing this relationship, the studies of Banki et al (2014), Loi et al (2017), Kim (2018), and Stylidis et al (2021) have shown that cognitive images have a significant positive impact on tourist satisfaction. On that basis, research hypothesis H2 is proposed:

H1: Cognitive image has a positive impact on tourist satisfaction

Besides, the relationship between affective image and tourist satisfaction has also been considered in previous studies. For example, in the study of O'Leary and Deegan (2005), Lobato et al. (2006), Loureiro and Gonzalez (2008), affective image is an important antecedent that has a significant influence on tourist satisfaction. To emphasize this relationship, in the study of Banki et al (2014), Stylidis et al (2021) showed that emotional images have a positive influence on visitor satisfaction. Therefore, research hypothesis H3 is proposed:

H2: Affective image has a positive impact on tourist satisfaction.

Research on the relationship between destination image and electronic word-of-mouth of tourists has been reviewed previously in studies on the tourism sector, whereby destination image positively influenced on the word-of-mouth of tourists (Bigné et al., 2001; Fakeye & Crompton, 1991; Lee et al., 2005). Several previous studies have also analyzed that cognitive image has a direct influence on electronic word-of-mouth (Prayogo & Kusumawardhani, 2016; Kanwel et al., 2019). Therefore, research hypothesis H3 is proposed:

H3: Cognitive image has a positive impact on tourists' e- word-of-mouth.

Additionally, the study of Uslu and Karabulut (2018) showed that the affective image has a positive impact on electronic word-of-mouth or destination attributes. On that basis, research hypothesis H4 is proposed:

H4: Affective image has a positive impact on tourists' e-word-of-mouth.

In the context of tourism research, the relationship between visitor satisfaction and electronic word of mouth has also been considered in some previous studies, such as in the study of Jeong and Jang (2011) have pointed out: customers have a positive electronic word of mouth motive due to a satisfied experience. Besides, tourist satisfaction about the destination has a positive impact on electronic word of mouth based on social media platforms (Teng & Wu, 2019; Ahn, Choi & Joung 2020); satisfaction by using WebChat will have a positive impact on electronic word of mouth engagement (Pang, 2021); Satisfaction was also clearly identified as a determinant of consumer electronic word of mouth (Chen et al., 2020).

H5: Tourist satisfaction has a positive impact on electronic word of mouth.

Based on the above theories, the authors propose a framework to analyze the relationship between destination image (include: cognitive image, affective image), tourist satisfaction, E-Word of Mouth as follows:

Figure 1. Analytical framework

Source: Authors

4. DATA COLLECTION

According to Hair et al. (2011) the number of suitable variables in the analysis must be at least 50, preferably 100, with an observed/measurement ratio of 5:1, which means the measurement variable requires a minimum of 5 observations. That means the minimum required number of observations is $n = 5k$. In this research, the total number of observed variables is 16, so the minimum number of samples is 80. The study applied the random sampling method of combined stratification according to the sampling criteria including gender, age, income, marital status, and the average number of trips per year to collect data. The survey subjects are tourists who visited Ninh Binh. The data are collected by answering a questionnaire on the Google Forms for those who have experienced travel. The survey was conducted from March 2023 to May 2023. The content of the survey includes personal information of the survey respondents and questions related to the relationship between destination image, satisfaction, and Electronic word of mouth of tourists in Ninh Binh province.

Based on reviewing the literature to model the analytical framework, a questionnaire was built and divided into 3 sections: The first was designed to measure the destination image of Ninh Binh. This part comprises 8 statements in total, measuring 2 dimensions of the destination image, including the cognitive image (5 items); affective image (3 items). The second section assesses the satisfaction of tourist levels includes 4 items. Simultaneously, measuring the tourist's electronic word-of-mouth level, including 4 items. The last section consists of questions relating to demographic information about respondents such as age,

gender, income, marital status, and frequency of travel. The first two sections are measured using a 5-point Likert rating scale which corresponds to 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = somewhat disagree, 3 = neither agree nor disagree, and 4 = somewhat agree, 5 = strongly agree.

This questionnaire was in Vietnamese and was used to survey domestic tourists who have been to Ninh Binh so that they could give more meaningful responses. 236 potential tourists were approached and 201 feedbacks were obtained indicating a response rate of 85%. All respondents are Vietnamese. The majority of respondents are between the ages of 25 and 35, with 59.4% female, 40.6% male. Average monthly income is from 10 million to 25 million. 45.5 percent are married.

5. MEASURABLE TEST

The data are collected by answering a questionnaire on the Google forms for those who have experienced travel to Ninh Binh. The survey was conducted from March 2023 to May 2023. The content of the survey includes personal information of the survey respondents, and questions related to the relationship between destination image, Tourist Satisfaction and E-Word of Mouth of Tourist traveled to Ninh Binh province.

Based on the theoretical overview and related previous studies, the research is conducted to analyze the impact of 2 destination image factors (Cognitive Image & Affective Image) on E-Word of Mouth of Tourist through intermediate variable is Tourist Satisfaction.

In order to analyze the data, first of all, we used exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to discover the checking structure of scale. More specifically, in this stage, one item was removed after reviewing the EFA results and then, confirmatory factor analysis is used (CFA) to test its construct validity within the sample. In addition, structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to test the proposed measurement model. The SEM model has proven efficient in many studies regarding the field of marketing management (Hair et al., 2012).

6. DATA ANALYSIS

Data collected are firstly tested to ensure reliability through Cronbach's Alpha value with the purpose of checking the internal consistency. In this study, scales which have a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient greater than or equal to 0.6 will be accepted. Besides, variables which have greater than 0.3 item-total correlations will be accepted; the others which have smaller than 0.3 item-total correlations will be eliminated from the analysis data. The results of this study indicated that all Cronbach's Alpha values of the 4 dimensions ranged from 0,782 - 0.839

Then, a validity test is conducted to measure whether the item or scale truly measures what it is supposed to measure and nothing else. In this study, a scale factor analysis is conducted for Destination Image scales namely Cognitive Image (COG), Affective Image (AFF) , and Tourist Satisfaction (SAT), E-Word of Mouth (EWM) scales. The results reveal that the questionnaire is a valid measure of the effects of destination image on the Tourist Satisfaction and E-Word of Mouth activities of tourists in Ninh Binh destinations because the items which are arranged within a scale in the questionnaire are proven under the same factors. The factor analysis results for all investigated components are presented in the following table:

Table 1: Contents of questionnaire survey

Dimension	Items	Coding	Source
Cognitive Image	Ninh Binh destination has many cultural and historical landscapes	COG1	Papadimitriou et al (2018), Loi et al (2017),
	Variety and high-quality accommodation	COG2	
	The weather in this destination is good	COG3	
	Ninh Binh destination has many traditional and unique dishes	COG4	
	Ninh Binh destination has many fun and entertainment activities	COG5	
Affective Image	Discomfort - Comfort	AFF1	Stylidis et al (2021), Kim et al (2019)
	Active - Excited	AFF2	
	Inhibition - Relaxation	AFF3	
Tourist Satisfaction	I am really satisfied with this destination	SAT1	(Chen et al., 2020).
	So glad I decided to visit this tourist attraction	SAT2	
	The visit to this tourist site exceeded my expectations	SAT3	
	Traveling to this place is an interesting experience	SAT4	
E-Word Mouth	of I am willing to let other Internet users know that I am a visitor to this destination	EWO1	(Liang et al., 2013), (Pang, 2021)
	I am willing to actively discuss this destination with others on the Internet	EWO2	
	If I had a similar experience, I would say good things about this destination on the Internet	EWO3	
	I am happy to provide a lot of information online about this destination to others on the Internet	EWO4	

Source: Authors.

The convergent and discriminant validity of all instruments is calculated by using AMOS 22.0. To establish convergent validity, we use AVE or cross loadings. Convergent validity is established if the values of AVE are above 0.5 (Hair et al., 2010). From this table we can clearly see that the values of AVE for all items are 0.5 or greater than 0.5. So for the research's structure, convergent validity is established.

Table 2: Discriminant validity (Fornell-Larcker criterion)

	Min	Max	Mean	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	COG	SAT	EWO	AFF
COG	2.80	5.00	4.1473	0,84	0,513	0,231	0,846	0,716			
SAT	2.00	5.00	4.0265	0,834	0,556	0,487	0,834	451	0,746		
EWO	2.50	5.00	4.2363	0,816	0,527	0,487	0,821	481	698	0,726	
AFF	2.00	5.00	4.0265	0,783	0,546	0,282	0,783	386	531	475	0,739

Source: Data analysis results

For analysis of convergent validity, the authors examine the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The values of AVE should be greater than 0.50, which means a 50% or more variance can be accounted for by these indicators (Hair et al., 2011). In this research, AVE for all latent variables is greater than 0.50.

Discriminant validity shows that one construct differs from the other construct. There are two approaches to find out the discriminant validity. One is Fornell and Larcker (1981) explaining AVE should be greater than the variance between the construct and other constructs. The second approach is that no item loading should be greater on the other construct than the construct it intends to measure (Hair et al., 2011). In other words, each construct should load higher on its assigned construct than the other constructs (Table 2). After establishing the reliability and validity of the present study through a measurement model, a structural model is calculated to find out the significance of the relationship between destination image, Tourist Satisfaction and E-Word of Mouth activities of tourists

Hypothesis testing

Results of SEM analysis confirmed that the measurement structure of the theoretical framework had an acceptable fit for the data ($\chi^2/df = 1.680$, $p < .001$, RMSEA = .058; CFI = .949; TLI = .937). This figure organizes the results of confirmatory factor analysis, which revealed that the final measurement model fit relatively well.

Figure 2: Relationship between structures in the model.

Source: Data analysis results

The estimated results of the main parameters in the research model (Table 2) show that the relationships are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The results show that the hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H5 about the relationship between the concepts proposed in the research model (H4) are accepted with statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). The rest of the hypotheses were rejected ($p > 0.05$).

Table 3: Direct relationship results

Hypothesis	Relationship	Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Result
H1	Cognitive Image ---> Tourist Satisfaction	0,396	0,089	4,462	0,000	Accept
H2	Affective Image ---> Tourist Satisfaction	0,282	0,083	3,381	0,000	Accept
H3	Cognitive Image ---> E-Word of Mouth	0,15	0,065	2,3	0,021	Accept
H4	Affective Image ---> E-Word of Mouth	0,082	0,07	1,175	0,24	Reject
H5	Tourist Satisfaction ---> E-Word of Mouth	0,455	0,089	5,125	0,000	Accept

Source: Data analysis results

When we move towards mediation and take tourist satisfaction as processes or mediator variables, then the impact of destination image (cognitive image & affective image) on E-Word of Mouth activities of tourists in Ninh Binh destinations. It is statistically significant and positive. It means that through tourist satisfaction, the E-Word of Mouth activities of tourists can also be enhanced. So we can say that partially tourist satisfaction mediates the relationship between destination image and E-Word of Mouth. The results of indirect effects are shown in Table 4

Table 4: Indirect relationship results

Indirect Path	Standardized Estimate	Lower	Upper	P-Value	Result
Affective Image ---> Tourist Satisfaction ---> E-Word of Mouth	0.233	0,108	0,288	0,001	Accept
Cognitive Image ---> Tourist Satisfaction ---> E-Word of Mouth	0.161	0,054	0,224	0,006	Accept

Source: Data analysis results

7. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

As the research results, some points are highlighted in the study: the impact of destination image (cognitive image & affective image) on E-Word of Mouth activities of tourists in Ninh Binh destinations through tourist satisfaction are as follows:

(1) Cognitive image —> Tourist satisfaction

Cognitive image has a direct and positive impact on Tourist satisfaction. This result is in agreement with previous studies. Specifically, destination image (the appropriate price of the destination) has a direct influence on visitor satisfaction (Park & Njite, 2010); Destination image has a positive and direct influence on visitor satisfaction (Banki et al., 2014). This suggests managers invest heavily in improving the various aspects which make up the destination perception image as this contributes to tourist satisfaction while at the same time sustainable development of all tourist destinations.

(2) Cognitive image —> E-Word of Mouth

Cognitive image has a direct and positive impact on the E-Word of Mouth. This result is

IN agreement with previous studies. For example, Uslu & Karabulut (2018) showed that an increased perceived value of a destination will increase the electronic word of mouth intention of the destination among tourists; or destination image has a direct and positive influence on electronic word of mouth (Pandey & Sahu, 2020). The above research results imply that when tourists have a positive perception of destination attributes, this increases the tourist's electronic word of mouth about the destination. The role of electronic word of mouth is becoming increasingly important as customers seek online reviews to get information about products and services. EWO was also found to have a significant impact on a customer's future purchase intention.

(3) Affective image → Tourist satisfaction

Affective image has a direct and positive impact on Tourist satisfaction. This result is in agreement with previous studies. According to Kanwel et al (2019), affective images have a direct and positive influence on tourist satisfaction. From the above research results, this relationship is understood that when tourists have positive feelings towards the destination, it will increase the visitor's satisfaction with the destination.

(4) Affective image → E-Word of Mouth

Affective image has no direct impact on electronic word of mouth. The results of this study are inconsistent with a few previous studies where the results of previous studies have shown that destination image has a positive and direct influence on electronic word of mouth (Prayogo & Kusuma Wardhani, 2016; Kanwel et al., 2019; Pandey & Sahu, 2020). The reason for this difference is because the studies of Prayogo and Kusuma Wardhani (2016); Kanwel et al (2019); Pandey and Sahu (2020) approach to destination image is not clearly expressed as cognitive image and affective image, but it was measured through many components of cognitive image aspect. Therefore, leading to the difference in results compared to the author's study. This finding also implies that affective images alone cannot directly drive tourists' electronic word-of-mouth intentions.

(5) Tourist satisfaction → E-Word of Mouth

Tourist satisfaction has a direct and positive impact on electronic word of mouth. This result is in agreement with previous studies. Research by Ahn et al (2020) has shown that tourist satisfaction with their festival experience has a positive impact on electronic word of mouth goodwill. The results of this study indicate that the need to enhance tourist satisfaction about the destination will promote electronic word of mouth behavior of visitors.

(6) Destination image → Tourist satisfaction → E-Word of Mouth

Destination image has a positive impact on tourists' e E-Word of Mouth through their satisfaction with the destination. This is a new discovery of the research. This result reinforces the relationship of Cognitive image and E-Word of Mouth when it is still statistically significant since the intermediate variable is tourist satisfaction. Besides, this result also proves that Affective image can positively affect the E-Word of Mouth through tourist satisfaction. From that, it is implied that Tourist satisfaction has an important role in the theoretical model, helping to strengthen and promote relationships.

8. CONCLUSIONS

Research towards building sustainable tourism development strategies in Ninh Binh province through improving the destination image in customers' mind, helps to promote their satisfaction and electronic word of mouth behavior. The study was carried out on the basis of research, synthesizing the theoretical basis and proposing a framework for analyzing score destination images, satisfaction and electronic word of mouth. From there, the study provides appropriate solutions and implications for sustainable tourism development in Ninh Binh province from the point of view of destination image, satisfaction and electronic word of mouth.

The study is a useful reference for stakeholders in the development of Ninh Binh tourism. Currently, the study deals with limitations in terms of time, resources and data availability. However, the study recommends some measures related to future research to inherit and develop issues related to brand image, visitor satisfaction and electronic word of mouth behavior.

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HOW DO FRONTLINE EMPLOYEES ADAPT TO DIGITAL HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT? TESTING A NEW SELF-REGULATED MECHANISM

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Abstract

The study effectively validates the process by which service staff can cultivate and improve their self-regulated adaptive mechanism in response to evolving work environments and settings resulting from their organization's implementation of digitalized human resource management. This is achieved through the application of individual-level ambidexterity, utilizing a construction model of adaptation approach. In the context of evolving work environments influenced by digital human resource management (eHRM), it is our contention that service personnel should engage their adaptive mechanisms by leveraging a particular personality trait, namely a proactive personality. This approach enables them to achieve a heightened state of ambidextrous behaviour, effectively managing the delicate balance between utilizing their current work resources and actively pursuing new initiatives. By doing so, service professionals can attain a superior level of proactive performance, as anticipated by service-oriented organizations. We conducted a survey among 350 frontline bank staff members across Vietnam's three regions, resulting in 202 valid responses. These responses were then used to evaluate our assumptions. The findings and recommendations of this study have practical implications for management training programs aimed at service representatives. Specifically, these insights can be applied to enhance their proactive performance in the context of the digital age.

Keywords: *Digital human resource management, employee ambidexterity, uncertainty adaptability, service performance, proactive personality, Vietnam*

1. INTRODUCTION

The advent of Industry 4.0 has resulted in the digitization and integration of data throughout the supply chain, leading to a range of advantages. These include the ability to offer digital products and services, effective management of specialized physical and virtual assets, streamlining and standardization of business processes, establishment of strategic partnerships, and enhancement of customer service (Akbari & Hopkins, 2022; Brahma et al., 2021). In this setting, service companies anticipate from their management the same efficiency gains in service process outputs as they have come to expect from the digital world (Quang & Hara, 2019). Like other organizational functions, HRM is becoming digitized (Ramachandran et al., 2023). Digital HRM (or e-HRM) essentially means carrying out HRM tasks through digital

technology applications (Theres & Strohmeier, 2023). Failure to adapt to the changes brought on by the digitalization of business activities is a major barrier to the digitalization of essential processes like human resource management (Shibata, 2022; Theres & Strohmeier, 2023). One of the biggest challenges facing modern service providers is recruiting and retaining talented workers who can adapt to the ever-evolving, increasingly digital Industry 4.0 environment (Zembski & Ulewicz, 2022). Handling the people-oriented changes aforementioned entails competent personnel (Hautala-Kankaanpää, 2022; Ramachandran et al., 2023) that can be recruited and/or developed with proper human resource management (HRM).

Despite practitioners' concerns, there has been limited research exploring employees' adaptability mechanism, their personal adaptive attributes, and how these variables influence their attitudes and performance (Mom et al., 2015). We argued that *employee ambidexterity* – the balance state between flexibility and efficiency for output optimization (Raisch & Birkinshaw, 2008) – might play a significant role in boosting their adaptability in a changing context such as the new adoption of eHRM. Our research sheds light on the central role of employee ambidexterity in the overall adaptive process that results in improved service performance by explaining a self-regulated mechanism of service employees toward such shifting circumstances. Literature suggests that ambidextrous behaviour benefits both employee and company output (i.e., being flexible on the job and quickly coping with changes by taking advantage of their existing knowledge and remaining open to new ideas to optimize their work performance (Mom et al., 2009; Scutto et al., 2019). Still, much is unknown about the contributing factors and mechanism of individual-level ambidexterity.

To fill this gap, this research develops and tests a theoretical framework based on the Individual Adaptability (I-ADAPT) theory (Ployhart & Bliese, 2006), which draws from Savickas's (2013) Career Construction Model of Adaptation (CCMA) theory, in order to evaluate the self-regulated adjusting mechanism of frontline service staff in light of the novel changes arising from HRM digitalization. In our research context, we examined numerous banking firms that had undergone various degrees of HRM digitization, namely transactional, relational, and transformational levels (Samson & Agrawal, 2020). We argue that in such dynamic work environments, service workers need to activate their adaptation mechanism by capitalizing on a particular personality trait (i.e., proactive personality) to achieve a higher level of ambidextrous behaviour in juggling "utilizing their existing work resources" and "proactively seeking for new initiatives" to achieve the higher proactive performance expected by service firms. Based on the arguments and discussions, this study proposes the following two research questions (RQs):

- *RQ1: How does employee ambidexterity enhance proactive service performance in the current digital HRM context?*
- *RQ2: How does employee ambidexterity serve as a mediator in the relationship between proactive personality and proactive service performance?*

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews extant literature and presents the hypothesis development for this study. Sections 3 and 4 outline the research methodology and the analysis of the results. Finally, Section 5 discusses the findings and presents the conclusion with the theoretical and managerial implications, limitations, and future research directions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resource Management (HRM) is one of the most important business processes to be digitized (Akbari & Hopkins, 2022). This facilitates the real-time monitoring and management of all interconnected activities related to operations and supply chain management (Hautala-Kankaanpää, 2022; Ramachandran et al., 2023; Theres & Strohmeier, 2023). HRM is evolving into digital HRM (or e-HRM) by incorporating information technology (IT), electronic mobility (e-mobility), media, and analytics to improve performance (Ramachandran et al., 2023; Theres & Strohmeier, 2023). As Deniz (2020) confirmed, HRM will change in response to the demands of Industry 4.0. As an example, AI is being used more and more in the recruiting process, while Big Data is being used to assess employee performance and provide incentives that are more aligned with individual contributions. Organizations may choose to adopt e-HRM at varied depths based on the contents, stakeholders, and objectives they hope to achieve with their IT-enabled HRM plans, policies, and practices (Bondarouk & Ruël, 2009). Overall, digitalization contributes to HRM in three areas (Theres & Strohmeier, 2023):

- To begin, HRM digitalization focuses on the operational benefits (such as cost savings and productivity) of e-HRM, which facilitates administrative HRM duties such as e-recruitment, e-selection, e-training, e-development, e-learning, and e-compensation (Strohmeier, 2007; Theres & Strohmeier, 2023).
- The second area of e-HRM, called *relational e-HRM*, refers to the use of IT to improve communication, collaboration, interaction, and relations between stakeholders in HRM-related tasks (Bondarouk et al., 2017; Theres & Strohmeier, 2023). By providing remote access to HRM data and services, e-HRM empowers employees and managers to better manage HRM operations on their own, which in turn improves service quality, speeds up resolution times, helps keep the peace in the workplace, and boosts overall employee satisfaction with HRM (Bissola & Imperatori, 2014; Bondarouk et al., 2017; Reddick, 2009).
- The third aspect of e-HRM is *transformational capacity*, which encompasses strategic alignment and integration between HRM and IT for the purpose of producing value for employees, managers, and the business at large as well as its partners (Bondarouk et al., 2017; Reddick, 2009; Theres & Strohmeier, 2023). Some examples of transformational e-HRM include the use of smart technology in knowledge management and a change in emphasis toward more important business challenges (such as organizational development and human capital management) (Bissola & Imperatori, 2014; Reddick, 2009; Rogiers et al., 2020; Theres & Strohmeier, 2023).

In response to the dynamic environments in which businesses and their personnel operate, previous research has explored the value of ambidexterity. In such a setting, continuous adjustment is needed to strike the right balance between flexibility and efficiency, which will eventually result in maximized outputs (Raisch & Birkinshaw, 2008). Firms' and individuals' ability to effectively balance exploration- and exploitation-related activities are key to survival and suboptimal performance but may hinder entire organizational and

individual gains (March, 1991). Concerning employee ambidexterity, scholars have paid less attention to what constitutes ambidextrous behaviour of staff (Klonek et al., 2021; Kao & Chen, 2016). For instance, O'Reilly III and Tushman (2011) and Jasmand et al. (2012) examined the mechanism of managers' and staff's attempts to balance between exploration- and exploitation-oriented actions when they deal with seemingly conflicting goals at different organizational levels (e.g., staff trying to offer the best customer service level, maintaining cross-/up-selling efforts or completing customer requests quickly during service contact). This suggests that staff ambidexterity is critical to the long-term success of businesses. Therefore, businesses must discover ways to boost their employees' ambidexterity to remain competitive in the face of the unpredictable working circumstances brought about by the digitization of HRM.

Hypothesis development

The I-ADAPT framework (Ployhart & Bliese, 2006) suggests that people's unique combinations of knowledge, skill, ability, and other qualities, such as personality, shape their responses to unfamiliar circumstances. According to Neureiter and Traut-Mattausch (2017), an individual's "adaptive readiness" may be defined as "a set of stable characteristics that reflect the individual's flexibility or willingness to adapt." In this study, we focus on 'proactive personality' as a signal of adaptive readiness. Crant (2000) defines a person with a *proactive personality* as an individual who is resilient in the face of adversity and who actively seeks to improve their surroundings via their own efforts in a wide variety of contexts. Although proactive personality has been shown to be a predictor of adaptability (Lee et al., 2021; Ling et al., 2022), its involvement in employee ambidexterity has only been the subject of a small number of research (e.g., Zhao and Gao, 2014; Kao and Chen, 2016). Individuals that exhibit a proactive mentality are those who are willing to take charge in a wide variety of situations, despite the influence of external factors (Crant, 2000). Specifically, adaptable workers approach their job and adjust to the changing environment either proactively or reactively (Ployhart & Bliese, 2006). Employees that are proactive about the future of their workplace may be more eager to acquire new knowledge and abilities (i.e., explore - one ambidextrous behavior) to maintain productive workflow and meet performance targets (Wang et al., 2011). Workers who take the initiative to improve their workplace are more likely to do so (Sonntag, 2017). Overall, previous studies (e.g., Kao & Chen, 2016) have found that a proactive attitude positively affects employee ambidexterity. Therefore, we hypothesize:

H₁: Service staff with a higher degree of proactive personality (PP) are more likely to have a higher level of employee ambidexterity (EA)

Next, Good and Michel (2013) found a positive effect of individual ambidexterity on adaptive task performance over and above general mental ability. In addition, employees with greater degrees of adaptability likely to attain favorable career outcomes and person-environment fit by implementing certain adapting behaviors, including proactive skill improvement (Pajic et al., 2018) and, more specifically - employee ambidexterity. Consistent with the findings of Bledow et al. (2009), ambidextrous service staff are characterized by cognitive and behavioral complexity and can dynamically adapt their tactics (such as being directive or providing autonomy) in response to contextual changes brought about by HRM

digitalization to achieve the required service performance. *Proactive service performance* (PSP), which Jang et al. (2020) have defined as "going above and beyond what is required of an employee in terms of their job description and that the employee undertakes on their own initiative and maintains over time" is a key outcome we chose to investigate in this study. Since frontline personnel in customer service must go above and beyond to delight consumers, the increasing complexity of HRM digitalization and the ever-evolving expectations of customers are important factors in the choice to focus on PSP.

Albeit a comprehensive understanding of individual ambidexterity is underdeveloped (Kao & Chen, 2016), the positive effects of ambidexterity on employee performance have been confirmed by a small number of empirical studies. For example, Jasmand et al. (2012) defined ambidextrous behavior as the ability to perform seemingly opposite tasks in the pursuit of competing service and sales objectives. Concerning the ambidexterity-performance relationship at the individual level, we presume that a higher level of ambidexterity will lead to better service performance, and so the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₂: Service staff with a higher level of employee ambidexterity (EA) positively leads to better proactive service performance (PSP).

Furthermore, we believe that ambidexterity among employees is a crucial cognitive response to investigate in the context of change-related coping behaviors in the face of moderate to severe stress and chaos at work as a result of HRM digitization. To our knowledge, there has been little research done on ambidexterity in the context of adaptation at the individual level (Uy et al., 2015). Career Construction Model of Adaptation (CCMA) theory (Savickas, 2013) suggests that traits indicative of an openness to change (i.e., adaptive readiness; "proactive personality"); and, in turn, that these traits have a positive impact on adaptive responses (i.e., one's actions and beliefs in response to new circumstances; "ambidexterity"); are important in achieving the desired result (i.e., PSP). Following this logic, we propose the following hypothesis:

H₃: Employee ambidexterity mediates the relationship between proactive personality and proactive service performance (PSP).

3. METHODOLOGY

To address the study questions at hand and build on previous work in the field of organizational research, we adopted a positivist methodology and a quantitative research strategy. We focus on the banking industry since we believe it to be a fitting environment for a service job like frontline banking that demands extensive contact with the public. There have been a number of macro- and micro-level events, most notably the COVID-19 epidemic and the present global recession, during the past three years that have greatly boosted financial organizations' need to minimize labor expenses in order to maintain profitability (Meyer et al., 2022), hence putting more pressure on staff to uphold a high service performance level while dealing with all the changes to remain employed. In this research, we control age (measured in years) and management level, as both could have an influence on proactive job behaviour (Janssen, 2000), as well as on individual adaptability and adaptation (Rudolph & Zacher, 2016).

The dataset was collected between August 2022 and October 2022 from 202 out of 350 frontline banking employees from different service branches and professional ranks in all three regions of Vietnam (Northern, Central, and Southern). This decision was made due to the fact that service workers need to rely heavily on their flexibility in order to deal with the stresses of continually engaging and serving clients, whose demands are both complicated and very variable. The YellowPages bank database was used as the basis for the sampling. vnn.vn and its administration were randomly contacted. After that, we distributed the surveys to the managers and requested them to distribute them to their teams. Respondents were given the option of receiving a VND 50,000 mobile top-up voucher or making a VND 50,000 gift to the Mountainous Underprivileged Students Fund (MUSF) charity for each form they voluntarily filled out. Descriptive profilings of the studied sample are given as follows:

Table 1. Profiling of respondents

Controls		Frequency	Percentage %
Gender		202	100%
	Male	59	29.2
	Female	143	70.8
Age group		202	100%
	18-25	39	19.3
	26-40	149	73.8
	Over 40	14	6.9
Company type		202	100%
	Private banks	105	51.9
	State-owned banks	46	22.8
	Foreign banks	40	19.8
	Others	11	5.5

The items used to measure critical variables in the research were adapted from past empirical studies with a scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The constructs were operationalized as follows:

- *Proactive personality (PP)* was assessed using the shortened version of PPS proposed by [Claes et al. \(2005\)](#) as a single factor.
- *Employee ambidexterity (EA)*. The explorative and exploitative work-related activities of employees were measured using the scale developed by [Kobarg et al. \(2017\)](#).
- *Proactive service performance (PSP)* refers to the work outcomes by service staff to fulfil service goals of improving both efficiency and quality of required tasks. We adapted the scale originally developed by [Rank et al. \(2007\)](#).

Data screening and cleaning were done to make the data ready for analysis. After data collection, we examined the whole dataset for missing values and outliers. Partial least squares structural equation model (PLS-SEM) was used to test the proposed relationships, following [Ringle et al. \(2015\)](#)'s guidelines. PLS-SEM is a well-established method to test and validate structural models for several reasons. **We also conducted confirmatory factor analysis**

(CFA) in PLS-SEM to evaluate the quality of our measurement model. In line with the procedure suggested by Hair et al. (2020), the significance of loadings and the convergent and discriminant validity of the constructs were assessed. All reliability tests were qualified as follows:

Table 2. Summary of Reliability and Discriminant validity testing

	PP	EA	PSP
PP	0.707		
EA	0.373	0.711	
PSP	0.327	0.417	0.816

Notes:

- Proactive personality (PP): Average Variance Extracted = 0.742, Composite Reliability = 0.868, Cronbach’s alpha = 0.812.
- Employee Ambidexterity (EA): Average Variance Extracted = 0.609, Composite Reliability = 0.841, Cronbach’s alpha = 0.811,
- Proactive Service Performance (PSP): Average Variance Extracted = 0.771, Composite Reliability = 0.945, Cronbach’s alpha = 0.843.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The structural part of our PLS-SEM demonstrated that service staff with a proactive personality tend to possess high EA and that this result is statistically significant, giving support to H1. Next, our model showed that service employees with higher EA are then associated with more proactive service performance and this positive relationship is statistically significant, substantiating H2. As can be inferred from Table 1, EA mediates the relationship between proactive personality and proactive service performance in that the indirect effect (see H3 estimates in Table 1) is statistically significant, proving H3.

Table 2. Hypothesis test results (based on 5000-replication bootstraps)

Hypothesis	Relationship	Estimate	Result
H1	Proactive personality -> Employee ambidexterity	0.696***	Supported
H2	Employee ambidexterity -> Proactive service performance	0.801***	Supported
H3	Proactive personality -> Employee ambidexterity -> Employee ambidexterity	0.447***	Supported

In order to attain proactive service performance, HRM digitization has led to a number of changes in the workplace, and this study intends to examine the direct predictive influence of proactive personality on ambidextrous behavior among service professionals. Our statistical findings significantly explained 60.8% of the variation in the model (R2=0.608). With the innovative underlying self-regulated mechanism connecting them all via the lens of adaptability, this study confirmed all of its assumptions and adds to the existing body of work on both staff ambidexterity and proactive service performance. Also, this study’s findings are consistent with those confirmed by past studies such as Alghamdi (2018), Kao and Chen

(2016), Rank et al. (2007), and Zhao and Gao (2014). Apparently, frontline service employees with proactive personalities will be in a better position to acquire ambidexterity, making it simpler for them to satisfy customers.

Lastly, the finding of EA is an empirically tested mediator between proactive personality and proactive service performance shed new light on the topic. Although studies have shown a correlation between proactive traits and PSP in the workplace (Zhao & Gao, 2014; Kao & Chen, 2016), to the best of our knowledge, no research has investigated the mechanisms at play here in terms of EA. The CCMA model by Savickas (2013) states that one's adaptability response (the cognitive act to acquire adaptation) is influenced by one's positive personality (i.e., adaptive readiness – willingness to adapt). As PP is considered a personal trait that must be 'nudged' to express actively to get the desired level of PSP, it makes sense to investigate the function of EA as a mediator between proactive personality and PSP.

5. IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSION

Theoretically, this research should provide a number of important contributions to the existing body of work. To begin, the research accomplishes its primary goal of explaining how service staff can cultivate and improve their self-regulated adaptive mechanism in order to deal with shifting work environments and settings that result from the organization's efforts to digitalize HRM by focusing on ambidexterity at the individual level. To better understand how working individuals adapt to cope with changes beyond the conventional mechanisms not based on control enforced by top management in today's tough business environment, our results aim to respond to the requests from many researchers (Tsui & Ashford, 1994; Contreras et al., 2020). Next, ambidexterity - the synchronized quest of exploration and exploitation, is allowed at the individual level of analysis in this study. As de Ruyter et al. (2020) found that the majority of studies have used a top-down approach when evaluating the effect of the organizational context on ambidexterity and that more studies are required to examine how lower-level factors like individual characteristics and behaviours may cause ambidexterity at the workgroup, business unit, and firm levels. Also, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to incorporate several theories of I-ADAPT and CCMA into the study of employee ambidexterity to shed light on the self-regulated adaptive mechanism that enables ambidextrous workers to achieve high levels of performance.

For practical purposes, the current findings may contribute to settling the ongoing dispute over the value of personality and flexibility in employee selection (Woods et al., 2020), particularly in the context of Industry 4.0. Better use of personality tests in the recruiting process might result from an appreciation of the complicated relationship between personality, flexibility, and performance in service employment. It's possible that, when hiring employees, it's not best practice to choose applicants in order of aptitude, as is common when utilizing ability tests, but rather to select the ones who "fit." In addition, the results of the study highlight the relevance of ambidexterity and staff adaptation procedures in times of uncertainty. Especially when digitization spreads, employees may be the impetus for or the barrier to change depending on the context. Employees that can adapt easily to new situations and learn quickly are often the most successful in fast-paced, ever-evolving workplaces. Human resource managers should think about how they can provide training that helps workers

feel more confident in their abilities to learn new skills and adjust to changing circumstances. Positive results are more likely when managers make sure the integration is a good fit for their employees' personalities rather than imposing it from on high. By giving workers a say in company decisions and allowing them more leeway in their day-to-day work, service industries may help staff feel more empowered and secure in their roles. In turn, this motivates specialists to take the initiative in resolving service issues by drawing on their vast store of knowledge and experience. Smart HR technology like mobile apps, design thinking, system analytics, and mobile platforms are proposed for service firms to take a more proactive approach, digital elements are integrated into work processes and routine manual work is changed into digital work (for better control and adding challenges), and reward and compensation, performance management, training and development, etc. are all digitized (for higher motivation) (Halid et al., 2020).

Before drawing any conclusions from this study, it is important to keep in mind a few limitations. The study's primary shortcoming is that it did not examine how various external factors could influence service workers' readiness to adopt HRM digitalization. Recent studies have shown the importance of factors including the specifics of their workplaces and the characteristics of their broader contexts (i.e. cultural, social, economic, technical) (Dolan et al., 2022). Future study should take into account a broader range of human characteristics, environmental variables, and their interplay in order to present a more nuanced picture of adaptation in a new work context. For instance, in Asian cultures where collectivism and power distance are prevalent, future research might investigate how the support (or lack thereof) from colleagues, union members, and/or managers/leaders affects the adaptation of frontline service personnel to the setting of digital HRM. Finally, concerns regarding social desirability bias are not addressed by the fact that the study relied on self-reporting. Including team member and supervisor assessments of PSP with customer data might help researchers gain a more precise assessment of actual staff performance in future studies. More research may be needed to determine exactly how EA affects PSP, but doing so will be well worth the effort.

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How do celebrity credibility and over-endorsement affect online celebrity brand equity on TikTok and followers' booking intention?

CÁC NHÂN TỐ ẢNH HƯỞNG ĐẾN HÀNH VI TIÊU DÙNG THUỐC LÁ Ở VIỆT NAM

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Tóm tắt

Hiện nay, số lượng thuốc lá được tiêu thụ mỗi năm tại các quốc gia nói chung và Việt Nam nói riêng đang ngày càng tăng, gây ra những vấn đề nghiêm trọng tác động đến người tiêu dùng. Chính vì điều này, bài viết đã thực hiện nhằm nghiên cứu và phát triển mô hình dựa trên các yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá bao gồm GDP bình quân đầu người, dân số, lạm phát, thuế suất tiêu thụ đặc biệt (TTĐB), giá sản phẩm và giới tính. Kết quả phân tích cho thấy, thuế suất TTĐB và giá sản phẩm có khả năng kiểm soát hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá. Từ đó, bài viết đưa ra những khuyến nghị nhằm kiểm soát hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá của người dân tại Việt Nam góp phần bảo vệ sức khỏe cộng đồng.

Từ khóa: thuế suất tiêu thụ đặc biệt (TTĐB), tiêu thụ thuốc lá, Việt Nam, hành vi, khuyến nghị

FACTORS AFFECTING TOBACCO CONSUMPTION BEHAVIOR IN VIETNAM

Abstract

Currently, the number of cigarettes consumed each year in countries in general and Vietnam, in particular, is increasing day by day, causing serious problems affecting consumers and the state such as diseases, and the burden of money medical and living expenses. With the goal of clarifying the factors affecting tobacco consumption behavior, the authors researched and built a model based on factors affecting consumption behavior such as GDP per capita, population, inflation, excise tax rate, product price, and gender. In addition, after analyzing the research model and studying related documents, the authors found that the excise tax rate and product selling price have the ability to control tobacco consumption behavior. Therefore, this study will provide important recommendations to control the tobacco consumption behavior of people in Vietnam and contribute to protecting public health.

Keywords: excise tax rates, tobacco consumption, Vietnam, behavior, recommendations.

1. ĐẶT VẤN ĐỀ

Hút thuốc lá là nguyên nhân hàng đầu gây tử vong trên thế giới (WHO, 2022). Trên thực tế, một trong những mối nguy hiểm nghiêm trọng nhất đối với sức khỏe toàn cầu là đại dịch

thuốc lá, giết chết hơn 8 triệu người mỗi năm, trong số đó có 1,2 triệu người liên quan trực tiếp đến việc tiếp xúc với khói thuốc thụ động (WHO, 2022). Hiện nay, ở các quốc gia có thu nhập thấp và trung bình việc sử dụng thuốc lá đang trở thành một vấn đề lớn. WHO ước tính, hơn 80% trong số 1,3 tỷ người sử dụng thuốc lá trên toàn thế giới cư trú ở các quốc gia có thu nhập thấp hoặc trung bình, nơi gánh nặng bệnh tật là đáng kể nhất và tỷ lệ mắc bệnh và tử vong liên quan đến thuốc lá là nghiêm trọng nhất. Do việc sử dụng thuốc lá, chi tiêu cho các nhu yếu phẩm như thức ăn và chỗ ở đã được thay thế cho việc mua thuốc lá trong gia đình. Điều này ảnh hưởng đến thu nhập, làm giảm các nhu cầu thiết yếu khác của gia đình. Chi phí tài chính cho việc hút thuốc lá là rất lớn, chưa kể đến chi phí cao cho việc điều trị các bệnh liên quan đến thuốc lá (WHO, 2022).

Theo nhiều nghiên cứu, chỉ chưa đến 2% phụ nữ trưởng thành sử dụng thuốc lá ở Việt Nam, trong khi có gần 50% nam giới trưởng thành hút thuốc. Tại Việt Nam, các bệnh liên quan đến thuốc lá được cho là nguyên nhân gây ra 40.000 ca tử vong sớm hàng năm (Marquez, 2019). Ngoài việc cướp đi mạng sống của con người, các bệnh liên quan đến việc hút thuốc làm giảm năng suất lao động của người mắc bệnh liên quan tới thuốc lá và tổn chi phí y tế. Tổng thất sẽ lớn hơn rất nhiều nếu xem xét các chi phí gián tiếp cho xã hội do bệnh tật và tử vong sớm, vốn chỉ được tính vào chi phí trực tiếp của 25 bệnh tật do thuốc lá gây ra (Duong, 2020). Người hút thuốc chi tiền cho thuốc lá, điều này ảnh hưởng đến thu nhập của gia đình và các chi phí thiết yếu khác, đặc biệt đối với các gia đình có hoàn cảnh khó khăn về kinh tế. Các gia đình thu nhập thấp ở Việt Nam phải chi 5% thu nhập hộ gia đình cho thuốc lá, chi cho giáo dục và y tế bằng với số tiền chi cho thuốc lá (Minh, 2019). Trong khi đó, nếu việc mua thuốc lá được thay thế bằng việc mua thực phẩm, 11,2% hộ gia đình có thu nhập thấp sẽ thoát nghèo (Duong, 2020).

Ngày nay, Chính phủ đã có nhiều hành động để hạn chế sự tiêu thụ thuốc lá ở người dân, tuy nhiên lượng thuốc lá được sử dụng vẫn có xu hướng tăng mạnh qua các năm. Vì vậy, việc thực hiện nghiên cứu này là nhằm mục đích xác định các nhân tố tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá tại Việt Nam, từ đó kết hợp với các nghiên cứu định lượng và định tính chuyên sâu sẽ là cơ sở vững chắc để xây dựng các chiến lược hạn chế hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá tại Việt Nam trong tương lai. Mặt khác, nếu kiểm soát được hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá thì sẽ mang lại nhiều lợi ích như bảo vệ sức khỏe cộng đồng, hạn chế chi phí được chi cho thuốc lá từ đó cải thiện kinh tế của các hộ gia đình, tiết kiệm chi phí y tế, vvv.

2. CƠ SỞ LÝ THUYẾT

2.1. Hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá

Hành vi tiêu thụ thuốc lá bị ảnh hưởng bởi nhiều yếu tố, bao gồm các yếu tố cá nhân (như nhận thức, hình ảnh bản thân, bạn bè đồng trang lứa), yếu tố xã hội (chuẩn mực xã hội), yếu tố văn hóa (như thói quen sử dụng thuốc lá truyền thống và sự tiếp biến văn hóa), sở thích cá nhân, và yếu tố tâm lý. Theo một bài báo của Trung tâm Kiểm soát và Phòng ngừa Dịch bệnh (CDC) năm 1998, hành vi tiêu thụ thuốc lá là kết quả của từng yếu tố này và sự tương tác phức tạp của chúng. Các yếu tố này tương tác với nhau để ảnh hưởng đến quyết định sử dụng và tiếp tục sử dụng các sản phẩm thuốc lá hoặc hành vi sức khỏe của người sử dụng thuốc lá (CDC, 2009).

2.2. Các nhân tố ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá

GDP bình quân đầu người, dân số, lạm phát, thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt, giá sản phẩm và giới tính đã được xác định và đề xuất là 6 yếu tố chính ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá. Những phát hiện này dựa trên nghiên cứu của Bauer và cộng sự (2007), Parks và cộng sự (2021), Dilley và cộng sự (2012) và các nghiên cứu liên quan.

(1) GDP bình quân đầu người: Theo Ngân hàng Thế giới (2023), GDP bình quân đầu người được xác định bằng cách chia toàn bộ tổng giá trị cung cấp cho nền kinh tế quốc gia cho tất cả các nhà sản xuất, cộng với bất kỳ khoản thuế nào đối với hàng hóa không được tính đến trong đánh giá đầu ra. Những thay đổi trong hành vi của người tiêu dùng, chẳng hạn như thói quen chi tiêu, có ảnh hưởng đáng kể đến GDP bình quân đầu người. Ví dụ, trong thời kỳ suy thoái, người tiêu dùng có thể cắt giảm mua hàng, điều này sẽ làm giảm thu nhập trung bình. Trên thực tế, nhiều nghiên cứu của Black và cộng sự (2012) đã chứng minh rằng tăng trưởng GDP ảnh hưởng đến quyết định mua hàng của người tiêu dùng, trong đó yêu cầu quan trọng hơn mong muốn.

(2) Dân số: Dân số và hành vi người tiêu dùng có mối liên hệ chặt chẽ với nhau vì các biến nhân khẩu học như tuổi tác, thu nhập, trình độ học vấn có thể tác động đến hành vi của cá nhân và hộ gia đình. Bằng cách ảnh hưởng đến quy mô và cấu trúc của thị trường hàng hóa và dịch vụ, sự gia tăng dân số và thay đổi nhân khẩu học có thể tác động đến hành vi của người tiêu dùng (Easley và cộng sự, 2019). Điều này đơn giản là do người cao tuổi có thể có những nhu cầu và sở thích khác với người trẻ, họ có thể có thói quen chi tiêu khác nhau. Nghiên cứu này của Easley và cộng sự (2019) cho thấy kinh tế học hành vi minh họa tác động của lớp dữ liệu trong đó khách hàng bị ảnh hưởng bởi các quyết định và hành động của người khác.

(3) Lạm phát: Lạm phát được hiểu là sự suy giảm sức mua của người tiêu dùng theo thời gian do giá hàng hóa tăng cao (Fernando, 2023). Theo Schuler (2023), hành vi tiêu dùng của cá nhân sẽ bị ảnh hưởng bởi những biến động của lạm phát. Từ việc so sánh các trường hợp từ các thời kỳ lạm phát, có thể thấy nhiều hậu quả của lạm phát trong việc mua sắm của người dân. Ví dụ, theo Khwaja và cộng sự (2007), lạm phát có thể ảnh hưởng đến sở thích về thời gian, do đó có thể ảnh hưởng đến việc hút thuốc. Hoặc những giai đoạn lạm phát cao có thể gây ra nhiều căng thẳng hơn, điều này có thể ảnh hưởng đến việc bắt đầu hút thuốc (Finkelstein và cộng sự, 2006).

(4) Thuế suất tiêu thụ đặc biệt: được coi là thuế gián thu thường được các tổ chức chính phủ áp dụng đối với hàng hóa hoặc dịch vụ giá cao có tác động tiêu cực đáng kể đến môi trường hoặc sức khỏe con người, như rượu, thuốc lá và nhiên liệu (Kagan, 2023). Tăng thuế suất thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt đối với thuốc lá đã được chứng minh là cách hiệu quả và tiết kiệm chi phí nhất để giảm tiêu thụ thuốc lá (Schafferer et al, 2018). Dựa trên đặc thù của từng quốc gia, thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt sẽ được đánh giá ở các mức khác nhau, thậm chí có thể khác nhau tùy theo khu vực.

(5) Giá sản phẩm: Giá sản phẩm được coi là giá trị được ấn định cho một đơn vị hàng hóa, dịch vụ, tài sản, đầu vào. Nó thể hiện số tiền mà người mua hoặc người tiêu dùng phải trả để sở hữu hoặc tiếp cận sản phẩm hoặc dịch vụ đó (Le, 2023). Một bài báo của Banton (2022)

lập luận rằng giá của một hàng hóa hoặc dịch vụ cụ thể được xác định bởi mối quan hệ giữa cung và cầu của nó tại bất kỳ thời điểm nào. Ngoài ra, lý thuyết kinh tế và nghiên cứu thực nghiệm cho thấy rằng khi nói đến việc tiêu thụ thuốc lá, người trẻ và những người có thu nhập thấp đặc biệt nhạy cảm với việc tăng giá. Điều này là do tỷ lệ thu nhập khả dụng của một người dành cho hàng hóa càng thấp thì cá nhân đó càng phản ứng nhanh hơn trước những thay đổi về giá (Farrelly và cộng sự, 2001).

(6) Giới tính: Một trong những yếu tố then chốt ảnh hưởng tới cách hành xử và xu hướng của người tiêu dùng là giới tính. Ở Mexico, 80% người hút thuốc có kế hoạch bỏ thuốc hoặc đang cân nhắc việc đó và 56,9% (57% nam và 56,4% nữ) cho biết đã cố gắng bỏ thuốc trong 12 tháng trước đó. Chưa có nghiên cứu so sánh về việc cai thuốc lá theo giới tính ở Mexico. Tuy nhiên, phụ nữ bị phụ thuộc nhanh hơn sau lần sử dụng đầu tiên, cho biết thời gian cai thuốc ngắn hơn và ít thường xuyên hơn cũng như hút thuốc trong thời gian dài hơn trong suốt cuộc đời của họ mặc dù nam giới hút thuốc thường xuyên hơn và tiêu thụ nhiều thuốc lá mỗi ngày hơn phụ nữ (Becker và cộng sự, 2017).

2.3. Giả thuyết nghiên cứu

Dựa trên mục tiêu xác định các yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá tại Việt Nam, tác giả đặt ra các cặp giả thuyết sau:

Đầu tiên, GDP bình quân đầu người là một trong những yếu tố chính ảnh hưởng đến tiêu thụ thuốc lá ở nhiều quốc gia khác nhau. Trong đó, nghiên cứu của Chauvin và cộng sự (2004) chứng minh rằng dân số ở các khu vực có GDP cao thì có tỷ lệ tiêu thụ thuốc lá cao hơn so với dân số ở các khu vực có GDP thấp. Ngoài ra, một nghiên cứu về những yếu tố như sự giàu có và thu nhập của hộ gia đình cho thấy những người có tài chính cao thường gặp khó khăn hơn trong việc ngừng hút thuốc so với những người không có việc làm, bao gồm sinh viên và người thất nghiệp (Thompson và cộng sự, 2019). Bên cạnh đó, theo một nghiên cứu của Jha (2020), hút thuốc lá là nguyên nhân gây tử vong hàng đầu ở các quốc gia có thu nhập cao (gây ra 41 triệu ca tử vong ở Hoa Kỳ, Vương quốc Anh và Canada từ năm 1960 đến năm 2020). Cụ thể, nghiên cứu này tuyên bố rằng tỷ lệ người trưởng thành hút thuốc ở các quốc gia có thu nhập cao tuy đã giảm đáng kể nhưng tình trạng hút thuốc vẫn còn khá phổ biến tại các quốc gia này. Trong một nghiên cứu khác của Bauer và cộng sự (2007) tại Đức, nhóm tác giả này đã khẳng định rằng những người có thu nhập thấp có nhiều khả năng hút thuốc hơn so với những người có thu nhập cao. Điều này là do những người có thu nhập cao coi trọng sức khỏe của họ hơn vì họ sẽ có nhiều cơ hội tiếp xúc với những dịch vụ và sản phẩm lành mạnh sau quá trình làm việc kéo dài. Mặt khác, người có thu nhập cao luôn phải chịu căng thẳng, dẫn tới việc tăng nhu cầu hút thuốc để họ có thể giải tỏa áp lực và căng thẳng một cách nhanh chóng.

H1: GDP bình quân đầu người tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá

Hành vi sử dụng thuốc lá có mối quan hệ mật thiết với yếu tố dân số. Bên cạnh đó, sự khác biệt về nhân khẩu học và dân số cũng đã được chứng minh là có tác động đáng kể đến việc sử dụng thuốc lá, xì gà và các mặt hàng thuốc lá khác (Ganz và cộng sự, 2022). Một nghiên cứu do Tiến sĩ Mehrshad Abassi thực hiện vào năm 2007 đã khảo sát dân số tại Iran ở độ tuổi 15–64 và kết quả khảo sát cho thấy tỷ lệ hút thuốc trung bình hàng ngày là 11,3% (5,6

triệu người: 21,4% nam và 1,4% nữ), với số người hút thuốc chiếm 1,7 triệu người (3,4 % dân số Iran) (Meysamie và cộng sự, 2010). Theo một nghiên cứu trước đây dựa trên dữ liệu do GATS thu thập năm 2015, tỷ lệ hút thuốc ở thanh niên từ 15 tuổi trở lên ở Việt Nam là 22,5% trên tổng dân số (45,3% nam giới và 1,1% nữ giới) (Hoang và cộng sự, 2017). Qua đó, những số liệu trên đã chỉ ra rằng tỉ lệ nam giới ở tuổi thanh thiếu niên và trưởng thành hút thuốc nhiều hơn so với nữ giới trong cùng độ tuổi. Ngoài ra, Corey và cộng sự (2017) phát hiện ra rằng những người trẻ tuổi và trung niên có nhiều khả năng hút thuốc hơn những người lớn tuổi. Hơn nữa, phần lớn các quốc gia có dân số già đều có tỷ lệ hút thuốc thấp hơn so với các quốc gia có dân số trẻ (World Bank, 2020).

H2: Dân số tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá

Trên thực tế, lạm phát có ảnh hưởng đến hành vi sử dụng thuốc lá của người tiêu dùng vì nó tác động đến điều kiện kinh tế và thu nhập cá nhân. Theo nghiên cứu của Dilley và cộng sự (2012), việc gia tăng giá thuốc lá ở Washington có thể không ảnh hưởng đến việc tiêu thụ thuốc lá do lạm phát làm giảm chi phí thuốc lá. Cụ thể, trong khi giá trung bình của một bao thuốc lá tăng 1,91 USD từ năm 2000 đến 2008, sau khi tính đến lạm phát, mức tăng chỉ đạt 0,63 USD. Hơn nữa, nghiên cứu của Guindon và cộng sự (2017) ở Argentina cũng chứng minh rằng giá cả không ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá từ thời điểm lạm phát cao đến thời điểm lạm phát cực kỳ cao. Ngoài ra, giá và thuế thuốc lá được điều chỉnh theo lạm phát làm giảm sự tiêu thụ thuốc lá của người dân (Kierstead và cộng sự, 2023). Điều này cho thấy rằng để duy trì việc giảm tỉ lệ hút thuốc lá hiệu quả, giá thuốc lá phải được tăng lên một cách thường xuyên để bù đắp cho lạm phát. Qua đó, để giảm sức mua của người tiêu dùng, các cơ quan chức năng phải đảm bảo rằng thuế thuốc lá được tự động điều chỉnh theo các biến động lạm phát, điển hình như ở Hàn Quốc và Liên bang Nga (Dan, 2022; Marquez và cộng sự, 2018).

H3: Lạm phát tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá

Có thể thấy, thuế suất thuế TTĐB có liên quan đến hành vi tiêu dùng của người dân các nước. Cụ thể, một nghiên cứu về sự thay đổi trong hành vi tiêu thụ thuốc lá trước và sau khi tăng thuế TTĐB cho thấy rằng khi tăng thuế TTĐB đối với thuốc lá, người tiêu dùng đã phải chuyển từ hút thuốc lá cao cấp sang thuốc lá thông thường để duy trì số lượng thuốc lá hút mỗi ngày (Chiou và cộng sự, 2014). Vì vậy, tăng thuế TTĐB có thể sẽ làm thay đổi cách thức tiêu thụ thuốc lá của người dân, về lâu dài, tăng thuế mạnh với các mặt hàng thuốc lá sẽ hạn chế số lượng thuốc lá được tiêu thụ. Theo một nghiên cứu được thực hiện tại Úc bởi Parks và cộng sự (2021), việc tăng giá hoặc thuế đối với thuốc lá không chỉ là một chiến lược kiểm soát hiệu quả giúp giảm tỷ lệ hút thuốc của người dân nói chung mà còn có thể được sử dụng để xóa bỏ sự bất bình đẳng kinh tế xã hội. Hơn nữa, nghiên cứu này còn phát hiện ra rằng tỷ lệ hút thuốc ở Úc giảm từ 28,2% xuống 19,7% do giá thuốc lá tăng từ 3,39 USD lên 11,60 USD từ tháng 1 năm 1991 đến tháng 12 năm 2006. Ngoài ra, Jiménez-Ruiz và cộng sự (2008) đã phát hiện ra rằng giá cả là một yếu tố quyết định quan trọng trong việc lựa chọn loại thuốc lá và lượng tiêu thụ thuốc lá trong các hộ gia đình. Cụ thể, tăng thuế TTĐB đối với thuốc lá dẫn đến giá cả cao hơn, điều này góp phần làm giảm tỷ lệ hút thuốc lá tại các hộ gia đình. Bên cạnh đó, nhiều nghiên cứu cũng đã được thực hiện để điều tra tác động của sự biến động giá đối với các sản

phẩm thuốc lá và xác định được rằng những thay đổi về giá thuốc lá có liên quan đáng kể đến thuế suất thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt.

H4: Thuế suất thuế TTĐB có tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá

Tăng giá sản phẩm được coi là phương pháp hiệu quả nhất để giảm tỉ lệ hút thuốc lá (Phan, 2015). Cụ thể, giá các sản phẩm thuốc lá càng cao thì càng có khả năng ngăn chặn người chưa hút thuốc có ý định bắt đầu hút thuốc cũng như những người đã bỏ hút thuốc trở lại. Đồng thời, việc tăng giá còn giúp ngăn ngừa sự gia tăng số lượng người bị nghiện, và có thể khiến những người đang hút thuốc lá bỏ thuốc hoặc hạn chế số lượng thuốc lá mà họ sử dụng. Bằng chứng là vào năm 1999, Ngân hàng Thế giới đã kết luận rằng mức tăng 10% giá thuốc lá trung bình sẽ làm giảm khoảng 4% nhu cầu của người dân ở các nước thu nhập cao và khoảng 8% ở các nước thu nhập thấp và trung bình (Fuchs và cộng sự, 2019). Tuy nhiên, theo một nghiên cứu khác của Laxminarayan và cộng sự (2004), họ sử dụng một mẫu gồm những người hút thuốc và không hút thuốc, kết quả nghiên cứu của họ cho thấy việc tăng giá thuốc lá không ảnh hưởng đến quyết định bắt đầu hút thuốc. Hơn nữa, nghiên cứu này cũng điều tra tác động tiềm ẩn của việc thay đổi giá đối với các mặt hàng thuốc lá và phát hiện ra rằng những thay đổi về giá thuốc lá có mối quan hệ tỷ lệ thuận và có liên hệ chặt chẽ với sự thay đổi lựa chọn giữa các loại thuốc lá của người tiêu dùng.

H5: Giá sản phẩm tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá

Hành vi tiêu thụ thuốc lá cũng chịu ảnh hưởng bởi yếu tố giới tính. Cụ thể, các yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến hành vi hút thuốc của nam và nữ, cũng như các yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến việc quyết định hút thuốc và số lượng tiêu thụ thuốc lá ở cả hai giới là khác nhau (Kilic và cộng sự, 2014). Theo Grunberg và cộng sự (1991), sự khác biệt về giới tính được thể hiện rõ ràng trong hành vi tiêu thụ thuốc lá, với quan điểm là nam giới có lượng người hút thuốc và sử dụng nhiều loại thuốc lá hơn nữ giới. Trong một nghiên cứu khác ở Puerto Rico của Latimer và cộng sự (2004), họ đã thực hiện một cuộc khảo sát kiểm tra tỷ lệ sử dụng chất gây nghiện theo giới tính ở độ tuổi thanh thiếu niên và kết quả cho thấy nữ giới có liên quan đến việc sử dụng thuốc lá, trong khi nam giới có liên quan đến việc sử dụng cần sa ở các trường trung học. Bên cạnh đó, theo một nghiên cứu về sự khác biệt giới tính trong việc tiêu thụ thuốc lá ở Thổ Nhĩ Kỳ của Kilic và cộng sự (2014), Thổ Nhĩ Kỳ có tỷ lệ hút thuốc cao đáng kể và có sự khác biệt theo giới tính trong việc sử dụng thuốc lá. Nghiên cứu này đã cho thấy gần một phần ba số người trưởng thành từ 15 tuổi trở lên (47,7% nam giới và 14% nữ giới) hút thuốc trong năm 2008. Hơn nữa, tỷ lệ hút thuốc của nữ giới ở Thổ Nhĩ Kỳ tăng đáng kể từ năm 1997 đến năm 2009, từ 10,9% lên đến 15,2% (Kilic và cộng sự, 2014). Tuy nhiên, Kong và cộng sự (2017) ở Hoa Kỳ cho rằng sự khác biệt về giới tính trong việc sử dụng thuốc lá điện tử ở thanh thiếu niên là tương đối không rõ ràng. Trong đó, tỷ lệ sử dụng thuốc lá điện tử dao động từ 1,6% đến 16,2% ở nam giới và 0,6% đến 16,8% ở nữ giới (Kong và cộng sự, 2017).

H6: Giới tính tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá

3. PHƯƠNG PHÁP NGHIÊN CỨU

3.1. Phương pháp thu thập dữ liệu

Để có thể đánh giá sự ảnh hưởng của các nhân tố tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá ở Việt Nam, tác giả đã sử dụng hai biến bao gồm biến độc lập (GDP bình quân đầu người, dân số, lạm phát, thuế suất thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt, giá sản phẩm, giới tính) và biến phụ thuộc (hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá). Bên cạnh đó, nhóm tác giả đã sử dụng dữ liệu bảng kéo dài 23 năm từ 2000 đến 2022 của 9 quốc gia có tỷ lệ hút thuốc lá cao, nhằm quan sát và đo lường được sự thay đổi của hành vi tiêu dùng và các biến theo thời gian dựa trên tập dữ liệu có ý nghĩa phù hợp với mục tiêu nghiên cứu, từ đó đưa ra các kết luận phù hợp với thực tế nhất.

3.2. Mô hình nghiên cứu

Dựa vào kết quả của nghiên cứu, có 6 giả thuyết được đề xuất. Để nghiên cứu về các giả thuyết này, nhóm tác giả đã lựa chọn sử dụng các mô hình OLS, FEM, REM, FGLS trên phần mềm Stata để phân tích rõ tác động của các biến độc lập nói trên đến biến phụ thuộc. Dựa trên các phân tích trước đó, sau đây là mô hình nghiên cứu của các tác giả:

Hình 1: Mô hình các yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá tại Việt Nam

Phương trình của mô hình được mô tả:

$$\text{LnTCB}_d = \text{LnGDP}_i + \text{Popul}_i + \text{Infl}_i + \text{Tax}_i + \text{Pric}_i + \text{Gen}_i (\text{dummy}) + \varepsilon$$

Ghi chú:

Tên biến	Nghĩa	Đơn vị	Giả thuyết được thành lập	Kết quả dự đoán của Hệ số Bata	Nguồn của dữ liệu
LnTCB_d	Hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá	Triệu bao 20 điếu	Biến phụ thuộc		Statista, WHO, GSO, OECD.
LnGDP_i	GDP bình	USD	H1: GDP bình quân		World Bank

Tên biến	Nghĩa	Đơn vị	Giả thuyết được thành lập	Kết quả dự đoán của Hệ số Bata	Nguồn của dữ liệu
	quân đầu người		đầu người có tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá	+/-	
Popul_i	Dân số	Triệu người	H2: Dân số có tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá	+/-	World Bank
Infl_i	Lạm phát	%	H3: Lạm phát có tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá	+/-	World Bank
Tax_i	Thuế suất thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt	%	H4: Thuế suất thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt có tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá	+/-	Statista, WHO, GSO, OECD.
Pric_i	Giá sản phẩm	VND	H5: Giá sản phẩm có tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá	+/-	Statista, WHO, GSO, OECD.
Gen_i (dummy)	Giới tính *		H6: Giới tính có tác động đến hành vi sử dụng thuốc lá	+/-	

* 0: Tỷ lệ nam hút thuốc cao hơn nữ

1: Tỷ lệ nữ hút thuốc cao hơn nam

4. KẾT QUẢ VÀ THẢO LUẬN

4.1. Kết quả

Bảng 1: Thống kê mô tả

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
LnTCB_d	207	7.732	0.669	5.991	8.612
LnGDP_i	207	9.185	1.322	5.977	10.966
Popul_i	207	88.887	62.84059	15.93	275.5
Infl_i	207	4.639	8.777	-1.7	80
Tax_i	207	61.091	17.484	25	90
Pric_i	207	76344.16	76831.1	1500	365690
Gen_i	207	0.0193	0.137	0	1

Nguồn: Tính toán kết quả từ Stata

Bảng 2: Mối tương quan giữa các biến

	LnGDP_i	Popul_i	Infl_i	Tax_i	Pric_i	Gen_i
LnGDP_i	1.0000					
Popul_i	-0.584	1.0000				
Infl_i	-0.187	0.048	1.0000			
Tax_i	0.150	-0.363	0.071	1.0000		
Pric_i	0.740	-0.389	-0.248	0.056	1.0000	
Gen_i	0.018	0.016	-0.026	-0.095	-0.030	1.0000

Nguồn: Tính toán kết quả từ Stata

Như kết quả ở bảng 1, mỗi biến có 207 quan sát được thu thập. Bên cạnh đó, bảng 2 cho thấy rằng khi tất cả các biến đều nhỏ hơn 0.8 thì mối tương quan giữa chúng là chấp nhận được.

Bảng 3: Phương pháp hồi quy OLS

LnTCB_d	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P> t 	[95% conf. interval]	
LnGDP_i	0.141	0.049	2.85	0.005	0.043	0.240
Popul_i	0.0009	0.0008	1.18	0.240	-0.0006	0.002
Infl_i	0.017	0.004	3.80	0.000	0.008	0.026
Tax_i	-0.001	0.002	-0.44	0.659	-0.005	0.003
Pric_i	-5.34e-06	7.66e-07	-6.96	0.000	-6.85e-06	-3.82e-06
Gen_i	0.289	0.283	1.02	0.308	-0.269	0.848

Nguồn: Tính toán kết quả từ Stata

Các tác giả đã sử dụng mô hình hồi quy OLS để đánh giá từng mối liên hệ giữa biến phụ thuộc và biến độc lập. Trong mô hình này, Prob > F = 0.0000, ngụ ý rằng giá trị P nhỏ hơn 0.05 và R-squared = 0.3283.

Bảng 4: VIF

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
LnGDP_i	2.89	0.346
Pric_i	2.31	0.433
Popul_i	1.73	0.578
Tax_i	1.18	0.846
Infl_i	1.08	0.928
Gen_i	1.02	0.983
Mean VIF	1.70	

Nguồn: Tính toán kết quả từ Stata

Từ kết quả của bảng 4, các tác giả kết luận rằng không có hiện tượng đa cộng tuyến giữa các biến vì VIF của chúng đều nhỏ hơn 5. Khi tác giả kiểm tra phương sai thay đổi trong mô hình hồi quy OLS, các tác giả đã khám phá ra $\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000 < 0.05$, trong đó chỉ ra hiện tượng phương sai thay đổi. Do đó, nhóm nghiên cứu tin rằng mô hình hồi quy OLS không phù hợp đối với cuộc điều tra này.

Tiếp đến, các tác giả thực hiện triển khai các mô hình FEM và REM nhằm xác định từng mối quan hệ giữa các biến. Sử dụng kiểm định Hausman để lựa chọn ra mô hình phù hợp nhất.

Bảng 5: Kiểm định Hausman

	fem	rem	Difference	Std. err.
LnGDP _i	0.042	0.107	-0.065	0.039
Popul _i	0.007	0.002	0.005	0.002
Infl _i	0.001	0.002	-0.0007	.
Tax _i	-0.001	-0.001	-0.0006	0.0009
Pric _i	-4.23e-06	-4.41e-06	1.79e-07	1.63e-07
Gen _i	0.009	-0.001	0.0103	.
Prob > chi2 = 0.4389				

Nguồn: Tính toán kết quả từ Stata

Theo bảng 5, Giá trị P ($\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.4389$) lớn hơn 0.05, cho thấy rằng mô hình REM là mô hình hiệu quả nhất. Khi thực hiện các kiểm định bổ sung, các nhà nghiên cứu đã phát hiện ra rằng trong khi không có mối quan hệ tự tương quan ($\text{Prob} > F = 0.0564 > 0.05$), thì phương sai thay đổi xuất hiện trong mô hình REM ($\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000 < 0.05$). Tương tự, mô hình này cũng không phù hợp đối với cuộc điều tra.

Cuối cùng, để giải quyết những thiếu sót của các mô hình trước đó, các tác giả sử dụng phương pháp hồi quy FGLS.

Bảng 6: Phương pháp hồi quy FGLS

LnTCB _d	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]
LnGDP _i	0.260	0.034	7.63	0.000	0.193 0.327
Popul _i	-0.0002	0.0004	-0.52	0.601	-0.001 0.0005
Infl _i	0.015	0.003	4.62	0.000	0.008 0.021
Tax _i	-0.006	0.001	-3.84	0.000	-0.009 -0.002
Pric _i	-5.56e-06	6.31e-07	-8.82	0.000	-6.80e-06 -4.33e-06
Gen _i	-0.017	0.158	-0.11	0.910	-0.328 0.292

Nguồn: Tính toán kết quả từ Stata

Mô hình FGLS đã giải quyết được những nhược điểm của các mô hình trước đó, với $\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000$ và mô tả mối quan hệ giữa các biến phụ thuộc và các biến độc lập như sau:

- GDP bình quân đầu người có tác động cùng chiều đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá của Việt, với $P > |z| = 0.000 < 0.05$ và $\text{Coef} = 0.26 > 0$.

- Dân số không có tác động tới hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá ở Việt Nam, với $P > |z| = 0.601 > 0.05$ và $\text{Coef} = -0.0002 < 0$.

- Lạm phát có tác động cùng chiều tới hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá ở Việt Nam, với $P > |z| = 0.000 < 0.05$ và $\text{Coef} = 0.015 > 0$.

- Thuế suất TTĐB có tác động ngược chiều tới hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá tại Việt Nam, với $P > |z| = 0.000 < 0.05$ và $\text{Coef} = -0.006 < 0$.

- Giá sản phẩm có tác động ngược chiều tới hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá tại Việt Nam, với $P > |z| = 0.000 < 0.05$ và $\text{Coef} = -5.56 < 0$.

- Giới tính không có tác động tới hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá tại Việt Nam, với $P > |z| = 0.910 < 0.05$ và $\text{Coef} = -0.017 < 0$.

4.2. Thảo luận

Các kết quả từ mô hình hồi quy FGLS cho thấy rằng trong khi các yếu tố lạm phát và GDP bình quân đầu người có tác động cùng chiều đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá tại Việt Nam thì các yếu tố như thuế suất thuế TTĐB và giá sản phẩm lại có tác động ngược chiều đến hành vi này.

Trên thực tế, có thể thấy rằng có một mối quan hệ phức tạp giữa mức tiêu thụ thuốc lá và GDP bình quân đầu người. Tuy nhiên, tùy vào từng quốc gia hay từ các góc độ khác nhau, mức GDP bình quân đầu người cao hay thấp sẽ có những tác động khác nhau (Brien, 2019). Ngày nay, ở các nước có GDP bình quân đầu người cao, cả chính phủ và người tiêu dùng đều ưu tiên các mối quan tâm về sức khỏe. Những người có mức thu nhập cao thường quản lý mức chi tiêu của họ một cách hợp lý, đặc biệt là những thứ cần thiết như các mặt hàng y tế (Chauvin và cộng sự, 2004). Vì lý do này, thay vì hút thuốc lá, họ sẽ sẵn sàng chi tiền cho các dịch vụ và sản phẩm giúp họ giải toả căng thẳng sau giờ làm việc và bảo vệ sức khỏe. Điều này không phù hợp với kết quả nghiên cứu vì khi GDP tăng thì tỷ lệ tiêu thụ thuốc lá giảm. Tuy nhiên, một số nghiên cứu được thực hiện ở các quốc gia có mức GDP cao lại chứng minh điều ngược lại, rằng những cá nhân có thu nhập cao thường có khả năng tiếp xúc với các quảng cáo thuốc lá nhiều hơn là những người có thu nhập thấp (Black và cộng sự, 2012). Mặt khác, nền kinh tế của các quốc gia này đang phát triển nhanh chóng, buộc mọi người phải làm việc liên tục hàng giờ đồng hồ và chuyển sang sử dụng thuốc lá như một liều thuốc giải toả căng thẳng nhanh chóng (Thompson và cộng sự, 2019). Do sự phát triển nhanh chóng của ngành thuốc lá, các sản phẩm thuốc lá cao cấp như xì gà cũng trở nên phổ biến. Các nhà sản xuất thuốc lá đã đánh vào nhu cầu thể hiện bản thân của những người có thu nhập cao bằng cách tính giá mỗi điếu xì gà lên tới hơn 1 triệu đồng tại Việt Nam. Bên cạnh đó, quốc gia có thu nhập cao luôn đặt ưu tiên trong việc cải thiện giáo dục, điều này góp phần tạo mối liên hệ chặt chẽ giữa GDP và giáo dục (Chauvin và cộng sự, 2004). Vì vậy, tỷ lệ tiêu thụ thuốc lá ở các quốc gia này sẽ thấp do người dân coi trọng giá trị sức khỏe và môi trường sống trong lành. Trong khi đó, giáo dục ít

được chú trọng hơn ở các nước có thu nhập thấp. Do đó, các công ty thuốc lá thường tận dụng những nhược điểm này để tăng khả năng tiếp cận thị trường và người tiêu dùng mục tiêu (Jha, 2020). Với những điểm này, rõ ràng GDP sẽ có nhiều tác động khác nhau đến hành vi sử dụng thuốc lá của người Việt Nam. Mức độ tiêu thụ thuốc lá sẽ tăng dần do tốc độ tăng trưởng nhanh chóng của GDP bình quân đầu người và những thay đổi trong quá trình sản xuất và tạo ra những sản phẩm thuốc lá phù hợp với thị trường của các doanh nghiệp thuốc lá.

Kết quả của mô hình ủng hộ tuyên bố ban đầu của tác giả rằng lạm phát có tác động đến tỷ lệ tiêu thụ thuốc lá. Trên thực tế, lạm phát là yếu tố tác động đến giá thành sản phẩm, hàng hoá bao gồm thuốc lá điếu. Theo Dilley và cộng sự (2012), việc tăng giá thành sản phẩm sẽ không làm giảm mức tiêu thụ thuốc lá khi lạm phát gia tăng đáng kể. Hơn nữa, giá thành đã trở nên ít quan trọng hơn trong việc hạn chế hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá trong thời kỳ lạm phát cao và siêu cao (Guidon và cộng sự, 2017). Các nghiên cứu này cho thấy rằng mặc dù giá thuốc lá trở nên đắt đỏ nhưng chúng chỉ hữu ích trong việc giảm tỷ lệ sử dụng thuốc lá trên toàn cầu hoặc ở Việt Nam khi điều chỉnh lạm phát phù hợp. Ngoài ra, Kierstead cùng cộng sự (2023) đã cho rằng mức tăng giá trung bình đáng kể hơn tỷ lệ lạm phát có thể hạn chế sự gia tăng tần suất sử dụng thuốc lá của người tiêu dùng.

Từ mô hình nghiên cứu, có thể thấy rằng hệ số Coefficient là -0.006 nghĩa là khi thuế suất thuế TTĐB ở Việt Nam tăng lên 1 đơn vị sẽ làm giảm hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá khoảng 0.006 đơn vị. Mặc dù hệ số này có thể không lớn, nhưng nó cũng chứng tỏ rằng tăng thuế suất thuế TTĐB sẽ làm hạn chế mức độ tiêu dùng thuốc lá. Trên thực tế, một yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến tỷ lệ sử dụng thuốc lá cao ở Việt Nam là Chính sách thuế TTĐB của quốc gia khiến chi phí thuốc lá ở mức thấp và không theo kịp lạm phát hay mức thu thập của người dân (Chaloupka và cộng sự, 2019). Người trưởng thành thuộc mọi thành phần kinh tế xã hội và nhân khẩu học sẽ có nhiều khả năng hạn chế sử dụng thuốc lá hơn khi thuế suất thuế TTĐB đối với thuốc lá tăng (Parks cùng cộng sự, 2021). Jiménez-Ruiz cùng cộng sự (2008) cũng cho rằng việc tăng thuế suất thuế TTĐB đối với các mặt hàng thuốc lá là một trong những biện pháp thiết thực và hiệu quả nhất để giảm mức tiêu thụ thuốc lá hàng năm. Về vấn đề này, Thái Lan đã sử dụng chiến lược tăng thuế TTĐB 11 lần, tăng thuế theo tỉ lệ phần trăm từ 55% đến 90%. Do những thay đổi này, tỉ lệ thanh niên Thái Lan hút thuốc đã giảm từ 32% vào năm 1991 xuống còn 17.4% vào năm 2021 (Le, 2023). Chiến lược này cũng khiến doanh số bán thuốc lá tại Trung Quốc giảm 3.3%, làm tăng thu thuế cho chính phủ Trung Quốc gần 11 tỉ USD (WHO, 2016). Lấy trường hợp của Philippines làm ví dụ, quốc gia này đã tăng thuế suất thuế TTĐB từ bốn loại thuế lên một mức duy nhất là 30 Pesos trên một bao thuốc lá (Schafferer cùng cộng sự, 2018). Theo các tác giả, việc tăng thuế suất thuế TTĐB là một yếu tố làm tăng giá thuốc lá bán lẻ, điều này làm giảm khả năng những người bắt đầu sử dụng thuốc lá lần đầu tiên và cản trở người tiêu dùng tiếp cận với mặt hàng độc hại này. Do đó, hạn chế sử dụng thuốc lá bằng cách tăng thuế TTĐB sẽ vừa bảo vệ sức khoẻ của người dân, vừa tăng thu cho ngân sách nhà nước.

Như giả thuyết ban đầu của tác giả, giá sản phẩm có tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá tại Việt Nam, đó là khi giá sản phẩm tăng thì số lượng thuốc lá sử dụng sẽ giảm. Các nghiên cứu tương tự cũng cho rằng khi các sản phẩm tiêu dùng, đặc biệt là thuốc lá có giá cao sẽ hạn chế khả năng bắt đầu sử dụng thuốc lá của người tiêu dùng hoặc có tác động lớn đến việc khiến những người này lựa chọn bỏ thuốc lá (Phan, 2015). Điều này có thể hiểu rằng

không phải cá nhân nào cũng có khả năng chi trả một khoản lớn cho việc sử dụng thuốc lá. Hơn nữa, khi giá thuốc lá tăng lên sẽ gây cản trở trong việc mua sản phẩm của người tiêu dùng, họ sẽ xem xét và cân nhắc kỹ hơn với một mặt hàng có giá thành cao hơn so với giá trị nó mang lại cho họ (Lê, 2023). Fuchs và cộng sự (2019) tin rằng việc tăng giá thuốc lá là cần thiết để hạn chế lượng tiêu thụ thuốc lá hàng năm. Nghiên cứu này cũng chỉ ra rằng với giá thuốc lá hiện tại, cần tăng giá thuốc lá thêm 10% để làm giảm số lượng thuốc lá bán ra mỗi năm vào thời điểm mức GDP ngày càng cao. Trái ngược với kết quả của nghiên cứu trên, Laxminarayan cùng cộng sự (2004) lại cho rằng việc tăng giá thuốc lá không có tác dụng làm giảm tỷ lệ hút thuốc, mà ngược lại nó kích thích người tiêu dùng chuyển sang các dòng thuốc lá khác. Theo quan điểm của các tác giả, việc tăng giá thuốc lá sẽ làm giảm mức tiêu thụ thuốc lá, nhưng việc tăng giá trực tiếp sẽ khó đạt được khi liên quan đến nhiều vấn đề khác.

Dựa vào kết quả thu được từ mô hình FGLS và các phân tích trên, có thể thấy rằng hai yếu tố tỷ suất thuế TTĐB và giá thành sản phẩm có tác dụng kiểm soát hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá tại Việt Nam. Tuy nhiên, trong khi hệ số giá thành sản phẩm là -5.56 thì tỷ suất thuế TTĐB chỉ là -0.006. Điều này có nghĩa là thuế TTĐB hiện hành có tác động không đáng kể đến tiêu dùng thuốc lá. Sau khi phân tích mô hình và các tài liệu nghiên cứu liên quan, các tác giả tin rằng thuế TTĐB chiếm tỷ trọng rất nhỏ trong giá thuốc lá khiến giá thuốc lá tăng, nhưng chưa đủ tác động đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá. Bên cạnh đó, như đã giải thích ở trên, trong thời kỳ lạm phát cao và GDP tăng nhanh, giá thuốc lá tăng nhưng không hạn chế tiêu dùng bởi vì chính sách TTĐB là chưa thực sự hợp lý. Vì vậy, chính phủ cần cải cách chính sách thuế TTĐB đối với các mặt hàng thuốc lá để có tác động gián tiếp đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá ở Việt Nam thông qua giá thuốc lá, điều này cần được xem xét cả trong thời kỳ lạm phát cao và thời kỳ GDP bình quân đầu người tăng trưởng nhanh.

Bên cạnh các yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến tiêu dùng thuốc lá, dân số và giới tính không ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá ở Việt Nam.

Mặc dù các tính toán của mô hình chỉ ra rằng dân số không bị ảnh hưởng bởi thói quen hút thuốc, hầu hết các bằng chứng đều chỉ ra điều ngược lại. Như đã trình bày, tuổi tác là yếu tố nhân khẩu học chính ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá. Một nghiên cứu ở Châu Âu đã chỉ ra rằng những người lớn tuổi có nhiều khả năng phải vật lộn với việc bỏ thuốc lá hơn những người trẻ tuổi vì nhiều lý do, chẳng hạn như hút thuốc lâu năm, ý định bỏ thuốc yếu, v.v. (Easley cùng cộng sự, 2019). Tuy nhiên, số lượng thanh thiếu niên hút thuốc đã tăng lên nhanh chóng ở nhiều quốc gia do sự phát triển nhanh chóng của ngành công nghiệp thuốc lá, đặc biệt là sự ra đời của thuốc lá điện tử. Cheung và cộng sự (2015) phát hiện ra rằng bộ não đang phát triển của người trưởng thành khiến họ đặc biệt dễ tổn thương bởi nicotin, điều này khiến họ dễ bị phụ thuộc vào việc sử dụng thuốc lá. Chất lượng của thuốc lá điện tử đã được cải thiện, đặc biệt là khi sản phẩm cung cấp liều lượng nicotin hấp dẫn giới trẻ hơn thuốc lá thông thường (Ganz cùng cộng sự, 2022). Trên thực tế, việc sử dụng thuốc lá điện tử đang ngày càng phổ biến ở các thành phố lớn của Việt Nam, đặc biệt là trong giới trẻ và những người có mức sống cao. Theo Khảo sát Sức khỏe Học đường năm 2019, có tới 2.6% học sinh từ 13 đến 17 tuổi sử dụng thuốc lá điện tử so với 3.1% thanh thiếu niên từ 15 đến 17 tuổi. Cụ thể, học sinh nam hút thuốc chiếm 4.8% và tỷ lệ này ở học sinh nữ là 1.4% ở độ tuổi 15 và 17 (Vuong, 2021).

Trái ngược với giả thuyết ban đầu mà tác giả đưa ra rằng giới tính có ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá, kết quả của mô hình nghiên cứu lại cho thấy điều ngược lại. Tuy nhiên, nhiều nghiên cứu trước đây đã đưa ra bằng chứng cho thấy giới tính có ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá. Nhìn chung, giữa nam và nữ sẽ có những kỳ vọng, mong muốn và lối sống khác nhau ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng, chẳng hạn như ngày nay nam giới có xu hướng sử dụng thuốc lá điếu hoặc xì gà, trong khi đó nữ giới ngày càng thích sử dụng thuốc lá điện tử hơn (Chelladurai cùng cộng sự, 2023). Trước đây, có thể thấy rằng việc phụ nữ sử dụng thuốc lá rất hạn chế hoặc gần như không xảy ra. Tuy nhiên, ngày nay với sự phát triển của ngành công nghiệp thuốc lá, ngày càng có nhiều dòng sản phẩm thu hút phụ nữ sử dụng, đặc biệt là sự ra đời của thuốc lá điện tử. Kilic cùng cộng sự (2013) chỉ ra rằng tỷ lệ phụ nữ sử dụng thuốc lá ở Thổ Nhĩ Kỳ đã tăng từ 10.9% đến 15.2% trong giai đoạn 1997-2009. Theo Ngân hàng Thế giới (2019), nam giới hút thuốc nhiều hơn nữ giới. Cứ 3 nam giới thì có một người hút thuốc. Ngược lại, cứ 16 phụ nữ thì chỉ có một người hút thuốc. Mặc dù vậy, việc sử dụng thuốc lá gần đây đã gia tăng ở phụ nữ, đặc biệt là thanh niên, người già và phụ nữ mang thai (Corey cùng cộng sự, 2017).

5. KẾT LUẬN VÀ KHUYẾN NGHỊ CHÍNH SÁCH

Kết quả nghiên cứu cho thấy có bốn yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá ở Việt Nam là GDP bình quân đầu người, lạm phát, thuế suất thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt (TTĐB), và giá sản phẩm, trong khi các biến dân số và giới tính không ảnh hưởng đến hành vi này. Trong đó, kết quả của mô hình thể hiện rằng thuế suất TTĐB và giá thuốc lá có khả năng kiểm soát hành vi tiêu dùng thuốc lá của người dân. Do đó, một số khuyến nghị được đề xuất nhằm giảm tỷ lệ tiêu thụ thuốc lá ở Việt Nam:

Thứ nhất, thay đổi cơ sở tính thuế: Trong điều kiện giá thuốc lá ở Việt Nam còn quá thấp, Việt Nam nên xem xét áp dụng mức thuế suất thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt như Trung Quốc và Philippines. Trên thực tế, thuốc lá không đắt vì thuế thuốc lá ở Việt Nam được áp dụng dựa trên giá xuất xưởng chứ không phải giá bán lẻ. Tuy nhiên, giá xuất xưởng thấp đến mức ngay cả khi bị đánh thuế, giá bán lẻ cũng không bị ảnh hưởng. Để tạo tác động lớn đến giá trị của một bao thuốc lá trước khi đến tay người tiêu dùng, Việt Nam nên chuyển từ việc đánh thuế dựa trên giá xuất xưởng sang đánh thuế trên giá bán lẻ thuốc lá hoặc nguyên liệu dùng để sản xuất thuốc lá. Để đảm bảo việc quản lý sức mua của người tiêu dùng theo cách tương tự như Hàn Quốc đã đạt được qua việc sử dụng kỹ thuật thuế hỗn hợp, mức thuế suất thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt đối với mặt hàng thuốc lá cũng phải được thay đổi thường xuyên theo lạm phát và GDP bình quân đầu người.

Thứ hai, quy định rõ ràng đối với các mặt hàng chịu thuế: Quốc hội và Chính phủ nên thiết lập các danh mục hàng hóa cấm tiêu dùng phải bao gồm các sản phẩm thuốc lá, thuốc lá điện tử và các thiết bị, linh kiện liên quan đến thuốc lá điện tử. Bên cạnh đó, để nâng cao hơn nữa hiệu quả của thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt trong việc giảm tỷ lệ tiêu thụ thuốc lá và nâng cao sức khỏe cộng đồng, Chính phủ cần tăng thuế suất thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt đối với những hàng hóa là nguyên liệu đầu vào để sản xuất ra các sản phẩm nói trên.

Thứ ba, nâng cao kiến thức và nhận thức của công chúng về tác hại của thuốc lá: Quốc hội và Chính phủ Việt Nam cần đưa ra những bằng chứng thuyết phục hơn cũng như phối hợp với các phương tiện truyền thông để tuyên truyền rộng rãi về tác hại của thuốc lá đến công chúng, đặc biệt là trong giới trẻ. Bên cạnh đó, các đoàn trường cũng cần chú trọng tuyên truyền cho học sinh, sinh viên về các tác hại của việc hút thuốc lá, tổ chức các buổi sinh hoạt chuyên đề, tổ chức các cuộc thi về phòng, tránh tác hại của thuốc lá..., từ đó có thể góp phần nâng cao nhận thức của giới trẻ về trách nhiệm thực hiện lối sống lành mạnh và ý thức hợp tác phòng, chống tác hại của thuốc lá.

Thứ tư, chống gian lận thuế và nạn buôn lậu thuốc lá: Cục Thuế cần tăng cường công tác thanh tra, kiểm tra để chống thất thu thuế và điều chỉnh các kênh kê khai thuế, quyết toán thuế, hoàn thuế nhằm chống gian lận thuế đối với mặt hàng thuốc lá. Bên cạnh đó cũng cần phải điều tra, xác minh, xử lý các đối tượng buôn lậu, gian lận thuế, hàng giả liên quan đến quản lý thuế thuốc lá. Điều này đòi hỏi phải trao đổi thông tin nhanh chóng và hợp tác chặt chẽ với các cơ quan liên quan.

Thứ năm, chống buôn lậu thuốc lá: Chính phủ cần hợp tác với các quốc gia khác để hình thành các chuỗi liên kết và giám sát quốc tế, giúp các cơ quan chức năng nắm bắt thông tin chính xác, kịp thời để ngăn chặn các hoạt động buôn lậu. Việt Nam cũng cần tăng cường kiểm soát buôn lậu tại các cửa khẩu và tại các điểm bán lẻ thuốc lá. Đặc biệt, để kiểm soát hiệu quả tình trạng buôn lậu thuốc lá ở Việt Nam, các cơ quan chức năng cần tập trung vào các tỉnh có tỷ lệ buôn lậu thuốc lá cao và các tỉnh giáp biên giới với các nước.

Cuối cùng, phân bổ hợp lý nguồn thu từ thuế tiêu thụ đặc biệt thuốc lá: Nhà nước cần hỗ trợ chi phí y tế cho những người hút thuốc lá thụ động vì dù không sử dụng nhưng họ vẫn bị ảnh hưởng nặng nề từ thuốc lá. Bên cạnh đó, nguồn thu từ thuế thuốc lá nên được phân bổ cho các hoạt động giáo dục nhằm nâng cao hiểu biết của giới trẻ về tác hại của thuốc lá. Ngoài ra, để tiếp tục duy trì lợi nhuận và tối đa hóa lợi nhuận, các công ty thuốc lá luôn tìm cách cản trở, ngăn chặn hoặc làm suy yếu các biện pháp tăng thuế thuốc lá. Để hạn chế tình trạng này, Chính phủ cũng cần có những chính sách và quy định rõ ràng để hỗ trợ các doanh nghiệp thuốc lá Việt Nam và nguồn kinh phí nên lấy từ nguồn thu từ thuế thuốc lá. Việc này được thực hiện với mục tiêu bảo vệ các doanh nghiệp thuốc lá trước các mặt hàng thuốc lá nhập lậu, thuốc lá giả, đồng thời góp phần bảo vệ sức khỏe và quyền lợi của người tiêu dùng.

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